

D.2.3: Expert Interviews - *Findings*

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Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Disclaimer: This deliverable has not yet been reviewed by the European Commission. Its content might therefore change as a result of the review process.

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Project Number:	101057253
Project Acronym:	POIESIS
Project Title:	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science
Title of Deliverable:	Expert Interviews - Findings
Work Package:	WP2
Due date according to contract:	31 August 2024
Actual delivery date:	...
Author(s):	Richard Woolley, Irene Monsonís Payá (CSIC)
Reviewer(s):	Martin Bauer (LSE), Tine Ravn (AU)
Editor(s):	Richard Woolley

ABSTRACT:	This deliverable describes the main findings of the expert interviews in the seven POIESIS partner countries.
Keyword List:	Experts, mediators, science communication, research ethics, scientific integrity, citizen integration in science, trust

Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	01/08/24	Richard Woolley	Report set-up
1.0	18/08/24	Richard Woolley	First draft
1.1	20/08/24	Irene Monsonís Payá	Editing
2.0	25/08/24	Martin Bauer, Tine Ravn	Internal review
2.1	29/08/24	Richard Woolley	Final revision

Acknowledgements

The POIESIS project partners wish to thank all those who contributed to the research activities presented in this reported.

In particular, we would like to thank the very many busy professionals - journalists, writers, communicators - working outside the R&I system and the many scientists working within it, for their time and invaluable insights.

Working with both researchers and non-academic actors participating in this study has been an enjoyable experience for the research teams involved.

We also thank our project expert, Matteo Merzagora, for his timely advice to focus on non-institutional participants in our 'mediator' interviews.

Executive Summary

This report presents the main results of the research work carried out by POIESIS project partners in Task 2.3 of Workpackage 2 (WP2). POIESIS develops an extensive research programme to systematically examine the interrelatedness of integrity, institutions, and integration with public trust (the 3i4T model). The global aim of WP2 was to define, at the European level, to what extent and how do research ethics and integrity (REI) practices in science support the broadening and deepening of public trust in science. In particular, this aim was to be explored in contexts of crisis and contestation, in which the science communication system is 'stress tested' from multiple angles.

Task 2.3 the Expert Interviews Study (EIS) conducted 119 interviews with institutional and non-institutional actors. Due to the ambition of the EIS to work with both institutional and non-institutional actors, two distinct interview instruments were developed. The first focused on Researchers in universities or research institutes with an emphasis on the integration dimension of the 3i4T model. The second focused on Mediators working between science and the public with a focus on the integrity dimension of 3i4T.

The two interview instruments used the SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic and climate change as case contexts. All partners were able to implement the EIS Protocol, including adapting to local linguistic and cultural realities. The EIS obtained novel qualitative data on the role of Mediators and the chains of mediation they structure in constructing relationships between integrity and integration and public trust in science, including the effects of institutional conditions. These data provide a robust and unprecedented basis for the development of Recommendations.

The structure of the report is as follows. The first section introduces the POIESIS project and describes the general approach and orientation of the EIS. Section 2 describes the research design, and the various aspects involved in the implementation of the EIS. Section 3 provides information on the EIS participants. Section 4 presents the results of the Mediator interviews and Section 5 results of the Researcher interviews. The final section presents an overall analysis of the results of the EIS.

Key themes and synthesized results relevant to the main Expected Outcome of the project, the POIESIS Recommendations, are developed throughout in the Report.

Research ethics and integrity issues in the conduct of science are not considered to have a significant impact on public trust in science.

- Mediators viewed the revealing of scientific misconduct in the public domain as a key professional responsibility, particularly science journalists.
- Researchers are rarely confronted by citizens with concerns about scientific misconduct; they doubt the reporting of fraud or other scandals has an important effect on their standing as a trustworthy profession in the eyes of citizens.
- Mediators and Researchers agree the revelation of scandals in the public domain improves citizens' perceptions of transparency and notions that 'the system' has the internal mechanisms necessary to 'fix itself'.
- Mediators and Researchers agree that trust in science is uneven across the population and linked to different information channels.
- Mediators and Researchers in France and the UK are convinced that a strong level of public concern about scientific misconduct exists in their societies. In the UK case, this was not viewed to signal a general decline in the trustworthiness of scientists. Data in France also does not support a decline in public perceptions of scientists' trustworthiness.

The further **integration of citizens** in science is viewed as making a potentially important contribution to maintaining and reinforcing public trust in science.

- Mediators consider that without an underlying degree of public interest and trust in science then they have no base audience.
- Integration measures that increase the size of the interested public enlarge the audience for science communication and opens potentially new channels for Mediators to interact directly with citizens.
- Researchers believe that creating opportunities for integrating citizens in science can improve public understanding of the uncertainty and lack of consensus that characterizes phases of scientific work and discovery.
- Researchers believe strongly that there are limits to the appropriateness and efficacy of citizen integration and that the specific research context must always be taken into account.

Perceptions of the **importance of institutions** in promoting public trust in science were strong and multi-dimensional.

- It was evident from participants that general levels of trust in authorities and public institutions vary between countries. These variations have specific cultural and historical contours, which can affect public trust in science.
- Mediators advocated greater investment in educational reform, scientific literacy campaigns, and public infrastructures designed to raise the capacities and opportunities of citizens to engage with scientific culture and work. For Mediators these investments would in turn improve the possibility of a science communication that is received as interesting and informative, by a discerning and critical audience.
- Researchers were particularly concerned about the mismatch between current research career and evaluation systems and the lack of incentives, training, recognition and rewards for dedicating time and resources to science communication and dissemination, public engagement work or citizen science.

Science communication underwent an extreme 'stress-test' in the COVID-19 pandemic.

- The confluence of high uncertainty, the increased reliance of citizens on social media during 'lockdowns', and a general public fear for the future of their 'way of life' placed Mediators and Researchers under pressure to communicate amidst a chaotic churn of 'fake news', deliberate and malicious misinformation, and ill-informed and sometimes panicked speculation.
- Mediators and Researchers agree that 'follow the science' is not a viable communication strategy to safeguard public trust in times of crisis.
- Mediators understand their communication role as reflexive. They invest in supporting scientific culture but are also aware of the importance of adopting a critical and independent perspective. They also articulate the need for this reflexivity to include a critical perspective on the integrity of the science communication sector itself, particularly if public trust in their own work is to be improved.
- Mediators were also strongly of the opinion that not all scientists should endeavour to communicate science if public trust is the goal. Mediators themselves try to work selectively with researchers that have the necessary capabilities.
- Researchers express a willingness to engage with the public through science communication and dissemination work. However, they doubt their efforts will impact public trust without a

more systematic and well-resourced approach to communication at the organizational level.

Results of the EIS also provide insights from the analytical perspective of **chains of mediation**.

- *Integrity* on the one hand functions as translation of the credibility of information sources and providers. On the other hand, interpersonal networks that stretch from science to society, and across professional communities of practice in science and media, are equally important for translating trustworthiness.
- Increasing *participative structures, mechanisms, and opportunities* across chains of mediation - from the lab to the neighbourhood - can create a patchwork of citizen integration that can help build a culture of public trust. But there are limits, in context sensitivity and in scale, that mean social integration cannot substitute for a sound, well-resourced, societal-level *institutional communication strategy*, but can complement and enhance such a strategy.
- Institutional Mediators tend to operate in more stable and routinized chains of mediation in which other Mediators are often their primary audience. Non-institutional Mediators tend to operate with more flexibility about topic choice and have more freedom to identify an angle to interest their primary audience the general public.

Mediators described **differences between the case contexts of climate change and COVID-19**.

- In climate change, Mediators perceive that the public considers the scientific evidence is strong and a consensus exists - while appreciating that the socio-political context remains volatile.
- In COVID-19, Mediators believe the public perceived that both the evidence base and the scientific consensus were fragile and that results may be unverified or even manipulated by interest groups. This meant the entire communication space around COVID-19 was for a time purely a contest over values and beliefs, which became virulent on some social media platforms.

Although a deeper analysis is still required the EIS appears to have produced findings that are **relatively consistent with previous POIESIS empirical studies**, the public consultation (D2.2) and the institutional focus groups (D3.2).

- Issues of *research ethics and integrity* in the conduct of scientific research were not linked to changes in levels of

public trust by either Mediators or Researchers. Public trust was not considered to be in crisis by either group of participants, although perceptions of growing or high concern did emerge, more so in some POIESIS countries than others. This was also consistent with previous results.

- *Citizen integration* was viewed positively, but with limitations and some moderating of expectations – again this initial and provisional assessment appears consistent with previous POIESIS studies on the surface.
- The need for *greater institutional development, support, and strategy* – both in terms of policies and investments of resources – is consistent with the findings of the institutional focus groups (D3.2).

This synthesis report does not fully capture all the **variations between national contexts** that are expressed with greater subtlety and sensitivity in the various National Reports. Variations between countries in general trust in institution and in the level of concern about scientific integrity expressed in public discourse are pointed out. However, readers interested in expanding their knowledge in this regard should also engage directly with these Reports (Appendix 4).

Table Ex.1 Recommendations for improving public trust in science based on Mediator suggestions

Country	Recommendations
Denmark	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhance transparency and quality in research communication through upholding impartial research, implementing rigorous quality checks, and disseminating processual and methodological explanations. 2. Formalize stakeholder inclusion at universities and encourage more citizen science and public engagement activities. 3. Bridge the gap between researchers and mediators and build co-partnerships. Place greater priority and value on science communication activities within academia, and support researchers in engaging with the public with a focus on effective communication. 4. Engage in direct dialogue with the audience, reduce the gap between science mediators and the public, and use their preferred platforms and channels for communication. 5. Place a higher priority on covering research in the media and put greater emphasis on explaining the value of science.

France	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first recommendation is to design a long-term communication plan that includes in-depth action to progressively build a shared culture. 2. The second recommendation relates to the need to support scientists more effectively with practical communication guidelines. 3. The third recommendation stresses the need to rebalance the work of communicating science by giving as much importance to the research process as to the findings. 4. A fourth recommendation concerns the reinforcement of school curricula with regard to science and critical thinking. 5. A fifth recommendation relates to the need to not be satisfied with a sloppy use of the notion of public trust in order to analyse its full social and political ramifications.
Germany	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve (school) education on science and the scientific method (scientific literacy). 2. Contextualise scientific findings in the communication process and explain the scientific process, including information regarding potential limitations and remaining scientific insecurities. 3. Communicate positively and constructively instead of conveying always more pessimistic and too generalising perspectives. 4. Create stable and safe working conditions in research, especially for young researchers. 5. Disentangle scientific findings and potential socio-political consequences in the discourses of all societal stakeholders.
Greece	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Institutional actions are needed to improve science communication. 2. Public or other institutional educational reforms targeting both the general public and the younger generations in particular are needed. 3. A responsible use of social media is essential in communicating science by public or research institutions and by individuals, targeting mainly - but not only- younger people. 4. A wider dialogue between science and society regarding the conduct of research and the use of its outputs. Some mentioned basically informative and science integration events, others expressed the opinion that the public must have a say on the way the science outputs are used. 5. More transparency in conducting research. This is meant to be used both on communicating and on conducting science as well.

Portugal	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engage scientists in institutional and non-institutional activities, showing the daily life of a scientist in different fields of knowledge, give them voice in society. 2. Create activities that are based on storytelling to guide the public through the scientific process until the result. 3. Create lines of funding specifically for science communication and science journalism.
Spain	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase investments in research ethics and integrity policies and procedures in universities and public research organisations, including through mandatory training for masters and doctoral students. 2. Reform the structure of research career incentives by renouncing the 'publish or perish' culture and by rewarding researchers for high quality communication and dissemination work. 3. Invest in a sustained educational programme to raise the level of scientific literacy and culture in primary and secondary school and, through lifelong learning, among the general public. 4. Create stable local-level infrastructures supporting the promotion of scientific culture and social integration in science, including public laboratories, reading and resource rooms, interactive activities, expert talks, etc., accessible to the entire population. 5. Open up public research laboratories for regular public visiting hours and for programmes of school excursions and work experience opportunities. 6. Invest in the provision of specialised training for early career researchers in science communication and media relations, including how to use social media platforms effectively. 7. Establish a system of effective sanction for scientists who engage in fraudulent behaviour in order to reduce the perception of impunity.
United Kingdom	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trustworthiness is key, not trust in science. 2. Train the public for critical thinking skills. 3. Public engagement is double-edged (positive and negative consequences) 4. The 'electoral model' of public engagement is to be avoided. 5. Ignore the 'trolls' and 'bots'. 6. Advocacy by scientists should be avoided.

Table Ex.2 Recommendations for improving public trust in science based on Researcher suggestions

Country	Recommendations
Denmark	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The media and politicians should pay great attention to science representation and to how scientific information is verified, received and used politically, ensuring that knowledge dissemination meets high standards and avoids intentional misrepresentation. 2. Attention should be focused on avoiding a negative framing of science and a political devaluing of higher education and the field of (science) communication. 3. A greater focus should be given to exploring how citizens and other stakeholders could be involved in research, broadening the concept of involvement to support and strengthen research-based knowledge. 4. Researchers should explore methods of communicating science in novel, pragmatic, and solution-oriented ways, while also increasing their presence in face-to-face dissemination. The academic system should place greater emphasis on the importance of science communication.
France	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first recommendation is to encourage scientific institutions to provide opportunities for scientists to reflect collectively on issues related to science and society. Some of the scientists we interviewed feel that, beyond the institutional discourse, their research organisation does not value the ability of scientists to develop a form of reflexivity 2. The second recommendation has to do with institutional guidance for scientists who decide to take a public stand on a particular issue. The scientists interviewed report a degree of uncertainty in their risk-taking, both professionally and legally. A feeling of uncertainty that calls for the production of practical guidelines dedicated to the public engagement of researchers. 3. The third recommendation relates to public communication by scientists in crisis situations. If we are to have a positive impact on public trust in science in a situation of great uncertainty, we need media resources that give scientists the time they need to develop a complex message. Collaboration with the mainstream media must

	<p>therefore be developed to ensure the conditions for this crisis communication.</p> <p>4. The fourth recommendation takes up the invitation described at the end of the previous section not to make short-term use of the notion of public trust. We must avoid opposing trust with ethics and integrity. Trust must not be used as a lever to cultivate opacity about any particular aspect of the way science works. On the contrary, we need to take a long-term view and be aware that the ideal of trust presupposes a form of openness and transparency</p>
Germany	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engage with a more critical or 'uninterested' public through new creative forms of communication. 2. Make science communication training an integral part of university curricula. 3. Give scientific news more space in institutionalised mass media. 4. Improve the recognition of science communication and social integration activities within the academic system. 5. Clarify the roles of science and politics in society and create more coherence in the interaction of both spheres. 6. Improve climate communication in a way that makes clear that prevention is always better (and cheaper) than reaction in the context of climate change.
Greece	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of participatory and informative events 2. Creation of Institutions that will oversee the way science is communicated 3. Reformation of the educational system and wider educational events
Portugal	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase scientific literacy through science communication and formal education 2. Promote transparency in research for the public and among peers 3. Train researchers for science communication and social integration 4. Integration is welcome, but with limits and only in certain parts of the scientific process
Spain	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve the scientific information supply chain by training and developing communication skills among scientists and reinforcing their collaborations with professional science communicators 2. Invest in permanent programmes designed to raise the level of scientific literacy and culture among school students and the general public

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Improve the recognition and rewards for science communication in the evaluation and career plans of scientists, particularly early career researchers 4. Create institutional policies and resource allocations to support and incentivise scientists committed to communication 5. Create an open public infrastructure of scientific data management and publications 6. Create stable local-level infrastructures of social integration into research, through institutions and key organisations 7. Enhance interdisciplinary research collaboration among social and STEM sciences 8. Promote transdisciplinary research approaches
United Kingdom	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Public engagement that promotes honesty and projects uncertainty will lead to a social justice agenda which ultimately results in a trusting, grateful, reassured public 2. Mediatisation encourages too much 'gloss' on the facts and thus undermines science. Public engagement through impact and attention seeking distracts individual scientists from main focus which is research 3. The deficit model does not work; more information is not the solution when values are at stake 4. Science cannot guarantee the conditions of its own functioning as 'orientation on truth' in public sphere goes beyond science. Science in the public sphere relies on the respect for truth being there. 5. Investing more in critical thinking skills will give public more tools to process information. 6. Epistemic humility, demonstrating trustworthiness is the issue, not lack of public trust in science, i.e. the problem is not with the public.

1. Introduction

1.1. About POIESIS

POIESIS is a three-year project funded by Horizon Europe. POIESIS brings together seven partners: Aarhus University (Denmark), London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE, United Kingdom), *Wissenschaft im Dialog* (WiD, Germany), National Technical University of Athens (NTUA, Greece), *Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique* (CNRS, France), *the Instituto Universitário de Lisboa* (ISCTE, Portugal), and the *Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas* (CSIC, Spain).

The 'HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44' call for proposals on 'Societal trust in science, research and innovation' integrated a set of three assumptions:

- First, that "... trust depends on scientists and engineers' capacity to demonstrate high standards of research integrity" and that breaches to research integrity, i.e. research misconduct or questionable research practices, will lead to mistrust.
- Second, that "... citizen and civil society's involvement in co-creating R&I agendas and contents makes research more relevant and responsive to society and strengthens co-ownership and trust".
- Third, the call assumes that these markers of responsible research practices - integrity and societal integration - are "fostered by conducive institutional governance arrangements and policy environments". The assumption is that institutions matter by enabling and supporting researchers to act responsibly.

As was described in the POIESIS project proposal, these three assumptions are intuitively appealing and plausible but required empirical validation. The EIS continued the critical approach adopted in prior POIESIS empirical studies, by fundamentally questioning these assumptions in the field. For example, the design of the EIS first sought to assess just how important issues of research ethics and integrity (REI) are in the work of Mediators and Researchers in communicating about science to citizens. Do science journalists prioritize or consider REI issues in preparing their different types of communication outputs? Or do they rely on the reputation and

generalized feelings of trust that are often associated with science? By taking this approach, the EIS was able to build on the emerging POIESIS perspective on these three underlying assumptions.

Adopting this perspective, POIESIS developed an extensive research programme to systematically examine the interrelatedness of integrity, integration, and trust, exploring also the role of institutions in fostering societal trust in science. POIESIS aims to do this through (i) analysis of existing data streams on citizen trust, responsible and questionable research practices, and institutional policies to enhance responsible research; (ii) implementation of a portfolio of case studies, specifically tailored to capture empirically the relatedness of integrity, integration, and trust, with a focus on the chains of mediation that connect research practices with, ultimately, the interpretation and assessment of these by wider, non-academic publics; and (iii) conducting a set of participatory research actions in which stakeholders actively co-create knowledge.

1.2. The 3i4T model

The POIESIS project is based on a conceptual approach adopted by the members of the consortium, the “Integrity, Integration, and Institutions for Trust” or 3i4T model (Figure 1). POIESIS considers integrity and integration as broad concepts facilitated by institutions, which through ‘chains of mediation’ affect public trust in science.

Figure 1.1. The 3i4T model

The concept of public trust refers to the confidence individual or social groups may have in the reliability of science and scientists. It is entangled with broader constellations of positive and negative “attitudes” towards science which have been explored in both cross-sectional and longitudinal studies (Allum et al. 2008; Bauer & Falade 2021; Gauchat 2012). The concept of integrity is concerned with the extent to which research practices are in accordance with appropriate ethical, legal, and professional frameworks, obligations, and standards. The concept of integration relates to the increased inclusion of citizens and societal stakeholders throughout the different phases of research and innovation cycles. The concept of institutions refers to the key actors and core processes involved in the pursuit of robust and relevant R&I in the interests of both science and society. Finally, the concept of “chain of mediation” relates to the mechanisms and processes that connect the integrity and ethics of research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of both these practices and their products by wider publics.

1.3. The mediation dimension

The POIESIS project is organised into five main Work Packages. The research results presented in this global report were produced as part of WP2, coordinated by the project's ISCTE partner in Portugal.

The POIESIS consortium designed WP2 as a series of cases studies using various methods and focusing on different objects of investigation: citizen meetings; individual expert interviews, and a survey experiment. Both the citizen meetings and expert interviews studies are from being 'small-scale', as the title of WP2 misguidedly suggests. In fact, both are relatively large-scale qualitative studies. The EIS alone conducted 119 interviews across the seven POIESIS partner countries.

Mediation is an important concept in POIESIS. A 'chain of mediation' is understood as a complex translation process which moves information from one context to another while transforming its form and content. Analytically we understand a chain of mediation as starting from knowledge production activities and the actors developing research practices on the work floor. Outputs of knowledge production then move through a series of actors and their networks. These actors are the mediators who transform the form and content. In POIESIS 'mediation' entails the cognitive and practice dimensions of Mediators work. The transformed outputs of sequences of mediation that reach particular public audiences through specific channels are of central interest. The concepts of mediation and chains of mediation have been part of the shared understanding of the 3i4T model that has ensured coherence among the various WP2 and WP3 studies. Further information on chains of mediation, including visualizations of generic models, can be found in Section 4 of the EIS Protocol (Appendix A).

1.4. The EIS in the POIEIS project design

The overall POIESIS design features a diverse set of empirical research studies. The EIS forms part of the sequence of studies conducted in 2023 and 2024 in WP2 and WP3. The first of these studies was the public consultation (Entradas et al. 2023), followed by the institutional focus groups (Dubois 2024), with the EIS being the third in this sequence. It was part of the POIESIS project design that relevant results and findings from the public consultation and the focus groups should be taken into account in preparing the EIS.

The findings of these first two studies were considered in the process of designing the EIS.

Figure 1.2. POIESIS data collection activities

The public consultation study included focus on both the integration and integrity dimensions of the 3i4T model. Findings regarding citizen participation were particularly relevant for preparation of the interviews with Researchers in the EIS. Between these two studies POIESIS investigates citizen integration in research from both the science and society sides. Findings regarding public perceptions of research integrity and ethics (REI) issues and if/how these relate to trust in science were particularly relevant to the preparation of the Mediator interviews. Between the two studies POIESIS investigates the integrity dimension from the perspectives of citizens, researchers and the mediators working between science and society.

The focus group study provided new insights into institutional actors' perceptions and practices regarding both the integrity and integration dimensions of the 3i4T model. The findings on the importance of institutional conditions were particularly relevant to

designing the Researcher interviews. For the Mediator interviews, each partner conducted a minority (n=2) of their interviews with institutionally based participants (e.g. working in research organisations) and a majority with non-institutional mediators (n=8). Between the focus group study and the EIS the integrity dimension was thus covered from the perspective of both scientific and societal actors. The generation of high quality and novel empirical data, which includes diverse actor perspectives and addresses all aspects of the 3i4T model from multiple sources, reflects a strong project design.

The structure of the POIESIS empirical programme has generated National Reports for each of the individual studies, which are then synthesized into a global report. A national-level comparative dimension is thus built into the project design. Specific national-level differences can be expected due to variation in institutional and organisational conditions in the seven POIESIS partner countries. Context-dependent insights emerging from the public consultation and focus group studies are summarised in Section 1.5.

1.5. National insights from previous POIESIS studies

The POIESIS project design (Figure 1.2) includes a diverse set of empirical studies using a variety of traditional and participative methods. Prior to the EIS, the public consultation (D2.2) and institutional focus groups (D3.2) have provided results and findings about the relationships between REI issues and public trust in science. This section contains brief national-level findings from these prior studies, both to provide additional context for the presentation of the EIS and to highlight the potential of the cumulative knowledge-building work being conducted in POIESIS.

In **Denmark**, citizens perceive reputable and traditional media as more trustworthy than social media. Citizens place a high value on the independence of media and communicators. With regard to the role of laypersons in research processes, Danish participants were concerned that their lack of expertise could have a negative impact on data quality and by extension scientific results.

Danish institutional actors rejected any general crisis in public trust in science, instead point to the increasing complexity of challenges to trust. Nevertheless, these actors connected inappropriate research practices, irresponsible science communication, and the pernicious influence of some private and

public vested interests with potential undermining of citizen trust. Doubts can then be exploited for ideological or political motives. Like citizens, institutional actors were also measured in their support for increased layperson's participation in research, suggesting that the suitability of individual research projects should always be taken into consideration.

In **France**, the previous tasks highlighted the importance of the collective sense of a crisis of trust between science and society. Although this belief is not objectively supported by opinion surveys such as *Les français et la science 2021*, it is very influential in the public debate.

The public deliberative workshop highlighted the complexity of the issue of generating trust. French participants particularly valued transparency in research processes and accepted that doubt is intrinsic to research. They mentioned the possibility that citizen participation could boost trust in science, but with the risk that this trust would only concern the most aware part of the population. While transparency was generally seen as a trust builder, it could paradoxically also seed distrust. Some participants argued that too much transparency might reveal instances of malpractice or fraud, negatively impacting public trust in science. Participants also expressed distrust arising from sensationalized announcements and unfulfilled promises. They underscored the inherent conflict between the long-term nature of scientific research and the media's haste to disseminate information. the complexity of the issue of generating trust. Participants also voiced concerns over compromised integrity due to conflicts of interest, unwarranted political affiliations, over-promised expectations, and occasionally, the questionable roles of certain institutions. A breach in a researcher's ethics was cited as a hallmark of integrity deficit.

The three focus groups held with institutional stakeholders helped identify possible courses of action in the French context. The following six actions were described as collective priorities: 1) developing a massive public communication strategy to promote science and critical thinking on social networks, seeing them as an "informational war zone"; 2) organising small-scale events to create and cultivate the link between citizens and scientists; 3) radically change the culture of research organisations when it comes to the handling of scientific misconduct: from secrecy to transparency; 4) changing the evaluation culture in science by giving priority to collective success over individual success, to quality over quantity; 5) training the entire scientific community in the values of scientific integrity, including senior researchers; 6) encouraging

scientific institutions to address the tensions and conflicting imperatives they contribute to generate.

In **Germany**, no general crisis of public trust in science is perceived, either by citizens or by institutional actors. However, some institutions and particular scientific disciplines are perceived as less deserving of complete trust. The role of media in holding science to account, as a publicly funded institution, is considered very important – not least because of a perceived lack of transparency about political and industrial interests in science.

In **Greece**, issues of REI are not commonly discussed among citizens or institutional actors, most likely due to the absence of high-profile research fraud cases. A more general distrust in institutions in Greek society, which can be linked to the economic crisis in the early 2010s and other major scandals, should be considered as part of how Greek citizens view all state-linked institutions. This may have some repercussions for public perceptions of scientific research.

In **Portugal**, an interest emerged in exploring ideas about how to attract and engage citizens who are not interested in scientific activities (the 'non-converted'). These are the citizens who never or rarely participate in scientific events or read scientific news, reaching out to whom is a particular difficult challenge.

In **Spain**, in the public workshop there was a common attitude towards research integrity as an issue connected with specific cases where scientists did not execute "good science". Despite the general interest in participation, workshop participants raised some concerns regarding the way in which the research would be designed to include citizens, how the results would be used, and a desirable level of participation of citizens in science. The focus group study generally affirmed that trust in scientists, as a socially valued profession, had been historically high in Spain and remained so now. The credibility of information sources and the perceived rigour of individual science communicators were mentioned as factors determining participating citizens' trust in a particular piece of information. Participants in the focus groups considered that the strong level of public trust could be under threat, due to the new patterns of communication through social media platforms that had opened up a space in which scientific credibility was undermined by 'vocal minorities'. The institutional actors in the focus groups consistently identified barriers and difficulties that accompany efforts to enhance citizen participation in research in Spain. Participants in the focus groups also believed that REI practices and the integration of citizens could be improved through sustained

efforts to improve institutional governance and process management. Institutional and organisational development of research ethics and integrity (REI) in Spain was perceived by the focus group participants to be in an early stage of its development and professional institutionalization.

In the **United Kingdom**, the public consultation produced several insights of particular relevance to the EIS, including:

- concerns about the impact of disinformation and misinformation propagated on social media and undermining trust in science are widespread in the UK public;
- there is a need for the public to have critical thinking skills, to identify false information;
- there is a surprising, generalised lack of credibility of mainstream media such as the BBC; and
- there is awareness and concern about open 'twitter wars' among scientists.

The institutional focus groups also produced insights relevant to the EIS:

- the notion of a crisis of trust in science is not backed by evidence and surveys show trust levels are stable and in a positive direction in the UK;
- there may be pockets of distrust fed by social media and fake news;
- there is a clear distinction between a researcher being trusted (relationship) and trustworthiness of research (science conduct);
- public engagement should be neither publicity nor marketing but a way to bridge the gap between science and its publics;
- public engagement could be risky and damaging without the right skill and more is not always better; and
- there is misalignment between UK Research Excellence Framework (REF) evaluation of UK universities and public engagement agendas.

An extended list of findings from the previous UK studies in POIESIS can be found in Section 1.2 of the UK National Report (Appendix 4g)

2. The EIS research approach and design

The Expert Interview Study, whilst using a standard social methodological approach of semi-structured interviews was a challenging study to design. The EIS sought to combine investigation into both the integrity and integration dimensions of the 3i4T model, with a focus on two different participant populations – Researchers and Mediators. Added to this, two case contexts – Covid-19 and Climate Change – were used to define our participant search. Finally, additional stratifications were included in our selection of Researcher and Mediator participants. The remainder of this Section describes the main tasks in developing the EIS and how various methodological and other design challenges were addressed.

2.1. Research questions

The research questions on which work package 2 pivots are the following:

- RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?
- RQ3: To what extent and how does the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?

In addition, the project aims to answer two research sub-questions in Work Package 2:

- How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the publics' trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?
- What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

Derived from these general questions, the empirical research questions of the EIS are:

- Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?
- How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science?
 - i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?
- What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

2.2. Research protocol

The research findings presented in this Report are the product of an empirical investigation based on a research protocol prepared by the Task 2.3 Lead CSIC (Monsonis & Woolley 2024). The EIS Protocol was not a POIESIS project deliverable. The EIS Protocol went through a number of iterations in its development based on comments from all POIESIS partners, discussion at the General Assembly held in Lisbon in February 2024, and with additional direct support from the Project Coordinator (Aarhus) and Work package 2 Lead (ISCTE). Work on the protocol commenced in November 2023 and the final version of the EIS Protocol was posted as an open document on the POIESIS Zenodo community on 7 May 2024.

The EIS Protocol contains:

- Study timeline
- Study objectives and research questions
- Study definitions
- Participant selection and invitation
- Interview guides for Researchers and Mediators
- Information sheet and informed consent form for participants
- Study ethics information
- Research data management and handling protocol
- National reporting strategy
- Quality control.

The Protocol can be viewed in full at Appendix A. The remainder of the Section thus contains abbreviated summaries of selected topics contained in the Protocol.

2.3. Ethics

An ethics approval application for Task 2.3 of POIESIS was submitted to the CSIC Ethics Committee in December 2023. Following one round of revisions a favourable report was received with approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2023). This information was included on the EIS Information Sheet and Informed Consent form provided to interview participants by national partners. These documents are included as appendices to the EIS Protocol.

2.4. Joint data handling agreement

Following the process undertaken for the public consultation and focus group studies, a joint data controller agreement (JDCA) was signed by all partners. The JDCA stipulates how data shall be handled and shared by national partners with the Task Lead. The purpose of the JDCA is to comply with Article 26 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The JDCA is attached as Appendix B.

2.5. Gender content of the research

The POIESIS project proposal contains general provisions related to ensuring gender balance in terms of participation in the various empirical studies included. In the EIS, each national partner strove to achieve a gender balance among participants. Details can be found in Section 3, which summarises the interviewees. No further gender analysis was included in the design of the EIS. For example, it was beyond the scope of the study to investigate whether there are gender differences or preferences in relation to the structure or outputs of chains of mediation. This is an avenue of investigation that would be an important future topic.

2.6. Semi-structured interview research

Semi-structured interview methodologies are highly flexible and can be used to conduct research that is predominantly deductive or inductive in character. In the case of the EIS, the i34t model and the multi-study design of the POIESIS project assigned a specific role, research object and set of questions. Interview schedules were thus designed that reflected both the pre-existing expectations of the research team and the existence of pre-identified essential information that the interviews were designed to elicit from participants.

As the EIS involved two distinct groups of participants, Mediators and Researchers, it was necessary to develop two distinct interview instruments. The interviews were designed in an iterative process between the Task Lead (CSIC) and the POIESIS team. Feedback from the national partners was used to shape a series of revisions in the interview designs. The Workpackage Leader (ISCTE) commenced interviewing (n=3) ahead of other partners and provided feedback leading to some final revisions of the instruments.

A supporting Interview Guide was produced that explained the aim of each question and elaborated on additional prompts that might be used. A training session was held online in which the interviews were reviewed and discussed. Between the supporting Guide and the training session the national partners were prepared to conduct interviews following a consistent approach.

2.7. Recruitment

Recruiting was structured according to criteria first outlined in the POIESIS proposal and specified in the EIS Protocol.

Table 2.1 Participant recruitment profiles

Type of expert	Profile and number of experts
Researchers (6)	Researchers on climate change (3, including 1 SSH) Researchers on COVID-19 (3, including 1 SSH)
Institutional mediators (2)	Institutional science communicators working at publishers (0 or 1) - (might be allocated at the project level) Institutional science communicators working at universities and research institutes (1 or 2)
Non-institutional mediators (8)	Professional science writers: authors of popular books or other content (minimum 1) Science journalists: major print, television, radio, magazines, etc. (minimum 1) Authors of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. (minimum 1) Other content creators (including disruptors, both 'contrarian' and 'activist' who use scientific research in relation to our cases) (minimum 1)

(Source: EIS Protocol, p.19)

Each national partner was responsible for their own recruitment, and to translate the EIS Information Sheet provided by CSIC. Details on the national level recruitment processes can be found in the various EIS National Reports.

2.8. National Reporting

Following the same procedure used in the previous Public Consultation and Focus Group studies in POIESIS, the Task Lead provided a National Report template. This template contained a set of intermediary tables, designed to enable the rapid harvesting of descriptive data and information for compiling in the Global Report. The Template included a series of sections in which national teams were required to write a text synthesis of their interview data based on the main EIS themes. A Codebook was provided that functioned primarily as an organizing device to assist National Report writers to identify and compile illustrative quotes for inclusion in their text summaries. Further provision was made in the template for description of any emerging themes. The Template also asked national teams to synthesize Recommendations from participants' suggestions for how to improve citizen trust in science.

2.9. Quality assurance

The EIS followed the POIESIS quality assurance process described in section 3.1 of D5.1 (Horbach & Ravn 2023). An internal reviewer was invited to provide comments on the draft of D2.3, with these comments taken into account in producing the revised version for submission. An additional reading and set of comments was also provided by the POIESIS Coordinator.

Due to the large volume of material expected in the National Reports, the EIS Protocol proposed an additional process to support quality assurance. This proposed process involved interchanging National Reports among partners for cross-reading and short comments. However, the timing of the delivery of National Reports made this approach practically unfeasible, as many partners went on annual leave immediately after submitting their National Report. In discussion with the Coordinator and Work Package Lead it was decided to shift to a centralized model to support quality assurance at the level of the National Reports. Whilst this Global Report was being prepared National Reports were read and edited by the team at Aarhus. Revised National Reports were then finalized and are attached at Appendix 4.

2.10. Interview translation

POIESIS partners wrote their National Reports in English, working off the local language transcripts of their interviews. In the subsequent activity of Task 2.3, partners will translate their interviews into English and deliver the transcripts to the Task Lead CSIC (September 2024).

3. Expert Interview Study participants

This section provides details on the Mediators and Researchers who participated in the EIS. Information on a variety of demographic and professional characteristics are contained in a series of tables. More detail can be found on participants by looking at the correspond tables in each of the National Reports. The first part of this section contains information on our Mediator participants, followed by information on our Researcher participants.

3.1. About our Mediators

Two types of Mediators were defined in the EIS Protocol:

- Institutional mediators: science communication officer working at publishers and universities; and
- Non-institutional mediators: Science writers; journalists; and authors of science-related blogs and podcasts; and other content creators.

Following discussions at the POIESIS GA in Paris in November 2023, it was agreed to place a very strong emphasis on involving Mediator participants from outside research and innovation organisations.

Targets were set for each POIESIS Partner to conduct 10 of a project total of 70 Mediator interviews for the EIS. Of these, eight should be with non-institutional mediators and two with institutional mediators (in total 56 and 14 interviews respectively). Within the non-institutional Mediator category, a further target was to interview at least one science writer, one journalist, one producer of science-related blogs and podcasts or other types of content. It was considered that these targets would ensure a broad spectrum of non-institutional communicators about science were covered in the EIS.

Secondary targets were also set for our Mediator sample. Gender balance was sought as closely as possible. Individuals at early, mid- and senior career stages were targeted, reasoning that this could increase the diversity of participants' target audiences.

Table 3.1. Mediator participant characteristics (n=78)

Country	Gender		Career stage			Mediator type			
	F	M	Early	Mid	Senior	Science writer or communicator	Journalist	Blogs, podcasts, other content	Institutional
Denmark	3	7	-	-	10	2	1	4	3
France	7	7	7	5	2	3	4	1	6
Germany	5	5	1	3	6	3	4	1	2
Greece	3	8	-	5	6	2	2	3	4
Portugal	8	3	1	4	6	1	2	6	2
Spain	3	8	1	5	5	5	1	2	3
UK	8	3	1	2	8	1	1	3	6
TOTAL	37	41	11	24	43	17	15	20	26

The overall target of 70 interviews for the EIS was exceeded with a total of 78 interviews conducted. Five of the seven POIESIS partners conducted more interviews than their target of 10.

The interviews were planned to be strongly prioritised toward the inclusion of non-institutional participants working as Mediators outside public R&I organisations. Overall, a total of 52 interviews were conducted with non-institutional Mediators, just below our target of 56. Four of the POIESIS partners met their target of 8 non-institutional Mediator interviews and one partner exceeded this target.

A total of 14 interviews with institutional Mediators were planned. This target was substantially exceeded with a total of 26 institutional Mediator interviews conducted. All POIESIS partners either met or exceeded their target of two institutional Mediator interviews.

In terms of the distribution by Mediator type, all POIESIS partners succeeded in achieving the planned diversity of participants. A relatively even balance was obtained between science writes and popularisers, journalists, and creators of other types of content.

Regarding our secondary sampling targets, a gender balanced sample was achieved overall. At the individual country level this was often not the case. In terms of the career stage of participants, more than half were at a senior career stage. Nevertheless, six of the seven POIESIS partners were able to include a good number of early and/or mid-career Mediators among their participants.

Further detail on the composition and any variation in the planned and final sample of Mediator participants can be found in Section 1 of the respective National Reports.

3.2. About our Researchers

As described in the EIS Protocol, participating Researchers should be topical experts in climate change and COVID-19, who are actively involved in studying and communicating about the content of science related to these topical areas. This focus on two cases with in-built public controversy and heightened science communication challenges for researchers was a planned element of the POIESIS project design.

Targets were set for each POIESIS Partner to conduct six of a project total of 42 Researcher interviews for the EIS. Of these, three should be with Researchers working on climate change and three with Researchers working on COVID-19. Of the three participants for each of our topic case areas, one interview should be with a Researcher from the SSH fields.

Secondary targets were also set for our Researcher sample. Gender balance was sought as closely as possible. Individuals at early, mid- and senior career stages were targeted, reasoning that researchers in different career phases might have varying degrees of opportunity and interest in communicating and working directly with citizens.

Table 3.2. Researcher participant characteristics (n=41)

Country	Gender		Career stage			Discipline				Case context	
	<i>F</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Early</i>	<i>Mid</i>	<i>Senior</i>	<i>Nat & Phys</i>	<i>Med</i>	<i>Eng</i>	<i>SSH</i>	<i>Climate</i>	<i>COVID-19</i>
Denmark	4	2	-	2	4	1	1	-	4	3	3
France	1	5	3	-	3	3	1	-	2	2	2
Germany	3	3	1	2	3	1	1	-	4	4	2
Greece	2	3	-	-	5	2	1	1	1	3	2
Portugal	5	1	1	1	4	3	1	-	2	3	3
Spain	3	3	-	2	4	2	1	1	2	3	3
UK	1	5	1	-	5	2	2	-	2	3	3
TOTAL	19	22	6	7	28	14	8	2	17	21	18

Overall, a total 41 interviews were conducted with Researchers for the EIS. This was one less than our plan to include 42 participants in this part of the study. Six of the seven POIESIS partners achieved their target of six Researcher interviews.

In terms of Researchers' disciplines, each POIESIS planned for two interviews with SSH Researchers for a total of 14 SSH participants. Preferably one of the SSH participants in each partner country would be working on each of our climate and COVID-19 case contexts. A total of 17 SSH Researchers participated in the interviews. Five of the seven POIESIS partners achieved their SSH Researcher target, whilst also succeeding in covering both case contexts.

Regarding our secondary sampling targets, a gender balanced sample was achieved overall. At the individual country level this was more mixed. In terms of the career stage of Research participants, two-thirds were at a senior career stage. Nevertheless, six of the seven POIESIS partners were able to include early and/or mid-career Researchers among their participants.

Further detail on the composition and any variation in the planned and final sample of Researcher participants can be found in Section 1 of the respective National Reports.

4. Mediators translating between science and society

This chapter describes and discusses the results of the EIS series of Mediator interviews. A total of 78 Mediators participated in the EIS. An overview of these participants is provided in Table 3.1.

In studying the relationships between REI and public trust in science, Mediators play a particularly crucial role in which the logics of the field of R&I overlap with those of the media field. Mediators in the EIS were approached from the perspective of being active agents involved in constructing the relationship between science and society. By targeting non-institutional Mediators in particular, we were able to follow the process between scientific practices and outputs and the general public as it passes through the hands of different types of professional and independent content creators.

The Mediator interview series was designed to focus principally on the integrity dimension of the 3i4T model. In what follows in this section we thus looked at how our Mediators source information, verify its quality, produce their own content, and deliver this work to different publics. Their experiences and perceptions of the importance of REI issues in their work are also brought into focus.

4.1. Chains of Mediation

Chains of mediation were defined in the EIS Protocol (p. 17) as “networks of actors, activities, and sequences of practices that connect research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of scientific research by the wider publics”. Mediators were defined primarily in their active role in shaping the content that passes through these chains, as a “node in the translation process that contributes to transforming the object/output”. This first section provides an overall mapping of the chains of mediation connecting science with society and the roles of Mediators in translating science to the public. It is based on, and can be read in conjunction with, Section 2.1 of the respective National Reports, where summary tables compiling descriptive information about Mediators and chains of mediation can be found (Appendix 4).

Table 4.1. Mediators' main sources of information for their work (n=78)

Country	Interpersonal networks		Science press releases		Science literature	Main-stream media	Social media	Selected others
	With researchers	With science communicators	Research performing organisations	Publishers				
Denmark	9	7	6	1	10	7	5	Political actors
France	13	5	5	5	4	5	7	RPO scientific leadership
Germany	10	5	6	-	10	3	3	Professional associations; Science Media Center
Greece	5	4	4	6	7	3	2	International publishers
Portugal	11	6	2	1	8	5	2	Technical manuals; documentaries & TV; Institutional committees; Clients; Websites
Spain	10	8	4	3	10	2	3	Professional associations; Legislation; Court sentencing repository; Science textbooks
UK	7	5	2	2	7	6	6	-
TOTAL	65	40	29	18	56	31	28	

Of the 78 Mediators participated in the EIS, 52 work in the private sector or independently, and 26 work in public R&I organisations, principally universities or research institutes (Table 3.1).

The **sources of information** most commonly used by Mediators (Table 4.1) include a notably direct interaction with both scientists and research results. A total of 65 Mediators (77%) rely on interpersonal networks with researchers for access to information for their work, while 56 (72%) read scientific articles. Interestingly, the next most common source of information are colleagues working in science communication. The importance for Mediators of being connected to interpersonal networks of professional colleagues stretching across science and the media fields is evident.

Press releases are a less common sources of information for Mediators. However, more than one-third use press releases from research performing organisations and almost a quarter use press releases from academic publishers. Mainstream and social media sources are equally prominent information sources overall, each being used by 40% and 36% of Mediators respectively.

A broad range of additional information sources are also used by Mediators. These include contacts in various types of institutional positions, technical and legal documentation, and professional organisations.

Table 4.2. Types of communication outputs produced by Mediators (n=78)

Country	Books	Articles	Audiovisual (TV)	Radio program	Podcast	Audiovisual (social media)	Text Post (Social media) *	Live (social media interaction)	Selected others
Denmark	4	8	2	3	4	-	7	-	Satisfaction survey; museum exhibitions
France	3	11	1	2	2	5	13	1	Games; graphic novel
Germany	2	9	2	2	5	-	4	1	Stage shows; Games; Art; Communication training; Networking platform; Videos/films
Greece	2	4	1	1	5	5	6	2	Education modules; Guided tours; Demonstration laboratories
Portugal	1	3	-	-	3	6	5	1	Digital games & art; Illustrations; Graphics, posters, flyers; digital games; Letter exchanges & meetings - scientists and children; Reports
Spain	4	5	3	3	2	6	5	1	Satisfaction surveys; Posters; Newsletters; Artistic performances; Illustrations; Protocols;

									Press releases; Art exhibitions
UK	4	5	5	3	5	2	7	3	-
TOTAL	20	45	14	14	26	24	47	9	-

Textual outputs are the most common **products of Mediators' work**. Articles of different types and text posts for social media are equally important forms for communication, being produced by 58% and 60% of Mediators respectively. Long form books are also a prominent form of output among our Mediators (26%).

Podcasts (33%) and audiovisual material designed for social media (31%) are the next most common outputs from Mediators' work.

The production of outputs designed for more traditional media forms such as television and radio is less common (18%) among Mediators.

Our Mediators also produce an enormous range of other types of outputs from their work. These include a diverse range of artistic outputs, games, and exhibitions. Many of these outputs have a more general educational purpose rather than seeking to communicate on a specific topic, highlighting the diversity of interests and capabilities of participating Mediators.

Table 4.3. Main communication channels used by Mediators (n=78 Mediators)

Country	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)							Selected others
	TV	Radio	Newspaper	Websites	Blogs	Newsletters	LinkedIn	Youtube	Twitter	Instagram	TikTok	Facebook	Other SN	
Denmark*	3	3	6	5	6	1	2	-	-	2	-	1	5	Museum exhibits; Education programs for children
France	2	1	5	11	3	3	3	4	10	1	-	1	1	-
Germany	-	3	4	7	3	3	4	2	4	5	1	-	5	Artistic performance; podcast platforms; live events
Greece	1	1	5	10	1	-	1	5	2	3	3	3	3	Museum exhibits; live events
Portugal	2	1	4	10	1	4	4	2	3	7	1	3	6	Art installations; Live events; Letter exchanges
Spain	5	6	6	5	3	3	6	6	8	7	2	-	3	Webinars; live events
UK	6	5	8	8	7	5	4	4	8	2	1	-	1	Whatsapp; Telegram
TOTAL	19	20	38	56	24	19	24	23	35	27	8	8	24	-

* Denmark: Social media not further specified n=6

The main **communication channels** used by Mediators are spread quite evenly between traditional media, purely internet-based outlets, and various social media platforms. Other channels mentioned by Mediators include exhibitions and live events.

Table 4.4. Audiences for Mediators' work

Country	Audiences
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Professional groups • School children
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Readers of national press in print or online • Citizens unfamiliar with scientific culture, particularly teenagers and young adults • Science-related professional groups
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Younger people interested in science, climate • Stakeholders in policy, industry, research • Journalism professional community
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adult and younger audiences with interest in science • Specialist audiences for medical, archaeology topics • Researchers and university students
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Students and teachers at various educational levels • Specialist medical and rural audiences
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Young people and students, educational • Citizens interested in climate change activism
UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Citizens interested in Climate change, education and activism

The main **audience** for Mediators work is the general public. However, Mediators also target specific audiences through particular channels depending on the type of output being communicated. Notable audiences for Mediators are young people and students, including those motivated by climate change knowledge and activism. There are

specialist audience tied also to different types of science and technology interest areas. The scale of Mediators' audiences was not consistently available or obtained in the context of the interviews. Many Mediators have personal audiences of modest sizes, but large numbers of readers or viewers through mass traditional media audiences. The Mediator sample includes many individuals with social media followers or subscribers numbering in the hundreds of thousands, and a couple of cases with more than one million followers or subscribers.

4.1.1. Assessing the credibility of information

Our Mediators have close interpersonal connections to researchers and are comfortable dealing directly with **scientific literature** (Table 4.1). These important sources of information for their work provide a certain level of institutional reputation-based credibility for information that Mediators may be considering translating into content for their audiences. However, the question of reliability of this information does not rely unquestioningly on reputations.

Institutional mediators **speak directly with researchers** and follow internal protocols to assure themselves of the credibility of information about a new scientific result.

I think our role is to ask, and when we don't understand or when we find it strange to talk to others in the area. (...) I ask [researchers] in the specialty area, right? "Look, is this article really like that or, or do you think it's too much?" And when we have researchers who tell us, "Maybe these adjectives are a little too much", we have to do the down grading. (PT_M02)

(...) when there is a research result to promote and publicise, there is a process that is the same for everyone. There has to be scientific validation by the Institute. And scientific validation means that (...) for example for a result in [...], we go and see the deputy scientific director in charge of [...], we say "Oh, we've received this result, what do you think of it? Do we publicise it or not?" So, whether the results comes to us from the delegation, from the communication office, or from the lab, the process is the same, it'll be the same ... no one will work individually I think. (FR_M09)

Although a research result may have already passed a process of peer review, institutional Mediators engage in a process of consultation

and verification to clarify for themselves that this scientific work merits dissemination and promotion.

Non-institutional science communicators also require more than reputation as a safeguard that information they may want to use for their work is credible.

So, it is definitely not enough to quote someone just because they have a title; you have to check if they can speak credibly, if it aligns with the rest of the research. So, it's important for me to be able to assess that. (DE_M03)

The issue of consensus is something that's often an important point when approaching a topic (...) When I work in a team, if we know that we have something to talk about, if we know that (...) scientists are more or less all in agreement, we'll start with that topic. That doesn't mean that you can't mention opposing views, and it doesn't mean that you can't mention certain things that are still being developed or on which there is no consensus, if that's not the focus of the topic. (FR_M11)

These science communicators place great store in understanding the **state-of-the-art in a particular topic or discipline**. The relationship of a particular finding or paper to the scientific consensus is important and something they feel it is important to personally understand.

The importance of interpersonal connections in building confidence and receiving assurance is highlighted here as well.

It's often difficult to get answers to these questions from press releases from universities. You don't usually get them from papers either. You're most likely to get them if you have researchers on the phone. (DE_M03)

As I only deal there with a very closed group of scientists, I already know that they are, at least initially, credible... (PT_M04)

It is important to me that the people I use as sources have standards of scientific integrity, and I try to determine that based on various criteria. Naturally, when I talk to experts, I don't initially discuss their integrity standards but try to determine it by other factors. (DE_M10)

Science journalists are particularly concerned about the credibility and reliability of the sources for their work. Many specialist science journalists work for large media organisations, where fact-checking and veracity of their contributions are essential. Their **training in a profession** with certain standards is considered a first line of assurance when dealing with novel or potentially attention-grabbing science information.

Once you are trained, you know by the book how the professional evaluation of research quality goes. And for that, you need to be a science journalist; you can't be anything else. That is the internal distinction we have, which is somewhat threatened by the sheer quantity of online content. (DE_M08)

As with science communicators, journalists also place a high value on the scientific consensus. The apparent novelty of a new results or finding does not alone guarantee its take-up by Mediators.

I must be able to reflect on the state of research. I cannot pretend that a single result fell from the sky and that nothing was known before. That is a common journalistic mistake, seeing paradigm shifts everywhere when there are none. When 50 papers make a statement and one says something different, it is still 50 to one. (DE_M08)

But perhaps even more important for specialist science journalists is to engage in a process of **third-party verification** or assessment of new information that they may wish to develop into new content.

The evaluation is done firstly indirectly through the fact that they have gone through a peer review process etc. And secondly, to the extent that they are in subjects in which I have a relative competence, I can also have a relative judgment. The second is in relevant material with which I come into contact through my network of associates, either at the university or former professional associates, with whatever credibility they can offer to the material proposed by them, with positive or negative connotations. And the third one, on the websites that I mostly trust, is a matter of whether they have proper citations to reliable sources or whether the very writing of their writers is trustworthy. (GR_M04)

So that's probably one of the most complicated parts of the job (...) It's really difficult. First of all because people change...

those who are serious can become not so serious, they can start talking nonsense about a subject... It's a constant job to get colleagues to reaffirm the seriousness of this or that person. I work like this a lot (...) I'll give you an example: a scientific study that we think is great. We want to talk about it. We'll call the researchers, the team, etc., and then (...) if we have time, we'll try to force ourselves to always call outside people we know, who have a good reputation, and say to them: "Oh, have you seen this? Is this interesting research?" (...) Of course we have to try to do some research. For researchers, we check the Retraction Watch database to see if they've had any articles retracted (...). (FR_M07)

These journalists use multiple sources of verification in order to gain an overall picture of the research they are assessing. This includes a dual assessment of the research results themselves but also of the scientist or research group that has produced the result. This is not a static landscape, and reputations are not eternal or universal. External validation of appearances needs to be updated and past experiences not assumed as taken for granted guarantees. As these journalists recount, this investigation takes a historical perspective in assessing the track record of the producers of the new results in terms of both credibility but also any prior incidence of poor practices that might be revealed.

Finally, as one journalist with a large daily newspaper explained, they sometimes receive privileged or advance notice of new articles that publishers or institutions wish to promote more broadly. Being provided access prior to the official publication date allows time for Mediators to perform their own credibility checks.

I have several sources of experts in scientific ethics, so we send them the paper, as we have access to the papers under embargo, a few days before publication we have 5 or 6 days to send it to experts in ethics and they tell us, "I don't see any problem in making an embryo with a mixture of human and monkey cells", or if this is controversial as it is ethics... (ES_M11)

Rather than rely on their own experience or knowledge of the scientist or institution producing new results, journalists also use the **services of specialists**, including in ethics, to assist them form confidence and a solid basis for their work.

Mediators thus employ a range of strategies in order to verify the credibility and reliability of source information. As a basic input to their work, it is vital to professional communicators and

journalists that they take all steps necessary to assure themselves to the nearest extent possible that they can be certain about the inputs they are using. Of course, such processes are not foolproof. However, they also provide evidence of due diligence for that moment when, to paraphrase one journalist, 'the lawyers arrive in your Editor's office'.

4.1.2. Creativity, translation, success

Mediators' creative process starts from the process of identifying a **topic or subject** to work on. There is significant difference between long-term topics and those that might be driven by the short-term news cycle. It is also important to identify topics that are of scientific importance but also have the potential to awaken the public interest. This means being proactive, being signed up to press releases, newsletters and other periodic outputs that are designed to alert the wider world to activity occurring in science.

Of course, our assessment is important in this regard: How relevant is what is being published or what the institution is working on for the public discourse? Many people think you get a press release and just write it down. But at least for us, it's different: we assess its relevance. If it doesn't have any, no matter how great the press release, it won't be processed because it's not relevant to us at the moment. (DE_M04)

The typical process is that we try to stay ahead of the game and identify the topic ourselves before any laypeople in the editorial office think it would be great to cover. (DE_M08)

For science journalists this is also important due to the reality that their field is **competitive**.

(...) the most beautiful analogy of my work is the funnel. So I receive this amount of information and I have this amount time to process it. And the problem I have is identifying the information that's really important. And it's true that sometimes, the fact that [X] or [Y] publishes a press release about an article that I've seen in a summary... I say to myself... In fact, I say two things to myself: 1) maybe this paper is really important; 2) the fact that [X] communicates on it, I have colleagues who are going to process it. So maybe I need to deal with it too. Either because it will come to the attention of my bosses who will say "oh,

there's something... and we don't have it...", or because in fact it will create a little flow on the internet so that this article will be read and there will be an expectation around it. (FR_M06)

Once a topic has been settled on, or agreed collectively, the creative process begins in earnest. A wide range of sources is used to **develop the background** against which Mediators' outputs are contextualised. This is often a time-consuming and difficult work.

The greatest or the most difficult task in my work is often getting an overview. DE_R03

Mediators consult secondary literature, relevant reports in mainstream media, social media, popular science magazines. Some Mediators refer to Wikipedia, mainly as an aggregator of interesting primary sources. Interpersonal networks are tapped into, both within the research community and professionally, although journalists are seemingly more guarded about their intentions than science communicators.

The creative process in preparing the overview and understanding the context is linked to the search for what is **relevant for the audience** and, within that, and **angle** through which it can be made **relatable** to the public. Essential ingredients of the communication such as 'numbers and facts should be presented in a way that resonates with people's daily lives. The most important objective being to reach the audience for example by the 'means of **storytelling** and incorporating surprising elements in the content' (DE NR, p.27).

Other Mediators reflect on the use of **humour** to 'break down the image of a cold and impersonal science' (FR NR, p.20).

For example, how do I explain ChatGPT? I don't do the phonetic joke that you can guess, but what I do is say "it's very simple, the mouse is eaten by the..." So children often answer "cat". It could be "tiger" but it's cat. The "sky" is... "blue" and so on. I tell them "well, it's a thing that predicts the next word". (...) And so what ChatGPT does is just predict the next word, the next word and it predicts sentences. And it's this simple mechanism (...) that is unreasonably effective. (FR_M10)

The importance of finding a **narrative that communicates relevance** of a story to the audience, using such techniques is the key to Mediators conceptualization of their translational 'magic'.

This creative is nevertheless embedded in a very consistent and rigorous workflow. Mediators across the POIESIS countries report a **systematic approach** to support the demands on, and potential of, their creativity.

An interest in dealing with a particular topic emerges and I search for relevant literature reconstructing the literature review, focusing on main issues. Research objects are highlighted, and this work proceeds with the corresponding incorporation of conclusions and in an effort in terms of popularization with an eye to the audience in which each product I produce is of interest... (GR_M04)

Creative processes are described as 'rich' in the sense that they always involve the use of diverse sources, interpersonal contacts inside science and in the media field (ES NR, p.24). Some of the sources also function as important nodes in science journalist dissemination networks, drawing attention to their work amongst relevant parties.

As summarised in Table 4.1, Mediators are highly reliant on their capacity to engage personally with the scientific literature.

...scientific publications are also a source for me, even if they're not yet popularised (...) it's a first step towards popularisation (...) let's just say that I'm a subscriber to the Science and Nature newsletters, for example, which gives me the latest news on what's being done, a bit of information on what's happening in the field of science at the moment, what's been published, the latest things (...) And then also in the community of popularisers, there's also mutual aid in the sense that we can ask for proofreading or say "here, I've seen this topic go by, what do you think? I'm not a specialist. Do you think it's important? I'd like to look at it from my angle... my speciality, my way of dealing with things". We can identify information that is circulating (...) (FR_M11)

However, what also emerges from this quote and is reflected widely by Mediators is the **collective dimension** involved in much of their work. Going beyond seeking to ensure the veracity and reliability of information they plan to use (Section 4.1.1.), exploring all the angles of a story within their own community of practice or

professional networks helps Mediators to sharpen the perspective they plan to adopt in using information to develop their outputs.

In journalistic contexts, the relationship between writers and in-house editorial teams also contributes to the translation of information into something that, ultimately, resonates with and can be understood by the perceived target audience. 'Every word may be proofread by in-house editors before publication. Some experts describe this editing work as a process in which the reader is taken from his or her level of scientific knowledge, which is generally assumed to be relatively low, to the level of scientific consensus that precedes the scientific information to be covered, and then from the scientific consensus to the scientific information itself, which alone constitutes the news' (FR NR, p.23).

For the profession of science journalism, however, sometimes the challenge of finding what is positively relevant for the audience can be inverted. There are situations where the journalist is placed in the 'difficult position' of having to downplay or critically assess some discovery hype or headline-grabbing scientific news.

They could say, 'Ah, he always makes it so complicated, says it's not as exciting as it really is. He always talks down the sensational news.' But no, I get the space from the editors to explain it thoroughly from the start. And sometimes, the sensation has to be downplayed compared to how it initially sounds in the reporting. But I enjoy that. (DE_M03)

A re-balancing of 'sensational news' attractive enough to ensure the public is well-informed about its merits is an important challenge as this German journalist identifies. It is indeed also a challenge for science journalists that, at times, they find it necessary 'in the public interest' to contradict or criticize the work of independent science communicators and content creators, or even institutional communication outlets.

The experiences and perceptions of our Mediators are also shaped by the **differences between institutional and non-institutional work roles**. The institutional translation process can begin because researchers contact the Mediator to prepare a communication strategy for results they have obtained. Equally it can begin because the mediator reviews the articles or patents produced by researchers in their organisation and contacts them to propose a communication strategy. This is where the process of creating institutional communication outputs, traditionally press releases, begins. The

content creation process involves interactive work between the Mediator and the scientist. Sometimes this process involves collaboration with other institutional mediators from other research organisations that have participated in the research to be communicated (ES NR, p.22).

Institutional mediators thus consider as key groups in their close mediation network both the scientists from whom they receive inputs, and the community of institutional mediators and science communicators with whom they collaborate and share professional concerns. These institutional mediators often follow a more **stable plan** in their activities as they depend on the institutional strategy for science communication, meaning that there are some regular activities that they conduct, for example hosting exhibitions or circulating newsletters.

Starting from the laboratory strategy, and this is scientific strategy, the political strategy in terms of intergovernmental organization, of assuming a communication strategy and then, based on that communication strategy, defining and implementing different activities that answer to the objectives of that communication strategy. (PT_M01)

For institutional Mediators, once their output has been prepared, they typically disseminate it through their non-institutional Mediator colleague network, made up of science journalists who they think will be interested in the topic and who can communicate it to the public through their media channels. Typically, institutional mediators do not engage in delivering their outputs directly to citizens. As the targets of these institutional outputs, usually press releases, science journalists need to be selective in view of the competitive environment in which they work (FR NR, p.21). The formation of tight networks between institutional and selected non-institutional Mediators working in mass media is thus a common part of the professional science communication landscape.

In contrast, non-institutional Mediators who are not science journalists have more freedom about topic selection and often a **less stabilised creative process and workflow**. Social media influencers, for instance, show less planning and more improvisation in their activities (PT NR, p.23).

In our world, it is rushing, sometimes in great whirlwind, we make an instantaneous assessment and immediately realise: this subject

*is going to be interesting; this is new, this is new for science.
No one has ever done this. (PT_M11)*

This process has a more *bricolage* or spontaneous feel to it. One non-institutional Mediator referred to the creativity and translation using the term 'concurrency' mean a dual process of learning about the subject matter while disseminating it (DK NR, p.26). This experience is echoed by another content creator:

The creative process is practically the research process. I call all my things the scientific process, because it's the same thing: research, hypotheses, I could go this way, no... the creative process for me is the same. (ES_M08)

It should be noted that this freedom is not the case for non-institutional Mediators working for private organisations, particularly those focused on R&I lobbying and policy issues. For these Mediators the topics, outputs, and channels that structure their translation process are required to conform closely to the objectives and protocols of their organisation (ES NR, p.21).

Mediators are able to articulate a clear vision of what they consider **success** in their work. Their descriptions reveal dual logics, a qualitative personal satisfaction with what their communication work may achieve, and a quantitative estimation of its reach or the 'eyeballs' that it attracts.

From a more personal perspective, many Mediators exhibit an ethic of care toward their audiences.

The most important thing for me is to open up new grounds for sensitivity, to reach new groups that have never dealt with these topics before. (DE_M05)

Successful for me are the cases where a person who takes advantage of a vulnerable patient to sell a (controversial) drug ends up with some kind of legal consequences, imprisonment or a fine. (GR_M05)

The real success for me is when I notice that someone does something differently in real life because of something they learned from me. (DE_M09)

Other Mediators' descriptions of their practice capture the educational qualities of their work.

My success would be if the knowledge about the aquatic environment and the climate, which we realists have, also became part of the general discussion. But it isn't. It's nowhere near being the framework for discussion. Instead, it's always about hysteria, exaggerated alarmism, or denial of facts. (DK_M10)

So success for me is to break this duality, (technophobia-technophilia) that is to put the place of technology in a... -both to protect technologies from possible limitations that a technophobic perception of what will happen if our machines take our jobs can impose- and to protect technology from a technophilic perception that doesn't see the risks. (GR_M09)

One Mediator whose creative process is based on art and combinatorial interdisciplinary experiments finds rewarding 'giving examples on how research can affect the life of society. She defines success in describing adequately to lay people how research is being conducted - the methodology of research and not necessarily in communicating success stories, since the biggest part of research is a story of failure. This can increase trust in research, since failures can be put into the framework of what research is, and not act as an indication of bad research' (GR NR, p.20).

Finally, this educational perspective can be designed or hoped to grow the public audience for communicating science. This includes by constructing online infrastructures that can benefit not just citizens but also his science popularising colleagues.

... there's what works for me ... and there's what works for the public. So I've seen two big breaks. There was the break with video. ... I really became aware of this phenomenon when there was an event ... with web videographers invited to the main lecture hall at ENS Lyon. ... We were expecting people to have left, and in fact the amphitheatre was full. There were people on the pavement who couldn't get in. So I thought, "Wow!" ... Then there was Zetetics, and you can see that with Zetetics, ... there's clearly an audience, and so on. There's the Zetetics meetings, which are a great way to get to know people. So it takes different forms, including events, etc... And we can see that it reaches people who, well... who might not have been reached by popularisation. (FR_M05)

Overall, Mediators express **personal desires** that their work 'reaches a wider audience, that it makes a difference, is placed in a relevant societal context, and creates insight and reflection. Additionally, that the population becomes more informed, that the output 'brings things to light,' and is well received by [both] professionals and relevant readers (DK NR, p.21).

In terms of '**measuring**' **success**, online delivery channels offer numerous metrics that can help monitor the effectiveness in delivering communication outputs, without being able to necessarily understand the impact they might have. For institutional mediators, the use of data about users may be 'off-limits' for privacy or ethical reasons.

That's a very good question, because we're actually a little bit stuck (...) We're committed to not tracking subscribers. But obviously, the other side of the coin is that we don't have the read rates. When we first started using the tool, we thought "gosh, it's going to give us that" and we blocked all those functions because we didn't want to be involved in that. So it's a bit difficult to measure... (FR_M04)

Rather, for such institutional Mediators a key indicator of a 'job well done' is the number of mentions their outputs receive from science journalists (FR NR, p.19; ES NR, p.22).

In the more competitive environment of science journalism the markers of success are more closely **monitored and quantified**.

(...) all newsrooms have more or less the same [technical tools] that allow us to count the number of page views we get per article, to count the number of conversions an article can generate, i.e. the number of times someone clicks on the article under the paywall, who is not normally a monthly subscriber, and who subscribes thanks to this article. This is a very strong signal that an article or topic is of interest (FR_M07).

While converting a reader into a subscriber is a highly valued outcome, more typical metrics are the number of clicks on an article link, the number of reads, and the volume and content of reader comments.

Science journalists working in mass media can be involved in monitoring how their work is received in **real-time**.

*We have that on our mobile phone and we look at it constantly, come on! ... Yes, yes, yes, of course, of course, in other words, we have the most read news on the website in real time. And of course, you go in to see what is working and you immediately see if it works because people are reading it, don't you? You have a minute or two minutes reading time, or if people are reading it because maybe the headline seemed attractive, but you see that they are only 10 seconds in, so the topic may have many clicks, but it is a ***** because no one is reading it in its entirety, right?*

Knowing the impression your work is making in real-time can be a stressful accompaniment where the logic of the media field is overlapping with logics of care and education embedded in science communication activities. In fact, this Mediator notes something of a shift in the way media organisations are self-monitoring and assessing their impact in the media space.

*And there is another important factor, which is that a few years ago the press went crazy with clicks. The objective was the click, so... well... there are still many newspapers that publish four paragraphs of information without a byline...4 paragraphs with information that maybe is not directly false, but is misleading, right? like 'closer to the cancer vaccine' and it is without a byline. That might get you a lot of visits that I don't know if they bring you anything nowadays, but well, that model, at least in [national newspaper], is over. Well, we never did that either, but now it's a subscription model. So readers pay for quality information, so now, yes or yes, we have to produce good quality information, with multiple transparent sources, in which the reader says, '*****, I want to pay for this quality information. In fact ... the 'press no longer looks for clicks, it looks for clock' because of the clock, in other words, the time readers spend in the paper. In other words, a reader, we can know how many seconds a reader is inside the news item and even up to which paragraph he/she reaches, can't we? So, the great success? Going back to the question you asked before about success, it is also that people read it in its entirety, that is, that they don't click on it and say 'This doesn't meet my expectations', but that they say, 'Damn, this exceeds my expectations and I'll read it in its entirety', right? So, we are looking for the clock, the dwell time, not the click. (ES_M11)*

As this science journalist Mediator describes approvingly, a model built on time citizens spend engaging with science communications is a model that promotes quality better than a model built on clicks, on the effectiveness of attention-grabbing headlines. The shift in

metric and monitoring reflects a change in the competitive business model - **from clicks to clocks** - impacting some actors in the media field. Perhaps the repercussions of the social media click-mining model may be starting to reside, or at least be viewed as open to a competing and quality-focused alternative. For the science journalist profession, their interested publics, and citizens at large, this seems to be a desirable change of direction.

4.1.3. Direct to citizens

The Mediator interviews in the EIS were principally designed to understand the salience of the integrity dimension of the 3i4T model in the mediation process. However, in the course of the interviews Mediators were also invited to speak about their direct interactions with citizens. Mediators are also engaged in **direct interactions with citizens**. Greater detail on these interactions can be found in Table 5 of the respective National Reports (Appendix 4).

Mediators described an impressive range of activities and forms of interaction that they undertake with citizens. These interactions include:

- Public town hall meetings
- Participation in activist groups for climate change
- Text interactions in closed and open social media networks
- Public forums or science promotion activities
- Exhibitions
- Stage shows or artistic performances
- School outreach and education events
- Live events on social media platforms
- 'Visit the lab' events
- Online interactive talks or dialogues
- Comments sections of blogs, podcasts, articles, personal websites
- Public lectures with question and answer session
- Direct correspondence, through email or messaging apps
- Book presentations with live audience

Direct interactions with citizens are part of the activities of around three-quarters of our Mediators. While many of the interactions occur with citizens who are already interested in science and technology related topics there is also an important component of educational

activities in which Mediators participate across the POIESIS countries.

While many interactions may be impersonal or brief, other face-to-face activities such as 'programs for schools or summer camps are recognised as having stronger lasting effects on the students' (PT NR, p.23).

People who were with us during high school in some activity, summer courses, those summer camps, that kind of academies, and you lose track of them (...). I had one recently who was there at the foundation as a volunteer at an event. So, she looked at me and said, "Ah, you must not remember me." (...) So, she said, "I discovered my interest in the brain, my fascination with the brain with you, so now I'm waiting to find out the results for the specialty. I'm trying to go into neurosurgery. (PT_M02)

Interactions through digital platforms are also considered valuable.

There [on Facebook] people made a lot of comments every time I released an episode, they made comments, and they were very nice, very, very positive. (PT_M10)

It is apparent across the POIESIS countries that **interactive formats are considered superior** for events such as exhibitions, talks, or lectures. However, several mediators mention receiving negative feedback from different types of citizens and stakeholders. A mediator from a national broadcasting corporation mentioned that they closed their Facebook commentary section due to the management workload and associated resource allocation (DK NR, p.22). Other Mediators participating in the EIS also mentioned taking a break or leaving some social media platforms due to negative interactions, mainly from 'bots' and other actors deliberately attempting to provoke or elevate controversy about climate change or COVID-19 vaccines.

Overall, Mediators engage directly with citizens to varying degrees. They can also have vastly different digital audiences depending on the size of their social media follower or subscriber bases, or the number of users of their traditional media platform. For those with large scale access to citizens, even if they only engage in direct interactions with citizens occasionally, these exchanges can also then be read by far larger audiences and potentially diffused across other platforms. This secondary effect of interactive formats

potentially amplifies the space of science communication into something of a pluriverse.

4.2. What matters about research ethics and integrity?

The POIESIS project has as part of its design the aim to test the **assumption that scientific conduct in terms of research ethics and integrity has an impact on public trust in science**. This assumption has an ambivalent logic:

- If research ethics and integrity practices in the laboratories and fieldwork sites of science are of high quality the level of public trust in science will be improved or maintained; and conversely
- If research ethics and integrity practices in the laboratories and fieldwork sites of science are of low quality the level of public trust in science will be degraded.

This consequentialist reasoning assumes that the appearance of scientific scandals, fraud cases, and unethical practices in the public media and information space, as examples of poor REI practices, will lead to a 'crisis' in public trust in science.

The EIS interviews with Mediators were designed to interrogate this assumption about the relationship between REI practices and public trust in science from Mediators' perspective. This section summarises Mediators perceptions and experiences regarding REI issues in their work. It is largely based on, and can be read in conjunction with, Section 3.2 of the respective National Reports, where greater detail and additional direct quotes from participants can be found (Appendix 4).

The Mediator interview instrument was designed with the sequence: A) Introduction; B) Background; C) Activities and audiences; D) Sources and translation; E) Research ethics and integrity; and F) Public trust in science (Appendix 1). Training for the interviewers ensured they did not ask or prompt participants to talk about REI prior to the dedicated 'hinge' question on REI (Question 11). In this way, if REI or REI-related issues were important to the work of Mediators they could be expected to arise spontaneously prior to Q11. If participants did start to talk about REI issues prior to Q11 then the interviewer was instructed to explore the topic like any other that emerged in response to the first 10 questions.

The result of this process was conclusive. Only one Mediator (of 78) explicitly mentioned REI issues directly in discussing their work, prior to being asked about it. In most POIESIS countries a small minority of Mediators mentioned issues related to the integrity of research practices or ethical questions regarding scientific conduct without explicitly using these terms. As one non-institutional mediator stated after being asked about REI:

These aren't concepts that I really think much about or use in those terms. But I believe that in practice, I'm constantly dealing with them, just without realizing that is what they're called or that is what I'm doing. (DK_M08)

4.2.1. How do research ethics and integrity matter to Mediators?

When the Mediator interview switched to the topic of REI, the following question was asked:

- Q11. What do you understand by the terms research ethics and integrity?

Many Mediators across the POIESIS countries found this question **challenging to answer**. There were few participants who distinguished between ethics and integrity and most of these were institutional Mediators working in research performing institutions. Rather Mediators were able to articulate quite orthodox descriptions of REI in scientific conduct that involved multiple aspects.

Ethics is more, it's more, it's broader than scientific integrity, in my opinion. In my experience, therefore, scientific integrity has more to do with following the rules, the principles of scientific research with regard to sharing observations, recording observations, recording results, especially when they are for publication, sharing information with colleagues (...) Not lying, being faithful to the results that you have and then that are reflected in the publications, being truthful when you go to talk to colleagues about sharing information, not hiding information for your own benefit. For me, this is more about integrity, scientific integrity, perhaps more to do with the practice of science within the community. (...) Ethics has more to do with just thinking about the type of experiment you want to do (...), knowing and adhering to ethical principles. (PT_M01)

[I]t is obligatory for every project you do to submit a proposal to the respective ethics committee before you do it, to evaluate whether the sociological research you are doing has an input. Not only the methodology you are going to use. (GR_M04)

Let's see, we are speakers about the work that is carried out in the research laboratories of [mentions the organisation where he works]. And in this research body, research is all subject to a bioethics committee, etcetera. (ES_M09)

As one institutional Mediator argued, it is also important to understand that scientific communities bare heterogeneous and normative concepts such as ethics and integrity can also have nuances at the disciplinary or specialism level.

...Everyone has their own idea of scientific integrity. It's quite interesting. You see... you give them a slide on the grey area, for example. I did a bit of backpedalling there, because everybody said, "Oh, but for me that's fraud, for me that should be there...". And that's the way it is in my field" (...) the whole point is that they are the ones who make the norms... and that's why I think it's a job, not of proximity, but of understanding the profession (FR_M04)

Mediators in several countries made the shift from trying to articular a vision of ethics or integrity to advocating the **value of transparency**.

You must not cheat, you must not make a money envelope... and invent your own data for something. You need to acknowledge and be aware of what others have done. And you must be very open about your processes. That is to say, you can certainly create something where you think your data is really good and shows something very interesting, which is completely opposite to the rest of the world. But it should ideally be repeatable by others. Otherwise, it's probably just you... (...). Openness is probably the most important thing (DK_M03)

And then there's something about honesty, but many variables come into play, and that's the issue of accessibility, that is to say that what you're doing as a researcher is accessible to the whole world. I strongly believe in open access. (ES_M03)

I would prefer transparency, which is more a preference of my generation, to objectivity. (DE_M10).

Transparency in the institutional context and objectives of science was also linked to REI practices to form a broader definition.

So, a clearly adhered process and methodology. Clarity about what is established and what is not. Honesty, if you will, and transparency regarding the funding and purpose of the research. I consider this extremely important in terms of integrity." (DE_M04)

Mediators agreed that scientists as much as journalists should act as honest brokers with transparency being the most important point in this regard (DE NR, p.28)

Many Mediators went beyond conceiving of REI in terms of practices on the shopfloor of science work to articulate broader visions. The line between research integrity and the integrity of science communication work was 'not always very sharp' (DE NR, p. 27). Many Mediators seem to consider the ethics of their own work more important than ethics in research (PT NR, p.22). Indeed, **research integrity, professional integrity, and personal integrity**, all seemed to be competing for space in Mediators' reflections.

Broader concerns about the conduct of science itself were one aspect of these reflections.

Another aspect that I would like to be able to take more into account is that they have a work ethic in terms of labour rights, but because of the way the communication sector and the research sector is, I can't always take this into account as much as I would like to. I apply it, but I have collaborators who do not. (ES_M02)

Some Mediators also demonstrated a keen understanding of researchers positioning in relation to 'scientific freedom and personal activism' (DE NR, p.27). Seeking transparency and taking a critical perspective about scientists' actions were described as markers of integrity in doing science communication.

Most [of] the media is run by people who are not scientists, who are very critical of science ... we would question science, we're not kind of totally pro what they do, we feel that we, as journalists, have the view to be able to question people on what they're doing, why they're doing it. (UK_M10)

And of course, there is also the question of how activist someone can be. This has almost become a derogatory term. But naturally, if you see something going wrong and it drives you crazy, you are more emotionally involved. But I think integrity is about clearly distinguishing and being transparent. (DE_M06)

Mediators also consider integrity in communicating science to be closely bound up with respecting the **limits of your expertise**. They are able to cast a critical eye over researchers' behaviours in this regard. These 'ventures into other disciplines' are often linked to 'overconfidence', or to a researcher promoting political views, and "more men than women" (DE_M06) are guilty of such transgressions.

This theme of sticking to your area of expertise is also cast as a facet of professional integrity for Mediators

I also did a lot of work on COVID (...) every day there were studies coming out on a subject that we knew very little about, and so the risk is to get it wrong. The risk is that we go too far in the conclusions we draw from these studies. This was the case, for example, with Didier Raoult's publications. I use this example because it is well known. But in fact the paper he published on the first treatments, on hydroxychloroquine, was a rag! [FR_M13]

In contexts where new topics are being presented under time pressure in politicized contexts such as COVID-19 pandemic this form of professional integrity appears even more important.

Other Mediators broaden the conception of what matters to them regarding ethic and integrity to encompass an **attitude of care and respect toward their audience**.

It's important to be honest, to tell the truth, but to adapt that scientific information to the kind of language that can reach and be accessible to the audience. So, I think that really, in terms of accessibility and also ethics, it would be important to respect the people we are talking to, not to patronise them, to be inclusive. And, even if we have to simplify things, don't be disrespectful. (...) To communicate with patients who are going through a serious health situation (...) that is serious or difficult, we can't create illustrations that are funny, for example. (PT_M05)

In summary, Mediators demonstrate a broad perspective on what issues of research ethic and integrity mean to them, and why they care about.

However, perhaps the most important point to understand about REI and Mediators' work is that, from the perspective of Mediators, the sets of institutional relations, professional networks, and trusted interpersonal connections that are described in section 4.1.1. on the **credibility of sources** also functions as the guarantors of the ethics and integrity of research. Mediators reflecting on REI issues produce descriptions that are closely aligned to their discussions of assessing the credibility of sources.

The evaluation is done firstly indirectly through the fact that they have gone through a peer review process etc. And secondly, to the extent that they are in subjects in which I have a relative competence, I can also have a relative judgment. The second is in relevant material with which I come into contact through my network of associates, either at the university or former professional associates, with whatever credibility they can offer to the material proposed by them, with positive or negative connotations. And the third one, on the websites that I mostly trust, is a matter of whether they have proper citations to reliable sources or whether the very writing of their writers is trustworthy. (GR_M04)

Above all, the first filter is the credibility we give to the source. It is not the same to read something in El País or in Nature as it is to read it in a digital Mediterranean or on a page, which is the first time you read it, that you find in a website (ES_M05)

Using these connections and institutional markers to verify the integrity of scientists echoes closely the experiences and perceptions described regarding information sources. A similar process also applies with regard to ensuring the integrity of the Mediators own work.

And then on the other hand, it is true that when there is something important, something big, I have always had contact with... I have a group, a chat with other colleagues from other media. The contact between us, between journalists who specialise in these issues, I think it is also key. ES_M05

I think our role is to ask, and when we don't understand or when we find it strange to talk to others in the area. (...) I ask [researchers] in the specialty area, right? "Look, is this article

really like that or, or do you think it's too much?" And when we have researchers who tell us, "Maybe these adjectives are a little too much", we have to do the down grading. (PT_M02)

In summary, it seems evident from the reflections of our Mediators that **de facto research ethics and integrity do matter significantly in their work**. The terms and the concepts they designate are not typically distinguished analytically by Mediators when recounting their perceptions and experiences. Rather they tend to have a tacit understanding of what they consider is the way things should be done. This understanding stretches right across the science - society continuum. An attention to honesty and transparency in their own practices mirrors their expectations of science and scientists. Mediators typically do not concern themselves with the minutiae of shopfloor practices in science, rather they rely on their interpersonal networks with researchers and other science communicators, and their knowledge of the workings of reputation and prestige in the science system to assure themselves of the credibility of sources and researchers alike. The rigorous attention to the credibility of information (section 4.4.4.) is more or less an index of how Mediators deal with the question of the ethical and integrity dimensions of research.

However, some Mediators, particularly science journalists, also have a keenly developed sense of ethics and integrity as it concerns the way scientists present themselves and their work to the public. Scientists who speak 'outside of their area of expertise' or exaggerate the novelty of an output are noticed by journalists. This concerns institutional Mediators, for whom science journalists are the most important audience for their outputs.

Credibility is one of our main, if not the main, currency we have to achieve our goals and if journalists can't trust us, then we won't achieve anything because they won't trust us. (ES_M04)

The relational repercussions for practices or outputs that fall below shared expectations within the science communication community of practice thus operates as a **strong incentive for integrity and ethical behaviour**. As one Mediator stated, research ethics and integrity "aren't concepts that I really think much about or use in those terms" (DK08). Yet even if not consciously thought about through these words, it seems evident that strongly developed and shared understandings of ethics and integrity are diffused across the workflows of our

Mediators and form a vital part of their professional and personal identities

4.2.2. Challenges, risks, pitfalls

In the course of their reflections and discussion, Mediators also identified a number of issues that they consider problematic. **Institutional issues** that impact on their particular context were mentioned in some countries. In the UK, one non-institutional Mediator argued that science was becoming caught up in a general sense of unfairness and inequality that feeds distrust.

So that's why I think a lot of people don't believe the science and they've gone down a route where they think that science is in the hands of a particular group with a particular agenda. (UK_M07)

In the Greek study, a general lag in institutional development was identified as challenge. According to institutional Mediators there 'the introduction of common good practices in conduct in research is somewhat behind in comparison with Western Europe and North America'. Mediators there are interested but also cautious when it comes to ethical issues, being 'more familiar with an ad hoc approach to resolving REI issues, taking into account the lack of standardized procedures' (GR NR, p. 20). In this context, one Mediator reflected on the value of **European level collaboration** for learning new approaches:

It defined the questions, the groups, the people very clearly and then we collectively made the people who would participate in the project a discussion where with criticism and feedback and so on, we formed the ethics of the practice itself, ()... the good practice itself which should be followed in the end in order to come out with a proper research... And through discussions and experience from colleagues I have formulated a standard procedure. (GR_M09)

In several POIESIS countries the issue of the institutional independence of research was also linked to research ethics and integrity. In particular, the issue of keeping vested interests from wielding too much influence was identified as a risk by Mediators.

Sometimes I read something and think, this might as well be a press release from the company's partners (...). A company plays a huge role, and in some ways, it is really good that we are not just working in our little glass bubble doing research. But I think there is too little focus on the arm's length principle, which I hear leading university officials talk about all the time.
(DK_M02).

The issue of, above all, ensuring that the final source of funding for publications is public, that there is no private entity.
(ES_M05)

Mediators' recognition that pressure was being exerted on the **arm's length principle** reflects their understanding of the governance of science and longer term trends in institutional arrangements.

Although, overall, research ethics and integrity issues in the **conduct of science** were not of high concern among Mediators, prominent public controversies in the COVID-19 context were considered impactful.

If we talk about Didier Raoult, for example, I don't think we've ever talked so much about scientific integrity. In the beginning, frankly, we were... There was [X] and there was us. In the beginning it was just [X] and us, mainly us, who were interested. And then, as the investigations came out and we realised he was talking nonsense... there was [Y]. That went on for a while until [Z] and so on. And then it really spread (...) because it was the Raoult character that absolutely fascinated the whole of France. And then everyone started talking about it because every day there were new developments, new statements (...) it was massive.
(FR_M07)

What really hurts science, it's when, particularly in France, the political and health institutions don't draw the right conclusions from the debate. So hydroxychloroquine is tested when it shouldn't have been... there was no reason to test it... the Raoult study is really no good... there was no reason to test hydroxychloroquine... Millions were spent and 15,000 uncoordinated clinical trials were carried out in France. None of them were completed... to test hydroxychloroquine, just so that university hospitals could say "we're testing hydroxychloroquine... we're listening to you". It's completely stupid. (FR_M06)

As these two French science journalists make clear, the Didier Raoult controversy reached the mainstream news media and attracted

considerable public interest. As they reflect, this is not only casts science in a bad light with citizens, but can also distort the actions of public health authorities who feel a different and possibly unfamiliar type of pressure arising from the mediatization of the issue.

A potential pitfall that can confront Mediators is tension between issues of ethics and integrity and the dominant logic of the media field to create attention and generate a 'splash'. This tension can manifest as **pressure on individuals** to conform or 'play along' with this logic. One type of pressure relates to time and the need to verify information whilst keeping up with the production cycle.

This time pressure we also have is very conditioning of good work. (...) Normally it is the researcher who is available the fastest and who always answers the phone and the one who has already been recommended to me because he is very good and talks about everything and always answers. (...) When sometimes there are even researchers who are working on much more specific sub-topics and much closer to what we need. (PT_M08)

Another type of pressure relates to satisfaction with the credibility of information and higher-level publishing imperatives.

If I receive a paper and, for whatever reason, the alarm bells ring that the paper might contain false data. That affects my integrity as well. I cannot lend a voice to a product that I know is not real; I am risking my own reputation and that of the whole centre. Another thing is that you are an errand boy and you have to publish it because the director tells you, 'This is going to be published'. (ES_M10)

When I have not given credibility to something and I have no choice but to publish because it happens, the way to do it is usually by not signing the piece. (ES_M05)

Here Mediators articulate how the model of credibility and personal and professional credibility can come into conflict with the content and attention model of the media and communication field. Although Mediators across most POIESIS countries were noticeably not overly concerned about the existence of social media competition, the pressure to 'keep up' that the relentless social media churn exerts on mainstream media was acknowledged to some degree.

I hate the social media game. It's no fun at all. I just like making these videos and hope to reach people. But without social media, it somehow doesn't work. (DE_M09)

I'm often very hesitant to attempt such things simply because I know that the [scope] is very limited. The possibility of actually providing context, classifying studies, ensuring that polarisation doesn't become even more extreme, that I would actually have to be even more polarising for these formats to be successful on social networks. At the same time, the question arises whether giving up entirely is the right approach. I haven't found a solution yet. But certainly, if we know how many hours people spend on these platforms, they are actually highly relevant [...] places where science communication and journalism should take place. (DE_M10)

The exception with regard to the impact of social media on Mediators is found in the UK. Both institutional and non-institutional Mediators in the UK recounted experiences of scenarios in which a segment of social media output could be considered as working to deliberately cast doubt on research integrity and to launch personal attacks on science communicators.

You don't know who's agitating, who's doing all those nasty contents, often it's bots (robots) ... when you look at the profile, you look at the history of that person. I mean, sometimes they've got like football, some of the ones that are really anti-cycling, they are thugs in other ways. (UK_M06)

I thought it really annoying to be publicly accused of bullying by someone with a lot of followers [on Twitter] ... other academics having a go at you ... because I was a critic ... I got really fed up with Independent SAGE and the Zero COVID crew ... and I got into arguments with them because they thought I was a minimizer. (UK_M02)

While the coping strategy, as one UK Mediator described it, is simple, "you just ignore it. You don't give energy to it ..." (UK_M06), the potential negative impact of such behaviour on the health and well-being of science communicators should also not be ignored. That such behaviour creates a negative image of science itself is not something that emerges in Mediators reflections.

Overall, Section 4.2 has summarized the relationship of our Mediators to the concepts of research ethics and integrity. It is apparent that REI as practiced in the conduct of science is not an explicitly high

priority issue among Mediators. This finding is consistent with prior studies in the POIESIS project that suggest threats to research integrity are perceived to emerge much more from external sources than from internal malpractice (DE NR, p.27; PT NR, p.22). It can be observed that Mediators' perceptions are aligned with those of the general public and agents involved in REI at the institutional level. The following Chapter 5 will extend the multi-perspectival analysis and assessment conducted in POIESIS to the Researcher community itself.

4.3. Does the public have trust in science?

In the POIESIS project, public trust in science is what the 3i4T model is designed to help us interpret and explain. The previous sections of Chapter 4 have sought Mediators' reflections on their experiences and perceptions directed toward in particular toward the integrity dimension of the 3i4T model. In this section attention shifts from questions about the "3i's" (integrity, integration, institutions) to asking Mediators directly about public trust in science.

This was the final topic in the Mediator interviews. Mediators were asked how they perceive the relationship between their own work and public trust in science, and about their perceptions of the impact of high profile fraud and misconduct cases on public trust. They were also asked for their opinions about supporting or improving public trust in science.

Section 4.3 is largely based on, and can be read in conjunction with, Section 3.3 of the respective National Reports, where greater detail and additional direct quotes from participants can be found (Appendix 4).

4.3.1. Mediators' points of view

Mediators in all POIESIS countries were familiar with the concept of 'public trust in science' and were not hesitant to discuss it. An immediate point of reference for Mediators in a majority of POIESIS countries was their perception of the general level of trust in science in their country. Many would cite the well-known survey data for their country that showed support for science and scientists

remains high. Others cited the general use of the term 'science' to refer to something reliable.

I always notice on platforms, like TikTok and others, how many people base their claims on supposed scientific findings. Without claiming that this is actually meaningful or that they are real scientific findings. But I simply notice how many people justify statements with science. That already proves that there is a certain acceptance that science can indeed produce reliable findings. (DE_M10)

However, in most countries there were also Mediators who did perceive a reduction in the general level of public trust in science.

I believe that in order to build trust, and I don't say reinforce it because trust is at a low ebb in many respects right now, you have to be very transparent about how you come to your conclusions. (ES_M02)

I think there's a crisis of trust... from the studies and figures I've seen, there does seem to be a crisis. Perhaps the word crisis seems a bit strong to me... in any case, a certain mistrust... or a desire to stop believing just anyone, just anyhow, and therefore to be somewhat suspicious of science... (FR_M03)

However, according to Mediators the level of public trust is **not consistent across all sections of the population**. Rather, Mediators perceive that the population is segmented, an understanding they have clearly in mind in relation to their target audiences. While science communication can have an effect on public trust, the relationship is mutually co-constitutive and without some parts of the citizenry having confidence in science there would be no 'market' for the outputs of science communication at all.

The moment when citizens, officials, institutions no longer trust the results, I might as well communicate with the wolf. It won't work. (DE_M02)

Well, I'm telling you, I think that the public that mostly attends already has that confidence in science and that the talks I give [mentions topic] do not give rise to many doubts about what you are talking about. (ES_M07)

Another segmentation of the public that Mediators identified was the strong sceptic group. This group was often associated with particular channels, mainly social media platforms.

I think that when you go into the public sphere it becomes very dangerous because it becomes toxic and it becomes dangerous because it mainly creates... isolates, creates bubbles. That is, it leaves the doubters in a bubble alone and then that bubble, as we know, inflates, gets its own networks, goes to social media and gets its own forms of post-truth. (GR_M09)

On the internet, a micro-bubble quickly selects and forms itself where one only exchanges with people who see things the same way. And - and this is the crazy part - this quickly becomes the truth. What is shocking is that this shapes our reality, and scientific evidence no longer plays a role. (DE_M05)

A person who both doesn't follow the scientific news and doesn't have a good grasp of how to follow the scientific data on the issue, trying to communicate it in this way does much more damage and we've seen it with misrepresentation of studies multiple times. With doctors coming on news shows who were basically winking at... the anti-vaccine movement. Yeah, this caused a huge problem. (GR_M05)

...yes, of course, I think like everyone else, I'm convinced that there is a terrible lack of understanding of research among the general public, and that this lack of understanding is in fact increasing, in terms of what research is, its methodologies and objectives... and that this needs to be remedied... That's it, I'm going to caricature a lot with this sentence, so put a lot of commas around it, but I think there's a form of obscurantism at the moment, at all levels, that's winning over the population and that it's important for everyone who can to fight against it. (FR_M01)

Mediators in the majority of POIESIS countries thus articulated a view that in general the level of public trust in science was strong. It was also their perception that this is not a homogenous phenomenon, rather they described public trust as being differentiated both in terms of population segments and choices about information channels.

In two POIESIS countries, the results of the EIS summarised above require further qualification. In the UK, while Mediators reported trust overall remaining high and cited recent data to support this claim (UK NR, p.20-1), some Mediators viewed a degree of stress on

public trust due to it being entwined in broader negative social conditions.

I think it's [distrust] tied up with ... move towards populism, general distrust of, you know, previous authorities, the remote expertise, elites and so on ... I kind of think this is just part of the current movement, hugely exaggerated by social media groupings and tribes ... in America, for example, you know the libertarian movement against state intervention and so on, scientists have just become aligned with state intervention. (UK_M02)

Looking at the UK recently, [there] is a very strong sense that there are people who are in it for their own gain, and not in it for everyone, and that's kind of the opposite of the Enlightenment, isn't it? That's a kind of medieval social structure in which a small number of people benefit and a very large number of people go hungry, which is, is what the mood of the country is, at the moment, you know, whether it's true or not and science has always been one of those things that has seemed to be in the control of the elite. (UK_M03)

In France, the prior POIESIS Focus Group study (D3.2) suggested that there is a strong level of general concern about the science-society relationship (FR NR, p.24). This result is supported by the interviews with Mediators for the EIS. French Mediators are also troubled by what they see as possibly a crisis of information and communication that is more generalized than the context of public trust in science.

When it comes to the relationship between science and society, I wouldn't say it's a crisis. I'd say it's more a situation of mistrust (...) which reached its peak during covid and health crises in general, which often shed light on the state of relations between science and society. Because, in the end, what happened during covid was that we realised (...) that society, to use a general term, was not aware of how science is done. And for me (...) the source of the mistrust that has arisen really lies in the communication choices that we've made since the 1980s (...) with the overdevelopment, the media coverage and the acceleration of communication methods. We've seen science summarised in its results. And that's a choice, a media choice, which is driven enormously by television, a lot of it, and by what we call the mass media, i.e. media that reach the majority of the population. But, and so it's these choices, to treat science through the results, without ever explaining how the results were obtained, and to give the impression that we only have results... (FR_M11)

(...) I have the feeling that the loss of trust is more widespread, i.e. it doesn't just affect the scientific question. It affects

the question of trust in information and the way it is processed. So science and politics, well, we know that at the moment. I mean, there are things that prove this very lack of trust, if only by the massive vote for the far right. It actually says something about a kind of political disenchantment. I think science is one of the collateral damages of this issue and of wider political issues. I think that the COVID pandemic and the way it was handled politically in France may actually have diminished the French people's trust in science (...) (FR_M13)

Overall, Mediators' perceptions support quantitative evidence in the POIESIS countries suggesting public trust in science remains high. However, **national political and institutional conditions** also seem particularly important to take into consideration when considering public trust more closely.

A thread running through the POIESIS project design has been attention to two case contexts for assessing REI, science communication and public trust, climate change and COVID-19. In the EIS generally, but particularly for the Mediators study the COVID-19 pandemic functioned like a 'natural experiment'. Mediators across all POIESIS countries reported being personally and professionally profoundly impacted by the pandemic. In effect, the **COVID-19 pandemic 'stress tested' science communication and public trust** to a quite brutal extent in all POIESIS countries.

I feel that it only became an issue since Corona. The question of whether I trust science or not because, for the first time, a broader mass engaged with science, listening to the Drosten podcast and dealing with methods. (DE_M01)

What is certain is that the Covid crisis has led to a breakdown in trust, not on the part of everyone, but on the part of a large proportion of the public towards the institutions. It's not specific to [X], it's really general... there was always this talk of 'they're lying to us', 'they're hiding things from us', 'they're not going to tell us the truth'... (FR_M02)

They'd say one thing with complete conviction, you know, like COVID is not an important thing, it's got a very low death rate ... in January and then, 7 days later, this is the biggest failure of science advice for a generation, I can't believe the government is full of you know, murderers or whatever (UK_M05)

The pandemic changed the way the public understands, listens, is interested in science in general, and then they were super onfire and super prepared and super interesting to listen to you and they

went from 0 to everything, because they believed everything, you told them anything and it was an audience that you could deceive directly, telling him anything. What happened? Okay, we're talking about people who don't have to know about science, okay? So, explaining to them that science is a home essay is very complicated because they need to start, develop and finish. The public needs to understand and live a complete scientific process, in their own flesh and in general in the flesh of the society around them. (ES_M08)

We saw that with COVID, with the pandemic, at least at the beginning that shock to society, "so, but isn't the science always right? Don't you know what it is...?" (...) It was a difficult period for science (...) there is that expression of what we, the communicators, present is the sausage already ready, but there is the whole thing, when there is still just the ground meat behind and everything the process of forming into sausage. (PT_M01)

I haven't done much before Covid-19, but I still noticed a switch in my videos and when I gave lectures. After Covid-19, people were much more critical when you said, 'Hey, what I'm telling you is supported by a study or by several studies', before they would say 'Okay, I believe you'. After, many people would say, 'I need to look into this more'. They rarely did, but there was an initial generalised mistrust. (DE_M09)

In the initial days of the pandemic, when uncertainty was extremely high, politicians and public health authorities leaned very heavily on the possibility of salvation through science. Appeals for calm and patience were accompanied in most countries by the mantra '**follow the science**'. For some Mediators this appeal to a kind of procedural rationality and search for evidence reflected hopeful faith in science more than it represented an intelligent communication strategy in the midst of the pandemic.

There is no 'follow the science'; that is simply factually incorrect. That is not how society works, especially not a democratic one. (DE_M04)

Science does not lead the way, you're not following science, you should not follow science. There should be evidence informed policy. It's not the scientist that decides the policy, to possibly say what the consequences of different actions might be. But the politicians have to weigh it up, and I think one of the big problems during COVID was the fact that SAGE and other scientists were obsessed with only a couple of metrics about infections and hospitalisations, forgot about everything else. No concern with the damage to education from school closures,

enormous harm done to poorer people, particularly young, poor people. (UK_M02)

From this perspective there are scientific findings on the one hand and there are different potential socio-political consequences building on these findings. These need to be negotiated in a democratic society. 'But there is never one 'correct' political consequence that can be drawn from a scientific finding' (DE NR, p.36). 'Follow the science' thus became a slogan that 'failed to project uncertainty', thereby failing to engage citizens about which strategies or which options were under consideration and heightening concern about hidden influences taking decisions out of their hands (UK NR, p.44).

For some Mediators, the COVID-19 'stress test' all showed some positive signs in relation to the resilience of the system and an improvement in some aspects of communication.

I think the pandemic helped this a lot. Suddenly it seems like everyone understands what science is, why it is important (...). Maybe the pandemic accelerated some things in the digital area, but it also accelerated some things in the area of communication and the relationship between the public and research. (PT_M04)

Much has also been said about the impact of the pandemic on the public's confidence in science, and I think it is a very positive impact. In other words, within the effect that the COVID had, let's just say that I believe that researchers, their image and therefore that of science, came out better off. (ES_M09)

Mediators were balanced in their assessment of this effect, rationalising that it was a positive that many citizens had now heard about peer review, for example. However, it was also the case that more citizens now understood that science is inherently uncertain, which is both a positive in terms of understanding research, but also has potential impacts on communication if the 'base level' of faith in the scientific method becomes eroded.

To a certain extent, the volatility of the COVID-19 pandemic was contrasted with the more stabilised science communication ecosystem around the longer running controversy over climate change.

What we have now [in terms of scientific evidence] is the best for now, but it is still likely to change, something else could come

along. We [at our institution] have established terms that indicate how certain something is, when it is very certain, pretty certain etc. That this does however not persist in the translation process towards the media and that it is understood quite differently in the public, yes, that there is a different understanding of scientific 'certainty', I believe this has a lot to do with trust. (DE_M01)

*I think that scientists and everybody in this community are very aware that when we talk about climate impacts, if we lie, if we exaggerate too much, people will stop believing in what is being said and then more and more people will start to deny climate change or think that it is exaggerated. And then they won't act and they won't, and there won't be a change in society. [...]
Without people's trust in scientists, well there will be no climate action and I think that's a priority. (ES_M04)*

In summary, the COVID-19 pandemic focused attention on just how important science communication processes are, particularly in times of crisis. From Mediators' perspective there was a profound impact on their professional field. For many, it was the 'event' that catalysed an intensification of public (mis)trust in science. It also provoked a corresponding surge in interest about the role of science communicators, especially when they are forced to the frontlines of socio-political struggles in liberal democratic societies.

4.3.2. Cogs in the machine; links in the chain, nodes in the network

It is likely that the COVID-19 pandemic caused some shifts in Mediators' self-understanding about their role in the complex of connections between science and society. This section summarises how Mediators view their own position relative to fomenting public trust in science. All of these reflections took place in 2024, by when the COVID-19 pandemic had become relatively normalised as a public health challenge in which the majority of citizens in the POIESIS had both been vaccinated against and experienced (multiple) COVID-19 infections. It is therefore impossible to know to what extent Mediators' reflections would have been different without the pandemic experience.

In general, many Mediators view their work as having the potential to contribute to build public trust and consider this to be an important responsibility.

I believe my work strengthens trust in science. I may not reach a huge number of people, but I believe those I do reach are positively influenced. I include researchers in my videos, letting them explain how they work and what they do. (DE_M09)

Let's say that both communication and scientific dissemination have become more professional, and this, I believe, has a direct effect on the public's confidence. (ES_M09)

So, I hope that it can provide a greater understanding of how science works, what researchers are interested in and contribute to, and in that way, by communicating it in a transparent manner, can also increase trust. (DK_M05)

I'd like to believe so (...). I think we have this role of allowing or creating conditions, creating opportunities for scientists to spend time with society. And I think that's half the battle for trust, to have an opportunity for dialogue. (PT_M02)

I certainly think they are important (the issues of public trust in his work). I mean, as a science communicator, I can understand that I bear quite a big responsibility in this part, to communicate this whole thing correctly and not to create false impressions, nor to distort reality to the public that follows us and trusts us, right? Because for better or worse there is a huge amount of trust. Which one might say we've earned as communicators of science, but I don't know if it is, if it's responsive, if it's fully responsive to reality. In any case, I certainly think they are important. So, I think they are something that one should keep in mind when one is active in this field. (GR_M07)

I believe that I have been, and continue to be, involved in inviting the public - in both the podcast and in my communications - into the research process, somehow building a bridge to the person who conducted the research. There is a certain credibility in that as well. (DK_M08)

It's important that we don't make mistakes, that what we present is really correct. If we spread information that is not right and it comes out, this is detrimental for trust. I also think we contribute to building trust by reporting on research processes and methods, giving people the opportunity to see what is behind it, how the results are achieved. (DE_M01)

I think so, or I hope so. (laughs) Mainly because illustrating is like to communicate without languages, anyone can understand. (PT_M05)

Essentially, it is about elucidation, or one could say about empowering people to think for themselves, to think more for themselves than they could before. If I read or hear something about a topic I didn't know much about before, and afterwards I feel I can discuss it better, more calmly, and more factually, then that is a success of journalism, especially science journalism, I believe. (DE_M06)

Mediators also seem aware that trust in science is a precondition for their own work to be successful, and for their aspirations to contribute to objectives they value that reach beyond the idea of building or reinforcing public trust in science.

I don't write to learn more, to earn money, because you don't earn so much writing in this country, nor for the ego. I write to change consciences, to activate people, to transform reality. (ES_M03)

Our goal is not to increase trust in science, our goal is to bring science closer to children. (PT_M06)

So I consider it a success, I would like to think that [...] I have changed the way of seeing life, science, education and training to all the people who have passed through my workshops, conferences, who have bought my book or who have gone to my exhibitions. (ES_M08)

Yes, regarding what we talked about earlier. Incredibly, incredibly important because... not just for me personally, but for the entire media profession. And not just science journalists, but really the entire journalism profession. It is really us who have a key role in ensuring that the public and citizens trust research, because it is not just... one thing is that citizens... that we are gatekeepers. The citizens' way of understanding research largely goes through the media. (DK_M04)

I think it has a lot to do with building trust in science, because I see it as a public service that is being provided, with public money, that people often don't know about. Without my work and that of the people who do my job, people would not know about it, or would know about it much less. At the end of the day, you are showing and making people aware of what society's money is being invested in and what kind of research is being done, and above all, for what purposes and with what criteria. (ES_M01)

Mediators thus express a clear interest in and value associated with helping to build public trust in science through their work. However,

it is also evident that this does not mean Mediators should become the 'fulfilment agents of science' (DE_M08) and simply report what science wants them to or what politics may try to dictate (DE NR, p.38). Rather, Mediators also see the importance of their critical role in informing citizens about science.

The fact that I have to mediate trust in research is not about putting scientists on a pedestal. Absolutely not. Because scientists really need to, what do you call it, lose a little bit of control in order for trust in the scientific process to be created. And that might be hard for the individual researcher, but I think about trust in research more than trust in the individual researcher. But citizens really need to trust that research, science, is a good thing. And I feel the same way, but it is not about me being a cheerleader. (DK_M04)

That's the primary goal, that's the primary goal [building public confidence in science]. And also, to ask questions about where science is, where science is going, how it should go.. (GR_M11)

My job is not only to communicate and explain science but also to question it and keep an eye on researchers because mistakes happen there too. I think, however, that it is crucial not to undermine the overall validity of science while doing so. (DE_M10)

This critical perspective extends also to their own professional milieu, to the functions that science communication has in relation to the science - society relationship, and to the way the chains of mediation that translate science to citizens operate. This also manifests as a concern about the public image of science communicators themselves.

I think that in this little world of communicators, popularisers and science journalism, there's this idea that we mustn't fragilize the trust that people may have in expert bodies, academies... I don't feel at all that I'm discrediting science in general and, on the contrary, that I'm giving a voice to scientists who work specifically on these very specific and very complicated subjects. In fact, I should be keeping a catalogue of all the tricks and sometimes deceptions that come out of the communications departments of these public research bodies, academies, etc. It's spectacular! In fact, it's spectacular! There are plenty of examples. At [X] recently, and I'm going to write about it because it really is a scandal... (...) there are plenty of examples (...) of scientific authority being used in the public arena (...) to protect interests. It's not going to work! That's not what science is for. (FR_M14)

My goal is not just to communicate science but to always try to serve a broader spectrum, to show diverse perspectives. When I'm in contact with press offices - and they do great work - I'm still always aware that they are not completely independent institutions at that moment. (DE_M10)

We are seen as mere 'fulfilment agents'. This bothers me a bit because I find it technically unpleasant to be perceived as such. I insist that the things we do and the content we spread are done with our eyes open, not just because we hold a microphone, but because we believe these contents belong in the public domain, and we still discuss them despite everything. (DE_M06)

Overall, Mediators are able to take a step back and critically observe their own position and role in communicating science to citizens and how this relates to public trust. Their personal reflections are built on relational understandings in which their own interdependence on others shapes their perspective. Mediators' perspective on their own significance to influence public trust is relatively modest. Their descriptions of the scope of their influence seem appropriately constrained by an understanding of their integration in a wider ensemble of social actors and forces.

4.3.3. Fraud in the public eye; for worse or for better?

Mediators were also asked for their opinion about whether publicly visible cases of fraud have a direct impact on public trust. They were also asked whether fraud cases in their country had impacted their own work. All POIESIS countries have had science scandals, including accusations of fraud, in the past 20 years. There has therefore been opportunities for experience Mediators to observe public reactions.

There is no doubt Mediators consider scientific fraud to be an existing and serious issue that undermines the science - society relationship.

We have to say that science has these norms and the one who did not comply breaks a social contract - so the question on misconduct is deeply political; it has to do with how you receive yourself as member of a society. (GR_M02)

Any fraudulent act in science seems to me a million steps backwards, but for everyone, for the colleagues of these people,

and for the scientific world, for the general public, that is, for the people and the people, for the economy, ... for the people who try to communicate science with rigor and with trust, because it gives me total hopelessness and distrust, but in the end I am an intermediary, I'm nothing more than that. (ES_M08)

Mediators do not consider that the public is preoccupied with scientific fraud and are not certain that many cases reach the public consciousness.

Even when [research performing organisations] fail to contain it [news about fraud or malpractice] with their levees, it still doesn't reach the public and therefore, I think the impact ends up being small. (EN_M02)

Perhaps in line with the critical perspective that many journalist Mediators consider as an important part of their professional role, overall public news about fraud was interpreted as a positive outcome.

It is true that there is a journalist who I think is doing a spectacular job [...] in the newspaper El País, who has uncovered different frauds and I think it is essential that they are uncovered. That this implies that citizens have more misgivings or that they don't see science as clean as possible. Well, I don't know, but I welcome the debate, I mean, what cannot be allowed is for fraudulent practices to be covered up and journalism one of its fundamental raisons d'être is to tell what others don't want you to tell. Always within the truth, obviously. And if the impact is negative, I think it will be negative in the first place, but not in the long term, because what is unethical is not intact, what is fraudulent must be exposed. (EN_M09)

I think they [exposer of fraud] are positive because in the end what they achieve is to improve the system. I think that in the end, the result is that the system is more reliable. (ES_M11)

Overall, Mediators downplayed the importance of public exposure of fraud cases and could also see this as vindication that they (the media) were playing their expected societally valuable role. Only a small number of Mediators had been directly involved in minor cases of alleged questionable practices. One institutional Mediator described a mistake made by scientists during the research process that they had to correct on the public record (PT NR, p.24).

Two years later, when they carried out a new analysis, they realised that a human measurement error had been made. So that result wasn't true after all, and we were very open about it... [we had to] to openly communicate what happened. (PT_M01)

In summary, the impact of research fraud on public trust was not a prominent feature of Mediators reflections. It is important to note that the question about this topic came late in the Mediator interviews. The prior focus on trust in information sources and issues of research ethics and integrity, may also have captured Mediators thoughts about the 'dark side' of scientific conduct sufficiently. However, it is also true that those Mediators working explicitly on the topic fraud argued that the importance of their work was more to do with 'fixing the system' than with providing solace to anxious citizens. Overall, Mediators thus believe that public trust in science and scientists remains relatively strong, at least relative to social institutions generally, and does not appear to be unduly damaged by revelations of research fraud in the public domain.

Overall, Section 4.3 has summarized the perceptions and experiences of our Mediators in relation to public trust in science. In common with other studies in the POIESIS project, Mediators regard public trust in science as relatively strong. However, they see public trust as unevenly distributed across different social groups. Concerns about social and political institutions in different countries are also an important factor to consider here. The level of public trust does appear to have shown significant resilience in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic that 'stress tested' science communication and public sentiment. Mediators view their work as making important contributions to maintaining and reinforcing public trust, but they also recognise their responsibility to provide a critical perspective on science and on science communication itself. It is important to bring scientific scandals and fraud to the public domain from the perspective of science journalists. Any perceived risk to public trust from exposing such malpractice is very much a secondary concern.

4.4. Other themes

Two additional themes emerged strongly from the Mediator interviews conducted in Germany, although these themes were also evident in other POIESIS country contexts and are mentioned in various National Reports (Appendix 4). First, Mediators voiced opinions on the

question of whether **researchers should be expected or obliged to communicate science**? Mediators were strongly of the opinion that this should not be the expectation and would not enhance public trust in science (DE NR, p.48). It was also emphasized that most researchers do not undergo any form of training in 'communicating', not even during their PhD. This is perceived as an important barrier for scientists to start engaging in science communication as they might just not feel competent enough to do so. Mediators were clear that they do not expect or wish to interact with every scientist who may have results to discuss, rather search for those "who communicate well, like to do it, and are competent" (DE_M06).

Second, an interesting theme emerged regarding the **similarities in the challenges and conundrums that confront both researchers and science journalists**. In contrast to scientists, surveys generally show only very limited trust in journalism among the public (DE NR, p.49). Little thought has gone into this question: people may trust scientists, but what if the problem is they do not trust the science communicator? Science journalists perceive that, much like in the case of scientific work, the public also does not understand the journalistic process. Political polarisation and 'fake news' are also problems for authentic science communicators. Some Mediators argued that opening up and making their entire process of journalistic work more transparent to the public is essential, just as they perceive it to be in the case of science.

4.5. Recommendations to improve public trust in science

This final sub-section compiles Recommendations on public trust developed in the various National Reports. Mediators participating in the EIS were asked for their opinions on how to improve public trust in science. They were specifically asked for suggestions related to young people in this regard. The Recommendations for each POIESIS partner represent a synthesis generated by that partner, based on the individual contributions made by participating Mediators in their country study. This section is based on and should be read in conjunction with the 'Synthesis of Recommendations' section (3.4 or 3.5) in each of the respective National Reports, where greater detail and discussion of Mediators' suggestions to bolster public trust in science can be found (Appendix 4).

Table 4.4 Recommendations for improving public trust in science based on Mediator suggestions

Country	Recommendations
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Enhance transparency and quality in research communication through upholding impartial research, implementing rigorous quality checks, and disseminating processual and methodological explanations. 7. Formalize stakeholder inclusion at universities and encourage more citizen science and public engagement activities. 8. Bridge the gap between researchers and mediators and build co-partnerships. Place greater priority and value on science communication activities within academia, and support researchers in engaging with the public with a focus on effective communication. 9. Engage in direct dialogue with the audience, reduce the gap between science mediators and the public, and use their preferred platforms and channels for communication. 10. Place a higher priority on covering research in the media and put greater emphasis on explaining the value of science.
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The first recommendation is to design a long-term communication plan that includes in-depth action to progressively build a shared culture. 7. The second recommendation relates to the need to support scientists more effectively with practical communication guidelines. 8. The third recommendation stresses the need to rebalance the work of communicating science by giving as much importance to the research process as to the findings. 9. A fourth recommendation concerns the reinforcement of school curricula with regard to science and critical thinking. 10. A fifth recommendation relates to the need to not be satisfied with a sloppy use of the notion of public trust in order to analyse its full social and political ramifications.
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Improve (school) education on science and the scientific method (scientific literacy). 7. Contextualise scientific findings in the communication process and explain the scientific process, including information regarding potential limitations and remaining scientific insecurities.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Communicate positively and constructively instead of conveying always more pessimistic and too generalising perspectives. 9. Create stable and safe working conditions in research, especially for young researchers. 10. Disentangle scientific findings and potential socio-political consequences in the discourses of all societal stakeholders.
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Institutional actions are needed to improve science communication. 7. Public or other institutional educational reforms targeting both the general public and the younger generations in particular are needed. 8. A responsible use of social media is essential in communicating science by public or research institutions and by individuals, targeting mainly - but not only- younger people. 9. A wider dialogue between science and society regarding the conduct of research and the use of its outputs. Some mentioned basically informative and science integration events, others expressed the opinion that the public must have a say on the way the science outputs are used. 10. More transparency in conducting research. This is meant to be used both on communicating and on conducting science as well.
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Engage scientists in institutional and non-institutional activities, showing the daily life of a scientist in different fields of knowledge, give them voice in society. 5. Create activities that are based on storytelling to guide the public through the scientific process until the result. 6. Create lines of funding specifically for science communication and science journalism.
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Increase investments in research ethics and integrity policies and procedures in universities and public research organisations, including through mandatory training for masters and doctoral students. 9. Reform the structure of research career incentives by renouncing the 'publish or perish' culture and by rewarding researchers for high quality communication and dissemination work. 10. Invest in a sustained educational programme to raise the level of scientific literacy and culture in primary and secondary school and, through lifelong learning, among the general public.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Create stable local-level infrastructures supporting the promotion of scientific culture and social integration in science, including public laboratories, reading and resource rooms, interactive activities, expert talks, etc., accessible to the entire population. 12. Open up public research laboratories for regular public visiting hours and for programmes of school excursions and work experience opportunities. 13. Invest in the provision of specialised training for early career researchers in science communication and media relations, including how to use social media platforms effectively. 14. Establish a system of effective sanction for scientists who engage in fraudulent behaviour in order to reduce the perception of impunity.
United Kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Trustworthiness is key, not trust in science. 8. Train the public for critical thinking skills. 9. Public engagement is double-edged (positive and negative consequences) 10. The 'electoral model' of public engagement is to be avoided. 11. Ignore the 'trolls' and 'bots'. 12. Advocacy by scientists should be avoided.

An overview of these 36 Recommendations reveals almost half of the Recommendations arising from Mediators suggestions focus on science communication (n=15). Other Recommendations target institutions (n=9), societal integration (n=8) and research integrity (n=4). This is consistent with the low degree of importance accorded to REI issues by Mediators in the main. Table 4.5 summarizes the Recommendations in their relation to the major elements of the 3i4T model.

Table 4.5 Mediator Recommendations suggestions mapped to the 3i4T model

3i4T model	Recommendations
Institutions	DK3; FR2; FR4; DE1; DE4; GR1; GR2; PT3; ES2
Integration	DK2; GR4; ES3; ES4; ES5; UK2; UK3; UK4
Integrity	GR5; ES1; ES7; UK1
Science communication	DK1; DK4; DK5; FR1; FR3; FR5; DE2; DE3; DE5; GR3; PT1; PT2; ES6; UK5; UK6

The focus of the Recommendations on science communication is unsurprising considering this is the focus of Mediator interviewees' professional roles and identities. The Mediator part of the EIS was centred on the integrity dimension of the 3i4T model. The Mediator interview was sequenced in such a way that we were able to test our assumption that Mediators would consider REI and important factor affecting public trust in science (see Section 4.2). The result of this procedure seems clear. Mediators in general downplayed REI issues as factor affecting public trust levels and their suggestions focused strongly on their area of expertise, science communication. The national contexts of France and UK varied to some extent from this pattern, although in neither country did Mediators explicitly link REI concerns to changes in public trust levels. Science communication Recommendations cover both the quality and delivery mechanisms for information and cover both the science and society perspectives.

Mediators made a significant number of suggestions relevant to the institutions dimension of the 3i4T model. Interestingly, many of the suggestions centred on improving the working conditions and careers incentives that shape researcher behaviours. Increased institutional support for training Researchers to work with Mediators and communicate science was also considered important.

Mediators concerns about the level of scientific literacy and 'absorptive capacity' in the general public for consuming information about science were also represented in their suggestions. A substantial number of Recommendations based on their suggestions target ways to better integrate citizens in science, including ways to create public infrastructures in which scientists, science communicators and citizens can more regularly interact.

5. Researchers translating between science and society

This chapter describes and discusses the results of the EIS series of Researcher interviews. A total of 41 Researchers participated in the EIS. An overview of these participants is provided in Table 3.2.

In any study of the relationships between REI and public trust in science, the research community is particularly important. Researchers in the EIS were approached from the perspective of being active agents involved in constructing the relationship between science and society. By targeting researchers involved with climate change and COVID-19, we were able to look closely at their work and experiences in the contexts of socio-technical crisis and controversy. The Researcher interview series was designed to focus principally on the integration dimension of the 3i4T model. In what follows in this section we thus looked at how our Researchers deliver their work to the public, their experiences and perceptions of having others (mediators) deliver their work to the public, and their activities in directly engaging with citizens.

5.1. Connecting science and society in contexts of public crisis and controversy

Researchers can be vital active agents in ensuring research results and findings, and general scientific expertise, reach the public in a timely way. There are numerous pathways for the dissemination and communication of science to citizens. Most Researchers participating in the EIS described using multiple of these pathways in communicating about their work. Table 5.1. contains a summary of these pathways.

Table 5.1. Pathways for Researchers' work to reach the public

Country	Descriptions of pathways
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional media, newspapers, radio, TV • Specialist events - public meetings, school visits • Policy making processes • Social media - project dissemination, podcasts
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific associations promoting engagement and visibility • Social media - dissemination, podcasts • Traditional media, newspaper, radio, TV • Websites, blogs
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional media, newspapers, radio, TV • Policy making processes • Specialist events - Night of Science (MSCA), Science Slam, public meetings • Employer organisation social media channels
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central government/public administration channels • Scientific publisher press releases • Specialist events - school visits • Traditional media, newspapers, radio, TV
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional media, newspapers, radio, TV • Social media - dissemination, podcasts • Specialist events - public forums, science cafés, school visits • Policy making processes
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional media, newspapers, radio, TV; Books • Through IPCC managed communication protocols • Website for real-time health monitoring • Social media public health communication
UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional media, newspapers, radio, TV; Books • Specialist events - public meetings • Social media - dissemination, podcasts, live interactions, chat apps • Websites, blogs

Researchers describe a broad range of pathways by which their research and expertise reaches the public. Most common across the POIESIS countries are the use of traditional and social media, and internet-based formats included website and blogs. Researchers also

disseminate their work through different types of specialist events dedicated to science, public meetings, and school visits. Some Researchers make contributions to public policy pathways.

Many of the pathways Researchers use to communicate and make visible their work and expertise are also contexts in which they interact directly with citizens (Table 5.2). In the majority of the POIESIS countries Researchers report involving citizens in aspects of the research cycle. Involving citizens in research projects happens in many different ways, including for data collection and analysis. Researchers also work directly with stakeholder groups, patient organisations, and industry partners, including through transdisciplinary project designs.

The contexts for interacting with citizens include a range of different types of events. These include open public meetings, school visits, and specialist science promotion and popularisation events.

Table 5.2. Forms of Researcher interaction with citizens

Country	Descriptions of interactions
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-creation and citizen science in research projects • Specialist events - public debates and dialogues • Research stakeholder consultations
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen science associations • Specialist events - Fête de la science, public awareness campaigns about climate • Participation in public climate action associations
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient organisation liaison and participation in research • Specialist events - public workshops • Citizen's council advising research project
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient organisation liaison and participation in research • Specialist events - public debates, school visits, public workshops • Citizen science for data collection • Stakeholder engagement activities in research projects
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting research projects integrating feedback and monitoring mechanisms with stakeholders • Collaborating on applied research with industry and agricultural stakeholders • Working with community groups on data requests, communication and monitoring activities
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Special events - public workshops, school visits • Transdisciplinary research designs involving wide range of stakeholders • Citizen science on Github involving coding and analysing data
UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Special events - broad range of public engagement activities • Consultations with public administration • Social media interactions with the public

Overall, the Researcher participants in the EIS are thoroughly embedded in science communication practices. These include working with a range of different types of professionals in media contexts, direct communication work with public either in person at specialist

events or through social media, and through the involvement of citizens in different aspects of research projects. Having summarised this background on our Researchers' involvement in communicating and interacting with the public, the following section focuses on Researchers' interactions with third party professionals (mediators) working in different parts of the media field.

5.2. About science communication and public attitudes

This section summarizes Researchers' experiences and opinions about communicating science, working with different kinds of media, and the impacts of science (mis)communication on public attitudes. It is based on, and can be read in conjunction with, Sections 4.1 and 4.2 of the respective National Reports, where greater detail and additional direct quotes from participants can be found (Appendix 4).

5.2.1. Research, mediation, science communication

A clear result from the EIS is the strong commitment to science communication among the Researcher participants. Researchers in all countries voiced positive attitudes toward communicating science to the public and expressed their willingness to undertake these activities.

Trying to reach the media (...) newspapers or even television. I think it is very important, it is something that I would really like to do, which is to take science, the science that I do, the research that I do further and to more people. (PT_R02)

I think that we have a duty, actually quite a significant duty, to contribute our knowledge when there are inquiries from the public. (DK_R01)

Almost all Researchers were currently active in science communication and had experiences to share in relation to using different types of communication channels.

Researchers had positive attitudes toward specialised science journalists. The professionalism of such journalists is highly regarded.

I believe that science communication and journalism specialising in environmental issues in general, and climate change in particular, are quite rigorous. (ES_R02)

Institutional support for researchers who are involved in working with journalists is also considered valuable.

I always place great value on the assessment of our press department. They usually say, 'We've had good experiences with this or that colleague. You can go ahead or not. (DE_R01)

I have several kinds of long-standing media contacts that I trust will look for insight and understanding, and not for a kind of slip of the word to misrepresent my position ... at the institute, we have a communication scheme through which media requests will be funnelled. This is great because it's not just indiscriminate funnelling of media requests. I can ask OK, who is this journalist? Can you do background research on them? (UK_R05)

It is noticeable that across all national contexts, confidence exists among Researchers regarding the good faith efforts of much mainstream media. Establishing ongoing relationships with trusted science journalists and other media professionals is considered both possible and desirable.

However, Researchers also describe challenges to establishing reliable pathways for their research to reach the public through the hands of media actors. It is important to be well-prepared and have a clear message to present. It is also important to ensure that media professionals understand the limits of a researcher's particular disciplinary and topical expertise.

(...) If you want to have a clear message, you have to try to identify before each interview the two or three key points you want to get out of the interview. If you don't, you get bogged down very quickly. That's all there is to it. And so there's a certain amount of preparation, which ... for me doesn't consist of writing down what I'm going to say, but of trying to think (...) of rereading the reference publications in this field and extracting from this field what the consensus is. (...) That's more or less the general approach (...) [FR_R02]

It is quite often journalists have a tendency to think, 'You have done something about the climate, so you know everything about the

climate,' and I am very careful to say, 'This, I know something about; this, I can give a qualified opinion on; this, I do not know anything about.' So, I talk to them, but I am also very explicit about what I can speak about based on research and what I cannot speak about based on research" (DK_R01)

Another challenge is the tendency is for even reputable journalists to emphasize aspects of a conversation or interview that leave Researchers feeling uncomfortable.

I mean, I've come to the conclusion that if you want something to happen, you do... It helps to go public (...) The only problem with going to the press is that you can't always trust the press. You know, you lose complete control. They will want a story. And you know that they may misrepresent thing so you... they... you have to go to a journalist you can trust if you're going to go to the press, I think. [FR_06]

Possibly a journalist might choose a sentence that is more spicy and more interesting and give it a priority or possibly give priority to something that is less important in my opinion in an interview than something else, just because it might be a little bit more catchy. It's not exactly a distortion of what has been said, but it may be a shift in the focus of what is said to some things that in the opinion of the journalist are perhaps more important than other things that have been said either by me or by a representative in the research centre in which I work. (GR_R06)

"My statements are, of course, presented and often taken out of context. We might have had a half-hour conversation, and then it becomes three sentences in a text, which also has a different focus. I experience that, but I always get my quotes to check. And that's fine. But I don't get to check the context. (DK_R06)

This kind of tension is not considered by Researchers to be due to bad intentions or incompetence on the part of journalists and other mediators. Rather, they recognise that even in the most highly reputable parts of the mainstream media a different logic of success is at play. This logic values attention and 'eyeballs' and operates on the classic journalistic principle of needing to find an 'attractive angle' on which to base a narrative.

At the same time Researchers recognise that converting complex scientific information into easily understood language suitable for laypersons is difficult and involves the risk of losing the quality of understanding.

In order to communicate in a way that is accessible and understandable to most people, I have to simplify. By simplifying, I run the risk of people misunderstanding what I'm saying or imagining that I'm saying certain things that I'm not saying, and so that, in my opinion, is one of the worst risks you run in communication. And so, in order to try to minimise this problem, what I advocate is that communication should be as correct as possible, and with as few words as possible. (PT_R03)

A distinctive challenge emerged in relation to urgency, particularly the time-pressures that were associated with communicating to the public during the COVID-19 pandemic. The sheer volume of demand for information and expert appearances during the COVID-19 pandemic could be quite extreme.

We have really worked daily with all the data samples, tried to keep up, and we have been in expert committees and done many things. And I have really tried to make podcasts and statements as much as I possibly could, so I could help explain what was happening. I thought that was really important (DK_R04)

So, in that context, I responded to requests to appear on television, radio, be interviewed for newspapers. And, I have a big social media following. I've got 180,000 followers on Twitter. You know, so I started off at the beginning of the pandemic with 50,000. So, I was putting out tweets and things. So, I've got social media, I've got mainstream media. I did a couple of blogs (UK_R01)

I had a standing weekly radio interview with CNBC and with the BBC. And then on top of this on any given week I would probably have at least three to four additional interviews. But if it was when a variant was announced or something, I mean, sometimes it would be booked, you know, the whole day, sometimes it would really be crazy. (ES_R03)

Some Researchers were thus drawn into a continuous, responsive, 'public-service' type of mode of communicating about COVID-19 on a real-time basis. As discussed in the Section 5.2.2., this could be a stressful and exhausting experience for some.

In the context of COVID-19 there was also perceived to be little time to deal with communicating the underlying complexity of how scientific knowledge progresses.

"What was not well presented at the beginning of the pandemic is that controversies in science are entirely normal and part of the process of approaching the truth. What often happens is that facts or the state of knowledge change because more insights become available. In the beginning, it was perceived as scientists having been wrong. And that might sometimes be the case, but not because they made a mistake, but simply because not enough information and data were available. In my perception, this improved over the course of the pandemic as the process of science was better explained. (DE_R01)

It is evident from Researchers' descriptions that adequately communicating to the public the process of science, and that scientific 'facts' are always to some degree open to revision and modification, is a general challenge that is common to both the climate and COVID contexts studied in the EIS.

Researchers in the EIS are interested and motivated to communicate their work to the public. A very diverse range of pathways are used to do this. The level of involvement in science communication activities varies within the Researcher cohort, with a particularly intense level of participation in interactions with journalists and social media characterising the experience of COVID-19 researchers during the height of the pandemic. Despite having broad confidence in the professionalism of third-party science communicators including journalists, the Researchers also describe the necessity to be vigilant about the detail of how their work and their expertise is represented to the public. Institutional support for communication activities is strongly valued where it is available.

5.2.2. Struggles with misrepresentation and misinformation

Even in good faith communication contexts working with professional journalists, Researchers understand that communicating their work through third parties is complicated and subject to logics that are somewhat alien to the scientific field. Even in mainstream media, the way research is positioned can subtly shift meanings and influence perceptions. Sometimes it is possible to negotiate to improve the way research is presented; other times views can be misrepresented.

They convey my sentences, but they can be placed in a context that I might not always feel is the one I had envisioned my own sentence in. That's one thing. And then there's something else

entirely. If it's a newspaper article, you can have... your text might be a small article over on the left, but the article next to it with a big picture and catchy headline can go in a completely different direction. And suddenly you become, well... entangled in something that maybe wasn't where you initially stood. (DK_R06)

I see that some people who straddle the line between republishing articles and trying to influence -that is, you can say that one goes to an influencer (rather to a journalist)- I see that in some cases there is a quite strong tendency for exaggeration, for distortion in order to get... extra clicks. And something else, which is unfortunately true, is that sometimes this is also done unintentionally, in the sense that not knowing terminology, science, not being familiar with it, they fall into slips and mistranslate what we might write on a website, on a social media site. So that's where it starts to get a little out of hand. And that's really where there can be distortion and where we can really get to levels of ridiculousness about how certain things are recorded. (GR_R05)

If we arrived on time, which was very rarely, and we asked them to please change it, they would change it. I would explain: "Look, I'm sorry. It's not exactly what I said and it might put fear into people like your grandparents, or it might put unnecessary fear or tremendous distress into young people, change it a little bit, right?" So we asked for changes and they accepted them, but we didn't always get it. Yes, sometimes there were sensationalist headlines. (ES_R01)

I gave an interview to a Basque newspaper, which I was asked to write, and which was then published with sentences that I didn't write... (PT_R01)

Somebody called me out of the blue, a journalist, that I knew, but not too well and asked me two questions, that interview lasted less than two minutes ... and they took one quote of it, and because of that, a whole collaboration that I build up with a certain institution, all the bridges were burned ... since then, I became even more cautious (UK_R05)

Researchers exhibit a nuanced understanding of the back and forth of communicating science through media channels. They understand that the media have commercial and other goals that go beyond purely communicating information, and they perceive a continuum reaching from unintentional misrepresentation toward more borderline practices.

However, there is another register in Researchers' discussions of their experiences when they encounter what they see as uninformed,

biased, or unprofessional practices. False equivalence or 'balance' is poorly regarded by some Researchers.

"I've had discussions with journalists who called me to confront me with an alternative viewpoint. And I've said, 'That is simply wrong. That's not a proper viewpoint.' Yes, people can have opinions, but this is actually a quantitative matter, something that can be known—like mathematics or something similar. (...) Why do we need to have two sides to this issue? It's completely insane. But other times, I've gone along with it because I can see that it's something where you can't just say 2 plus 2 equals 4. It's actually much more complicated. (DK_R04)

Similarly, a Researcher in Germany noted the example of a TV show inviting five experts on to discuss climate change. One of these experts was a climate change denier, effectively representing 20% of the experts on stage, but totally overrepresenting the prevalence of such an opinion among climate researchers. This Researcher insisted that while it is crucial for democratic public discourses that all opinions are heard, marginal minority opinions should not be given too much space in the media.

The problem of deliberate disinformation is then experienced as something extremely problematic and confronting personally as well as professionally.

...we certainly went through phases where screenshots were being used to spread misinformation and that was probably one of the most impactful because it was so incorrect and like in a way that you can't... You know, I'd say you can't even argue and take out of context. It really has been twisted. And so, it was maybe the most painful if that's the right word ... they would take screenshots and try and use them as proof of something. I mean, any conspiracy theory you can think of. And then when we would catch them and fix them, we would use that as proof of a cover up (ES_R03)

(It) was the word trick that he used, which in mathematics is quite usual to say this is the trick to solve the problem, and that's the way he'd used it, he was actually trying to reconcile two ways of looking at past data and they didn't quite match up, but he found a way of making them match up and that's the trick, and that's what they got him on. (UK_R06)

Well, since it is basically a battle for public opinion, what they did was to take a phrase from the journalist who interviewed me, not even a phrase of mine, and they attributed it to me. (ES_R05)

The increased workload and sense of responsibility that Researchers reported taking on board during COVID-19 also brought with it some anxiety about maintaining clarity and accuracy of communications. This was particularly the case due to perceptions that communications could be misused.

I worked very hard to try and if I was writing a Twitter thread to think very carefully about, you know, could any of these tweets on their own, could they be used in a way that I wouldn't want? So how can I change it up a bit, so that's not the case. (ES_R03)

Researchers also reflected on their experience of the deliberate and calculated politicisation of scientific issues.

They created problems for me when they started to polarise. When it became polarised and there was one region against another, one [political] party against another, one city against another. Well, that worried me a lot and it really upset me because the only enemy was the virus, that is to say, there was no need to look for more enemies. It was big enough, wasn't it?' (ES_R01)

Now there are subjects for which controversy has no reason to exist. If there is controversy, it's only because people want it, isn't it? There are things where science says it's like this or it's not, full stop. Therefore, wanting to create controversy in areas where there is no longer any chance of controversy seems to me to be inadvisable. (PT_R03)

The polarisation was really political because in the very early stages when people were talking about the [COVID] vaccine, it wasn't politicians, there was not this clear cleavage, let's say that Republicans were against and Democrats for, and then it became just a political issue and that was a disaster. Who's to blame for that? I don't know necessarily, it's complicated. (UK_R02)

I think that the risks come more from political agendas, from political agendas more towards ultra-liberalism, extreme right, that are not interested in scientific information because, for example, with regard to climate change, other impacts of global change, because it does not interest, let's say, their voters in general, nor big capital, big business, because basically what is

being said is to stop the growth of production and industrial processes, as we understand them now, and consumption, I am speaking in general. And also people who, perhaps out of... I think it is born out of fear, resort to theories... to understand what is being conveyed and place it within conspiracy theories. I think those extremes for me are extremes and they are not... it's not so generalised, what happens is that it makes a lot of noise, especially amplified by social media. It can generate negative attitudes and, moreover, by giving an opinion, very dangerous.
(ES_R06)

A common experience of being participants in a ceaseless, complex struggle to provide clear and transparent public communication about issues such as climate change and COVID-19 thus emerged among Researchers across the POIESIS countries. This struggle was regarded by many as involving a powerful personal emotional cost.

"I am someone who likes to go out into the public pretty far to communicate research findings, but I also have colleagues who say, 'Wow, no, we don't want that. We want to do research and not become targets for attacks'. (DE_R04)

"It simply is a high price to pay, as you can see with Mr. Drosten, who is still dealing with court cases years after the pandemic. Personally, I can't imagine paying such a high price. I think it's important [to communicate], but I definitely think there are limits. (DE_R01)

One Spanish Researcher described the use of social media 'trolls' to undermine scientists communicating about climate change as a deliberate strategy of 'attrition', while another Spanish Researcher made the decision to leave Twitter after many years of active engagement with citizens on the platform due to frustration and exhaustion. An experience of rising reticence or withdrawal from the struggle can thus be considered a reflection that these personal costs have indeed become prohibitive.

In summary, Researchers reported a strong positive overall attitude to science communication, including the contexts of the climate and COVID-19 crises. Equally, the majority of Researchers were able to recount personal experiences of what they considered misrepresentation or questionable mediation practices impacting on their communication efforts. A significant number of Researchers had even experienced the malicious use of their work to deliberately create misinformation. It was also clear from Researchers' collective

experiences that there are numerous dimensions to the challenge of obtaining appropriate coverage in communication channels, which requires vigilance and attention to detail on the part of individuals and/or the support of institutional supporting actors or protocols.

5.2.3. Effects on public attitudes

Extending from their reflections on the personal experiences of communicating about sciences in the contexts of climate change and COVID-19, Researchers were also able to draw out some potential or perceived implications for the formation of public attitudes. While a separate section (5.4) deals in some detail with Researchers' thoughts on citizen trust in science more generally, this sub-section briefly highlights Researchers' concerns about how misinformation and the politicisation of science can have deleterious effects on public attitudes.

The entanglement of science, research results in the political polarization linked to climate change and COVID-19 are of particular concern to Researchers when it comes to influence on public attitudes.

I also believe that with the increasing polarization happening in the political landscape, both in Denmark and elsewhere, there is a growing perception in some circles that research is deeply political and ideological. There is a belief that there is an underlying agenda in much of the research communication aimed at influencing the political debate in certain directions, even when it comes from experts (...). So, I think that the tension, in which research communication finds itself, is between this expert role that tries to free itself from the political mud and, on the other hand, the communication that is already perceived as part of the mud and is therefore susceptible to political attacks and accusations of bias and so on (DK_R02)

The most profound effect of this entanglement is identified by this researcher as the emergence of the perception that science is inherently the product of ideological or political forces. Researchers are expected to play active roles as experts in the public sphere, but the framing of their opinions as 'aligned' one way or another politically, particularly on social media, can impact on public attitudes.

In response to some exaggerations within climate change reporting and social media, it can seem entirely logical to citizens to have a greater suspicion about what they are told.

...it may lead to exaggeration, to negativity, it may lead to anything. It can lead which we see it every day not only in our own section and to the creation of myths, conspiracy theories, whatever. And unfortunately, I see, in some people I notice that there is exactly a negativism and a reduction of trust and a reduction of trust in the scientific community, precisely because in this context of the over-dissemination of information from various channels uncontrolled, a feeling is created in some people that "we are all being fooled," so to speak" (GR_R05)

While many Researchers consider that citizens are capable of understanding that competing scientific views exist in relation to climate change or COVID, this may play into the hands of those who seek to undermine the credibility of science. However, the declining credibility of some social media platforms was conversely thought to be potentially reducing the importance of this kind of obvious 'politicking' in the minds of most citizens.

Despite the many challenges they described, Researchers in all countries maintain a conviction that the majority of the population remain supportive of the scientific profession and have confidence in their work. Belief in the value of science communication was seemingly also resilient among our Researchers, in all POIESIS countries.

In Portugal, as you know, scepticism, cynicism about climate change is, has been, relatively residual. (PT_R01)

Nevertheless, a clear result from Researchers' recounting of their experiences and perceptions of communicating science is that public confidence must be fought for on a terrain of struggle and contestation. Researchers need to interact and negotiate to build trust with mediators in order to enhance the quality of communication pathways to citizens. This is particularly the case in contexts such as climate change and COVID-19, where serious threats to the integrity of information must be confronted on a seemingly continuous basis.

5.3. Integrating citizens in research

This section summarises the experiences and perceptions of Researchers on the integration of citizens in science. It is based on, and can be read in conjunction with, Section 4.3 of the respective National Reports, where greater detail and additional direct quotes from participants can be found (Appendix 4).

5.3.1. Why integrate citizens in science?

Interviews with our Researchers (n=41) revealed a positive attitude toward the integration of citizens in science. This positivity was based primarily on first-hand experience, but also on more general or philosophical arguments. While there were some idiosyncratic opinions voiced by some Researchers, overall the support for citizen integration can be summarised under four main themes.

First, Researchers were clearly able to articulate how interacting with and including citizens in their work processes was able to **amplify their perspective on their own research.**

Sometimes questions arise that I, as a scientist, had not really considered, because we scientists exchange ideas among ourselves. Perspectives from society can emerge, allowing me to look at my field differently, which is a gain for me from a scientific perspective. (DE_R05)

So depending on your research question, citizen science can be a good idea. That is, a really good idea, to obtain some of the tacit knowledge, or the inaccessible knowledge, that many citizens possess" (DK_R01)

The inclusion of the perspectives and knowledge of citizens was particularly linked to benefits related to problem definition and research question formation across the POIESIS countries.

Second, integration of citizens was seen as making a positive contribution to **bringing science and society closer together.**

I think it [social integration] makes a lot of sense and is also really good because it can involve people in the scientific

process, which for many is somewhat mysterious. They think, 'I don't know exactly what the scientists are doing.' This approach can... not necessarily remove inhibitions but bring them a little bit closer. (DE_R04)

In other words, people don't understand that in science we work with uncertainty, that is, uncertainty is part of the scientific process. [...] They want very concrete data, concrete numbers, "this is how it's going to be" [...] So what I think is that we need a scientific culture and if the participation of citizens in the scientific sphere facilitates this approach and this understanding of what science is, I think it would be quite positive. (ES_R02)

[I]f he sees on a second level that what he does, that the time he spends has some impact, has some effect. Someone who participates in a project as a stakeholder, a fisherman or a farmer or a tourist, a hotelier in an area, if they see that by participating there, it led somewhere. He said his opinion, it got through somehow and got somewhere, it was heard anyway it was tried to be promoted then even more so he will want to get involved because he will see that it is worthwhile". (GR_R04)

People think "What do I, as a person, bricklayer, secretary, manager of a company, have to do with these things in academia?" (...) There is a greater perceived distance, in which there are fewer socioeconomic, cultural conditions, etc. to get in touch with science issues... "I don't want to know about that. I want to make lunch for my son and be able to buy it, have money to buy food and have time to cook it. Now these guys come with these talks", right? (PT_R01)

I think that also helps, the fact that one participates helps to feel part of the great social enterprise, which is science, right? And it's not just a few people who are very closed in their laboratories. (ES_R01)

Researchers clearly articulate a vision of the relationship between science and society in which being part of science-in-action brings with it feelings of belonging or shared interest that reduces the distance between citizens that working scientists.

Third, societal integration can **improve context sensitivity** in the conduct of problem-oriented research.

When we analyse the results and obtain descriptive tables, we can have this feedback from the community on the interpretation of the results. When we see, for example, that the infection is higher among men who have sex with men in the Brazilian community. We

need to talk to those who do the tests, with those at the checkpoint to understand what meaning this result has for them and we often discover things. We realised, for example, in this specific case, that there is a lot of migration from Brazil and there are a lot of people who already had a diagnosis and need to access care. (PT_R04)

We spent the first year co-designing the package of care because, although both countries had low control of blood pressure, the detail was different, and it had to be reflective of the local context, but as importantly, of course, it had to have buy in, you know, buy in by those who were using it. (UK_R03)

"Our lack of linguistic knowledge of Siri or other languages, and we didn't want to have a third person intermediating in this (...). So, we made the point of having a refugee. (PT_R03)

The inclusion of stakeholders or citizens with particularly important cultural knowledge or competences can augment research teams capacities to conduct research in which specific local or in-group characteristics are central to the feasibility or quality of the research process.

Fourth, the French context revealed an important role for opening up science to outsiders to improve the **transparency and integrity** of science. There is a perception that there is an excessive amount of questionable practices and/or unacceptable conduct within in research.

I think that what we need to change... what we need to change so that we no longer have these cases, so that all this really stops, is the way in which researchers are evaluated, the pressure that is put on publish and all that. And ethics committees won't solve that problem. In fact, ethics committees are a band-aid on a broken leg (...) people do this to keep their jobs... And I think that's where the problem lies. [FR_R05]

As summarized in the French National Report (p. 36), a dysfunctional interface between science and politics is often described as the starting point for thinking about the role of citizens and their ability to influence scientific and technological decisions.

We need to bring science back into society in a way, because it's not up to science to explain the world we live in and make it accessible. It's up to science to help build a shared world.

Otherwise, at some point, everyone is going to say that MY world prevails and we'll have power issues, epistemological power grabs, almost religious power grabs (FR_R01)

Biosafety is not a problem for researchers in their ivory towers, it's a question of knowing how science and society fit together in the end and what society's choices are when it comes to risky scientific projects (...) It's a political issue that must not remain in the hands of experts. That's all there is to it. Experts must never be allowed to play with matches. It's very dangerous. (FR_R02)

Ensuring that science is not a 'closed shop' entirely in the hands of experts is thus considered an important reason for the enhancement of societal integration in science.

5.3.2. How to integrate citizens in science?

Researchers' experiences with integrating citizens in their work provide many insights into what is important in making participation work. **Building trust and relationships** are viewed as essential.

Because to work in this way you always have to have trust. If they don't trust you, it's very difficult for them to really participate. (ES_R02)

"People realise that a certain knowledge was necessary in a certain community, in a certain group. And then they say "Look, those people didn't really understand the importance of this issue. It would be important for you to go there and talk to them. (PT_R03)

But Researchers were emphatic that the inclusion or participation of citizens cannot be done for 'tick box' reasons, to satisfy research funders for example. According to one German Researcher (p. 74), citizens notice when they are not taken seriously and when participation is 'fake', arguing that this can have negative consequences for public trust in science.

Rather, participation of citizens or stakeholders needs to be **integrated and 'upstream' in the research cycle**, not limited to the final dissemination phases of a project.

Over time I began to realise and modify my way of being in science in relation to the public a little. And one of the more or less obvious ways is to ask people what bothers them and what problem they have that I can help solve. (PT_R03)

[I]n 99% of the cases... the discourses of participation are really discourses regarding dissemination and diffusion. [There is no co-design of research projects, in the best of cases there is a consultation at some point in the execution methodology and in most cases there is a final benchmarking to know how the results are contrasted and synchronised with the perceptions of citizens, but in the design phase there is zero.. I would problematise the very concept of citizen participation, because I believe that the way it has been incorporated into the discourse of scientific policies is very White Wash and diluted, that is, it is an idea of making consultations, of..., but not of being incorporated into the design of the experiments, so to speak. (ES_R04)

A research project that takes citizen participation seriously has to include it at least in the development.... well, it should include it in the theoretical part, but certainly in the methodological development. (ES_R04)

As well as being serious about integration and to promote it as broadly as possible across the research cycle, Researchers also emphasise the **responsibility** that comes with bringing citizens and stakeholders on-board. Whereas the discourse of citizen science and participation tends to deal with an abstract and neutral individual or social group, many Researchers are aware they are negotiating collaboration with concrete individual and social identities.

I think it can go both ways, you know. Let's say I do a project with climate activists; how would the right wing in Denmark perceive such a project? They would probably see it as part of the muddle, where our research and politics are completely intertwined. (...) That's where I see some problems too, you know, the idea that there exists a space where we can all step in and at some point agree on the best solution for, for example, the climate. I don't really believe in that. (DK_R02)

One of the things we face has to do with the sensitivity of this topic: climate activism, radical kids who go around throwing things (...). Radical kids who go around throwing things and who are dangerous and, therefore, have to have a certain amount of secrecy. (PT_R01)

[I]t must be done with a lot of responsibility, with a very, very well designed methodology to understand how, why, who, as always, right? It makes no sense to involve more people, even though it is sometimes difficult to define the group of actors or stakeholders who are affected by the phenomena under investigation. This must be done with criteria of responsibility, fairness, participation and equality. In other words, you have to be very clear about the criteria, the principles, the methodology based on the questions you are asking. (ES_M06)

I would wish that [patient organisations] are involved directly in project planning. Depending on the project, one could ask, 'Are there any considerations we should take into account? How do patients want to be addressed about this research project? What is appropriate? How do they want to be informed? (DE_R01)

Researchers thus advocate strongly that if citizen science or other forms of layperson or stakeholder involvement are worth doing, then they must be done seriously, with as full involvement in the research cycle as possible. This must be done with care and attention to the potential vulnerabilities of participants, with Researchers being keenly aware that participation too can be subject to politicisation.

5.3.3. Understanding the limits of citizen integration

Of course, Researchers do not only see the positive side to embarking on citizen integration and neither have their experiences been uniformly good. Rather, Researchers are able to draw some limitations to participative practices. Any idea that integration should be mandatory, for example at the level of research funding, is widely and strongly rejected.

Many Researchers believe that the type and level of citizen integration that is appropriate for any research project or line is always **context dependent**.

Get involved in working on the bench with me? No. Getting involved in order to follow results, yes. But this has to do with communication, right? The way I communicate the results of the laboratory experiments we do here. Now, of course, for me it doesn't make any sense for the public to be in the laboratory. (PT_R05)

I am really torn. For some funding programmes, yes, for others, no. As scientists, we have a duty to communicate what we do, as we are funded by taxpayer money. Therefore, everyone has the right to know what we do, not just through cryptic journals but in an understandable way. However, tying it to research funding in a mandatory way is not something I support. There are programmes where it makes sense, but there should still be basic research conducted for the sake of knowledge, not just for communication.
(DE_R04)

A second limitation to the societal integration is external and relates to the **perceived lack of institutional support**.

I would primarily say that if it [social integration] is required, then time and money must be allocated for it. And this means that it needs to be established in such a way that the concept must first be understood at a societal level. (DE_R06)

I believe that it is not a project endorsed by the institutions, that they do not believe it, that is, that it is a project that is couched in rhetorical language, that it is a political correctness, that it is something that has to be done, but the means are not provided to do it. And what is more, I believe that in none of the phases of the management of science policy is participation really included. ' (ES_R04)

A shortfall in resources is allocation is perceived as an important problem, as is a lack of training opportunities on both the science and the society sides.

So I think that overall the problem of increasing citizen participation in science is very directly related to the existence of both the intention and the funds to create the appropriate procedures, because it's not something that you can just take someone and say you're going to do this. You have to train them, you have to give them a fee.. (GR_R05)

The other barrier there is probably that we are not born knowing. Learning to communicate takes time, doesn't it? (ES_R01)

It seems evident from Researchers comments that social integration should not be considered as always essential or even necessary, but where the benefits of participation are apparent then greater support from R&I institutions and organisations are needed.

5.3.4. Understanding the challenges of citizen integration

Researchers also articulate challenges that are associated with participatory processes in their research work. The most prominent of these are concerns and anxieties about **data quality** when laypersons are involved in research.

If they are interested and invest their time, I trust they will do it well and not maliciously distort the results or degrade the quality. (DE_R01)

In my opinion, yes, the citizen should be allowed to participate in research, but we just have to be very careful how we use his contribution, because he has neither the experience nor the knowledge to distinguish the right information -he may not do it on purpose- but he may not be able to distinguish the right information from the wrong information. (GR_R05)

Imagine, making a portrait of marine litter in Portugal, OK, it's interesting, but is the data well collected? Can we be confident in the way they are collected, are they right? Therefore, this doubt persists. (PT_R05)

Though it is also pointed out by one Researcher that data quality issues are also a function of training.

The limitation is mainly how good I, as a project coordinator or supervisor, am at ensuring that I properly convey instructions to that person. (PT_R06)

Another challenge identified by Researchers is the need to **manage expectations** of citizen participants.

Managing expectations is not easy. In such processes, it is essential to be open from the beginning about the limitations and what the collaboration serves. (DE_R05)

Some Researchers consider it inappropriate to cede control of research agendas.

I see the disadvantage or concern that other topics might be prioritised because they are seen as more directly relevant to people here (DE_R03)

Another considers there are also trade-offs linked to trying to 'evangelize' science to those who do not have any predisposition to be interested.

"Of course, it's fun to talk to scientifically interested citizens, but we probably need to take another step and think about how we can reach those who have little trust in us and may not have the motivation to engage with it on their own. But this is laborious and probably not always enjoyable. DE_R01

This leads toward a major challenge that Researchers identify with integrating participation in their work – the problem of **time**.

Transformative research is time-consuming because you speak a different language, you have to translate scientific terminology, assess what you get and from whom, and so on. These are things you don't necessarily have to ask in a purely scientific environment. (DE_R05)

So, encouraging and promoting participation requires a lot of time and energy, that you have to work in research in a different way. [...] so I think the only negative thing, more from the perspective of those of us who dedicate ourselves to research, is this: the frustration that can be generated by all the time you are putting in and then maybe you do something and just three or four motivated people come and that's it, but well, even so, I think it has to be done, that is to say that this is how it works. (ES_R02)

As a scientist, I also see the practical negative aspects because it will consume an enormous amount of time. (DE_R01)

It takes a lot of time, and this time is not always planned for. They [research funders] want a participative research design within six weeks, which is just not possible (DE_R06).

Although the impoverished nature of Researchers' time also hints at another underlying change, which is the exploitation of free

citizens' labour in a model that some claim is the apotheosis of a neo-liberal model of science (Mirowski 2010).

But clearly having that be open and available showed that you can have citizens involved in science like that in ways where it can make sense and they can make really valuable contributions because we as scientists, we're stretched, we're stretched so thin for so long. That this was absolutely welcome and really necessary work because there wasn't enough of us to do it. (ES_R03)

Many of these challenges identified by Researchers then roll into a related concern about the career impacts of devoting extended amounts of time to citizen or stakeholder integration processes and activities.

Young people have their whole careers ahead of them and they need all these activities that they can do willingly to be valued because if not, we lose them. And that is a barrier that is not valued and that there is not enough time. As it is not valued, young people's bosses don't give them the time to do it, right? As it is not valued, they end up abandoning it because there are other things that give you more, more security that you have the merits to later have a better contract, stability and be able to continue researching. (ES_R01)

For many scientists, especially early-career researchers, such projects are immensely time-consuming. You can't make many publications from them, which is unfortunately one of the main currencies in science, especially during the doctoral and post-doc phase. This is a systemic problem. (DE_R04)

It was a double-edged sword in ways that I didn't necessarily expect. [...] And I think a lot of people would still maybe say that you know, yes, it's very nice and it's very good you did that. But at the end of the day, it's not research. And if you're going to be a university professor, that's not, that's not the communications department. (ES_M03)

The challenges to adequately recognise and reward some types of citizen integration and public engagement work in systems of academic career advancement are consistent with the concerns that have led to reform movements such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)). The premium on publication outputs for early career researchers in particular can restrict the use of participative methodologies prior to establishing an independent

research careers. This is compounded by a lack of institutional support for systematic training of doctoral candidates in public engagement and science communication methods and skills.

Overall, the picture painted by our Researchers suggests a nuanced understanding of the benefits, limitations, and challenges of societal integration. Not all of our Researchers engaged in such activities – but even these individuals were largely supported of the rationale and principles guiding integration and participation actions. There is a belief among most of our Researchers that integration activities can bring science and society closer together, with the implication that public awareness and trust is likely to be improved by such interactions, although some do question this assumption.

It is evident that, amongst those Researchers who are firmly committed to integration practices, there is a strong perception of insufficient institutional support in terms of funding, training, and recognition. This is an important finding in relation to the 3i4T model, suggesting that public trust can be enhanced by a more systematic approach to supporting integration mechanisms. This approach should be balanced and targeted as Researchers were strongly of the opinion that participation and integration measures are not for universal application. Rather, they should become a more commonly used set of objectives and actions where the integration of citizens has the potential and possibility of being mutually beneficial.

5.4. Public trust in science

This section summarises the experiences and perceptions of Researchers regarding public trust in science. It is based on, and can be read in conjunction with, Section 4.4 of the respective National Reports, where greater detail and additional direct quotes from participants can be found (Appendix 4).

5.4.1. Researchers' perceptions of citizen trust

Overall, Researchers perceive that the public does have trust in science. However, in most POIESIS countries this perception of trust is directly entangled with how Researchers view citizens' **trust in the scientific profession**.

People have quite a lot of trust in science in general and in scientists in particular. (ES_R02)

I think that, by default, and with regard to scientists (...), the group of scientists in general are well-regarded people. (PT_R03)

In fact, the respect for the scientific profession is perceived by some as covering for concerns about science itself.

I think this trust is an "idol with feet of clay". Because it's not a real trust, (...) it's made of the elevation of a profession. (PT_R05)

This reflects a general sentiment that, despite initial statements about public trust, leads into perceptions that there are challenges or threats to the status of science in the eyes of the public. Researchers' self-reflection on the **state of science**, as insiders, leads many to consider that the emergence of public concerns are entirely legitimate.

I kind of live in a bubble. There are some people who are with me, they are concerned about the hierarchies of power in the construction of science, that is a very critical perspective of how science is seen, but no one is doubting science per se. (PT_R06)

I think it's really problematic at the moment that trust in science is being weakened because there's such a lot of fraud. And that is being used by those who want, you know, who are anti-science. And they are pointing to, you know, there's reports that, you know, a certain percentage of papers of fraud in this paper mills and so on. People will point to that, say, well, you can't trust anything, you know, and people who are sort of anti-vax will say, you know, well, all the, all the... So it's bad. But I think the way of dealing with that is to be very open, that you are very proactively dealing with cases where there is problems and fraud. Not to pretend it's not happening because again, you have to think in the longer term that this is going to come out. And if it's, you know, you can't hide it forever. And if it comes out that you have been attempting to hide a problem, it's much, much, much worse than if you deal promptly with the problem. And make it, you know, it's clear that you have got mechanisms for doing so. But I get this reaction a lot because I'm trying to, you know, have a meeting on how we handle fraud and I found that people don't want to touch it. People in the scientific establishment typically are

nervous of the topic because they take the view that if you talk about fraud and how it should be handled, then other people will come in and sort of think that science, not just science, perhaps the whole of academia is flawed (FR_R06)

[W]hat relationship does science have with citizenship in the abstract, I think it is very difficult to say at this historical moment, I think we are experiencing a regression, a regression, and this regression can be blamed both on the proliferation of conspiracy theories, Fake news, I don't know how many, but also on science, that is, science, the institution of science is the one that is delegitimising certain internal currents such as the social sciences, the humanities, participation, so, I don't know if I'm answering your question, but it seems difficult in the abstract, it seems difficult to me, I think, but I do believe that we are at a historical moment in which what I understand as... . The paradigm of science or the structure, not in a Kuhnian sense, of the, the structures of scientific knowledge, is being eroded on two sides, on the side of society, with conspiracy theories, and on the side of science itself, with a naturalistic conservatism of what is good science. (ES_R04)

And I think science probably deserves it, that loss of trust ... I think scientific integrity has eroded I think the science peer review process is broken. (UK_R05)

At the same time, Researchers' believe that **public awareness** of problems in the institution of science are part of the transformation of science that is necessary to eventually reverse the trend toward erosion of trust.

And it's true that... it probably damaged a bit the image or the trust of the public in science with a capital S perhaps... But at the same time, it has brought to light things that I think the public was not necessarily aware of, the pressure to publish for example, which will perhaps help in the end to solve this problem of evaluating researchers (...) (FR_R05)

You could say it's terrible there are many retractions, or you could say it's wonderful there are many retractions because actually its scrutiny and if something's incorrect then it gets retracted, in some sense, that's the way it should be, and even with the best will, let's say someone can write a paper which leads to wrong conclusions, that can happen, and so fundamentally, that things are retracted, to me, is not a bad thing ... I think healthy science should have a process of retraction, (UK_R02)

The same logic, that problems should be open to public scrutiny is also referred to in relation to the sometimes fraught process of trying to produce vaccines under time pressure directly in the public view.

When there are failures or when there is an adverse effect of a vaccine, to say look, precisely the fact that the adverse effect of the vaccine is detected, means that it is being thoroughly monitored, if nothing is detected, it means that it is not being looked at. The positive side of finding something negative is that it is being investigated. And the same goes for integrity and ethics.' (EN_R01)

The parallel drawn with REI issues reflects a general view among researchers that concealment of failures, whether technical or ethical, is not to be tolerated.

In summary, Researchers' general perceptions about public trust in science are positive, but qualified in two main ways. First, they view that public trust is more invested in scientists, in their fellow humans and professionals, than it is in science. Second, their own tacit knowledge about the science system tells them that threats to public trust are logical and entirely in keeping with the flaws they themselves acknowledge as posing serious challenges to science.

5.4.2. Citizen concerns about science

When asked about their direct experiences of citizens expressing concerns about science, our Researchers had little to recount. Of particular interest to POIESIS, Researchers were unlikely to mention research ethics and integrity (REI) issues as prominent among the concerns of citizens. This is not to suggest that REI is not a concern among citizens, rather it is to say that this is not the perception among our Researchers.

The public has no clue about plagiarism, p-hacking and all that ... not any of these aspects concern the public and how they look at science. These are the debates that are there in academia, but they don't drive public debate, I have not heard anyone mentioning, oh, okay, because you're just a paper mill machine, we can't trust your science. (UK_R05)

Researchers across the POIESIS countries have a very consistent and clear view of what is the primary reason for citizens' concerns about science. Put simply, Researchers' attribute citizens' concerns largely to the **uncertainty** that is the structuring principle of scientific discovery and the scientific method.

I think their [citizens'] concern is the classic one: "Well, they will come up with something new tomorrow, so can we trust what they say today?" I don't know how widespread this is, but it's what everyone seems to think citizens are thinking. But I don't know how common it is in reality. (DK_R01)

Then 'the science' that found this out at the beginning is not wrong, but is simply overtaken in the course of scientific work. Communicating this aspect is often challenging. (DE_R02)

Yes, I think it's true that there is to some extent a crisis of trust between science and society and that (...) what happened at the time of Covid didn't help, because... there were things that were a bit contradictory. And it wasn't very well understood by the public, so science didn't know. This is perhaps something that... it's always difficult to make people understand that there are things that we can say with great confidence, even certainty, and other things that we don't know, or that we know but with much more doubt. So there you have it: we have scientific elements, but they may be wrong afterwards. So there you have it, science in the making, and that's not easy to convey to the general public. (FR_R03)

I think the fact that science can change is still something that's not very well understood and it's really hard to convey to people. (ES_R03)

This structure of uncertainty also manifests itself in the contemporaneous existence of multiple valid scientific perspectives on a topic of challenge. That a healthy science community does not speak with a single unified voice when facts are still in dispute can create multiple 'scientific truths', which may make their way into public space.

This will create a confusion, so to speak, in the sense that if there is something, if some people, if they present two views, which was very frequent at the time and with climate change, of course it's done by scientists, but with Covid it was even more so. If some people say something contradictory, whose view is

valid, whose view is right, whose view should I follow, why does he explain it better than the other one?. (GR_R04)

One study says one thing, another study says something else (...) I think that creates more confusion in people and some distrust. (PT_R04)

In addition, there is the question of how scientific advice is translated into public policy actions and how well the public understands where scientific advice ends and political decisions begin.

The final thing I might add is the confusion between science and policy. Because I think that's another one. And this of course is also a line that can be genuinely blurred between scientists and politicians. And I think there's still a lot of discussion among scientists about what kind of advice do you give as a scientist? You purely send the numbers or do you give a recommendation, or do you downright tell people? If you don't do the stupid advice, where do you draw that line? What's your job as a scientist? How does that bounce up with perhaps your feeling of morality as a human? You know, can you live with yourself to just give numbers if you, especially if you know the government might misinterpret them, but I think especially from the outside people can not... can also not understand that interaction. (ES_R03)

The social and epistemological organisation of science and its political relationship to society is not intuitively easy for citizens to understand. This is specially so when, at later stages in a particular research cycle or paradigm, certain 'facts' become universally accepted, creating an image of science as always 'black and white'.

This is summarised in the Portugal National Report (p.47), which then also makes the link to the fact that the capacities of individual citizens to understand 'scientific progress' are not evenly distributed throughout societies: "Not only misinformation can hinder trust in science, but also the **great amount of scientific information** produced at a very fast pace and immediately available, combined with the **lack of certainty** in science where different studies can point to different and, sometimes, inconsistent results. This challenge relates to the lack of scientific literacy as people do not know the scientific process".

Researchers' indeed do perceive that, on the society side, the **scientific literacy** needed to understand scientific uncertainty is not always available.

...I believe there is a really, really big difference between rural and urban areas, and I think there's a big difference in - how should I put it - one's social capital in relation to this, and one's experience with the education system. (DK_R01)

Studies are for example published showing a 10% probability of something happening within a certain period. This is obviously alarming, but it is still just a 10% probability, not a deterministic event. I think it is hard for people to understand that predictions often involve probabilities, and it is challenging to interpret this correctly. (DE_R03)

Those who have lower self-efficacy - that is, confidence in their ability to understand research - do not seek answers about what is happening, but rather answers on how they should act in the situation, what they should do in that situation. (DK_R05)

However, Researchers also perceive that creating a bridge of understanding between scientific uncertainty and general public depends on **science communication**, which may not be entirely up to the task.

I think it's probably how it's communicated to them, because I think the other one (the conduct of science) they can't know, and they can't have a very clear opinion. But how it's communicated to them and how articulately and documented and substantiated. I think that's what's troubling them. (GR_R06)

With this challenge further amplified by the challenge of **crisis communication**:

The scientific community simply jumped in at the deep end and there were lots of people who simply said 'Yes, I'll go out there and contribute something because I have to deal with it'. But of course, they had no idea how it worked, especially at the beginning. At my university, I think we had the first media training courses on Covid-19 research about a year into the pandemic. Of course, a lot had already happened, and a lot had gone brutally wrong. Because these were things, of course, or

simply researchers whose work had never and would never have met public interest before. (DE_R02)

The logic of the argument has turned full circle, with the capacity of Researchers to communicate about the uncertainty of science to a public audience with varying capacities to understand the message, then folded back into a perceived **lack of support from institutions**. From the perspective of the 3i4T model underpinning POIESIS, it is important to recognise the crucial role for institutions that emerges across multiple points of Researchers' descriptions of their experiences and perceptions.

Researchers' are also convinced that citizens' are more concerned about whether the **promised benefits of science** are being realised than more esoteric issues of REI in how science is done.

Although there are, of course, always negative examples of science being falsified, I believe the main issue is the transferability and applicability for the individual citizen. (DE_R01)

"Citizens' guide to research assessment is the usefulness of the practical results. (GR_R02)

There is a perceived divergence between what science investigates and what the real problems are. (DE_R04).

In summary, for Researchers the question of whether citizens have trust in science opens up a complex set of interrelations between the institution of science, the vocation or profession of being a scientist, the general public perception of the integrity of social and state institutions, and citizens' opinions and perceptions about the role of science and technology in their worlds. Added to this complicated terrain is the impact of specific challenges or threats, such as climate change and COVID-19 and how these direct intrusions into everyday life impact on relationships between scientists and society. Researchers' perceptions on this question required some unravelling, as the most immediate response – that public trust is high – is qualified and problematized in subsequent discussion in Researchers are able to articular multiple dimensions relevant to citizens' concerns about science.

5.4.3. Rationales for the perceived vulnerability of public trust in science

Along with their descriptions of citizens concerns about science, Researchers can also articulate strong rationales for any undermining of public trust. These rationales seem to indicate an underlying perception among Researchers that public trust in science is somewhat precarious or under threat.

First, many Researchers consider public trust in science to be contingent on the **general level of trust** in (state) institutions. For example, one Greek Researcher highlighted that lack a general suspiciousness regarding institutions is 'part of the emotional logic of the Greek people' (GR_R01). Similar sentiments expressed by one German Researcher ties public trust in science to an "underlying trust factor that impacts many areas of life" (DE_R04). Another Researcher ties in a suspicion of market institutions, and 'the pressure of global capitalism to generate results, which sometimes leads to the introduction of untested technologies, and we have examples of this, unfortunately, throughout history (ES_R05).

Second, Researchers are preoccupied by public perceptions that **suggest science is not independent** but controlled by external influences. A perception exists among the public that research can be manipulated when it is funded by private interests (Greece NR, p.40). The independence of scientists is also not clear to many citizens.

The misunderstanding of how science works as far as how, like, how do you scientists do this and how do we make these decisions and who's in control of what scientists say is also another thing that people really misunderstood in the pandemic. Some of this is just plain conspiracy theories. But on the other hand, I also think that it often reflects a genuine lack of understanding about, you know, who pays me, who decides what I say, who's pocket am I in? ... I think that misunderstanding of actually scientists are very independent compared to employees of most other companies. Something that also could maybe help to build some trust that we are not mouthpieces for a university or anything else. (ES_R03)

Third, Researchers connect public doubts about their independence to malicious actors, who deliberately seek to **politicise and undermine science** - with this polarisation often being replicated or naturalised in public discourse.

Massive lobbying efforts, with think tanks and multi-million-dollar companies investing heavily to foster mistrust, are probably the biggest factor. (DE_R04)

The [perceived] lack of integrity in science is also spurred on by this disinformation, favoured by economic interests, especially in those areas that are detrimental to them. So there are tendencies, well, when you see death threats against Aemet technicians, you say that we have completely lost the plot, don't you? (ES_R05)

...I mean, I think there are problems, but there are actors in society that are actively trying to make it more than it is and to undermine trust for all sorts of reasons ... There certainly is a problem ... Because they are libertarians who believe that nobody should be telling them what to do and there are (also) people who are going to be opposed to that because they make these things, and it hits their bottom line ... and you can get a coalition coming together, you know, each echoing each other's voices ... astroturf essentially, so what seemed to be public grassroots organisations are entirely a creation of the people who are making money out of it ... marketing doubt, manufacturing doubt (UK_R03)

Finally, Researchers are also very clear that the advent of **social media channels** and the transformation of the traditional media order makes misinformation easier to promote and, conversely, citizens' searches for credible information more difficult.

What used to be done only by the Bild newspaper - capturing people's attention with simple slogans - is now much easier on social media. There are actors who deliberately engage in this, consciously spreading misinformation to mislead people. (DE_R05)

It takes years to build trust and a minute to tear it down. So, when somebody comes out and either intentionally or unintentionally, or by mistake, says something that doesn't stand up right, automatically the trust is shattered. So yes, there is a serious issue about how information is being handled by the media, by the social media and so on, which have a serious responsibility because they just have to increase their penetration, they have to increase clicks, they have to increase their television... as they call it, their viewership. But sometimes members of the scientific community also play the media game for their own agendas...(GR_R05)

As the pandemic began and social media became almost the only means of communication for many people, the situation gained a new level of significance. (DE_R02)

The perceived chaos and 'anything goes' nature of the information space in which science and scientists become entangled, and struggle to control their message is symptomatic of a deeper problem that is of profound importance of understand public trust in science. As described in the UK National Report (p. 40) the 'crisis of trust' in such a context becomes a '**crisis of truth**' where facts are relativised and consensus often fragile and fleeting.

...it's part of a much bigger challenge, a bigger societal challenge where ... evidence is malleable, facts are malleable to one's political views, particularly on social media and so once that is, once you allow that to be an accepted part of a societal conversation, well then it doesn't matter how rigorous you go about either doing or explaining what you doing in science, its dismissed with the wave of a hand. (UK_R05)

Overall, Researchers express concern and understanding for what they consider to be the main rationales underpinning citizens doubts about science. In these reflections Researchers articulate their concerns that confusion and conspiracy are potent weapons, and in the hands of malicious actors armed with social-media based communications expertise public trust in science is indeed vulnerable. These rationales step away from more immediate concerns about the conduct of science and science communication. Instead, rationales are located on a macro-terrain of public concerns about industry or state control of science, and the manipulation of a more chaotic public science-media information space by actors with vested political or economic interests.

5.5. Other themes

Three additional themes emerged from the Researcher interviews. First, in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic response in Spain, one Researcher who was deeply involved in local and regional initiatives was extremely concerned by the apparent **devaluing of social science and humanities research**.

Well, I mean, with all due respect, but the research that can be done in virology or epidemiology, in other words, clinical or biological studies, etc., the results will be the same, whether they are done in Israel, Japan or Spain, but the social research that is done in Seville, Valencia or Madrid will not be done in

Israel, Japan or Australia, in other words, either it is done in Seville, Valencia or Madrid or it is not done at all. (ES_R04)

According to this Researcher, failure to fund appropriate levels of place-based SSH research that paid attention to class and culture issues was an oversight on the part of commissioning authorities. The devaluing of SSH emanating importantly from the structure of scientific expert bodies in the Researchers experience.

But my perception of one of the things that happens is that within science there are internal delegitimisations. So one thing that I found fascinating is how the social sciences are delegitimised.

Despite the obvious relevance of SSH knowledge and research skills, in the context of the pandemic governments, policymakers and other scientists seem to regress toward a highly technical understanding of how to combat urgent social and public health challenges.

Second, in the context of discussions about social integration in science, researchers in Portugal and Spain mentioned concerns about the potential for exploitation of societal participants. In Spain, one Researcher referred to **'helicopter' scientists**, who 'fly in' to a research context in order to capture what they need in terms of data and results, often through collaboration with a local partner, then 'fly out' once they have what they need to generate academic publications. This withdrawal to the 'ivory tower' was mentioned by several Researchers in Spain to refer to public perceptions of the somewhat utilitarian relationships that scientist can have with stakeholders and research participants.

Similarly in Portugal, concerns were expressed about exploitative researcher practices.

From the perspective of young people who are very involved and committed to these issues, how will this effort, this work, these aspirations, etc., be appropriated by researchers. (...) It involves values, it involves worldviews, it involves priorities, it involves ideologies, it involves a series of issues. And therefore, it is clear that there is a difficulty here in terms of managing all these things so far in the writing process of researchers. (PT_R01)

This **intellectual extractivism** refers to an exploitation of knowledge without a proper recognition or compensation of the public's contribution:

These academics come, you know, they want to, they want to take advantage of us and then we won't gain much from it. (PT_R01)

Finally, a theme that emerged in Germany and the UK was the emergence of a kind of **private science designed to weaken trust in public science**, the results and findings emanating from public institutions such as universities. The strategy exploits trends toward Open Science, in which researchers are expected to make data available for re-use. In the UK, some politically aligned actors with sophisticated statistical and data visualization skills do just this, "generating their own graphs and interpretations" as a means to produce a dissenting report on the scientists results. In Germany, Researchers report that partly that increasingly, 'scientific studies' are used to support any kinds of arguments in public and political discourse but without using any criteria to assess whether these 'studies' are actually of (good) scientific quality. In fact, many may be considered by the research community to be pseudo-science, but this does not prevent them obtaining an equal footing in many public debates or information spaces.

5.6. Recommendations to improve public trust in science

This final sub-section compiles the Recommendations on public trust developed in the various National Reports. Researchers participating in the EIS were asked for their opinions and suggestions regarding changes to policy or practice that could contribute to improving public trust in science. The Recommendations for each POIESIS partner represent a synthesis generated by that partner, based on the individual contributions made by participating Researchers in their country study. This section is based on and should be read in conjunction with the 'Synthesis of Recommendations' section (4.5 or 4.6) in each of the respective National Reports, where greater detail and discussion of Researchers' perspectives on changes to policy or practice in their national system context can be found (Appendix 4).

Table 5.3 Recommendations for improving public trust in science based on Researcher suggestions

Country	Recommendations
Denmark	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The media and politicians should pay great attention to science representation and to how scientific information is verified, received and used politically, ensuring that knowledge dissemination meets high standards and avoids intentional misrepresentation. 6. Attention should be focused on avoiding a negative framing of science and a political devaluing of higher education and the field of (science) communication. 7. A greater focus should be given to exploring how citizens and other stakeholders could be involved in research, broadening the concept of involvement to support and strengthen research-based knowledge. 8. Researchers should explore methods of communicating science in novel, pragmatic, and solution-oriented ways, while also increasing their presence in face-to-face dissemination. The academic system should place greater emphasis on the importance of science communication.
France	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The first recommendation is to encourage scientific institutions to provide opportunities for scientists to reflect collectively on issues related to science and society. Some of the scientists we interviewed feel that, beyond the institutional discourse, their research organisation does not value the ability of scientists to develop a form of reflexivity 6. The second recommendation has to do with institutional guidance for scientists who decide to take a public stand on a particular issue. The scientists interviewed report a degree of uncertainty in their risk-taking, both professionally and legally. A feeling of uncertainty that calls for the production of practical guidelines dedicated to the public engagement of researchers. 7. The third recommendation relates to public communication by scientists in crisis situations. If we are to have a positive impact on public trust in science in a situation of great uncertainty, we need media resources that give scientists the time they need to develop a complex message. Collaboration with the mainstream media must

	<p>therefore be developed to ensure the conditions for this crisis communication.</p> <p>8. The fourth recommendation takes up the invitation described at the end of the previous section not to make short-term use of the notion of public trust. We must avoid opposing trust with ethics and integrity. Trust must not be used as a lever to cultivate opacity about any particular aspect of the way science works. On the contrary, we need to take a long-term view and be aware that the ideal of trust presupposes a form of openness and transparency</p>
Germany	<p>7. Engage with a more critical or 'uninterested' public through new creative forms of communication.</p> <p>8. Make science communication training an integral part of university curricula.</p> <p>9. Give scientific news more space in institutionalised mass media.</p> <p>10. Improve the recognition of science communication and social integration activities within the academic system.</p> <p>11. Clarify the roles of science and politics in society and create more coherence in the interaction of both spheres.</p> <p>12. Improve climate communication in a way that makes clear that prevention is always better (and cheaper) than reaction in the context of climate change.</p>
Greece	<p>4. Creation of participatory and informative events</p> <p>5. Creation of Institutions that will oversee the way science is communicated</p> <p>6. Reformation of the educational system and wider educational events</p>
Portugal	<p>5. Increase scientific literacy through science communication and formal education</p> <p>6. Promote transparency in research for the public and among peers</p> <p>7. Train researchers for science communication and social integration</p> <p>8. Integration is welcome, but with limits and only in certain parts of the scientific process</p>
Spain	<p>9. Improve the scientific information supply chain by training and developing communication skills among scientists and reinforcing their collaborations with professional science communicators</p> <p>10. Invest in permanent programmes designed to raise the level of scientific literacy and culture among school students and the general public</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Improve the recognition and rewards for science communication in the evaluation and career plans of scientists, particularly early career researchers 12. Create institutional policies and resource allocations to support and incentivise scientists committed to communication 13. Create an open public infrastructure of scientific data management and publications 14. Create stable local-level infrastructures of social integration into research, through institutions and key organisations 15. Enhance interdisciplinary research collaboration among social and STEM sciences 16. Promote transdisciplinary research approaches
United Kingdom	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Public engagement that promotes honesty and projects uncertainty will lead to a social justice agenda which ultimately results in a trusting, grateful, reassured public 8. Mediatisation encourages too much 'gloss' on the facts and thus undermines science. Public engagement through impact and attention seeking distracts individual scientists from main focus which is research 9. The deficit model does not work; more information is not the solution when values are at stake 10. Science cannot guarantee the conditions of its own functioning as 'orientation on truth' in public sphere goes beyond science. Science in the public sphere relies on the respect for truth being there. 11. Investing more in critical thinking skills will give public more tools to process information. 12. Epistemic humility, demonstrating trustworthiness is the issue, not lack of public trust in science, i.e. the problem is not with the public.

An overview of these 35 Recommendations reveals differences in the relative degree of generality or specificity. There is some consistency between countries in that, perhaps unsurprisingly, most Recommendations focus on either institutions (n=12) or science communication (n=13), compared with research integrity (n=4) and societal integration (n=4). Table 5.4 summarizes the Recommendations in their relation to the major elements of the 3i4T model.

Table 5.4 Researcher recommendations mapped to the 3i4T model (n=35)

3i4T model	Recommendations
Institutions	FR1; FR2; DE4; DE5; GR2; GR3; PT3; ES2; ES3; ES4; ES7; UK4; UK5
Integration	DK3; PT4; ES6; ES8
Integrity	FR4; PT2; ES5; UK6
Science communication	DK1; DK2; DK3; FR3; DE1; DE2; DE3; DE6; GR1; PT1; ES1; UK1; UK2; UK3

The focus of the Recommendations on institutions and science communication is perhaps unsurprising considering the methodological approach undertaken. The Researcher part of the EIS was centred on the integration dimension of the 3i4T model. The Researcher interview was sequenced in the following order: background; case context; citizen integration; public trust in science; recommendations for change. This was done deliberately to find out whether having left the topic of citizen integration behind, participants would return to it in making their suggestions for improving public trust in science. The result of this procedure seems clear.

A similar research design was used to address the integrity dimension of the 3i4T model in the Researcher interviews. In the section of the interview on public trust in science, interviewers were trained to not prompt for REI issues until after the second and final question. REI issues did not feature prominently in Researchers unprompted responses. This was consistent with Researchers' predominant opinion (once prompted) that the public were not really aware about issues of questionable research practices and REI malpractice as drivers of distrust.

In contrast, Researchers were preoccupied with issues related to the complexity of science communication, media attention logics, the chaos of social media, and the prevalence of deliberate misinformation. It is unsurprising therefore that the majority of Recommendations focus on how science communication can be improved and how institutional support is imperative in order to contribute to enhancing public trust in science. Finally, it should be reiterated clearly that Researchers do not believe that there is a general problem of distrust of science in any of the POIESIS countries. Rather, Researchers are concerned that public trust is vulnerable under contemporary socio-political and mediatized conditions, and reflect a commitment to contribute to reducing this vulnerability

through communication and to a lesser extent integration and integrity practices.

6. Concluding remarks

The research findings presented in this global report were produced as part of Work package 2 of the POIESIS project, coordinated by the project's ISCTE partner in Portugal. The Expert Interview study (EIS, Task 2.3) was led the project's CSIC partner in Spain.

The EIS continued the POIEIS project's interrogation of the three main assumptions underlying the 'HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44' Call.

- First, that "... trust depends on scientists and engineers' capacity to demonstrate high standards of research integrity" and that breaches to research integrity, i.e. research misconduct or questionable research practices, will lead to mistrust;
- Second, that "... citizen and civil society's involvement in co-creating R&I agendas and contents makes research more relevant and responsive to society and strengthens co-ownership and trust"; and
- Third, that these markers of responsible research practices - integrity and societal integration - are "fostered by conducive institutional governance arrangements and policy environments". The assumption is that institutions matter by enabling and supporting researchers to act responsibly.

Based on the POIESIS project 3i4T model, the global aim of the EIS was to test whether research ethics and integrity (REI), social integration in science, and institutional conditions matter for public trust in science. The moderating variable was science communication as a key process of information translation from science to society, i.e. from the shopfloor practices of research work to the everyday lives of the general public.

The research approach was a series of semi-structured expert interviews (n=119). Two distinct groups of experts were invited to participate in the EIS, Mediators (n=78) and Researchers (n=41). The Mediator interviews prioritized the importance of integrity for public trust in science, while the Research interviews prioritized the importance of integration. A distinct interview instrument was prepared for the two types of experts. Despite their emphases on a particular dimension each, both interview instruments were also designed to cover the entirety of the 3i4T model.

All partners were able to implement the research protocol and, where necessary, adapt it to local realities in order to obtain what we consider to be unprecedented qualitative data. This Global Report is based on the National Reports produced by each POIESIS partner and does not represent a separate analysis of individual interview transcripts. Rather, D2.3 synthesizes and summarizes information that is itself a synthesis and summary of each set of interviews at the national level.

In the following step of T2.3, national partners will provide English language translations of the transcripts of their interviews to the Task Lead (CSIC). Work on scientific outputs will then commence using this set of 119 interview transcripts. The National Report template designed for Task 2.3 restricted to some extent the possibility for partners to analyze their interviews in full. It can therefore be anticipated that additional results and themes of interest will emerge from the EIS dataset, once it is analyzed without project reporting objectives as the primary focus.

This Global Report presents material from the National Reports from the seven POIESIS partners. It does not completely capture the insights of these Reports, which should be read in conjunction with the various sections of this Global Report. In terms of results and findings, it is also not the intention to further interpret the results of the synthesis presented in the preceding chapters. Rather a set of global level findings based on the 3i4T model and the three main assumptions being investigated by the EIS.

Research ethics and integrity issues in the conduct of science are not considered to have a significant impact on public trust in science.

Mediators viewed the emergence of scientific misconduct in the public domain as a key responsibility, particularly science journalists.

Researchers are rarely confronted by citizens with concerns about scientific misconduct; they doubt the reporting of fraud or other scandals has an important effect on their standing with citizens as a trustworthy profession.

Mediators and Researchers both argued that the revelation of scandals in the public domain improves citizens' perceptions of transparency and notions that 'the system' has the internal mechanisms necessary to 'fix itself'.

Mediators and researchers agree that trust in science is uneven across the population and linked to different information channels.

Mediators and Researchers in France and the UK were more convinced that a strong level of public concern about scientific misconduct exists. In the UK case, this was not viewed to signal a general decline in the trustworthiness of scientists.

The further **integration of citizens** in science is viewed as making potentially important contribution to maintaining and reinforcing public trust in science.

Mediators consider that without an underlying degree of public interest and trust in science then they have no base audience. Integration measures that increase this scope of the public that has an opportunity to develop and interest and deepen their trust in science enlarges the audience for science communication and opens potentially new channels for Mediators to interact directly with citizens.

Researchers believe that creating opportunities for integrating citizens in science can improve public understanding of the uncertainty and lack of consensus that characterizes phases of scientific work and discovery. Researchers believe strongly that there are limits to the appropriateness and efficacy of citizen integration and that the specific research context must always be taken into account.

Perceptions of the **importance of institutions** in promoting public trust in science were strong and multi-dimensional. It was also evident from participants that general levels of trust in authorities and public institutions vary between countries and have specific cultural and historical contours, which can affect trust in science.

Mediators advocated greater investment in educational reform, scientific literacy campaigns, and public infrastructures designed to raise the capacities and opportunities of citizens to engage with scientific culture and work. For Mediators these investments would in turn improve the possibility of a science communication that is interesting and informative, but discerning and critical.

Researchers were particularly concerned about the mismatch between current research career and evaluation systems and the lack of incentives, training, recognition, and rewards for dedicating time and resources to science communication and dissemination, or to public engagement work or citizen science.

Science communication was argued by participants to have undergone an extreme 'stress-test' in the COVID-19 pandemic. The confluence of high uncertainty, the increased reliance on social media during 'lockdowns', and a general public in fear for the future of their

'way of life' placed Mediators and Researchers under pressure to communicate amidst a chaotic churn of 'fake news', deliberate and malicious misinformation, and ill-informed speculation.

Mediators and Researchers agreed that 'follow the science' is not a viable communication strategy to safeguard public trust in times of crisis.

Mediators understand their communication role as reflexive, they are invested in supporting scientific culture, but also aware of the importance of adopting a critical and independent perspective. They also articulate the need for this reflexivity to include a critical perspective on the integrity of the science communication sector itself if public trust in their own work is to be improved.

Mediators were also strongly of the opinion that not all scientists should endeavour to communicate science if public trust is the goal. Mediators themselves try to work selectively with researchers that have the necessary capabilities.

Researchers express a willingness to engage with the public through science communication and dissemination work. However, they doubt their efforts will impact public trust without a more systematic and well-resourced approach to communication at the organizational level.

Viewed from the perspective of **chains of mediation**, integrity on the one hand functions as translation of the credibility of information sources and providers. On the other hand, interpersonal networks that stretch from science to society, and across professional communities of practice in science and media, are particularly important for translating trustworthiness.

Increasing **participative structures, mechanisms, and opportunities** across chains of mediation - from the lab to the street - can create a patchwork of citizen integration that can build a culture of public trust. But there are limits, in context sensitivity and in scale, that mean social integration cannot substitute for a sound, well-resourced, societal-level institutional communication strategy, but can complement and enhance such a strategy.

Institutional Mediators tend to operate in more stable and routinized chains of mediation in which other mediators are often their primary audience. Non-institutional Mediators tend to operate with more flexibility about topic choice and have more freedom to identify an angle to interest their primary audience the general public.

Mediators described **differences between the case contexts of climate change and COVID-19**. In climate change, Mediators perceive that the

public considers the scientific evidence is strong and a consensus exist - while appreciating that the socio-political context remains volatile. In COVID-19, Mediators believe the public perceived that both the evidence base and the scientific consensus were fragile, and that results may be unverified or even manipulated by interest groups. This meant the entire communication space around COVID-19 was for a time purely a contest over values and beliefs, which became virulent on some social media platforms.

Institutional and other **variations between national contexts** are treated at a summary level in this Global Report. Attention is drawn mainly to the differences in national levels of trust in institutions and the degree of public concern about science. More nuanced and informed perspective on these differences can obviously be reached through a comparative cross-reading of the National Reports.

Finally, although a deeper analysis is required the EIS appears to have produced findings that are **relatively consistent with previous POIESIS empirical studies**, the public consultation (D2.2) and the institutional focus groups (D3.2). Issues of *research ethics and integrity* in the conduct of scientific research were not linked to changes in levels of public trust by either Mediators or Researchers. Public trust was not considered to be in crisis by either group of participants, although perceptions of growing or high concern did emerge, more so in some POIESIS countries than others. This was also consistent with previous results. *Citizen integration* was viewed positively, but only with limitations and some moderating of expectations - again this initial and provisional assessment appears consistent on the surface. Lastly, the need for *greater institutional development, support, and strategy* - both in terms of policies and investments of resources - does appear emerge as a consistent finding between the institutional focus groups and the EIS.

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APPENDICES

(Attached as separate documents)

1. EIS Protocol
2. EIS Interviewer Guide
3. Joint Data Controller Agreement
4. National Reports
 - a. Denmark
 - b. France
 - c. Germany
 - d. Greece
 - e. Portugal
 - f. Spain
 - g. United Kingdom

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TRUST IN SCIENCE

D.2.3: Expert Interviews - *Appendices*

Author(s): Richard Woolley, Irene Monsonís Payá (CSIC)

Reviewer(s):

Editor(s):

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

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T2.3: Protocol for expert interviews

Author(s): Irene Monsonís-Payá (CSIC) and Richard Woolley (CSIC)

Reviewer(s):

Editor(s):

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *n/a*

Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101057253
Project Acronym:	POIESIS
Project Title:	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science
Title of Deliverable:	T2.3: Protocol for expert interviews
Work Package:	WP2
Due date according to contract:	
Actual delivery date:	
Author(s):	Irene Monsonís-Payá (CSIC) Richard Woolley (CSIC)
Reviewer(s):	
Editor(s):	

ABSTRACT:	
Keyword List:	

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Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	28-12-2023	Irene Monsonís-Payá and Richard Woolley	Draft for ethics approval and sharing with Coordinator (Aarhus)
0.2	06-02-2024	Irene Monsonís-Payá and Richard Woolley	Incorporation of comments and suggestions from the Coordinator
1.0	20-02-2024	Irene Monsonís-Payá and Richard Woolley	Clean version for circulation to Consortium
2.0	29-03-2024	Irene Monsonís-Payá and Richard Woolley	Revised Version with updated Timetable and Appendices
2.1	15-04-2024	Irene Monsonís-Payá and Richard Woolley	QC added, final versions of Appendices attached
3.0	29-04-2024	Irene Monsonís-Payá and Richard Woolley	Incorporation of comments and suggestions by partners

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1 Introduction

The POIESIS project seeks to carry out a series of research activities to “systematically examine the interrelatedness of integrity, integration, and trust, and the role of institutions in fostering a research climate that is conducive to societal trust in science” (POIESIS Project Proposal, 2021:2). The project will answer its main objective through four research questions:

- RQ1: How can the nature and scale of public trust and mistrust in science be characterised and which are the factors that affect the relationship?
- RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research *integrity* (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?
- RQ3: To what extent and how does the *integration* of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?
- RQ4: To what extent and how can *institutions* provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that are conducive to public trust in science?

The research plan of the POIESIS project includes a combination of analysis of primary and secondary data to respond to the different research questions and provide policy recommendations to enhance citizen trust in scientific knowledge production. Data collection includes several research activities in Work Packages 1 to 3 (Figure 1):

- In Work Package 1, secondary data on public opinion and trust is collected about the two topical areas of the project, Covid-19 and climate change. WP1 address RQ1.
- In Work Package 2 case studies are conducted to obtain primary data on the relatedness of integrity and integration and public trust with a focus on the chains of mediation between science and citizens. WP2 address RQ2 and RQ3.
- Work Package 3 examines how institutions can contribute to shaping research practices and citizen trust through a series of participatory research activities. WP3 also address RQ2 and RQ3, and RQ4.

The POIESIS project explores the role of a variety of actors who play the role of third-party mediators between researchers and publics on two topical areas: the Covid-19 pandemic and the science related to climate change. These topical focus areas were selected as both resemble each other in multiple facets, allowing comparison across cases but these two topical areas differ in other aspects, allowing for wider coverage and assessment of generalizability.

<i>Resemblances</i>	<i>Dissimilarities</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Both are timely and of continuous importance to a sizable set of stakeholders</i> 2. <i>They saw integrity issues emerging and entering the public debate (e.g. the hydroxychloroquine and 'climategate' cases)</i> 3. <i>The way in which data and research findings have been communicated to the public has (seemingly) had great influence on public perceptions of science for both areas.</i> 4. <i>Both are related to a wide set of academic disciplines.</i> 5. <i>Both have triggered novel discussions regarding Open Science and have, among others, led to a significant increase of data sharing, the establishment and uptake of open data and article repositories, and the use of open access publishing models.</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Climate science has consistently been part of Eurobarometers and other data streams regarding public trust in science for a considerable duration, thereby providing the opportunity to trace historical trends. Pandemic related research is obviously recent, thereby allowing us to answer questions about how newly emerging themes either follow traditional patterns of mediation or create their own dynamics and chains of mediation.</i> 2. <i>Climate science has been fairly well institutionalized, among others reflected in the establishment of dedicated research centres, journals, and conferences. Again owing to its novelty, Covid-19 research is only currently going through this process of institutionalisation, thereby allowing us to study how this process affects and is affected by public trust in science.</i>

Interviews will be conducted in all POIESIS partner countries with academics and mediators with working knowledge and expertise related to either Covid-19 or climate change.

Figure 1: Data collection activities for POIESIS

This document sets out a guide for the conduct of the experts' interviews in Work Package 2 corresponding to task 2.3 of the project. The document contains the following elements:

- an overview of task 2.3 “Expert interviews”;
- a description of the study objectives and research questions
- study definitions;
- a description of the process for selecting and inviting experts;
- ethics approval;
- the expert interview instrument/guide for semi-structured interviews;
- a reporting template; and
- data processing procedures.

2 Task 2.3: Expert interviews

Task 2.3 “Expert interviews” is part of work package 2 “Small case-studies”, led by ISCTE and which main objective is “to conduct a series of small case studies based on consultative and deliberative actions to examine how practices of integrity and integration affect public trust in science with a focus on the chains of mediation between science and citizens, and to share results and recommendations” (POIESIS Project Proposal, 2021:33 Part B). In POIESIS, a chain of mediation is understood as a complex translation process. Analytically a chain of mediation can be understood as starting from knowledge production activities and the actors developing research practices on the work floor. Outputs of knowledge production can then move through a series of actors who transforming the informational form and content as it passes from one context to another.

Task 2.3 is led by CSIC and involves all project partners. The task is planned to start in August 2023 and end in February 2025 (month 12 to 30). The description of the task in the project proposal is as follow:

Box 1: Description of task 2.3 in the POIESIS proposal

Task 2.3: Expert interviews (CSIC lead, supported by all partners; M12-M30)

This task will involve interviews with mediators, academic experts, and researchers, and will be informed by the results of the public consultations. These expert interviews will be individual interviews with a sample of mediators for each topical area (16 interviews per country, 112 interviews in the consortium). This task will involve:

- Selection/Invitation of interviewees; this will be done by national teams, in collaboration with the Permanent Recruitment and Engagement Working Group.
- Preparation of the interview guide. This will be led by CSIC and the WP leader in close cooperation with all partners.
- Interviews will be conducted in each country by POIESIS partners. All interviews will be audio recorded, then transcribed and translated into English for comparative purposes.
- Analysis will include comparative elements and will focus on understanding how the chains of mediation through which responsible and irresponsible practices are conveyed may affect citizen trust in science.

The Expert Interviews will be semi-structured interviews conducted in person or online. Each interview is planned to take approximately 45 minutes. Introducing the interviews, and reciting Ethics conditions for the study before and after the interview means approximately one hour will be needed for the interaction between the interviewer and the participant. There are two groups of interviewees 'Mediators' and 'Researchers' and the interview instruments are different for each of these groups. Questions will focus on

identifying the roles and activities of the interviewee in translating scientific information to public audiences of different types. Each interview will be recorded, transcribed, and translated into English.

Preliminary categories of categorical information (e.g. job title, organisation type, etc.) that will be collected are described in the Pre-coding Scheme appendix to this Protocol. Following initial Pilot Interviews, the Pre-coding Scheme will be revisited and amended as necessary. The data collected will also take the form of descriptive passages and quotes that provide discursive responses to interview questions. Initial thematic codes will be provided in the Pre-Coding Scheme for use in analysing this discursive data. Additional codes can be created by individual coders as required and will be added to the pre-coding to form a final codebook for the interview analyses.

Each national team will write a National Report based on a template provided by the Task Leaders (CSIC). The various National Reports will be used as the basis for a comparative analysis and a summary report written by CSIC. The main output of the task, Deliverable 2.3 “Results from expert interviews” will be publicly available in August 2024.

2.1 About this protocol

As the first task of Work Package 2, the main characteristics of the process for conducting the expert interviews and the recruitment strategy were defined and included in Deliverable 2.1 "Protocol for empirical case studies" (Entradas et al., 2022).

This Protocol for Task 2.3 of POIESIS is provided by CSIC to the project partners to summarize and provide the necessary information to carry out the Expert Interviews. The document will also be submitted as part of the ethics approval process for the Expert Interviews in POIESIS, through the Ethics Committee of CSIC (the Spanish National Research Council). Updated versions of the Protocol will be provided to the Ethics body approving the study should significant modifications be required during the study process.

The Protocol (including any updated versions) will be made openly available, as with other POIESIS research protocols submitted as formal Deliverables under the POIESIS project Grant Agreement.

The document includes inputs from D2.1 and from the project meetings held by the POIESIS consortium to date. The Protocol draft will be shared among the project partners to enable discussion of its content at the Lisbon Consortium Meeting (February 2024) and subsequent revision and validation of a collectively agreed version.

2.2 Chronogram of internal activities

The completion of Task 2.3 and D2.3 requires a series of activities to be undertaken:

- Drafts of the Interview Instruments for Mediators and Researchers prepared and shared for comment with Coordinator and WP Leader

- Revision of draft based on initial comments
- Drafting of Pre-coding Scheme and Template for National Reports
- First version of the Protocol and the Interview Instruments shared with Consortium and revised following discussion at Lisbon meeting (Feb 2024)
- Piloting the interview instrument
- Revision of the Pre-coding Scheme for analysing interviews
- Revision of Template for National Reports
- Online training session for the researchers developing the interviews on the content of the protocol and instruments.
- Conduct of 16 interviews in each country
- Transcriptions and translation into English of the interviews. Writing of the national reports in English following using the template supplied (national partners).
- Writing of the comparative report resulting in D2.3 (CSIC).
- Dissemination and communication activities such as writing of a scientific paper and presenting the results at scientific conferences.

Table 1 summarizes the internal milestones of task 2.3, the projects responsible, and the expected date for completion.

Table 1: Dates and responsibilities for internal milestones in task 2.3

Month	Project Month	Milestone	Responsible
November – December (2023)	16	Draft Protocol/Guide for Expert Interviews - Materials (informed consent, information sheet, interview instrument) -Ethics approval -Joint data control agreement	CSIC
January (2024)	17	Feedback on First draft	Aarhus, ISCTE
February	18	Version 1 of Protocol and Interviews for discussion (Lisbon)	CSIC, All
March	19	Revision of Protocol & desing of National Report template	CSIC
April	20	Piloting and revision interviews	CSIC, AU
April	20	Final Protocol and Interview	CSIC
April	20	Online training for interviewers	CSIC
May - June	20-22	Interviews conducted	Each partner
July	23	National Report in English	Each partner
August	24	Synthesis Report Deliverable 2.3	CSIC
September	25	Translation of the interviews into English	Each partner
April (2025)	32	Draft scientific article	CSIC lead

3 Study objectives

The expert interviews are designed to contribute to the general objectives of WP2: examining how practices of integrity and integration affect public trust in science with a focus on the chains of mediation between science and citizens, and sharing results and recommendations.

The research questions on which work package 2 pivots are the following:

- RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?
- RQ3: To what extent and how does the *integration* of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?

In addition, the project aims to answer two research sub-questions in Work Package 2:

- How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the publics' trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?
- What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

The specific objective of task 2.3 Expert interviews is to understand in deeper detail the views of the 'supply' side on how (ir)responsible research practices can best be communicated and how that might affect public trust in science.

With these considerations in mind, the specific research questions for the in-depth interviews are presented in the following sub-section.

3.1 Research questions

The research questions of the expert interviews are:

- Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?
- How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science?
 - i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?

- What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

4 Study definitions

The expert interviews seek to “study the **chains of mediation** that connect research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of these by wider publics. We will examine the **actors that play prominent roles in such chains**, to understand what their roles comprise, and how communication practices may be improved to foster public trust in science.” (POIESIS Project Proposal, 2021:8 Part B).

Figure 2: Chain of mediation: a translation process

In the context of task 2.3, a chain of mediation can be visualised as a translation process starting from knowledge production and the actors developing research practices on the work floor, moving through a series of actors (n=x) transforming that information as it passes from one context to another.

A chain of mediation can be developed in multiple ways:

- Traditional linear chain of mediation.** A chain of mediation could follow a traditional linear chain’s structure: knowledge is translated into the form of scientific dissemination practices whose results will be transformed back through institutional science communication services to reach the press and finally the public.

Figure 3: Traditional linear chain of mediation

- Traditional quasi-linear chains of mediation.** Another possibility following a quasi-linear traditional chain of mediation could be that the knowledge is transferred both from the laboratory to the publishers and to the institutional press offices, but the latter not only translates information from the laboratory but also from the publishers (Figure 4). In a similar way, the knowledge from the laboratory could be directly translated by the media (Figure 5). Thus, the translation chain incorporates complexity as multiple translations can occur among different mediators in the chain.

Figure 4: Quasi-linear traditional chain of mediation (I)

Figure 5: Quasi-linear traditional chain of mediation (II)

- Disruptive chains of mediation.** Finally, we could find chains of mediation where mediators in the traditional chains of mediators are mixed with disruptors of the chain (other content creators -such as bloggers or podders- that both create new paths and impact in the traditional model (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Disruptive chain of mediation

These models represent our initial 'ideal-type' expectations about some possible configurations of chains of mediation. Actual empirical configurations are likely to be more diverse and there are potentially a wide variety of chains of mediation linking research ethics and integrity (REI) and societal integration practices in science to the public. These models also provide an initial reference point for the possibility of asking participants in 'mediator' interviews to draw diagrammatically how they see their own position in translation and communication of science and of REI practices.

These ideal-types are simple schematics for visualising sequences of actors through which translation processes may operate. These sequences follow a simplistic linear logic that are not meant as representations of actual chains of mediation, which are likely to be far more messy and involve information flows in multiple directions. The interviews will allow participants to describe the complex information ecosystems in which they work and how they understand, interpret, and act in them. In this sense, the schematics shown are intended only as initial sense-making tools for developing a shared understanding among POIESIS interviewers.

Table 2 summarises elements that fall within our definition of chains of mediation.

Table 2: Definition of elements within chains of mediation

Element	Definition
Audience	The intended recipient of a mediating actor’s output
Chains of mediation	Networks of actors, activities, and sequences of practices that connect research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of scientific research by the wider publics.
Channels	TV, newspapers, blogs, social media (Facebook, Twitter, Twitter/X, chat apps (WhatsApp/Telegram/Signal), face-to-face events/`event-makers
Intermediary	A node in the translation process that does not transform the object/output
Mediating actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional: Science communication officer working at publishers and universities • Non-institutional: Science writers, journalists and authors of science-related blogs and podcasts, and other content creators (disruptive content creators)
Mediator	A node in the translation process that contributes to transforming the object/output
Objects/outputs	Press release, Web, Blog, Article
Publics	Citizens, CSOs, social groups, clubs, etc.
R&I institutional actors	Universities, research institutes, publishers, research funders, foundations, private companies that perform R&I
Translation	Moving something from one context to another while changing it from one form to another

5 Participant selection and invitation

We will interview researchers and mediators and the selection criteria will combine a topical and process approach:

- The researchers will be topical experts in climate change and COVID-19, actively involved in studying and communicating about the content of these topical areas.
- The mediators will be professionals communicating science, but no one will be excluded by topical area. This means that mediators could be specialised in communicating climate change and COVID-19, or not. This will hence be social scientists / communication scientists and mediators reporting on a more meta-level.

Project partners will be responsible for contacting and engaging the experts, with the support of NTUA. To ensure the best selection of participants, partners will work with NTUA and the task leader (CSIC) to try and ensure the best possible approximation of the types of mediator and researcher roles foreseen in the study design. If, for practical reasons, certain criteria such as gender, cannot be met on a national level, it will be the responsibility of the task leader to ensure – at the overall project level - that this discrepancy will be compensated for in terms of the general sampling and recruitment strategy of the study. An effort will be made to recruit participants at national and project level that form a sample that is balanced in terms of gender, age, education, and social status wherever possible.

At national level the proposed selection of experts includes the following distribution of profiles (Table 3). Partners will focus on national recruitment, however, the inclusion of 'international' participants on the basis of their expertise and value-added for the project will also be possible.

Table 3: Participant profiles

Type of expert	Profile and number of experts
Researchers (6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers on climate change (3, including 1 SSH) • Researchers on COVID-19 (3, including 1 SSH)
Institutional mediators (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional science communicators working at publishers (0 or 1) – (might be allocated at the project level) • Institutional science communicators working at universities and research institutes (1 or 2)
Non-institutional mediators (8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional science writers: authors of popular books or other content (minimum 1) • Science journalists: major print, television, radio, magazines, etc. (minimum 1) • Authors of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. (minimum 1) • Other content creators (including disruptors, both ‘contrarian’ and ‘activist’ who use scientific research in relation to our cases) (minimum 1)

6 Ethics and research data management

This protocol and its appendices were submitted to the CSIC Ethics Committee as part of the ethics approval process for Task 2.3 of POIESIS.

As part of the study ethics approval process, project partners will be asked to sign a form confirming they have read and will comply with the Ethics requirements established in this Protocol. The compliance form is attached as APPENDIX A. Poiesis Partners ethics compliance form.

POIESIS partners in some countries may also need to notify relevant authorities of their intention to conduct research and that an ethics approval has been obtained from the CSIC Ethics Committee. It is the responsibility of POIESIS to notify the appropriate ethics institution or organisation in their countries if required.

A reference to the ethics approval information is included in the information sheet and informed consent form for participants. An informed consent must be signed by each participant. Without a signed consent form data collected cannot be used.

6.1 Ethics approval by the Ethics Committee of the CSIC

The procedure established by the Ethics Committee of the CSIC involves the following steps that were followed by INGENIO:

1. In order to initiate the ethical evaluation of the research, the investigator in charge of the research submitted the following documentation:
 - a. The Assessment Request Form, duly completed and signed, to the CSIC Ethics Committee. Research involving human subjects, samples, and/or human data (as the POIESIS project), requires filling in the data referring to the research and the researcher(s) researcher/s and answering all the questions formulated in section A of the application document.
 - b. Information sheet for participants (Appendix B)
 - c. Informed consent (Appendix C)
2. The applicant may be contacted to request further information and/or additional documentation, or to make changes to the submitted documentation.

The ethics approval application for Task 2.3 of POIESIS was submitted in December 2023. An ethics approval was received from the CSIC Ethics Committee with the approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2023). This information should be included on the information sheet and informed consented form provided to interview participants by national partners.

6.2 Data handling and management

The data resulting from the experts' interviews should be treated following the guidelines provided in the Data Management Plan of the POIESIS project (Ravn & Horbach, 2023). In this section, we will highlight the key elements of data handling and management to be considered when conducting the expert interviews.

6.2.1 Type of data collected

In Task 2.3 each national team will conduct 16 expert interviews. Therefore, general personal data (non-sensitive personal data) will be collected and stored. The identity of participants will be blinded at the earliest possible moment in the processing of the interview files. An encrypted file storing the identities of participants and linking these to the Code Identifiers (e.g. PT Cov-1, DK CC-2) will be stored securely by each national team. The precise metadata required and formatting of Code Identifiers and Interview transcript files will be specified in the National Report Template.

Signed informed consent forms will be treated confidentially by each national partner. The signed consent forms will be stored securely by each national partner in a local dedicated institutional repository.

Following the Data Management Plan of the POIESIS project (Ravn & Horbach, 2023:10), the qualitative data collected will be pseudonymised, this means that all directly identifying information from the interviews will be removed. Only national project partners collecting data through interviews will be able to reverse pseudonymisation (to identify interviewees in their national studies with the content of the interviews). Therefore, the interviewees will be preserved in all published materials from the study.

The interviews will be recorded, transcribed, and translated into English. The original recording and transcription in the original language will allow the partners to analyze the content of the interviews following a thematic analysis approach (using NVivo). The goal is to identify patterns, themes, and sub-themes that emerge from scientists' and mediators' conversations about public trust.

6.2.2 Data security: processing, sharing, and storage of data

The **original recordings and transcriptions of interviews** will be processed separately by each national project partner and safely stored through approved institutional facilities of the nationally responsible project partner. Direct quotes from the interview can be included in the descriptive-analytical summary of the interview(s). However, these should be avoided where the identity of the interviewee would be revealed. Once deliverable 2.3 has been approved, audio recordings and transcripts in the original language should be destroyed 5 years after the last publication of the expert interviews study, following the coordinator's (Aarhus University) Policy (Ravn & Horbach, 2023:19).

Prior to data collection commencing in the project, the research team will engage in a process to develop conventions for file labelling and file storage. This will be documented and will ensure coherence and shared understanding among the research team with respect to formats and standards for storing data. File labelling protocols will include Month, year and type information, along with pseudonym information for interview transcripts.

The **translated transcription** will be pseudonymised by the respective project partner and processed through qualitative analysis software (Nvivo). The translated transcription and analysis undertaken through Nvivo will be shared with the CSIC to elaborate on the final deliverable of the task. Data sharing will be done through the SharePoint used in the project POIESIS which is a secure web-based solution with Two-factor authentication (Ravn & Horbach, 2023:19). Transcriptions will be produced through Microsoft Office software (Ravn & Horbach, 2023:10). The translated transcription will be stored securely in SharePoint by the respective project partner and INGENIO, in order to analyze and describe the overall results of the Expert Interviews, which will result in Deliverable D2.3 of the project. After a period of five years after the last publication, the translated transcriptions will be destroyed.

Each partner will then produce a short report summarising the main findings. The whole corpus will then serve for comparative analysis across the involved countries, coordinated by CSIC in D2.3. The **reports** generated by each project partner will be sent by email to CSIC and uploaded to the SharePoint platform. It will be the responsibility of each project partner and the POIESIS consortium in general, to ensure that any direct quote included in the reports that is used in subsequent project outputs does not reveal the identity of the expert/interviewee concerned.

A Joint Data Control Agreement will be signed by the project partners containing comprehensive information about data security, handling, and use (APPENDIX D. Joint Data Control Agreement).

7 National reporting and coding strategy

The National Report template and codebook will be prepared by CSIC. Revision and validation of both will involve discussion and opportunity to provide comments and feedback involving all partners. The template will contain two parts: Part A reporting on the Mediator interviews; and Part B reporting on the Research interviews.

Informal support sessions will be conducted by CSIC online at the end of May to review progress in interviewing with all partners. A second informal meeting will discuss the National Report writing process and ensure a common understanding of the instructions contained in the template.

Each National Report will include:

- Introduction and participants
- Categorial data collection
- Discursive thematic data summaries
- Analytical summary
- Policy recommendations

National Reports will not require any formal comparison or synthesis of the two distinct interview series. However, the analytical summary will invite reflections on results of the Expert Interview study as a whole.

8 Quality control

A simple quality control process will be used to support POIESIS partners prepare their National Reports. The complete draft of each report will be shared with one other partner prior to the final deadline for submitting each report to the Task Lead (CSIC). Partners will be required to read the draft report and comment on its development and identify any areas for suggested changes or improvements. This process will also allow each partner to identify areas in which their own draft report might be improved. It will be the responsibility of each partner to respond to the comments received as they consider best.

APPENDIX A. Poiesis Partners ethics compliance form

Please return the signed form to:

Dr Richard Woolley
Coordinator, Task 2.3 of the POIESIS project
INGENIO (CSIC-UPV)
ricwoo@ingenio.upv.es

POIESIS Expert Interviews

Confirmation of compliance with the Study's Ethics Declaration

I, the undersigned [], hereby confirm to have received, read, and understood the ethics and data management requirements presented in the Protocol for Experts Interviews of the POIESIS project. When conducting the expert interviews' study in my role as project partner of the POIESIS project, I will diligently adhere to the principles outlined in the Protocol, particularly with regard to obtaining written informed consent of the interviewees, data protection, data management, and data handling. To this end, I confirm to have received the Protocol for the Expert Interviews, the POIESIS Data Management Plan (D5.2), the support material to obtain informed consent and information on Data Protection Compliance. In case unforeseen ethical issues arise during the study process, I will immediately inform the Study Lead and the Coordinator, and collaborate closely with them to resolve any such issue.

Place and date

Signature

Project Partner

An ethics approval for this research was received from the CSIC Ethics Committee with the approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2023).

APPENDIX B. Informed consent form

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

EXPERT INTERVIEWS STUDY (T2.3)

Project title:	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science – POIESIS
Funding organization:	European Commission, Horizon Europe (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01)
Responsible researchers:	[Name, role of the responsible researcher]
Organization:	[Name of the organization]
Phone number:	[Phone number]
E-mail:	[Email]

I _____, with ID _____ [Replace with the relevant information for your country]:

DECLARE that I have read the Participant Information Sheet on the Expert Interviews Study, of which I have been given a copy, that I have been given sufficient time, that I have been given the opportunity to ask questions and that I have received sufficient information from the researcher, _____, who has explained to me the conditions of my participation in this research in an appropriate manner. I have also been assured of the confidential treatment of my data.

I further declare that I understand that my participation is voluntary, so I can freely withdraw from the research and revoke my consent, at any time, and for any reason.

- I GIVE my consent to participate in the proposed research.
- I DO NOT give my consent to participate in the proposed research.

I sign in duplicate and will keep a copy:

Date and signature of participant

I _____, researcher responsible for obtaining this informed consent, with ID _____ [Replace by the relevant information in your country]:

DECLARE that I have explained the characteristics and scope of the research to the participant, taking into account his/her capabilities, and I have informed him/her of the potential risks and direct benefits derived from the same.

Date and signature of the person responsible for obtaining informed consent.

An ethics approval for this research was received from the CSIC Ethics Committee with the approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2024).

APPENDIX C. Participant information sheet. Expert Interviews (T2.3)

INFORMATION SHEET FOR PARTICIPANTS

EXPERT INTERVIEWS STUDY (T2.3)

Project title:	Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science – POIESIS
Funding organization:	European Commission, Horizon Europe (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01)
Responsible researchers:	[Name, role of the responsible researcher]
Organization:	[Name of the organization]
Phone number:	[Phone number]
E-mail:	[Email]

I. Introduction

This information sheet is given to you as a participant in the Expert Interviews Study in the framework of the POIESIS project (Task 2.3). You are invited to participate in this activity voluntarily and are kindly requested to read this information sheet carefully and to ask any questions you may have. The ethical aspects of the research have been assessed and approved by the CSIC Ethics Committee.

II. General outline of the Project

The POIESIS project aims to study the relationship between trust, science, and research integrity and integration practices in a world where there is an increasing need for clear and open scientific information. We will run a series of events involving different actors including scientific experts and members of the public. One of these activities is semi-structured interviews to discuss and collect expert opinions on the role of science communication, scientific integrity, trust in science and scientific institutions, and public communication of science.

POIESIS is a consortium project. The project is coordinated by the University of Aarhus (Denmark) and involves the following partners: London School of Economics and Political Science (UK), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Germany), National Technical University of Athens (Greece), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (France), Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal) and CSIC- Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spain).

POIESIS is being implemented in **Spain** under the leadership of **Richard Woolley, researcher at INGENIO (CSIC-UPV) - Institute for Innovation and Knowledge Management**.

Your participation in the study is very valuable as it will contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field of science. Specifically, your participation will contribute to understanding how research practices are transferred to the public through different types of communication. You will be interviewed by trained researchers, who will conduct a semi-structured interview about your professional role, the procedures and sources of information you use in your work, your experience in science communication, and how you manage issues of integration and integrity.

III. Nature of your participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary and you may choose to participate or not.

Should you agree to participate, the interview will be audio-recorded for the exclusive use of the research team. The recordings will not be shared on any public platform. Participants may end their participation at any time during the interview. They may also request the deletion of their data by a simple request to the study coordinator in your country [Name and email of the responsible researcher]. However, pseudonymised data that has already been published cannot be deleted.

The experts who will participate in the interviews have been selected on the basis of their professional expertise and experience. Sixteen experts will be interviewed in each country, for a total of 112 interviewees.

IV. Procedures and information relating to the data obtained in the interview

You will participate in a semi-structured interview of approximately 45 minutes to one hour duration. The interviews will take place in the period May to June 2024 in the seven POIESIS partner countries.

The interview will be audio-recorded for transcription, translation into English, and analysis of the content, which will be used for research purposes only. The interview will be pseudonymised before transcription and translation. Pseudonymisation will be carried out by the project partner responsible for conducting the interviews in your country, [Name of the project partner]. Please take care not to mention any confidential or defamatory information during the interview.

Data management procedures will be in accordance with the European Union (EU) general data protection regulation (GDPR) and with the joint data management agreement (JDCA) managed by INGENIO (CSIC-UPV) as lead partner of Task 2.3, and signed by the rest of the project partners. Following these protocols, appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented in such a way as to ensure that data processing complies with the requirements of the GDPR and guarantees the protection of the data subject's rights. The data will be stored electronically for five years after publication of the research results.

We intend to share the project findings with all interview participants as soon as possible.

No significant risks associated with participation in the study are foreseen. Thus, no potentially critical ethical implications of the research results on human dignity and integrity, nor on the privacy of individuals, are foreseen. Participants are selected on the basis of their merit and professional positions and no high risks are foreseen in the selection of professional stakeholders for this particular study.

V. Funding of the research

The POIESIS project, Grant Agreement number 101057253, has been funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01).

VI. Team responsibilities and financial compensation for participants

Your participation in this study is strictly confidential. Your personal data will always be processed by authorised personnel subject to the duty of secrecy and confidentiality. INGENIO (CSIC-UPV), as

task coordinator, ensures the use of appropriate technical, organisational and security measures to protect personal information. The entire research team is obliged to maintain the confidentiality of all personal data. Transcripts translated into English of the interviews will be processed by the lead partner of the task, in this case, INGENIO (CSIC-UPV).

One of the project partners is located in the UK, where there is an adequacy decision by the European Commission, and as such, applies protection measures and guarantees your rights in the same way as the European Union.

Your personal data will be kept for five years after the last publication related to the expert interviews, after which time it will be destroyed. The partners of the POIESIS consortium share responsibility for the processing of your personal data which are collected and processed exclusively for the purposes of the study, lawfully based on Article 6 (a) of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). All partners signed a joint Data Controllers Agreement.

The study is coordinated in [Name of your country] by the researcher [Name and email of the responsible researcher], who can be contacted to clarify doubts, share comments or exercise your rights in relation to the processing of your personal data. You can use the contact details above to request access, rectification, deletion or limitation of the processing of your personal data, data portability, or any other rights you may have.

[Name of the project partner] does not disclose or share information related to your personal data with third parties, except when legally required to do so.

Thus, in terms of data protection, we will comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), as well as with [Name of the national legislation in terms of data protection].

Likewise, you are informed that the [Name of the project partner] has a Data Protection Officer, who is [Name, email, contact data of the Data Protection Delegate in the project partner organization].

Participants will be reimbursed for any travel expenses arising from their participation in the interview.

VII. More information

As a participant in this study, you have the right to clarify any doubts you may have at any time and to request more detailed information about the research. To do so, you can contact the study coordinator in [Name of the country]: [Name and email of the responsible researcher].

For more information on the project, please visit the following website: www.poiesis.eu.

If all your doubts have been clarified and you have the conviction to participate in this study, you can sign the Informed Consent form.

An ethics approval for this research was received from the CSIC Ethics Committee with the approval number 300/2023 (6 February 2024).

APPENDIX D. Joint Data Control Agreement

Attached as a separate file.

APPENDIX E. Interview instrument: Mediators

Research interview instrument for mediators

A. Introduction

- Short presentation/recap of interview objectives
- Information about management of interviewee's personal data, informed consent

Format of the interview: This interview has five short sections. The first two sections (six questions) are designed to collect some basic information about your role in communicating about science. I would ask you to provide quite short, direct answers to these questions.

In the following three sections (total of nine questions) there will be opportunities for fuller responses and discussion.

If you are ready I will now start recording, and then begin the recording by asking if you agree that we record the interview.

B. Background

1. What is your occupation and/or professional role?
2. (*If applicable*) Could you also describe your employer organization and its main purposes or objectives?

C. Activities and audiences

3. What are the main activities that you carry out in your science communication work?
 - Prompt: what are the main outputs or products of your work?
4. What are the main channels through which you publish or promote your work?
5. How would you describe your target audience?
 - Prompt: Audience demographics (age, education)? A more traditional 'boomer' audience or the 'instatoktube' social media generation? Mix?
 - Prompt: What is the size/scale of this audience (e.g. viewers, followers, etc.)?
6. How do you interact with citizens (and/or target audience) as part of your work?
 - Prompt: Through events (e.g. science café, public fora, etc.) or continuous (e.g. comments section after online articles, social media etc.)
 - Prompt: Mainly face-to-face or online?

- Prompt: Do you consider your work highly interactive or more traditional broadcast/publishing in style?

Thank you for providing all this information. We will now move to some more open questions, starting with your information sources and how you use them.

D. Sources and translation

7. Could you please describe your professional network and main connections that are essential for you to do your work?

8. What are the main sources of information or inputs for your work?

- Prompt: Scientific articles? Press releases? Network contacts? Etc.
- Prompt: How do you assess the credibility of these inputs?
- Note: Please do not prompt for REI here
- Note: If interviewee mentions REI, fraud, QRPs, or other related topics, explore by asking for (a) concrete example(s) related to their assessment of credible sources

9. Can you describe your core 'creative process'? (possible triggers 'thought process' or 'workflow')

- Prompt: How do you work your 'magic'? ... turning these sources/inputs into the products of your work
- Note: If they are unsure, ask them to describe how they produced a successful or favourite piece of work
- Prompt: If necessary follow up to clarify the inputs/sources used in this example

10. What do you consider success in your work?

- Prompt: How do you assess that? (e.g. self-evaluation, metrics, reviews, etc.)

Thank you for those detailed responses, I would now like to ask you about research integrity and ethics in science.

E. Research ethics and integrity

11. What do you understand by the terms research ethics and integrity? [Hinge question that should be asked in this way whether the interviewee has mentioned REI previously or not]

- Prompt: How are REI issues important for your work?
- Prompt: Can you describe an example in the context of your work on Covid/Climate? (Explore if they have a positive and a negative example)

And finally, I would like to ask some questions about your (professional) perceptions about public trust in science.

F. Public trust in science

12. How would you describe the relationship between your work and public trust in science?

- Prompt: Do they see their work as aiming: to build public trust, to offer a critical perspective, to undermine or debunk science, to promote 'alternatives', etc.

Note: don't ask the following question (Q13) to a disruptor/contrarian interviewee, go to Q14

13. Have you ever felt that news about irresponsible or fraudulent practices in science could negatively affect public confidence in your work?

- Prompt: Do you have have any concrete experience? How did/do you deal with this?

14. From your perspective, what would improve public trust in science?

- Prompt: If possible explore for both REI- and citizen interaction-related suggestions

15. Would you recommend specific ways to improve trust in science among the younger 'social media' generation?

- Prompt: if unsur, probe for how to communicate with them, how to involve them

F. Debriefing

- Additional comments you would like to make us aware of?
- Repetition of agreements (consent etc.)

National partners are free to offer to disseminate study outputs to participants in whatever manner they prefer, provided they make arrangements that respect participants' privacy. National partners also have discretion about whether they provide a national language summary of (national or synthesis) results for participants, or simply make Deliverables (English) available.

APPENDIX F. Interview instrument: Researchers

Research interview instrument for researchers

A. Introduction

- Short presentation/recap of interview objectives
- Information about management of interviewee's personal data, informed consent

Format of the interview: This interview has four sections. The first two sections (four questions) cover your current position and your work in relation to the topic of COVID/Climate Change.

We will then move to questions about citizens connections to research, and finally to questions about public trust in science.

If you are ready I will now start recording, and then begin the recording by asking if you agree that we record the interview.

B. Background

1. What is your current position and professional role(s)?
2. Can you describe your work on the topic of COVID/Climate Change?
 - Prompt: has the public nature of debate and controversy affected your work?

Thankyou. I would like now to ask you about the communication of your work in the area of COVID/Climate Change

C. Case context

3. What are the main ways in which your work on COVID/Climate Change reaches the public?
4. Do you consider your work (or colleagues in your field) is accurately and fairly presented to the public by others (eg. Journalists, social media influencers, publishers, etc.)?
 - Prompt: Any experience of misrepresentation?
 - Prompt: Do you have any strategies to ensure appropriate coverage?

Thanks for those answers. I would like now to move to the topic of citizens' participation in science.

D. Integration of citizens across the research cycle

5. What is your opinion regarding increasing the involvement of citizens in scientific research? (If they are unsure, mention Citizen Science)
 - Prompt: what positives do you see? What negatives?
6. Are citizens involved in, or connected to, your own research?
 - Prompt: Do you organise dissemination, communication, or interactive events with citizens?
 - Prompt: At what stage(s) of the research cycle do you typically involve citizens? (Research cycle stages: Problematization; Research Design; Experiment or Fieldwork etc.; Analysis; Defining results; Dissemination and/or communication)
7. In your experience, what barriers are there to greater participation of citizens in science?
 - Prompt: Institutional or organisational barriers?
 - Prompt: Scientists skills or interest

Ok, thank you again for your responses. I would now like to move to the topic of public trust in science.

E. Public trust in science

8. In your experience, what concerns do citizens express about science?
 - Prompt: Probe for whether citizens express concerns about the conduct of science (fraud, unethical or irresponsible practices) or the outcomes of science (dangerous technologies, negative impacts, etc.)
9. In your opinion, what are the most powerful factors or forces driving citizens' concerns and public distrust of science, especially about Covid/Climate Change?
 - Prompt: Probe for conduct (REI) or context (misinformation, social media, public understanding, etc.)

Finally, taking into account citizens' concerns and the factors affecting distrust you described, I would like you to imagine that you have total freedom to introduce policies that you believe would lead to improved public trust in science

10. What would be your three most important policy priorities?
 - Prompt: if they are unsure, they can make change to how research is conducted (inc. REI), to institutions/organisations, to how science is communicated to the

public, to how citizen's are involved in science, or anything else – seemingly radical or left-field ideas should not be discouraged or excluded

F. Debriefing

- Additional comments you would like to make us aware of?
- Repetition of agreements (consent etc.)

National partners are free to offer to disseminate study outputs to participants in whatever manner they prefer, provided they make arrangements that respect participants' privacy. National partners also have discretion about whether they provide a national language summary of (national or synthesis) results for participants, or simply make Deliverables (English) available.

APPENDIX G. POIESIS data processing information sheet

Attached as separate file

REFERENCES

Entradas, M., Ziegler, R., Fuglsang, S., Ravn, T., Horbach, S. P. J. M., & Kavouras, P. (2022).
Deliverable 2.1 - Protocol for the empirical case studies Work Package.

POIESIS project proposal. (2021).

Ravn, T., & Horbach, S. P. J. M. (2023). *D5.2: Data Management Plan.*

Interviewer guide: research instrument for mediators

Section	Content	Rationale	Comments/Reporting info
A. Introduction	Short presentation of interview objectives	All REI, privacy, and data management processes must be adhered to.	<p><i>In questions Q1-Q10 the interviewer doesn't prompt for REI.</i></p> <p><i>If REI issues are mentioned they should be treated as any other theme.</i></p> <p><i>REI will be introduced specifically in Q11.</i></p>
	Information about management of interviewee's personal data		
	Request permission to record interview		
B. Background	1. Could you please describe for me in a few sentences your occupation and professional role?	Brief summary of job/role	Occupation Job title
	2. Could you also describe your organization and its main purposes or objectives?	Brief summary of institutional context	Sector Organisation type Mission of organisation Audience/client base
C. Activities and audiences	3. What are the main activities that you carry out in your science communication work?	This question aims to obtain a brief description of the main activities of the mediator's work.	Tasks Objects (outputs)
	4. What are the main channels through which you publish or promote your work?	This question aims to obtain a brief description of the channels used to share the outputs and products of interviewees work.	Channels
	5. How would you describe your target audience?	This question aims to obtain a brief description of the interviewee's main target audience(s).	Age Education Generation (boomers, digital youth, etc.) Size/scale
	6. How do you interact with citizens (and/or target audience) as part of your work?	This question aims to obtain a brief description of how (if) interviewees interact with the public.	Events Continuous forms of engagement Face-to-face or online, or both

D. Sources and translation	7. Could you please describe your professional network and main connections that are essential for you to do your work?	This question aims to understand where interviewees are positioned in the chains of mediation between science and society, by gaining an overview of their professional relationships.	Network domains: science; publishing; professional associations; media organisations; etc. Formal/informal relations
	8. What are the main sources of information for your work?	This question aims to obtain an overview of the sources and resources used by the interviewee in their professional activities. The prompt aims to understand how interviewees assure themselves of the credibility of the sources they use, (e.g. fact-checking; trust relationships, etc.)	Scientific literature Mainstream media Science press releases – RPOs, Publishers Social media Interpersonal networks with researchers Interpersonal networks with science communicators <i><u>DO NOT</u> prompt for REI. If REI issues are mentioned treat as any other theme. REI will be directly introduced in Q11.</i>
	9. Can you describe your core 'creative process'?	This question aims to understand how mediators transform information.	Inputs/sources used Process Outputs produced
	10. What do you consider as success in your work?	This question aims to understand interviewee's perception of quality work, and how they measure or assess this.	Self-satisfaction Professional peer review (formal or informal) Professional audience metrics User interactions (downloads, reviews, comments, etc.)
E. Research ethics and integrity	11. What do you understand by the terms research ethics and integrity?	This question aims to open a short discussion about REI and its place in their professional work process (if any). HINGE QUESTION	Their understanding of REI How it features in their work Its importance in their work An example (Covid/CC)

F. Public trust in science	12. How would you describe the relationship between your work and public trust in science?	The question aims to understand how they see their work contributing to science-society.	Aims to promote science and innovation Aims to build public trust Aims to inform and/or educate Offers a critical perspective on S&T Seeks to undermine or debunk science Aims to promote alternative views/solutions
	13. In your opinion, how does news about irresponsible or fraudulent practices in science affect public confidence or interest in your work?	This question encourages the interviewee to reflect on how their own work appears in the context of public concerns about science.	Illustrative example
	14. From your perspective, what would improve public trust in science?	This question directly seeks interviewees' <u>recommendations</u> for improving public trust in science.	Media/information channel related Audience related REI related Citizen engagement related Citizen integration related
	15. Would you recommend specific ways to improve trust in science among the younger 'social media' generation?	This question directly seeks interviewees' <u>recommendations</u> for improving public trust in science among younger generation. ONLY ASK IF NOT COVERED IN Q14	Media/information channel related Audience related REI related Citizen engagement related Citizen integration related
G. Debriefing	Additional comments Repetition of agreements (consent, etc.)	Open up for interviewee-initiated comment	

Interviewer guide: research instrument for researchers

Section	Content	Rationale	Comments/Reporting info
A. Introduction	<p>Short presentation of interview objectives</p> <p>Information about management of interviewee's personal data</p> <p>Request permission to record interview</p>	All REI, privacy, and data management processes must be adhered to.	
B. Background	1. Could you please describe for me in a few sentences your occupation and professional role?	Brief summary of job/role	Occupation Job title
	2. Can you describe your work on the topic of COVID/Climate Change?	Brief summary of researcher's work in the topic area (Climate Change or Covid-19)	Academic Technology transfer Innovation Institutional (e.g. public health) Science Communication
C. Case context	3. In which ways that you are aware of has your Covid/Climate work been presented to the public by others (e.g. by journalists, social media influencers, publishers, etc)?	This question aims to understand how the researcher's work is communicated to the public, use the prompt for their assessment of the quality of this communication.	Channels
	4. In your opinion, what effects do debate and controversy about Covid/Climate research have on public attitudes toward science, and toward your own work?	This question aims to understand researchers' views on how contest over facts impacts on public trust.	Positive effects or outcomes Negative effects or outcomes
D. Integration of citizens across	5. What is your opinion regarding increasing the involvement of citizens in scientific research?	This question aims to understand their opinion about integration and participation of laypersons in research.	Positives Negatives

the research cycle	6. Are citizens involved in, or connected to, your own research?	This question aims to identify the interviewee's involvement in integration activities with citizens and the public.	Type of activity Context Medium (in-person, online) Social group(s) Frequency Scale (n participants) Phases of research cycle
	7. In your experience, what barriers are there to greater participation of citizens in science?	This question aims to learn about barriers to social integration derived from the interviewee's experience. EXPERIENCE-BASED ONLY	Institutional barriers Organisational barriers Skill or capability barriers (researchers) Public interest
E. Public trust in science	8. In your experience, what concerns do citizens express about science?	This question aims to obtain information about the interviewee's direct knowledge of citizens' concerns but can also include interviewees' perceptions.	<i>In Q8 the interviewer prompts for REI.</i> Concerns about conduct of science Concerns about outcomes of science
	9. In your opinion, what are the most powerful factors or forces driving citizens concerns and public distrust of science, especially about Covid/Climate Change?	This question aims to open a short discussion of the scientific and societal factors that they consider are shaping public trust in science.	<i>In Q9 the interviewer can prompt for REI again.</i> REI issues Social media Public understanding of science Scientists' communication skills
	10. What would be your three most important priorities to improve public trust in science?	This question asks for the interviewee's recommended changes or policy interventions in the context of public distrust discussed in Q9.	<i>In Q10, if citizens' participation/integration is not among the three recommendations, the interviewer can prompt for it.</i> Recommendation 1 Recommendation 2 Recommendation 3

			Social integration recommendation
H. Debriefing	Additional comments Repetition of agreements (consent, etc.)	Open up for interviewee-initiated comment	

Joint Data Controller Agreement

THIS JOINT CONTROLLER AGREEMENT is made on {date}, hereinafter referred to as the 'Effective Date'

Between

- Data Controller 1: Aarhus University, established in Nordre Ringgade 1, 8000 Aarhus, Denmark, VAT number DK31119103, the Coordinator of the consortium, and
- Data Controller 2: Iscte - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, established in Avenida das Forças Armadas, 1649-026 Lisbon, Portugal, VAT number PT501510184,
- Data Controller 3: Wissenschaft im Dialog gGmbH, established in Charlottenstraße 80. D-10117 Berlin, Germany, VAT number DE 231831941,
- Data Controller 4: National Technical University of Athens, established in Heroon Polytechniou 9 Zographou Campus, Athina 15780, Greece, VAT number EL099793475,
- Data Controller 5: Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, established in Rue Michel Ange 3, 75794 Paris, France, VAT number FR40180089013,
- Data Controller 6: Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, established in C/ Serrano, 117, Madrid 28006, Spain, VAT number Q2818002D,
- Data Controller 7: London School of Economics and Political Science, established in Houghton Street, London, WC2A 2AE, United Kingdom, VAT number GB629588094,

hereinafter, jointly referred to as "Joint Controllers" or "Parties" relating to the project entitled:

Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science, in short: **POIESIS**, hereinafter referred to as 'Programme'.

Purpose

The purpose of this agreement concerning joint data responsibility (the 'Agreement') is to comply with Article 26 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), according to which, joint data responsibility exists when two or more data controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing personal data.

In the case of joint data responsibility, the joint controllers shall establish their respective responsibilities for compliance with the obligations under the GDPR in a transparent manner.

This Agreement is designed to enable the Parties to comply with the requirements for joint data responsibility in Article 26 of the GDPR, in particular as regards the exercise of the data subject's rights and the obligation to provide the information referred to in Articles 13 and 14.

1. Joint data responsibility

1.1. This Agreement sets out the overall division of responsibilities between Parties about the processing of personal data in connection with the Expert Interviews planned within Work Package 2 of the Programme.

1.2. The Agreement shall, in accordance with Article 26(2) of the GDPR, duly reflect the respective roles and relationships of the parties with the data subjects. The essence of the Agreement shall also be made available to the data subjects.

The data subject may, however, regardless of the terms of the Agreement, exercise his or her rights under the GDPR with regard to and against each of the Data Controllers.

The "internal" division of responsibilities in this Agreement also does not prevent the supervisory authority from exercising its powers against each of the Data Controllers.

1.3 The Parties have jointly decided which types of data to process, methodology, study sample, detailed analysis plan and analytic strategy – and hence jointly determined and agreed on the purpose (why data is being processed) and the essential means of the processing.

2. Overall allocation of responsibilities

2.1. All data controllers have agreed that in connection with the processing of personal data collected during the Expert Interviews the Parties have joint data responsibility. In assessing this, account has been taken, inter alia, of:

The Programme includes seven partners from different institutions and countries that are responsible for processing the personal data of their own country and, after anonymization, data will be shared with Data Controller 6.

- 2.2. All data controllers are responsible for obtaining expressed consent from the data subjects to collect and process personal data - article 6(1)(e) - and special categories 'sensitive data' - Article 9(2)(a) of the GDPR - in their countries for the purposes of Expert Interviews only. All data controllers are responsible for providing the information referred to in the article 13 of the GPDR to the data subjects on behalf of all parties.
- 2.3. All data controllers are responsible for audio recording the Expert Interviews, transcribing the recordings to their own language, and ensuring the pseudonymisation of the personal data for five years after the last publication, date from which audio recordings shall be deleted.
- 2.4. All data controllers shall translate the transcripts to English and share the transcripts with Data Controller 6, ensuring the anonymisation of personal data.
- 2.5. The pseudonymized transcripts in the original language and in English shall be destroyed 5 years after the last publication.
- 2.6. Data Controller 6 is responsible for receiving and processing the anonymised data of the other data controllers in order to analyse and describe the overall results of the Expert Interviews, which will result in Deliverable D2.3 of the Programme.

3. Principles and processing eligibility

- 3.1. Each Party is responsible for ensuring that there is a valid basis for processing personal data and demonstrating this to the national supervisory authority.
- 3.2. Each Party responsible for complying with the principles for the processing of personal data to the extent that the rules apply to the Party's responsibilities under this Agreement.

4. Rights of data subject's

- 4.1. Parties shall be responsible for safeguarding the rights of data subjects by complying with the following rules of the GDPR:
 - the obligation to provide information when collecting personal data from the data subject,

- the obligation to provide further information if personal data have not been collected from the data subject,
- the data subject's right of access,
- the right of rectification,
- right to erasure (right to be forgotten),
- the right to restriction of processing,
- the obligation to provide information in relation to the rectification or erasure of personal data or the restriction of processing,
- the right to data portability (except for public authorities); and
- the right to object to processing.

4.2. Each Party is responsible to respond to the requests or enquiries about the observance of the data subjects' rights in relation to the data collected by themselves.

4.3. If a Party receives a request or an enquiry from a data subject concerning the matters covered by the responsibilities of another Party as set out above, the first Party will forward this to the relevant Party as soon as possible for that Party to respond to the request or enquiry.

4.4. The Parties are responsible for assisting each other to the extent appropriate and necessary for all Parties to comply with their obligations to the data subjects.

5. Security of processing and evidence of compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation

5.1. Parties shall be responsible for compliance with Article 24 of the GDPR, with regards to implementing appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing complies with the GDPR; taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes in question of the processing of personal data as well as the risks of varying probability and severity for the natural persons' rights and freedoms. The measures shall be reviewed and updated as necessary.

5.2. Parties' measures shall, if proportionate to the processing activities, include the implementation of appropriate data protection policies.

- 5.3. Parties shall be responsible for compliance with Article 25 of the GDPR by design and data protection by default settings.
- 5.4. Parties shall be responsible for compliance with Article 32 of the GDPR on processing security. This implies that all data controllers, taking into account the state of the current technical level, the implementation costs and the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing concerned, as well as the risks of varying probability and severity to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to those risks.

Parties shall therefore carry out (and prove) a risk assessment form and then implement measures to mitigate the identified risks.

6. Use of data processors and sub-processors

- 6.1. Parties are entitled to use data processors and / or any sub-processors in connection with the joint processing provided that the personal data i) either are not transferred outside of EU/EEA or ii) only are transferred in compliance with the Data Protection Regulation Chapter V.
- 6.2. In the event of the use of data processors and / or sub-processors, Parties shall be responsible for compliance with the requirements of Article 28 of the GDPR. Accordingly, a Party shall, inter alia:
 - use only data processors who can provide the necessary guarantees that they implement appropriate technical and organizational measures in such a way as to ensure that processing complies with the requirements of the GDPR and ensures the protection of the data subject's rights,
 - ensure that there is a valid data processor agreement between the relevant Party and the data processor, and
 - ensure that there is a valid sub-processor agreement between the data processor and any sub-processor.
- 6.3. Each Party shall be informed, upon request, by the other Parties if the personal data is processed by data processors and, where applicable, sub-processors.

- 6.4. If personal data are processed by data processors and where applicable sub-processors, each Party shall be informed, upon request, of the content of the agreements between the other Parties and the data processor / sub-processor.

7. Records of processing activities

- 7.1. Parties shall be responsible for complying with the requirement in Article 30 of the GDPR on records of processing activities. This implies that each Party shall establish a record of the processing activities for which the Parties are joint controllers.
- 7.2. Parties shall inform upon request the other Parties of the content of the above record.

8. Notification of personal data breaches to the supervisory authority

- 8.1. Parties shall be responsible for compliance with Article 33 of the GDPR on the notification of personal data breaches to the supervisory authority.

9. Communication of personal data breaches to the data subject

- 9.1. All Parties shall be responsible for compliance with Article 34 of the GDPR regarding the communication of personal data breaches to the data subject.

10. Data protection impact assessment and prior consultation

- 10.1. Parties shall be responsible for compliance with the requirement in Article 35 of the GDPR on data protection impact assessment. Where a type of processing, in particular using new technologies and by virtue of its nature, scope, interrelation and purposes, is likely to result in a high risk to the natural person's rights and freedoms, each Party shall, prior to the processing, carry out an analysis of the implications of the envisaged processing activities for the protection of personal data.
- 10.2. Each Party shall also comply with the requirement in Article 36 of the GDPR to consult the supervisory authority in advance, where appropriate.

11. Transfers of personal data to third countries or international organisations

- 11.1. The Parties jointly may decide that personal data may be transferred to third countries or international organisations.
- 11.2. Each Party shall be responsible for compliance with the requirements of Chapter V of the GDPR in the event of transfers of personal data to third countries or international organisations.

12. Complaints

- 12.1. The Parties shall each be responsible for handling any complaints from data subjects, if the complaints relate to a breach of the provisions of the GDPR, for which the Party is responsible under this Agreement.
- 12.2. If one of the Parties receives a complaint that should rightly be dealt with by another Party, the complaint shall be forwarded to that Party as soon as possible.
- 12.3. If one of the Parties receives a complaint, where part of the complaint should rightly be dealt with by another Party, that part shall be forwarded to that Party for that Party to respond as soon as possible.
- 12.4. The data subject shall be informed of the essential content of this Agreement when one Party forwards a complaint or part thereof by the receiving Party to the another Party.

13. Informing the other Party

- 13.1. The Parties shall inform and liaise with each other of any material facts affecting the joint processing and this Agreement.

14. Indemnification for third-party claims

- 14.1. In the event that a breach of the GDPR on by a Party leads to sanctions of the other Party, such as e.g. administrative fines as well as fines set by the courts, the first Party ('Indemnitee') will hold the latter Party harmless.
- 14.2. In the event that a breach of the GDPR by a Party leads to payment of compensation to a data subject, such compensation will be considered direct

losses in the internal relationship between the Data Controllers. Further, the Party causing such compensation ('Indemnitee') shall keep the other Parties harmless for any other reasonable losses suffered in connection with the processing of the claim.

- 14.3. In the event that a Party seeks indemnification under this Agreement it is a condition for the Indemnitee's indemnification obligation i) have the agreement of the defaulting party, or ii) that the claim is finally awarded by a court of competent jurisdiction.
- 14.4. The limitations of liability agreed to in the POIESIS project Grant number 101057253, do not apply.

15. Choice of law and venue

- 15.1. This Agreement shall be governed by the law of one of the EU Member States, provided such law allows for third-party beneficiary rights. The Parties agree that this shall be the law of Belgium, as the Programme is funded by the European Union under the Horizon programme.
- 15.2. Any dispute arising from this Agreement shall be resolved by the courts of an EU Member State. The Parties agree that those shall be the courts of Belgium.
- 15.3. A data subject may also bring legal proceedings against a Party before the courts of the Member State in which he/she has his/her habitual residence.
- 15.4. The Parties agree to submit themselves to the jurisdiction of such courts.

16. Entry into force and termination

- 16.1. This Agreement shall enter into force upon signature by all Parties hereto.
- 16.2. This Agreement shall remain in force as long as the personal data concerned are processed, or until this Agreement is replaced by a new agreement, laying down the division of responsibilities in relation to the processing.
- 16.3. Authorised signatures:

[Data Controller 1]

[Data Controller 2]

Name: _____ Name: _____

Position: _____ Position: _____

Date: _____ Date: _____

[Data Controller 3]

[Data Controller 4]

Name: _____ Name: _____

Position: _____ Position: _____

Date: _____ Date: _____

[Data Controller 5]

[Data Controller 6]

Name: _____ Name: _____

Position: _____ Position: _____

Date: _____ Date: _____

[Data Controller 7]

Name: _____

Position: _____

Date: _____

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Expert Interviews - *Denmark*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: CSIC

Contributors: Tine Ravn, Christina Løth Andersen and Simon Fuglsang

August 2024

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1 Introduction

This section provides a brief background on the expert interview study and the objectives of the overall POIESIS research project. Additionally, it highlights inputs to the expert interview study from previous POIESIS tasks within a Danish context and summarizes the process of organizing and conducting interviews with mediators and researchers.

1.1 Research questions for Task 2.3

The general objectives in POIESIS are to:

- Investigate the relationship between research integrity, public engagement in research, and trust in research.
- Examine how scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent communication, and/or misinformation affect public trust.
- Examine the various role that institutions related to research, communication, and funding play in promoting a research climate that is conducive to society's trust in science

The expert interview study investigates how knowledge and science dissemination between research and citizens takes place. We aim to understand complex 'chains of mediation' processes and how (ir)responsible research practices are perceived and best communicated, as well as how they potentially affect citizens' trust in research. In the expert interview study, the following research questions are examined:

More specific research questions

How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?

- Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?

What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

1.2 Insights from Task 2.2 and Task 3.1

POIESIS includes a large empirical programme to investigate its research questions, including a public deliberation study (task 2.2) that included seven deliberative workshops across the seven POIESIS partner countries. A total of 169 citizens participated in the study (27 in Denmark), which aimed to explore attitudes of the public towards science, including public trust in science and whether and how it is affected by research integrity values and societal integration in science (Entradas, Sousa and Yan, 2023).

Some of the following results found in the Danish deliberation may also be thematized and reflected in the Danish part of the expert interview study:

- Overall, citizens perceived reputable and traditional media as more trustworthy, while social media was generally seen as less reliable.
- Media and their credibility were significant topics in the Danish deliberation. Citizens emphasized that trust can be diminished if a communication actor is not independent and has too close connections to the individuals involved or the subjects being researched.
- According to the citizens, various circumstances determine how citizen involvement affects trust in research. They presented both potential advantages and disadvantages of involving citizens in research. The primary concern was that the lack of expertise among citizens might risk compromising the quality and validity of the data.

Another empirical study in POIESIS (task 3.1) comprises a focus group study with 22 focus group interviews (a total of 131 participants, 18 Danish participants) across all seven project countries with institutional actors, who in various ways are engaged with research integrity and/or public involvement in research, research support, open science, science communication, and research funding. The purpose of the study was to investigate how and to what extent different institutions can provide policies and procedures that enable researchers to act in ways that promote public trust in research. Additionally, the study examines how research integrity and public involvement are perceived (Dubois, 2024). For the three Danish focus group interviews conducted, the following findings can be emphasized:

- There is no perceived general crisis in trust in science; however, increasing and complex challenges related to trust between science and society were identified.
- Questionable or detrimental research practices, irresponsible science communication, and the influence of private and political

interests are some of the main factors contributing to these challenges

- “Cracks in trust” influence increased politicization and ideological instrumentalization of science.
- Overall agreement that public integration and participation can clearly bring society closer to science and scientists but there are different ideas about the desirable extent of citizen involvement with several participants noting that not all research projects are equally conducive to such involvement.

The complex relationship between science and society, issues of trustworthiness and independence concerning different actors within the chains of mediation, and diverse views on the effects of participation might also emerge as themes in the expert interviews.

1.3 Brief summary of organising the interviews

In the Danish study, and in alignment with the study protocol (Monsonís-Payá and Woolley, 2024), 10 interviews with mediators and 6 interviews with researchers were conducted. Interviewees were recruited based on their key professional experience and expertise through a purposeful sampling strategy (Patton 2015) aimed at securing representational diversity across the pre-defined study sample criteria (please see below).

Potential interviewees were identified through desk research and network recommendations (e.g., from science communication experts and researchers). Potential interviewees received an invitation email to participate in the study and potentially one reminder email. Upon invitation acceptance, interviewees received a more detailed invitation letter describing the objectives of the POIESIS project and the particular study, an informed consent form, and an AU information sheet regarding data processing and data protection. All information sheets were adapted to a Danish context and translated/written in Danish. Interview guides for both mediator and researcher interviews were also translated into Danish.

All interviews were conducted online, and each interview lasted an hour on average, with the longest interview lasting an hour and 24 minutes and the shortest 49 minutes. Interviews were conducted by study participant TR (10 interviews) or participant CLA (6 interviews). All interviews took place between May 8 and June 10, 2024.

1.4 Data processing

Interviews were recorded through Microsoft Teams and transcribed verbatim through the automatic speech recognition (ASR) system WHISPER, for which a data agreement is in place and approved for use by Aarhus University. All interviews were then individually and carefully checked by participant CLA or a student assistant for transcription accuracy to improve the reliability and validity of the data. Subsequently, interview transcripts were coded in the software and data facilitation programme NVivo (by TR) using the codebook provided by the study coordinator. Interviews were coded through a systematic and primarily deductive approach in alignment with the codebook design to support the comparative and across-case research design of the study. The coding strategy also encompassed an inductively oriented approach, where emerging sub-topics and themes were coded and added to the final coding tree/list. Project member SF manually coded all interviews to populate the descriptive tables in section 2.1 and 2.2. All interviews have been securely stored in a specific project system folder with granted access for AU project members only.

2 Participants in the Expert Interview study

This section contains descriptive information about all interviewees. Mediators are described in section 2.1, and researchers in section 2.2. All sections follow the general scheme for the project report but contain added comments or notes to clarify specificities for the Danish case and/or the specific interviewee.

The table of expert categories below provides an overview of the sample criteria and profiles specified in the study research protocol (Monsonís-Payá and Woolley, 2024, p. 19). All categories in terms of position and expertise are represented in the Danish sample of experts. Numbers marked in bold and italics indicate the Danish study sample representation when diverging from protocol measures. However, while the sample strategy includes an analytical distinction, in practice, several mediators cover multiple categories in their current profession or have previously been employed in different positions within and across institutional and non-institutional settings. For instance, one of the institutional mediators is also a book author and former science journalist (see overview, table 1).

Participant profiles as indicated in research protocol

Type of expert	Profile and number of experts
Researchers (6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers on climate change (3, including 1 SSH (2)SSH) • Researchers on Covid-19 (3, including 1 (2)SSH)
Institutional Mediators (2, 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional science communicators working at publishers (0 or 1), (1) – might be allocated at the project level • Institutional science communicators working at universities and research institutes (1 or 2), (2)
Non-institutional mediators (8, 7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional science writers: authors of popular books or other content (minimum 1, (2)) • Science journalists: major print, television, radio, magazines, etc. (minimum 1) • Authors of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. (minimum 1), (3) • Other content creators (e.g. “contrarian”, “activist”, among others (minimum 1)

(Source: Monsonís-Payá and Woolley, 2024, p. 19)

Mediators are all well-established in the Danish science communication ecosystem. For all mediators, outputs and channels used in prior roles or those that are now discontinued are indicated in the associated tables. Furthermore, there is a tendency among the Danish mediators to broadly

refer to social media collectively, rather than referring to specific channels. This is indicated in Table 4 by an asterisk. Some categorizations required additional explanations and have been indicated as a note in the "other" field.

Researchers equally represent research within the fields of Covid-19 and climate research (please see Table 8). Two of the three Covid-19 researchers work within the SSH field (social science and humanities), and this is also the case for two of the climate researchers.

2.1 Mediators

Table 1. Demographics and occupation

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Mediator type**	Organization type (where applicable)	Occupational Description	Topic CV/CC
DK_M01	F	Senior	Institutional mediator	University publisher	Editor at university publisher	
DK_M02	M	Senior	Institutional mediator	University	Research communicator, Journalist	
DK_M03	M	Senior	Science writer	National broadcaster	Journalist	Covid
DK_M04	F	Senior	Science journalist	Newspaper	Journalist, book author	
DK_M05	M	Senior	Institutional mediator	University	Research communicator, book author	
DK_M06	M	Senior	Science-related outlets	Independent	Consultant, communicator	Covid
DK_M07	M	Senior	Science-related outlets	Independent	Consultant, journalist	Climate
DK_M08	F	Senior	Science-related outlets	Independent	Communicator, journalist	
DK_M09	M	Senior	Science-related outlets	University museum	Curator, Ph.D.	
DK_M10	M	Senior	Other content creators	Independent	Consultant	Climate

Table 2. Mediators' main communication tasks

Id.	Description of mediators' main communication tasks
DK_M01	Editor of (popular) science publications. Coordination with authors and reviewers. Interaction with readers at conferences or online.
DK_M02	Communication strategy, press releases, and public relations. Regular column in national newspaper. Curates public communication efforts.
DK_M03	Editing and quality checking science related news. Producing articles. Producing and preparing analyses for other journalists.
DK_M04	Producing articles for national newspaper.
DK_M05	Mediating between researchers and media outlets. Research dissemination. Author of popular science books.
DK_M06	Blog on the covid pandemic.
DK_M07	Science communication consultant and journalist. Part-time writing of scientific articles for specialist journals. Involved in climate organisation.
DK_M08	Podcast host. Writer for specialist journal. Teaches communication. Previously in-house communicator at university.
DK_M09	Science museum curator. Producing educational content aimed at school children.
DK_M10	Blog on climate and environmental policy. Public climate and environmental policy debates.

Table 3. Outputs produced by Mediators

Id.	Books	Articles	Audiovisual (TV)	Radio program	Podcast	Audiovisual (social media)	Text Post (Social media)	Live (social media interaction)	Other: (please describe in a few words only)
DK_M01					p		p		
DK_M02									
DK_M03									
DK_M04									
DK_M05				p	p				
DK_M06									
DK_M07							p		
DK_M08			P	p					
DK_M09		See note							Note: Writes academic articles
DK_M10									
<i>Notes: p: previous activity</i>									

Table 4. Channels used by Mediators

Id.	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)						Chat apps		Other: (please describe in a few words only)
	TV	Radio	Newspaper	Websites	Blogs	Newsletters	LinkedIn	YouTube	Twitter	Instagram	TikTok	Other SN	WhatsApp	Telegram	
DK_M01				p	p		*	*	*	*	*	*			Making output available "where people are". I.e. at a low price in grocery stores.
DK_M02							*	*	*	*	*	*			
DK_M03							*	*	*	*	*	*			
DK_M04															
DK_M05							*	*	*	*	*	*			Sends press releases to "media in general", used to work in national media
DK_M06													note		Note: Facebook
DK_M07			p		p										Specialist journal
DK_M08	p	p													Specialist journal
DK_M09															Museums. Education programmes for children
DK_M10							*	*	*	*	*	*			

*Notes: * mentions social media in general. p; previous activity*

Table 5. Audience addressed by Mediators

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' audiences/size estimate where known
DK_M01	General public.
DK_M02	General public. Potential students. Public policy professionals.
DK_M03	General public. Journalists.
DK_M04	Newspaper readers, specifically higher education segment belonging to upper-middle class.
DK_M05	General public, indirect through media.
DK_M06	General public. People with interest in health care politics.
DK_M07	Profession specific communication. Previously general public in blog-format.
DK_M08	General public. Specific professional groups. Podcast listeners.
DK_M09	General public. 200k visitors annually, 30 % school children.
DK_M10	General public, climate debate participants.

Table 6. Mediators' interactions with citizens

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' social interaction practices
DK_M01	Indirect through connecting researchers to public forums, e.g. media, festivals. Interactions with readers on social media and conferences.
DK_M02	Facilitates researcher-stakeholder interaction through public forums. Interacts through social media.
DK_M03	Starts by indicating no interaction due to resource intensity. Still direct contact with readers. Assessment of public opinion on social media.
DK_M04	Direct contact with readers. Public forums organized by newspaper.
DK_M05	No interaction in current position. Previously (science journalism): Vox pops on science related news, public science festivals, answering reader emails.
DK_M06	Social media interaction.
DK_M07	Previously through interaction on blog.
DK_M08	Feedback and reactions on podcast.
DK_M09	Indirect, creates interactive exhibitions for school children and the general public that combine science history and contemporary societal discussions. Museum conducts user experience studies.
DK_M10	Social media interaction.

Table 7. Mediators' sources of information

Id.	Interpersonal networks		Science press releases	RPOS	Publishers	Mainstream media	Social media	Other: (please add text)
	With researchers	With science communicators						
DK_M01		*						International collaboration with university publisher network
DK_M02		*						
DK_M03		*	See note					Discusses the unaligned timelines between academia and journalism, leading to interactions prior to publication.
DK_M04		*						Personal network.
DK_M05		*						
DK_M06								Political actors. Personal network.
DK_M07								
DK_M08								Both national and international science communicator networks.
DK_M09		*						
DK_M10								

Notes: * with close colleagues

2.2 Researchers

Table 8. Description of the Researcher interviews sample

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Position or title/Career stage**	Organisation type	Topic CV/CC#
DK_R01	F	Senior	Senior researcher	University	Climate, SSH
DK_R02	M	Mid	Assistant professor	University	Climate, SSH
DK_R03	F	Mid	Postdoc	University	Climate
DK_R04	F	Senior	Professor	University	Covid
DK_R05	M	Senior	Associate professor	University	Covid, SSH
DK_R06	F	Senior	Professor	University	Covid (+Climate), SSH

Table 9. Researcher notes

Id.	Note
DK_R01	Environmental social science. Studies public policy and public involvement on environmental and climate issues.
DK_R02	Environmental humanities. Studies how the climate crisis and its (lack of) solutions is portrayed in media.
DK_R03	Climate researcher. Studies climate change in the arctic.
DK_R04	Epidemiology researcher. Expert in pandemics.
DK_R05	Sociologist, studies volunteering. Studied the processes of volunteering during covid lockdown.
DK_R06	Business communication researcher. Studies crisis management and crisis communication, for instance in relation to Covid-19 and climate change.

Table 10. How Researchers work with the public

Id.	Brief description of how the researchers' work reaches the public
DK_R01	Social media, done primarily at project level and mostly by colleagues. Public lectures at educational institutions (secondary and high school). Participations in public dialogue events (organized by unions and/or public authorities). Media interviews (written media and radio and not TV).
DK_R02	Involved in public debates, mainly through established written media.
DK_R03	Likes the idea of public dissemination but does not participate personally.
DK_R04	Involved in public debates, dialogues and talks. Provided information to Covid-19 policy-making. Newspaper articles, national radio and television, guesting podcasts. Previous efforts to engage sceptics.
DK_R05	Mediated by journalists.
DK_R06	Mediated by journalists.

Table 6. Description of social integration practices of Researchers

Id.	Brief notes of Researchers' social integration practices
DK_R01	Involved in cocreation activities through two European projects with local stakeholders, both individual citizens and civil society organizations (CSO's). Public dialogue events.
DK_R02	Is not currently involved in citizen engagement with science. Likes the idea of involvement and plans to integrate public involvement in future projects.
DK_R03	Works occasionally with native Greenlanders to draw on their specialist knowledge and experience.
DK_R04	Participates in public debate through a wide range of dialogue events.
DK_R05	Is not involved in citizen engagement with science but finds it likely to happen, as public engagement and citizen science formats are well-established within the researcher's particular field of research.
DK_R06	Citizen involvement through data collection and as research subjects.

3 Analysis of Mediator interviews

3.1 Chains of mediation

'Chains of mediation' refers to "networks of actors, activities, and sequences of practices that connect research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of scientific research by the wider publics" (Monsonís-Payá and Woolley, 2024, p. 17). As both institutional and non-institutional actors in the chain of mediation, mediators in the study engage in a wide range of activities and communication formats and interact with a broad array of target audiences as displayed in the descriptive tables above. The interviews and the professional backgrounds of the mediators indicate that they are well-established in the Danish science communication landscape, in institutional and non-institutional communication networks and that they all have a profound understanding of the Danish communication ecosystem and the various roles and work procedures due to their extensive experiences. Eight out of ten mediators have a university background, and several of these mediators also have a background in journalism (Table 1). Additionally, several interviewees have been or are currently involved in multiple communication roles (e.g. media, university PR, consultancy). Hence, mediation structures seem to be characterised by this fluidity in the roles and organizational links of the mediators.

Chains of mediation models

The more traditional and linear chain of mediation from researchers → publishers → institutional press → media → public only partly seem to characterise the process of translating information from science to society. For institutional science communicators at universities, press releases concerning novel study findings are for instance still published and covered by the media. However, institutional science communicators also apply various other formats such as features, social media etc. and proactively search for stories through knowledge of research projects, researcher collaborations etc. One institutional science communicator for instance mentions the broad span from more direct to 'indirect' and 'subtle' forms of communication. He provides the example that the writing of a feature for a certain national media do not constitute research dissemination per se but acts as a 'teaser' for gathering additional scientific information, often resulting in increased collaboration between researchers and stakeholders (e.g. industry, politicians, etc.).

Another institutional science communicator points to the fact that several newspaper and dedicated media science sections have closed, consequently 'making it increasingly difficult to get this kind of

content through the media than it was before' (M05, p. 3). A former institutional science communicator has, through personal experience, observed how research dissemination varies between universities and faculties, reflecting different interpretations of dissemination obligations as part of their third mission activities that according to the mediator may be caused by varying distances to practice and societal-related topics.

In general, multiple sources of information are applied, including scientific articles, scientific conferences, researcher interviews, day-to-day news, communication with colleagues, and informal networks, among many other inputs. While a traditional mediation model still exists, it does not reflect the reality, complexity, and multiple translation processes taking place within the Danish science communication landscape.

Overall, mediators do not seem to position themselves firmly in a prescriptive chain of mediation but rather appear as more autonomous actors attempting to bridge science and society relations (please see section 3.3 for details).

Translation processes – from knowledge production to public dissemination

A mediator working as a science journalist at a national newspaper states that the particular newspaper does not focus their attention on new or 'breaking' research results communicated through press releases, for instance. Rather, the mediator prefers to write about 'new knowledge emerging' and identify 'research tendencies or how we can apply a research perspective to something current in society' (M04, p. 1-2).

In the process of disseminating scientific knowledge to different target audiences, several mediators emphasize the importance of not only explaining the research but also focusing on narrating the scientific process in order to increase reader understandings of complex research topics and studies. A journalist from a national broadcasting corporation notes that articles with detailed data explanations always receive positive feedback from readers. It was mentioned that this also became evident during the pandemic, where readers reacted positively to explanatory text, and some reacted negatively to simplified text describing, for instance, the number of daily coronavirus deaths without accounting for whether they died 'of or with corona' (M03, p. 3). Additionally, several mediators mention the importance of the potential stories being relevant to society and having a societal impact. Aspects such as reader identification, fascination, and the potential of conveying the controversial nature of the science are also mentioned.

In the transformation process of turning scientific knowledge into a journalistic product, a non-institutional journalist describes his mediation/creative process through the concept of 'concurrency,'

which refers to the process of learning the subject matter while disseminating it. An institutional science communicator emphasizes the following aspects of importance in the transformation process:

"I think there are two things: you need to be on top of communication, but of course, integrity and credibility are absolutely essential. If you lose those, then nothing else really matters" (M02, p. 6).

The issue of credibility is a recurrent theme as detailed below. Other important aspects mentioned for the process of transforming inputs into products include thorough research, valid results, sound source referencing, a critical approach, and independence in relation to potential conflicts of interest.

These aspects are closely related to mediators' perception of success criteria. Mediators refer to the scope and type of public mention but underline the qualitative aspects of success parameters: That the research reaches a wider audience, that their work makes a difference, is placed in a relevant societal context, and creates insight and reflection. Additionally, that the population becomes more informed, that the output 'brings things to light,' and is well received by professionals and relevant readers.

A blog post communicator also mentions the level of interaction from readers as a parameter of success. Another non-institutional mediator includes the criterion of impacting the public discussion on climate issues.

"My success would be if the knowledge about the aquatic environment and the climate, which we realists have, also became part of the general discussion. But it isn't. It's nowhere near being the framework for discussion. Instead, it's always about hysteria, exaggerated alarmism, or denial of facts" (M10, p. 7).

For the procedure and outcome of translation processes, several mediators reflect upon the nature of science-based knowledge and their role when disseminating it:

"Basically, I believe that research-based knowledge is the best kind of knowledge. I would much rather have something that is research-based than something that is not. So that's one thing. That's the first hurdle we need to get people to agree on. And having said that, we also need to open a discussion about how research-based knowledge is not the absolute truth. It's the best guess we have right now" (M08, p. 5).

"I try to include an understanding of the [research] process and describe the journey to the breakthrough in the articles because I think it's incredibly important. Therefore, I also try to convey when there are frictions and disagreements - professional disagreements. Researchers are often not very happy about that...". (M04, p. 3)

The latter quotation highlights the different role perceptions between researchers and science mediators in relation to content dissemination. The mediator from a national newspaper describes a research culture where she perceives a tendency among researchers to focus primarily on facts and results, expressing authority rather than conveying enthusiasm about the research questions and process. Another mediator suggests that journalists could be more critical of researchers and challenge them more. Yet another mediator observes a 'fairly toxic' debate about researcher integrity, which he partly attributes to social media, the media in general, and some politicians. This environment results in researchers becoming more cautious about participating in public debates according to his experience as a university science communicator.

Citizen interactions

The majority of mediators interact with citizens to some extent as part of their communication activities (see Table 5 for details). Several interact directly or indirectly with readers or listeners through designated social media platforms or through blog posts, podcasts, articles, and email comments. Some journalists also mention citizen interactions and citizens as cases or sources of information. A few mediators, both institutional and non-institutional, provide examples of public dialogue events or the organization of citizen science projects as part of their current or former positions. A science journalist from a national newspaper conveys that they have an increasing focus on involving citizens/readers through different types of events and talks.

Several mediators mention receiving negative feedback from different types of citizens and stakeholders. A mediator from a national broadcasting corporation mentioned that they closed their Facebook commentary section due to the management workload and associated resource allocation. Two mediators, addressing Covid-19 and climate issues respectively, explicitly mention that they engage with serious critics and sceptics of their work up to a certain point.

3.2 About research ethics and integrity (REI)

On the topic of how mediators understand and define research integrity and research ethics – and how these influence their own practices – mediators generally raise research integrity concerns or positives in alignment with field-specific understandings and definitions of research integrity. Practices and guidelines concerning data collection, (gift) authorships, FFP practices (falsification, fabrication and plagiarism), research collaboration and open science are for instance articulated directly or indirectly in relation to the specific nomenclature. Several mediators introduce issues of integrity and ethics without prior probes but without using the specific terminology of research integrity and research ethics. As noted by one non-institutional mediator:

“These aren't concepts that I really think much about or use in those terms. But I believe that in practice, I'm constantly dealing with them, just without realizing that is what they're called or that is what I'm doing” (M08, p. 9).

By definition, research ethics concerns the moral principles governing research, including the treatment and protection of humans, animals, the environment, and data. In contrast, research integrity involves the professional standards for conducting research and handling data in terms of execution, treatment, results, and reporting (Steneck, 2006). One institutional science communicator describes this field-specific definition, while most mediators seem to understand the concepts together, primarily focusing on issues related to research integrity. Mediators' definitions can be categorized and listed according to the following topics mentioned across interviews. The list represents issues mentioned collectively but does not necessarily express consensus on all items among mediators.

Research integrity:

Research practices:

- Need for account of uncertainties
- Not fabricate or plagiarise data
- Cite correctly and be aware of others' work
- Experiments should preferably be replicable
- Be true to the scientific method, but not trust the method blindly. Randomized controlled trials not the only valid method
- Data transparency and open access to data

Research collaboration:

- Need for openness about research financing
- Openness about potential conflicts of interest

Research publication and communication:

- Need for accuracy, clarity and impartiality
- Researchers need to be aware of and stay within own areas of expertise. Show humility
- Avoidance of demagoguery
- Argumentation for interpretations
- Avoidance of being co-author without article contribution or understanding of the article content
- Avoidance of political activism

Research ethics:

Research practices:

- Be true to the tradition of research
- Fair and ethical treatment of research subjects
- Inclusion of relevant research stakeholders and subjects (e.g. autistic people in autism research)
- Ethical considerations of visitors' modesty in museum exhibitions

REI as part of own practices

Research integrity and research ethics practices are part of mediators' work and are addressed in various ways in the descriptions of their work and communication activities, as well as in how they assess the credibility of inputs.

Mediators' perceptions of integrity in science communication, journalism, and research appear interrelated and largely overlapping. This does not imply a juxtaposition between science communication by researchers and science communication by different mediators but rather that many integrity practices and principles are alike – both in terms of how mediators assess and fact-check research sources and approach their own writing and communication practices. Research and research studies/sources are critically assessed according to methodological transparency, validity and soundness of results and disclosure of potential conflicts of interests. The arm's length principle, referring to the ability to conduct impartial research, is also mentioned by several institutional and non-institutional mediators as a significant integrity principle.

"Sometimes I read something and think, this might as well be a press release from the company's partners (...). A company plays a huge role, and in some ways, it is really good that we are not just working in our little glass bubble doing research. But I think there is too little focus on the arm's length principle, which I hear leading university officials talk about all the time" (M02, p. 8).

Several mediators explicitly mention that they conduct extensive research on particular questions and are preoccupied with evidence but do not necessarily have the same in-depth knowledge of the topic as a researcher working in that specific area. In this regard, mediators apply a number of measures to assess credibility and fact-check, such as peer review processes, assessment of journals in terms of ratings, simple Google searches, checking survey questions and source data, using their own methodological skills, training, and experience, and consulting with colleagues, experts, and researchers, among other approaches.

A mediator notes that some short communication and news formats might pose a challenge in providing methodological transparency and fully accounting for the process. Another interviewee mentions the seemingly paradoxical nature of knowledge dissemination.

"There is an inherent paradox in dissemination. You often want to omit certain details and present a cleaner story because it's easier to understand. Naturally, some nuances are lost in the process of dissemination. This is unavoidable. One can only hope that people read further and grasp the nuances because they cannot be fully captured in a headline and subheadline. There are certainly ethical considerations to reflect on in this regard. However, I am very mindful of including nuances in the article" (M05, p. 7-8).

REI in relation to COVID-19 and climate topics

Two mediators have worked on Covid-19-related issues, and two mediators are engaged with climate issues. One of the Covid-19 mediators experienced the need to be very source-critical during the pandemic due to polarized positions among researchers. At the same time, the mediator assesses that the extensive use of field-specific experts in the media landscape likely reduced public polarization on corona-related issues in Denmark. He critiques that the Danish healthcare and political authorities were not more responsive to critical voices and to a greater extent included new and diverse inputs to increase public trust in the authorities. Both climate mediators - although from opposite points of view - identify polarized opinions on the topic of climate change and agree on the difficulties of disseminating knowledge on the issue. One of these mediators points to an "intense political struggle to define what constitutes

objectivity and professionalism" (M10, p.3), which, according to the mediator, is reflected in a peer review battle over which articles to publish.

ID here	Additional quotes
M01	I actually have to ensure that correctness, even though it originally comes from something correct, I am the final link, the last one before it reaches the public. So I think what we do - we have an enormous task - not only to communicate it in an understandable way but to communicate it correctly. That's the method we use. And we are also very - in relation to integrity and research ethics - that it's also very visible or the process is transparent, because you get peer reviews. But we do have an anonymous peer review process, which is, of course, to ensure impartiality and to allow for all forms of comments, which ultimately also helps the author (p. 3).
M09	The really good thing about a university museum is that there is relatively close proximity to the researchers. And that is, of course, something that is enormously important because, as a university museum, we are very, very aware that we need to be credible (p.6).
M03	You must not cheat, you must not make a money envelope... and invent your own data for something. You need to acknowledge and be aware of what others have done. And you must be very open about your processes. That is to say, you can certainly create something where you think your data is really good and shows something very interesting, which is completely opposite to the rest of the world. But it should ideally be repeatable by others. Otherwise, it's probably just you... (...). Openness is probably the most important thing (p.6-7).

3.3 About public trust in science

Mediators generally express high awareness and familiarity with public trust in science and perceive it to be an essential part of their professional role to increase public trust in science through clear, sound, and high-quality science communication processes and products. Transparency in the communication of both research outputs and research processes are also mentioned as a means to increase trust:

"So, I hope that it can provide a greater understanding of how science works, what researchers are interested in and contribute to, and in that way, by communicating it in a transparent manner, can also increase trust" (M05, p. 9).

"I believe that I have been, and continue to be, involved in inviting the public - in both the podcast and in my communications - into the research process, somehow building a bridge to the person who conducted the research. There is a certain credibility in that as well" (M08, p.10).

Several mediators explicitly mention a high level of credibility in their work and in their institutions as essential for their work and institutional legitimacy. The importance of institutional legitimacy is evident in all interviews with mediators representing universities, a university museum, a university publisher but also for mediators representing national media such as a newspaper or national broadcaster corporation. The mediator from the latter organisation emphasizes that public trust in science is promoted by careful communication on a case-by-case level but also dependent on the organisation's credibility in general as 'one bad one [story] does much more harm than 100 good ones do good':

"So, in terms of trust, if we only communicate something that we ourselves believe we can stand behind, we think that it... somehow increases trust. Both in us as an organization and in research in general, right? (...) I think it's difficult for our users to distinguish. Often, I don't think they even think about whether it's Aarhus University or Aalborg University; they just see the word university. And it becomes even harder when it involves some think tank or another... or. And then I think that the credibility the study gains with the user who encounters it through us is actually very much supported by the credibility we have" (M03, 7-8)

The same mediator also sees his role as 'qualifying the public debate' (M03, p. 6) and other mediators see their work as a means to promoting dialogue with the public. As a response to the question on how mediators would describe the relationship between their work and public trust in science and whether this is something actively thought about, one mediator states:

"Yes, regarding what we talked about earlier. Incredibly, incredibly important because... not just for me personally, but for the entire media profession. And not just science journalists, but really the entire journalism profession. It is really us who have a key role in ensuring that the public and

citizens trust research, because it is not just... one thing is that citizens... that we are gatekeepers. The citizens' way of understanding research largely goes through the media" (M04, p.10).

In addition to applying the concept of a gatekeeper, another mediator uses the concept of being a 'bridgebuilder' (M09) between the university and the public. One institutional mediator describes his role as a 'doorman,' mediating between science and society to open up greater interest in science-related issues and science-based policy-making. When asked directly, two non-institutional mediators and consultants have not specifically considered the effect their work has on public trust in science.

In general, while most mediators see their work as an effort to build trust, this does not mean addressing research in a non-critical fashion. In relation to the quote above, the mediator from a national newspaper also expresses that:

"The fact that I have to mediate trust in research is not about putting scientists on a pedestal. Absolutely not. Because scientists really need to, what do you call it, lose a little bit of control in order for trust in the scientific process to be created. And that might be hard for the individual researcher, but I think about trust in research more than trust in the individual researcher. But citizens really need to trust that research, science, is a good thing. And I feel the same way, but it is not about me being a cheerleader" (M04, p.10).

Generally, a lack of transparency in disclosing conflicts of interest and funding sources is seen as potentially decreasing trust in science. Several mediators also mention that having to navigate a complex and global media landscape with disinformation and conflicting communications concerning research findings can decrease public trust in science. Mediators also agree that media cases about irresponsible research or research misconduct have a negative effect on trust in science. Two mediators express that such cases may, in particular, increase distrust among citizens already sceptical or critical of science. However, while agreeing on the seriousness of such cases, mediators do not agree on the level of negative impact of malpractice cases. Nonetheless, in general, a consensus seems to exist that such cases are few in a Danish context and therefore do not play a significant role in factors impacting public trust in science.

In general, mediators do not seem to identify a crisis of trust in the Danish context, but they do point to areas of concern as specified above. Across the interviews, mediators were asked to provide a set of recommendations for improving public trust in science, including

recommendations targeted at a young demographic. These recommendations are both general and specific to their work context (please see section 3.5 for a detailed list of recommendations).

ID here	Additional quotes
M01	<p>“Working with communication also ensures that we don’t end up contributing to people staying in this ivory tower. We want to get out of it. And I believe that when you see more and more research in business, in cultural life, in book form in the way you read good stories, it creates a belief that it becomes part of one's education in a different way. That's what I think” (p. 11).</p>
M03	<p>“Another, and probably more important thing, but anyway... it is just to be very, very strict about the research practices in place, so that no meat scandals arise... to have strict enough rules that doctors must... no, let's say researchers must disclose their interests. Where the money comes from, etc. Be very strict about openness and have various professional quality checks (...). And as media, we can ensure that we are responsible enough to be open about weaknesses, and not jump to conclusions, and only communicate things that we ourselves believe to be of proper quality” (p.10).</p>
M04	<p>“They might handle sensitive topics that they fear could be misunderstood, and I fully understand that. But I don't perceive that there is any crisis. And then, of course, the question is how can we improve it. Wow, there are so many good initiatives in Denmark. (...). If something needs improvement, it is probably that our own... the media... could prioritize science more. And I am deliberately not saying that they should hire more science journalists, because they have skilled journalists who can write about science. But the major media outlets, DR and TV2, have no science programs” (p. 11).</p>
M08	<p>“The universities can definitely do something as well, and I have a personal pet peeve regarding the centralization of communication that we see at universities. There is something lost there in terms of the opportunity to both train researchers in their everyday practice. That is, having someone alongside them constantly, who continuously emphasizes communication and brings the stakeholder and recipient perspectives into the discussions about the research. And who also has detailed knowledge” (p. 3).</p>

3.4 Other themes

Additional relevant and related topics have been covered in the sections above. For instance, different role perceptions of researchers and science mediators emerged as a minor but inherent topic in several interviews.

3.5 Synthesis of recommendations

Collectively, mediators provided a set of recommendations for improving public trust in science. The recommendations are displayed in the table below, categorised according to a main topic (i.e. research integrity, public engagement with science, organisation and resources, targeted communication and science education) and according to the specific topic and mediator source.

Mediators pointed to the need to focus more attention on targeted communication in relation to meeting the audience 'where they are' and engaging with the public through their preferred platforms and channels. They also stated the need to allocate more resources to science communication initiatives at both an institutional level and within the general media sector. For instance, prioritising and valuing science communication activities within academia to a greater extent, increasing national science programs, and engaging in direct dialogue with the audience rather than merely writing for a specific target group were among the suggestions mentioned.

Mediators also suggested implementing formalised stakeholder inclusion within universities and encouraging greater participation of researchers in public debates. Several recommendations inherently aim to bring researchers, science communicators, and the public closer. One suggestion, for instance, is to integrate the media more into the world of research. A mediator from a university publisher mentioned that researchers sometimes experience their work being taken out of context and turned into clickbait headlines. In turn, closer collaboration would result in researchers being more comfortable with giving their opinions according to the mediator and also ensure a better match between researcher and expertise, avoiding researchers commenting on issues outside of their area of expertise.

Mediator recommendations to increase public trust in science

General topic	Specific topic	Recommendation	Med.
Research integrity	Processual transparency	Publish content along with explanations of the publishing and communication processes	M01
	Arm's length principle	Increase focus on the principles of arm's length in research collaboration and clarify their implications for research communication.	M02
	Quality criteria	Implement rigorous quality checks for research practices	M03
	Responsible media	Report weaknesses transparently and only publish after thorough quality checks	M03
Public engagement with science	Formalized procedures for public engagement	Universities should formalize the inclusion of stakeholders in their processes	M08
	Citizen science	Enhance citizen science initiatives and expand public engagement activities overall	M05, M08
	Public debates	Encourage greater participation of researchers in public debates	M09
	Foster reflection on sensitive issues	Foster reflection on sensitive and key societal issues to bolster public trust in science	M09
	Bridge gap between	Promote greater integration of media	M01

Organisation and resources	researchers and mediators	within the research community	
	Institutional researcher support	Support researchers in engaging with the public, focusing on communication rather than branding Prioritise and value science communication activities within academia	M08, M05
	Avoid researcher activism	Encourage universities to discourage activism among researchers, promoting more strict university management	M10
Targeted communication	Science - society dialogue	Engage in direct dialogue with the audience rather than merely writing for a specific target group	M01
	Bridge gap between mediators and audience	Reduce the gap between experts/mediators and the audience	M01
	Engage with the audience where they are	Engage with the public through their preferred platforms and channels	M03, M06
	Improve scientific knowledge	Focus on improving public knowledge of science rather than aiming to increase trust	M06
	Politicization of research	Reduce the politicization of research and ensure it is not exploited for political agendas	M07
Education	Increase science programmes	Increase the prioritization of science programs on national television	M04

	Greater media focus on science	Media should place a higher priority on covering research	M05, M07
	Explain the value of research	Place greater emphasis on explaining the value of science and avoid treating it as mere entertainment	M04, M03
	Explain societal impact of research	Provide more information on the societal impact of science, while acknowledging the importance of basic research	M07
	Science education	Place greater focus on enhancing science education in primary schools	M08
	No higher education cut downs	Ensure higher education opportunities are not reduced	M08

On the topic of improving trust in science for a younger generation comfortable with social media, mediators generally find it more challenging to provide recommendations specifically tailored to this group. Nonetheless, a recurring suggestion seems to resonate with the main recommendation to meet the audience where they are, and to actively engage them in dissemination processes.

“I believe that in relation to young people and social media and all that - I think we need to remember to meet them in their own language, in their own needs for knowledge. We can't just sit and say, well, we'll take some text and slightly modify it for social media. (...) It's also about not just saying we're going to adapt our communication to fit, but also about getting them involved and being active participants in the communication” (M01, P.13).

Three mediators also suggest increasing collaboration with science media influencers or producing more science communication content on social media platforms used by young people.

“There are, for example, some skilled influencers (...). Universities could consider creating more collaborations with them. I think we're a bit conservative in that regard today” (M05, p. 12).

The mediator from a university museum specifically mentions an initiative where a group of young people assisted in curating an exhibition and co-designed its content. The initiative aimed to bring young people and researchers closer together to increase interest in, and potentially trust in, science.

Based on the set of recommendations provided by mediators, the following suggestions capture the most consistent ideas across the five main categories in terms of promoting trust in science.

Overall mediator Recommendations
Enhance transparency and quality in research communication through upholding impartial research, implementing rigorous quality checks and disseminating processual and methodological explanations.
Formalize stakeholder inclusion at universities and encourage more citizen science and public engagement activities.
Bridge the gap between researchers and mediators and build co-partnerships. Place greater priority and value on science communication activities within academia, and support researchers in engaging with the public with a focus on effective communication.
Engage in direct dialogue with the audience, reduce the gap between science mediators and the public, and use their preferred platforms and channels for communication.
Place a higher priority on covering research in the media and put greater emphasis on explaining the value of science.

4 Analysis of Researcher interviews

This section presents key themes from the researcher interviews and summarizes the main findings concerning their work, practices regarding science dissemination, inclusion of citizens in the research cycle, and researchers' perspectives on public engagement and public trust in science.

4.1 Researcher contexts: Covid-19 and Climate Change

The six researchers in the Danish part of the study are at different career levels, with four in various permanent senior positions and two in a postdoctoral and assistant professor position, respectively. However, all are experienced researchers, and the two in temporary positions are nearing the completion of their appointments. The researchers are divided between focusing on Covid-19 or climate research, with one researcher covering both topics in her work. Four researchers broadly work within the social sciences and humanities (SSH), and all represent four geographically dispersed universities across Denmark.

The following table provides an overview of the researchers' work within the context of Covid-19 and climate research. The information expands on the descriptions provided in Table 9 but does not include details that might breach the anonymity of the interviewees.

Id.	Description of research
DK_R01 climate	Senior researcher in environmental social science. Studies public policy, local governance and public involvement in environmental and climate issues and has been engaged with institutional RI policy-making.
DK_R02 climate	Assistant professor in environmental humanities. Studies how the climate crisis and its (lack of) solutions are portrayed in the media, both now and in relation to the future, through primarily a philosophical lens.
DK_R03 climate	Climate and postdoctoral researcher. Studies climate change in the Arctic with a particular focus on its effects on soil and plants.
DK_R04 Covid-19	Professor of epidemiology with particular expertise in pandemics, focusing on both historical and contemporary pandemics and pandemic preparedness.

DK_R05 Covid-19	Associate professor in sociology. Studies volunteering and political activism. Studied the processes of informal civil society volunteering during the Covid-19 lockdown.
DK_R06 Covid-19	Professor and business communication researcher. Studies crisis management and crisis communication, for instance in relation to Covid-19 and climate research.

Public debate and controversy regarding both Covid-19 and climate change have impacted their work to varying degrees, both directly and indirectly. Two climate researchers indicate that their particular focus on climate issues - specifically on local governance rather than technical solutions and STEM research, and on the Arctic rather than Denmark and national agricultural issues - attracts less awareness and debate compared to the more emphasized counterparts. As one of the interviewees expresses:

“For example, the political governance rationales, behaviour, and consumption, and thus, policy-making at the EU level - all of this actually contributes to maintaining the societal structures, production methods, mobility patterns, and so on, which produce these environmental and climate problems, and which also make some of these things difficult to change. So, in that way, it appears somewhat in its absence but also in the discussions it catalyses because it is deprioritized, right?”
(R01, p. 3).

Two Covid-19 researchers mention a more direct impact on their work. For a crisis communication researcher, it is noted that the scale and scope of the Covid-19 pandemic made the choice of topic inevitable. The same is evident for the researcher working within the area of pandemics. She also highlights the dissemination challenges related to navigating within a field that suddenly became ‘public property,’ meaning that many non-epidemiologists suddenly acted as experts. The third researcher, who conducts research on volunteering, found that the pandemic provided a unique opportunity to study how tasks normally handled by the Danish welfare society became civil society tasks and were managed through, for example, informal networks and online forums.

4.2 About science communication and public attitudes

All researchers agree on the importance of research dissemination. This position aligns with a recent Danish study, which indicated that 69% of the surveyed researchers (n=3864) found science communication

really important or fairly important, compared to 11% who found it less important or not important (Danish Board of Technology 2023, p. 30).

Researchers present their work to the public in broad and various ways (see also Table 10), through channels such as written media, social media, TV/radio, podcasts, talks to various audiences, and participation in public dialogues. Five of the six researchers present their work to the public through outlets other than scholarly publications, generally through written and traditional media, and by participating in interviews addressing their areas of expertise. Three of the researchers explicitly speak to the high importance of sharing their knowledge with the public and participating in the broader public debate:

"I think that we have a duty, actually quite a significant duty, to contribute our knowledge when there are inquiries from the public" (R01, p. 5).

The researcher also mentioned that she is very careful to comment only on issues within her own areas of expertise and often finds herself having to mark this demarcation:

"It is quite often journalists have a tendency to think, 'You have done something about the climate, so you know everything about the climate,' and I am very careful to say, 'This, I know something about; this, I can give a qualified opinion on; this, I do not know anything about.' So, I talk to them, but I am also very explicit about what I can speak about based on research and what I cannot speak about based on research" (R01, p. 5).

Another researcher within the areas of climate research also speaks to the importance of being involved in the public debate but with an aim of trying to influence it to the extent possible. To him the line between activism and research is blurred:

"That is also why it blends together for me, because much of what I engage in is based on the knowledge I have acquired through my research. But I believe I have a very strong urge to participate in the public debate (...) being very polemical and provocative is also part of it. And I think many researchers are not very comfortable with that. But I find it - I am very comfortable with it. In fact, it really appeals to me a lot. And sometimes there can be... I sometimes think that the research world can become too dull. Yes, partly because we communicate too much internally without really getting our

messages out, because I actually hear plenty of normative positions, and lots of politics, and lots of opinions internally in research discussions. But it just remains in what is a closed space. And it doesn't really get out there, I think" (R02, p. 3).

A third researcher emphasises a similar want to contribute with research to society and to a public debate but highlights the role of translating and explaining complex data and research concerning Covid-19 to the population:

"We have really worked daily with all the data samples, tried to keep up, and we have been in expert committees and done many things. And I have really tried to make podcasts and statements as much as I possibly could, so I could help explain what was happening. I thought that was really important" (R04, p. 1).

This researcher also initially tried to explain and discuss with the most corona-sceptic citizens during the pandemic, as she believed it to be 'a matter of doubt' (R04, p.1). However, when the efforts proved to be ineffective, she discontinued them.

In general, this researcher thinks that she has been well represented in the media and has had a lot of 'airtime'. However, she has observed that the most distinguished traditional newspapers have opinions of their own, which sometimes complicates the interview and the written result, whereas she finds that the less well-reputed national media present her statements as she expresses them. Across interviews, the misrepresentation of researchers' work in the media does not come across as a major or consistent issue. However, three researchers explicitly mention examples of their work being framed or contextualized in misalignment with their intentions, and a fourth researcher also pointed to this issue as it was experienced by a colleague.

On this topic, one researcher point to the fact that she fact check her quotations but not the particular framing:

"My statements are, of course, presented and often taken out of context. We might have had a half-hour conversation, and then it becomes three sentences in a text, which also has a different focus. I experience that, but I always get my quotes to check. And that's fine. But I don't get to check the context (...). They convey my sentences, but they can be placed in a context that I might not always feel is the one I had envisioned my own sentence in. That's one thing. And then there's something else entirely. If it's a newspaper article, you can have... your text might be a small article over on the left, but the article

next to it with a big picture and catchy headline can go in a completely different direction. And suddenly you become, well... entangled in something that maybe wasn't where you initially stood" (R06, p. 3).

Another researcher provides the example of experiencing factual mistakes but also points to the experience of particular misnomer angling and the polemic tightening of a story as the most frustrating aspect of misrepresentation. According to the interviewee, this may explain why some researchers are hesitant to contribute to the public debate, particularly those employed in precarious positions. The researcher himself uses polemic discussion as a strategy to disseminate his perspectives but finds it problematic when it occurs without his consent.

Two interviewees points to another aspect of scientific representation in the media; the journalistic tendency to frame issues in a confrontational manner:

"I've had discussions with journalists who called me to confront me with an alternative viewpoint. And I've said, 'That is simply wrong. That's not a proper viewpoint.' Yes, people can have opinions, but this is actually a quantitative matter, something that can be known—like mathematics or something similar. (...) Why do we need to have two sides to this issue? It's completely insane. But other times, I've gone along with it because I can see that it's something where you can't just say 2 plus 2 equals 4. It's actually much more complicated" (R04, p. 3).

Nonetheless, the same researcher points to the importance of the media and stresses that she has had a well-functioning collaboration with journalists during the pandemic. The other researcher finds that - rather than a confrontational approach - a representation of different perspectives would provide 'a broader, deeper, more insightful picture of the reality we need to relate to' (R01, p. 7). A third aspect mentioned by the same researcher entails the occasional tendency for journalists to credit broadly to a 'professor' which underline an 'authoritative knowledge' but misses the important information of specific research areas and methods to fully understand the particular area of expertise.

The topic of authoritative expert knowledge also emerges as an issue of importance in researchers' perspectives on whether controversy around climate or Covid-19 research impacts public attitudes. Several researchers in both fields of research point to an ambiguity regarding research knowledge that may concurrently reduce and add to the polarization of public perceptions. A social science climate researcher states that citizens, on the one hand, are more than capable of understanding the presence of two opposing positions in

climate research but that it may enhance already existing and potentially negative views of research. A researcher in crisis communication points to a decrease in social media credibility, mentioning the concepts of 'hate holders' and 'faith holders' and the experience of polarization on social media, e.g., on the question of vaccination. At the same time, she mentions that citizens in Denmark generally understood the seriousness of the situation and that the use of humour in Danish Covid-19 media campaigns was successful as a dissemination and behaviour change strategy. A third researcher focusing on Covid-19 points to Danish research and data that show a relatively limited polarization in the Danish context on Covid-19 issues. This data indicates a large mainstream group and a small group of citizens who positioned themselves in a very sceptical stance compared to the general population.

A fourth researcher in climate research highlights another duality regarding authoritative knowledge vis-à-vis attitudinal polarization:

"On the one hand, expert knowledge is still a part of the public debate. And that expert knowledge somehow still carries an aura of objectivity and authority (...). I also believe that with the increasing polarization happening in the political landscape, both in Denmark and elsewhere, there is a growing perception in some circles that research is deeply political and ideological. There is a belief that there is an underlying agenda in much of the research communication aimed at influencing the political debate in certain directions, even when it comes from experts (...). So, I think that the tension, in which research communication finds itself, is between this expert role that tries to free itself from the political mud and, on the other hand, the communication that is already perceived as part of the mud and is therefore susceptible to political attacks and accusations of bias and so on (R02, p. 8).

Experts generally seem to agree that the media has a profound and important role to play in the way science is represented to the broader public and in enhancing public trust in science (please see section 4.4).

4.3 About the integration of citizens in research

The six researchers are involved in citizen engagement with science in different ways and to various extents (please also see Table 11). Two researchers do not integrate citizens into their current research activities. One of these researchers plans to involve citizens in

future research projects if they are funded, highlighting the positives of "trying to create change together with the partners one collaborates with" (R02, p.9). The other researcher states that he has not given it much thought but could envision using citizen science activities since this is a well-known engagement format within his area of research. Two other researchers are highly engaged in involving citizens in their work; one through co-creation activities with local citizens and CSOs concerning climate issues and the improvement of local policies and governance approaches as part of two European projects. The other researcher does not apply public engagement methods as part of her research but is highly engaged in science dissemination and public debates through a range of dialogue events. The two remaining researchers are engaged to some extent in involving citizens in their research. One involves different stakeholders and businesses in the data collection process as research subjects. The other researcher occasionally collaborates with native Greenlanders to draw on their specialist knowledge and experience. She has also taken part in a sound recording citizen science project as a citizen participant.

Researchers generally express a positive view towards citizen involvement in science. Still, two researchers also explicitly mention that the relevance of citizen involvement depends on the particular research question and research project:

"So depending on your research question, citizen science can be a good idea. That is, a really good idea, to obtain some of the tacit knowledge, or the inaccessible knowledge, that many citizens possess" (R01, p. 9).

"I think it depends on what you are studying. I mean, if you want to study how citizens react to something, then it makes sense to involve them. And one of the ways we involve them is when we study a crisis. Then we also study the reactions and statements during a crisis" (R06, p. 5).

The first researcher (R01) questions whether citizen involvement activities enhance general public trust in science. Another climate researcher points to an initiative during the Danish Science Festival where groups of citizens can 'order' a talk from a researcher. The researcher believes that such in-person lecture/dialogue events could increase public trust in science.

Two other researchers express more explicit doubt, both mentioning that 'it can go both ways' in terms of increasing trust:

"I think it can go both ways, you know. Let's say I do a project with climate activists; how would the right wing in Denmark perceive such a project? They would probably see it as part of

the muddle, where our research and politics are completely intertwined. (...) That's where I see some problems too, you know, the idea that there exists a space where we can all step in and at some point agree on the best solution for, for example, the climate. I don't really believe in that" (R02, p. 9).

But in terms of trust, I don't know. Whether it creates trust in research by doing it, I really don't know. I think it can go both ways. I believe many would be quite shocked at how unstructured and how little 'laboratories' there are in a lot of research (...). In other settings, I also think people might be completely, well. I think within our field, social sciences and humanities, many would be surprised at how - what do you call it - unbiased researchers are in their approach (R05, p. 20).

Both researchers emphasize political differences as a barrier to whether citizen involvement in science has the potential to increase trust in science. In relation to specific obstacles for involving citizens in research, it is mentioned that it is resource-demanding in terms of work and administration (R02); that the quality of citizen-collected data might be reduced and uncertainties increased; and that citizen science in some areas, for instance in climate research, might be challenging to implement (R03). Additionally, some research subjects might be difficult for citizens to be involved in (R04).

4.4 About public trust in science

Researchers point to a number of citizen concerns about science, observed either through their field of research or through general observations. Interviewees link these concerns to the products of science rather than the conduct of science. As the following quotations highlight, citizens might question the truth of what is presented to them if contradictory research findings are provided or if findings contradict their beliefs and desires. An example of this is climate research, where the research-established need to change our consumer habits and use of resources is not welcomed by many citizens according to the climate researcher.

"In the climate debate, we clearly experience a situation where researchers and citizens are somehow in opposition. As researchers, we are trying to tell citizens, almost shouting at them through a megaphone, that they need to act differently and make changes. Meanwhile, the citizens just respond like this

[shows a middle finger]. So, I clearly see a conflict there.” (R02, p. 11).

“There are those who don't believe they are being told the truth. That can be difficult” (R04, p. 9).

This researcher also highlights the confusing aspects for citizens when non-Covid-19 experts comment as experts or when disagreements among Covid-19 experts arise. Drawing on Ulrich Beck's thesis on risk society and the effect of invisible risks on expert dependency, another researcher addresses the issue of expertise, noting that some experts are trusted while others are not. This creates increasingly polarized views and opposing arguments, intensified by modern communication technology, on matters such as Covid-19 vaccines and climate change. It is also mentioned that the sheer amount of information and impressions tends to keep citizens in certain camps, and many do not trust expert knowledge unless it is 'massive' and characterized by a high degree of consensus.

“I think their [citizens] concern is the classic one: “Well, they will come up with something new tomorrow, so can we trust what they say today?” I don't know how widespread this is, but it's what everyone seems to think citizens are thinking. But I don't know how common it is in reality. And I believe there is a really, really big difference between rural and urban areas, and I think there's a big difference in - how should I put it - one's social capital in relation to this, and one's experience with the education system” (R01, p. 11).

In the last quotation from a climate researcher, geographical, educational, and social capital differences are emphasized as potential factors influencing citizens' concerns about research. Another researcher mentions a difference in levels of self-efficacy as affecting the type and extent of research dissemination requested and consequently impacting trust in science:

“Those who have lower self-efficacy - that is, confidence in their ability to understand research - do not seek answers about what is happening, but rather answers on how they should act in the situation, what they should do in that situation” (R05, p.17).

Three researchers explicitly point to the representation of science by politicians and the media as significant factors that may influence public trust in science. One example mentioned is that some politicians have named specific researchers as conducting poor

research due to their field of study, which is seen as eroding trust in research. Additionally, the devaluation of higher education by some politicians in favour of vocational education is cited as a discursive representation that may undermine public trust in research. The following quote illustrates the important aspect of science representation and the observation that citizens are increasingly concerned and feeling unsafe, which also influences the level of trust according to the researcher:

"I think it's the amount of things happening around us. The lack of control, self-control, also plays a role. We are incredibly influenced by threats. Notions of something serious that could happen make us highly influenced by the media. We are greatly affected by the discourses from politicians and also by social media. Right now, I think citizens are extremely concerned about geopolitical issues, and climate problems are extremely prominent(...).We talk so much about citizenship and social responsibility today. We do this because citizens and consumers have become much more concerned than they were in the past" (R06, p. 8).

This researcher also highlights the 'Velcro effect' in crisis research, indicating that a history of crises can create an increasingly negative reputation and expectation. For example, a university and its researchers might suffer from several scandals. Another example mentioned is that consistent claims of researchers being biased might result in researchers withdrawing from disseminating their research.

4.5 Other themes

All interview themes have been addressed in the sections above, including the topic of public trust in experts and expert knowledge, which emerged as a distinct cross-cutting theme across researcher interviews.

4.6 Synthesis of recommendations

Researchers' recommendations on how to enhance public trust in science align with several topics raised during the interviews. Media and politicians have an important role to play in how they represent science, as highlighted by interviewees, and several recommendations include the discursive framing of how knowledge is disseminated and validated by these stakeholders.

- It is recommended that the media focus on fact-checking and verifying scientific expert knowledge and how it is received and used politically to secure high standards of knowledge dissemination and avoid intentional inaccurate representation.
- It is also suggested that politicians refrain from dismissing research that does not match their political agendas.
- It is suggested to avoid contrasting vocational education with higher education from primary school onwards and to rather accommodate diversity. Greater emphasis on teaching children to be critical and to 'teach children to learn' is also suggested.
- Relatedly, it is advised that politicians should avoid negatively framing the field of communication as a profession less important than frontline workers, as this contributes to decreasing trust in communicators (in Denmark this is often articulating as warm vs. cold hands).

Researchers focus their attention on enhancing the involvement of citizens in research rather than on matters related to research ethics and research integrity. For instance, researchers suggest to:

- A greater focus should be given to exploring how citizens and other stakeholders - e.g., those engaged with art and culture - could be involved in research, broadening the concept of involvement to support and strengthen research-based knowledge.
- Relatedly, researchers should increase their awareness of their study sample strategies, ensuring greater representation rather than researching groups akin to the researcher in question.
- Influencers could be a group of mediators potentially enhancing trust in science.
- Researchers could also explore new and other ways of communicating science, e.g., by communicating knowledge in a more pragmatic and solution-oriented way. It is also proposed to increase researcher presence in direct and face-to-face research dissemination.
- Science communication should receive greater acknowledgement within the academic system.

Recommendations proposed by researchers address various main targets, including individual researchers, citizens, politicians, research

performing institutions, media, and the educational and political systems. These recommendations can be summarized as follows to improve public trust in science:

Overall Researcher Recommendations
The media and politicians should pay great attention to science representation and to how scientific information is verified, received and used politically, ensuring that knowledge dissemination meets high standards and avoids intentional misrepresentation.
Attention should be focused on avoiding a negative framing of science and a political devaluing of higher education and the field of (science) communication.
A greater focus should be given to exploring how citizens and other stakeholders could be involved in research, broadening the concept of involvement to support and strengthen research-based knowledge.
Researchers should explore methods of communicating science in novel, pragmatic, and solution-oriented ways, while also increasing their presence in face-to-face dissemination. The academic system should place greater emphasis on the importance of science communication.

5 Conclusion

As part of the Danish expert interview study, 10 interviews with mediators and 6 interviews with researchers were conducted to explore how knowledge and science dissemination between research and citizens takes place and to gather recommendations on approaches to increase public trust in science.

Interviews with mediators suggest that while a traditional mediation model still exists, it does not capture the reality, complexity, and multiple translation processes within the Danish science communication landscape. Overall, mediators do not position themselves firmly within a prescriptive chain of mediation; instead, they act as more autonomous actors trying to bridge the relationship between science and society. Mediators emphasize credibility in their work and high institutional legitimacy as important aspects in the process of transforming scientific inputs into products. Other aspects include thorough research, valid results, reliable source referencing, a critical approach, and maintaining independence to avoid potential conflicts of interest. The importance of researcher independence and impartial research is also mentioned, which aligns

with the findings from the deliberative workshop with citizens (please see section 1.2).

Most mediators engage with citizens directly or indirectly through social media, blog posts, podcasts, articles, and email comments. Some mediators have also taken part in public dialogue events or citizen science projects as part of their present or former positions. On the topic of how they define research integrity and ethics and integrate principles into own practices, mediators generally do not use the specific terminology of research ethics and research integrity but still apply the concepts in alignment with field-specific understandings and definitions of research integrity, in particular. Mediators include a large number of research integrity principles and practices related to the themes of research practices, research collaboration, and research publication and practices. In relation to their own work, mediators highlight overlapping principles in how research studies/sources for instance are critically assessed according to methodological transparency, validity and soundness of results and disclosure of potential conflicts of interests.

Mediators generally exhibit high awareness and familiarity with public trust in science, considering it an essential aspect of their professional role. Similar to the previous studies (section 1.2) they do not identify a general crisis of trust but highlight areas of concern that may decrease public trust in science, such as having to navigate a complex media landscape partly characterised by disinformation and conflicting science representations. Mediators provide a long list of recommendations to enhance trust in science, summarised in the following five suggestions:

Overall Mediator Recommendations
Enhance transparency and quality in research communication through upholding impartial research, implementing rigorous quality checks and disseminating processual and methodological explanations.
Formalize stakeholder inclusion at universities and encourage more citizen science and public engagement activities.
Bridge the gap between researchers and mediators and build co-partnerships. Place greater priority and value on science communication activities within academia, and support researchers in engaging with the public with a focus on effective communication.
Engage in direct dialogue with the audience, reduce the gap between science mediators and the public, and use their preferred platforms and channels for communication.
Place a higher priority on covering research in the media and put greater emphasis on explaining the value of science.

The interviews with researchers in climate and Covid-19 research found that public debates and controversies surrounding Covid-19 and climate change have impacted researchers' work in various ways.

All researchers agree on the importance of research dissemination, and they engage with the public through diverse channels such as written media, social media, TV/radio, podcasts, public talks, and participation in dialogues. Generally, researchers emphasize the significant role that media and politicians play in science representation, consequently affecting public trust in science.

Overall, misrepresentation of researchers' work in the media does not emerge as a major or consistent issue across interviews, but several researchers mention instances of their work being framed or contextualized in ways that misalign with their intentions.

Researchers identify citizen concerns toward science as stemming from research outputs disseminated in contradictory ways or conflicting with personal beliefs or desires, potentially leading to uncertainty about the truth of the knowledge and research findings presented. In this regard, authoritative expert knowledge emerges as a main issue in how climate and Covid-19 research controversies impact public attitudes. Several researchers note that ambiguity in research knowledge and in the role and objectivity of experts can both reduce and increase the polarization of public perceptions.

The six researchers are involved in citizen engagement with science in different ways and to varying extents, ranging from none to extensive engagement. Overall, researchers express a positive view towards citizen involvement in science, though two explicitly mention that its relevance depends on the research question. Despite the general positive stance, several researchers express doubt as to whether citizen involvement can increase trust in science. Political differences are mentioned as one obstacle along with challenges related to resource allocation and data quality.

Researchers provide several recommendations related to increasing public trust in science through science representation and citizen involvement, summarized according to the following four suggestions:

Overall Researcher Recommendations
The media and politicians should pay great attention to science representation and to how scientific information is verified, received and used politically, ensuring that knowledge dissemination meets high standards and avoids intentional misrepresentation.
Attention should be focused on avoiding a negative framing of science and a political devaluing of higher education and the field of (science) communication.

A greater focus should be given to exploring how citizens and other stakeholders could be involved in research, broadening the concept of involvement to support and strengthen research-based knowledge.

Researchers should explore methods of communicating science in novel, pragmatic, and solution-oriented ways, while also increasing their presence in face-to-face dissemination. The academic system should place greater emphasis on the importance of science communication.

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poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Expert Interviews - *France*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

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Lead partner for this deliverable: *CSIC*

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1 Acknowledgement

The French POIESIS team would like to express its sincere gratitude to the 20 experts contacted in the course of the research presented in this report. All of them, whether communication officers, science journalists, science popularisers or researchers, generously shared their valuable time and insights during the interviews. Their expertise and perspectives have been instrumental in shaping the findings of this study.

2 Introduction

This section describes the various elements associated with the completion of POIESIS task 2.3 by the French team. This task was carried out between May 2024 and August 2024, immediately following the writing of the national and synthesis report for task 3.1. (See deliverable 3.2 - Focus Groups - Findings. Exploring Institutional Roles in Fostering Public Trust in Science).

2.1 General and specific research questions

Task 2.3. essentially consisted of conducting semi-structured sociological interviews with a target group of experts. Some of the research questions that guided these expert interviews were general:

- 1) To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science? (POIESIS RQ2);
- 2) To what extent and how does the *integration* of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?

Some others research questions were more specific:

- 3) How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?
- 4) Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?
- 5) What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

2.2 Insights from previous tasks

In the French case, the previous tasks have highlighted the importance of the collective sense of a crisis of trust between science and society. Although this belief is not objectively supported by opinion surveys such as *Les français et la science 2021*¹, it is very influential in the public debate.

¹ See the report of the 8th wave of this national survey, https://www.science-and-you.com/sites/science-and-you.com/files/users/documents/les_francais_et_la_science_2021_-_rapport_de_recherche_web_v29112021_v2.pdf

The public deliberative workshop (task 2.2) has highlighted the complexity of the issue of generating trust. French participants particularly valued transparency in research processes and accepted that doubt is intrinsic to research. They mentioned the possibility that citizen participation could boost trust in science, but with the risk that this trust would only concern the most aware part of the population. While transparency was generally seen as a trust builder, it could paradoxically also seed distrust. Some participants argued that too much transparency might reveal instances of malpractice or fraud, negatively impacting public trust in science. Participants also expressed distrust arising from sensationalized announcements and unfulfilled promises. They underscored the inherent conflict between the long-term nature of scientific research and the media's haste to disseminate information. the complexity of the issue of generating trust. Participants also voiced concerns over compromised integrity due to conflicts of interest, unwarranted political affiliations, over-promised expectations, and occasionally, the questionable roles of certain institutions. A breach in a researcher's ethics was cited as a hallmark of integrity deficit.

The three focus groups held with institutional stakeholders (task 3.2) helped identifying possible courses of action in the French context. The following 6 actions were described as collective priorities: 1) developing a massive public communication strategy to promote science and critical thinking on social networks, seeing them as an "informational war zone"; 2) organising small-scale events to create and cultivate the link between citizens and scientists; 3) radically change the culture of research organisations when it comes to the handling of scientific misconduct: from secrecy to transparency; 4) changing the evaluation culture in science by giving priority to collective success over individual success, to quality over quantity; 5) training the entire scientific community in the values of scientific integrity, including senior researchers; 6) encouraging scientific institutions to address the tensions and conflicting imperatives they contribute to generate.

2.3 Brief summary of organising the interviews

A total of 20 experts interviews were conducted, 4 more than what was expected in the protocol. The first interview took place on 7 June 2024 and the last on 10 July 2024. The addition of 4 extra interviews is mostly due to the fact that some experts gave us the opportunity to contact people who were not initially planned.

The month of May 2024 was used to identify and solicit experts. Experts were selected on the basis of the nature of their expertise, their visibility and any pre-existing relationships with the investigators. Initial contact was generally made by email, describing the nature of the project and the interview setting. Out of a total of 20 interviews, 18 were conducted online with the zoom app provided by the French national research organization (CNRS) and 2 face-to-face with a digital recorder.

The composition of our expert population is as follows: 6 researchers, 8 non-institutional mediators, 6 institutional mediators.

The 6 researchers contacted have all worked in recent years or spoken publicly on the topics of Covid19 or climate change (3 researchers for each topic). It should be noted that given the time constraints associated with this task, it was not possible to conduct an interview with a social scientist.

The interviews generally lasted around 60 minutes and were conducted in pairs by the French POIESIS partners, with two exceptions: a 30 minutes interview due to an unforeseen change in availability of the expert and a 2 hours interview with a researcher. Some experts, particularly communication officers, sometimes expressed surprise at being asked to be interviewed and sometimes doubted their ability to make a useful contribution to the research. The conditions under which the interviews were conducted were excellent and most interviewees asked to be kept informed of the progress of the project.

We had no particular difficulty with the interview guide. The main difficulty has been practical: transcribing and analysing the qualitative data in time.

2.4 Data processing

The recorded interviews were all stored on Sorbonne University's DropSU repository website. This institutional website is currently the most suitable for guaranteeing data security. It should be noted that the CNRS has just opened a new SDrive website, which will benefit from the same security measures for data transfer and management.

The French team produced a verbatim transcript of the 20 interviews. All transcriptions were made in the original national language. Using computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS/NVivo), the data from the transcripts was then coded using a common coding scheme provided by the coordinator of the task.

The two coding schemes – one for the mediators, one for the researchers – are reproduced below.

Coding scheme for Mediators

Parent Codes	Child Codes	Description
Research ethics and integrity	REI_definition [M1]	Mediators' description of what they understand by REI
	REI_work [M2]	Mediators' description of how REI or REI-related issues are relevant to, or part of, their work
	REI_assess [M3]	Mediators' description of how they assess or evaluate the credibility of scientific information they use in their work
	REI_case [M4]	Mediators' experiences of REI issues related to the Covid-19 or Climate Change cases

Public trust in science	Pubtrust_contrib [M5]	Mediators' perspectives on the contribution that their work makes to the science-society relationship
	Pubtrust_pubatt [M6]	Mediators' perspectives on the impact of news of scientific fraud and misconduct on public attitudes
	Pubtrust_own [M7]	Mediators' experience of fraud or misconduct impacting on their own work, including their response
	Recomm_pubtrust [M8]	Mediators' recommendations for improving public trust in science
	Recomm_young [M9]	Mediators' recommendations for improving public trust in science among younger 'social media' generation

Coding scheme for researchers

Parent code	Child code	Description
Science communication	Scicom_channels [R1]	Channels or Mediators through which Researchers' work is presented
	Scicom_presentation [R2]	Researchers' perceptions about qualities of presentation of their work
	Scicom_response [R3]	Researchers' responses to, and/or sentiments regarding, poor or mis-representation of their work
	Scicom_impact [R4]	Researchers' perceptions about how public controversy impacts public attitudes
Social integration	Socint_recognition [R5]	Researchers' awareness of, and perspective on, citizen participation in research
	Socint_rationale [R6]	Rationales underlying Researchers' views on citizen integration, positive or negative
	Socint_ownact [R7]	Modes or activities that connect citizens to Researchers' own work
	Socint_ownvol [R8]	Frequency or scale of Researchers' interaction with citizens
	Socint_owncyc [R9]	Connection of Researchers' interactions with citizens to phases of the research cycle
	Socint_owncit [R10]	Types or groups of citizens involved in Researchers' own work
	Socint_ownbest [R11]	Researchers' opinions on the most effective or appropriate way(s) to integrate or interact with citizens
	Socint_barriers [R12]	Researchers' perceptions of barriers or obstacles to greater integration of citizens in research
Public trust in science	Pubtrust_concern [R13]	Researchers' experience or perceptions that citizens' do have concerns about science
	Pubtrust_conduct [R14]	Researchers report concerns expressed by citizens about the conduct of science

	Pubtrust_outputs [R15]	Researchers report concerns expressed by citizens about the products or impacts of science (and technology)
	Pubtrust_other [R16]	Researchers report other concerns expressed by citizens
	Pubtrust_rationale [R17]	Rationales or explanatory factors used by Researchers to explain challenges to maintaining trust, or rising distrust, in science among citizens
	Pubtrust_challenge[R18]	Researchers' perceptions about whether the conduct of science or the context for communicating science is the biggest challenge for maintaining or enhancing public trust (or something else)
Synthesis of recommendations	Recomm_socint [R19]	Researchers' recommendations related to social integration in science
	Recomm_REI [R20]	Researchers' recommendations related to research ethics and integrity
	Recomm_other [R21]	Researchers' other recommendations

These coding schemes were intended to draw our attention to a number of themes that are expected for the analysis developed in the following sections of this report, but these themes are not of equal importance or frequency. Some themes may not have appeared, and conversely some themes that emerged during the interviews gave rise to the production of new codes.

3 Participants in the Expert Interview study

This section describes the main characteristics of the experts interviewed.

3.1 Descriptive tables

3.2 Mediators

Table 1. Demographics and occupation (grey background: institutional mediators ; white background: non institutional mediators)

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Mediator type**	Organization type (where applicable)	Occupational Description	Topic CV/CC#
FR_M01	F	Mid	Communication officer	RPO	Head of internal communication	CV
FR_M02	M	Early	Communication officer	RPO	Communications director of a regional delegation	CV
FR_M03	F	Early	Press officer	RPO	Responsible for press communication	CV
FR_M04	F	Senior	Communication officer	Office for research integrity	Integrity communication officer	
FR_M05	H	Early	Author of science-related blog	University	Co-founder of a platform for science blogging	
FR_M06	H	Mid	Journalist	Newspaper (print & online)	Journalist specialized in science and environmental issues	CC
FR_M07	H	Early	Journalist	Newspaper (print & online)	Journalist specialized in science with a strong focus on covid	CV
FR_M08	F	Mid	Communication officer	Research organization	Head of the Press Office	CV-CC
FR_M09	F	Mid	Communication officer	Research organization	Communication director of a national research institute in social sciences	
FR_M10	H	Senior	Science populariser	RPO	Former scientist now working as scientific mediator	
FR_M11	F	Early	Science populariser	Newspaper (print & online)	Designer and host of popular science videos	CV, CC
FR_M12	H	Early	Science populariser	Online platform	Designer and host of popular science videos	CC
FR_M13	F	Early	Journalist	Radio	Journalist specialized in science and technology	CV, CC
FR_M14	H	Mid	Journalist	Newspaper (print & online)	Journalist specialized in science and environmental issues	CV, CC

Table 2. Mediators' main communication tasks

Id.	Description of mediators' main tasks
FR_M01	Developing communication modalities adapted to RPO strategy. Producing online articles for a large professional community associated with a national research organization
FR_M02	Developing communication modalities adapted to RPO strategy. Producing science news articles, making online videos, producing science outreach games, organization of events bringing scientists into contact with the general public
FR_M03	Developing communication modalities adapted to RPO strategy. Communicating with the general public media, popularising scientific work to make it accessible to journalists, putting journalists and scientists in touch with each other.
FR_M04	Providing resources to scientific integrity officers, raising awareness of scientific integrity issues within the scientific community
FR_M05	Writing articles about how science works - creator of a professional platform of science blogs
FR_M06	Writing articles about scientific actualities with a specific focus on environmental issues
FR_M07	Writing articles about scientific actualities with a specific focus on covid and health issues
FR_M08	Developing communication modalities adapted to RPO strategy. Popularising scientific work to make it accessible to journalists, putting journalists and scientists in touch with each other, Communicating with the general public media
FR_M09	Developing communication modalities adapted to RPO strategy ; producing online articles about RPO scientific actualities ; popularising scientific work to make it accessible to journalists, putting journalists and scientists in touch with each other.
FR_M10	Developing scientific mediation strategies centred on IT; intervening in educational circles and associations
FR_M11	Producing popular science videos
FR_M12	Producing popular science videos ; talks or conferences in a variety of contexts (schools, companies, associations, etc.)
FR_M13	With a daily segment on a national radio, presenting the latest scientific news
FR_M14	Writing articles about scientific actualities with a specific focus on environmental issues

Table 3. Outputs produced by Mediators

Id.	Books	Articles	Audiovisual (TV)	Radio program	Podcast	Audiovisual (social media)	Post (Social media)*	Live (social media interaction)	Other: (please describe in a few words only)
FR_M01									
FR_M02									Science outreach games
FR_M03									Graphic novel
FR_M04									
FR_M05									
FR_M06									
FR_M07									
FR_M08									
FR_M09									
FR_M10									Interventions in schools and associations
FR_M11									
FR_M12									
FR_M13									
FR_M14									

*Includes memes, photographs, videos and text

Table 4. Channels used by Mediators

Id.	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)						Chat apps		Other: (please describe in a few words only)
	TV	Radio	Newspaper	Websites	Blogs	Newsletters	LinkedIn	YouTube	Twitter	Instagram	TikTok	Other SN	WhatsApp	Telegram	
FR_M01															
FR_M02															
FR_M03															
FR_M04															
FR_M05															Mastodon
FR_M06															
FR_M07															Facebook
FR_M08															
FR_M09															
FR_M10															
FR_M11															
FR_M12															
FR_M13															
FR_M14															

Table 5. Audience addressed by Mediators

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' audiences/size estimate where known
FR_M01	Around 150,000 people (RPO professional community)
FR_M02	The general public in the Paris area
FR_M03	General public, with a particular focus on audiences unfamiliar with scientific culture
FR_M04	Three types of audience: science journalists, scientific integrity officers, the scientific community.
FR_M05	The scientific community and the general public with an interest in science
FR_M06	National audience reading the press (print or online)
FR_M07	National audience reading the press (print or online)
FR_M08	General public, with a particular focus on journalists
FR_M09	RPO professional community, science journalists and the general public
FR_M10	Schools and associations in south-east France ; general audience
FR_M11	General public, with a particular focus on audiences unfamiliar with scientific culture, teenagers and young adults
FR_M12	General public, with a particular focus on audiences unfamiliar with scientific culture, teenagers and young adults
FR_M13	The general public listening to national cultural radio early in the morning
FR_M14	National audience reading the press (print or online)

Table 6. Mediators' interactions with citizens

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' social interaction practices
FR_M01	No direct interaction
FR_M02	Interaction through scientific outreach events such as film debates or exhibitions.
FR_M03	No direct interaction
FR_M04	No direct interaction
FR_M05	Interaction through reader's comments
FR_M06	Interaction through reader's comments
FR_M07	Interaction through reader's comments
FR_M08	No direct interaction
FR_M09	Interaction through reader's comments
FR_M10	Direct interaction with secondary school students during presentations in schools or associations
FR_M11	Interaction through viewer's comments
FR_M12	Interaction through viewer's comments
FR_M13	Interaction through listeners and reader's comments
FR_M14	Interaction through reader's comments

Table 7. Mediators' sources of information

Id.	Interpersonal networks		Science literature	Science press releases		Mainstream media	Social media	Other: (please add text)
	With researchers	With science communicators		RPOs	Publishers			
FR_M01								RPO Scientific leadership
FR_M02								RPO Scientific leadership
FR_M03								RPO Scientific leadership
FR_M04								
FR_M05								
FR_M06								
FR_M07								
FR_M08								RPO Scientific leadership
FR_M09								RPO Scientific leadership
FR_M10								
FR_M11								
FR_M12								
FR_M13								
FR_M14								

3.3 Researchers

Table 8. Description of the Researcher interviews sample

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Position or title/Career stage**	Organisation type	Topic CV/CC#
FR_R01	M	Senior	Senior research fellow	Public research institute	CV / CC
FR_R02	M	Senior	Senior research fellow	Public research institute	CV
FR_R03	M	Early	Junior research fellow	Public research institute	CC
FR_R04	M	Early	Assistant professor	Public research institute	
FR_R05	M	Early	Assistant professor	University	
FR_R06	F	Senior	Emeritus professor	University	

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior ** ECR; recognised researcher; senior researcher; leading researcher (Professor)

Table 9. Researcher notes

Id.	Note
FR_R01	Biophysicist, team director in a biology institute - highly involved in science and society issues
FR_R02	Biologist specialised in the study of coronavirus - involved in the controversy surrounding the origins of the Covid crisis
FR_R03	Astrophysicist - highly involved in the public debate about climate issues
FR_R04	Researcher initially trained in epidemiology - chair in Global change and health - highly involved in science and society issues
FR_R05	Specialist in data processing and visualization - heavily involved in detecting fraud associated with the covid period
FR_R06	Professor of developmental psychology - heavily involved in detecting scientific fraud

Table 10. How Researchers work with the public

Id.	Brief description of how the researchers' work reaches the public
FR_R01	Through extra academic publications, expertise reports and a strong commitment in science & society associations
FR_R02	Through publications channels promoted on social media
FR_R03	Through his involvement in an association of scientists that makes public visibility an objective in its own right
FR_R04	Through his involvement in an association of scientists that makes public visibility an objective in its own right
FR_R05	Through publications channels promoted on social media ; strong presence on social networks
FR_R06	Blogging and social networking

Table 6. Description of social integration practices of Researchers

Id.	Brief notes of Researchers' social integration practices
FR_R01	Participation in multiple citizen science associations
FR_R02	Articles in the mainstream media, through participation in events such as the Fête de la science
FR_R03	High-profile media campaigns to raise public awareness on climate issues, involvement in climate related associations.
FR_R04	Participation in multiple citizen science associations and high-profile media campaigns to raise public awareness on climate issues
Fr_R05	Articles in the mainstream media and social media
FR_R06	Blog, articles in the mainstream media and social media

4 Analysis of Mediator interviews

This section provides an initial analysis of the interviews conducted with the mediators. As mentioned above, this population can be broken down into two main categories: 6 institutional mediators and 8 non-institutional mediators, i.e. a total of 14 experts.

The institutional mediators (group 1) are mostly communication or press relations officers in research organisations or agencies involved in promoting research integrity in France. The group of non-institutional mediators can be divided into two subgroups of equal size: 4 science popularisers (group 2a) and 4 science journalists (group 2b).

It is important to note that each group may have collaborative and sometimes antagonistic relationships with the other two groups in the pursuit of their professional objectives.

Group 1 members, generally associated with a strong reputational stake – promoting the brand of their research organisation –, systematically seek to capture the attention of Group 2b and may develop collaborations with members of Group 2a.

Group 2a members generally aim to make scientific information and, more generally, the research process comprehensible to the general public, with a specific focus on the younger part of the population. They distance themselves from the communication codes used by Group 1 and may use the output of Group 2b as a source of information for their work.

The members of Group 2b present science news to their readers or listeners, but also aim to produce original investigations on a scientific and technological topics. They distance themselves from the communication codes used by group 2a and may use the production of group 1 as a source of information for their own work.

4.1 Chains of mediation

The relational dimension of the concept of “mediation chain” leads us to focus on four dimensions of the experts' activity: 1) the sources and resources used to carry out their activity, 2) the evaluation of the reliability of these sources and resources, 3) the creative work of processing information, 4) the evaluation of the quality of the work and its dissemination.

We discuss these four dimensions for each of the three groups identified above. Given that qualitative research is concerned with detailing situations, we have chosen to quote extracts from interviews.

Group 1. As the members of the first group generally aim to promote the research done in their research organisation, and beyond that the

public image of this organisation, the question of the origin of sources seems inseparable from that of their reliability. The sources are internal to the organisation - researchers, research units, internal management - and the validation of these sources is also carried out internally, most often through an internal scientific authority.

(...) when there is a research result to promote and publicise, there is a process that is the same for everyone. There has to be scientific validation by the institute. And scientific validation means that (...) for example for a result in [...], we go and see the deputy scientific director in charge of [...], we say "Oh, we've received this result, what do you think of it? Do we publicise it or not?" So, whether the results comes to us from the delegation, from the communication office, or from the lab, the process is the same, it'll be the same ... no one will work individually I think. [FR_M09]

We receive proposals that can come from the head of our organisation, from institutes and from different departments when I'm speaking internally. So when I'm talking about this aspect... We'll make sure that the topic has already been scientifically validated by the department to which the people involved in this research report. [FR_M08]

Group 1 is associated with the production of online articles or press releases written for journalists, with the idea that the latter will be a conduit to the general public. This "editorial" work is often carried out by a small group of 2 or 3 people, some of whom may be more specifically responsible for a particular aspect of institutional communication, such as the RPO's presence on social media. While certain topics are imposed, the members of Group 1 generally have a certain amount of freedom in the choice of formats. Some opt for producing multiple 'scientist portrait', which make it easier to embody research results:

(...) We did a very interesting portrait of a researcher who started out as a dentist, who began his career working in prison, and who at the same time was a rugby fan and continued to be a rugby referee. So that's the kind of personality we like... we like to show this diversity and this kind of commitment, to show that a passion for research also means working with disadvantaged people, with prisoners. [FR_M01]

Group 1 is also frequently involved in organising institutional events or cycles of events. This activity, which was mostly interrupted during the Covid period, can take a wide variety of forms, from an awards ceremony to a film-debate session. But the experts frequently stress the importance of renewing the formats of these events by giving priority to interactive situations.

(...) we realise that all the events where (...) interaction is proposed, both between the participants and the researcher, but

also between the participants themselves, are going to be formats that work much better than formats without interaction (...) it encourages people to ask questions (...) and perhaps also to take the step of signing up and taking part. [FR_M02]

Finally, when it comes to evaluating the work carried out and, more importantly, disseminating it to the target audience, the members of Group 1 rely heavily on different types of quantitative indicators: the number of views generated by an article, the ratio between the number of people registered for an event and the number of people present, the number of retweets when they use Twitter, various statistics from the website, etc. For ethical reasons, some experts may refuse to trace online users, but they soon find it difficult to assess the success of their communication:

That's a very good question, because we're actually a little bit stuck (...) We're committed to not tracking subscribers. But obviously, the other side of the coin is that we don't have the read rates. When we first started using the tool, we thought "gosh, it's going to give us that" and we blocked all those functions because we didn't want to be involved in that. So it's a bit difficult to measure... [FR_M04]

But beyond the use of quantitative indicators, particular importance is attached to the number of mentions by journalists, who are the prime target of Group 1. These journalistic mentions are presented as proof of a job 'well done' or 'completed', which allows a topic to exist in the public arena.

Group 2.a. Group 2.a differs from Group 1 in the degree of freedom it enjoys in its choice of topics and treatments. There is no institutional authority to say what can or cannot be covered, no institutional brand to promote, but often a search for a balance between scientific actuality, perceived public expectations and personal interest. This personal interest can evolve over time and partly redirect the activity of popularising science, as in the case of this populariser on YouTube initially specialized in environmental issues:

And then at a certain point, I said to myself (...): well, the environment, I love that, but there are already about fifty videos on my channel (...) you can find new topics of course, all the time, but the passion wasn't really there any more (...) I was learning less on a daily basis (...) and so I said to myself "come on, I'll switch to all the sciences". So now I'm learning a lot more. But I spend more time making the videos. [FR_M12]

Beyond the question of personal interest, the members of group 2a often have some initial training in science and technology and can easily use scientific newsletter, research reports or even research articles as resources for their own work. These resources are

identified through monitoring work carried out via general media, but more often via social media. The members of group 2.a are also aware that they are part of a collective and do not hesitate to interact with members of the collective if necessary:

(...) scientific publications are also a source for me, even if they're not yet popularised (...) it's a first step towards popularisation (...) let's just say that I'm a subscriber to the Science and Nature newsletters, for example, which gives me the latest news on what's being done, a bit of information on what's happening in the field of science at the moment, what's been published, the latest things (...) And then also in the community of popularisers, there's also mutual aid in the sense that we can ask for proofreading or say "here, I've seen this topic go by, what do you think? I'm not a specialist. Do you think it's important? I'd like to look at it from my angle... my speciality, my way of dealing with things". We can identify information that is circulating (...) [FR_M11]

The identification of useful information is usually accompanied by a reflection on its significance, but also on its reliability or ability to achieve consensus within the scientific community:

The issue of consensus is something that's often an important point when approaching a topic (...) When I work in a team, if we know that we have something to talk about, if we know that (...) scientists are more or less all in agreement, we'll start with that topic. That doesn't mean that you can't mention opposing views, and it doesn't mean that you can't mention certain things that are still being developed or on which there is no consensus, if that's not the focus of the topic. [FR_M11]

When science popularisation work is done online, with videos, an important part of the activity is to define the format or the essential elements to achieve the most effective visual communication. To the extent that the target audience is a broad public not necessarily familiar with science and technology, this means thinking about the choice of words and images to be used and made understandable. For one of the experts, it also means introducing an interactive dimension by carrying out vox pops in which passers-byers are asked whether or not they believe in a particular idea related to the topic in question. For another expert, it means combining scientific results with humorous scenarios to break down the image of a cold and impersonal science.

When it comes to popularising science on site, for example in school classes or associations, one needs to draw on professional experience as well as a good knowledge of the public, as is the case with this expert in computer science and artificial intelligence:

For example, how do I explain ChatGPT? I don't do the phonetic joke that you can guess, but what I do is say "it's very simple, the mouse is eaten by the..." So children often answer "cat". It

could be "tiger" but it's cat. The "sky" is... "blue" and so on. I tell them "well, it's a thing that predicts the next word". (...) And so what ChatGPT does is just predict the next word, the next word and it predicts sentences. And it's this simple mechanism (...) that is unreasonably effective. And if people aren't quite sure what unreasonably effective means, you take a coin, toss it, it comes up heads and tails about 500 times, right, but who explains that? Nobody does. What's more, whatever the coin, whether it's a euro or a dollar, it doesn't matter whether it's a boy or a girl throwing it, whether the weather's fine or not. So there are some things that are unreasonably effective (...) [FR_M10]

The members of Group 2.a generally have the impression that their work is becoming increasingly visible, or even enjoying some form of institutional recognition, if only because of the growing number of collaborations with researchers or scientific institutions. This does not mean, however, that it is always easy to assess the quality of their own work or its dissemination to the public. For those who work online, counting the number of views is an important way of checking whether a video has worked or not, with some possible surprises depending on the subject. Online comments left by the audience may also serve as an indication. For those working on site, the essential part of the evaluation is the speaker's own feelings, the type of interaction generated by the presentation, but also the comments received after the presentation. More generally, some experts associate the idea of success with expanding and discovering new audiences for popular science, like this expert who initiated in France a collaborative platform for science popularisers:

(...) there's what works for me (...) and there's what works for the public. So I've seen two big breaks. There was the break with video. (...) I really became aware of this phenomenon when there was an event (...) with web videographers invited to the main lecture hall at ENS Lyon. (...) We were expecting people to have left, and in fact the amphitheatre was full. There were people on the pavement who couldn't get in. So I thought, "Wow!" (...) Then there was Zetetics, and you can see that with Zetetics, (...) there's clearly an audience, and so on. There's the Zetetics meetings, which are a great way to get to know people. So it takes different forms, including events, etc. (...) And we can see that it reaches people who, well... who might not have been reached by popularisation. [FR_M05]

Group 2.b. For our third group, made up of science journalists, the sources and resources used are multiple. They subscribe to the newsletters of major journals, which generally allows them to keep up to date with forthcoming scientific news. They are present on social networks, which they use as a monitoring tool. They are the main target of Group 1's communication activities and therefore

regularly receive press releases. But they also have a network of contacts within the scientific community who can pass on information directly. A recurring problem mentioned in the interviews is the management of this flow of information and the identification of information that is important or likely to be covered by journalism in an information market that remains, above all, competitive. This competitive dimension is present in the words of this journalist specialised in environmental issues:

(...) the most beautiful analogy of my work is the funnel. So I receive this amount of information and I have this amount time to process it. And the problem I have is identifying the information that's really important. And it's true that sometimes, the fact that [X] or [Y] publishes a press release about an article that I've seen in a summary... I say to myself... In fact, I say two things to myself: 1) maybe this paper is really important; 2) the fact that [X] communicates on it, I have colleagues who are going to process it. So maybe I need to deal with it too. Either because it will come to the attention of my bosses who will say "oh, there's something... and we don't have it...", or because in fact it will create a little flow on the internet so that this article will be read and there will be an expectation around it. [FR_M06]

The members of Group 2b attach particular importance to the question of the reliability of sources. Having sometimes been at the centre of the controversies surrounding the COVID crisis, they have seen scientists, hitherto considered credible, lose credibility by speaking out on issues unrelated to their field of expertise. They have also seen public policies based on self-appointed experts. Hence the importance, in their view, of being extremely careful in assessing the reliability of their sources.

So that's probably one of the most complicated parts of the job (...) It's really difficult. First of all because people change... those who are serious can become not so serious, they can start talking nonsense about a subject... It's a constant job to get colleagues to reaffirm the seriousness of this or that person. I work like this a lot (...) I'll give you an example: a scientific study that we think is great. We want to talk about it. We'll call the researchers, the team, etc., and then (...) if we have time, we'll try to force ourselves to always call outside people we know, who have a good reputation, and say to them: "Oh, have you seen this? Is this interesting research?" (...) Of course we have to try to do some research. For researchers, we check the Retraction Watch database to see if they've had any articles retracted (...). [FR_M07]

It's very common for scientists to talk absolutely rubbish in public about subjects that are not exactly their own, and sometimes about subjects that are really adjacent to their field. And it's really striking, because I don't trust anything

a basic biologist says about the implications of new genomic techniques (...) it's no more valid than what an ordinary person would say, someone who doesn't know anything about science. So this is very common. On the other hand, when people speak in their own field, on their own subject, and in a very precise way (...) their words are always very precise and trustworthy (...) Well, it's basic sociology, I suppose, but when they go out, when they go back to their lab, they know that if they've said something stupid (...) it's the people around them who are going to look at them sideways. [FR_M14]

Although the members of group 2b are clearly different from the members of group 2a in terms of professional objectives and communication codes, they share the same attention to the public accessibility of oral or written expression. An important part of their work is to make their readers or listeners understand the interest of a particular piece of scientific information or the value of a particular journalistic investigation related to scientific or technological issues. Every word may be proofread by in-house editors before publication. Some experts describe this editing work as a process in which the reader is taken from his or her level of scientific knowledge, which is generally assumed to be relatively low, to the level of scientific consensus that precedes the scientific information to be covered, and then from the scientific consensus to the scientific information itself, which alone constitutes the news. This task is complicated by the fact that journalists do not always have a clear idea of their audience. Some can rely on data generated by consulting articles online. But others say they write without a specific audience in mind.

Science journalism is not just about making things comprehensible for a general audience; it is also sometimes about unlearning certain preconceptions about the scientific community and how it works. The members of group 2b do not always have a scientific background, but when they do, counter-intuitively, this background is not always described as a benefit:

(...) when I look back at what I have missed out, what I haven't done well as... what I haven't understood, in fact most of the things I haven't understood, the issues I have dealt with on health, environment and that sort of thing, I didn't understand them because I had a scientific background, so that didn't help me at all in fact (...) there's a whole set of mental reflexes that (...) prevent you from understanding certain processes, including processes that come under natural science (...) I find it quite interesting that what I imagined could be a resource, yes, was in fact more of an obstacle. [FR_M14]

For some journalists, this ability to get rid of certain reflexes or preconceived notions about science is also described as a line of demarcation from members of group 2a, but also from part of their own professional group:

(...) I'm quite dissatisfied with the way science journalism works today. I mean, the strength of science journalism is that it serves (...) a form of social criticism (...) That's what we need today. We don't need, it seems to me, flashy articles about the latest spacecraft to visit, I don't know, which of Jupiter's satellites, that sort of thing. That's all very well, but at the end of the day you hand the keys over to ESA or NASA and they give you very good papers (...) [FR_M14]

As with the two previous groups, the question of how to measure the success of an article's circulation involves the use of digital tools. But these tools are generally more efficient and provide strategic information associated with the information market, in particular the ability of articles to generate economic value.

Newspaper editors are particularly interested in articles that can convert the reader's initial interest into a purchase or subscription:

(...) all newsrooms have more or less the same [technical tools] that allow us to count the number of page views we get per article, to count the number of conversions an article can generate, i.e. the number of times someone clicks on the article under the paywall, who is not normally a monthly subscriber, and who subscribes thanks to this article. This is a very strong signal that an article or topic is of interest [FR_M07]

Given that the temporality of scientific information in the media is very different from the temporality of scientific research, the experts in Group 2b know that they do not have time to reflect too long on their successes and failures. An expert, responsible for a column on a national radio station, has to produce a story every day based on an original research result. Every effort is made to ensure that the information is reliable, but the very work of popularisation can sometimes give rise to a form of uncertainty:

(...) I write a five-minute column every day. That's all the time I have, just one day to write it, and a day goes by very quickly. So either you get the analogy straight away, or you get an image that's clear enough, and that's how you manage to popularise it, with the help of the researchers I interview (...) Sometimes I realised that I shouldn't have taken this point. I should have taken another point to illustrate this information, but these are marginal issues. And then, as I said on the radio, we're moving forward, in other words, I've done one column and the next day I've got another. We have to move forward, we can't just sit on these issues. [FR_M013]

In this high-pressure working environment, the journalist has limited time to evaluate her work in popularising science, but each column draws on the successes and failures of the previous ones. She may also rely on feedback from listeners, either via social networks or via the radio's contact interface.

4.2 About research ethics and integrity (REI)

While the experts were all selected for their potential ability to speak on issues related to research ethics and scientific integrity, the interviews with some of them revealed deeper connections. This was particularly the case for two members of group 2b who, after an initial period of professional training in the scientific field, became science journalists:

(...) Well, that was 15-20 years ago now, but even then [in biology] postdocs weren't doing well and had trouble finding work. Everyone was sad, or under pressure... It was tough, it was a tough environment and I think it's often very lonely. Human relationships weren't easy (...) I wasn't happy at the bench (...) A little anecdote, during my undergraduate studies, my first research internship: the guy from the lab next door called me and said, "Come on, I need a fresh, naive pair of eyes. He said look at this article and zoomed in. So it was an article on Western blots, where proteins migrate and all that... He said look, I'm zooming in and I'm zooming out to a place where there's no trace. There's no line. And he zooms in and out and there we see pixels that change. The pixel has changed there? well, yeah, the pixel has changed... it looks like they've erased it... that's what it looks like. First internship of research. So I know it exists. [FR_M06]

(...) I was just at the Institute [X]. So I did a degree in biochemistry (...) and I stayed there for three years. And then I started to undergo a professional conversion, which didn't happen overnight. But there was also a kind of disillusionment with scientific research, with what it was (...) it was also about issues of scientific integrity. It's funny that we're talking about this, because one of the reasons I left was because I felt that we weren't doing research for research's sake, in other words that there was a real desire on the part of certain people, not necessarily my director, but certain people, to get funding at any cost by inventing a scientific question without necessarily answering it (...) [FR_M13]

Apart from these specific situations, which helped to define career paths, members of Group 1 felt that they had no significant difficulty in communicating on the issues of scientific integrity and research ethics. The aim of this communication may be to convey an institutional message, for example when the president of an organisation gives a speech on the subject or when a new scientific integrity officer is appointed.

(...) I've been more involved in relaying information on these subjects (...) and we try to remind people regularly. And on [research] ethics, the [X] group is very active. So, in a way, it's quite simple for me. All I have to do is pass on what they're doing and not do any more... After that I'm convinced

that on all these issues (...) there's only one thing that can work in internal communication, and that's repetition. [FR_M01]

(...) We interviewed [X], for example, for the newsletter a few years ago. We did an interview in the newsletter on these subjects, and [Y] also wrote an editorial in the newsletter on the same subject. So we're not opposed to doing it at all. It's just that maybe it hasn't occurred to us recently, but if the subject came up again, why not (...) [FR_M09]

Of the 6 institutional experts interviewed, only one had the main task of communicating on scientific integrity issues with two priority audiences: research integrity officers, who needed to be provided with resources, but also science journalists, who needed to be provided with information. Despite the often negative press coverage of issues relating to scientific integrity, the view of this expert, a former science journalist, remains mostly positive:

(...) I think they do a good job. Frankly, I understand their constraints in talking about scandals or affairs, because you see they talk to the general public (...) Maybe it's because I was a science journalist, but I'm not going to teach them their job. I give them topics, I say it seems interesting to me. That's what we can offer you (...) and [X] we always keep him in the loop. There are people, you know, like [Y], who follow these things from much further away, but I always keep him informed (...) And that's an important dimension, it's this support and this sharing of culture, it's not done on the basis of publicity stunts, it's really long-term. And so our idea, as I said before, is to try to give information to this group of people... and more afterwards if we can spread the word [FR_M04]

This deliberately slow communication can also sometimes target the scientific community, with the unexpected benefit that it may contribute to enrich the pre-existing definition of scientific integrity:

(...) Everyone has their own idea of scientific integrity. It's quite interesting. You see... you give them a slide on the grey area, for example. I did a bit of retropedalling there, because everybody said, "Oh, but for me that's fraud, for me that should be there...". And that's the way it is in my field" (...) the whole point is that they are the ones who make the norms... and that's why I think it's a job, not of proximity, but of understanding the profession (...) [FR_M04]

But of course, in the case of France, whether for the Group 2a or 2b members, it was the Covid crisis that helped make scientific integrity a central public issue. Most of them were confronted with the issue of scientific integrity through the case of the French microbiologist Didier Raoult and his work on COVID. Some of them even played a key role in demonstrating the fragility of this work, sometimes exposing themselves to legal action by Raoult and his team.

If we talk about Didier Raoult, for example, I don't think we've ever talked so much about scientific integrity. In the beginning, frankly, we were... There was [X] and there was us. In the beginning it was just [X] and us, mainly us, who were interested. And then, as the investigations came out and we realised he was talking nonsense... there was [Y]. That went on for a while until [Z] and so on. And then it really spread (...) because it was the Raoult character that absolutely fascinated the whole of France. And then everyone started talking about it because every day there were new developments, new statements (...) it was massive. [FR_M07]

(...) I also did a lot of work on COVID (...) every day there were studies coming out on a subject that we knew very little about, and so the risk is to get it wrong. The risk is that we go too far in the conclusions we draw from these studies. This was the case, for example, with Didier Raoult's publications. I use this example because it is well known. But in fact the paper he published on the first treatments, on hydroxychloroquine, was a rag! In other words, it shouldn't normally be published anywhere. Normally it's impossible for it to be published. All you have to do is pick up the paper. I read it because I have very little experience, very little, but when you read the paper and the reviews, there's really nothing to it. (...) [FR_M13]

While Didier Raoult has provided food for thought on the place of scientific integrity in France, the Covid crisis has also provided insights into the relationship between science and politics. Because Raoult benefited from political attention that had no scientific basis, the crisis appears to some experts as an exceptional situation from which we are still struggling to draw the main lessons:

What really hurts science. It's when, particularly in France, the political and health institutions don't draw the right conclusions from the debate. So hydroxychloroquine is tested when it shouldn't have been... there was no reason to test it... the Raoult study is really no good... there was no reason to test hydroxychloroquine... Millions were spent and 15,000 uncoordinated clinical trials were carried out in France. None of them were completed... to test hydroxychloroquine, just so that university hospitals could say "we're testing hydroxychloroquine... we're listening to you". It's completely stupid. And finally, we can't take into account the fact that the virus is transmitted by aerosol. So yes, we're having a big debate, positive or negative, but the fact is that we're not drawing the right conclusions from it. That's a shame. Because... "it's at the end of the ball that we pay the musicians"... So if at the end there had been someone who could have said "Yes, but that's it". But we didn't get that, we didn't get that. [FR_M06]

4.3 About public trust in science

As shown in a previous task of the POIESIS project², there is a general concern in France about the nature of the relationship of trust between science and society. So it's hardly surprising that many of our experts, both institutional and non-institutional, share this concern.

(...) on a personal level, yes, of course, I think like everyone else, I'm convinced that there is a terrible lack of understanding of research among the general public, and that this lack of understanding is in fact increasing, in terms of what research is, its methodologies and objectives... and that this needs to be remedied... That's it, I'm going to caricature a lot with this sentence, so put a lot of commas around it, but I think there's a form of obscurantism at the moment, at all levels, that's winning over the population and that it's important for everyone who can to fight against it. [FR_M01]

What is certain is that the Covid crisis has led to a breakdown in trust, not on the part of everyone, but on the part of a large proportion of the public towards the institutions. It's not specific to [X], it's really general... there was always this talk of 'they're lying to us', 'they're hiding things from us', 'they're not going to tell us the truth'... [FR_M02]

(...) I think there's a crisis of trust... from the studies and figures I've seen, there does seem to be a crisis. Perhaps the word crisis seems a bit strong to me... in any case, a certain mistrust... or a desire to stop believing just anyone, just anyhow, and therefore to be somewhat suspicious of science (...) [FR_M03]

This expression of concern can be accompanied by an original reflection on the origins of this supposed crisis, as shown by the two extracts below. In the first one a science populariser directly links the existence of mistrust to communication choices made in the 1980s. In the second one, a science journalist interprets the crisis of trust in science in the terms of a collateral damage.

When it comes to the relationship between science and society, I wouldn't say it's a crisis. I'd say it's more a situation of mistrust (...) which reached its peak during covid and health crises in general, which often shed light on the state of relations between science and society. Because, in the end, what happened during covid was that we realised (...) that society, to use a general term, was not aware of how science is done. And for me (...) the source of the mistrust that has arisen really lies in the communication choices that we've made

² See deliverable 3.2 - Focus Groups - Findings. Exploring Institutional Roles in Fostering Public Trust in Science)

since the 1980s (...) with the overdevelopment, the media coverage and the acceleration of communication methods. We've seen science summarised in its results. And that's a choice, a media choice, which is driven enormously by television, a lot of it, and by what we call the mass media, i.e. media that reach the majority of the population. But, and so it's these choices, to treat science through the results, without ever explaining how the results were obtained, and to give the impression that we only have results, completely forgetting the scientific consensus, the way in which scientific knowledge is created, completely forgetting the research phase, which is enormous, the questioning, the back and forth, completely forgetting also what makes up the scientific method. ... how you experiment... how you set up a protocol, for example, or how you create a study, sweeping all that under the carpet, in order to provide one-off information about a particular result, a particular thing, a particular discovery, and this stretches the link that can exist between science and society... So that link is totally stretched (...) [FR_M11]

(...) I have the feeling that the loss of trust is more widespread, i.e. it doesn't just affect the scientific question. It affects the question of trust in information and the way it is processed. So science and politics, well, we know that at the moment. I mean, there are things that prove this very lack of trust, if only by the massive vote for the far right. It actually says something about a kind of political disenchantment. I think science is one of the collateral damages of this issue and of wider political issues. I think that the COVID pandemic and the way it was handled politically in France may actually have diminished the French people's trust in science (...) [FR_M13]

Although this concern is dominant, some respondents, particularly those in groups 2a and 2b, also develop views that are sometimes quite critical, either of the idea that there is a crisis of trust or of the very idea of trust itself. The idea that a possible crisis of trust should not be fuelled is described by one journalist as an indirect way of trying to discredit his own work on breaches of ethics or scientific integrity.

I think that in this little world of communicators, popularisers and science journalism, there's this idea that we mustn't fragilize the trust that people may have in expert bodies, academies... I don't feel at all that I'm discrediting science in general and, on the contrary, that I'm giving a voice to scientists who work specifically on these very specific and very complicated subjects. In fact, I should be keeping a catalogue of all the tricks and sometimes deceptions that come out of the communications departments of these public research bodies, academies, etc. It's spectacular! In fact, it's spectacular! There are plenty of examples. At [X] recently, and I'm going to write about it because it really is a scandal... (...) there are

plenty of examples (...) of scientific authority being used in the public arena (...) to protect interests. It's not going to work! That's not what science is for. [FR_M14]

4.4 Synthesis of recommendations

Through their various comments, the experts, institutional or non-institutional, have emphasized various dimensions likely to give rise to specific recommendations. In this section, we list 5 elements that we feel are sufficiently important to fuel the collective reflection, with an interview extract for each.

- 1) While most communication officers consider that they have no difficulty in principle in communicating about the issues of integrity and trust, they also generally acknowledge that their communication on these topics is generally irregular. But, as one officer pointed out, when it comes to integrity and research ethics, communication should require patience and repetition. The first recommendation is therefore to design a long-term communication plan that includes in-depth action to progressively build a shared culture.

I'm convinced that on all these issues, whether it's this one or even good practice in human resources, there's only one thing that can work in internal communication, and that's repetition. Even if I were to write the most beautiful article in the world, with a splendid infographic and so on, it might be seen by a lot of people on the Internet. Maybe it'll be very popular at the time and I bet that three months later if you ask anyone: "Does this mean anything to you?", they'll say "No". So I think the only way to change practices and mentalities is to repeat, repeat, repeat and repeat. [FR_M01]

- 2) During the interviews, most of the experts stressed that the voice of the scientists, during the Covid crisis, did not always live up to expectations. This may be because scientists spoke outside their area of expertise, or because they were not sufficiently trained to speak effectively in the media. In any case, a second recommendation relates to the need to support them more effectively with practical guidelines.

We're currently thinking about guidelines for the scientist's public expression (...) There was a consultation some time ago... (...) to give a few basic rules, and to support scientists (...) as best we can on these issues. [FR_M08]

- 3) Specialists in the popularisation of science aim to communicate the state of knowledge and the latest discoveries to the general public. But as one populariser observes, mass communication has tended for many years to emphasise the result at the expense of the process. A third recommendation stresses the need to rebalance

the work of communicating science by giving as much importance to the findings as to the research process.

We've seen science summarised in its results. And that's a choice, a media choice, which is driven enormously by television, a lot of it, and by what we call the mass media, i.e. media that reach the majority of the population. But, and so it's these choices, to treat science through the results, without ever explaining how the results were obtained, and to give the impression that we only have results, completely forgetting the scientific consensus, the way in which scientific knowledge is created, completely forgetting the research phase, which is enormous, the questioning, the back and forth, completely forgetting also what makes up the scientific method. [FR_M11]

- 4) Because particular attention is paid to misinformation, which primarily concerns people using social networks, it seems essential to maintain and develop their scientific culture and critical thinking skills. However, as one science journalist pointed out, some science subjects or fields have disappeared from the syllabus at secondary school level. A fourth recommendation concerns the reinforcement of school curricula with regard to science and critical thinking.

(...) It's important to have a general culture, but scientific culture, science, it's everywhere! (...) So the stakes are enormous, and I'm still on my butt about these problems of reform (...) I mean, take away science! biology! (...) In fact, you're not really thinking about the future generation, and the future generation is far from stupid. In fact, they can be extremely well informed, even with social networks. And I think it's not giving them the right tools, it's not giving them a sufficient knowledge base. [FR_M13]

- 5) Finally, some journalists and popularisers stressed the importance of not being too naïve about the uses of the notion of trust. Not that we should necessarily cultivate distrust of the scientific community, but this notion, like the very notion of research integrity, can be used to delegitimise forms of expression perceived as too critical. A fifth recommendation relates to the need not to be satisfied with a sloppy use of the notion of public trust in order to analyse its full social and political ramifications.

I think that in this little world of communicators, popularisers and science journalism, there's this idea that we mustn't fragilize the trust that people may have in expert bodies, academies... I don't feel at all that I'm discrediting science in general and, on the contrary [FR_M14]

5. Analysis of Researcher interviews

This section provides an initial analysis of the interviews conducted with the researchers. Our population of respondents is made up of 6 scientists who all had the opportunity to speak publicly about issues related to covid or climate change.

Not all of them are specialized in either COVID or climate change, but all of them felt it was important to take a public stand, either to uphold the standards and values of research integrity, or to make the general public and public authorities aware of the urgent need to take action on climate change. A large part of the interviews was devoted to detailing various aspects of this public engagement.

Our sample is very unbalanced in terms of gender, with 5 men and only 1 woman. It is more balanced in terms of career advancement, with three early careers scientists, and three senior scientists.

For ease of discussion, we distinguish between two groups of scientists: Group 3a, whose public visibility is associated with the Covid crisis, and Group 3b, whose public visibility is associated with climate issues.

5.1 Researcher contexts: Covid-19 and Climate Change

This section presents the areas of expertise of the members of groups 3a and 3b and the way in which they have been involved in either Covid or climate issues.

Group 3a. This first group is made up of a biologist (FR_R02), a data scientist (FR_R05), and an experimental psychologist (FR_R06).

FR_R02 works in a laboratory that focuses on the structure and function of viral proteins. After gaining experience in virology abroad, he became interested in reverse genetics and the modification of viral genomes. He has been heavily involved in the study of coronaviruses for about twenty years. During the Covid crisis, he contributed to the public debate on the origin of the virus, weighing up the arguments in favour of the zoonosis hypothesis and those in favour of a laboratory accident hypothesis. He is a regular public speaker on the importance of biosafety in research.

FR_R05 is a young researcher who wrote his doctoral thesis in the field of data visualisation, in particular to facilitate interaction with complex data. After two post-docs abroad, he was recruited by a foreign university, first as a research engineer and then as an assistant professor. Very active in social media and post-publication peer review platforms, he is a member of the sleuth community. During the Covid period, he played an important role in exposing integrity violations in the research team led by the microbiologist Didier Raoult in Marseille.

FR_R06 is a professor emeritus in the UK. Her work has developed in the field of developmental neuropsychology, but she also quickly became interested in issues of methodology and epistemology in science. Very active in social media and post-publication peer review platforms, she is a member of the sleuth community. During the Covid period, she played an important role in exposing integrity violations in the research team led by the microbiologist Didier Raoult in Marseille.

Group 3b. This second group is made up of a biophysicist (FR_R01), an astrophysicist (FR_R03) and an epidemiologist (FR_R04).

FR_R01 runs a laboratory in a biology institute of a large French research organisation. After three years as a postdoc abroad, he was recruited in France to work on a range of proteins at the interface between biochemistry and biophysics. He sees the climate crisis as "the mother of all crises" and is involved in a number of groups, foundations and associations working to raise public awareness of the climate issue but also to rethink the relationship between science and society.

FR_R03 is a junior researcher at a large French research organisation. He is an astrophysicist and studies stellar explosions. He is a member of a collective dedicated to developing environmental ethics in research. He is publicly committed to ecology and is also vice-president of a vegetarian association. He takes part in a number of spectacular public actions as part of a group of scientists trying to raise collective awareness of climate issues.

FR_R04 is a junior researcher, initially specialised in the fields of epidemiology and mathematical modelling. Recruited as assistant professor in a research and teaching organisation, he has recently been appointed to a prestigious position in a biology institute. He is working on the links between health and climate. He considers that his research comes with a degree of responsibility for how it is used: "If I have a position on climate, it is that we cannot absolve ourselves of responsibility for what is done with our findings once we have put them on the table". He is a member of a number of groups of concerned scientists who are trying to raise collective awareness of climate issues.

5.2 About science communication and public attitudes

For groups 3a and 3b, public visibility of their actions and opinions is a strategic issue. No matter how well an action is carried out, it is only worthwhile if it has some form of public visibility. For members of the first group, this means publicly exposing breaches of research integrity by certain teams working on Covid. It may also mean encouraging public debate on a difficult issue for the scientific community, that of biosafety. For the second group, the aim is to create significant events to attract public attention and to raise awareness of the importance of climate issues.

In both cases, the communication targets are primarily the journalists and the media. These media are seen as useful relays to civil society, but also as levers to open up situations that may appear to be blocked:

(...) Journalists are interested and that's a bit of a "game changer"... Unfortunately, it's a "game changer". In other words, it's good that journalists are interested, and I always say thank you to journalists who ask me to explain something, thank you for talking about it, it's good, it's important, but it's a shame that we need that to move things forward. [FR_R05]

Each researcher has their own unique experience of how to interact with the media. None of them have received any specific media training from their home institutions. For some, it is important to be prepared in advance to deliver a limited number of key messages:

(...) If you want to have a clear message, you have to try to identify before each interview the two or three key points you want to get out of the interview. If you don't, you get bogged down very quickly. That's all there is to it. And so there's a certain amount of preparation, which ... for me doesn't consist of writing down what I'm going to say, but of trying to think (...) of rereading the reference publications in this field and extracting from this field what the consensus is. (...) That's more or less the general approach (...) [FR_R02]

For others, it is important not just to pay attention to what you say, but also to *how* you say it. In this extract from an interview, a researcher looks back critically at the way in which a television channel reported on a particularly spectacular action:

(...) It was channel [X] (...) I'd just come out of prison and the headline, which wasn't just about me, was "Des actions et zéro sanction". (...) I have a bad memory of it, and I probably wondered afterwards if I'd been sufficiently prepared, because I had the impression that the image given wasn't great, because I was smiling on the screen, and as a result, and with that headline, it was really catastrophic. So if I'd smiled less it might have been a bit better. But I find it hard not to smile. No, but I could practise. So I had this experience where I said to myself afterwards, well, I'll try to be less naive next time. [FR_R03]

The goal is to communicate about objective facts as much as subjective states. One has to be able to convey the importance of the moment, and that means making the feelings of fear, anger or outrage visible. The researchers we interviewed are sometimes involved in acts of civil disobedience, acts that are considered legally 'risky' and whose radical nature is described as a useful way of breaking out of the normal processing of scientific information and attracting the attention of journalists and the public alike.

Well, somewhere we have to create this situation of abnormality in order to have the possibility of getting media coverage that

will allow us to transmit the positions that we take in reports or others (...) there's the little shock that we have to create (...) the media, the journalists, tell us that in order to have an article, there has to be news. So at some point you have to create the news (...) well, we know how it works, don't we? The action is reported and then we have a little space to explain why we did it and what we support, defend or criticise. [FR_R04]

But of course, even if all the conditions are met for a piece of information or an opinion to be in the public domain, there is no guarantee that journalists will pass it on in the expected way. The researchers interviewed mentioned the various criteria used to differentiate between media: the type of medium (radio, television, Internet, etc.), the time allowed to elaborate a point of view, the possibility of preparing the interview in advance, the initial interest or training of the journalist, the editorial line of the media, etc.

[Some journalists] are systematic in the way they ask questions, and even if we answer every time, they keep asking the question until they get something they like. That's it. And then there are journalists who are really curious and have a scientific background, with whom there's a real discussion and things go well and it's interesting. Again, you have to sort things out bit by bit. So, yes, now there is a whole range of media that I respond to much less. [FR_R02]

I mean, I've come to the conclusion that if you want something to happen, you do... It helps to go public (...) The only problem with going to the press is that you can't always trust the press. You know, you lose complete control. They will want a story. And you know that they may misrepresent thing so you... they... you have to go to a journalist you can trust if you're going to go to the press, I think. [FR_06]

But sometimes, even in media that are not necessarily sympathetic to the cause being defended, there can be some pleasant and unexpected surprises:

(...) I was actually quite suspicious. Of course, that's channel [X]!! At first I thought, OK, I'll do it to reach everyone. But I was a bit suspicious and I thought, what am I getting myself into? how well is what I'm going to say going to be represented in the end? and so on. And in the end it went really well. The journalist made quite a good impression on me. She told me that it was different between the website and TV. So maybe there's a bit of that... [FR_R03]

The specific case of the two sleuths in our sample of respondents is interesting because they both have benefited from high media visibility during the Covid crisis, with numerous portraits in the scientific and general press. And even if this visibility is considered to be an indispensable means, this does not prevent these

researchers from criticising the media coverage they receive, particularly when it contributes to an undue heroisation of the work of detecting scientific fraud.

(...) Sometimes it's [the journalist] who push in that direction
(...) It gives an irreproachable image (...) it's not really the case and that's not the aim... So it gives this image of the person who knows better than everyone else, when that's not necessarily the case (...) And the image of the "white knight" is a bit strange to me. It's rarely portrayed that way, except maybe for [X]. And [X] got a lot of positive coverage for her work because she was probably the first to really do it in such a serious way (...) I have the impression that there's a spin going in a positive direction, but I hope it's not taken to extremes with ... the "white knights of science" ... it was a bit strange because it gives a very bad image. It gives the impression that we're above it all and that's not the case at all. [FR_R05]

Our respondent is expressing a form of ambivalence towards the journalistic narrative. On the one hand, there is the perception of a positive spin, useful in establishing the issues of integrity and ethics as public problems. On the other hand, the journalistic narrative is perceived as entrapping researchers in stereotypes that do not do justice to the nature of their commitment.

5.3 About science and the integration of citizens in research

Most of our respondents were fairly critical about various aspects of contemporary science. This critical discourse may focus on specific aspects, such as the multiple conflicts of interest observed during the Covid crisis.

(...) there is the problem of conflicts of interest (...) at least in the United States there are obvious problems with a number of people who have worked with the Wuhan lab and who have been direct collaborators and who are now not declaring these conflicts of interest in major papers that are trying to show that this is a zoonosis without... without... without discussing the arguments of the opponents... and that's a problem. That's a problem for me. [FR_R02]

It may also focus on scientific misconduct and the inability of institutions to act quickly to punish them. But these problems are often described as symptoms of more structural dysfunctions that call for fundamental change.

I think that what we need to change... what we need to change so that we no longer have these cases, so that all this really stops, is the way in which researchers are evaluated, the pressure that is put on publish and all that. And ethics committees won't solve that problem. In fact, ethics committees

are a band-aid on a broken leg (...) people do this to keep their jobs... And I think that's where the problem lies. [FR_R05]

This determination to change applies both to the way the scientific community operates and to the nature of its relations with civil society or political authorities. For example, one of the members of Group 3b has been heavily involved in expert assessment activities related to regulatory science. He remembers this as a very difficult experience which gradually led him to radically rethink his view of the relationship between science and politics:

And here is a second discovery: these interfaces between science and politics are completely rotten. They don't do science, or do it very badly, whether in [X] or [Y]. Nor are they accountable to the health, environmental and social issues they are supposed to serve. They are in their mission. It is purely procedural. Their frame of reference is procedural. The rest doesn't exist. And because it doesn't exist, you can do anything and be manipulated by anyone. [FR_R01]

This dysfunctional interface between science and politics is often described as the starting point for thinking about the role of citizens and their ability to influence scientific and technological decisions. Social integration therefore seems inextricably linked to the building of a 'shared world' or some form of advanced scientific democracy:

(...) We need to bring science back into society in a way, because it's not up to science to explain the world we live in and make it accessible. It's up to science to help build a shared world. Otherwise, at some point, everyone is going to say that MY world prevails and we'll have power issues, epistemological power grabs, almost religious power grabs [FR_R01]

(...) Biosafety is not a problem for researchers in their ivory towers, it's a question of knowing how science and society fit together in the end and what society's choices are when it comes to risky scientific projects (...) It's a political issue that must not remain in the hands of experts. That's all there is to it. Experts must never be allowed to play with matches. It's very dangerous. [FR_R02]

Most of the respondents who have developed this discourse on the need to bring science back into society are aware that the majority of the scientific community is often hardly in favour of it. Scientists usually see it as a potential loss of autonomy in the choice of subjects and the way they are studied. However, as one interviewee pointed out, there are already many areas that are regulated and where scientists are not free to do what they want.

We cannot experiment on animals, let alone humans, and this is completely accepted. There are areas where this is completely accepted. And we can see that new concerns are being brought into these restricted areas of research. Environmental issues

are now starting to emerge. There are some ... well, there are some areas that are a little bit emblematic, like augmented viruses, which have really been the subject of debate, with the idea that this is a textbook case. If we can't regulate that, if we can't agree on that (...) then we're not going to succeed in everything that has to do with synthetic biology, the use of genome editing and so on. [FR_R04]

While there is a general desire among the interviewees to rethink the relationship between science and society in depth, and while some of them already participate in discussion forums involving scientists and citizens, few of them specify the best way to operationalise the integration of citizens in science. This problem of operationalisation was exceptionally raised during the following interaction:

Q. And in that specific case, are you in favour of the option proposed in France by the Agence de la biomédecine, where there would be a wide circle of citizens who would have a kind of right of control over what is done in the scientific community?

A. Yes, I'm in favour of that. And above all, the key point in this question is... it's the international aspect. That's it. What the history of biotechnology regulation shows us is that research, like capital, goes where there are the least restrictions. So if you have strong regulation in Europe and no regulation in India, for example, research is bound to go to India (...) [FR_R02]

5.4 About public trust in science

Like members of groups 1, 2a and 2b, members of groups 3a and 3b have been exposed to the public discourse on the crisis of trust between science and society. They sometimes share the view that the public is increasingly distrustful. This is the case, for example, with one scientist who gives a very mixed assessment of the Covid crisis:

Yes, I think it's true that there is to some extent a crisis of trust between science and society and that (...) what happened at the time of Covid didn't help, because... there were things that were a bit contradictory. And it wasn't very well understood by the public, so science didn't know. This is perhaps something that... it's always difficult to make people understand that there are things that we can say with great confidence, even certainty, and other things that we don't know, or that we know but with much more doubt. So there you have it: we have scientific elements, but they may be wrong afterwards. So there you have it, science in the making, and that's not easy to convey to the general public. [FR_R03]

This observation about the difficulty of communicating about unstabilised results is shared by a large number of respondents. In

this type of situation, stresses one of the scientists interviewed, it is no longer possible to communicate with the public without conveying the complexity of the situation:

(...) I think it was important not to limit ourselves to simple information such as whether people should be vaccinated or not. It was more important, for example, to talk about the benefits of vaccination in general, perhaps with a historical approach, reminding people of the benefits of vaccination throughout history. What are the risks, what are the benefits, and then to say where we are with the science, and every time to say here's some evidence to suggest this, let's see if it holds up. And so it's often a discourse that's a little bit complex and therefore not very well suited to the format of certain particularly new media. Television is a... a very poor medium for information, I think in retrospect. [FR_R02]

Crisis situations call for a transformation in the way we communicate, and that means taking a much longer time than what is usually available in the general media.

But what is more interesting here is not so much the scientist's perception of the state of public trust in science, but the way in which they deal with the argument that their public engagement, their work on scientific fraud, or their contributions to controversies related to the origin of the Covid crisis, may fragilize the image or the credibility of science. Here we find a use of the notion of trust already observed with one of the members of group 2b. There is sometimes an expectation of preserving trust at all costs, at the risk of generating intractable moral conflicts.

I know that my head of unit was made aware of the fact that we had to be careful ... that we would lose trust in science if we revealed a certain number of things that were realities, truths, but we shouldn't say them. I cannot support that position. I'm sorry. If there are experiments going on in the laboratory to make chimeric viruses, and I'm interviewed in the media and asked if that's being done, I can't say we're not capable of doing that if I know it's being done. It just doesn't seem ethical [FR_R02]

And [the deputy director of my department] also let me know a few things about the fact that he (...) wasn't necessarily convinced that civil disobedience as a scientist was the right thing to do, precisely in terms of the credibility of science and the role of science in society. He didn't think it was the right thing to do. So I got some feedback and that was the only time [FR_R03]

This situation of potential moral conflict is particularly acute for members of the sleuth community. Should we denounce scientific fraud at the risk of undermining trust in science? The answer given by our two interviewees is clearly positive: when working on issues of

scientific integrity, one must take a long-term view and realise that nothing would be more counterproductive than to conceal the reality of practices in the name of a misunderstood ideal of trust:

And it's true that... it probably damaged a bit the image or the trust of the public in science with a capital S perhaps... But at the same time, it has brought to light things that I think the public was not necessarily aware of, the pressure to publish for example, which will perhaps help in the end to solve this problem of evaluating researchers (...) [FR_R05]

I think it's really problematic at the moment that trust in science is being weakened because there's such a lot of fraud. And that is being used by those who want, you know, who are anti-science. And they are pointing to, you know, there's reports that, you know, a certain percentage of papers of fraud in this paper mills and so on. People will point to that, say, well, you can't trust anything, you know, and people who are sort of anti-vax will say, you know, well, all the, all the... So it's bad. But I think the way of dealing with that is to be very open, that you are very proactively dealing with cases where there is problems and fraud. Not to pretend it's not happening because again, you have to think in the longer term that this is going to come out. And if it's, you know, you can't hide it forever. And if it comes out that you have been attempting to hide a problem, it's much, much, much worse than if you deal promptly with the problem. And make it, you know, it's clear that you have got mechanisms for doing so. But I get this reaction a lot because I'm trying to, you know, have a meeting on how we handle fraud and I found that people don't want to touch it. People in the scientific establishment typically are nervous of the topic because they take the view that if you talk about fraud and how it should be handled, then other people will come in and sort of think that science, not just science, perhaps the whole of academia is flawed [FR_R06]

5.5 Synthesis of recommendations

Through their comments, the scientists have emphasized various dimensions likely to give rise to specific recommendations. In this section, we list 5 elements that we feel are sufficiently important to fuel the collective reflection, with an interview extract when necessary.

- 1) The first recommendation is to encourage scientific institutions to provide opportunities for scientists to reflect collectively on issues related to science and society. Some of the scientists we interviewed feel that, beyond the institutional discourse, their research organisation does not value the ability of scientists to develop a form of reflexivity.

(...) There are so many signals that say that the paradigm of academic freedom as it was conceived [in the 1960s] doesn't make sense (...) It's the people in the institution who are saying: 'it doesn't work anymore'. And there is potentially another paradigm (...) Except that we don't know how to do it, we are in a community that has no reflexivity... that has never learned reflexivity [FR_01]

- 2) The second recommendation has to do with institutional guidance for scientists who decide to take a public stand on a particular issue. The scientists interviewed report a degree of uncertainty in their risk-taking, both professionally and legally. A feeling of uncertainty that calls for the production of practical guidelines dedicated to the public engagement of researchers.

I suppose it might help to have a few more guidelines, a few more things to know what you can do without having to worry. Because it's true that there's always... there's always a little bit of uncertainty, a little bit of doubt. You don't really know to what extent you're overstepping the boundaries of what's acceptable or not. Yes, I suppose... I'm inclined to think that the institutions could actually have statements, things that say to what extent you can engage as a researcher, and even encourage it, actually value it. I think that would be positive. [FR_R03]

- 3) The third recommendation relates to public communication by scientists in crisis situations. If we are to have a positive impact on public trust in science in a situation of great uncertainty, we need media resources that give scientists the time they need to develop a complex message. Collaboration with the mainstream media must therefore be developed to ensure the conditions for this crisis communication.

Well, I think it's precisely by moving away from simplistic discourse and sterile debate between those who are for and those who are against... to a discourse based on complexity that we can rebuild trust. Because perhaps that's what we as scientists have failed to do, and that is to talk about complexity. [FR_R02]

- 4) The fourth recommendation takes up the invitation described at the end of the previous section not to make short-term use of the notion of public trust. We must avoid opposing trust with ethics and integrity. Trust must not be used as a lever to cultivate opacity about any particular aspect of the way science works. On the contrary, we need to take a long-term view and be aware that the ideal of trust presupposes a form of openness and transparency.

(...) I think the way of dealing with that is to be very open, that you are very proactively dealing with cases where there is problems and fraud. (...) you have to think in the longer term

that this is going to come out. And if it's, you know, you can't hide it forever. And if it comes out that you have been attempting to hide a problem, it's much, much, much worse than if you deal promptly with the problem. [FR_R06]

- 5) Finally, the fifth and final recommendation relates to the difficulty of operationalising the interviewees' desire to bring science back into society. As already indicated, few of the interviewees seem to be able to outline concrete ways of creating new forms of interaction between scientists and citizens. It seems important to learn from the experiences of the last twenty years and to develop training initiatives for the scientific community.

6. Conclusion

This national report presents the French results of task 2.3. of the European POIEIS project. For the purposes of this report, a total of 20 expert interviews were conducted. The composition of our expert population is as follows: 6 researchers, 8 non-institutional mediators, 6 institutional mediators.

Within this population we have distinguished 5 distinct groups: the group of institutional mediators (group 1), the group of science popularisers (group 2a), the group of science journalists (group 2b), the group of scientists who have chosen to make themselves visible to the public on the issues of the covid crisis (3a) and the scientists who have chosen to make themselves visible to the public on the issues of the climate crisis (3b).

This population is, of course, very limited in size and is not intended to represent a broader population. However, the interviews allow us to go into detail about both practices and representations. And because these interviews are often very rich, we have chosen to use a significant number of extracts for each theme in this report, always taking care to diversify the sources used.

In addition to describing the population surveyed, the first section of this report analysed the mediators' interviews, while the second section analysed the scientists' interviews, leading to a set of recommendations for each, which we present here as a conclusion:

- Recommendation 1 - when it comes to scientific integrity and research ethics, communication should require patience and repetition from the institutional mediators. The communications departments of research organisations should therefore design **long-term communication plans to progressively build a shared culture of ethics and integrity**
- Recommendation 2 - most of the experts stressed that the voice of the scientists, during the Covid crisis, did not always live up to expectations. This may be because scientists spoke outside their area of expertise, or because they were not sufficiently

trained to speak effectively in the media. In any case, a second recommendation relates to the need to support them more effectively with **practical guidelines dedicated to public communication**.

- Recommendation 3 - the respondents involved in the dissemination of scientific knowledge point out that mass communication has tended for many years to emphasise the finding at the expense of the research process. Indeed, in the interviews, the experts link the lack of trust to a lack of understanding of the research process. A third recommendation stresses the need to **rebalance the work of communicating science by giving as much importance to the findings as to the research process**.
- Recommendation 4 - Because particular attention is paid to misinformation, which primarily concerns people using social networks, it seems essential to maintain and develop their scientific culture and critical thinking skills. However, as one science journalist pointed out, some science subjects or fields have disappeared from the syllabus at secondary school level. A fourth recommendation concerns the **reinforcement of school curricula with regard to science and critical thinking**.
- Recommendation 5 - A fifth recommendation relates to the need to **avoid an idealised and over-simplistic vision of the very notion of trust**. Science is made up of critical thinking, and the civil society should embrace the ideal of critical thinking, including with regard to the social and political uses of the notion of trust.
- Recommendation 6 - In addition to carrying out research activities, which is their primary mission, research **organisations should be encouraged to create opportunities for scientists to reflect on issues of ethics, integrity and, more broadly, the relationship between science and society**.
- Recommendation 7 - To the extent that scientists feel a moral responsibility to speak out on issues such as climate change, research organisations should support their employees by **developing practical guidelines to reduce the personal and legal risks associated with taking a public stance**.
- Recommendation 8 - An exceptional crisis situation calls for an exceptional communication situation: to consolidate trust in science, **research organizations should work with the mainstream media to enable scientists to communicate complex messages**.
- Recommendation 9 - **It is essential to avoid opposing trust with ethics or integrity**. Scientists cannot be asked to keep silent about what they know on the pretext that this might weaken the credibility of science. Both scientific bodies and scientists should take a long-term view of trust, bearing in mind that it presupposes a form of openness and transparency.
- Recommendation 10 - As few of the interviewees seem to be able to outline concrete ways of creating new forms of interaction between scientists and citizens, it is up to scientific bodies

and scientists to **review the initiatives taken over the last 20 years on issues of scientific and technical democracy and to organize dedicated training for the scientific community.**

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Expert Interviews - *Germany*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *CS/C*

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1 Introduction

The 16 German expert interviews took place between the 24th of April and the 27th of June 2024. Six researchers from the field of climate change and Covid-19, two institutional, and eight non-institutional mediators have been interviewed answering questions about their work, their perceptions of and experiences with research integrity and public integration in the research cycle, and their recommendations on how to strengthen public trust in science.

This report provides an overview of the organisation of the interviews (Introduction), the participants and their profile (chapter 2), the main arguments made in regard to integrity and trust in science by the mediators (chapter 3) and about public integration¹ and trust in science by the researchers (chapter 4). A short conclusion then reflects on common themes that have emerged in the interviews but also before, in the POIESIS focus groups and the public consultation.

The upcoming chapter provides a brief reminder of the research questions in WP2 of the POIESIS project, in which the interviews are organised, aims to answer, some background on the potential inputs to Task 2.3 from previous POIESIS studies in Germany, and then summarises the process of organising and conducting interviews with Mediators and Researchers.

1.1 Research questions for Task 2.3

The Expert Interview study contributes to answering the following research questions of the POIESIS project.

General research questions	More specific research questions
<p>RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?</p> <p>RQ3: To what extent and how does the <i>integration</i> of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?</p>	<p>How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?</p> <p>Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?</p> <p>What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?</p>

¹ The term 'integration' is used here under the definition of the POIESIS project: *Increased inclusion of citizens and societal stakeholders throughout the different phases of research and innovation cycles.*

1.2 Insights from Task 2.2 and Task 3.1

The expert interviews are the third empirical study conducted by POIESIS following 7 public consultations with citizens, organised in summer 2023, and 21 focus groups in total (three per country) with institutional actors in Spring 2024. Several observations have been made in Germany throughout these two studies with very different groups of actors that shape expectations for the expert interviews:

- Very generally, ‘trust in science’ is not perceived to be in crisis. It is rather trust in institutions or particular scientific disciplines that are perceived to be problematic in some contexts.
- The approaches to the concepts of research integrity and public integration vary considerably across groups of actors – according to whom one talks, there are differences in the definition but also the perception of the importance of these concepts.
- The relation between science and the media is perceived as crucial for public trust in science by various actors.
- Without any prompts for it, citizens at the public consultation and two out of three focus groups with different institutional actors extensively discussed the interplay of science and politics and science and industry. Both were always perceived as non-transparent and nearly always as highly problematic.

It is expected that these patterns are also observed in the expert interviews. The latter are also expected to provide more detailed insights into the ‘translation process’ between scientific findings and public perception of such findings, and the role different types of media play in this regard.

1.3 Brief summary of interview organisation

For the German expert interviews, six researchers and in total ten mediators have been recruited. Interesting **profiles of interview candidates** have been identified combining different approaches: first of all, suggestions for interview candidates have been collected among colleagues at Wissenschaft im Dialog (WiD). WiD is deeply rooted in the science communication community in Germany and colleagues working in different projects therefore have not only a deep knowledge of the German science communication landscape but also a huge network in this regard, that has already proven to be very helpful for POIESIS in the past. These first suggestions have then been complemented by further desktop research, always striving for achieving a balance of gender, different professional profiles and seniority levels in the sample. It was consciously aimed for including people at the beginning of their career in the sample as well. This way it was ensured to have a variety of perspectives represented in the expert interviews, including the ‘new generation’ of researchers and mediators.

For the mediators, we additionally aimed to cover different ‘mediating processes’, e.g. in different forms of media (radio, print journals, YouTube videos etc.), in relation to different topics (climate change, Covid-19 but also beyond), and for the institutional mediators to target different actors than in the focus group, which had mainly university communicators. Regarding the researchers, a successful starting point of research for potential interview candidates was a participatory online programme in which pupils can ask questions to researchers about specific topics but also their everyday working life in science. It has been

considered – and found to be true – that researchers having participated in this project might be particularly interested in discussing questions about public integration and trust in science. Several researchers have been recruited from this pool, the others, as indicated, have been identified through further desktop-research.

Potential interview candidates have been **contacted** via e-mail, explaining in detail what the POIESIS project and the expert interviews are about. It was made clear from the very beginning that interviews would be anonymised, and strict rules of data protection would apply. A deadline for feedback was given in the first e-mail and once this deadline had passed, a second e-mail was sent as a friendly reminder.

The overall **feedback in the recruitment process** especially among the mediators was very positive. Most of them responded rather quickly and were very motivated to participate in the project. The final sample consists, as planned, of two institutional and eight non-institutional mediators from different target groups (see Protocol T2.3). The only group of mediators that was impossible to be recruited in the German sample were activists. Despite several attempts to contact actors from climate change movements, no or only negative responses have been received.

Researchers were more difficult to recruit than mediators and this is even more true for researchers working on Covid-19. Despite efforts and different contact strategies, only two and not three researchers could be recruited from this field, one with a medical and one with a SSH background. To keep the researchers' sample at the same size, a fourth researcher from the field of climate change was recruited. The researchers sample therefore consists of two researchers working on Covid-19 and four researchers working on various aspects of climate change. In total, three out of the six researchers interviewed work have a SSH background. It was a surprise that researchers were so much more difficult to reach than mediators and it will be very interesting to compare experiences across POIESIS partner countries in this regard.

Coming to the **organisation of the interviews**, once a contact was established, potential interview candidates were asked to suggest two or three possible slots for the interviews and dates were fixed accordingly. Except for one interview that has been cancelled due to longer illness of the interview candidate and one that has been postponed for a week due to illness as well, all interviews took place as initially scheduled. One week before the interview, the candidates received the informed consent form, and all sent it back signed on time before the respective interviews. All interviews took place online with the same interviewer. Before starting the interview, the interviewer presented the POIESIS project and the objective of the interview once again and explained the next steps of the process. The duration of the interviews varied between 45 minutes and 1,5 hours but on average, they lasted around 60 minutes. Researchers' interviews are generally shorter than the ones with mediators. All interviews have been recorded. The **interview instruments** for researchers and mediators were very well suited for the interviews and only extended by one introductory question in the block on trust in science: "In your perception, how would you describe the current state of trust in science in Germany?"

A few days after the interview, all candidates received another e-mail thanking them for their time and efforts. All interviewees expressed their interest in being informed about the results of the interview study and the further progress of the project.

1.4 Brief summary of data processing

All sixteen interviews were recorded – with the permission of the interviewees – and then automatically transcribed with the help of the software f4x. The transcripts have been proofread and then analysed using the qualitative data processing software Atlas.ti. Mediators’ and researchers’ interviews have been analysed separately using different codebooks closely related to the chapters of this report (see Appendix). The main arguments from the two groups of interviewees were then extracted from the coded material and condensed for this report. The report focuses on opinions expressed by a majority or at least several of the interviewees but also gives space for individual opinions that seem particularly pertinent for addressing POIESIS’ research questions. The coding did not strictly follow the chronological order of the interviews as sometimes topics of interest were addressed in several parts of the interviews. The qualitative analysis of the coded material is the basis of the following chapters of this report.

Before providing the translated transcripts of the interviews to the Work Package Leader, they all will be carefully anonymised.

2 Participants in the Expert Interview study

The tables in sub-sections 2.1 and 2.2 present the sample of the mediator and researcher interviews in more detail and make comparisons at the international level easier. The level of detail is chosen to be as precise as possible but as general as necessary to ensure the anonymity of the interviewees.

2.1 Descriptive tables – Mediators

The following tables describe the sample of mediators interviewed for the POIESIS project, summarising their demographics and occupation, main communication tasks, outputs, channels used in their work, audiences addressed, their interactions with citizens, and finally, their main sources of information.

Table 1. Description of the Mediator interviews sample

ID	Gen.	Career stage*	Mediator type**	Organization type (where applicable)	Occupational Description	Topic CV/CC#
DE_M01	F	Mid	Institutional mediator working at universities or research institutes	Research Institute outside of University	Head of Communication	CC
DE_M02	F	Senior	Institutional mediator working at universities or research institutes	Research Institute at University	Head of Communication	CC
DE_M03	M	Senior	Professional science writer / communicator // Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc	Independent	Podcast Producer, Author of books, Science journalist	Sometimes CC but focus is on another discipline

DE_M04	M	Senior	Science / general journalist	Journalism platform	Chief Editor and Managing Director	CC
DE_M05	M	Senior	Professional science writer / communicator // Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. // Other content creator	Independent	Artist, Author, Performer	CC
DE_M06	F	Senior	Science / general journalist // Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.	Public Broadcasting (radio)	Editor and Head of Science Department	CV, CC, among others
DE_M07	F	Junior	Professional science writer / communicator	University & Independent	Post-Doc and independent science communicator	None, medical field
DE_M08	M	Senior	Science / general journalist	Weekly magazine (print & online)	Author and former Head of Science Department	CC & CV & others
DE_M09	M	Mid	Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.	Independent	Video producer, Podcaster	CC
DE_M10	F	Mid	Science / general journalist	Independent (mainly radio)	Author and editor	CC but also many others

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior

** Mediator type:

- Institutional Mediators working at publishers / working at universities or research institutes;
- Non-institutional mediators: a) Professional science writers/communicators; Science/general journalists; Authors of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.; Other content creators

Covid-19 or Climate Change or both (where applicable).

Table 2. Mediators' main communication tasks

ID	Description of mediators' main tasks
DE_M01	Collecting, synthesising and reviewing material from several research institutes on a specific topic to produce various outputs, handling press requests
DE_M02	'Translating' material from research institute into various outputs, handling press requests
DE_M03	Conducting background research and producing various outputs
DE_M04	Conducting background research, writing, working towards network creation
DE_M05	Exchanging with researchers and other stakeholders, producing various outputs, participating in live events
DE_M06	Coordinating the work of different authors and editors towards a common goal, oversight: "find, identify, and ensure the good implementation of topics"
DE_M07	Producing different text outputs to create a social media & online presence
DE_M08	Conducting background research, holding background conversations, producing journalistic outputs
DE_M09	Identifying salient topics, conducting background research and producing various outputs
DE_M10	Conducting background research and process scientific information for various outputs

Note: Mediators focussed their explanations on other aspects of their work, such as outputs and audiences than on their 'main tasks'. Therefore, and because most mediators are engaged in very different kinds of activities, the content of this table is very general. The most important considerations of mediators' creative process are reported in section 3.1.3.

The answers in Table 3 are limited to the outputs mediators mentioned during the interviews themselves and can therefore be considered to be the most important ones. Many of them may occasionally also produce videos etc. and all those saying they are active on social media (see Table 4) obviously also produce output there, but rarely mentioned this actively.

Table 3. Outputs produced by Mediators

ID	Books	Articles	Audiovisual (TV)	Radio program	Podcast	Audiovisual (social media)	Text Post (social media)	Live (social media interaction)	Other:
DE_M01									Live events, films (not necessarily TV); note: no clear mention which kinds of post on social media
DE_M02									Live events, press releases; quote: “we actually do everything related to communication” - there might be other formats from the table not mentioned explicitly
DE_M03									Stage shows, Workshops
DE_M04									Communication trainings, networking platform, background materials
DE_M05									Art, Games
DE_M06									Not clarified which kinds of posts on social media
DE_M07									
DE_M08									Live events

DE_M09									Videos/films (not TV)
DE_M10									

The answers in Table 4 are limited to the channels mediators mentioned during the interviews themselves and can therefore be considered to be the most important ones. Many of them may occasionally or even regularly also use other channels but did not mention them explicitly. Social media for example has for many mediators been kind of automatically implied in the question. Explicitly asking about it, one of them said: “Of course! It would not work without it” (DE_M02).

Table 4. Channels used by Mediators

ID	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)						Chat apps		Other:
	TV	Radio	Newspaper	Websites	Blogs	Newsletters	LinkedIn	YouTube	Twitter	Instagram	TikTok	Other SM	WhatsApp	Telegram	
DE_M01															Live events
DE_M02															Own print materials, via institutions and big organisations
DE_M03															Science magazines, live events, podcast platforms; note: no specific question asked about social media
DE_M04															
DE_M05															Very different channels, scheme not applicable for this mediator; mostly artistic performances
DE_M06															Online-platforms of media channels, podcast platforms; note: not clarified which further social media channels

DE_M07															
DE_M08															Live events; note: magazine not newspaper and no specific social media channels mentioned
DE_M09															Podcast platforms
DE_M10															Podcast platforms

Note: often mediators mention a website with an included blog, not really two separate things.

Note: the column 'Newspaper' nearly always implies online platforms of the respective newspapers / magazines as well.

Table 5. Audiences addressed by Mediators

ID	Brief description of Mediators' audiences/size estimate where known
DE_M01	4 audiences: Politics, industry (but not much addressed), research community, young public (not general public)
DE_M02	The general public and stakeholders (e.g. politics, public authorities, funders etc.) related to climate + international network of research community
DE_M03	Varies across activities: middle aged for podcast, children for books, people in their 20s without children for radio, retired for magazine
DE_M04	Other journalists (around 100.000 articles (scientific and non-scientific) using their own work, network of around 500 journalists, collaborations with around 1500 journalists), communicators of all sorts in the field of CC; 13.000 newsletter subscribers, 1.500.000 website visits per year
DE_M05	Reaching outside the scientific bubble, younger generations reached through artistic expression
DE_M06	Varies across activities: radio = middle aged but also 20-30 years, rather high level of formal education, but still as inclusive as possible; podcast = interested public, tendency a bit younger than for radio, generally higher formal education, objective is however to reach a group as diverse as possible
DE_M07	General public to improve basic knowledge of natural science, people affected by a particular disease
DE_M08	General public, print with another audience (50+) than online (-20 years)
DE_M09	Younger adults, young families, aged mid 20-mid 40 interested in climate & nature (around 9.000 Follower, video reach between 1.000 and 50.000 views)
DE_M10	Strongly depending on the format - everything between teenagers and older audience with higher level of formal education

Table 6. Mediators' interactions with citizens

ID	Brief description of Mediators' social interaction practices
DE_M01	Live events, social media discussions
DE_M02	Live events, social media discussions
DE_M03	E-Mail exchanges, stage shows, workshops and book presentations
DE_M04	No direct interactions with citizens as they are not the imminent audience
DE_M05	Many public talks, workshops after artistic performance, e-mail exchanges
DE_M06	Public events, e-mail exchange, social media
DE_M07	Social media interactions (but very early in the process, still building an audience)
DE_M08	Feedback, moderation of live events
DE_M09	Mainly online but also participation in live events
DE_M10	Limited, mostly comment sections under articles, feedback via e-mail, but the person is rather working in the background

Table 7 lists sources of information mediators explicitly mentioned to use for producing their outputs. These are often similar but not equivalent to the mediators' networks.

Table 7. Mediators' sources of information

ID	Interpersonal networks			Science press releases				Other:
	With researchers	With science communicators	Scientific literature	RPOs	Publishers	Mainstream media	Social media	
DE_M01								Newsletters to get an overview of topical issues
DE_M02								Important scientific organisations
DE_M03								Wikipedia as a source for interesting primary sources (but not as a source itself)
DE_M04								Main source for monitoring: social media
DE_M05								Nature observation
DE_M06								Interest groups / Associations, NGOs, citizens, important scientific organisations, Science Media Center Germany, Science magazines
DE_M07								Important scientific organisations
DE_M08								Important scientific organisations, as head of department: executive level of organisations, politics

DE_M09								Professional associations, Our World in Data, Science Media Center Germany, important scientific organisations, Federal Statistical Office, citizens (people affected by/involved in the topic); note: mainstream and social media as inspiration for interesting topics
DE_M10								News alerts, Science Media Center Germany

2.2 Descriptive tables – Researchers

The following tables describe the sample of researchers interviewed for the POIESIS project, summarising their demographics and occupation, the scientific focus of their work, their main dissemination channels and engagement in social integration practices.

Table 8. Description of the Researcher interviews sample

ID	Gen.	Career stage*	Position or title/Career stage**	Organisation type	Topic CV/CC#
DE_R01	F	Senior	Senior Researcher	Research Institute linked to a hospital	CV
DE_R02	M	Mid	Post-Doc	Research Institute linked to a university	CV
DE_R03	F	Mid	Research group leader	Interdisciplinary Research Institute	CC
DE_R04	M	Senior	Professor	University	CC
DE_R05	M	Senior	Research Associate	Research Institute linked to a university	CC
DE_R06	F	Early	PhD student	University	CC

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior ** ECR; recognised researcher; senior researcher; leading researcher (Professor)

The following information is kept very general in order to guarantee the interviewees' anonymity.

Table 9. Researchers' scientific focus

ID	Note
DE_R01	Researcher in the medical field working, among other topics, on Covid-19 infections despite vaccination
DE_R02	Researcher in the field of SSH working on social and political consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic
DE_R03	Researcher in the field of applied economics working on socio-economic impacts of climate change in the Global South
DE_R04	Researcher in the field of SSH working on socio-ecological transformations at different levels
DE_R05	Researcher from the natural science dealing with energy transition and sustainable energy supply
DE_R06	Researcher in SSH working on social consequences of climate change for younger generations

Table 10. How Researchers' work reaches the public

ID	Brief description of how the researchers' work reaches the public
DE_R01	Media requests (mainstream and science journalism), radio interviews, during Covid-19 pandemic also policy advising
DE_R02	Traditional media (newspapers), communication channels of research institute and other scientific organisations
DE_R03	Traditional media, radio
DE_R04	Traditional media (newspapers), contribution to science communication blog, in the past also science slams
DE_R05	Traditional media, talks and presentations for citizens and different stakeholders, specific interaction formats
DE_R06	Through specific interaction formats and typical communication events (Long Night of Science), media requests

The activities mentioned in this table relate to activities that go beyond the communication of scientific results via various channels (see above).

Table 6. Description of social integration practices of Researchers

ID	Brief notes of Researchers' social integration practices
DE_R01	Projects with involvement of patient organisations
DE_R02	Currently none, focus groups to assess validity of quantitative data streams planned
DE_R03	Workshops with stakeholders and focus groups with affected target groups in the Global South
DE_R04	Workshops with stakeholders, no social integration of citizens in current projects
DE_R05	Implied in research projects in the context of a living lab - co-creation of science and society
DE_R06	Youth Council planned to be involved in planning and evaluation of research projects (in the sense of a citizens' council)

3 Analysis of Mediator interviews

The upcoming chapter presents the most important arguments brought forward by the mediators during the interviews. The chapter is structured in five sections: section 3.1 provides insights into mediators' perspectives on their mediation work, including their motivations, different audiences, creative processes and other relevant aspects of their mediating process. Section 3.2 synthesises mediators' thoughts on the topics of research integrity and the trustworthiness of different sources, especially regarding the question of how to actually assess this trustworthiness. Section 3.3 then presents mediators' perceptions of the state of public trust in science, the main concerns they think citizens have towards science, the most important rationales or reasons for mistrust and also some thoughts on the mediators' own role in regard to trust. Very shortly, section 3.4 introduces two additional themes that came up recurrently in the mediators' interviews: science communication more generally than covered in the section on chains of mediation and, secondly, the specific role of media in the translation process between science and society. The chapter ends with a synthesis of the recommendations made by the mediators, structured along different dimensions of trust they address.

3.1 Chains of mediation

The first section of this chapter deals with mediators' thoughts and perspectives on the mediating process, their own motivations in their work as mediators, their audiences and what having different audiences implies, the most important aspects of their creative process, and, finally, other themes that came up in regard to the overarching topic of chains of mediation (social media, networks, and direct interactions).

3.1.1 Mediators' motivations and objectives

Mediators express different motivations and objectives in relation to their work. One recurring objective several of the mediators mentioned is to make science accessible for non-experts: “building bridges between science and the public” (DE_M05); “acting as an interface between experts and the broader discourse” (DE_M04). To reach this objective, mediators focus their work on demystifying complex scientific concepts and presenting them in a way that is understandable and relatable. Such accessibility is not merely about simplifying information but ensuring that it is embedded in the relevant context. They aim to deliver well-researched information one can trust and use. Indeed, one mediator described specifically that a huge part of his motivation lies in transforming misunderstood quick headlines into comprehensive and accurate overviews. Another one said their main objective was to work towards clearing up misunderstandings in regard to scientific topics which evolve around headlines.

In this same vein, another key motivation for mediators is the objectification of discussions around scientific topics. Particularly important in this regard, according to several mediators, is the accurate representation of how science truly works, including information on existing blind spots, uncertainties, and the scientific process itself: “We

always want to convey how science works, including the gaps and open questions, and that is quite demanding” (DE_M06).

Some of the mediators also indicated personal fulfilment and the pursuit of activities that they find pleasurable and meaningful as part of their motivation. Such personal satisfaction is closely tied to their professional objectives, as they believe that doing things that make them happy enhances the quality and impact of their work.

Mediators working on climate change, added agenda-setting to the more general motivations explained above. They aim to keep the most important topics relating to climate change on the public agenda. Additionally, and depending on their activities and audiences, mediators added that they aim to improve the work of other actors also working on climate change; that they “hope [to] contribute to keeping the climate protection discussion fact-oriented” (DE_M04); that they strive to sensitise people to the importance of nature and our relationship with it (“I want to encourage people to see themselves as part of the whole again, to meet nature on equal terms.” – DE_M05); and that they are trying to fulfil a model function for others with the objective for our children to have a safe future.

Lastly, and in relation to climate change but also other topics, several mediators expressed that they aim to contribute to a more positive framing of science and scientific findings instead of always ‘bad news’: “Instead of being bombarded with bad news from all sides, we want to sprinkle in some positivity, which will hopefully spread optimism and motivation” (DE_M09). The observation that science in public discourse is very often linked to ever more negative findings was made by several mediators and estimated to have an important influence on public trust in science (see section 3.3). Mediators in the interviews expressed the desire to work in the opposite direction to inspire action and engagement, encouraging individuals to become pro-active in seeking and implementing solutions.

3.1.2 Mediators’ audiences

Generally, one can say that the audiences of the mediators who have been interviewed are very diverse. Even more, many of the mediators actually have several different audiences depending on the various activities they engage in. In this regard, mediators’ audiences range from young children in daycare to retired engineers, encompass various political and societal stakeholders, and many others. The following paragraphs therefore do not explain the different audiences of the mediators in detail (see Table 5 in this regard) but present some overarching thoughts mediators expressed in regard to audiences and how to address them.

First of all, mediators clearly agreed that different audiences require different communication approaches, formats and channels. For example, one of the institutional mediators described that her institution tries to reach young people rather via social media but addresses political stakeholders mainly in live events. In this regard, mediators use different formats to reach people in various situations of their daily lives, e.g. podcast for car rides, radio emissions for cooking in the kitchen. Being engaged in different

formats can therefore lead to capturing more audiences than when one concentrates on only one. Then again, different formats – and with it, different audiences – require mediators to vary the language they use and also, for example, the amount of sources they cite – without compromising content depth and quality.

Regarding different audiences, one mediator also underlined that people differ in regard to their receptiveness for different kinds of messages: some individuals are better reached by facts, while others respond better to emotional appeals and arguments.

Finally, several of the mediators raised the question of difficult-to-reach audiences and how to deal with the fact that their content is mostly consumed by an already interested public. And indeed, they had different opinions about this:

“You have to reach people outside the scientific bubble. People who voluntarily go to a natural history museum or attend [a scientific conference] already know all this. There’s not much to gain there. But art and culture are great because: who wants to read a boring paper? But if I package it with [art], I can reach entirely new audiences.” – DE_M05

“I think it’s legitimate to reach this bubble [of the already scientifically interested]. I don’t think it’s correct to say we’ve already won them over for science, so we don’t need to communicate with them anymore. Because those people can still have a big impact, and it’s important to keep them engaged with good science communication. At the same time, I’m very aware that I won’t reach many people who don’t have the intrinsic motivation to engage with these findings.” – DE_M10

Reaching new audiences and target groups and improving an overall public understanding of science and the scientific process has also been an important part of the mediators’ considerations in regard to recommendations to enhance public trust in science (see section 3.5).

3.1.3 Mediators’ creative process

Once again, this section does not describe the mediators’ individual creative processes but rather synthesises the main important points brought forward in this regard. Very generally said, mediators described important differences in their creative processes depending on what kinds of outputs they produce. Mediators differentiated on the one hand between online and offline content, longer and shorter formats, and on the other hand also between rather long-term topics they work on or news-driven content.

For nearly all mediators, their creative process involves first of all identifying salient topics that are at the same time important within the scientific community and awaken public interest. This aspect is particularly important for science journalists (“The typical process is that we try to stay ahead of the game and identify the topic ourselves before any laypeople in the editorial office think it would be great to cover.” DE_M08), but other

mediators equally underline the importance of identifying the most relevant topics of the moment. On the one hand, this means searching pro-actively and independently for interesting topics, for example as one mediator notes, by monitoring social media. This search is however limited by a lack of time and resources. In this regard, news outlets, news alerts, and platforms such as the Science Media Center are invaluable for identifying interesting new findings according to several mediators. On the other hand, once facing new scientific findings, the relevance of the latter for public discourse needs to be assessed:

“Of course, our assessment is important in this regard: How relevant is what is being published or what the institution is working on for the public discourse? Many people think you get a press release and just write it down. But at least for us, it’s different: we assess its relevance. If it doesn’t have any, no matter how great the press release, it won’t be processed because it’s not relevant to us at the moment.” (DE_M04)

Once a relevant scientific topic identified, many mediators underline the significant challenge of obtaining a comprehensive overview regarding this topic. This is crucial as all of them see it as one of their main objectives to provide well-contextualised information to their audiences (see section 3.1.1). One mediator emphasised that this is even the most difficult aspect of his work. It is made even more difficult by the fact that it is not common in all scientific disciplines to provide a state of the art in a new scientific paper itself. Press releases, for example from universities, also only rarely provide the actual scientific context for the new finding at stake.

To navigate this challenge, mediators employ a variety of strategies. A majority of them stated that they start by consulting secondary literature, including reports on the topic in mainstream media or popular science magazines. Another valuable starting point for one of the mediators is Wikipedia, not at all as trusted source of information but as a means of identify interesting primary sources that are linked in the articles.

Once an initial overview is established, mediators turn to primary literature and scientific studies for more details and also get into contact with researchers working on these topics directly. Having some basic knowledge about the topic beforehand is essential in these conversations to prevent researchers from defaulting to a simplistic, ‘journalism-mode’ explanation, which might lack the depth and precision needed for accurate science communication. Interestingly, mediators have very different approaches when they reach out to researchers: one mediator said that it is easier to reach scientists via their communication departments, likely because the request is more formal then and might have more weight, while another one said they often contact researchers directly and this works better.

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the information received, mediators further often seek second opinions from other researchers (see also section 3.2.2). This step of

double-checking with additional experts helps to verify facts and to provide a well-rounded perspective on the topic.

Time is a crucial factor in this entire process of gathering and contextualising information, and it is often a scarce resource, especially in the fast-paced world of journalism. The extent to which mediators are able to engage in this thorough process of contextualisation often depends on the resources available to them but also the format of their work. How much background information and research is needed also differs for mediators depending on whether the topic at stake is part of their own thematic expertise. For mediators without a scientific background, the task is even more difficult as scientific papers can be lengthy and highly technical. The temporary nature of scientific findings further adds complexity, as new perspectives can emerge even after an article is finished (see also section 3.3 about public trust in science).

At the end of the creative process is the output created by the mediators. In this regard, mediators underlined that in no matter which form, outputs need to be comprehensible and relatable to the public. Numbers and facts should be presented in a way that resonates with people's daily lives. The most important objective is always to reach the respective audience and make them remember their own content, for example by means of storytelling and incorporating surprising elements in the content.

Reflecting their own creative process, several mediators, especially science journalists, expressed their 'difficult standing' in the sense that objectifying sensational debates and often downplaying the significance of said-to-be new scientific breakthroughs or, in the context of climate change delivering always bad news, sometimes can be perceived as killjoys. However, one mediator underlined that he is happy to have the possibility to act as a contextualising intermediary in this regard:

“They could say, 'Ah, he always makes it so complicated, says it's not as exciting as it really is. He always talks down the sensational news.' But no, I get the space from the editors to explain it thoroughly from the start. And sometimes, the sensation has to be downplayed compared to how it initially sounds in the reporting. But I enjoy that.” – DE_M03

3.1.4 Further themes in regard to chains of mediation

Further topics discussed by the mediators in regard to their process of mediation were the use of social media, the importance of personal networks, and different forms of interactions with the mediators' audiences.

Social media plays a pivotal role in modern mediation. Several mediators indicated that Twitter was once a key platform for science communication but that this long over. LinkedIn has emerged as a significant platform in this regard, newer social media channels like Mastodon and BlueSky have not yet achieved the same level of success.

TikTok, on the other hand, is viewed as a platform with lots of influence but it is also considered to be dangerous by several mediators. Two of them even expressed a desire for it to be banned. Very generally, when reflecting on the question whether to engage in social media or not, mediators mainly came to the conclusion that they do not really have a choice (see also section 3.5 on recommendations):

“I hate the social media game. It’s no fun at all. I just like making these videos and hope to reach people. But without social media, it somehow doesn’t work.” – DE_M09

“I’m often very hesitant to attempt such things simply because I know that the [scope] is very limited. The possibility of actually providing context, classifying studies, ensuring that polarisation doesn’t become even more extreme, that I would actually have to be even more polarising for these formats to be successful on social networks. At the same time, the question arises whether giving up entirely is the right approach. I haven’t found a solution yet. But certainly, if we know how many hours people spend on these platforms, they are actually highly relevant [...] places where science communication and journalism should take place.” – DE_M10

Long-lasting personal networks are indicated to be crucial for their work by a majority of mediators. Using these networks but also snowballing effects building on their initial networks help them acquire new contacts and information. Mediators mentioned that it helps building such networks to express gratitude and recognise efforts, particularly when engaging with researchers as a journalist. Further, one’s own institutional affiliations, both current and former, help to build networks, as they indicate that one comes from the same ‘bubble’. Networks do however not only serve as sources of information but also as support systems for others in the field:

“I believe that [...] I now have a network of people who are also concerned about the climate, and it’s very enriching. But someone doesn’t start there. I remember how lonely I felt when I first encountered these issues. So, I would like to try to connect these people.” – DE_M09

Mediators engage in different forms of **interactions** with their audiences. In this regard, several mediators who primarily work online underlined the great experience of live interactions at offline events. They describe these as opportunities to receive positive feedback and create personal connections.

Regarding different forms of interactions, all mediators made clear that it is important to keep the eyes open for different audiences. While organising formats of science communication for children, such as children’s universities, is perceived to be very important, one mediator also emphasised the equal importance of debate formats for adults to create an interaction and not to lose out on audiences (see also section 3.1.1).

ID here	Additional quotes
DE_M09	“Some people are very receptive to fact-based arguments; they need the reasoning behind why, for example, a vehicle works more efficiently than a combustion engine. Others need an emotional appeal.”
DE_M05	“Making them understand that everything that goes against nature ultimately goes against us humans.”
DE_M03	“The greatest or the most difficult task in my work is often getting an overview.”
DE_M03	“It’s often difficult to get answers to these questions from press releases from universities. You don’t usually get them from papers either. You’re most likely to get them if you have researchers on the phone.”
DE_M08	“But the ideal solution [when identifying interesting topics] is to recognise something that carries weight in the scientific community and also captures public interest.”
DE_M09	“The real success for me is when I notice that someone does something differently in real life because of something they learned from me.”
DE_M05	“The most important thing for me is to open up new grounds for sensitivity, to reach new groups that have never dealt with these topics before.”

3.2 About research integrity and the trustworthiness of sources

The upcoming section synthesises mediators’ views on research integrity and – as this goes strongly together in their discourses – their main criteria for the assessment of trustworthy sources and the importance this has for their work. The section ends with a few positive and negative examples of integrity and trustworthy sources that have been mentioned by several mediators each.

Very generally, one can say that the first reaction to the question of what research integrity is and what it means for the mediators was very often, ‘Wow, this is a difficult question’ and answers often started with a negative definition, i.e. what research integrity is not. From an analytical point of view, mediators discussed aspects of three different dimensions of integrity: research integrity, journalistic integrity, and personal integrity. The delineation between scientific and journalistic integrity was not always very sharp in this regard. Many norms and values are coherent in both dimensions – being honest, transparent, contextualising findings (see also below) – but it has also been mentioned several times that combining the functioning logics of journalism and research is often challenging. Demands, expectations, and objectives differ between the two worlds: journalism often seeks to capture clicks and attention, aiming for broad reach, whereas

science and scientists prioritise a differentiated and ‘neutral’ communication of new findings. The personal integrity of mediators, then, relates to mediators having to reflect on their own values and standards, for example in the choice of events they attend, or moderate, the topics they report on etc. It seems particularly difficult for mediators to juggle these different dimensions of integrity, certainly more than for researchers.

As a last general note, interestingly, actual scientific misconduct, such as data fabrication or falsification, was not a significant concern for mediators – neither in their own spontaneous reaction to the question of research integrity nor when asked about it directly. They did not perceive scientific misconduct as widespread in the scientific community and also considered that it is not strongly related to public trust in science. In this regard, they saw issues like hidden agendas, interest-led research, third-party interests, and lobbying as much more problematic. This very same picture has already emerged from the public consultation as well as from the focus groups in Germany. One could therefore draw the preliminary conclusion, that no matter from which perspective – as very different groups of actors have participated in the different POIESIS studies – perceived threats to research integrity are much more about external influences rather than internal scientific practices.

3.2.1 Mediators’ definitions of research integrity

Taken altogether, mediators had rather similar definitions of research integrity even though with varying focal points.

One of the key principles of research integrity in the view of mediators is to communicate solely within one’s field of expertise and declining requests outside of it, even when coming from prominent media outlets. Integrity demands honesty, adherence to facts, transparency about sources, and the inclusion of all observations, regardless of whether they support one’s hypotheses. Mediators stress that clinging to untenable viewpoints is against research integrity and that it is very important to make clear when one defends a minority opinion in the field. Respecting others’ expertise and not advancing oneself unjustifiably is essential. The wish was expressed that researchers would more often refer to colleagues with similar expertise in order to make the field of research more visible and clearer to the mediators. Further, a rigorous research process must always be more important than outcomes or considerations of potential applications of the findings one wishes for.

Transparency, righteousness, and authenticity in communication are crucial, with a focus on being open about uncertainties and limitations and pro-actively talking about them. Researchers should be upfront about funding sources and any interest-led research, ensuring independence from external influences such as political expectations. These principles also extend to mediation and communication more generally. In essence, research integrity is about maintaining honesty, transparency, and authenticity as well as being aware of and open about one’s own expertise and its limitations in both research and communication.

One mediator specified that research integrity means being objective and transparent “and partly, I would prefer transparency, which is more a preference of my generation, to objectivity” (DE_M10). This leads to probably the most prominent topic in the mediators’ discussion of research integrity: potential conflicts of interest and the question of activism, i.e. how activist are researchers allowed to be?

Nearly all mediators emphasised that conflicts of interest and activism pose significant challenges to research integrity. While they are aware that being truly ‘objective’ is not realistic, they perceive striving to avoid interest-led research as crucial. In this regard, scientists’ engagement in industry or politics can potentially undermine the perception of the latter’s integrity, necessitating transparent disclosure of such activities. Generally, addressing potential conflicts of interest proactively is viewed positively.

Mediators also reflected on their own work in this regard and highlighted the importance of contextualising contributions from people having scientific expertise but working for example in industry or are activists. They consider it as crucial to acknowledge these people’s potential biases in their communications. Especially in the field of technology, most experts come from industry. It is therefore even more important to keep in mind that they might pursue their own interests, according to the mediators.

Related to potential conflicts of interest is also the question of how activist researchers, particularly in fields like climate change, can or should be. Several mediators stated that many scientists in this discipline feel compelled towards activism due to the urgency of the issue – and the feeling that nothing is being done – but that the line between scientific freedom and personal opinion is thin. It should always be made clear which part of one’s communication is about a scientific discovery and which part of it is about one’s own personal and normative conviction regarding what it means. Generally, transparency and honesty about scientists’ (but also mediators’) activism and related information are vital as “[t]he greatest danger to the presumption of integrity is the suspicion of a hidden agenda” (DE_M08). A suggested approach is for scientists to clearly distinguish when they speak as private citizens versus as researchers.

“There are plenty of examples where not only economic but also socio-political engagement can indeed clash with scientific results and ultimately raise questions. Whether it actually damages integrity probably depends on how the individuals handle and manage it. But it certainly raises questions.” – DE_M04

“One remains integer when one marks it: ‘I have made the following findings, let’s say about the current state of climatic development in Germany and the weather consequences. But I also have a belief, a normative conviction, about what that should mean’.” – DE_M08

“And of course, there is also the question of how activist someone can be. This has almost become a derogatory term. But naturally, if you see something going

wrong and it drives you crazy, you are more emotionally involved. But I think integrity is about clearly distinguishing and being transparent.” – DE_M06

A challenge in this regard, especially in the field of climate change, is that “there is a strong desire for advice. People want to know what they should do. [...] And as a scientist, navigating that jungle is not always easy” (DE_M02).

As mentioned above, mediators reflected also on the relation between research integrity and journalistic norms. One mediator said there should be guidelines for communication equivalent to those of good scientific practice for researchers. Another one expressed the opinion that scientific integrity actually encompasses pretty much the same standards as existing guidelines for good work in journalism, such as the press code of conduct. In any case, mediators agreed that scientists as much as journalists (and other mediators) should act as honest brokers with transparency being the most important point in this regard.

3.2.2 Mediators’ assessment of the trustworthiness of sources

The arguments presented in this section are primarily based on the interviewees’ answers to the question of how they assess trustworthiness of their sources (asked before prompting for research integrity). When the question about trustworthiness of sources was asked, only one mediator made the connection to the concept of research integrity. Nevertheless, the answers to this question were very much coherent with the mediators’ main important points in the definition of ‘research integrity’ (see section 3.2.1) and therefore should be thought together.

From an overall perspective, one can say that mediators base their assessment of the trustworthiness of sources on three main factors: formal criteria, the expertise of the authors, and, very importantly, their own expertise and experience in the field.

Formal criteria

Among other formal criteria mediators use to assess the trustworthiness of sources, peer-review is clearly perceived to be the most important mechanism of quality control. Many mediators stated that they exclusively use peer-reviewed sources in their work. In the few exceptional cases in which they use pre-prints or else, they clearly communicate about that and explain why they need to work with these sources and what that means for the certainty of the findings. Mediators also rely on the reputation of journals and their impact factor when assessing the trustworthiness of a new scientific study and – if time allows – also on citation indexes of particular authors. Important is also the institution behind any publication, its reputation, and of course the question of whether institutions or organisations are financed by external stakeholders. Both institutional mediators in the sample stated that they depart from the basic assumption that what the researchers in their research centres are doing is trustworthy. However, the individual expertise of the authors and, for example, their career stages still play a role in assessing their work.

Expertise of authors

This leads to the expertise of authors as the second factor that has been mentioned by all mediators in relation to the question of how they assess the trustworthiness of their sources. When searching for reliable sources or researchers to deepen their knowledge on a specific topic (see section 3.1.3), mediators look out for experts in the field. Crucial questions in this context are: Who actually conducts research on this topic? Who has already published in this field? Of course, the position and career advancement of researchers plays a role in this regard but not exclusively:

“So, it is definitely not enough to quote someone just because they have a title; you have to check if they can speak credibly, if it aligns with the rest of the research. So, it's important for me to be able to assess that.” – DE_M03

Mediators underlined that when talking to researchers it is very important to them that the latter clearly communicate their own certainties and uncertainties and the limitations of their own work. A majority of mediators stated that it makes researchers more reliable to act as honest brokers, not trying to convince them of only their point of view but already offering some contextualisation themselves.

One mediator clearly stated that his objective in searching for potential experts to rely on in specific disciplines is always to do enough background research about the individual people to be able to make a statement about their general positions and the quality of their work. Once their expertise established, these researchers then enjoy a leap of trust from the side of the mediator the next time he sees some content coming from them. In this regard, networks and snowballing effects play an important role because once you have established the trustworthiness and expertise of one leading actor, the people who work closely with them are easier to trust as well.

Own expertise and experience

Besides relying on formal criteria and the authors' individual expertise, the most important factor for mediators in assessing the trustworthiness of sources is their own expertise and experience in the field. They state that over the years, they have come to know reliable sources in the respective disciplines, some of the most important authors in the field, and also know what is 'going on' in the different disciplines content-wise. When they hear about a potentially 'new' finding for example, they are often directly able to judge whether the discovery is really new or not:

“You develop a certain competence over the years on specific topics, so you can say, 'I've heard that three times before; it was new last year, so it can't be new now.’” – DE_M02

Mediators vary in their self-assessment regarding the question in how far they are able to judge on the quality of the scientific work itself. One mediator clearly stated that he

has ‘an eye for statistics’ and is able to see when results have been ‘optimised’ or seem weird, others stated that they are not able to assess the quality of the scientific work as such but rather go by the assessment of the author(s) and also the knowledge of the topic more generally. Another mediator clearly noticed differences in his ability to assess the quality of scientific work himself depending on whether the content relates to his own field of expertise or not.

All mediators strongly underlined the importance of contextualisation and getting second opinions in the assessment of sources’ trustworthiness and also to gain a comprehensive overview of the field. When assessing a ‘new’ scientific finding they conduct background research on questions like how did others communicate on this topic? How can the finding be contextualised in the field? They also compare newer data with older models and often ask a second expert to comment on the new study and therefore conduct a ‘mini peer-review’ themselves (see also section 3.1.3). In this regard, they strongly rely on their own personal network and years of experience in their work. Taken altogether, mediators always check the plausibility of any new scientific discoveries. They further judge it as crucially important that researchers themselves pro-actively address the limitations of their own research:

“Are they trying to hide something from you, or do they come to you with the whole truth and explain where there may still be gaps? Not knowing something, in my opinion, also impacts credibility.” – DE_M09

“We are always sceptical when someone gives the impression that they can answer everything.” – DE_M06

Overall, gaining an overview of the state of research and being able to contextualise new findings might be the most important aspect in mediators’ assessment of the trustworthiness of sources:

“I must be able to reflect on the state of research. I cannot pretend that a single result fell from the sky and that nothing was known before. That is a common journalistic mistake, seeing paradigm shifts everywhere when there are none. When 50 papers make a statement and one says something different, it is still 50 to one.” – DE_M08

Importance of research integrity for the mediators’ work

Knowing trustworthy sources is vital for mediators to avoid disseminating unreliable information. They feel a responsibility towards their audience to provide accurate and reliable information. This topic is omnipresent, even if not always explicitly discussed in terms of ‘integrity’ (although the mediators’ definition of research integrity is very similar to their definition and criteria for trustworthy sources, see section 3.2.1). This means,

mediators work under the premise of choosing reliable sources, but assess researchers' integrity indirectly through their work and reputation:

“It is important to me that the people I use as sources have standards of scientific integrity, and I try to determine that based on various criteria. Naturally, when I talk to experts, I don't initially discuss their integrity standards but try to determine it by other factors.” – DE_M10

Mediators recognise that trust in science is built on the consistent delivery of accurate and transparent information. Their own credibility depends on the reliability of the sources they use and their ability to contextualise and accurately present the information. This responsibility underscores the importance of ongoing assessment and verification processes in their work. The responsibility to transmit reliable information extends to the choice of platforms and methods used to communicate scientific findings.

One mediator with a non-scientific background very honestly stated that assessing scientific sources correctly is a very challenging task for him as he never learned how to do it – but that it is of course crucial for his work. This reflects the important challenge for mediators to be at the crossroads of science and communication and juggle the partly diverging requirements of both.

3.2.3 Positive and negative examples in regard to research integrity

Asked about positive or negative cases of research integrity, examples of poor research integrity invoked by mediators often involved researchers giving unfounded opinions in a discipline which is not their own. There has been a particularly prominent example for this during the Covid-19 crisis in Germany which has been mentioned by nearly all mediators. According to the mediator, such ventures in other disciplines often happen out of one's overconfidence and also to support the own political views. It goes exactly against the crucial criteria of knowing one's own expertise highlighted several times by mediators regarding the assessment of trustworthy sources (see above). Several mediators observe that such unfounded interventions in disciplines outside of the researchers' actual expertise are more often observed among male than female researchers and also that “more men than women” tend to communicate the limitations of their expertise or findings not very clearly (DE_M06).

The replication crisis, which raised concerns about the reliability of published research for example in the field of psychology, and which was one of the case studies discussed in the public consultations of the POIESIS project, was also mentioned once as an example of poor scientific integrity. The mediator perceived the crisis to have had an important impact in the scientific field but beyond that, was noticed rather by an interested public.

One reliably trustworthy source, and therefore positive example in regard to research integrity, mentioned by several mediators is the Science Media Center Germany. In the context of climate change, several mediators referred to the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) and the PIK (Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research). More generally, mediators estimate positive examples of integrity to be researchers who do not claim undue credit for their work and are transparent about their individual contributions to group work.

In conclusion, mediators are very aware of the multifaceted nature of the concept of integrity and highlight the different dimensions it entails for their work: scientific, journalistic and personal integrity. Their approach to ensuring trustworthiness in the sources they use involves relying on articles having gone through peer-review, and clear communication of uncertainties as well as transparency about conflicts of interest from the side of the experts they consult. Contextualisation is the key for all mediators in this regard. Although ‘research integrity’ as a term is not strongly present in the mediators’ daily work – and the question about it raised some hesitancy among some of them – their explanations of how to assess trustworthy sources show how crucial research integrity implicitly is for their work and how reflected they are in dealing with it.

ID	Additional quotes
DE_M03	“So, don’t invent things, don’t conceal the achievements of others, and don’t stubbornly cling to your own standpoint without good reason. These are the three things that come to mind first, without much thought.”
DE_M03	“Integrity includes acknowledging when other research groups or researchers have achieved similar, the same, or even better results.”
DE_M04	“It must be clear to me that what makes science ‘science’ is adhered to and that this takes precedence over how [results] will be used later.”
DE_M04	“So, a clearly adhered process and methodology. Clarity about what is established and what is not. Honesty, if you will, and transparency regarding the funding and purpose of the research. I consider this extremely important in terms of integrity.”
DE_M06	“And that also relates to how someone communicates, whether, for example, they clearly state where their expertise ends and say, ‘I can still say something about it, but you need to ask someone else as well,’ or whether they themselves mark uncertainties. That significantly impacts the assessment.”
DE_M02	“What is scientific freedom? What is personal opinion? That is sometimes a fine line.”
DE_M08	“Once you are trained, you know by the book how the professional evaluation of research quality goes. And for that, you need to be a science

	journalist; you can't just be anything else. That is the internal distinction we have, which is somewhat threatened by the sheer quantity of online content.”
DE_M03	“Press releases from universities, as I said, generally have substance but are one-sided.”
DE_M07	“There are often interviews where the scientists, for instance, whenever a TV crew or journalism team comes in for an interview, the first thing the professors do is to unpack their white coats, even though they never wear a coat in their entire lives otherwise.”

3.3 About public trust in science

This section explores the complex dynamics surrounding public trust in science, drawing on the insights provided by mediators. It will be particularly interesting to compare the main arguments presented here with those made by researchers on the same topic (see section 4.4). This section first of all covers the mediators’ perceptions of trust in science from a rather general perspective, then examines reasons for mistrust, and in the end, presents how the mediators see their own role in regard to trust in science. The findings are organised into various sub-chapters to provide a comprehensive understanding of this complex topic.

3.3.1 Perception of trust in science

When asked about their perception of the current state of trust in Germany, mediators responded from three different perspectives: from a general point of view, talking about trust in science as a system and with a focus on differences between societal groups; related to climate change; and in the context of Covid-19.

General

The majority opinion among mediators is that basic trust in science in Germany is high – with some mediators basing this statement on concrete figures they know, others on their overall perception. One mediator specified that he thinks, people have a basic trust in the scientific method itself, independent of individual actors, e.g. researchers; another one noted that the public generally trusts in the fact that scientists are working to generate scientific findings rather than serving government or third-party interests. Several mediators also invoked the fact that in Germany, even climate change deniers, anti-vax activists etc. very often justify their discourses with (pseudo-)scientific arguments. One then highlighted what this means, in turn, for the standing of science in the public discourse:

“I always notice on platforms, like TikTok and others, how many people base their claims on supposed scientific findings. Without claiming that this is actually

meaningful or that they are real scientific findings. But I simply notice how many people justify statements with science. That already proves that there is a certain acceptance that science can indeed produce reliable findings.” – DE_M10

This phenomenon can however also be dangerous because such pseudo-scientific findings and relying on ‘scientific studies’ for any kind of argument creates a false image of science and conveys the messages that scientific findings are not necessarily reliable.

A majority of mediators further observes active attempts to undermine trust in science in public discourse and perceive this as a great danger and an important reason for growing mistrust in parts of society (see also section 3.3.2): “There is a very high level of trust in scientists, which is targeted whenever it suits certain people to cast doubt. Unfortunately, a few people do this almost for fun” – DE_M04.

One mediator raised the thought that negative reactions to the presentation of scientific findings are not always due to the fact that people do not believe in these findings but that the latter do not match one’s individual worldview:

“And then someone says again, ‘We need to explain things better’. No, we actually need to understand what’s happening first. Then we can think about the right communication. But if we just sit there and say, ‘People are a bit too stupid, they don’t have time, and they’re not well-informed,’ and then explain the same facts for the hundredth time in another language, it doesn’t change anything unless we understand why there’s such a strong counter-reaction.” – DE_M04

This aspect is also underlined by another mediator who adds that knowing and understanding the fears and apprehensions in regard to specific topics and in relation to a specific audience helps to actually address these and therefore reach people.

There are two last aspects in regard to trust in science from a very general perspective that mediators discussed: first, mediators also invoked the importance of scientific freedom and the need for ‘basic research’ which may not have immediate practical applications but is essential for long-term scientific progress. They noted that this kind of research appears not to be very ‘useful’ at first sight in the eyes of many citizens and that this is partly problematic. This aspect has also been discussed as a concern in regard to intensified social integration in the research process (see section 4.3.2) and was an important topic of debate in the German POIESIS focus groups as well.

Second, overall, the role of institutions in regard to public trust in science did not play an important role in mediators’ discourses with the exception of one institutional mediator who specified that the institutional affiliation of researchers is in her view crucial for trust in science. Laypeople are not able to check on individual researchers and their expertise, but they may trust in the reputation of an institution. She noticed however, that the importance of such institutional affiliation is often neglected in the media, when

researchers are only cited by their profession (e.g. ‘XY is a marine biologist’) instead of mentioning where the expert is working.

Differences in trust across societal groups

Mediators reflected extensively on differences between societal groups in regard to trust in science. Several of them stated that polarisation and anti-science attitudes are loud voices in the current public discourse, amplified through social media platforms, but that they do not think that these people reflect a majority opinion in the German public.

Several mediators also noted that those who are sceptical towards science, are very often the same people who are sceptical towards other institutions, such as journalistic and political ones as well. These people generally question all kinds of ‘authority’ and it is therefore difficult to distinguish these different dimensions sharply:

“The target group that expresses fundamental criticism towards science is also generally critical of the media organisations I work for or fundamentally does not trust journalistic integrity. So, it is not that easy for me to separate.” – DE_M10

Mediators also reported on their own individual experiences with people who are rather sceptical towards science. One stated that he sometimes tries to engage and start an interaction with ‘haters’ online and sometimes succeeds in having positive feedback (one researcher reported similar experiences, see section 4.2.2). Two other mediators noted that the critiques they receive are often at a very high level of detail and often appear to have the objective of displaying first of all the critics’ own expertise on the topic (both noted that it is more often men than women doing so). In this regard, yet another mediator stated that in his experience, the biggest challenge when it comes to public trust in science are neither people with high nor low levels of formal education, but those in the middle suffering from an “illusion of competence”: “Trust is difficult with people who think they can generate their own theories but do not have the tools for it” (DE_M08).

Finally, the complex question of reaching people who are very distant from science has been discussed by many mediators (a recurrent topic in all discussions held in the course of the POIESIS project so far). It was noted that many people still perceive scientists as sitting in their ‘ivory tower’ and having no connection to real life and the people’s daily life problems. There are even very dominant fears in this regard as one mediator from the medical field reported that people often react with panic when she explains that she conducts research on a specific disease (because they are afraid of getting infected etc.).

Building on that, she developed the thought that if people are not in contact with science and do not understand what is going on, why should they trust science and scientists then? If they would do so (trust in science) without an actual understanding of science as a system, this would be blind – instead of ‘informed’ – trust and this is not the desired outcome either.

Trust in science and the Covid-19 pandemic

Mediators saw the Covid-19 pandemic as a critical juncture in regard to public trust in science. Several of them stated that they have the impression that the entire question of whether one trusts in science has only been a topic of discussion since the pandemic. This is because, for the first time in a long time, a majority of the population actually has been confronted with and dealt with scientific questions and took an interest in what was going on. Even people who normally never are in touch with science, suddenly knew about incidence rates, R-values etc.:

“I feel that it only became an issue since Corona. The question of whether I trust science or not because, for the first time, a broader mass engaged with science, listening to the Drosten podcast and dealing with methods.” – DE_M01

The Covid-19 pandemic had positive but also negative consequences for public trust in science, according to the mediators: on the positive side, more people obtained a basic understanding of scientific processes and have now already heard about terms like ‘peer review’.

On the negative side, the pandemic has also led people to actually question what is happening in science. Due to a lack of understanding in this regard, this has had detrimental consequences for trust in science. One mediator estimated further that those already critical of science before the pandemic have become even more sceptical and have now a bigger platform to spread their opinions. In this regard, one mediator reported that in his perception, since Covid-19, people are much more sceptical when one says, ‘this fact is based on a scientific study’. Before the pandemic, the reaction generally was ‘Ok, I believe you’. Something being based on a scientific study was a convincing argument for the quality of the presented fact, but this has changed during the crisis. The mediator, however, noticed that this observation is not as present anymore as it had been directly after the pandemic and that it is of course – once again – influenced by the voices who are ‘loud’ in public discourse, not necessarily reflecting a majority opinion.

With regard to the negative impact the Covid-19 pandemic might have had on trust in science, several mediators also underlined the role of political actors in this context. The latter did not want to communicate about scientific uncertainty but rather pretended certainty. The important lack of transparency in this regard has turned out to be negative for the image of science even if though what happened rather laid in the hands of political actors. One mediator specified that political decision-makers should have made much clearer that the pandemic was an unusual situation in which nobody had any concrete experiences of which would be the right way to go. Decisions had to be taken to protect vulnerable target groups, but nobody could be sure whether in the end, these measures would actually be the most efficient ones. The mediator argued that transparency and honesty would have been better than continuously pretending complete certainty about the next steps to take.

From a rather general point of view, one mediator observed that the Covid-19 pandemic also highlighted a general lack of understanding of natural science and medical basics in the population, for example the difference between viruses and bacteria. This has changed her perspective on what can be assumed as basic scientific knowledge.

Trust in science and climate change

A majority of mediators is convinced that trust in climate research has generally increased in the last decades due to the constantly increasing evidence and hard facts regarding climate change. They also believe that the strong consensus among researchers has contributed to this. Mediators note a shift from questioning the existence of climate change to discussing its implications and the question of what is really important about that.

An important challenge in this regard, according to several mediators, is the communication of uncertainties and also different levels of probabilities which is particularly important in the context of climate change:

“What we have now [in terms of scientific evidence] is the best for now, but it is still likely to change, something else could come along. We [at our institution] have established terms that indicate how certain something is, when it is very certain, pretty certain etc. That this does however not persist in the translation process towards the media and that it is understood quite differently in the public, yes, that there is a different understanding of scientific ‘certainty’, I believe this has a lot to do with trust.” – DE_M01

The exact same argument has been raised in the researchers’ interviews as well.

3.3.2 Reasons for and rationales in regard to mistrust in science

This next section summarises the three main reasons or rationales working against trust in science mediators discussed in the ten interviews: the politicisation of scientific discourse, the role of social media, and the oversimplification of scientific content.²

Politicisation of scientific discourse

Nearly all mediators identify the politicisation of scientific discourse as the most important reason for increasing public mistrust in science. They note that as long as scientific findings are presented outside the political debate, they are generally trusted. However, once they enter (or are drawn into) the political arena, they become part of a “Kulturkampf” and lose their perceived neutrality. Mediators clearly notice different

² Mediators have also been asked what role controversies in regard to science might play for public trust, but all arguments raised in this regard could be attributed to superordinate points made in this report. Therefore, there is no specific section on this point.

public reactions to topics depending on whether they are part of a current political debate or not: “I believe I create a kind of friendly atmosphere towards science. It is very different, of course, when I talk, for example, about climate change and energy transition. Then I’m directly involved in the political confrontation” (DE_M03). Mediators further note that political actors consciously use and misuse scientific findings to justify their political positions.

In the same vein, mediators underline that scientific findings and individual or political opinions on the consequences that should be drawn from these findings must be separated much more clearly. Researchers and mediators actually very much agree on this point and both groups have formulated this as a strong recommendation in order to enhance trust in science (see section 3.5 and 4.5). One mediator raised the example of the Fridays for Future slogan ‘Follow the science’ in this regard and explained why he considers this to be not only problematic but wrong: there are scientific findings on the one hand and then there are different potential socio-political consequences building on these findings that need to be negotiated in a democratic discourse. But there is never one ‘correct’ political consequence that can be drawn from a scientific finding. This clear distinction between scientific findings and individual opinions already has played a role in regard to questions of conflicts of interest and activism among researchers (see section 3.2.1) but seems to be even more important in regard to the politicisation of scientific discourse in the eyes of a majority of mediators. In other words, when scientific findings are used to support political agendas without a necessary reflection, this may contribute to undermining the public’s perception of science as a ‘neutral’ force.

Social media

The second important reason for distrust in science that has been raised by mediators is the use of social media and the power of algorithms. According to several mediators, social media is as dangerous because it creates bubbles where people are confronted exclusively with content that reflects their own worldview, and this in turn then creates their reality:

“On the internet, a micro-bubble quickly selects and forms itself where one only exchanges with people who see things the same way. And – and this is the crazy part – this quickly becomes the truth. What is shocking is that this shapes our reality, and scientific evidence no longer plays a role.” – DE_M05

Regarding such bubbles, one mediator notes that the more popular the content he creates becomes, the more it also appears in contrary bubbles and the more he is confronted to haters and negative reactions. Social media can be used easily to amplify misinformation and contribute to the spread of false or misleading scientific claims – once again an argument extensively discussed in the researchers’ interviews as well.

Despite these challenges, some mediators see social media as an opportunity to engage with broader audiences. They emphasise the importance of using these platforms to

provide accurate and accessible scientific information, even if this means navigating through negative reactions and misinformation (see also sections 3.1.4 and 3.5).

Oversimplification of scientific content

Even if less frequently discussed than the politicisation of scientific discourse and the logic of social media, an oversimplification of complex scientific phenomena and content has also been identified as being potentially detrimental for public trust in science by several mediators. Several mediators underlined that today's problems are so complex, that they cannot and should not be explained in an oversimplified way because this would not be credible in the eyes of the audience:

“You cannot continue [...] saying today that people are so disturbed and insecure, and that everything is so polarised that we now have to simplify everything. Because the experience of complexity that people have today – when you turn one screw to tackle a problem, something else falls off elsewhere – leads to the fact that people just do not believe this. A journalism or science communication that says, ‘We’ll simplify all this complexity for you so that only one factor remains,’ won’t be believed by anybody. [...]” – DE_M08

Considering such oversimplification of complex scientific content as problematic has several implications for recommendations to foster trust in science, starting with explaining problems from the very beginning and not only in their current shape, honestly communicating scientific uncertainties, and showing a variety of perspectives in one's own content (see section 3.5). This requires, however, lots of time (for explanation) and is very difficult to reconcile with fast-paced online journalism and the logics of social media.

3.3.3 Mediators' own role in regard to trust in science

Mediators have different and nuanced views of their own role in regard to trust in science: some estimate that their work contributes to trust in science, others consider trust in science to be the basis for their own work to be successful, and others again underline the fact that working towards increased trust and building on trust is not mutually exclusive. In any case, one can observe a strong relation between mediators' perception of their role in regard to trust and their general motivations and objectives (see section 3.1.1) demonstrating how crucial the concept of public trust in science is for them.

Those mediators, who think that their work contributes to public trust in science, argued, for example, that through their content they “create a friendly atmosphere towards science” (DE_M03), or that their work strengthens trust because they put a focus on communicating about the scientific process:

“I believe my work strengthens trust in science. I may not reach a huge number of people, but I believe those I do reach are positively influenced. I include

researchers in my videos, letting them explain how they work and what they do.”
- DE_M09

One mediator, who is also a researcher, explained that her primary focus is on creating a trust relationship with her followers in order to enable an actual discussion and encourage them to ask questions, but she “would, of course, be happy if [her] contributions strengthened trust in science. It’s not necessarily the main goal [she] pursue[s], but it would be cool” (DE_M07).

Those mediators who primarily see their work as building on trust in science (even if the demarcation is very often thin and as stated, most mediators underlined that relying on and contributing to trust in science goes together) clearly stated that their work would be in vain if there were no more trust in scientific findings: “The moment when citizens, officials, institutions no longer trust the results, I might as well communicate with the wolf. It won’t work” (DE_M02). This is particularly true for complex and sometimes abstract topics like climate change: climate forecasts go far into the future and are partly not palpable right now. Without trust in scientific expertise, people would just not believe in them. One mediator particularly stressed that they want their audience to have informed trust in science because they want to contribute to rationalising debates, and this is only possible on an informed basis. Several mediators also raised the point that trust is also crucial for them when it comes to the question of which information and to which degree of detail this information is transmitted to the audience:

“The invisible is often more relevant for trust than the visible. It is the same with our products. For example, when we make a podcast episode that is one hour and fifteen minutes long, and we then make a small input from it that is four minutes long, or even a social media post. I need to be very clear about why I can highlight exactly this without distorting the topic or creating a false balance effect or anything like that. [...] If we omit things, we are sure that they can be omitted.” - DE_M06

Without audiences trusting mediators in their choice of information, the latter, and journalists in particular, might be confronted with allegations of ‘hidden agendas’ or of being, for example, “fulfilment agents of science” (DE_M08), meaning that they would just report what science (or politics) dictates to them. The journalists among the mediators underlined very strongly that this is not at all how they see their role: in consciously choosing and selecting the content they report, they aim to make relevant contributions to the public discourse and do want to do that as independently as possible. In this regard, one independent mediator clearly stated that she sees institutional science communication as very different from her own:

“My goal is not just to communicate science but to always try to serve a broader spectrum, to show diverse perspectives. When I’m in contact with press offices – and they do great work – I’m still always aware that they are not completely independent institutions at that moment.” - DE_M10

Still in relation to mediators' work building on trust and the choice of information, one journalist also added that they do not only need public trust for their work but that trust from the side of researchers is equally essential: in order to collaborate effectively, researchers must trust in the content creation of mediators and in their respectful and adequate handling of the information they provide them with. Especially when time is short, several feedback loops between journalists and researchers might not be possible. It is then "even more important, that [researchers] say 'Yes, I believe it is in good hands'" (DE_M06). At the same time, mediators need to be able to trust researchers that the information they give them is correct. Mutual trust in the relationship between scientists and mediators is therefore very important for their work and for good science communication to come to light.

In all they do – also when aiming to work as a regulatory force between science and society, as several journalists indicate they do – the mediators interviewed in this study are very conscious of the responsibility they carry in regard to public trust:

"My job is not only to communicate and explain science but also to question it and keep an eye on researchers because mistakes happen there too. I think, however, that it is crucial not to undermine the overall validity of science while doing so." – DE_M10

"It's important that we don't make mistakes, that what we present is really correct. If we spread information that is not right and it comes out, this is detrimental for trust. I also think we contribute to building trust by reporting on research processes and methods, giving people the opportunity to see what is behind it, how the results are achieved." – DE_M01

Altogether, it can be stated that mediators perceive basic public trust in science to be high in Germany. However, they also clearly identify differences among societal groups in regard to trust on the one hand, and important challenges to public trust in science on the other hand. The latter mainly come in the form of targeted dissemination of misinformation, especially in social media, and an increased politicisation of scientific discourse. Mediators also made clear that oversimplifying complex scientific topics can be detrimental to trust in science.

In the appreciation of their own role in regard to trust in science, some mediators argue that their work builds on trust in science, others that they contribute to trust in science. Most of them, however, state that both go together. In any case, public trust in science plays an important role in their work, even if trust in science or the 'trust' mediators are confronted with sometimes gets mixed up with trust in journalism or other institutions. Especially journalists further perceive their role to be a regulatory force between science and society, scrutinising scientific findings and also scientists but without however displaying science in general in a way that could be detrimental to public trust. To achieve this balance is not always easy. Indeed, all mediators are very conscious about their responsibility in regard to public trust in science.

ID	Additional quotes
DE_M03	“[Trust] certainly took a hit during that time because, I believe, media discovered that you can produce sensational news that click well and sell well by exaggerating scientific dissent from the normal scientific process into a scandal or a quarrel. Damage certainly occurred there.”
DE_M04	“There is no ‘follow the science’; that is simply factually incorrect. That is not how society works, especially not a democratic one.”
DE_M08	“The basic trust that scientists aim to generate knowledge for the sake of knowledge and not for the government is robust.”
DE_M10	“People do not have a fundamental aversion to using scientific findings as a guide for decisions.”
DE_M03	“Where scientific findings and recommendations are still untouched by this political battle, I believe trust is still relatively high, and the findings are considered. For example, people use disinfectants in swimming pools because they know disinfectant helps. They do not want athlete’s foot. That knowledge still reaches the public and helps them to know how to avoid harm. But it can be sabotaged by the political side, and this is happening more and more.”
DE_M06	“We are seen as mere ‘fulfilment agents’. This bothers me a bit because I find it technically unpleasant to be perceived as such. I insist that the things we do and the content we spread are done with our eyes open, not just because we hold a microphone, but because we believe these contents belong in the public domain, and we still discuss them despite everything.”
DE_M09	“I haven’t done much before Covid-19, but I still noticed a switch in my videos and when I gave lectures. After Covid-19, people were much more critical when you said, ‘Hey, what I’m telling you is supported by a study or by several studies’, before they would say ‘Okay, I believe you’. After, many people would say, ‘I need to look into this more’. They rarely did, but there was an initial generalised mistrust.”
DE_M09	“I’m not a fan of TikTok at all. I find it a really bad platform on various levels, but I am there because I don’t want to leave the field to others. There is still a lot to do, especially in a time when media are under pressure.”
DE_M06	“But I actually believe, especially when we say we want to rationalise debates, it is important to acquire and foster informed trust. Otherwise, it’s just a concert of opinions, and we want to avoid that. So, it is essentially crucial for our work that one can justifiably rely on us.”
DE_M03	“[This person said] ‘Yes, your opinion is different from mine, but you did a really good job.’ That was a big compliment for us. It made us very proud, and I see it as a confirmation of my approach to explain things from the

	beginning, to say what is, then to introduce the arguments slowly, and only at the very end to come to what the current political discussion is about.”
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3.3.4 General reflections on science communication

The interviews with mediators mainly focused on three major topics: the mediators’ own ‘mediating processes’, perceptions and assessment of research integrity, and thoughts on public trust in science. The analysis of the interviews has, however, shown that two further themes have been considered to be important for a majority of mediators, and these are presented shortly in the upcoming section: the process of science communication from a more general perspective, and the specific role of the media in ensuring the translation process from science to society.

Obviously, the process of science communication is at the core of mediators’ work and therefore part of all considerations made by the mediators during the interviews. However, many of them also raised more general thoughts on the process of science communication that did not have a place in this report before.

The first question that has been raised by several mediators (and researchers) is whether all researchers should do science communication. All mediators answered this question with ‘No’ and were further convinced that it would not enhance public trust in science if every researcher was obliged to engage in science communication. Making this mandatory was therefore not perceived as a good option by any of the mediators. Nevertheless, many of them, particularly those with a scientific background themselves, underlined that most researchers do not undergo any form of training in ‘communicating’, not even during their PhD. This is perceived as an important barrier for scientists to start engaging in science communication as they might just not feel competent enough to do so. Two other barriers have been identified in this regard, mainly by one mediator coming from the field of research and just starting to build an activity as a science communicator: at universities, it is generally expected that one is dedicated 100% to research. Science communication activities are perceived as “exotic” (DE_M07) and not always supported by superiors (but also by colleagues). In addition to that, young researchers aiming to start engaging in science communication might fear negative reactions and ‘shit storms’ as nearly everybody nowadays knows someone who has already been confronted with that or has at least prominent examples in mind (see also chapter 4 on the researchers’ interviews).

Related to the observation that many researchers do not undergo any communication training during their studies, from the journalistic perspective, there are also rather practical criteria when choosing researchers for their content: they search for those “who communicate well, like to do it and are competent” (DE_M06). This is not always a straightforward choice and obviously also leads to strong selection among the researchers chosen for their content. This can, of course, be seen critically because it raises the important question of which voices are heard in the public discourse, and

journalists also stressed that they consciously try to avoid calling upon always the same experts. Nevertheless, they also have to take such decisions in regard to their time and other resources and so it is sometimes easier to rely upon someone they know is communicating well. One journalist further specified that many researchers need to learn that communication means ‘reduction’ and that they cannot cover all eventualities in their inputs. In this regard, the mutual trust between mediators and researchers is crucial again (see section 3.3.3).

Related to the question of who should communicate is also the question of what should actually be communicated. Institutional mediators report that sometimes researchers come to them and say they have discovered something new and expect it to be communicated. They however know that it is not really relevant for public discourse at this moment. Then the question arises whether to communicate about it anyway to please the expectations of the researcher or how to make clear in a diplomatic way that this is not something to talk about right now.

With regard to research on science communication, one mediator insisted on the fact that even though she finds this discipline certainly very useful, communication also needs to be ‘done’. It is good and important to know what is working in regard to science communication but that does not help if it is not implemented. There need to be enough people with enough energy to actually do the communication. Interestingly though, and without prompting for it, another mediator defended the opposite opinion: she said that for her, research on science communication is crucial, because many people have assumptions in regard to how communication should ‘look like’, but we do not know enough about whether these assumptions are actually true. She perceived this to be an important obstacle for researchers aiming to start doing science communication and saw research on science communication as very helpful in this context.

As a last aspect of mediators’ general thoughts on science communication, one very experienced mediator shared his opinion that science communication as such is a success story in Germany: even though there are lots of things to criticise, the overall evolution is very positive. He expressed the prevailing feeling that the ‘science communication bubble’ and the various actors that are part of it are working together towards something good.

3.3.5 Trust and the role of the media

The role of the media in the mediation process between science and society has, in the same way as science communication, already played a role in many of the considerations mediators have made during the interviews. Once again, this section presents just a few more general arguments in this regard because the role and responsibility of the media clearly were a crucial topic for the mediators during the interviews.

It has already been reflected on the fact that trust in science and trust in journalism often become entangled to some extent (see section 3.3) and therefore, the question of why surveys generally show only very limited trust in journalism among the public is crucial also for the mediating process translating scientific findings into public knowledge.

The first argument brought forward in regard to the question of why people do not trust in journalism is simply because they do not know how journalism works – very similar to a recurring explanation of low trust in science. More specifically, one mediator explained that people often accuse journalists and media of being influenced by politics or other external actors and that everything is controlled from ‘above’, someone telling the journalists what to communicate. This is obviously not true, but the accusation comes from a lack of public understanding of how journalism works. According to this mediator, most journalists are either not aware of lack of understanding or they are but still do not want to change it because it is just more comfortable inside their bubble. On the other hand, some media are already trying to work on this, opening up and making their entire process of journalistic work more transparent.

That many of the trust dimensions in society are probably connected – trust in science, journalism, politics, institutions etc. – has already been discussed before (see section 3.3.1). Overall mistrust towards ‘the elites’ is another reason for low trust as much in science as in journalists according to the mediators. Many parallels can actually be recognised between the discussion about trust in journalism and trust in science.

While journalists are able to work towards making their work more transparent and increasing public understanding of journalism, there is another aspect contributing to low trust in journalism which they are not able to influence according to one mediator: the fact that “controversy works. Of course, for a headline to trigger, it has to trigger. Meaning, either in one direction – when it confirms one’s views – or in the other direction: ‘I find it horrible what they are writing’. If it doesn’t [trigger something], it doesn’t attract attention” (DE_M04). This striving for headlines and sensations is not new at all but has gained another dimension with social media and online journalism. Another mediator added that in his eyes, there has been a clear decrease in qualitative content accompanying the rise of online journalism: in this fast-turning wheel, there is not much time for consciously selecting topics and quality control. And indeed, several mediators indicated that it is very difficult for them to achieve a balance between communicating well-founded, non-sensationalist content and the need to generate clicks. They aim to be transparent about scientific uncertainties, the temporality of the findings, to offer different perspectives, and, at the same time, create media attention. The need to combine the different demands and objectives of science and journalism is a challenge all mediators encounter constantly, and which is very dominant in their daily work.

But what is the role and responsibility of media in regard to the translation process between science and society then, or what should it be?

The answers to this question are partly linked to how mediators see their own role (see sections 3.1.1 and 3.3.3), but a majority of mediators also formulated their vision of how media should act in the mediating process more generally. The most often mentioned

aspect in this regard is that media should contextualise findings. Presenting people with mono-causalities and oversimplification – by the way also in regard to political discourses – is detrimental to trust (see also section 3.3.2). This contextualisation is seen as one of the most crucial but also most challenging exercises by many of the mediators (see section 3.1.3). Journalism should work as a corrective between science and society, not just reproducing any information received, but questioning information, looking behind the news and putting it into context. In the eyes of several mediators, journalism is successful when it succeeds in transmitting information without creating misunderstandings and when it enables the audience to think for themselves:

“Essentially, it is about elucidation, or one could say about empowering people to think for themselves, to think more for themselves than they could before. If I read or hear something about a topic I didn’t know much about before, and afterwards I feel I can discuss it better, more calmly, and more factually, then that is a success of journalism, especially science journalism, I believe.” – DE_M06

Altogether, one can say that during the interviews, mediators reflected extensively not only on their own role in the mediating process but also on the process of science communication and the role that media should play in this process more generally. The responsibility the mediators carry in this regard becomes very obvious in their visions, but also in their constant challenge to bring together partly diverging demands and objectives of science and journalism. With regard to trust, it is important to keep in mind the fact that trust in science and trust in journalism or other forms of mediation are often difficult to separate or disentangle. The question of how to deal with this confusion should definitely also be kept in mind for the recommendations formulated in the POIESIS project.

ID	Additional quotes
DE_M03	“We should ensure that consensus-based, inclusive decision-making, calm decision-making, and slow decision-making processes gain more weight again and become the norm in democratic discourse (again). This corresponds to the way science generally works. In that sense, I believe the political process used to align better with the scientific process because both involved slow and deliberative decision-making.”

3.4 Synthesis of recommendations to foster public trust in science

The following section explains which recommendations mediators gave to foster public trust in science. The majority of them were formulated at the end of the respective interviews and relate to important arguments raised by mediators during the discussions before. They are presented briefly in this section, focussing on the recommendations themselves without repeating all the underlying arguments. Some of the thoughts and aspects mediators considered when it came to the question of what to do to enhance public trust in science were, however, new as well, and these are explained in more detail.

Altogether, mediators identified recommendations in regard to very different aspects of the mediating process and addressed to different target groups. The following recommendations are structured accordingly, distinguishing general recommendations for an improved mediating process, with sub-sections for recommendations exclusively addressed to researchers and institutions; recommendations regarding the relationship between science and politics; recommendations with regard to 'Gen Z', i.e. younger generations; and recommendations specifically relating to climate communication. At the end of this section, a table summarises the most important and most dominant recommendations in the mediators' discourses in short sentences.

3.4.1 Recommendations for an improved mediating process

The following, most extensive recommendation section synthesises mediators' reflections on how to improve the mediating or the translation process between science and society to foster public trust. Aspects covered by the mediators in this regard are an increase in public knowledge about science and the scientific process, interactions between science and society, different audiences and target groups, recommendations on the mode and content but also regarding different channels of communications. All of these first recommendations are not addressed to specific actors but are relevant for all stakeholders in the mediating process in order to enhance public trust in science. This includes mediators as much as communicating scientists, but also other relevant societal stakeholders. The recommendations should therefore be considered from various perspectives each. These 'general recommendations' are followed by a few more ones, specifically addressed to scientists and institutions.

Knowledge

According to the mediators, increasing scientific literacy is fundamental to enhance public trust. People need to understand how science and the scientific process work in order to be better able to assess new scientific findings and, for example, to identify fake news. This, in turn, would strengthen trust. The most suitable long-term solution in this regard seems to be school education as it is the only moment in life when one still has access to all groups of society. Mediators therefore suggested that citizens should learn early in school how science works: having an idea, a hypothesis, a method, a finding, then maybe later new findings shedding another light on the former ones etc.

This recommendation – of fostering scientific literacy and precisely going via schools to do so – has been made in the public consultation and the focus groups as well.

Interaction

Many mediators insisted that “trust is in humans and individuals” (DE_M02) and that in regard to communicating scientific findings, it is important that there is “not just an institution or a scientific paper behind it, but also a person who can comment on the creative overall process” (DE_M04). Mediators therefore emphasised the important role that actual ‘people’ play in the mediating process and that trust can be increased through personal contacts and increased interaction. This can take place in very different forms and formats, at debate events, but even online. DE_M07 states: “If I were to try to build trust, I would simply approach people openly and at eye level, trying to have a normal conversation”. She further raised the very legitimate question of why people should trust in something that is totally distant from them. This is complemented by another mediator insisting that “informed trust is important. It must not be blind trust. That’s why I said people should be empowered to think for themselves” (DE_M06).

Related to interactions and in regard to mediators and scientists’ understanding of public opinion, mediators further suggested aiming for an understanding of reasons behind the rejection of scientific findings. One should not always directly try to improve communication measures when encountering criticism. Instead, one should first aim to understand why certain scientific findings are rejected, for example, because they do not match the recipient’s worldview. Once one understands the rejection’s underlying reason, it is much easier to find adequate approaches and measures to react to it. DE_M06 explains why it is so important to know and understand the audiences’ questions and also fears: “And if I know where which fears have to do with insecurity and lack of knowledge or only partial knowledge, then I can address these questions without putting myself above them.”

Mediators’ recommendation of more and increased interaction at eye-to-eye-level is however not limited to the relation of science and society but also applies to another crucial relationship in the mediating process: the relation of science and media. It was suggested that both create a much more constructive dialogue building mutual trust and understanding. This would lead to a much better and more successful translation process from scientific findings into public knowledge.

Target groups / Audiences

The question of which target groups or audiences to reach with science communication has been very present in mediators’ discourses. One suggestion in this regard, made by several mediators, has been not to reach out exclusively to those already ‘convinced’ – even if they should not be neglected either – but to those who are ‘undecided’. The convinced anti-science hardliner will be nearly impossible to win over in terms of trust, but those who are just barely in contact with science and hesitate in regard to their stance

towards it should be an important target group of science communication. In this regard, one mediator suggested that when it comes to reflecting on new formats of science communication, one should not always think only of big numbers and plan to do another new great podcast, which in the end will only reach the already interested. Instead, one should play more creatively with different formats, even smaller ones, by going into schools, developing games etc. Important is to try to have an actual impact at this level.

Another mediator reported that she grew up in a village and cannot recall any event related to science communication in the last ten years. She therefore raised another important issue, namely target groups, science communication and the urban-rural divide. How to ensure that all people have access to science communication? She sees social media as an important opportunity in this regard, making it possible to reach people who do not have science communication events close by or who have other constraints that hinder them from attending such events.

Mode and content of communication

How and what to communicate is, of course, one of the most crucial aspects for mediators in regard to enhancing public trust in science. First of all, DE_M02 stated: “I think a certain clarity and certainty in communication is simply an important trust-building measure”. Even more important – and stressed by a huge majority of mediators – is, however, the content of all forms of communication.

First of all, it is crucial to explain the process behind any findings. This applies to science and the scientific method – how have scientific findings been generated? – but also to journalism itself, making the functioning of journalism much clearer to the public.

Further, mediators insist that in order to convey the complexity of scientific topics and to work against populist – oversimplified – messages, it needs much more explanations ‘from the beginning’, comprehensive and in detail, to understand the functioning of entire processes and not just the current picture of issues. This requires lots of resources of course – on the side of communicating actors but also regarding the necessary attention span of the audience.

Related to this and with the same objective in mind, mediators emphasise the importance of contextualisation – as researchers as well as mediators and in regard to one’s own scientific findings and those of others – and pro-actively dealing with uncertainties. The recognition of one’s own expertise but also limitations is crucial for (communicating) researchers but also mediators in this regard. One mediator insisted on the necessary “humility before the subject matter” in their work (DE_M06).

“How was this data collected? What does it really mean? [The objective is] that there is not just a headline, but that also a comprehensive context is provided. I believe that helps. If people perceive that, it strengthens their trust as they understand how these results are achieved.” – DE_M01

“Explaining one’s own limitations is also crucial. Explaining coherently that science also has limits, that certain things are unknown, and how to deal with uncertainties is a big topic in climate research. The classification of external and internal information is important.” – DE_M02

Mediators underline that complexity reduction is, of course, important in the translation process from science to society, but that oversimplification is a dangerous trend in today’s reporting practices. People are aware of the complexity of scientific and also daily life’s problems and presenting them with an overly simple solution might lead to mistrust and suspicion.

Transparency is another key word in the context of the mode and content of science communication. One should explain openly and honestly what potential conflicts of interests of involved actors might be – and again, this concerns mediators and researchers alike. A difficult discipline in this regard is the medical field according to one mediator, because the development of medication is not possible without the pharmaceutical industry. The latter has, however, a very difficult standing in the public perception, and mentioning its involvement in any kind of processes might directly have a detrimental impact on trust. Helpful in regard to transparency, according to one mediator, could be an initiative he has heard about to make registering all scientific studies mandatory, including the ones that are not published, for example because their findings go against the interest of the funders. This could make it easier for mediators to gain a comprehensive overview of the actual state of the art in the relevant field but could also directly enhance public trust in science because there would be no ‘hidden findings’ anymore.

Coming from a rather different perspective, but equally recommended by several mediators, is the avoidance of ever more negative and pessimistic messages in science communication. Several mediators insist that it is important to actually focus on the positive and the pleasurable when talking about science, and one sees this as a way to penetrate the bubbles of social media and get people ‘back to reality’. One mediator explained that in his eyes, it is not scientific findings that induce individual transformation processes but that only emotions can have this effect: “Wonder is always the most important thing. Wonder is the beginning of any understanding and the spark of any transformation process. We need to understand this” (DE_M05). Another mediator added that people who are interested in science also want to have fun with new and cool scientific findings. They do not want to hear about all the bad in the world all the time.

In the same direction, several mediators suggested not only communicating positively but also constructively. While prohibitions and dystopian messages will just lead to a fatalistic ‘I cannot change anything anymore anyway’-attitude among many people, giving concrete and constructive indications can lead to an increased feeling of self-efficacy, which in turn leads to a more positive attitude overall:

“If someone tells me, ‘Actually, we should all stop eating meat,’ and I’m a meat-eater, this triggers resistance in me. But if someone tells me that even reducing

meat consumption to twice a week has a measurable effect, it's a completely different story.” – DE_M06

Channels

In regard to channels of communication, mediators insist on the necessity to reflect on the channels one wants to use and also to reflect on the question of which audiences one is able to reach via which channels. It is then important to understand how the mediation channel(s) of one's choice actually function and to be authentic in the way of using them.

Regarding social media, the overall consensus of mediators has been that they are an obligation, not a choice nowadays, and that the question should not be whether we communicate via social media but how. Social media is where the people are, and this is why mediators should be there, too. Mediators explicitly mentioned not wanting to leave the floor to other actors, specifically from the edges of the political spectrum in this regard. At the same time, it is important to reflect on the question of how to communicate via social media and how this can be done while remaining true to one's own principles, one's own objectives and one's own integrity.

“The question isn't whether to communicate, but how to do it in a world that functions as it does now. We can wish for something else, but if we have to be on social media, then we must do it in a way that meets our goals and integrity while still being effective out there. Trust doesn't come easily. That's the thing.” – DE_M04

Towards scientists

While most recommendations mediators made are addressed to mediators and (communicating) researchers alike, some also focus only on researchers' behaviour. First of all, it was suggested that researchers reflect on how to carry out conflicts in public and especially on social media. It was underlined several times that most people are not aware of the fact that dissensus between researchers is an intrinsic part of the scientific process. Observing conflicts between researchers, they might actually draw wrong assumptions and get the impression that 'science' does not agree and is, to some degree, just depending on the perspective from which one looks at it. It is therefore even more important to increase public knowledge about the scientific process (see above) but also that researchers carry out such conflicts on a factual level without becoming personal in their disputes.

“Then comes the responsibility of scientists. They need to consider how to publicly conduct scientific discourses. We can't assume that observers of these discourses taking place on social media have the same background knowledge about science and its processes. They only see the headlines. And these look like 'science' is not in agreement and on top of that, scientists are arguing intensely, sometimes even personally.”

Mediators further encourage researchers to strengthen public trust through the creation of personal trust relationships, enabling an actual dialogue between researchers and citizens, who often consider the former as residing in their 'ivory tower'. In this regard, it is not necessary that every researcher decides to do public science communication. Just talking to people about their work in their daily life, spreading the message that researchers are 'only humans' as well, would already be helpful. It is however crucial in this regard to have actual conversations and to not lecture from above.

Towards scientific institutions

Finally, and still in regard to an improved mediation process, mediators addressed a few recommendations specifically to scientific institutions. First of all, and rather at a systemic level, mediators wish for a better availability of scientific data (keyword open access), but also a better processing of scientific findings in an accessible format. Especially mediators with a non-scientific background struggle with extracting the most important key messages from 400 pages-long documents.

Still at the systemic level, several mediators emphasise the importance of providing better working conditions in the form of stable funding and job security for researchers. They raise the question of how one is supposed to conduct great and innovative research when, at the same time, one constantly has to worry about one's own job. The high dependency on external funding further leads to project proposals being oriented towards potential funding grounds rather than truly relevant research topics. This aspect might not be directly related to trust in science at first sight but was underlined several times as a pre-condition for 'good research' for society and the common good. In turn, it then becomes also a pre-condition for good research communication: "As long as you don't have cool results to present, I can't talk about cool results" (DE_M09).

Related to that is the recognition of science communication activities as a fundamental aspect of researchers' work, which was also discussed by one mediator, but will be elaborated upon in more detail in chapter 4.

With regard to individual institutions, mediators emphasise that trust needs to be earned and that this works only through a certain presence in the public discourse. If institutions want to be trusted, they need to engage with the public. It is also important to clearly communicate about their own expertise and mandate when making statements in regard to specific scientific findings, especially when these statements go into the direction of policy advice. Many scientific institutions and organisations, such as the Leopoldina in Germany, might not be known to the broader public. According to several mediators, these institutions taking over important roles in the process of policy advice 'out of nowhere' raises many questions and mistrust in the public eye.

3.4.2 Recommendations regarding the relation between science and politics

The last recommendation in regard to institutions has already raised the important topic of policy advice. The relation between science and politics played an important role in the mediators' discourses and therefore deserves its own category of recommendations. Several precise recommendations have been made by mediators in this regard. All of them are however strongly related to one another and basically address the necessity of disentangling scientific and political discourses.

Clarification of roles

Much of the frustration emerging from the increased politicisation of scientific discourses, is, according to mediators, due to a confusion of roles between science and politics. As this confusion can be identified also in the public, mediators suggest, on the one hand, to talk much more about the necessity and justification of scientific expertise. But on the other hand, it is important to make it much clearer that science does not have a mandate and not the authority for decision-making in society. There should be a clear division of responsibility: science can advise and point out future scenarios. In a democracy, however, it is up to other actors – politicians but also citizens themselves, for example in citizen councils – to gather this advice from several relevant scientific disciplines and then take decisions under consideration of various perspectives on what is best to do. The objective here would be to find a balance between expertise and democratic discourse in the decision-making process and – equally important – to clarify the different roles both have in the public discourse. In this regard, the role of democratic discourse for society and how it can be protected in times of social media, populism, and propaganda is crucial as DE_M08 insisted: “We need to agree on the role of expertise and how it must be protected, as well as on the role of democratic discourse and how its ethics can be safeguarded.”

Distinction of scientific findings and potential socio-political consequences

Due to this confusion of roles, but also to the increasing demand of concrete advice addressed to science and scientists, mediators observe an important mix-up of ‘value-free’ scientific findings on the one hand and potential socio-political consequences on the other hand. Different actors certainly base the latter on scientific findings but also on their own individual and / or professional perspective. This observation relates to political actors but also to researchers themselves, who, when asked for advice, also take over two roles at the same time – the one of the researcher and the one of the adviser. Mediators insist that the above-mentioned clarification of roles and, as a next step, the clear distinction of scientific findings and the various socio-political consequences one could draw from it, are crucial for increasing trust in science. This distinction needs to be made by political but also all other kinds of societal stakeholders and researchers themselves.

Related to that, mediators formulate the clear demand towards political actors to treat scientific findings respectfully and not to misuse them for their own political agenda – for example, by clearly stating where a scientific finding ends and where the own opinion

begins. One mediator, however, pushed this demand even further, pleading for the commandment that politicians should not be allowed to lie anymore. He does not address this only to populist or extremist parties but observes that politicians consciously distort or omit facts in established political parties as well.

3.4.3 Recommendations with regard to Gen Z

A specific question was addressed to mediators in regard to enhancing trust among the younger generations and what would be necessary to do so. According to a majority of mediators, it would be a wrong assumption to think that ‘Gen Z’ functions differently than ‘us’. Different mediators gave different reasons for this opinion, but the basic message still was the same. Among the reasons why Gen Z should ‘just’ be considered as part of different potential audiences in the same way as other societal groups, mediators argued that the socio-psychological factors influencing the behaviour of the young generation are exactly the same as for adults: when older people start to enter the ‘social media game’, they behave and react entirely the same, the entire mechanism work in the same way. Here the question would rather be how to reach different audiences via different channels and what one wants to achieve with the own communication overall. Another mediator argued that we should avoid lumping everyone together. Rather, we can find diverging audiences within Gen Z itself that we should think about in regard to trust in science. Other socio-cultural and socio-economic variables may play a much more important role than age in this regard. Again another mediator stated that we all have once been the ‘young generation’ and that in any case, every generation and every audience needs to be considered differently. Communication always needs to be adapted: when there is no Twitter anymore, then we need to go elsewhere, when people do not read print anymore, then we need to focus on online communication etc. Indeed, the general consensus of mediators was that social media is not an option to discuss but a necessity in regard to exchange and science communication nowadays (see above). They would not limit this observation to younger generations, though.

In the same context as saying that Gen Z is not a generation different from other younger generations before it, mediators also underlined that we should not underestimate ‘this generation’. They stated that it is a prejudice that they are all addicted to their phones and do not want to achieve anything. Nevertheless, it is important to reach and inspire them. To do so, mediators suggest what they also suggested more generally to foster interest in science – and hopefully trust as well: not only focussing on negative findings or topics in regard to science, but rather on raising interest and curiosity. They also underline that an entertaining factor is important for reaching audiences with science communication – but again that this is not specific to Gen Z. It is important, though, that this ‘entertainment’ engages without being flat and still ensures well-researched and well-founded content, because – as said – none of the audiences of the mediating process should be underestimated. They are aware of complexity, and they expect to be taken seriously, no matter their age or background.

3.4.4 Recommendations regarding climate communication

Next to the recommendations for enhancing trust in science rather generally, some of the mediators further formulated recommendations in the specific context of climate communication. One of these recommendations relates to the one about disentangling scientific findings and political but also media agendas: “The climate protection debates in Germany, but also across Europe and the whole world, are still highly polarised and often far from factual bases. There is still much to be done, especially at a time when the media is under pressure” (DE_M04). In a similar vein, mediators also insisted on the importance of explaining with much more perseverance why it is necessary to take many prevention measures now even though not all influencing factors and scenarios are totally certain. A transparent and comprehensive approach to and communication about scientific uncertainties is crucial in this regard but needs to be able to build on a common understanding of scientific processes in the public.

Several other mediators insisted also in the context of climate communication on the importance of not only communicating about (future) disasters but to frame topics positively and constructively. Different needs of audiences were discussed in this context again, and based on that, mediators suggested not to talk about facts alone but to address emotions. In this regard, DE_M05 insisted on the importance of “childlike amazement” and “wonders” and the simple mechanism that we always want to protect what we love. We therefore need to make people love nature again, ensuring nearly automatically that they will want to protect it: “What we love, we automatically want to protect” (DE_M05).

Lastly, it became very clear in the discussions that we cannot think climate change and also climate communication as a national problem but need to think global and also consider communication much more in the international context. “CO₂ molecules don't have national flags” (DE_M05) and this must become even clearer in political as much as in public discourse.

Altogether, mediators formulated many different recommendations in order to improve conditions of the mediating process from various perspectives. They further addressed the relation between science and politics which has been perceived as crucial for public trust in science as well by nearly all mediators. With regard to Gen Z, mediators largely agreed that this younger generation should not be considered ‘apart’ but that, as for every audience, strategies of science communication need to be adapted to their expectations and needs. Social media plays an important role in this regard, but the younger generation is not the only audience for which this is true. Finally, mediators also formulated recommendations in the specific context of climate communication. The most dominant recommendations in the mediators’ discourses are summarised in the table below.

Mediators' main recommendations:

1. Improve (school) education on science and the scientific method (scientific literacy).

2. Contextualise scientific findings in the communication process and explain the scientific process, including information regarding potential limitations and remaining scientific insecurities.

3. Communicate positively and constructively instead of conveying always more pessimistic and too generalising perspectives.

4. Create stable and safe working conditions in research, especially for young researchers.

5. Disentangle scientific findings and potential socio-political consequences in the discourses of all societal stakeholders.

Note: Different key recommendations have consciously been chosen for mediators and for researchers to broaden the perspectives of what can be done.

4 Analysis of Researcher interviews

The upcoming chapter synthesises the most important arguments raised by the six researchers interviewed for this study. Four of them work on the topic of climate change and two conduct research on Covid-19. Section 4.1 briefly summarises their respective fields of expertise while carefully adhering to anonymity standards. The rest of the chapter is then structured along three main topics: science communication, public integration in the research process, and public trust in science. More specifically, section 4.2 presents the researchers' experiences and feedback regarding own communication activities as well as third-party reporting about their research. It then explains researchers' perspectives on the influence of controversies in this regard. Section 4.3 presents mediators' experiences with citizens' involvement in their own research and then provides a detailed overview of their assessment of such involvement: what are positive and negative aspects of social integration and what are the main obstacles in this regard? Section 4.4 is complementary to section 3.3 for the mediators' interviews and presents first of all the researchers' perception of the state of public trust in Germany, reasons they see for mistrust and the rationales behind these observations. The chapter ends with a synthesis of the recommendations made by the researchers, structured along the different topics and target groups they address.

4.1 Researcher contexts: Covid-19 and Climate Change

The following section presents a very brief snapshot of each researcher's work and expertise and, when relevant, their thoughts on whether public controversies in the context of climate change or Covid-19 have had an influence on their work. The latter aspect is discussed in more detail in section 4.2.2.

4.1.1 Researchers working on Covid-19

Researcher DE_R01 is a senior specialist working at a research institute linked to a hospital. The researcher is from the medical field and conducts research on various infections, the circumstances under which there are outbreaks of such infections in clinical environments, and also on the backgrounds of Covid-19 outbreaks despite vaccination.

Researcher DE_R02 has a Post-Doc position at a research institute linked to a university. The researcher comes from the field of SSH and conducts research on social and political consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic mainly based on quantitative data. One topical focus of the researcher's work are conspiracy theories and the question of who is attracted by them. The researcher turned to working on consequences of the pandemic during the pandemic itself without having planned such a focus initially.

4.1.2 Researchers working on climate change

Researcher DE_R03 is from the field of applied economics and works at an interdisciplinary non-university research institute. The researcher is a research group leader and deals with socio-economic impacts of climate change in the Global South. The researcher reports that in the context of controversies in the public debate, their work and the work of their partners is sometimes questioned and that they generally feel the 'mood' towards climate change research in public discourse. More generally, the researcher has the impression that media and public interest in Germany has decreased in the last five years, and that this evolution is even stronger for topics that are not directly related to our daily lives at first sight – for example socio-economic impacts of climate change in the Global South.

Researcher DE_R04 is a university professor from the field of SSH and works on socio-ecological transformations at different levels (individual, groups, systemic) as well as on the interrelation of nature and public health. The researcher notes that the existence and urgency of climate change as such is not controversial at all but that in public discourse and especially media representation, there often is a problem of false balance when giving too much space to minority opinions that do not represent the scientific consensus.

Researcher DE_R05 is a senior researcher working at a research institute linked to a university. The researcher is from the field of natural sciences and mainly works on energy transitions and ways to improve sustainable energy supply. The researcher has a long history in modelling energy systems and advising for example cities at the international level in this regard. For already a few years now, the researcher is however implicated in the planning and realisation of a living lab with a focus on energy topics. The main focus of the researcher's work is nowadays on more applied and society-oriented research.

Researcher DE_R06 is a PhD student at a university. The researcher is from the field of SSH and conducts research on social consequences of climate change for children and teenagers. The researcher states that generally spoken, it is difficult to say whether controversies have an influence on people's view on science or whether the latter fuels controversies – both are mutually dependent.

4.2 About science communication and public attitudes

The next section presents researchers' experiences with science communication from the perspective of third-party reporting as well as in communicating on their own. In relation to these experiences, researchers' perspectives on the potential influence of controversies on public attitudes in the context of climate change and Covid-19 are summarised.

The term ‘science communication’ is used here for all kinds of top-down communication acts no matter whether they were initiated by external actors, e.g. a newspaper, or by the researchers themselves. Public integration in the research process, then (see section 4.3), is anything that goes beyond this form of communication and involves an orientation towards dialogue.

4.2.1 Experiences with science communication

From a general point of view, researchers engage in diverse forms of science communication themselves and also have experiences with third-party reporting to varying extents, primarily through interviews and contributions to mainstream media. All of them have overall made mainly positive experiences in this regard, as much in their own communication activities as in others communicating about their work.

Some of the researchers name the press or communication department as important actors in the context of third-party reporting about their research. Either, as one researcher reports, for the dissemination of their results or, more importantly, to channel media inquiries. Researchers explain that when they receive interview requests, they often rely on the advice and experiences of their communication department who tells them with which actors they have already had positive experiences:

“Yes, no negative experiences so far, fortunately. Although I always place great value on the assessment of our press department. They usually say, ‘We’ve had good experiences with this or that colleague. You can go ahead or not.’” - DE_R01

One researcher reports that their press department currently offers a seminar on science communication for researchers which the researcher perceives as very useful. They are for example also learning about standard rules in dealing with the media. Nevertheless, she also noticed that the process of who got to take part in the seminar was somewhat in-transparent and that generally, she has always perceived the press department as a kind of black box. One researcher further notes having observed sometimes diverging interests between researchers and their press departments. It is therefore even more important to have personal contacts there and to know whom to talk to in order to resolve these differences through means of personal exchange.

Experiences with third party reporting

The clear majority of researchers have had very positive experiences with media reporting about their work. Most of them state that content had been simplified but was still accurate. More generally, researchers also had a positive impression of science journalism attesting it overall high quality and good explanations and contextualisation of topics in longer texts. Sensational headlines in the media were more often perceived as problematic than the texts beneath them. One researcher also assessed the reporting of news in her discipline more generally and stated that she sees a sometimes-problematic framing in the direction of overdramatising things. She notes that this might

however also be related to the researcher speaking and not necessarily to the reporting of the media.

Next to these overall very positive observations, some researchers also report negative experiences they have had in the context of third-party reporting on their work. One researcher explains that generally, his experience with the reporting as such is very positive but that the public reactions to the reporting are more often the problem. In this regard, comment sections beneath (online) newspaper articles were mentioned where sometimes people pick one sentence out of context from the interview and then make something totally different out of it. Another example in this direction are instances when the own work reaches anti-science bubbles on social media or specific blogs and is attacked heavily. A similar experience has been reported by one of the mediators (see section 3.3.2). One researcher explains that she personally has not had any negative experiences so far but that she knows many colleagues who have been in this situation and that this obviously influences her position towards media inquiries. Very specifically she says to be reluctant to talk to 'Bild' (the biggest German tabloid) for example out of fear to be misrepresented even though her press department has advised her to talk to them because of their very large reach.

Several of the researchers raised the more general question of how to explain complex scientific results adequately to journalists, especially when noticing that the interviewer clearly is in search for headlines. As DE_R02 noted: “[This search for headlines] is very, very difficult to reconcile with how I view my own work.”

Experience with own communication

Similar to their experiences in third-party reporting about their own work, researchers are also overall satisfied with their experiences in communicating about their research themselves. The extent of their experiences in this regard differs among the researchers depending on their career level.

Several of the mediators explain that they really enjoy engaging with different audiences such as pupils, their students, but also other stakeholders. One researcher reports in this regard that he believes his engagement in the field of social integration leads to different stakeholders getting in contact and asking him to give talks etc.: “These are media that would not normally have approached me as a hardcore scientist or a scientist not working in a transformative area” (DE_R05). From his perspective, his engagement in this field demonstrates openness and increases visibility across different societal actors. This in turn leads to an increased exchange with stakeholders from various perspectives.

A very particular experience of science communication has been made by another researcher: she was involved in policy-advising during the Covid-19 pandemic. She reports that she has perceived this process as very respectful and observed very appreciative behaviour also among members of ministries. Of course, it was frustrating when decisions were taken differently than one had advised, but it was also clear to her

that, as ‘medical advisers’, they only provided a medical perspective on the topic and that politicians had to consider many more perspectives in their decisions. Asked about transparency in the process, the researcher reported that as they were part of the discussions, they obviously overheard why this or another decision was taken; when decisions were taken later, however, then there was no further explanation why the decision diverged from their advice. She did not perceive this negatively, though, as she says there was just no time for detailed explanations.

Not all experiences of researchers regarding their own science communication are positive, though. Several researchers state that social media is a very difficult terrain and that particularly X, formerly Twitter, has becoming a very frustrating experience nowadays, even more because it was a rich platform for scientific exchange before. Mediators observed the exact same development in this regard.

In the specific context of SSH research on the Covid-19 pandemic, DE_R02 reports that public discussions in his field are often challenging because people do not succeed in making the abstraction between research results and their own experiences during the pandemic: “Joining in the discussion is great, but [often they do so] with preconceived opinions that are based on their own experience or anecdotal evidence from their own environment” (DE_R02).

More generally, several researchers raised the point that an important question for all researchers today is how far they want to go into the public with their work, always keeping in mind that this might have important consequences, also at a personal level:

“I am someone who likes to go out into the public pretty far to communicate research findings, but I also have colleagues who say, ‘Wow, no, we don’t want that. We want to do research and not become targets for attacks.’” – DE_R04

“It simply is a high price to pay, as you can see with Mr. Drosten, who is still dealing with court cases years after the pandemic. Personally, I can’t imagine paying such a high price. I think it’s important [to communicate], but I definitely think there are limits.” – DE_R01

This reflection regarding the degree of one’s own communication and desired visibility, always with examples of researchers in mind who have had very negative experiences in this regard, is very prominent both among researchers from the field of Covid-19 and climate change and across all career levels.

4.2.2 Thoughts on controversies

When asked about their impression of whether controversies related to the pandemic or climate change have an influence on public perceptions of science or specifically of their work, researchers first noted that it is often not entirely clear whether controversies influence people's view on science or whether sceptical voices actually fuel controversies but that both are probably mutually dependent. Regarding these sceptical voices, and in the same way as one of the mediators reported (see section 3.3.1), one researcher states that he finds it interesting to sometimes pro-actively search for interaction and exchange with people who at first seem to be very critical and anti-science. He emphasises that they are part of society and that we, as researchers, should be interested in their perspectives. In his experience, after a few first minutes of polemic statements from these voices, actually interesting and enriching discussions can emerge.

In the context of climate change, the majority reaction of researchers from this field to the question of controversies was that actually, nothing about climate change as such is controversial anymore. Researchers insisted that there is nearly no scientific topic in which researchers agree as much as in regard to the existence of climate change and the fact that it is man-made. DE_R04 states: "You always get people at lectures who say things like, 'Well, climate change isn't really that bad.' As a scientist, I have to deal with that, and we as a society have to be able to handle it", which he perceives as possible as it is minority opinions we are talking about here. However, public debates become problematic the moment false balances are created in regard to these minority opinions. One researcher gives the example of a TV show inviting 5 experts on climate change with one of them being a climate change denier. This person then represents 20% of the experts on stage, totally overrepresenting such an opinion among researchers. The researcher insists that it is crucial for democratic public discourses that all opinions are heard but also that marginal minority opinions should not be given too much space in the media.

DE_R06 adds to the observation that not many people deny the existence of climate change anymore, but that "now, it's more about discourses like 'Yes, but we also have to think about the economy,' or 'Well, it's too late now anyway.' These are the kind of delay discourses that are now playing a bigger role".

DE_R03 shares the opinion that as such, climate change is not a controversial topic. In the context of her own work, she makes two observations about public discourses on climate change, though, one for the countries in which she conducts her research and one for Germany. In the context of countries in the Global South, first of all, she states that climate change is a very salient topic as people on-site already experience its consequences very clearly in their daily lives. However, she adds that many people have also understood that today, 'money' lies in all that is connected to climate change. This is due to the fact that many projects and actions which formerly took place under the umbrella of development co-operation are nowadays reframed as related to climate change by international organisations. For Germany, she states:

“I must say, it is very fascinating to see which topics garner interest. To summarise it simply, everything that affects us here in Germany or Europe generates a lot of interest. However, topics that remain on the African continent or elsewhere generate significantly less interest. [...] There is a much greater interest in plants like coffee and cocoa, which ultimately affect our breakfast or dessert, much more than, for example, maize or millet yields in Africa, which are obviously much more important for the people there.” – DE_R03

In the context of Covid-19, researchers observe that particularly in the beginning of the pandemic, it was not clear to the public that controversies are a normal part of the scientific process and that scientific results constantly evolve, especially in the context of an ongoing pandemic. They did not understand that when ‘evidences’ change, this does not necessarily mean that researchers were wrong but that there was not enough data or that other parameters had changed. According to one researcher, this has improved in the course of the pandemic when the process of generating scientific findings has been put more into the focus of the debate. Another ‘normal’ part of the scientific process but which has not been much observed by the public before the pandemic is researchers disputing scientific findings among themselves. People first had to understand that researchers do not fight ‘personally’ but that not having the same opinion is also part of the game.

Beyond that observation of public discourse, the researcher working in the medical field has also had the experience that, in the aftermath of the pandemic’s peak, actors from within science and especially within the medical sector did not want to deal with anything related to Covid-19 anymore (e.g. in research projects working on what has happened during this time).

Overall, researchers report very positive experiences with science communication, both from a communicating but also from a third-party reporting perspective. One can note the varying role of press departments among researchers in this regard with some relying entirely on them, some not even mentioning them in the context of their communication activities, and some also reporting diverging interests and even potential subliminal conflicts with them. Despite their overall positive reflections, most researchers can, however, also tell stories about more negative experiences regarding science communication activities. These are mostly related to public reactions to media reporting rather than the reporting itself. Particularly striking is the observation of ‘anti-science bubbles’ in this regard, coherent with observations made by mediators, which clearly draw the image of parallel worlds existing in the universe of social media.

Even though not all researchers have had negative experiences with personal attacks or online harassment themselves, several of them stress a feeling of doubt in regard to engaging in public science communication and an omnipresent underlying fear of becoming the target of attacks when doing so. They observe such thoughts among themselves and colleagues especially since the pandemic and independently of scientific discipline, career stage or other variables.

ID	Additional quotes
DE_R01	<p>“What was not well presented at the beginning of the pandemic is that controversies in science are entirely normal and part of the process of approaching the truth. What often happens is that facts or the state of knowledge change because more insights become available. In the beginning, it was perceived as scientists having been wrong. And that might sometimes be the case, but not because they made a mistake, but simply because not enough information and data were available. In my perception, this improved over the course of the pandemic as the process of science was better explained.”</p>

4.3 About the integration of citizens in research

Discussing the topic of public involvement or social integration in the research process has once again – as it has been the case in the public consultation and the different focus groups – revealed very different and diverging views on the concept itself on the one hand and its implementation on the other hand. These do not necessarily seem to be connected to one’s own experiences in this regard or the discipline one works in. The most important influencing factor in this regard might actually be the angle from which social integration is mainly perceived. Very simply put: from the angle of citizen science projects, i.e. citizens collecting uncontroversial data vs. from the angle of citizens councils, i.e. citizens deciding on research agendas.

Regarding differences between disciplines, within the sample, SSH researchers did have less personal and practical experience in social integration practices than researchers from other fields. They did not have more positive or negative opinions in this regard than the others, though.

From a very general perspective, researchers first discussed the question of whether social integration practices should be pushed further and, in this context, whether such practices should become a mandatory part of funding guidelines. One researcher underlined that in his perception, an important principle of publicly funded research is to communicate. Researchers are paid by taxes and therefore are obliged to communicate about what they do and in a way that is understandable by non-scientists. Even though this is perceived as very important, he and other researchers were convinced that it would not be a good idea to relate science communication and social integration practices directly and automatically to funding conditions, at least not for all kinds of projects. It might certainly be useful in some contexts, but for example, they do not see a necessity, a utility, or even the possibility of social integration in the context of basic research. Researchers therefore agreed that not all scientific projects and processes need social integration – some do and there is more to be done, but it would not do any good to make it mandatory in all scientific disciplines.

Researchers also stated that much has already happened in regard to social integration – and science communication – in the last few years. Building on that, the remaining section first presents the researchers’ own practical experiences in various forms of social integration and then discusses the positive and negative aspects researchers identified regarding social integration. In the last sub-section, the main obstacles researchers see to increasing integration and/or making it better are addressed.

4.3.1 Experiences with social integration

The researchers who participated in the POIESIS interviews are engaged in very different forms of social integration and also to varying degrees. Some have very much and extensive experience in this regard. Others have less to no concrete experience in the field of ‘participation’, but all are regularly in exchange with stakeholders etc. and are thus to some extent involved in social integration practices.

Concretely, one of the researchers, who conducts research in the Global South, states that her work on-site would not be possible without integrating many stakeholders – collaborations with research institutes and universities, workshops with stakeholders from politics, civil society, researchers, NGOs, international organisations etc. These stakeholders are either consulted at the beginning of the research process to get feedback and integrate new ideas, or towards the end to discuss results and the potential practical use of these results. The researchers on-site are also in contact with affected target groups during their quantitative and qualitative data collection, but this rather takes place within the frame of traditional data collection.

Another researcher is currently not actively involved in a project encompassing social integration, also because of the many barriers this implies (see section 4.3.2). Despite this last observation, this researcher’s overall perspective of social integration is very positive.

The researcher who is involved in the organisation of a living lab has much experience in the field of social integration and in very different forms. He emphasises that for them “co-creation of science and society” (DE_R05) is crucial, i.e. thinking and reflecting together with society regarding what could be changed and how. They organise various activities and projects in this regard such as workshops, competitions, creative projects etc. The researcher explains that they try to have as many projects as possible with a true participatory nature, meaning that citizens are integrated in all phases of the project cycle. Funding applications are mostly written by the researchers alone, but when enough resources are available, they also aim to involve citizens in actually designing the project.

Another researcher reports that in her faculty, the foundation of a Youth Council accompanying research projects in the same way as a citizen council is currently planned. The objective is to integrate teenagers in the entire research cycle as an advisory body, from the planning of the project to the evaluation process.

In the medical field, one researcher explains that the involvement of patient organisations is increasingly aimed for. The objective then is to discuss questions of what should be considered in the project, how and when patients would like to be addressed and informed etc. The problem she sees in this regard lies not only in researchers' limited resources but also in limited resources from the side of patient organisations. She explains that she has already tried to actively involve patient organisations in her projects but did not receive any feedback from them. In the same way as researchers, they are just overwhelmed with the many important tasks but the few resources they have.

One researcher mentioned that, beyond regular exchanges with stakeholders, his team is in the planning phase of organising focus groups with citizens to assess the validity of quantitative data and to synthesise qualitative and quantitative data streams. This of course involves citizens in the research project but rather from a research design than social integration perspective. This example shows that the understanding of the term 'social integration' is not totally clear in some contexts and might need to be sharpened.

4.3.2 Assessment of social integration practices

Most researchers did not see social integration entirely positive or uncritical independently of their own experience in this regard. Many of them identified positive aspects of increased social integration, but also raised caution about potential negative factors in such a process. Beyond positive and negative aspects, researchers gave even more weight to the numerous obstacles impeding more or better social integration practices – from the sides of citizens, of researchers, and also at the systemic level.

Positive aspects of social integration

Researchers stressed three different dimensions of positive aspects of social integration during the interviews: bringing science closer to the citizens; benefiting from an external perspective as a scientist; and being able to design research around society's actual needs.

The first and most often raised argument by the researchers is that social integration can contribute to a more positive image of science and to increased trust in science. Social integration leads to an increased exchange and more interactions between citizens and researchers. This can contribute to slowly but progressively changing attitudes and opinions towards science in a positive way. One researcher noted that this effect is difficult to measure, though.

It is, however, not only the increased personal exchange with researchers that can be beneficial for trust in science. Projects, such as citizen science, also bring the scientific process closer to the people, making it more tangible, and people might understand better 'what science is about'.

This perspective of how social integration might benefit citizens is complemented by the perspective that such processes are also beneficial from a scientific perspective: citizens can contribute perspectives and questions that researchers do not normally come up with as they have their own – scientific – view on things.

“Sometimes questions arise that I, as a scientist, had not really considered, because we scientists exchange ideas among ourselves. Perspectives from society can emerge, allowing me to look at my field differently, which is a gain for me from a scientific perspective.” (DE_R05)

Additionally, “the more stakeholders around the table, the more perspectives can be considered” (DE_R01).

Lastly, researchers underline that through social integration, research might be able to understand the core of society’s interests and questions: “We do things where we are really very close to the population. We think about what can be done, what things can make a difference, and we try to include [the citizens] and work together” (DE_R05). Actual co-creation of science and society is perceived to be very beneficial for both sides – at least in some scientific disciplines. Once again, researchers distinguished very clearly between basic and applied research in this regard (see above).

Negative aspects of social integration

In regard to potentially negative aspects of social integration, researchers raised three main points: the quality of data; the problems of providing citizens with agenda-setting power in the field of research; and the complexity of expectation management. Further, they critically discussed who the target groups of social integration measures actually are, and how to handle the great responsibility that comes with it.

Quality of data

First of all, researchers raised the hypothetical argument that data collected in the course of citizen science projects might not be representative and contain mistakes because citizens participating in such projects are not experts in the field. Several researchers thought about this aspect, but all disagreed with it themselves. They were all convinced that participants of such projects would not consciously sabotage their results and further, that it is better to have data one can work with than no data at all – as long as it is communicated transparently where the data is coming from.

“If they are interested and invest their time, I trust they will do it well and not maliciously distort the results or degrade the quality.” – DE_R01

“I’d rather have data that approximates reality than no data at all.” – DE_R04

Nevertheless, researchers also pointed out that scientific data collection done by citizens also has limitations. This would for example absolutely not be possible in the field of medical research.

Agenda-Setting Power

Looking at social integration from another perspective, integrating citizens in the entire research process might also mean providing them with agenda-setting power. This difficult topic was also controversially discussed in the POIESIS focus groups. One researcher insisted that such a controlling function of citizens in the field of research would require a deep public understanding of the functioning of science and the scientific method. In his eyes, such an understanding is however non-existent in large parts of society. Another researcher argued that especially in her field of research, she would view providing citizens with agenda-setting power rather critically because she already perceives a lack of public interest for her research topics as soon as they do not seem to concern ‘ourselves here in Europe’ directly. She therefore fears that citizens might not be capable of judging which kinds of research are important in her field: “I see the disadvantage or concern that other topics might be prioritised because they are seen as more directly relevant to people here” (DE_R03). She adds that the current research agenda is already strongly influenced by external factors from different dimensions, such as political decisions, funding calls issued by RFOs etc.

From a more positive perspective, one researcher noted that in her point of view, integrating citizens in the research process could be understood in the sense of systematically presenting research topics to the public, asking whether they are interested in them and would like to provide feedback. If they are not, this would not have the consequence that the research is not conducted as such, but that it is done without public feedback. This way, citizens would have the opportunity to be included and express their opinions but without research projects entirely depending on it.

Expectation management

Another critical aspect of social integration, equally already discussed extensively in the POIESIS focus groups, is expectation management for citizens. Particularly the researcher working in a living lab emphasised that one needs to be careful and very transparent regarding the expectations social integration raises among citizens: it might be that people think because they have contributed their opinion in a research process, that the output at the end will also directly reflect this opinion. It is therefore crucial to be, from the beginning of the process, very clear about the integration’s limitations and the influence citizens’ involvement will have on the final output.

From a slightly different perspective but still related to expectation management, another researcher insisted that one needs to be careful with claiming participation to become an overall concept, because it just cannot be applied to all scientific disciplines. Citizens might however expect it to be.

The expectation management of citizens involved in the research process is already not a negative but rather a critical aspect to consider in regard to social integration. The same is true for the last two points discussed by researchers in this context.

Target groups / Audiences

An important question for researchers (and mediators, see for example section 3.1.2) when it comes to science communication as much as social integration practices is: for whom do we do these projects? Researchers suspect that most participants, for example in citizen science projects are already interested in science. But how can target groups or audiences be reached that are not interested? Or, even more, who do not trust in science and whose trust we therefore aim to increase? This question is crucial for researchers when reflecting on the broader topic of social integration. They are also aware that engaging with uninterested audiences might not always be pleasant for researchers themselves, though:

“Of course, it’s fun to talk to scientifically interested citizens, but we probably need to take another step and think about how we can reach those who have little trust in us and may not have the motivation to engage with it on their own. But this is laborious and probably not always enjoyable.” – DE_R01

Responsibility

A last important aspect to consider – which could potentially turn into negative consequences for trust in science – is the responsibility researchers carry in projects which involve citizens (equally discussed in the focus groups). A majority of researchers stressed that they are very conscious of the implications it has or might have when non-scientists are part of a scientific project. One researcher noted that if one was to overwhelm citizens during the process or also to show non-integer behaviour as a scientific actor engaged with citizens, such as being influenced by third parties etc., then one could do more harm than good with social integration projects. He makes the comparison with a chemical laboratory that might explode because of human error, but that could just be rebuilt after such an incident. The same is not true for trust in social integration projects. Another researcher emphasised that she believes social integration can contribute positively to trust in science but only when done seriously. Participants notice when they are not taken seriously and when ‘participation’ is just set up to receive more funding or to comply with guidelines. In such cases ‘fake’ or pseudo social integration can actually even have negative consequences for public trust in science. In this regard, the researcher insisted that scientists engaged in such projects actually need to get used to receiving feedback from non-scientists, and that taking this feedback seriously means to actually be open to re-think their plans and objectives.

Obstacles regarding social integration of citizens in the research process

The main points researchers discussed with respect to obstacles in the context of social integration are: the necessary translation process in both directions; a lack of resources,

especially time and money; and the actual motivation to take part in social integration practices – on the side of citizens as much as on the side of researchers.

Translation process

Several researchers underlined that research projects integrating citizens in the scientific process require an extensive translation process in both directions. On the one hand, it is necessary but difficult to translate scientific findings and also researchers' everyday scientific language in a way that is adapted to citizens involved in the projects. On the other hand, 'translation' is also needed in the other direction because some things that one might expect as a researcher function very differently from the public perspective:

“Transformative research is time-consuming because you speak a different language, you have to translate scientific terminology, assess what you get and from whom, and so on. These are things you don't necessarily have to ask in a purely scientific environment.” – DE_R05

One researcher underlined, that public understanding of the functioning of science would make things easier, but that: “I personally see the greatest obstacle in the lack of understanding of scientific work” (DE_R02). In any case, it is necessary for researchers to reflect very carefully and in much detail on questions like: In which complexity does one translate the own scientific findings? How does one assess the input received from the outside? Who is included in the process and at which stages?

Resources

It has already been shown from different angles that according to researchers doing social integration 'right' requires many resources, mostly time and money.

The lack of time might be the most recurring argument among researchers when it comes to obstacles for engaging in social integration projects. Translation processes are long, organising projects is difficult, detailed evaluations are needed, and all of this becomes even more difficult when done transdisciplinary. Several researchers further stress the high bureaucratic effort of social integration projects, for example concerning data protection measures, authorisations for interviews, photos etc.

The problem is often not as such that social integration projects take time, but that this time is not truly accounted for. For example, in many cases, funding organisations push increasingly harder to have research projects in which citizens are involved, but without providing the necessary framework conditions for it: “It takes a lot of time, and this time is not always planned for. They want a participative research design within six weeks, which is just not possible” (DE_R06).

There also is a significant problem at the systemic level especially for younger researchers who would like to engage in social integration and also science

communication activities more generally (see also section 3.5.1 of mediators' recommendations): social integration projects require a lot of time but are not recognised as very valuable in the academic system. One cannot make many publications out of it, which are, however, the most important currency for young researchers to advance in their careers. The additional lack of recognition for engaging in this field leads to many young researchers focussing much less on such activities than they would actually like to.

Lack of time as an important obstacle to social integration is not only limited to researchers, though: representatives of civil society, patient organisations etc. all only have limited capacities. This needs to be taken into account when asking for increased integration of different societal actors in the research process.

In addition to a lack of time, many researchers also mention a lack of money as being an obstacle for social integration. Such projects cannot be done 'on the side' and therefore it is important to have the actual funding to do so.

Given that resources seem to be the most important obstacle for many researchers to engage in social integration on the one hand but that, on the other hand, funding organisation constantly ask for increased engagement in this regard, one researcher very explicitly formulated the demand that research funding organisations should provide the necessary resources and comprehensive concepts to implement social integration practices correctly.

Motivations

Obstacles in regard to social integration do not only relate to a lack of resources, but also to the dimension of motivations of all actors involved in the process. Particularly the researcher working in a living lab stressed the fact that people's lives have only 24 hours and that citizens might want to spend this time doing other things than 'science' (conducting science themselves or being scientific research subjects). For him, this is a totally justified position and one should not judge this negatively by saying that people necessarily should have an extensive interest in being involved in science. The challenge that emerges from this is to create public interest and convince people that one's project or offer is how they want to spend some of their lifetime.

Another researcher added to this that it is really challenging to find adequate channels of communication to actually reach people who might be interested in participating in a research project. She underlined that social integration is not established as a concept in the public and that she has experienced that asking people whether they could imagine engaging in a research project might create confusion as people are just not familiar with this idea.

It might therefore not only be due to the provision side (science and the scientists) that there is not more social integration already but partly also due to a lack of public interest.

Motivation is, however, not only an issue for potential participants of social integration projects but also for scientists. As for science communication (see section 3.4.1), several

researchers underlined that not all scientists are interested in conducting research in which non-scientists are involved – no matter how many resources they would have at hand. This is especially but not exclusively true in regard to basic research. The researchers in the interviews perceived this position as totally justified and defended the argument that not all researchers need to engage in social integration and that science also needs researchers who conduct research, teach, but do not go further ‘into the public’.

The researchers’ assessment of social integration, i.e. the integration of citizens and other stakeholders in the research process, varies across interviewees. While some see the concept mainly from the citizen science perspective and are very positive towards it, others – who rather think about citizens receiving a certain degree of agenda-setting power in science – assess it rather critically. The positive and negative arguments as well as the obstacles discussed in view of social integration are very similar to the ones discussed in the focus groups and partly also in the public consultation. One can say that there are indeed very diverging opinions on the desirability of social integration in the research process from different perspectives. Opinions differ however not really between groups of different stakeholders involved in the process (citizens, institutional actors, researchers), but rather within these groups.

ID	Additional quotes
DE_R04	“I am really torn. For some funding programmes, yes, for others, no. As scientists, we have a duty to communicate what we do, as we are funded by taxpayer money. Therefore, everyone has the right to know what we do, not just through cryptic journals but in an understandable way. However, tying it to research funding in a mandatory way is not something I support. There are programmes where it makes sense, but there should still be basic research conducted for the sake of knowledge, not just for communication.”
DE_R04	“I think [social integration] makes a lot of sense and is also really good because it can involve people in the scientific process, which for many is somewhat mysterious. They think, ‘I don’t know exactly what the scientists are doing.’ This approach can... not necessarily remove inhibitions but bring them a little bit closer.”
DE_R03	“Depending on when in the process we do it, we present our research approach at the beginning of a study or new work in a country. We discuss it and ask questions, often in group sessions to get specific input. This has been very helpful because new topics were brought up that we hadn’t considered, allowing us to identify specific expertise. Later in the process, we present the research results and discuss in smaller groups how to use them, translate them into actions, projects, programmes, etc.”
DE_R01	“I would wish that [patient organisations] are involved directly in project planning. Depending on the project, one could ask, ‘Are there any

	considerations we should take into account? How do patients want to be addressed about this research project? What is appropriate? How do they want to be informed?”
DE_R05	“Managing expectations is not easy. In such processes, it is essential to be open from the beginning about the limitations and what the collaboration serves.”
DE_R01	“As a scientist, I also see the practical negative aspects because it will consume an enormous amount of time.”
DE_R04	“For many scientists, especially early-career researchers, such projects are immensely time-consuming. You can’t make many publications from them, which is unfortunately one of the main currencies in science, especially during the doctoral and post-doc phase. This is a systemic problem.”
DE_R06	“I would primarily say that if [social integration] is required, then time and money must be allocated for it. And this means that it needs to be established in such a way that the concept must first be understood at a societal level.”
DE_R05	“People want to live their lives, and everyone has their idea of how to spend their 24 hours a day. We have to figure out how to spark their interest and get them to say, ‘Oh, I want to participate in that,’ and dedicate their time to it.”

4.4 About public trust in science

The upcoming section synthesises researchers’ assessment of public trust in science from different angles. First of all, researchers’ overall perception of the state of trust in Germany is presented. Then, researchers’ thoughts on citizens’ concerns about science and reasons for mistrust as well as rationales behind different observations in this regard are discussed. All sub-chapters distinguish arguments regarding public trust in science more generally and in the specific context of climate change.

4.4.1 Perception of public trust in science

Researchers’ perceptions of public trust in science are, in the same way as for mediators (see section 3.3), rather positive. There are no apparent differences across researchers from different disciplines (climate change vs. Covid-19, natural sciences vs. SSH) in the general assessment of trust in science. Researchers working on climate change however often added specific points in regard to trust in climate research beyond their more general considerations.

General

Altogether, all researchers, as much as all mediators, perceive public trust in science to be rather high. Researchers often compared science and scientists to other groups of public actors in this regard and emphasised that science still enjoys much more public trust in comparison to others.

This being said, researchers also shared observations of recent (negative) evolutions in regard to trust in science and of critical aspects in public interaction with science. Researchers unanimously agree that trust in science has seen an important evolution in the last years, strongly related to the emergence of climate change and Covid-19. Both are very prominent but also controversially discussed scientific topics in the public discourse. Against this backdrop, researchers observe an increased politicisation of scientific discourse (see also section 3.3) further fuelled by the strong media interest in both topics. This has resulted in many public discussions being based on partial knowledge. Moreover, researchers are particularly concerned about the increased mix-up of scientific findings and facts on the one hand with political opinions and suggested conclusions based on these findings on the other hand. Scientific findings are being appropriated by political actors to support their individual positions but without clearly separating between both (the scientific finding and the political opinion).

This has a spillover-effect on the public discourse where, according to researchers, the same trend can be perceived. One researcher stated, for example, that since the pandemic, as soon as people get to know that one is a researcher, their statements about scientific facts are questioned – also in day-to-day interactions. Even worse, researchers have increasingly become the target of – physical and psychological – attacks and it has become very difficult to communicate about science neutrally.

Another, partly related observation is that increasingly, ‘scientific studies’ are used to support any kinds of arguments in public and political discourse but without using any criteria to assess whether these ‘studies’ are actually of (good) scientific quality. Mediators shared this same impression that all kinds of actors, including citizens, apparently agree that science is really important because they all try to base their discussions on said-to-be scientific content. However, a lack of understanding of the scientific method leads to a confusion of actual scientific and pseudo-scientific content in this regard. This is not only dangerous in the sense that false information is spread but it is also detrimental to public trust in science.

Researchers noted that relativising arguments in the sense of ‘If you say my study is not scientific, why should I then believe in the study you talk about’ have become a more integral part of public discourse. Before, they were rather to be found at the extreme edges of public opinion. Generally, researchers identify very loud anti-science and conspiracy-led minority opinions in public discourse, often among groups where trust in political actors and other institutions is also very low. Several researchers agree however, that these voices are certainly very loud but still only represent a minority opinion in

society. One researcher added that critical voices towards science are supported by different communication channels, social media certainly but also specific newspapers.

From a different perspective, two researchers also assessed public trust towards their specific institutions. Both perceived public trust in their own work as rather high and saw the reason for this in their institution's high reputation and also a certain visibility of the institution in the media. One researcher stressed specifically that such trust in the own institution comes with an important responsibility to deal with it carefully (see also section 4.3.2).

Climate change

Similarly to the mediators, researchers stated that there are not many hardcore climate change deniers anymore. At the same time, there is a pretty large group of sceptical actors questioning the importance of fighting climate change or the amount of resources that should be invested in it (see also section 4.2.2). According to researchers, such discourses of delay can be observed in different societal dimensions including politics and therein also from the side of traditional mainstream parties.

Related to that, researchers think that the positioning of political parties might have an influence on public perception of climate change research. But they perceive another aspect of discussion around climate change as even more important: we live in a world where many of the things people like or like to do are questioned because of some rather abstract concept like climate change with consequences that do not seem to affect us much right now here in Germany. Researchers underline that it is comprehensible that people feel resistance against this development because they want to keep their life the way it is. It is easy for the relevant actors to pick people up at this point and to offer them seemingly simple but in fact pseudo-solutions for not needing to change their lives. Following such ideas can be seen as a psychological phenomenon of searching for the last straw to be able to keep the car, continue to eat meat etc.:

“We live in a time where many people see their habits and what they enjoy doing being questioned because of an abstract concept like climate change. Being asked to change their lives because of this leads to significant resistance. Those who sow doubt have an easy job of capturing people's attention.” – DE_R05

From another perspective, “a sense of fatalism has set in for some people, who believe it is too late to make a difference. They see how fast everything is changing and how much needs to be done to counteract it, which would be very costly” (DE_R03).

Researchers working on climate change share these observations with mediators from the same field who see a potential solution in more positive and constructive communication in the context of climate change but also science more generally (see section 3.5.1).

4.4.2 Citizens' concerns about science

Based on their different observations on the state of trust in science in Germany and recent developments in this regard, researchers discussed recurrent concerns citizens express about science. In their arguments, one can once again distinguish between aspects concerning science more generally and those that are specifically related to climate change.

General

First of all, it can be stated that researchers reflecting on citizens' concerns about science did not once raise the issue of scientific misconduct themselves. When prompted for it explicitly (which was done in half of the interviews), researchers expressed that yes, sometimes there are voices claiming that scientific findings are forged, yes, the climate-gate scandal may have done some damage, and yes, plagiarism allegations sometimes emerge in the media. However, all researchers emphasised that in their impression, these are not the actual concerns citizens have about science and the scientific system.

DE_R01 stated for example: "Although there are, of course, always negative examples of science being falsified, I believe the main issue is the transferability and applicability for the individual citizen." This impression reflects a majority opinion among the researchers who add that science happening in the 'ivory tower' is one of the main concerns citizens have regarding science. "There is a perceived divergence between what science investigates and what the real problems are" (DE_R04).

The second main concern citizens have is, according to researchers, related to the financing of science and scientific projects. Depending on the respective context, worries are expressed that science is industry-controlled (when research projects are funded privately) or that science is state-controlled (when research projects are funded publicly): "There is concern that science is not conducted for its own sake but is state-controlled" (DE_R04). In both cases, citizens suspect that science is not conducted to generate findings oriented towards the common good but is instead influenced by non-transparent third-party interests.

Climate change related

Citizens' concerns about science in the context of climate change are often related to climate models and their trustworthiness. Several researchers noted that citizens might have difficulties understanding these models and especially the probabilities on which they are built. DE_R03 explains:

"Studies are for example published showing a 10% probability of something happening within a certain period. This is obviously alarming, but it is still just a 10% probability, not a deterministic event. I think it is hard for people to understand that predictions often involve probabilities, and it is challenging to interpret this correctly. Such studies are further often simplified in media headlines." – DE_R03

Although organisations such as the IPCC are working towards more accessibility of their materials also for non-scientists, this still is an important problem when it comes to public trust. The same argument about the difficulty to interpret probabilities in the context of climate change has also been made by a mediator working in the same field (see section 3.3.1).

4.4.3 Reasons for and rationales in regard to mistrust in science

While the two previous sections have synthesised researchers' perspectives on how trust in science currently 'looks like', from a general and a climate change-related perspective, the upcoming section focuses on the reasons and rationales behind observed tendencies of mistrust in science. This time, researchers also included the dimension of Covid-19 in their reflections agreeing that this was a critical juncture for public trust in science (see also section 3.3.1 for the mediators' perspective on this).

General

There are three main rationales and influencing factors researchers believe to be at the bottom of the observations they have made regarding tendencies of public mistrust in science.

First of all, researchers identify a general "underlying trust factor that impacts many areas of life" (DE_R04) and that has an influence on science but also on other societal dimensions such as politics. Mediators had called this a critique of elites while researchers rather see increasing mistrust towards institutions and specifically publicly founded institutions at the core. Regardless of the way it is framed, generally rising suspicion and mistrust within different dimensions of society are perceived as having an impact on public trust in science by a majority of interviewees.

The second important reason several researchers identify for increasing mistrust at least among parts of society is strong lobbying and significant amounts of money being invested into consciously fuelling mistrust:

"Massive lobbying efforts, with think tanks and multi-million-dollar companies investing heavily to foster mistrust, are probably the biggest factor." – DE_R04

Third, there is social media. Researchers were of different opinions as to whether the increased use of social media should be seen as an actual reason for increased public mistrust in science or rather as a tool in the hands of powerful actors fuelling mistrust in this regard. In any case, they agree that social media plays an important role in creating closed bubbles and spreading misinformation. This has been especially true since the pandemic when online communication suddenly became the number one way of

communicating for nearly everybody and for several months during the lockdowns. Social media and its algorithms became very powerful in this time.

This increased importance of communicating via social media comes with another evolution: an increased pluralisation of the media landscape. According to one researcher, until a few years ago, there were very few clear leading media channels from which people got their information (plus talking to friends and neighbours). Today, there are manifold ways of informing oneself but with no checks of quality in place. Social media has further become less and less ‘guided’ and controlled (see for example the evolution of X, formerly Twitter), which makes it increasingly easier for different actors to spread misinformation:

“What used to be done only by the Bild newspaper – capturing people’s attention with simple slogans – is now much easier on social media. There are actors who deliberately engage in this, consciously spreading misinformation to mislead people.” – DE_R05

Covid-19 related

As many researchers invoked the Covid-19 pandemic when talking about rationales for public mistrust in science, a few more specific arguments in this regard are presented below.

In the very beginning of the pandemic, trust in science skyrocketed in Germany but then decreased again over time accompanied by a strong polarisation of public discourse. Researchers explain this the following way:

“Initially, there was hope that science would save us, but as the pandemic dragged on, people became impatient. Although the vaccine development process was incredibly fast from a scientific perspective, it still took two years for people to get their lives back, which felt like a long time.” – DE_R01

The entire process of vaccine development was perceived as very problematic in the eyes of citizens according to researcher DE_R01. Already from the start, trust in the pharmaceutical industry is generally very low in Germany. Then, even though people were impatient to return to daily life, they were confused that a new vaccine could be developed as quickly as it was. Therefore, many people were very suspicious and did not trust in the effectiveness of this vaccine. Being able to provide an internal perspective, researcher DE_R01 explains that the speed of the process was due to lots of public money, at the national and international level, being invested in various pharmaceutical companies so that they all could work in parallel and with all possible means towards an effective vaccine. In her perspective, the lack of communication and transparency in this regard certainly contributed to people’s mistrust. Nevertheless, she also thinks that more

transparency might possibly have led to public discontent as well because, in the end, much public money has also been spent for vaccines that did not turn out to be effective.

Regarding the role of researchers, one researcher perceived the Covid-19 pandemic as a problematic mix of urgency and lack of communication training:

“The scientific community simply jumped in at the deep end and there were lots of people who simply said ‘Yes, I’ll go out there and contribute something because I have to deal with it’. But of course, they had no idea how it worked, especially at the beginning. At my university, I think we had the first media training courses on Covid-19 research about a year into the pandemic. Of course, a lot had already happened, and a lot had gone brutally wrong. Because these were things, of course, or simply researchers whose work had never and would never have met public interest before.” – DE_R02

Researchers had to juggle their high motivation and willingness to contribute to the public debate on the one hand and very high scientific uncertainty and a lack of experience in science communication on the other hand. In addition to that, the lack of public understanding of scientific processes, that this researcher sees as a core problem in regard to trust in science, played an important role during the pandemic as well: large parts of the public did not understand that it is an intrinsic part of science that scientific findings evolve and are adapted over time:

“Then ‘the science’ that found this out at the beginning is not wrong, but is simply overtaken in the course of scientific work. Communicating this aspect is often challenging.” – DE_R02

Climate change related

Aiming to find rationales to explain public mistrust in science in the context of climate change, researchers mostly discussed two related arguments: climate change being a very abstract concept with many uncertainties on the one hand, and always more negative future predictions made by climate research on the other hand.

Regarding the first aspect, researchers note that everybody knows that climate change exists but, at the same time, that we do not and cannot know or predict all exact consequences.

“It is a very abstract challenge, and I believe this makes it difficult for many people to respond appropriately. [...] If I knew that in ten years, climate change would cause a specific event and we could take a specific action to prevent it, then I believe there would be much more trust.” – DE_R04

This does not only lead to less trust in science but also to a feeling of lacking self-efficacy – neither politics nor we, as citizens, can really do anything. According to one researcher, this kind of fatalistic attitude is increased even further by the fact that better scientific methods today predict an always more negative future. Instead of increasing the understanding of the urgency of the situation, people seem to be less and less receptive to and / or increasingly familiar with negative news caused by climate change. An example for this, mentioned by the researcher, is the current flooding disaster in Southern Germany and the historically bad election result of the Green Party in the European elections in Germany just right after.

Altogether, in the same way as the mediators, researchers all agreed that public trust in science is overall rather high in Germany. Nevertheless, they also identified some critical or even dangerous tendencies of increasing mistrust in science among parts of society. The main concerns citizens have about science, in the eyes of the researchers, is first, the perception that science operates in an ivory tower, far away from citizens’ actual problems, and second, an influence of third-party interests via channels of scientific funding. The main rationales researchers see behind rising mistrust in science are a generally increasing suspicion towards institutions in society which also concerns scientific ones as well as the conscious spread of misinformation by varying kinds of actors aiming to support their (mostly political) agenda. Social media plays an important role in this regard. Researchers and mediators alike perceive the Covid-19 pandemic as an important juncture for public trust in science in Germany.

ID here	Additional quotes
DE_R05	“In our living lab, we have built a precious trust, and we are very aware of its value.”
DE_R02	“As the pandemic began and social media became almost the only means of communication for many people, the situation gained a new level of significance.”
DE_R02	“Scientific findings can change over time as new data emerges. This does not mean the research was bad; it just reflects the evolving nature of scientific inquiry.”

4.5 Synthesis of recommendations to foster public trust in science

The last section of this chapter synthesises researchers' main recommendations to enhance public trust in science. In the same way as for the mediators, the recommendations are presented rather briefly in this section, focussing on the recommendations themselves without repeating all the underlying arguments that have been explained in detail in the previous sections of this chapter.

The recommendations are structured according to their three main themes: improving the mediating process between science and society; clarifying the relations between science and politics; and improving climate communication. At the end of this section, a table summarises the most important and most dominant recommendations in the mediators' discourses in short sentences.

Altogether, although the recommendations that researchers formulated are not identical to the ones of the mediators (see section 3.5), they are highly comparable and addressed to similar groups of actors. Therefore, the recommendations presented below are consciously structured in a very similar way as for the mediators in order to facilitate the direct comparison.

4.5.1 Recommendations for an improved mediating process

The following section synthesises researchers' ideas on improving the mediating or the translation process between science and society with the objective of fostering public trust in science. Recommendations cover the direct relation between the public and researchers, science communication done by researchers, and suggestions how to improve the mediating process addressed to 'the media' and scientific institutions.

Relation public - researchers

In regard to the relation between the public and researchers, several researchers asked for more direct interaction. This interaction needs actual exchange, though, not just another talk with 60 people coming and listening to a topic in which they are already interested. Researchers should engage in an exchange with a more critical and 'uninterested' public even though this might not always be easy. New creative communication paths should be found for that. One researcher also emphasises the potential of social integration in this regard:

“What I would see as an opportunity these days, which is perhaps a completely new aspect, is that by involving people [in the research process], you might be able to restore a bit of public trust. Of course, that would only ever be a small circle, you cannot involve as many people as you like. There's a limit to that. But then they tell others about it, and it's reported that people were involved. This can of course also contribute to [trust].” – DE_R05

In order to increase an overall understanding of science and scientific literacy in society, several researchers suggest focussing on schools, because it is the only place where all societal groups can still be reached. There should be more direct interaction formats between researchers and younger people but beyond that, it would be necessary to include scientific literacy in school curricula. One should not only learn how to cite formally correct – what already happens – but much more important, to assess the trustworthiness of sources of information, to think critically and to understand the process of producing scientific findings with all it implies.

Science communication by researchers

Another important recommendation several researchers made was better training and education of researchers in science communication activities. Many researchers have difficulties communicating – even within the scientific community – and existing training in this regard would not only help but also motivate them further to engage in science communication activities. In the best-case scenario, such training would be part of the mandatory university education every student has to go through. Once again, as for scientific literacy in the broader public, university is the only place one is able to reach all future researchers. And even though not all students stay in academia, the ability to communicate, to constructively deal with counter-opinions etc., is useful in all other contexts as well.

Another aspect in relation to motivating researchers further to engage in science communication and also social integration is the necessity to provide more information about what is actually possible in this field. According to one researcher, one cannot force researchers to engage in these kinds of activities, one needs to raise curiosity and show that it is fun to do so.

Another researcher further thinks that a more fundamental discussion concerning the responsibility for science communication in the field is needed:

“What I would wish for is more consideration of the question: who is actually responsible for science communication? Does it fall within the job description of researchers? If so, then they need to learn it. If so, then there should be training opportunities, which, at the moment, you find occasionally, but researchers currently have to decide for themselves to pursue this path.” – DE_R06

Towards the Media

Researchers also see the media as having a responsibility to contribute to improving the mediating process between science and society. For example, they wish for larger and more balanced media interest in topics related to science. They are aware that such an increased visibility would not automatically lead to more trust in science, though. It would be up to scientists to then use these platforms accordingly.

“One charming idea I found is that certain scientific positions should be more firmly anchored in mass media. We already have stock market news in the Tagesschau or the Tagesthemen for decades. Why don't we have climate news or other relevant scientific matters included?” – DE_R04

Researchers also underline the necessity for media reports to improve in what concerns the contextualisation of scientific findings. They should not leave people alone with catastrophic news just to generate headlines, but always contextualise, offer potential solutions, and pick up emotions.

As has become obvious in the previous sections of this chapter, researchers – and mediators – perceive social media to have a crucial role when it comes to public trust in science. Two researchers picked this up in their recommendations as well departing from the basic assumption that social media has come to stay, and that therefore the question arises of how to design such platforms in a better way.

One researcher suggests that there should be much more and much stricter regulation in regard to fake news. The other one goes much further in her vision and expresses that social media should function with different algorithms. There could for example be an algorithm spreading the most credible or trustworthy news, one that shows some change in perspective from time to time etc. However, she clearly said to be aware of the fact that this will not work as long as social media is related to private economic interests.

Towards scientific institutions

Researchers address three main recommendations to scientific institutions in order to improve the mediating process between science and society. The first one is to institutionalise Open Access in science and make data much more accessible.

The second one is a better recognition of science communication activities in the academic system. To make it an integral part of researchers' work, it requires much more attention and recognition, such as making it a criterion of calls for tenured positions whether someone is active in science communication or not.

“It is simply not sufficiently appreciated within the academic system. It is an important task, and there should be greater attention and recognition for it when it is done.” – DE_R03

The third recommendation, or rather claim, several researchers address to scientific institutions is to overcome the problematic system that researchers constantly face the challenge to secure their jobs. They are so occupied with trying to obtain third-party funding that there is no time and energy left for engaging in the field of science communication or social integration.

“So, as a scientist, you need the time and space to do [science communication], right? Not be constantly occupied with applying for third-party funding and securing your own position and livelihood but knowing that you have time allocated for science communication because it is simply important.” – DE_R01

4.5.2 Recommendations regarding the relation between science and politics

One of the most recurring themes during all the interviews (mediators and researchers) was the increased politicisation of the scientific discourse. Several researchers also formulated recommendations in this regard. They emphasised that to increase public trust in science, it is important that citizens are able to differentiate between scientific findings on the one side and political opinions based on these findings on the other side. They also noted, however, that the instrumentalisation of scientific content for political agendas certainly mainly comes from the side of political actors, but that researchers also need to be very careful when they actively enter public discourse with political opinions. It is understandable that they do so, especially when they have the impression that important topics are neglected by politics. Nevertheless, doing so raises the important question of how activist researchers should or are allowed to be (see also section 3.2.1).

One researcher further formulated the recommendation to create more coherence within the relation between science and politics:

“I believe that if science and politics behaved more coherently with each other, that would also help. We currently have the problem that science warns and advises extensively through expert reports, but politicians do not take it seriously at all. This can lead citizens to think, 'Well, if politicians are not implementing it, then it might not be that bad,' and that scientists are just making a fuss. So, a stronger alignment between politics and science could contribute to this, up to a certain point. Because if everyone agrees too much, it might also seem strange, as we somewhat saw with Covid-19.” – DE_R04

4.5.3 Recommendations regarding climate communication

In the same way as the mediators, researchers also formulated recommendations in the very specific context of climate communication emphasising the importance this topic has for our future.

In the same vein as mediators, researchers argued that it is important to communicate positively rather than only negatively all the time. One must understand that people find it of course difficult to imagine changing their life because of an abstract phenomenon like climate change. It is important not to patronise them but to constructively explain what can be done and why it is important to do so.

Related to that, one researcher made a recommendation as simple as important:

“It is always, always much cheaper to invest in climate protection than to pay for the consequences later. But that doesn’t seem to get through. [...] making it clear that prevention is better than reaction, I think that currently really doesn’t work.“
- DE_R03

Improving communication in this regard is even more crucial because people have the impression that all they do now does not have a direct and immediate effect to stop climate change while still costing them money and efforts today. It is important to improve the long-term understanding in this regard.

Altogether, researchers, as mediators did as well, came up with numerous recommendations on how to improve the mediating process between science and society. They equally perceived the interaction between science and politics as a crucial factor influencing public trust in science ‘from the outside’ and formulated similar recommendations as the mediators to disentangle both spheres in public perception. Finally, researchers also formulated recommendations in the specific context of climate communication – without having been asked to do so specifically. The most dominant recommendations in the researchers’ discourses are summarised in the table below.

Researchers’ main recommendations:
1. Engage with a more critical or ‘uninterested’ public through new creative forms of communication.
2. Make science communication training an integral part of university curricula.
3. Give scientific news more space in institutionalised mass media.
4. Improve the recognition of science communication and social integration activities within the academic system.
5. Clarify the roles of science and politics in society and create more coherence in the interaction of both spheres.
6. Improve climate communication in a way that makes clear that prevention is always better (and cheaper) than reaction in the context of climate change.

Note: Different key recommendations have consciously been chosen for mediators and for researchers to broaden the perspectives of what can be done.

5 Conclusion

This conclusion does not have the objective to summarise all that has been said before. Sections 3.5 and 4.5 presenting mediators' and researchers' recommendations to enhance public trust in science are already fulfilling this task. Instead, this conclusion highlights a few thematic fields discussed by researchers and mediators alike – although they have not been asked the same questions. Doing so, it also refers back to results from the analysis of the German focus groups and the public consultation (see also section 1.2 in this regard) and, in the end, formulates some preliminary thoughts on how all these insights together might relate to the POIESIS 3i4t model.

First of all, and very importantly, mediators and researchers alike perceive **trust in science** to be rather high in Germany. In this regard, they align with the perception of all focus groups. Nevertheless, all of them also identify tendencies of mistrust in society, fuelled by some very loud anti-science but also anti-institutional voices in public discourse. Although representing a minority opinion, their slogans and simplistic messages spread rather successfully, very much facilitated by the increased use of social media. The Covid-19 pandemic is seen as the key critical juncture in the relation between science and society in the recent past by researchers and mediators alike. It has brought 'science' back into the middle of public discussions but also increased doubts and even mistrust as new scientific findings – with high uncertainty – quickly got blended with political decision-making.

This **politicisation of scientific discourse** or rather even the appropriation of scientific content by different political agendas was clearly the most dominant topic in all interviews, focus groups, and also citizens' discussions. However, it was in the interviews where researchers and mediators alike identified the problematic aspect of it in the clearest way: the problem from the perspective of citizens is not as such that scientific findings enter the political area, but that there is a lack of distinction between where scientific facts and findings end and potential social and political consequences, taken on the basis of these findings, begin. Researchers and mediators clearly see politicians in the responsibility of making efforts in this regard, but in many interviews, a strongly related question was discussed as well: how activist are researchers themselves allowed to be? Opinions differed in this regard, but all interviewees emphasised that transparency and pro-active self-reflection vis-à-vis the public are necessary when one steps out of their role as 'neutral researcher' and starts defending an actual agenda.

Interestingly, compared to discussions in the focus groups and the public consultation, the interaction between science and industry played a much less important role in the interviews with researchers and mediators.

Another topic that has been discussed not only by researchers and mediators, but also by institutional actors and citizens, are **audiences of science communication** and social integration: a clear majority of interviewees asked themselves for whom they actually do

their communication activities. They agreed that it is totally valid, and also necessary, to address those who are already interested in science. Nevertheless, many of them also stressed that they would like to reach new audiences, those who are not interested and even more those with increasing mistrust in science. The question of whom science communication activities are actually for is clearly a central one for all kinds of actors who are part of the mediating process.

Not totally unrelated, all actors POIESIS has spoken to in Germany, including citizens, attest the broader public an important lack of understanding for the scientific method and a general **lack of 'scientific literacy'**. Without exception, all see this as a crucial problem in the relation between science and society and many suggest tackling this problem already in school, when all societal groups can still be reached.

Reflecting on the **POIESIS 3i4t model** and all insights provided by the various groups of actors within the last year, several preliminary observations can be made:

Research integrity, at least in the sense of **scientific misconduct** is not a very dominant topic either in the interviews (with mediators but also with researchers who could have raised the issue in regard to trust in science), focus groups or in the public consultation. All actors acknowledge that there are cases of scientific misconduct and that these might potentially have short-term consequences for trust in science. However, no matter which group of actors, all did a) perceive misconduct as an exception rather than the rule among researchers and b) insist that this is not the main problem in the relation between science and society. Instead, they see lobbyism, the fear of **interest-led research**, and also the above-mentioned politicisation and thereof resulting polarisation of scientific discourse as much more important issues.

Regarding **social integration**, very similar positive as much as negative aspects and obstacles have been discussed in the interviews and focus groups and to a large part also in the public consultation. While all groups of different actors clearly see the potential of social integration and think it is good, useful and necessary to integrate citizens in the research process in specific contexts, overall, critical questions and obstacles had more weight in the discussions than positive aspects. In essence, an increasing demand for ever-more social integration (from funders and other institutions) faces an important lack of resources and also a lack of training in this regard on the side of researchers. This has potentially dangerous consequences as all actors emphasise that social integration practices need to be taken seriously. If they are not, they could even be detrimental for public trust in science.

Further, there is a consensus among participants from interviews, focus groups and again even among citizens from the public consultation that social integration cannot be part of projects in all scientific disciplines. A detailed reflection of where it is useful and to what extent is very much necessary.

Looking at the **role of institutions**, insights from the empirical material have shown that it is mainly the institutional actors who see institutions in an active role to work towards trust in science. Institutions' reputations and the influence such reputation has for public trust in the content coming from these institutions have also been discussed in the interviews but not as a very prominent theme. The academic system as such is however repeatedly seen in the obligation to improve working conditions for researchers ending the endless sequencing of short-term contracts and job dependency on third-party funding. In the same vein, actors in the interviews and focus groups alike ask for an increased recognition of science communication activities in academic careers. Institutions and their reputation play an important role for non-institutional mediators when they assess the trustworthiness of sources. All of these aspects seem however rather indirectly related to public trust in science.

Mediators and chains of mediation are clearly seen to have an important role in ensuring the translation process between science and society. It is their responsibility to transmit information, to choose trustworthy content, and to contextualise new scientific findings, according to researchers and mediators alike. Mediators emphasise in this regard how difficult it often is to juggle expectations, demands, and objectives of 'science' on the one and 'journalism' on the other hand. This does not only apply to science journalists, but also to all other mediators who need to create the attention of their audience before even being able to start transmitting information.

The further impact different channels of communication have on trust in science has already become very clear in the public consultation. The role of social media has been discussed extensively in this regard by citizens, but also by institutional actors, mediators and researchers.

Improving the mediating process between science and society – together with disentangling scientific and political discourses – has clearly been the focus of researchers' and mediators' recommendations to foster public trust in science.

Altogether, it seems that there are no or only very few linear connections between research integrity, at least in the sense of scientific misconduct, and public trust in science. For social integration, the connection does not seem entirely clear either. These observations from the qualitative data collected for POIESIS in Germany are coherent with the literature review (see D1.2) coming to the result that there is not much empirical evidence regarding the relation between trust in science on the one hand and integrity or integration on the other hand. They can also be linked to the recent quantitative analysis of Eurobarometer data conducted for POIESIS (see D1.3) showing that apparently, public trust in science does not work along separate concepts (such as 'integrity' or 'integration'). It rather seems to function along overarching social lines and – when having a look at the qualitative data – to be strongly related to societal developments and framework conditions as well. These observations for public trust in science in Germany are however of very preliminary nature and need to be deepened and systematised in the upcoming months.

Appendix

Codebook for Mediators' Interviews

Codes

- Mediation_Process
- Mediation_Interaction
- Mediation_Motivation
- Mediation_Networks
- Mediation_Audiences
- Mediation_Quotes
- Integrity_Definition
- Integrity_before_hinge
- Integrity_Assessment
- Integrity_Importance
- Integrity_Examples
- Integrity_Quotes
- Trust_Perception
- Trust_Role
- Trust_Controversies
- Trust_Quotes
- Trust_Recommendations
- Trust_Recommendations_GenZ
- Other_Politics
- Other_RoleMedia
- Other_SciComm
- Other_Quotes

Code Groups // Sub-sections

- 3.1 Chains of mediation
- 3.2 About research ethics and integrity
- 3.3 About public trust in science
- 3.5 About public trust in science
- 3.5 About public trust in science
- 3.4. Other themes
- 3.4. Other themes
- 3.4. Other themes
- 3.4. Other themes

Codebook for Researchers' Interviews

Codes

- Work_Topic
- Work_Controversies
- SciComm_Experiences
- SciComm_Formats
- SciComm_Controversies
- SciComm_Other
- SciComm_Quotes
- Integration_Experiences
- Integration_Assessment_positiv
- Integration_Assessment_negativ
- Integration_Obstacles
- Integration_Quotes
- Trust_Perception
- Trust_Concerns
- Trust_Rationales
- Trust_Quotes
- Trust_Recommendations
- Other_Themes
- Other_Quotes

Code Groups // Sub-sections

- 4.1 Researcher contexts
- 4.1 Researcher contexts
- 4.2 About science communication and public attitudes
- 4.3 About the integration of citizens in research
- 4.3 About the integration of citizens in research
- 4.3 About the integration of citizens in research
- 4.3 About the integration of citizens in research
- 4.3 About the integration of citizens in research
- 4.4. About public trust in science
- 4.5. About public trust in science
- 4.X. Other themes
- 4.X. Other themes

Note: No further relevant themes were identified in the researchers' interviews which is why the last two codes were not used in the final analysis.

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Expert Interviews - *GREECE*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: CSIC

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1 Introduction

This section provides a brief background on the inputs to Task 2.3 from previous POIESIS tasks in each partner country and summarises the process of organising and conducting interviews with Mediators and Researchers.

1.1 Research questions for Task 2.3

The Expert Interview study contributes to answering the following research questions that guide POIESIS.

General research questions	More specific research questions
<p>RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?</p> <p>RQ3: To what extent and how does the <i>integration</i> of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?</p>	<p>How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts? <p>What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?</p>

1.2 Insights from Task 2.2 and Task 3.1

Based on the experiences gained in the context of the application of Tasks 2.2 and 3.1, as well as in the context of other projects we were expecting that the interviewees were not going to bring the term Research Integrity (RI) to the discussion; this is because in Greece RI is quite below the radar of both the research community and other stakeholders related to the research enterprise at large. Another reason could be that in Greece there was no research fraud scandal, so the mass media have not devoted articles related directly to RI. Another theme we were expecting to be discussed at the interviews was the general lack of trust

in institutions. This was quite evidence in previous empirical studies we did in the context of another EU-funded project. This lack of trust is not only created by the overarching post-modernist culture, but also due to the relatively recent economic crisis and due to other major scandals, that affected the way Greek citizens perceive the effectiveness of Greek governments and state institutions in general.

1.3 Brief summary of organising the interviews

We have conducted eleven Mediator interviews and five Researcher interviews. The potential interviewees were identified through our professional networks, as well as by directly contacting non-institutional mediators. All potential interviewees were approached via email, following the instructions of the task leader. In Greece recruiting researchers working on COVID-19 proved to be very challenging. In the end, only two interviewees provided interviews, instead of three, as was planned by the protocol. In addition, no researchers were from SSH. We were not able to locate researchers from SSH; however, GR_R02 had a background that could be perceived as related to SSH. All interviews were conducted online, via Zoom. Two interviewers made all 16 interviews; 4 interviews were made by both interviewers, 5 were made by Leonidas Ananiadis, and 7 by Panagiotis Kavouras.

1.4 Data processing

The audio recordings of all interviews are being kept on NTUA's secure server. They were transcribed by the Amberscript software. The coding of the interviews was made by the commenting function of Microsoft Office Word, i.e. not with the use of a dedicated qualitative data processing software.

2 Participants in the Expert Interview study

2.1 Descriptive tables

Information in the tables have been compiled to provide a comprehensive description of roles, outputs, channels, audiences, interaction types, and information sources of our Mediators. Information in the tables in sub-section 2.2 will be compiled to provide a description of the research, communication, and citizen interaction practices of Researchers.

2.2 Mediators

Table 1. Demographics and occupation

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Mediator type**	Organization type (where applicable)	Occupational Description	Topic CV/CC#
GR_M01	F	Senior	Institutional	Research Performing Organisation (publicly funded)	Responsible for science communication with the use of novel technologies	n.a.
GR_M02	M	Senior	Non-institutional (science journalist & science communicator)	Newspaper (print) and Science Museums (presentations)	Editorial board and Lecturer at a relevant post-graduate course	n.a.
GR_M03	F	Mid	Institutional	Foreign RPO and Science Museum in Greece	Science communicator	n.a.
GR_M04	M	Senior	Non-Institutional	University, Daily and Weekly press, science and political journals	Science Journalist, Researcher, Lecturer	CC
GR_M05	M	Mid	Non-Institutional	Freelancer	Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.	CV/CC
GR_M06	M	Mid	Non-Institutional	Freelancer	Archaeologist, Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. (Social media, documentaries, books etc.)	n.a.
GR_M07	M	Mid	Non-Institutional	Freelancer	Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.	n.a.

GR_M08	M	Senior	Institutional	Academic library - University at Central Greece	Librarian	n.a.
GR_M09	M	Mid	Non-Institutional	Independent Science Writer, Greek University	Professional science writer, researcher, other content creator (Left)	n.a.
GR_M10	F	Senior	Institutional	Academic library - University at South Greece	Librarian	n.a.
GR_M11	M	S	Non-Institutional	Popularised science website, Foreign University (outside EU)	Professional science writer; Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.; University Professor	n.a.

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior

** Mediator type:

- Institutional Mediators working at publishers / working at universities or research institutes;
- Non-institutional mediators: a) Professional science writers/communicators; Science/general journalists; Authors of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.; Other content creators

Covid-19 or Climate Change or both (where applicable).

Table 2. Mediators' main communication tasks

Id.	Description of mediators' main tasks
GR_M01	Dissemination of research results produced by the interviewee's RPO through articles published at the Greek press or TV, interviews for the radio and TV from researchers from researchers of the interviewee's RPO. Articles that feature at the RPO's webpage and Social Media channels. Sometimes short YouTube videos. Lately, if the research project is relevant, we develop educational modules that can be presented in schools.
GR_M02	Dissemination and communication of research with an emphasis on its social impact; to highlight the value of the engagement of citizens in the decision-making process related to research.
GR_M03	Science communication to school students and general public for the research that is being developed at a foreign RPO. A similar set of tasks when the interviewee was working at a science museum in Greece.
GR_M04	A) articles in the daily and periodical press on science and technology issues, in terms of scientific developments and social impact, B) education in science and technology issues, through the highlighting of its philosophical and historical layout to future teachers, C) public actions in the context of academic activity and beyond, addressing a wider audience again on issues of public understanding of science.
GR_M05	Creating video of science-related content for his social media channels, where he refutes pseudo-scientific claims and reveals scientific fraud cases.
GR_M06	Writing books, shooting documentaries, posting video on social media, podcasts broadcasting of science-related (History and Archaeology) content
GR_M07	Creating video of science-related (Science) content for his social media channels
GR_M08	Responsible for measures that counteract FFP, Seminars to researchers and to university students on Open Science, Communicating the activities of Greek academic libraries that foster Open Science.
GR_M09	Writing science articles on websites and journals; participates on research projects of science communication.
GR_M10	Responsible for the sector of science communication of Greek academic libraries.

GR_M11	Writing science articles on websites and journals; part of the publishing team on a popularises science website; writing popularised science books.
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Table 3. Outputs produced by Mediators

Id.	Books	Articles	Audiovisual (TV)	Radio program	Podcast	Audiovisual (social media)	Text Post (Social media)*	Live (social media interaction)	Other: (please describe in a few words only)
GR_M01									Educational modules for schools, Guided tours in an innovative science museum.
GR_M02									Podcast: Three documentary short films on the history of scientific revolution of the 16 th and 17 th centuries and the connection of scientific progress with political, cultural, and ideological context.
GR_M03									Demonstration laboratories, adapted to children of different ages and to lay people.
GR_M04									Live Public Actions (Forums etc.)
GR_M05									Live Public Actions (Forums etc.)
GR_M06									
GR_M07									Live Public Actions (Forums etc.)
GR_M08									Seminars to researchers and university students and presentations at conferences
GR_M09									Live Public Actions (Forums etc.)
GR_M10									Facilitating the free availability of all the outputs of Greek universities

GR_M11									
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*Includes memes, photographs, videos and text

Table 4. Channels used by Mediators

Id.	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)						Chat apps		Other: (please describe in a few words only)
	TV	Radio	Newspaper	Websites	Blogs	Newsletters	LinkedIn	YouTube	Twitter	Instagram	TikTok	Other SN	WhatsApp	Telegram	
GR_M01															The innovative science museum
GR_M02															
GR_M03															
GR_M04															
GR_M05															Facebook
GR_M06															Facebook
GR_M07															Facebook
GR_M08															Seminars to researchers and university students and presentations at conferences
GR_M09															
GR_M10															
GR_M11															

Table 5. Audience addressed by Mediators

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' audiences/size estimate where known
GR_M01	No specific information about audience and size, except for the case of the innovative science museum: the last six months the total number of visitors were approximately 2500 people. Approximately 1700 are students from schools of secondary education.
GR_M02	No specific information for the journalistic articles. The interviewee replied in a qualitative manner: he said that the audience (the readers) are, according to the interviewee's estimation, citizens interested in all cultural endeavours of society; they are "active citizens". Mainly over 40 years old for the communication activities in Science Museums.
GR_M03	Students of different ages and lay people. The foreign RPO's science communication facility has opened in the October of 2023, so there are not yet annual visit data. The target is to have 300.000 visitors per year; until now the peak number of visitors in one day was 2.400.
GR_M04	Mixed, with each of these actions having a different focus. The articles are primarily addressed to a general audience. A few thousands to a few dozens of thousands on daily and monthly basis.
GR_M05	The ages are about 20 to 35 years old. He is targeting people who have a certain skill set. In fact, as the goal of the material is that someone, regardless of their academic background - even if they don't have any - can understand the essence of the video; he also has a relatively large audience, which is in the 15 to 17 age group; of course there are also people who have never went to university, but basically the people who attend are university students; he is aiming at people who don't have fixed views. So if a video about vaccination is going to be created, certainly his goal is not to convince people who are 100% anti-vaccine and they're not going to change their minds. He is targeting people who are either not entirely convinced by the issue or people who have never thought about the issue before and are just looking for information / it's a little bit puzzling because there are a lot of people who watch and have never subscribed. There are also a lot of people who are

	double subscribing, but right now the numbers that are showing on YouTube are 117 thousand approximately.
GR_M06	His target audience is mainly adults, who are not in the immediate field of the humanities, but who enjoy and want to have knowledge and information about archaeology. Mostly ages from approximately 20 to approximately 40. The so-called "dynamic audience". He has 90,000 followers on Instagram, approximately 50 thousand on Facebook. 3,000,000 listens on podcast and about 36,000 weekly subscribers. His books have all become bestsellers
GR_M07	The aim is to reach whoever is likely to find it interesting. Of course, it's inevitably geared towards an audience that is more or less of his age, because the way he communicates and the way he uses media resonates more with people around his age. / YouTube has about 280,000 subscribers, on Facebook the number is about 40-43,000, on Instagram is close to 30,000 and TikTok which is the newest medium is 12,000.
GR_M08	Researchers, university students, general public.
GR_M09	The audience he is targeting is definitely adults, probably young adults, in the sense that it's a subject that's very much a concern for our generations and younger generations than his. He wouldn't say that he is trying to target a specific audience. / The truth is that he doesn't have a clear picture about the size of the audience. He perceives from the interviews and from the circulation of the newspapers, which is small, but especially from podcasts or other interventions in the public sphere, especially online, is that there is a great deal of engagement, that is, a large part of the public is concerned, engaged and anxious and worried about what will happen.
GR_M10	Faculty members, Researchers (all career stages), university students
GR_M11	The audience is the young people and the people who have an interest. They may not have studied science and technology, but they have an interest in it. And more broadly and people who have studied and just want to broaden their horizons. So, especially now, right now, we are also opening up to young Greek scientists. First of all, let them talk and I think, I think that by getting in touch with them, the new people will show you the ways in which communication has to be done when targeting

new people. There are no specific numbers on followers, but the sense is that there is still room to go further.

Table 6. Mediators' interactions with citizens

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' social interaction practices
GR_M01	Interaction is mostly based on social media, where they always respond to all questions posed. Direct interaction is made at the innovative science museum; interaction with the visitors is an integral part of the guided tours.
GR_M02	With regard the work in Science Museums: the presentations were by-design interactive. The visitors were not invited to just listen and read, but to actively discuss with everyone and, at the end, to comprehend what is the new knowledge that they have conquered.
GR_M03	An introductory session when all visitors ask any kind of questions. Then, as they perform the demonstration experiment the interviewee is in constant interaction with the visitors. At the end of the experiment the visitors are involved in a form of a debate, discussing what happened in the "laboratory." There are also questionnaires; roughly, a 10% of the visitors reply to these questionnaires. For the occupation at the Greek science museum there was only a questionnaire to be filled after the visit to the museum.
GR_M04	The rest of the activity is with public online or on-site lectures where the interaction is direct and immediate.
GR_M05	Public town hall meetings; scientific conferences; replies to commentators on his social media channels.
GR_M06	Public town hall meetings; replies to commentators on his social media channels
GR_M07	Public town hall meetings; replies to commentators on his social media channels
GR_M08	Discussions with lay people at the booth of academic libraries at the International Book Exhibition of Thessaloniki. Discussions with students from secondary education that visit academic libraries.
GR_M09	Public town hall meetings; scientific conferences; podcasts.
GR_M10	Through all member of her professional network, via internal discussion lists. Through direct interaction with the community of each university. There is a website where announcements of new services as well as interviews from our members so that we disseminate all useful information about academic libraries.

GR_M11	Replies to commentators on his articles on the website; replies to commentators on live podcasts and interviews.
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Table 7. Mediators' sources of information

Id.	Interpersonal networks		Science press releases					Other: (please add text)
	With researchers	With science communicators	Scientific literature	RPOs	Publishers	Mainstream media	Social media	
GR_M01								Direct interaction only with researchers from the interviewee's RPO.
GR_M02								
GR_M03								Direct interaction only with researchers from the interviewee's RPO.
GR_M04								
GR_M05								
GR_M06								
GR_M07								A proposal by his followers

GR_M08								Direct interaction with large international scientific publishing houses.
GR_M09								Lay people and organisations related to his field of research (trade unions etc.)
GR_M10								Direct interaction with large international scientific publishing houses and communication with members of academic libraries.
GR_M11								

2.3 Researchers

Table 8. Description of the Researcher interviews sample

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Position or title/Career stage**	Organisation type	Topic CV/CC#
GR_R01	M	Senior	Leading researcher	Private hospital	CV
GR_R02	F	Senior	Senior researcher	Currently at a Greek university and at a Nation-wide entity dealing with ethics of disruptive technologies	CV
GR_R03	-	-	-	-	CV
GR_R04	M	Senior	Associate Professor	Greek university	CC
GR_R05	M	Senior	Senior Researcher	Meteorological Institute	CC
GR_R06	F	Senior	Senior Researcher	Research institute - Atmospheric Physics	CC

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior ** ECR; recognised researcher; senior researcher; leading researcher (Professor)

Table 9. Researcher notes

Id.	Note
GR_R01	Medical Doctor, with specialty in Pathological Oncology of human lung. With the outbreak of COVID-19 the interviewee was called to put a halt to the majority of Phase I clinical trials he was conducting and start treating COVID-19 patients. The interviewee contributed to the study of the side effects of the Astra Zeneca vaccine.
GR_R02	Researcher on infectious diseases related to tuberculosis, related at a very basic research level with COVID-19 pandemic. Member of an advisory expert group (mainly from a moral bioethical point of view) that was established on COVID-19 from a nation-wide entity dealing with ethics of disruptive technologies and Bioethics.
GR_R03	-
GR_R04	Engineer working on how climate change affects the marine environment and its impacts on some basic parameters, like temperature change, wind pressure change, etc.
GR_R05	Physicist working on research of Climate Change and the issues that arise from it.
GR_R06	Researcher in Atmospheric Physics, with expertise in atmospheric pollution and climate change.

Table 10. How Researchers work with the public

Id.	Brief description of how the researchers' work reaches the public
GR_R01	Through centralized communication from the government.
GR_R02	The results of the advisory committee on COVID-19 were conveyed officially from the nation-wide entity through the entity's website. The themes were: (a) mandatory vaccinations for health professionals and (b) optimising of clinical trials in the pandemic period.
GR_R03	-
GR_R04	Through traditional publication channels (articles, publications, press releases) and through stakeholder engagement activities on research projects.
GR_R05	Through traditional channels and through the website and social media of his Institute (indirectly).
GR_R06	Through newspaper articles written in simple language and through visits at public schools

Table 6. Description of social integration practices of Researchers

Id.	Brief notes of Researchers' social integration practices
GR_R01	There was no mentioning on social integration practices.
GR_R02	Patient's organisations and patients' representatives have, in our days, entered dynamically, by participating at biomedical research and they are the link between patients and researchers.
GR_R03	-
GR_R04	Science communication activities and workshops through EU-funded projects, Science Festivals, plans to organize soon citizen science data collection activities.
GR_R05	Through data collection activities (observation of weather stations installed on citizens houses) and through workshops that take place in the context of research projects or through some public events organized by the Institute.
GR_R06	Through newspaper articles written in simple language and through visits at public schools. In some cases, through public events for the general public, where journalists are also invited.

3 Analysis of Mediator interviews

3.1 Chains of mediation

GR-M01 creates content for communication to the wider scientific community. She uses Facebook, twitter, Instagram, and YouTube in the case of the interviewee's work in an RPO. In the cases of questions from these media she always responds. Communication is done towards academic institutions rather than the general public. For the interaction in the context of the innovative museum, interaction is done on a constant basis during the visits since the tour to the museum is by-design interactive. The general public is not categorized in any sub-groups whatsoever, with the exception of students from public education, primary and secondary. The communication should be done with the use of plain language, without technical jargon. Of course, these must be accompanied by a communication platform of any kind - to provide to lay people the chance to express their opinions.

Her creative process is based on art and by combining different research fields, i.e. computer science and humanities; this is something that is appealing to the general public. Also, by giving examples on how research can affect the life of society.

She defines success in describing adequately to lay people how research is being conducted - the methodology of research and not necessarily in communicating success stories, since the biggest part of research is a story of failure. This can increase trust in research, since failures can be put into the framework of what research is, and not act as an indication of bad research. Its main sources come from the research that is conducted in the RPO where she works.

GR-M02's networks are universities, schools, i.e. institutions that provide education, in general. Lay people really want to participate. The model of the scientists that does one-way communication no longer exists.

"Because when people enter a collective process, where they feel that their words count, that they can articulate questions, articulate arguments and feel that they themselves are the protagonist, somehow they will do it and they will do it automatically".

In a sense we do not need "lecturers" but people that facilitate discussions upon specific or non-specific questions. Attendees do not have to be convinced; they have to be made to develop a critical view of the core concepts of the discussion. We have to cultivate the tool of critical reflection.

The creative process is based on the concept that, e.g. it is not interesting to just speak about Newton; it is interesting to speak why we speak about Newton (based on Socrates' concept of aporetic dialogues). Then, the conclusions of a discussion are being articulated by the attendees, not by GR-M02. He finds an interesting story to tell; then he finds who are the "heroes" of the story. Then he involves the participants to the story, something like participating at a role-playing game, always with a bit of humour. His sources are always academic - peer reviewed publications or books.

GR-M03 is designing experiments for science communication for lay people at a foreign RPO. At the Greek science museum, she designed events for science communication to lay people.

The creative process at the Greek science museum is to design events that have a "flavour" of the season. For example, there was one communication activity called "frozen experiments" that was in tune with the winter period that this was released. When asked about her main sources she stated:

"We communicate with people that work in the relevant department of the entity; this is our resource. For the Greek science museum, the sources were mainly scientific articles".

GR-M04 mainly interacts with his fellow researchers and their scientific work. He uses the existing scientific literature and the latest press releases of well-known national and international RPOs. He also takes inspiration from current events relevant to his scientific field or to the general scientific and social agenda. He describes his creative process as follows:

"An interest in dealing with a particular topic emerges and I search for relevant literature reconstructing the literature review, focusing on main issues. Research objects are highlighted, and this work proceeds with the corresponding incorporation of conclusions and in an effort in terms of popularization with an eye to the audience in which each product I produce is of interest..."

He addresses his audience mainly through articles in newspapers, websites and scientific or political blogs, as well as at some public activities, like scientific or political forums. He measures success with the impact his work has and the discussions and debates it provokes.

GR-M05's interpersonal network contains both researchers and fellow science communicators. He also uses scientific literature and renowned scientific magazines to be up to date with the latest outputs of the scientific community. Finally, he also monitors current issues, mainly through social media platforms. His main task is to create video of science-related content for its social media channels, where he refutes pseudo-scientific claims and reveals scientific fraud cases. GR_M05 is looking to spot something

suspicious through the aforementioned channels and then tries to check if the "suspect's" claims are false by looking at the existing scientific literature and official statistics on the subject. A great variety of social media channels, podcasts and websites are the main ways in which he communicates with its audience, while he also participates in some public science forums and debates. He declares:

"Successful for me are the cases where a person who takes advantage of a vulnerable patient to sell a (controversial) drug ends up with some kind of legal consequences, imprisonment or a fine".

GR-M06's main sources of information derive from the existing literature, as well as press releases from both publishers and RPOs in his scientific field (History and Archaeology). GR_M06 chooses subjects that either he believes should reach the general public, or subjects that he thinks might be of interest to them, even if those latter themes seem a little bit trivial to his peers. His main communication channels consist of almost every social media platform and ways to interact through those platforms. He also maintains a website and publishes best-selling popularized books regarding his scientific field. He considers his work successful when he gains the attention of people who thought that they were not interested in History and Archaeology.

GR-M07 also has a rich network with other scientific communicators and takes inspiration from scientific literature and renowned scientific magazines. He uses social media and might take ideas from his followers for the theme of his next videos. Otherwise, he comes up with an idea and then he checks what is written or displayed internationally about it. If he is pleased with what he has found, he starts to study meticulously the subject to acquire an adequate knowledge of it. After the script is written and carefully reviewed, then the video production begins. He mentioned using YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, Facebook and his own website, in order to interact with his audience, as well as some public meetings and forums. Success for him is to be able to define your own the content of your work and to collaborate with people you appreciate.

GR-M08 & GR_M10's professional network is mainly students at Greek universities, faculty members, their peers and secondarily lay people. Main channels of communication are the network's website, human networks - communities of practice, and conferences. They also are active in professional discussion groups, through which they exchange best practices. They use social media accounts, but not yet consistently. Through visits from students from the secondary education to the network's premises they provide information about what they do. According to both success is defined as the acknowledgement that a student or a researcher was served.

GR-M09's network is composed of both researchers and mediators. He heavily uses the scientific literature and press releases of reliable publishers and RPOs to write his articles. Scientific articles he

might read in newspapers are also a source of inspiration. He also uses a network of lay people and organizations related to his field of research (activists, trade unions etc.). The theme he chooses relies on his social and political ideas, but when he begins to write he tries to distance himself from them and face the issue with clarity and sobriety. Then, he starts to organize its plan. He authors popularized articles which are published on newspapers, websites and blogs, while he has also featured in science communication podcasts. He defines success by the social impact of his work and also by his own words:

“So success for me is to break this duality, (technophobia-technophilia) that is to put the place of technology in a... - both to protect technologies from possible limitations that a technophobic perception of what will happen if our machines take our jobs can impose- and to protect technology from a technophilic perception that doesn't see the risks”.

Finally, **GR-M11's** network consists of both researchers and science mediators. It uses scientific literature, all kinds of reliable press releases and newspaper articles. He describes his creative process as hard mental work, to achieve a very important goal: to popularize the outputs of his science to the general public. Apart from the website, where he is member of the editing team, he writes articles of popularized science on newspapers and features in some podcasts. He declares that he will consider his work on science communication successful if that will attract many young people and will help younger mediators and researchers to emerge from it.

3.2 About research ethics and integrity (REI)

Since most of the Greek mediators - either by writing articles or publishing videos - are creating popularized scientific content, they indirectly mentioned REI issues in the process of creating the aforementioned content, mostly when questioned about the ways they evaluate their sources. However, there were no direct mentions of this terminology prior to the hinge question.

All but one Mediator (GR-M04) seemed to understand Ethics and Integrity inseparable when trying to define it, while everyone connected it with the way research is conducted, rather than the riskiness and dangerousness of its products, maybe with the exception of GR-M09 who mentioned the input of research:

“it is obligatory for every project you do to submit a proposal to the respective ethics committee before you do it, to evaluate whether the sociological research you are doing has an input. Not only the methodology you are going to use”.

In order to define REI, some focused on the concept of transparency (GR_M01) some on the lack of biases while performing research (GR-M05, GR-M06), others focused on its reproducibility (GR-M04, GR-M07),

other referred to avoiding plagiarism, following IPR rules and, in general agreeing on a general set of incentives (GR_M02), while GR_03 and GR_M10 mentioned the independence economic or personal interests. GR_M08 mentioned the representation of women in research and be very aware of the responsibilities to the society. GR_M09 mentioned the representativeness of the sample someone is using while conducting scientific research (GR-M09). GR-M11 linked REI and its violation with issues such as competition for publications that hinders the production of quality scientific work, predator journals that are largely the responsibility of large scientific publishers, and cases of conflicts of interest, stressing that it is not easy by any means for a researcher to have integrity with the current situation at the scientific community.

All mediators seem to pay particular attention to the way they evaluate their sources of information. They claim to check the peer-review process of the articles they use (GR-M04, GR-M09, GR-M11), the reliability of the sources of an article they are going to use (GR_M02, GR_03, GR-M05, GR-M09), the credibility of the scientific journals they use (GR_02, GR_M03, GR-M06, GR-M07, GR-M09). GR-M04 describes his evaluation process as follows:

"The evaluation is done firstly indirectly through the fact that they have gone through a peer review process etc. And secondly, to the extent that they are in subjects in which I have a relative competence, I can also have a relative judgment. The second is in relevant material with which I come into contact through my network of associates, either at the university or former professional associates, with whatever credibility they can offer to the material proposed by them, with positive or negative connotations. And the third one, on the websites that I mostly trust, is a matter of whether they have proper citations to reliable sources or whether the very writing of their writers is trustworthy".

Moreover, GRM-05, GR-M06 and GR-M11 emphatically stated that they view their work among others as a way to restrict, or even expose cases of REI breaches (this is the very nature of GR-M06's work).

GR_03 remembered describing to their audience the exciting results of room temperature superconductivity that proved to be the result of scientific fraud. Also, GR_M03 referred to the fact that what working at the Greek science museum the group of communicators were disagreeing about the vaccination strategy and climate change; this resulted to not including related themes to the activities of the museum.

GR-M06 whose work is directly dedicated to that cause shares an experience about the COVID-19 pandemic:

"It was certainly an analysis I did of a Greek pension doctor who, during the pandemic, was selling and giving people instructions to take methotrexate, for... to cure the side

effects of the Covid 19 vaccines. Methotrexate, if you don't know, is an anti-cancer drug with very serious side effects. You don't take it like that. It can cause you harm. Doctors give it to cancer patients but under very strict instructions. And this man was going on Facebook as a doctor giving methotrexate to cure the side effects of the Covid vaccines”.

GR-M07 has also produced some interesting and extensive material about Climate Change.

The answers given to this topic reflect the general situation regarding REI issues in Greece, where the introduction of common good practices in conducting research is somewhat behind in comparison with Western Europe and North America. This does not mean that the mediators interviewed are indifferent about ethics and deontology in research and the way they are communicating science. They are very much interested and very cautious about it, however they are more familiar with an ad hoc approach to resolving REI issues, taking into account the lack of standardized procedures. In addition, they have developed an ethos that has been the result of their personal study and interests; as a result they are guided more by their intuition and less by a shared knowledge on how to deal with REI issues. Interaction in the context of HORIZON projects helps greatly to improve their perspective on those features. As GR-M09 recalls he was impressed from a collaboration with a Western European RPO: “It defined the questions, the groups, the people very clearly and then we collectively made the people who would participate in the project a discussion where with criticism and feedback and so on, we formed the ethics of the practice itself, ()... the good practice itself which should be followed in the end in order to come out with a proper research... And through discussions and experience from colleagues I have formulated a standard procedure, a standardisation that I am glad to see is the same as the one that you experts follow”.

ID here	Additional quotes
GR_M02	There is a complex social context, so when you confront the citizen that science is not the absolute truth, but it is the best route you have to the truth and is open to constant questioning, constant revision, then that automatically makes it science. In my opinion at least more valid than saying it is the truth.
GR_M03	We were a team of Physicists, Biologists, and Chemists; we did not agree on whether vaccines were good or if climate change was real. There was a very intense discussion among us. This is why we did not organize any workshop on these issues. However, questions about COVID-19 were always brought from our audience, tot so much

about climate change. In these cases we had to respond to these questions quite diplomatically.

3.3 About public trust in science

All mediators were familiar with the concept of public trust in science and comfortable to talk about it. They also consider their work as an effort to contribute to maintaining, building or raising this trust; GR-M07 noted that:

"I certainly think they are important (the issues of public trust in his work). I mean, as a science communicator, I can understand that I bear quite a big responsibility in this part, to communicate this whole thing correctly and not to create false impressions, nor to distort reality to the public that follows us and trusts us, right? Because for better or worse there is a huge amount of trust. Which one might say we've earned as communicators of science, but I don't know if it is, if it's responsive, if it's fully responsive to reality. In any case, I certainly think they are important. So, I think they are something that one should keep in mind when one is active in this field",

while GR-M11 states:

"That's the primary goal, that's the primary goal (to build public confidence in science). And also, to ask questions about where science is, where science is going, how it should go, etc."

GR_M11 adds another dimension that was brought about also by other five mediators (GR_01, GR_M02, GR_M03, GR-M04, and GR-M09), which has to do with providing their audience with a critical view not of science *per se*, but of how it is conducted and how its outputs are used. For example, GR-M04 stresses:

"So, from this point of view, I think the crucial thing is to form a sense and a criterion of scientific rationality that takes into account that science as a social enterprise does not develop in a vacuum, so it must be subject to critical examination".

GR_M02 brought the perspective of science communication as a balancing activity

"Science communication has a prominent effect on how societies perceive sciences. Unfortunately, mass media have a much stronger effect than universities. When science communication is being done in a purely journalistic style, not in a scientific style - science is being demonized or deified."

Moreover, most of the mediators see their work as a medium to fight pseudo-science and theories that damage what public considers to be science. GR-M06, an archaeologist, for example says:

"...because for several years, at least in Greece, science remained outside the broader public domain and the field was infested with pseudo-scientific approaches for extraterrestrials etc. For running around too much fake... what we popularly call "sprayed things"¹. Now I don't know how to render that in English. And slowly now my own science and other science is now starting to come to the forefront and speak to the general public. Because we now realize that the purpose of science is to reach the final recipient, which is the general public. Because we do science for all of us. We cannot remain indifferent and indifferent to the fact that the public has wrong perceptions and creates wrong impressions of our science".

All mediators expressed their deep concerns about the impact news of scientific fraud or malpractices have on public trust in science. GR-M09 and GR-M11 in particular consider things to be extremely dangerous, to create the basis for the development of pseudo-science and conspiracy theories and to have deep routes inside the context that science is conducted. GR-M09 characteristically stated:

"I think that when you go into the public sphere it becomes very dangerous because it becomes toxic and it becomes dangerous because it mainly creates... isolates, creates bubbles. That is, it leaves the doubters in a bubble alone and then that bubble, as we know, inflates, gets its own networks, goes to social media and gets its own forms of post-truth".

Others, such as GR-M05, GR-M06 and GR-M07 were more troubled about the impacts of bad practices in communicating science. GR-M05 argued:

"A person who both doesn't follow the scientific news and doesn't have a good grasp of how to follow the scientific data on the issue, trying to communicate it in this way does much more damage and we've seen it with misrepresentation of studies multiple times. With doctors coming on news shows who were basically winking at... the anti-vaccine movement. Yeah, this caused a huge problem".

GR-M04 on the other hand offered an additional dimension by stating that malpractices distract the attention from a more essential and constructive critique to the wider social context that the scientific research is conducted.

An interesting perspective related to research misconduct was brought by GR_M02:

¹ A Greek popular jargon term for conspiracy theorists. It comes from one - completely unfounded claim - that supports that the exhaust gases of an aeroplane in flight, usually visible from the ground like white smoke, are actually chemical substances that make people more compliant to the machinations of governments.

"Science communication plays an important role and it is equally important to have a decent education system. We have to say that science has these norms and the one who did not comply breaks a social contract - so the question on misconduct is deeply political; it has to do with how you receive yourself as member of a society."

GR_M03 mentioned:

"Trust in science can be built is to communicate the exact role of a researcher, how a researcher has come to a point to do cutting-edge research, what were her studies, how she collaborates with other researchers. And the other part is transparency, in terms of the resources devoted to a specific study. Why this study is being funded."

All mediators believe that those malpractices affect their work, either directly (GR-M04, GR-M05, GR-M09) or indirectly (GR-M06, FR-M07), or as a factor that moves them and motivates them (GR-M11).

Regarding their recommendations for improving public trust in science, below there is a list per mediator:

GR_M01 uses simple language, no technical jargon, that explains the scientific method, and how science can affect everyday life; Be transparent and put the term "certainty" into the correct context. This is explicated by the following quote:

"When science communication is done properly the audience leaves more concerned and more relaxed, at the same time. For, example after a seminar on Didactics of Physics to secondary education teachers, we had concerns from them that it seems not to be any kind of certainty from science and how this could be conveyed to their students. This is where we had to explain in more detail what certainty might mean and how progress is made to sciences."

A similar approach was made by **GR-M02**. This mediator suggested that

"We have to reveal the shortcomings of science, as not the bearer of the absolute truth, without running the risk of been accused of relativism. But you need delicate narratives, in order not to run the risk of letting people think whatever they think for science. The answer is social consent. Even if you communicate Physics the tools provided by social sciences and anthropology are valuable."

Also, researchers have to get rid of the

"teacher's mentality, who has to know everything. We do not know everything and this has to be communicated."

As for the younger generations, this mediator believes that communication via social media need to be very concise and be able to provide additional audiovisual content.

GR_M03 declares that in cases of research misconduct the communication has to focus on why such things happen. Also, the age of people has to be taken very seriously. More specifically, it was said the following:

“Younger people are usually more open-minded; the discussions are more open. Older people come with more established ideas and make arguments to support them. The issue of religion also comes from such ages. Younger people are more focused on the concept of an experiment, without delving into the repercussions of what the experiment brings about.”

GR-M04 suggests that it takes various interventions in the whole chain of production of scientific knowledge and the way the public understands it. For him those actions go beyond the limits of the scientific project itself, even beyond the limits of the educational process. It concerns a more general concept of developing a critical attitude towards the social process as a whole. As for the younger generations he believes that because of the general social and political context, the way of understanding the scientific knowledge worsens since there is a shift towards those methodological traits that question the possibility of rationality and objective acquisition of knowledge. So, the development of critical view is essential but not enough according to him. We need to

“complement this process with a framework for the development of a social activity that will encourage the consideration of the motives of those cases that are potentially problematic for the development of science and that raise the greatest doubts about the credibility of the scientific project”.

GR-M05 calls for the improvement of science communication through wider collaboration of RPOs with science communicators and the education of relative journalists in scientific issues. He also calls for citizen science programs to educate the public on the way science is conducted and for transparency in the scientific process. Especially for younger generations he advocates for a better educational system in schools condemning the current one, and since he observes that it is difficult to gain the attention of younger people, he suggests earning it with “teasers” just like he does in his own videos, and by persuading them that science provides better quality to their own lives.

GR-M06 suggests a more massive and targeted science communication effort by both Institutions and Universities, while also trying to “tackle” the elitism that characterizes part of the scientific community. The latter needs to open up to the public and try to explain to them in a simple way the complicated nature of the scientific process step by step. Social media is a great medium to achieve that particularly to the younger generations according to him.

GR-M07 also focuses on the improvement of science communication especially in Greece, where barring some individuals' efforts, the few Institutions that were created seem inadequate. He recognizes however that science communication has its limits; trust in Institutions is needed and is difficult to gain this trust in Greece. The children need to be more in contact with research Institutions and the way research is carried out. He also sees social media as a great asset to gain younger generations, while he believes that we need to adapt to their "codes" and "language" in order to communicate with them more efficiently.

GR-M08 calls for transparency in research and for a communication strategy implemented by experts in order to attract younger people:

"A better visibility of cases of research misconduct would do good, in the long run. You definitely need a strategy to address young people through social media, in order to foster interest, e.g. by creating podcasts with students and professors. For this you need people with knowledge about these means of communication".

GR-M09 also highlights the need for improvement of science communication, particularly in the sense that a dialogue between scientists and society must be opened. The former need to hear the needs and wants of the latter and to approach them with sobriety and simplicity. This requires better education from both sides, but modern societies are able to provide them with this. More specifically in approaching the younger generations, he sees very positively efforts of individuals like influencers and YouTubers (such the ones we also interviewed) and thinks that they have livened up young people's interest in science.

GR-M10 on the contrary focused more on Open Science and on the role of institutions to enhance it:

"We need to change the attitude of institutions to adopt more deeply open science, by boosting social media campaigns, where facts will be explained with a scientific but simple - sometimes humoristic - language".

GR-M11 almost immediately turned his attention to younger generations. He calls for massive reforms at the schools and universities educational programs. He also stresses that the scientists must visit and give lectures at schools, the various research programs need to be made to give such lectures as a prerequisite in order to receive funds. He also advocates for a dialogue between science and society with the latter in charge of the final decision (he mentions the historical paradigm of the Athenian Democracy).

GR_M02	The preacher, the priest in this case, always knows. Why; Yes, because it is a transcendental doctrine. Such is
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precisely what emerges from revelation. But when we talk about something which It is a social practice, no one can know better than anyone else and certainly no one can know everything in every situation.
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3.4 Other themes

GR_M10 mentioned that a good example is how academic libraries dealt with the pandemic situation. It was an emergency situation, for which libraries did not have an emergency plan. Despite the fact that libraries were closed for a long time there were always colleagues who were keeping all services functional. This was acknowledged by researchers, since the access to publications was not affected by the lockdowns. This was brought about as an example where communication of academic findings was not hampered, despite the extremely difficult situation of the social distancing measures.

3.5 Synthesis of recommendations

The vast majority of mediators focused on the improvement of science communication methods both on the general population and the younger people as well. These improvements are mainly aimed at institutions and the role they have to play to improve the quality of communicating science, whether this concerns the State, major RPOs such as Universities, etc.

Institutions also play an important role on the call of many researchers for educational reforms, in order to improve the qualities of the "receivers" of communicational efforts. Since calls for educational reforms go usually hand in hand with science communication improvements, we can safely assume that this role is given to the public most of the times in those arguments, which are based on the hypothesis that we need to improve the qualities of both the transmitters and the receivers of the messages.

However, the public does not have a passive role to play in this process, according to most of the mediators. Some call for more Open Science actions and some other call for a wider dialogue with society concerning scientific conduction, its outputs and its implementations. While the latter definitely has many wider implications, it also implies to practices of social integration not only to the way that science is conducted but also to the use of its products.

GR-M04 for example emphasizes not only in the ability of the social subject to acquire knowledge but also to their ability to change the wider social context through collective efforts and actions. This process is essential for him to improve not only public trust in science, but also to understand its real nature and purpose.

The way the public understands and defines science is also a key issue for many mediators. According to them, people tend to look for “absolute truths” in science while this is not its real nature. A part of the aforementioned educational reform actions is to make the public understand that uncertainty is part of the way research and science in general is conducted.

Three mediators called for transparency of research as a way to enhance public trust. This was seen either as part of the communication improvement efforts or by itself.

The use of simplified and popularised language in communicating science is also highlighted by many mediators, especially when talking about the younger generation of people. Concerning raising trust in science in them, social media play a vital role according to almost every mediator, whether this will be through institutional actions or through individual efforts such as private social media channels. The aforementioned educational reforms that many mediators recommended also have them as their main targets.

Recommendation 1
Institutional actions are needed to improve science communication.
Recommendation 2
Public or other institutional educational reforms targeting both the general public and the younger generations in particular are needed.
Recommendation 3
A responsible use of social media is essential in communicating science by public or research institutions and by individuals, targeting mainly -but not only- younger people.
Recommendation 4
A wider dialogue between science and society regarding the conduct of research and the use of its outputs. Some mentioned basically informative and science integration events, others expressed the opinion that the public must have a say on the way the science outputs are used.
Recommendation 5
More transparency in conducting research. This is meant to be used both on communicating and on conducting science as well.

4 Analysis of Researcher interviews

4.1 Researcher contexts: Covid-19 and Climate Change

4.1.1 Covid-19

GR-R01 during COVID-19 outbreak, was working in a British hospital on Phase I clinical trials on lung cancer. At that time, he had started running his own research protocol at the University of Tokyo, regarding the phenotype of human immune cells, in lung cancer in different phases of treatment and in different types of lung cancer. Currently, he is leading the section of Pathological Oncology in a Greek private hospital. During COVID-19 pandemic he started treating COVID-19 patients. The interviewee contributed to the study of the side effects of the Astra Zeneca vaccine.

GR-R02 was member of an advisory expert group that was established on COVID-19 from a nation-wide entity that provides advice on Bioethics and ethical aspects of disruptive technologies. The advice aims purely at policy makers of the highest national level, i.e. to members of the Greek government and the Greek parliament. The main topics addressed was on whether the vaccination of health workers would be obligatory and on the betterment of the planning of clinical trials on COVID-19. GR-R02 participates at communication activities in the form of lectures/seminars targeting students of the secondary education. There was no explicit mentioning that the public debate and controversy had an impact of GR-R02's work; an indication for this was that GR-R02 mentioned that, while it was part of the public debate, prioritisation of patients for treatment was not part of its work.

4.1.2 Climate Change

GR-R04 is an Associate Professor at a Greek public University. He is an Engineer working on how climate change affects the marine environment and its impacts on some basic parameters, like temperature change, wind pressure changes etc. Furthermore, he studies the effect on structures built in the coastal zone, either ports or activities that are developed in the coastal zone and how we can adapt to climate change and its effects on the coastal zone. He also participates on European research programs related to his work that demand stakeholders' involvement. He faced some controversy when a press release of his work on possibilities of a Tsunami in the Mediterranean Sea was disseminated poorly by journalists at websites and social media.

GR-R05 is a Senior Researcher (physicist) at one of the most prestigious Greek Meteorological Institutes. His work involves both direct and indirect ways of approaching the issue, directly on research of topics related to climate change, indirectly on explaining whether a particular weather phenomenon is associated (or

not) with climate change. This latter aspect, and the fact that the conversation is revolved more around it over the past few years, is where GR-R05 identifies how the controversy around climate change affects his work.

GR-R06 is working at a prestigious research institute on Atmospheric Physics, on atmospheric pollution and climate change. The head of the laboratory where GR-R06 is employed is a world-class researcher on Atmospheric Physics, most specifically, on Ozone layer depletion. This laboratory, in the context of the communication activities of the umbrella research institute, participates in public events for lay people and visits at public schools. The public debate on climate change has not affected the way GR-R06 communicates its work and the results from its work.

4.2 About science communication and public attitudes

4.2.1 Covid-19

The communication of **GR-R01's** research output on measures about COVID-19 was centrally coordinated by the state. The information provided was well-structured in the sense that all existing data and gaps in knowledge were communicated.

GR-R02's research results were conveyed via the official communication channels of the national committee, mainly the entity's website. These releases were further disseminated by other websites and newspapers. Provided that further dissemination is done without interpretation of the collective opinion of the national committee, then no issues arise. Communication is also done via special sessions targeting members of the Greek parliament - with positive feedback (however this is a very special and small target audience).

4.2.2 Climate Change

GR-R04's work is mainly presented via science articles and press releases of these articles, through the European research programs he participates and their dissemination channels, as well as through public forums such as Science Festivals and Researcher Nights. He is very cautious about the presentation of his work on social media and from journalists and third parties in general that do not have a direct relation with his scientific field and prefers dissemination and communication channels that are more or less directly controlled by him or his research associates:

"If you do this in an organized way to an audience that's in the context of a stakeholders meeting or a training etc., there you can build the context and say I'm going to tell you about these five things, so we can understand them".

This cautiousness is probably also explained by his aforementioned experience (sect. 4.1) on the poor misinterpretation of his article about the possibilities of a Tsunami in the Mediterranean Sea:

"something that is done widely and very generally to a general audience and can be picked up by anyone. That was our problem and then, in the case I was telling you about with the Tsunami is that any outlet, any journalist can interpret it any way they want and twist it any way they want".

Although he does not directly mention any feelings about the incident his disappointment was clear, and he seems to recognise these misinterpretations of science articles by the Mass Media as the main reason for causing public controversy that affects his work. However, his view is that you can't put all the blame to dissemination and communication channels. The scientific community and the general education of the public also play their parts:

"Of course, the responsibility is always on both sides, that is, to a certain extent, the scientific community was either not as involved or not as interested or didn't know how to convey what was happening so well. That is, because it is very difficult for a particular, for a particular scientific work to popularize it to society... on the other hand there is a key part of how educated the public or the audience is on these issues".

GR-R05's main dissemination channels include traditional publication channels such as articles, publications, press releases, as well as stakeholder engagement activities (workshops, Town Hall meetings) on research projects. However, his work is also becoming known through the Social Media channels of the Institute he works at, which gain much attendance in cases of extreme weather conditions. On such cases he might also be called on Mass Media for weather forecasting.

He seems quite content with the way his work is usually presented to the public, but like GR-R04 is also expressing his discomfort about the exaggerations that some journalists and social media influencers intentionally or unintentionally use in order to gain attention. This could lead to the distortion of his work:

"But beyond that, I see that some people who straddle the line between republishing articles and trying to influence -that is, you can say that one goes to an influencer (rather to a journalist)- I see that in some cases there is a quite strong tendency for exaggeration, for distortion in order to get... extra clicks. And something else, which is unfortunately true, is that sometimes this is also done unintentionally, in the sense that not knowing terminology, science, not being familiar with it, they fall into slips and mistranslate what we might write on a website, on a social media site. So that's where it starts to get a little out of hand. And that's really where there can be distortion and where we can really get to levels of ridiculousness about how certain things are recorded".

The conversation and the impact of climate change has some positive aspects on GR-R05's work in the sense that more people in comparison

to the past is interested in it. Furthermore, it gets the people more alerted on extreme weather conditions that may decisively impact their lives and they may take more measures in order to protect themselves. On the other hand -and in relation to the aforementioned exaggeration by some of the Media- controversy may cause a series of negative effects. In his own words:

"the negative ones have to do mainly with the distorted and wrong absorption of information. It may lead to ημιμάθεια (a Greek word that negatively describes a person who is half-educated on a subject, but most of the times is not aware of that and thinks he is fully familiar with it - sciolism), it may lead to exaggeration, to negativity, it may lead to anything. It can lead which we see it every day not only in our own section and to the creation of myths, conspiracy theories, whatever. And unfortunately, I see, in some people I notice that there is exactly a negativism and a reduction of trust and a reduction of trust in the scientific community, precisely because in this context of the over-dissemination of information from various channels uncontrolled, a feeling is created in some people that "we are all being fooled," so to speak".

GR-R06's research work is mainly communicated through newspaper articles written in simple language for the general public and through visits at public schools. Additionally, with less traditional channels, like social media such as Facebook and Instagram. Those are also used to promote the public events for the general public she also participates, where journalists are also invited.

She appears generally pleased with the way her work is presented to the public, noting that sometimes some mediators might highlight something less important according to her own view, in favour of something that might impress the people more:

"Possibly a journalist might choose a sentence that is more spicy and more interesting and give it a priority or possibly give priority to something that is less important in my opinion in an interview than something else, just because it might be a little bit more catchy. It's not exactly a distortion of what has been said, but it may be a shift in the focus of what is said to some things that in the opinion of the journalist are perhaps more important than other things that have been said either by me or by a representative in the research centre in which I work".

GR-R06 also stresses that while the conversation -when conducted in proper ways- about climate change may prove to be beneficial, but this does not apply to disputes or controversies which are mostly biased and may confuse the public:

"Now look; Conversations are generally good. It's good to hear different opinions. Controversy is not so good. I don't know the controversy shows a rivalry sometimes that can be unsettling

to people. I think in general when there is a debate it shows who is the one who has arguments and supports what they are saying and who basically sometimes wants something to be said because they have basically formed it in their mind without being able to prove it and justify it. I am all for these debates and I think they are good”.

A difference noted between COVID-19 and climate change researchers is that the latter seem to use personal communication channels more than the former (especially GR-R04 and GR-R06). This could be explained to a certain extent from the fact that especially during the pandemic the COVID-19 communication channels were more centrally controlled in general. A common ground on the other hand is that most of the researchers are cautious regarding communication channels that are not directly controlled by them or the scientific community in general, whether they use those channels or not.

4.3 About the integration of citizens in research

All researchers are aware about citizens involvement in research and are generally in favour of such actions. They believe that it is exceptionally useful in cases where a certain group of citizens, which participates in the research might directly benefit from its findings. They also observe a rise of citizens participation over the recent years; according to GR_R02 this is influenced by the fact that patients' organisations have entered the biomedical field quite dynamically. They have played a significant role for the participation of patients in research projects and to sharing information about research projects. According to GR-R04 could also be explained from the fact that the Horizon projects that many researchers participate demand such actions.

According to GR_R02, public participation is clearly positive and very important; for technologies like AI public's opinions (citizens or citizen's organisations) must be taken into account. This will help so as the results of such technologies will be used in a socially accepted way. Patient's needs have to inform the course - the design of a research project, especially when it is translational research and when it has to do with open issues of Bioethics.

GR_R02 does science communication, for practical reasons, mainly online. Sometimes she visits schools or schools pay a visit to the premises; in the latter case she asks from teachers to introduce the aims of such visits to their students prior to the visit. GR_R04

GR-R04 and GR-R05 however, identify that the researcher needs to set some boundaries and to lay out very meticulously the framework of citizens participation in order to secure the quality of his research. As the latter characteristically states:

“In my opinion, yes, the citizen should be allowed to participate in research, but we just have to be very careful

how we use his contribution, because he has neither the experience nor the knowledge to distinguish the right information -he may not do it on purpose- but he may not be able to distinguish the right information from the wrong information”.

Citizens are involved mostly in the data collection phase of researchers work. Either by installing systems and stations on their properties that measure the weather conditions and the solar radiation in the cases of GR-R05 and GR-R06, or by taking photos of the coastal lines in order for GR-R04 and his colleagues to observe their evolution through the seasons. They all also participate in workshops and public events to inform the people of the progress of their research and get feedback, especially from citizen groups that are more or less affected by it. Those are practices that are essential in all of the researchers work, especially in the case of GR-R05.

These are also the methods that the researchers identify as most appropriate. GR-R05 stresses that in his scientific field, this is the maximum that they can gain or demand from citizens participation while GR-R04 notices that citizen science is proving to be more fruitful and gains more recognition when certain stakeholders groups see that their participation has a direct impact on them:

“if he sees on a second level that what he does, that the time he spends has some impact, has some effect. Someone who participates in a project as a stakeholder, a fisherman or a farmer or a tourist, a hotelier in an area, if they see that by participating there, it led somewhere. He said his opinion, it got through somehow and got somewhere, it was heard anyway it was tried to be promoted then even more so he will want to get involved because he will see that it is worthwhile”.

The main obstacles identified to enhance the citizens participation in science included the following: GR-R01 referred to the lack of appropriate structures that support and integrate patients in research protocols. There are specific hospitals, but a lack of a network of such entities. GR-R02 mentioned the behaviour of researchers, which sometimes do not find useful to listen to citizen’s or even patient’s opinions, especially for research projects that are more related to fundamental research. Another obstacle, again according to GR-R02, is that collaborative research that integrates citizens needs more resources that research that does not take into account citizen’s opinions. Also, citizens themselves are not so well informed about the usefulness of their involvement in research projects. Other obstacles are the lack of education and expertise on behalf of the public (GR-R04, GR-R05, GR-R06), the precarious nature of the voluntarily work (GR-R04, GR-R05, GR-R06) and the lack of funds that according to the GR-R05 could help solve some of the aspects of the previous two:

“So I think that overall the problem of increasing citizen participation in science is very directly related to the

existence of both the intention and the funds to create the appropriate procedures, because it's not something that you can just take someone and say you're going to do this. You have to train them, you have to give them a fee, you have to give them... It might take some travels; it takes funds anyway. So, I think that's where it usually comes down to...".

4.4 About public trust in science

All the researchers reported citizen concerns about science as part of their experience, however this does not seem to be a prevalent aspect in their work. GR-R01 interpret this as reflecting the problems public health system faces in Greece and the approach some doctors have with their patients. According to his words this lack of trust "*is part of the emotional logic of Greek people*". According to GR_R02 the lack of trust to science reflects the lack of trust to the system in general. She puts the low rate of organ donation in Greece, as a benchmark.

GR-R04 and GR-R05 justified some of those concerns, mainly due to lack of expertise on behalf of the majority of the general public. Their reported concerns included the confusion of citizens regarding science communication and its outputs, as well as suspicions about conflicts of interest and corruption. In general, they were hesitant to explain those concerns rather than report specific ones.

GR-R05 seems the most concerned of them regarding the potential threats on of a massive decline of citizens trust in science:

"It takes years to build trust and a minute to tear it down. So, when somebody comes out and either intentionally or unintentionally, or by mistake, says something that doesn't stand up right, automatically the trust is shattered. So yes, there is a serious issue about how information is being handled by the media, by the social media and so on, which have a serious responsibility because they just have to increase their penetration, they have to increase clicks, they have to increase their television... as they call it, their viewership. But sometimes members of the scientific community also play the media game for their own agendas, which I don't know, and even if I did, I wouldn't want to analyse them".

Not only GR-R05 but all of the researchers seem to identify the way science is communicated - both by mediators, or directly by the scientific community- as the main reason for the fall of public trust. They seem to identify some aspects on the way science is conducted and about its impact and products, but they clearly prioritize the communication factor. As GR-R06 also notes:

"I think it's probably how it's communicated to them, because I think the other one (the conduct of science) they can't know, and they can't have a very clear opinion. But how it's

communicated to them and how articulately and documented and substantiated. I think that's what's troubling them".

Regarding public concerns about the way science is conducted, GR-R02 mentioned that citizens are interested in seeing the results of research been applied to everyday life or clinical practice and be benefitted from them. According to her words: "*Citizens' guide to research assessment is the usefulness of the practical results.*" GR-R04 and GR-R06 highlighted the very nature of science and research, which by itself contains a certain level of uncertainty, and sometimes even conflicting views and opinions between scientists. This seems to destabilize peoples trust who mainly want clear and certain answers to their problems. GR-R04 characteristically stresses:

"This will create a confusion, so to speak, in the sense that if there is something, if some people, if they present two views, which was very frequent at the time and with climate change, of course it's done by scientists, but with Covid it was even more so. If some people say something contradictory, whose view is valid, whose view is right, whose view should I follow, why does he explain it better than the other one?".

Conflicts of interest, or suspicions about conflicts of interest and corruption in general is another aspect that GR-R05 and GR-R06 stress. According to the former this is not only due to scientists and science itself, but corruption is a wider social problem that makes citizens justifiably suspicious; even more explicitly, it was mentioned that points of concern from citizens' perspective is that research can be manipulated, when it is funded by private companies. Also, when debates among researchers reach the public sphere - the truth seems not to be crystal clear. GR-R04 also stated that the pressure to continuously produce more and more new scientific results rendered the scientists themselves unable to follow all the new scientific developments, let alone the general public, and this causes even more confusion.

4.5 Other themes

There were no other related themes that derived during the researchers' interviews.

4.6 Synthesis of recommendations

GR-R02 stressed that all research programmes should have an interdisciplinary character. Collaboration with SSH and people with knowledge in Ethics and Deontology is necessary in all research projects. Openly inform citizens on the limitations and risks of research, as well as on the measures researchers take to minimise the

risks. People should be informed when things have gone wrong with research.

GR-R04 and GR-R05 seemed quite confident and extensive in the recommendations they had to make. As mentioned before, all three researchers identified the quality of science communication as a negative factor for public's trust in science. Therefore, their proposals were focused in solving those problems and improving this quality. Similarly, GR-R02 was quite persistent on having wider participatory events; as she said *"To have scientists closer to the citizens."*

Science integration was mainly confined to education programs and to science communication events (GR-R04, GR-R05, GR-R06) and to some extent to the participation of citizens in the data collection phase of the research cycle. GR-R06 seemed to be mainly focused on the latter, believing that scientists have the main responsibility to promote them.

GR-R04 and GR-R05 proposed also the creation of Institutions that will organize and oversee a responsible and appealing way to communicate scientific results both on Mass and social media, while simultaneously trying to limit the influence of "unresponsible" communication channels. Education programs are meant to be a centrepiece of these efforts, whether this will be through the universal public education system or as an initiative of other actors or organisations that could put pressure on the State Institutions and Private Corporations through the integration of citizens and positive results.

Recommendation 1
Creation of participatory and informative events (GR-R02,GR-R04, GR-R05, GR-R06).
Recommendation 2
Creation of Institutions that will oversee the way science is communicated (GR-R04, GR-R05).
Recommendation 3
Reformation of the educational system and wider educational events.

5 Conclusion

As mentioned at section 2.1, based on the experiences gained in the context of the application of Tasks 2.2 and 3.1, as well as in the context of other projects we were expecting that the interviewees were not going to bring to the discussion the term RI. Indeed, this was the case in the present study, however, when the term was brought by the interviewer, the interviewees presented a broad array of concepts that were relevant to RI. Greek interviewees apparently are sensitised to RI-related issues, despite the fact that they seem to lack the knowledge that they fall under the umbrella term of RI.

From the eight, in total, recommendations that were selected as the most important, in this report, half of them made references to institutional measures or to the need of setting of new types of institutions. This seems to be contradictory with the general mistrust to institutions spotted in the context of different empirical studies from the Greek research group, one of which was made in the context of POIESIS. This might probably relate to the fact that in these previous studies the participants were lay people, while in the present study the participants were researchers and communicators.

One result that was not expected is the awareness and acceptance by most of the interviewees of social integration. This specific aspect was a bit controversial at the focus group study of POIESIS, in the sense that social integration in the form of citizen science received both positive and negative response. In this study the responses were more homogeneous and more towards the positive side.

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Expert Interviews - *Portugal*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *CS/C*

Authors: Marta Entradas, Inês Sousa, Feng Yan

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1 Introduction

This report describes the results of the POIESIS ‘Expert Interview Study’ conducted in Portugal as part of Task 2.3.

The goal of the interviews was to investigate the views of experts involved in public communication of science in the topics of climate change and Covid-19, including *researchers* (hereafter ‘researcher interview’) and *mediators* (hereafter ‘mediator interview’), about research integrity and social integration in science. Among the mediators, we considered *institutional mediators* such as institutional science communicators working at universities and research institutes, and *non-institutional* mediators such as professional science writers, science journalists, author of science-related blogs/podcasts and other content creators. As for the researchers, we considered scientists working in topics related to climate change and COVID-19. These researchers are all actively involved in studying and communicating about the content of those topical areas in climate change and COVID-19.

1.1 Research questions for Task 2.3

The Expert Interview study contributes to answering the following research questions that guide POIESIS.

General research questions	More specific research questions
<p>RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?</p> <p>RQ3: To what extent and how does the <i>integration</i> of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public’s trust in science, i.e. how are ‘chains of mediation’ organised and how do they impact levels of public trust? • Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts? • What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

1.2 Insights from Task 2.2 and Task 3.1

From the results of the Public Deliberative Workshops (Sousa & Entradas, 2023) and Focus Groups in Portugal (Entradas et al., 2024), there was an interest in exploring ideas about how to attract and engage citizens who are not interested in scientific activities (the ‘non-converted’), such as those who never or rarely participate in scientific events or read scientific news. As such, we brought the issue to the attention of the interviewees during the interviews.

1.3 Brief summary of organising the interviews

We conducted a total of seventeen interviews with Portuguese experts: eleven mediator interviews – 2 institutional mediators and 9 non-institutional mediators –, and six researcher interviews.

The POIESIS coordinator of the expert interview study (CSIC) provided a protocol for the selection of the interviewees based on specific criteria, and an interview guide. Following this protocol, we interviewed six researchers, three of them working on climate change related topics, and three on COVID-19, including social scientists and; and eleven mediators, including two institutional mediators, i.e. communicators working in institutional contexts of research and eight non-institutional mediators, i.e. individuals not working in research performing, research funding, or other institutional roles in science, research, and innovation.

To select interviewees: a) we used web search through key words, such as COVID-19, climate change, journalist, science communication, and b) we used our personal networks. We identified potential participants and their contacts which consisted of 69 potential interviewees: 45 researchers, 6 institutional stakeholders, 18 non-institutional mediators. From this list, we selected a total of 17, who we thought would be more likely to accept the invitation. We approached them through email, in which we introduced the aim of the POIESIS project and basic information about the interview such as the goals and duration. We sent reminders and replaced contacts whenever needed. There is no deviation from the protocol in the selection of mediators and researchers.

All interviews were one-to-one, conducted online by a researcher from the POIESIS Portuguese team using the Zoom platform. The questions asked during the interviews followed the interview guide. Yet the semi-structured character of the interview allowed for flexibility in the order of the questions as well as the questions asked. There were times when interviewees covered topics in previous questions. All interviews were conducted in the mother language, Portuguese, and lasted in average about 49 minutes.

1.4 Data processing

All the interviews were recorded using the recording function of the Zoom platform. The audio recordings were then transcribed into text (Portuguese) and translated into English for later analysis by the coordinating team of this task (2.3.). Content analysis was conducted in the Portuguese transcripts using MAXQDA software. Data coding for qualitative analysis was based on the codebook provided by the coordinator of the expert interview study (CSIC) and previously discussed with the whole POIESIS team. Data analysis is presented in this report in three main sections: science communication, social integration, public trust in science. We also include a synthesis of recommendations for increasing trust in science.

2 Participants in the Expert Interview study

In this section, there are eleven tables (seven for Mediators and four for Researchers). In them, we present basic information about the interviewees including socio-demographic characteristics and occupation, and main communication activities, such as for example, communication tasks, outputs, type of interactions with the public, channels and practices of communication.

2.1 Descriptive tables

The tables in sub-sections 2.2 present information on institutional mediators and non-institutional mediators. Specifically,

- Table 1: Mediator's demographic and occupational information
- Table 2: Mediator's main communication tasks
- Table 3: Outputs produced by mediators
- Table 4: Channels used by mediators
- Table 5: Audience addressed by mediators
- Table 6: Mediators' interactions with citizens
- Table 7: Mediators' sources of information

The tables in sub-sections 2.3 are all targeted to researchers. To be more specific,

- Table 8: Researcher's demographic and occupational information
- Table 9: Researcher's scientific discipline and the focus of their work
- Table 10: Researchers' work with the public
- Table 11: Social integration practices of researchers

2.2 Mediators

Table 1. Demographics and occupation

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Mediator type**	Organization type (where applicable)	Occupational Description	Topic CV/CC#
M01	F	Senior	Institutional mediator	RPO – European Organization for Research	Head of Education, Communications and Outreach	Not applicable
M02	F	Senior	Institutional mediator	RFO and RPO - Private	Head of Communications, Events & Outreach	Not applicable
M03	F	Junior	Non-institutional mediator	Podcast/ Instagram	Producer of Podcasts and influencer	Not applicable
M04	M	Mid	Non-institutional mediator	Not applicable	Digital artist-freelancer	Not applicable
M05	F	Mid	Non-institutional mediator	Not applicable	Scientific illustrator-freelancer	Not applicable
M06	F	Senior	Non-institutional mediator	Non-profit organization	Founder of a non-profit organisation for science education	Not applicable
M07	F	Senior	Non-institutional mediator	Non-profit organization	Co-founder of a letter exchanging program between scientists and students	Not applicable
M08	M	Mid	Non-institutional mediator	Newspaper	Journalist and responsible for podcasts for newspaper	Not applicable
M09	M	Mid	Non-institutional mediator	Environmental non-profit organisation	Science communicator and event producer	CC
M10	F	Senior	Non-institutional mediator	Podcast/ Columnist (print)	Author of podcast, columnist for a regional newspaper, author of	Not applicable

					newsletter on archaeology and prehistory	
M11	F	Senior	Non-institutional mediator	Newspaper	Journalist and Editor of the Science section of newspaper	Not applicable

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior

** Mediator type:

- Institutional Mediators working at publishers / working at universities or research institutes;
- Non-institutional mediators: a) Professional science writers/communicators; Science/general journalists; Authors of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.; Other content creators

Covid-19 or Climate Change or both (where applicable).

Table 2. Mediators' main communication tasks

Id.	Description of mediators' main tasks
M01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinating the group “Education, Communications and Outreach” (65-70 people) • Carrying out various institutional communication activities, including communication in crisis situations (when they arise) and science communication activities such as writing press releases • Education and outreach: Coordinating and organizing projects and programs for teachers and students.
M02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinating the team of “communication, events and outreach” • Project management: working with the designers on visual communication, proofreading, approving texts, reviewing translations • Education and outreach: organising activities for primary school children, going to schools.
M03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making podcasts about the daily life of scientists/PhD students • Organising/participating in events such as the National Scientists’ Day • Maintaining social media: Instagram and the “Women in Science” project (short stories/cartoons on visible women in science)
M04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translating science to the public mainly through media arts and digital arts • Using art installations to communicate science, helping citizens experience the related scientific concepts • Designing digital games, video games and films
M05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making scientific, medical and biomedical illustration for books, posters, leaflets, etc. • Setting goals to disseminate, to change a behaviour, (e.g., how to convince people to recycle or stop smoking)
M06	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing educational programs for children (for example, for children’s migrant community, or ‘taking scientists to primary schools)
M07	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination: Supervising teams • Communication activities: institutional communication, organising webinars, seminars, etc. • Applying for funding for research • Reading letters exchanged by scientists and children (punctually)
M08	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for the newspaper’s podcast content and strategy

M09	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-ordinating the communications department and the Portuguese Ecology Society, working between academia and civil society
M10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making podcasts that interview researchers (working in archaeology related topics); • Producing a newsletter (in archaeology) • Writing articles on daily life science for a regional newspaper
M11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Editing the science section of the newspaper; writing articles • Distributing work to other people in the team • Making proposals and receiving proposals for work to be published, discussing the proposals and making decisions • Suggesting/choosing/looking for images, illustrations to accompany the newspaper articles • Disseminating the articles through various channels

Table 3. Outputs produced by Mediators

Id.	Books	Articles	Audiovisual (TV)	Radio program	Podcast	Audiovisual (social media)*	Post (Social media)**	Live (social media interaction)	Other: (please describe in a few words only)
M01									No information
M02									Events: European night of researchers, research symposium, annual retreat (internal event), organise theses defences
M03									No information
M04									Digital games and art installations
M05									Scientific figures, illustrations, thesis' covers, scientific posters, graphic abstracts for books, posters, campaigns, leaflets or flyers
M06									Short experimental activities, digital games, hands-on activities
M07									Exchanging letters and organising meetings between scientists and children
M08									No information
M09									Technical and scientific reports
M10									No information
M11									No information

*Includes memes, images, photographs, and videos

**Includes text

Table 4. Channels used by Mediators

Id.	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)						Chat apps		Other: (please describe in a few words only)
	TV	Radio	Newspaper	Websites	Blogs	Newsletters	LinkedIn	YouTube	Twitter	Instagram	TikTok	Other SN	WhatsApp	Telegram	
M01															No information
M02															No information
M03															Podcast (Spotify)
M04															Art installations; video games
M05															Magazines; social media
M06															Educational programme (scientists go to their primary schools); European programme (Speed Dating)
M07															Scientists exchanging letters with students; conference and talks. Facebook
M08															No information
M09															Events (like Oeiras Science Festival, BioBlitz activities)
M10															Facebook; Spotify; Soundcloud
M11															Facebook

Table 5. Audience addressed by Mediators

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' audiences/size estimate where known
M01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public (whoever are interested) • Teachers and students • PhD students in the centre • Younger people and local groups • 75,000 visitors in two days during the weekend for the opening days in 2019 • Social media: 1 million followers on Instagram; 2.5 million followers on Twitter • Visits to the website: around 100,000 visits (60% living more than 600 kms away)
M02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elementary school children • General public, young people
M03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young people, high school students, university students • Scientists • People already interested in science
M04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All kinds of audiences/ordinary citizens
M05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public Specific groups such as children or patients • Professional groups like nurses and doctors, • Researchers and experts
M06	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools with high failure rates, students from poor backgrounds who receive support from the State • Schools in rural areas • Teachers • Researchers
M07	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children • Students aged between 10 and 18 in PALOP (Portuguese-speaking African countries) • Scientists • Teachers and mentors from associations

M08	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subscribers of the newspaper (over 45, 50 years old) • Audiences of the podcast (n average age 35) • The niches who value a specific content • The mass audiences/General public
M09	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Farmers • Students, professionals and municipalities • Their associates (Tens of thousands)
M10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Archaeologists or people who are very interested in the topic (these are likely people over 45, mostly women) • More than 250 followers on Spotify
M11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public

Table 6. Mediators' interactions with citizens

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' social interaction practices
M01	In-person: Science Gateway; exhibitions; guided tours; visits to the laboratory; "hands-on" laboratories; public events; trips to local schools; activities for children Online: Regular weekly post called "Guess what it is" on social media; interaction in social media (e.g., lives or posts on Facebook and LinkedIn)
M02	In person: outreach events for elementary school children, like summer courses and summer camps; European night of Researchers, open days; a mentoring program taking place in schools; small group sessions and mentoring of students Online: Newsletter for people who are interested in specific topics; emails
M03	In person: direct contact with people including university students and secondary school students; through face-to-face workshops Online: interaction on Instagram (comments, likes), Podcasts; webinars
M04	In person: conferences; being invited to visit one international organization and take part in a hackathon on communication Online: interaction on social media; feedback received on videos
M05	In person and online: feedback received during the creative process from the audiences with the illustrations
M06	In person: workshops Online: Training for scientists
M07	Online: video calls between scientists and children
M08	Online: number of views or auditions of the podcast
M09	In person: conferences Online: Choosing a natural event, in spring and telling people about it on social media
M10	Online: comments from listeners of the podcasts
M11	Online: readers' comments on the articles; readers comments by e-mail

Table 7. Mediators' sources of information

Id.	Interpersonal networks		Science press releases					Other:(please add text)
	With researchers	With science communicators	Scientific literature	RPOs	Publishers	Mainstream media	Social media	
M01								Scientific Policy Committee (SPC) and the Finance Committee (FC)
M02								Internal collaborators and external collaborators (scientists and the medical, clinical community)
M03								Institutional websites, LinkedIn and Twitter
M04								Documentaries and TV shows
M05								Clients; websites and magazine articles; anatomy and surgery manuals; programmes like human anatomy in 3D
M06								
M07								
M08								
M09								
M10								
M11								

2.3 Researchers

Table 8. Description of the Researcher interviewees sample

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Position or title/Career stage**	Organisation type	Topic CV/CC#
R01	F	Senior	Associate Professor, Senior Researcher	Public university	CC
R02	F	Early	Junior Researcher	Public university	CV
R03	M	Senior	Assistant Professor, Leading Researcher	Research and Technology centre	CC
R04	F	Senior	Senior Researcher	Institute of Public Health	CV
R05	F	Senior	Senior Researcher	Public university	CC
R06	F	Mid	Invited Assistant Professor	Public university	CV

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior ** ECR; recognised researcher; senior researcher; leading researcher (Professor)

Table 9. Researcher notes

Id.	Note
R01	Social scientist working on communication of climate change, public participation in environmental technologies and environmental issues
R02	Biochemical researcher working on Parkinson's disease (interconnection between Parkinson's disease and intestinal microbiome)
R03	Climatologist working on fundamental and applied climatology, like agricultural sciences and application of animal/plant species and forest fires, as well as extreme events (droughts, heat waves)
R04	Public health and epidemiology researcher working on HIV infection in migrant populations in a Lisbon cohort of men who have sex with men
R05	Marine biology scientist working on marine litter and microplastics
R06	Social scientist working in the area of migration from a decolonial and gender perspective, including on the impact of COVID-19 on gender inequalities in Academia, and international students

Table 10. How Researchers work with the public

Id.	Brief description of how the researchers' work reaches the public
R01	Own initiative and voluntary work; writing for the project's website and social media; participation in public events; speaking in schools and universities via invitation; interviews with Portuguese and international media
R02	Instagram page dedicated to science communication of basic concepts; making videos; showing people the scientific process; feedback through comments and messages on Instagram
R03	Interviews for the radio, newspapers, and television; asking people what their practical problems and contributing to solutions by presenting the research to farmers
R04	Organization of seminars open to the community; forums of the scientific community and scientific articles that are shared with the community; science cafés
R05	Public talks; talks at schools; public conference on marine litter
R06	Podcast; press releases; Twitter/X; interviews with traditional media; storytelling; communication with decision makers; organization of events with NGOs

Table 11. Description of social integration practices of Researchers

Id.	Brief notes of Researchers' social integration practices
R01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting research projects involving focus groups and fieldwork • Generating debate around issues on the role of young people in climate change • Getting feedback from the targeted groups • Organizing a monitoring group made up of young climate activists • Bring together people with different profiles, including people in more disadvantaged situations or racialised groups
R02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explaining to people what a scientist does in social media • Communicating with community groups
R03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperating with society, mainly groups of farmers, to identify and solve specific problems
R04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving people from the community in projects • Sharing and circulating the articles with the community for getting feedback on scientific results • Receiving requests for data analysis from the community, talking privately with one or two people who represents the community's concerns about the research
R05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing the Portuguese Marine Litter Association to call on volunteers to carry out monitoring actions • Motivating people to get involved in the monitoring actions • Making the research public, published and accessible • Building relations with the Portuguese Plastic Producers
R06	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participating in a project about Refugee Women Organizing dialogue fora with international students • Involving political decision-makers, journalists, social networks and the general public in communication activities

3 Analysis of Mediator interviews

3.1 Chains of mediation

In this section we briefly describe the mediators' work by characterizing their main role and position in their network, their creative process and ways of interacting with their audiences and citizens. This description complements the information in Tables 1, 2, 5 and 6.

Main role and network position

In the mediators' discourse it was possible to identify four main roles when connecting science with society: a) informing (i.e., providing scientific information to the public in an accessible manner), b) intermediating (i.e., serving as a neutral bridge scientists and the public), c) consulting (i.e., engaging with clients to understand their specific needs and concerns when communicating scientific information), and d) educating (i.e., helping people to better understand science, its concepts and its relevance to societal issues) (Turnhout et al., 2013). To evaluate mediators' position in their networks, we considered the degree of centrality of these main roles in the relationship between science production and the public, defining three positions: central referring to individuals who occupy central positions within the network, being closer to the production of science; middle referring to individuals who connect different people and groups within the network, such as peers, and outside the network, such as specific audiences, and peripheral referring to individuals who are located at the network's border and enable the flow of knowledge between scientific production and societal stakeholders (see figure 1).

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the mediators' position in the science-public network

Some mediators believe that their role is **informing** by providing understandable scientific information to the public, using simple and accessible language. These mediators aim to translate complex scientific knowledge, sometimes developed through fundamental research (e.g., particle physics, neuroscience), to society. However, these mediators also recognise that, despite the desire to reach the broad public, it is those who are interested in the topics or science who continue to seek out the information. Examples of these mediators are institutional communicators (M1 and M2) and social media influencers (M3 and M10). These mediators occupy a **central position within the network**, by aggregating and distributing information to a broad audience. Although influencers are not always recognised as central figures in these knowledge networks, they are still able to influence people in their informal networks (i.e., social media accounts), taking advantage of their close relationships with their followers.

“It’s always difficult to communicate fundamental research, research that is knowledge for knowledge’s sake. We are not, we are not looking for any treatment or cure (...). And very complex, it really is very complex. Being able to explain this in a way that excites, creates... Creating a taste, curiosity for science, that is, that is a challenge, it is a challenge that we have.” (M1)

Two journalists (M8 and M11) explained that they see themselves as neutral intermediaries between science and society, so their main role is **intermediating**. Their main role is to write about science topics that are important to people’s lives, i.e., that are relevant to solving real problems for all people or for specific people (e.g., patients). In addition, they also write about science policy in the national and international context, which also implies that they relate to important policymakers, scientific institutions and the professional class of researchers. According to our participants, their job implies to contact a lot of different people to ask questions, so their network is very wide, and they are constantly establishing new connections. Their position is **peripheral** as they are located at the external boundary of the network in the sense that they seek to explain complex scientific concepts to the public. This more external position does not detract from their importance, but rather shows the need to possess specialised knowledge or expertise to accomplish the “simplification goal”.

“I think that by explaining to people, through audio, scientific investigations and scientific work, it’s a brutal advantage.” (M8)

For three other mediators (M4, M5 and M9), we see it as closer to a **consulting role**, and they work as freelancers. Their main goal is engaging with stakeholders (e.g., scientists, scientific institutions, decision-makers, companies), which they consider clients, to understand their science communication needs and tailor scientific information to meet these needs. This means, for example, identifying the audiences, the message and the channels to be used, which vary considerably from client to client, and which translate into a huge variety of outputs (e.g., posters, books, art installations, videogames, etc.). These mediators take up a position in the **middle of the network**, facilitating the dissemination of scientific information to groups within the network such as other researchers (e.g., drawing up scientific posters for presentation at conferences) and to groups outside of the network with the aim of provoking curiosity and changes in

behaviour (e.g., scientific illustration of children’s books, elaboration of technical-scientific reports for business associations).

“We’re not here thinking about doing something educational (...) but simply playing with that concept and demystifying it a bit. And create in the person who is viewing this work a little more curiosity about that topic (...). I don’t intend to teach.” (M5)

“I am much more focused [in my communication] and we have to because we are not informing, we are just trying to provoke behaviour (...) and we always want a positive behaviour, in our opinion.” (M9)

Finally, two mediators (M6 and M7) mentioned that their main purpose is **educating the public**, especially children and young people, by creating enthusiasm and curiosity. Their main goal is to foster scientific literacy among students by integrating science as part of their learning experiences at school. These mediators seek to go beyond the mere transmission of information, considering that their role is to build the capacity to understand science. They also want to contribute to scientific vocations by bringing scientists and students together. Their activities are carried out with the institutional support of the schools with which they establish partnerships. Similar to journalists, these mediators have a **peripheral position** in the network as they aim to create a bridge between science and society. Their role is vital in ensuring that scientific knowledge reaches specific groups within society.

“Our goal is to bring science closer to children so that children can deconstruct this idea that science is very difficult and only for the most intelligent. Science is for everyone.” (M6)

The process

The work process is relatively similar for all mediators, with slight changes depending on the activity they are preparing and the output they want to produce. The process begins with identifying the objective of the activity, followed by identifying the audience they intend to reach, choosing the channel to use (not applicable in cases where mediators only use one), and planning (with more or less rigor) the activity. The mediators then collect the information necessary to prepare the activity, using their different sources of information (mainly researchers and scientific articles), and carry out the activity.

It is interesting to note **some variations in this process**, which essentially depend on the flexibility in choosing the objective of the activity and in preparing and implementing the activity. For example, institutional mediators follow a more stable plan in their activities as it depends on the institutional strategy for science communication, meaning that there are regular activities every year (e.g., programs, exhibitions, newsletters).

“Starting from the laboratory strategy, and this is scientific strategy, the political strategy in terms of intergovernmental organization, of assuming a communication strategy and then, based on that communication strategy, defining and implementing different activities that answer to the objectives of that communication strategy.” (M1)

Social media influencers, for instance, show less planning and more improvisation in their activities, as these also depend on their availability. Journalists decide on the topics to be addressed in a journalistic article, in a video report or in a podcast episode, depending on the notoriety of the subject (e.g., trending in the news, great discovery for science, involvement of Portuguese researchers in the discovery, etc.).

“In our world, it is rushing, sometimes in great whirlwind, we make an instantaneous assessment and immediately realise: this subject is going to be interesting; this is new, this is new for science. No one has ever done this.” (M11)

Interaction with audiences and citizens

As showed in Tables 5 and 6, mediators interact with their audiences and citizens in multiple ways. *Institutional mediators* present the greatest diversity of audiences and interact with them through different activities. These mediators also recognise that most of their activities are in-person events such as exhibitions or guided tours with brief interactions between scientists and the public, but these are important to reach more people. Other activities such as programs for schools or summer camps are recognised as having stronger lasting effects on the students.

“People who were with us during high school in some activity, summer courses, those summer camps, that kind of academies, and you lose track of them (...). I had one recently who was there at the foundation as a volunteer at an event. So, she looked at me and said, “Ah, you must not remember me.” (...) So, she said, “I discovered my interest in the brain, my fascination with the brain with you, so now I’m waiting to find out the results for the specialty. I’m trying to go into neurosurgery.” (M2)

Among the *non-institutional mediators*, some carry out their activities mainly online, such as mediators 3, 4, 7, 8, 10 and 11, therefore interactions are also in digital platforms (e.g., comments in social media, streaming apps or websites, meetings in digital platforms).

“I get a lot of messages from them [the students] because they see the posts and then they ask me things.” (M3)

“There [on Facebook] people made a lot of comments every time I released an episode, they made comments, and they were very nice, very, very positive.” (M10)

The majority of participants highlighted that they prefer a **true interaction with their audiences**, characterised by a **bidirectional dialogue**. Even in activities with less direct interaction with the public, practitioners say that there are ways to receive more or less regular feedback.

3.2 About research ethics and integrity (REI)

The topic of research ethics and integrity (REI) did **not** emerge **spontaneously** in any of the interviews. In fact, even after being asked directly about the importance of REI in their

work, the majority of mediators gave very superficial answers and were more focused on **ethics in their work** than on ethics in scientific research. This result was consistent with the results of our previous national studies in the POIESIS project, especially with the discussions during the focus groups where REI-related issues have taken on little relevance.

When asked to define REI, only six mediators answered directly to the question. Institutional mediators, who had been researchers in life sciences in the past, provided the most sophisticated answers. Still, it was difficult for participant to distinguish between ethics and integrity.

“Ethics is more, it’s more, it’s broader than scientific integrity, in my opinion. In my experience, therefore, scientific integrity has more to do with following the rules, the principles of scientific research with regard to sharing observations, recording observations, recording results, especially when they are for publication, sharing information with colleagues (...) Not lying, being faithful to the results that you have and then that are reflected in the publications, being truthful when you go to talk to colleagues about sharing information, not hiding information for your own benefit. For me, this is more about integrity, scientific integrity, perhaps more to do with the practice of science within the community. (...) Ethics has more to do with just thinking about the type of experiment you want to do (...), knowing and adhering to ethical principles.” (M1)

This difficulty is also seen in Mediator 5, who is a scientific illustrator. This participant defined REI in her work, focusing mainly on the idea of respecting the audience that the client wants to reach. In her words:

“It’s important to be honest, to tell the truth, but to adapt that scientific information to the kind of language that can reach and be accessible to the audience. So, I think that really, in terms of accessibility and also ethics, it would be important to respect the people we are talking to, not to patronise them, to be inclusive. And, even if we have to simplify things, don’t be disrespectful. (...) To communicate with patients who are going through a serious health situation (...) that is serious or difficult, we can’t create illustrations that are funny, for example.”

REI-related issues in mediators’ work

Participants’ views on how cases of REI-related issues have affected their work was mostly associated to the idea of communicating to the public **how scientific work is done**, that is, the ethical principles that should guide scientific research, particularly how the objects of study should be treated in research.

“In the last few posts on animal research, I’ve talked a lot about ethics and the impact and responsibility we have.” (M3)

One mediator (M10) mentioned the problem of pseudoarchaeology, defined as an inaccurate interpretation of archaeological aspects of history (e.g., lack of scientific evidence, distortion of historical information), in which some researchers, but especially

members of the public, rely on pseudoscientific interpretations to construct sensationalist and conspiracy theories. In her words:

“In the case of archaeology, there are some examples of researchers – deep down, I don’t know if I can call them researchers, because in methodological terms they are quite criticizable... But I can’t say that they interfere with my work.”

Even so, this topic received little attention from the interviewees, and most did not have examples of situations in which cases of lack of scientific integrity had affected their work. One participant mentioned that **Portugal historically shows a high level of trust in science** and “*scientists were not involved in major scandals*” (M9). Two other participants also mentioned that they believe that **cases of scientific misconduct do not reach the public**, even if they are reported in the media: “*The communities we work with, frankly, I think these issues go by the wayside.*” (M6) Together, these results can justify the lack of attention given to this topic in the 11 interviews with the mediators.

Assessing REI in mediators’ work

Interviewees argued that their responsibility is to **use reliable sources** of information in their work, mostly researchers in their institutions or in other reputable institutions, but also peer-reviewed scientific papers and other media. Our mediators mentioned that they highly trust researchers at the institutions with which they work closely.

“I think our role is to ask, and when we don’t understand or when we find it strange to talk to others in the area. (...) I ask [researchers] in the specialty area, right? “Look, is this article really like that or, or do you think it’s too much?” And when we have researchers who tell us, “Maybe these adjectives are a little too much”, we have to do the down grading.” (M2)

“As I only deal there with a very closed group of scientists, I already know that they are, at least initially, credible, because they are part of my institution and that I have known for many years.” (M4)

The perception of the two journalists of whether issues of research integrity have affected their work and how they manage relationship with researchers was slightly different from the other mediators. While they acknowledge that cases of research integrity have not affected their work in any way, they highlighted the difficulty that it is to access to reliable sources, and that the pressure to obtain comments from a scientific perspective can sometimes imply contacting researchers who are not experts in the topic but are available at the moment of the contact, thus, compromising information.

“This time pressure we also have is very conditioning of good work. (...) Normally it is the researcher who is available the fastest and who always answers the phone and the one who has already been recommended to me because he is very good and talks about everything and always answers. (...) When sometimes there are even researchers who are working on much more specific sub-topics and much closer to what we need.” (M8)

REI-related cases on Covid-19 and Climate Change

Only one mediator (M9) reported a REI-related case on climate change. The reported case deals with the suspicion of scientific fraud on the part of a group that carried out research in Alentejo by a group of decision-makers. According to the participant, there was no misconduct, but the suspicion was raised due to other interests and lobbies by political parties and economic groups. In his words:

“We identified temporary ponds or temporary lagoons, which are habitats that have water in winter and dry up in summer. And they have a very rich community of biodiversity. There are species that only exist there. There are species with marvellous evolutionary adaptations that, we’ve discovered that if a pond doesn’t have water for four years, the eggs remain viable there and when it rains, they hatch, for example. So there really was interest from an ecological and scientific point of view in those ponds (...). We were listened to a lot by the political power (...). And we explained, “look, this is seasonal, the habitat is there, maybe you don’t see it now, but it’s there. It’s been validated by the University, the European Commission received this information, so do what you want”.”

3.3 About public trust in science

Mediators’ contribution to trust in science

Mediators did not show difficulties in understanding the questions related to public trust in science and none were reluctant to talk about the topic. Nine out of the 11 mediators agreed that **their work can positively contribute to trust in science**, while two mentioned that it was not their purpose. These two mediators (M6 and M7) were interested in **making science more accessible** to the public, especially for children, but without aiming to increase their trust.

“I’d like to believe so (...). I think we have this role of allowing or creating conditions, creating opportunities for scientists to spend time with society. And I think that’s half the battle for trust, to have an opportunity for dialogue.” (M2)

“I think so, or I hope so. (laughs) Mainly because illustrating is like to communicate without languages, anyone can understand.” (M5)

“Our goal is not to increase trust in science, our goal is to bring science closer to children.” (M6)

The mediators who consider that their work contributes to maintain or increase trust in science suggest that they do so by a) creating opportunities for **dialogue between scientists and society**, b) showing who the **scientists are** and what they **do**, c) presenting the great **scientific discoveries** and their **relevance** to people’s lives, d) using **art and hands-on activities** to stimulate interest and curiosity in science.

“Showing people that the themes can have some connection, that all science themes can have a connection with our lives.” (M10)

REI-related issues on public attitudes

As described earlier in this report, mediators did not show great concerns about lack of scientific integrity or its potential impact in public's image of science, and some interviewees even revealed that they consider it to be an issue that receives no attention from society, even though it is reported in the media.

“I think that they [the public] may have this notion [about misconduct] when big news break on media, but on a daily basis they don't. I would say it's not something that's present in them.” (M3)

Yet, one mediator who works with Climate Change topics expressed concerns with the origin of **research funding** and how this can affect the public's perception of scientists and science, particularly when it comes to private companies requesting studies on the impact of their activity on the environment.

“Someone who profits millions from a polluting and socially unacceptable activity can give two pennies to science and show that they are doing a great thing.” (M9)

The topic that emerged in conversations about ethics, and indirectly related to REI issues, was **fake news and misinformation**, not necessarily the responsibility of scientists, but how it can have an impact on public attitudes towards science.

“Now anyone can make beautiful graphics or beautiful illustrations. that doesn't mean that they're correct, so I would say that we have to start worrying about what can really be conveyed this scientific communication, because what is the source? Is the source reliable? Otherwise, it's going to be more fake news and it's going to generate more doubts on people.” (M5)

“Websites, social media accounts with tens of thousands of followers, with nothing but false information about prehistory. (...) In the meantime, a series came out on Netflix which was a huge success, and which is literally pseudo-archaeology.” (M10)

How REI-related issues impacted work

Six of the 11 interviewees addressed the topic of how ethics and integrity impacted their own work, but the examples given were related to the **dissemination of false information** that does not necessarily originate from scientific fraud or bad research practices, and which is often perpetuated by **people outside academia**. One mediator (M1) mentioned a mistake made by scientists during the research process, but with no malicious intent. She said: *“Two years later, when they carried out a new analysis, they realised that a human measurement error had been made. So that result wasn't true after all, and we were very open about it.”* This affected her work as the team had to prepare a statement explaining the situation and they decided, in her words, *“to openly communicate what happened”*.

One journalist (M11) associated lack of integrity to situations when a scientist decides to talk to her about a topic that he or she is **not an expert** on, with the aim of getting noticed. In her words:

“Journalists are looking for a researcher to talk to about something, let’s say the pandemic, to talk about a specific topic, and for some reason they can’t find that person (...) And they find someone else to comment on it, and sometimes that other person isn’t the best person. So, the researcher is also taking advantage of a situation to promote himself or herself, but that give the idea that if you’re a scientist, you can talk about anything. Well, no, you can’t.”

Mediators’ views on improving public trust in science

Mediators struggled to make tangible recommendations and propose specific measures or initiatives that contribute to build trust in science. However, they suggested several principles that should be considered when designing measures or policies to this purpose, which are the following: a) show people/scientists doing science; b) tell stories; c) create experiences that engage the person; d) use humour and appropriate language. Furthermore, four mediators highlighted that more funding for science communication, including science journalism, is required and urgent.

People connect to people

One of the most mentioned ideas by mediators was the importance of **showing people doing science**, that is, showing scientists at work, and give them voice in society. In the opinion of the majority of participants, the humanization of scientists by giving them voice can greatly contribute to trust in science, particularly of children and young people.

“I think that this can also promote the trust of the public, scientists having a more present voice, whether through traditional media such as the newspaper, or in other ways, whether science on the street, whether in exhibitions, museums, on television, in others and themselves on their platforms and in their... Other formats.” (M11)

Showcasing scientists could also be an important way of promoting people’s identification with science. Identification is a psychological process in which a person identifies with the characteristics of another person or group (Bandura, 1986), which can lead to modelling and imitation because it offers a vision of “what could be their future” and this strongly influences future behaviour. On the one hand, when children and young people meet or interact with a scientist, in person or through social media, they may want to **imitate their behaviour** and thus want to be a scientist. According to the participants, this can be relevant to show that science is accessible to everyone (“The priority is for more children to feel that science can be for them, so that they feel that if they want to be a scientist, they can be one.” – M7) and to increase scientific vocations (“In order to generate scientific vocations, we have to give examples of people who have achieved this success.” – M5).

On the other hand, and here considering the general public, the humanization of scientist can also lead people to feel **empathy** (i.e., the ability to put oneself into the feelings, thoughts, and perspectives of other people), especially when mistakes are made, and questions are raised.

“The main content is always the day-to-day life of a scientist or PhD student. (...) I think the main thing for me is to show my face, me.... I think people connect with people. (...) Because if they connect, then they’ll feel more comfortable to question and if they question, they’ll listen to the justification or the answer and they’ll have more confidence in it.” (M3)

“Scientists are not different people, they have their lives, they have problems as everyone else.” (M9)

Considering the fundamental role that scientists play in bridging science and society, mediators also suggested that **training scientists** on philosophy of science and communication with the public is important. One mediator suggested, on the one hand, to offer a broader perspective of the foundations and assumptions of the scientific process and methods, demonstrating the diversity of scientific knowledge and the relevance of ethics when doing science. This was one of the few mentions to REI-related topics in the recommendations for trust in science. On the other hand, and for most mediators mentioning the need for training scientists, they believe that scientists should understand the importance of communicating to their audiences and know how to do it.

“I would say at the level of training of scientists, at the university. There should be mandatory disciplines, disciplines or workshops, a mandatory test, I don’t know, but they would have to have philosophy of science, ethics, the sociology of science, issues of integrity, integrity and responsibility in the practice and communication of science.” (M7)

Storytelling

Some mediators also suggested that an attractive way to get the public’s attention to science is to **tell stories** about the people – as we discussed before – and about the research. If people are curious about the story of the discovery, if they understand the scientific process, they will likely trust more science. This is also useful to implement one of other participants’ suggestions of showing and explaining the scientific process.

“People are interested in people and stories. So, if we want to talk about cancer, let’s talk about cancer to caregivers of cancer patients, for example. It’s always about finding the human part of the experience, here is not communicating science just for the sake of communicating science. For me, it’s short because only people interested in science will be the appropriate target audience.” (M7)

“Sometimes you can also tell it like a story in the sense of how you got to this result, but it’s telling a story and I also have this idea and I always ask for photos of scientists because science has faces. Science is done with people and it’s not this abstract thing in the laboratory just for the mouse. It’s the mouse, but it’s the mouse and the person.” (M11)

Create experiences

Some mediators suggest that to connect the public to science it is important to go beyond the educational purpose of science communication and to **create experiences**, that are based on doing and on emotions, and fun. An **affective experience** of science can be particularly important to spark the interest of the non-converted. Thus, two mediators, in particular, highlighted the need to appeal to the emotions of the public, but also of scientists who are involved in these activities.

“This [videogame] isn’t school, it’s not an educational book... It’s more playful than educational.” (M4)

“I’m a big believer in the mantra of “small and meaningful is beautiful”. It is preferable to carry out an intervention with few people and it means a significant experience, significant for all parties involved, that is, there is a win-win that the scientist also leaves there knowing, with new learning, rather than just doing something for the sake of doing it.” (M6)

Language: simple, simpler, slang

The use of **accessible language** to the audience was mentioned by half of the interviewees, and they highlighted the importance of simple language for understanding the subject to be communicated. At the same time, three mediators also mentioned the importance of not being condescending or oversimplifying the speech. One journalist mentioned the relevance of podcasts to this end.

“It is much more natural for us to explain something to someone through our voice than to write it in an article for the simple reason that our language tends to simplify too (...) the general public who have to be informed about these advances, these progresses, these investigations in the best possible way and if we are too technical, we fail. So, the audio here is a brutal doorway.” (M8)

This recommendation seems particularly important for young people, and can mean, for example, to use memes or use expressions that well-known among this group.

“To connect with them [young people], it’s a lot about following their trends, the ways they talk, the expressions they use (...). And using their expressions makes them feel more connected to us too, because they feel that we speak in the same way as they do, but because here we’re lowering the level of scientific language a little bit and maybe we’re not going to please everyone.” (M3)

“It is important to be honest, tell the truth, but adapt this scientific information to the type of language that can reach and be accessible to the audience (...). Don’t be too paternalistic towards children and simplify things too much.” (M5)

Funding for science communication

Four mediators (M7, M8, M10, M11) spoke about the need for specific lines of **funding for science communication**, particularly from the national agency, the Portuguese

Foundation for Science and Technology. This measure would be essential to promote science journalism, in the opinion of mediator 8, at a time when only one newspaper in Portugal – Jornal Público – has a science section with journalists exclusively dedicated to science. In many other newspapers, which have good reputation, scientific news are written by journalists who do not specialise in science.

“I really think that specific funding for hiring science journalists should be considered.” (M8)

“I think it would be interesting to open a line of funding, however small, in the FCT for science communication projects.” (M10)

Institution’s role on trust in science

Institutions have also an important role for improving trust in science, by creating “*curiosity and love for science*”, which can contribute to “*greater understanding, involvement, acceptance*” of science (M1).

In the opinion of institutional mediators, their role in building trust in science involves helping the public to **understand** what is being done in their institutions and to recognise the value of science. This means using **simpler language in their materials** (e.g., news on website, newsletter), an added challenge when working with basic science, and **involve scientists in the activities** (e.g., guided tours, meetings).

“It’s for people to understand. “I know what you do is expensive, you build very expensive equipment, but it’s worth it for the questions you have and the answers you’re trying to get to those questions.” I think that would be a big step for us to get public’s trust.” (M1)

“Recognising the value of science and bringing scientists closer together, making them accessible. “If I have a question about this, I can talk to him/her about it”. Usually, a person doesn’t look at the scientist as someone who is approachable.” (M2)

In relation to the younger audience, the two mediators spoke of the need to reach out to these young people, particularly from disadvantaged communities, in the sense of “science out-of-doors”. This means **taking scientists and activities to the schools or neighbourhoods** (or other community groups) that these young people attend in an attempt to make science truly inclusive and accessible, in a space where they are most comfortable because it is familiar to them. Interestingly, these future goals that the mediators set for their institutions are in line with the work that mediators 6 and 7 do in their programs to bring scientists and children closer together. In this sense, the establishment of partnerships between scientific institutions and non-formal science education programmes could be important in increasing the accessibility and understanding of science.

“We’ve been talking about of reaching the non-covered. In other words, audiences in socially unprivileged areas. (...) We have to get out of our comfort zone. We

have to go to them first, we have to go to them where they are, because they don't come to our institution.” (M1)

Mediator 2 gave a specific example of how scientists, especially young scientists, can easily connect to young people by sharing similar interests and language, reinforcing what was discussed before. She told the following story:

“When we do activities, I think it's always easier to take someone who is closer to their age, their interests... For example, during these mentoring processes, one of the girls who do mentoring has a fixation with Asian and Korean culture. She's even spent a season in Korea, learning Korean. And immediately, this was a point of connection during the conversations with the kids. Because apparently K-pop, and that whole movement of cartoons, of manga, Asian culture, apparently has a very big penetration on the kids before secondary school up to eighth, ninth grade. So, the concerts, the series, lots of series that I'd never heard of and this scientist, who is much closer to their age than I am and who has very similar interests, immediately found a point to get into. Then they were talking about evolution.”

3.4 Other themes

Covid-19 and public image of science

Seven out of the 11 mediators mentioned that the COVID-19 pandemic was a landmark event for the public's image of science. Four participants considered that the image of science emerged stronger from that crisis, as people were able to acknowledge the importance of scientific discoveries in their daily lives and scientists gain more recognition in the public sphere with a regular presence in media. Additionally, the quick response from science in developing vaccines contributed to greater trust in science.

“I think the pandemic helped this a lot. Suddenly it seems like everyone understands what science is, why it is important (...). Maybe the pandemic accelerated some things in the digital area, but it also accelerated some things in the area of communication and the relationship between the public and research.” (M4)

On the other hand, three participants mentioned that trust in science decreased during or after the pandemic due to the lack of consensus among scientists during the crisis, particularly at its beginning. They cited examples of the fluctuating advice from scientists regarding protective measures against COVID-19 and the lack of knowledge of the scientific process from the public.

“We saw that with COVID, with the pandemic, at least at the beginning that shock to society, “so, but isn't the science always right? Don't you know what it is...?” (...) It was a difficult period for science (...) there is that expression of what we, the communicators, present is the sausage already ready, but there is the whole thing, when there is still just the ground meat behind and everything the process of forming into sausage.” (M1)

3.5 Synthesis of recommendations

Mediators' recommendations for increasing or maintaining public trust in science are mostly based on the idea that **science should be more accessible and inclusive** and that, by making it understandable and aligned with people's interests, it can also be interesting and valuable.

Most mediators highlighted the **importance of scientists** in connecting science and society. They were perceived as an important link or bridge between these two worlds. Here, mediators suggested that scientists' image should be used, for example, by showing their photos working, their job should be explained, including references to the scientific process and eventual mistakes made. Young scientists can be especially important to impress young people due to the high potential of sharing similar ideas, preferences and language. Engaging scientists in communication activities is however dependent on **training** to better prepare them for balancing scientific accuracy of their common language with the simplicity required by the public.

Storytelling can also be a powerful tool in communicating science, as stories make science more relatable by connecting complex concepts to everyday experiences and appeal to emotions that hold the audiences' attention. These suggestions seem particularly relevant for activities where the goal is not to educate the public but awake their curiosity and interest in science.

Despite being a less frequent recommendation among interviewees, **funding for science communication**, including for science journalism, was also mentioned. Interviewees considered that funding also serves as a signal from agencies of the relevance of communication activities in science.

In the opinion of the two institutional mediators, institutions have to **leave** their usual **physical spaces** to reach the unconverted. There are groups that remain very distant from science, particularly groups of underprivileged children and young people, and it seems important to go to the places where these groups live, study or spend their free time to create opportunities for interaction with scientists.

These are the top 3 recommendations of our mediators:

- | |
|---|
| 1. Engage scientists in institutional and non-institutional activities, showing the daily life of a scientist in different fields of knowledge, give them voice in society. |
| 2. Create activities that are based on storytelling to guide the public through the scientific process until the result |
| 3. Create lines of funding specifically for science communication and science journalism |

4 Analysis of Researcher interviews

4.1 Researcher contexts: Covid-19 and Climate Change

In this section we provide a brief snapshot of researchers' work, complementing the information in Tables 8 and 9. We also explore how public controversy about Climate Change and Covid-19 topics impact their work.

Researchers 1, 3 and 5 are interested in the Climate Change topic, the first one from a social sciences perspective. Researchers 2 and 4 develop their research on Public Health research and did some studies about the Covid-19 pandemic. Researcher 6 studies (anti)migration movements and international mobility in academia.

Researcher 1 works mainly about communication on climate change and other environmental issues. She states that *“when I’m talking about communication, I’m thinking of communication in a very broad sense. Not just in some more conventional, sometimes more transmissional meanings, more linked to the idea of transmitting information (...), but also the different levels of context that are associated with all this, the way in which, as a society, we create, recreate senses and meanings for things, and how this is linked with social and political structures at various levels”*. She participated in and coordinated several projects related to public participation in environmental technologies or environmental issues, currently focusing more on activism and youth activism linked to climate change.

Researcher 3 is a climatologist and is mainly interested in the variability of specific aspects of the climate and climate change of a particular place or region. He works in a university focused on agricultural sciences *“so it’s climatology applied not only to human systems, but also to natural systems”* such as the impact of climate change on animal species and plant species (e.g., productivity of certain species, behaviour of agroforestry systems, forest fires). He is also interested in topics related to data quality, development, test, and adaptation of new methodologies for analysing environmental data.

Researcher 5 works primarily in marine biology, *“but also sometimes with a foot in the part that’s more physics or more geology”* and is currently researching marine litter and microplastics. She has a long experience in animal ecology research and worked in projects such as studying the plankton in the Tejo River, the environmental impacts on clams in Ria Formosa, and the bioperturbation of sediments by organisms that live in sediments.

Researcher 2 is a young researcher and focuses mainly on Parkinsons' disease and how the disease relates to intestinal microbiome, the 'gate brain access', aiming to discover new therapeutics. She has limited research experience on the topic of Covid-19 as she was a master's student at the time.

Researcher 4 investigates HIV infection in migrant populations, with a cohort of men who have sex with men. During the Covid-19 pandemic, similarly to other researchers *“who worked in public health and especially on this issue of infectious diseases”* she diverged to keep up with what was happening in Covid-19 and, with her team, she developed

seroprevalence studies, aiming “to measure the extent of the infection using serological markers, antibodies and not just the diagnosis because we knew that the infection was clearly underdiagnosed.”

Researcher 6 describes herself as “a precarious researcher in the area of migration from a decolonial and gender perspective”. In her studies about migration, she also studied mobility and currently she works with mobility within higher education, that is, students and researchers coming to Portugal. During the pandemic, she coordinated two studies: one aiming to understand the impact on gender inequalities in academia during the pandemic, especially the impact for women, and other about the impact on the experiences of international students in Portugal.

Perceived controversy

All researchers interviewed considered that **controversies** associated with the topics of Climate Change and Public Health, Covid-19 in particular, **have not** negatively affect their work. From the perspective of the three Climate Change researchers, there is really no room for controversy on this topic, since science has consistently shown, through various studies, that climate change exists and there are anthropogenic causes of climate change.

“I’ve been doing research into climate change for many years. (...) What we know today is nothing like what we knew 30 years ago. And so, controversy is an aspect that, let’s put it this way, can be more acceptable when the state of knowledge on a given subject is still not very deep and so there are divergent opinions, naturally, this is healthy. (...) Now there are subjects for which controversy has no reason to exist. If there is controversy, it’s only because people want it, isn’t it? There are things where science says it’s like this or it’s not, full stop. Therefore, wanting to create controversy in areas where there is no longer any chance of controversy seems to me to be inadvisable.” (R3)

Furthermore, one researcher (R6) highlighted that she takes advantage of the controversy associated with public perception of how COVID-19 affected people’s lives, particularly marginalised, discriminated against or socially devalued groups. In her words:

“My work started from that. I start precisely from this inequality, that not everyone will be affected in the same way. My idea is always to move on from this discourse that the pandemic has affected everyone in every way. No, it hasn’t.”

4.2 About science communication and public attitudes

Science communication: Experiences with the media

With the exception of Researcher 2, who had no experience with traditional media, all the researchers have already communicated their research by giving interviews to

newspapers and/or television programmes, and consider the **experience to have been positive**. They believe that in general journalists are accurate, thorough, and prepared to ask questions and raise doubts, but it depends on the journalist.

“It depends. In some cases, yes, absolutely. I think they’ve probably done a better job than I could have done myself. (...) We know that there are people who are knowledgeable, discerning, competent and rigorous, and if they have any doubts, they will contact the person or try not to write about what they haven’t understood very well.” (R1)

“I’ve only had good experiences, so far I’ve only had good experiences with journalists.” (R5)

Researcher 6 asserted that although she has no experience of misrepresentation of her work, she feels that journalists have a rushed approach to a quick response, which she does not appreciate. Interacting with journalists is something that this researcher does not enjoy, as well as Researcher 4 who said, “*I don’t like it very much*”. On the contrary, Researcher 2 would like to have this experience of communicating to the public through traditional media as she already uses social media to do it. In her words:

“Trying to reach the media (...) newspapers or even television. I think it is very important, it is something that I would really like to do, which is to take science, the science that I do, the research that I do further and to more people.”

Two researchers reported negative experiences. Researcher 1 had two situations of distortion of her work with two foreign newspapers. The journalists have completely misrepresented the message she wanted to convey. In her words:

“I gave an interview to a Basque newspaper, which I was asked to write, and which was then published with sentences that I didn’t write. (...) After a lecture in The Netherlands, the lady distorted a lot of what I said, and I wrote back, and I have the feeling that my correction was never published.”

Researcher 6 reported a situation in which the journalist took a long time to correct a mistake she missed in her text.

“One was because he asked me for a written text (...). And when I wrote it down, I forgot to put a ‘no’, so when I finally read it, I said to him “There’s a ‘no’ missing and it completely changes my speech.” He said, “I’ll rectify it”. Two days later. Everyone should have read it by now.”

When communicating their research, the interviewees say they do not prepare in any special way, but try to speak simply, correctly, unambiguously and with few words, and repeat the ideas. Their main objective is to be **comprehensible to the public**, without raising questions about the message they want to convey.

“In order to communicate in a way that is accessible and understandable to most people, I have to simplify. By simplifying, I run the risk of people misunderstanding what I’m saying or imagining that I’m saying certain things that I’m not saying, and so that, in my opinion, is one of the worst risks you run in communication. And so,

in order to try to minimise this problem, what I advocate is that communication should be as correct as possible, and with as few words as possible.” (R3)

“I always think that when I give my talks and make my statements about things, that I do it in a very, very sure, very affirmative way that doesn’t leave much room for doubt.” (R5)

“I repeat it a few times. I write it down if I’m asked to write it down. Others I repeat 75 times.” (R6)

Science communication and public attitudes

The researchers interviewed consider that the potential controversy about Climate Change and Covid-19 **does not affect public attitudes** towards the topic, science in general or their own work. Their perspective is justified by the absence of strong ‘anti’ movements in Portugal and a generalised acceptance of the scientific results without question. The perspective is similar for the Climate Change and Covid-19 researchers.

“In Portugal, as you know, scepticism, cynicism about climate change is, has been, relatively residual.” (R1)

“The controversies don’t bother me in the slightest, so I’m not bothered in the slightest by this aspect.” (R3)

4.3 About the integration of citizens in research

Social integration: rationales and practices

All researchers considered that **citizen involvement** in research is an **added value**, but only in specific phases of the research process, about which opinions also varied. The two Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) researchers agreed that the involvement of citizens in research is important for research itself, the researchers and the public debate, and both have several examples of social integration practices that they commonly use in their projects such as a dialogue forum, a collaborative laboratory, a monitoring group, and discussion groups.

“As part of the project’s own research dynamics, which involved a lot of focus groups, a lot of fieldwork at various levels, we tried, whenever possible and without conditioning the research process, but creating ramifications and developing parallel activities also to give some, well, I didn’t want to say projection to the project, that’s not just the idea, it’s to generate some debate around this issue of the role of young people in climate change issues.” (R1)

“I took part in a project on refugee women in which our researcher was a refugee. (...) I’ve created a dialogue forum, you know because I want to sit down with the international students and talk to them; a collaborative laboratory, where I want to bring together these students and the people who work institutionally with student mobility and get them to talk to each other.” (R6)

For these two researchers, it is crucial to think about **public involvement** in science in a very **integrated** way, not the ‘end of pipe’ logic but rather an **upstream** involvement, which suggests that this involvement is essential for research practices to be considered ethical and responsible. They emphasised that the public cannot be a mere receiver of the message, but rather interlocutors of researchers.

For researchers 2 and 5, the **public should be engaged** especially in the **communication** of results’ phase. For Researcher 5, involvement in data collection would require validation of the data by researchers afterwards.

“Engaging the public means continuing to do what I’m doing [communicating through social media], which is the easiest way.” (R2)

“Get involved in working on the bench with me? No. Getting involved in order to follow results, yes. But this has to do with communication, right? The way I communicate the results of the laboratory experiments we do here. Now, of course, for me it doesn’t make any sense for the public to be in the laboratory.” (R5)

For researchers 3 and 4, the public can be important in some studies of their field of research in an **initial stage**, to **identify the problems** that need to be solved and the needs to be addressed. Researcher 3 also considered that sometimes the public can participate in **data collection**, such as in citizen science projects. Researcher 4 mentions public engagement approaches in regard to involvement of patients in the research process by providing the data, but also in the context of data collection by the technicians at the checkpoints, the community centres, who collect the data and a peer approach is used, i.e., the technicians are men who have sex with men.

“Over time I began to realise and modify my way of being in science in relation to the public a little. And one of the more or less obvious ways is to ask people what bothers them and what problem they have that I can help solve. (...) Use the public to provide information. This might be useful. Someone reported, for example, intense precipitation, or a hurricane, mini hurricane or anything else and reports. “I detected it here, it lasted that long, I even made a film.” So, these are the kind of contributions that I think are very positive for science.” (R3)

In summary, we can identify three profiles of researchers regarding their views on citizens’ involvement in research: a **full involvement**, researchers who agree that involvement should happen in all the phases of the scientific process (researchers 1 and 6); a **partial involvement**, in the identification of research problems and in data collection (researchers 3 and 4); and a **residual involvement** only in the communication of scientific results (researchers 2 and 5).

Characteristics of citizens involvement in researchers' work

Here we describe how citizens are involved in the researchers' work, the groups that are involved and the frequency of involvement. We identify similarities and differences among researchers' practice.

For researchers 1 and 6, the SSH researchers, the involvement of citizens in their own research is a **typical part** of their practice and it usually happens in several different phases of the scientific process. Researcher 1 includes a monitoring group made up of young climate activists, *"including people in more disadvantaged situations or racialised groups"*. They were involved in the **design of the project, meet in a regular basis** to discuss the project, and she believes that this group is very important for their research.

Researcher 6 involves political decision-makers, non-profit organizations, the general public, and specific groups such international students or refugees in her research. The researcher recognises that her **limitations can be overcome by the skills** that a citizen can have. In her voice: *"Our lack of linguistic knowledge of Siri or other languages, and we didn't want to have a third person intermediating in this (...). So, we made the point of having a refugee."*

Researchers 3 and 4 direct their efforts towards **identifying priorities** for research and **presenting and discussing** research **results** with their target groups on a regular basis, but with the intention of increasing the frequency of these contacts. Researcher 3 involves different stakeholders in the identification of research problems and communication of results such as chestnut producer groups. The researcher tries to do this involvement *"with some regularity"*.

Similarly, Researcher 4 also involves the local community (i.e., the technicians in the community centre) in data collection very often and on the discussion of the results, for instance, by sending the tables with the results to the technicians. *"The checkpoint coordinator, who listens to the technicians and who listens to the participants, give us feedback and we also try, as much as possible, to give feedback on the results."* In the future, this researcher would like to do more in terms of involvement. According to her: *"I would like, for example, to be able to go twice a year to make a presentation with results, discuss some problems in data collection, even to demonstrate to the partner institution that there is this care in the way the data is collected and how the information is being handled, the decisions we make. (...) I wish I did this or had done this more often."*

Finally, researchers 2 and 5 are essentially focused on **communicating their research** findings to their audiences. Considering that Researcher 2 conducts her research on a lab and her study objects are mice, she believes that **communication is the best way of involving people** in science. Researcher 2 communicates her research through an Instagram account she created for this purpose and her audiences are young people (*"from the 20s to the 30s"*) and older people, that is, a reflex of her own network of family and friends. In her words: *"I think true science communication starts with the people closest to us."*

Researcher 5 has a well-established relationship with the Portuguese Association of Plastics Manufacturers because she believes that *"the industry started wanting to be part*

of the solution”. She attends some of events organised by this association, and vice-versa, in an attempt to maintain a healthy **collaboration** between the parties.

Effective ways of interacting with citizens

All researchers, regardless of the level of involvement of citizens they advocate or use in their research, believe that **keeping an open dialogue with the public** is crucial. This means, from their perspective, creating opportunities for direct interaction, in person (e.g., forums, focus groups) or online (e.g., social media), with the possibility of discussing ideas and results, asking questions and defining priorities for research.

“Listening to the stakeholders and understanding what they need, instead of sitting down and imagining what I would like to do about that issue.” (R3)

“When we analyse the results and obtain descriptive tables, we can have this feedback from the community on the interpretation of the results. When we see, for example, that the infection is higher among men who have sex with men in the Brazilian community. We need to talk to those who do the tests, with those at the checkpoint to understand what meaning this result has for them and we often discover things. We realised, for example, in this specific case, that there is a lot of migration from Brazil and there are a lot of people who already had a diagnosis and need to access care.” (R4)

For researchers, it is also important to **develop and maintain long-term relationships** with the target groups of their research, not only because of their potential usefulness in the design of future projects that respond to the needs of the community, from a **co-creation perspective**, but also for the support that can be given by these groups when implementing measures or putting other initiatives in place. This can, ultimately, contribute to showing the value of science in everyday life.

“There were connections that already came from behind and then, in the structure of the project itself, we designed spaces for this co-creation work.” (R1)

“I want to explain things in our daily lives so that people understand that science is everywhere. I try to explain why science is not only important when a pandemic like COVID-19 comes, science is everywhere.” (R2)

“People realise that a certain knowledge was necessary in a certain community, in a certain group. And then they say “Look, those people didn’t really understand the importance of this issue. It would be important for you to go there and talk to them.” (R3)

Two researchers also mentioned that public involvement in research is seen as a **good practice by funding agencies**, such as FCT, which can help to legitimise this concern. In the words of Researcher 4: *“I think this is increasingly requested in FCT projects, other projects, other funding agencies, I think this has been more valued.”*

Barriers to social integration

The main barrier pointed out by researchers for social integration was the **distance perceived between the public and science**, the scientific community and scientific institutions (i.e., the psychological distance to science). This distance results from a **lack of knowledge of who scientists are** and what they do, and **how scientific results affect people's** lives, and can result in the public's low interest of being involved in scientific activities.

“People think “What do I, as a person, bricklayer, secretary, manager of a company, have to do with these things in academia?” (...) There is a greater perceived distance, in which there are fewer socioeconomic, cultural conditions, etc. to get in touch with science issues... “I don't want to know about that. I want to make lunch for my son and be able to buy it, have money to buy food and have time to cook it. Now these guys come with these talks”, right?” (R1)

“I think people, many people, have no idea what a scientist does.” (R2)

Another important barrier, mentioned by three researchers, is the general **public's lack of technical knowledge** to participate in some research tasks, such as data collection or data analysis. This would require, on the part of the researcher, validation of the results, which represents an increased effort for the researcher himself.

“Imagine, making a portrait of marine litter in Portugal, OK, it's interesting, but is the data well collected? Can we be confident in the way they are collected, are they right? Therefore, this doubt persists.” (R5)

With a contrary opinion, Researcher 6 points out the **coordinator's ability to train citizens** for different tasks as the only barrier to public involvement in research. In her voice: *“The limitation is mainly how good I, as a project coordinator or supervisor, am at ensuring that I properly convey instructions to that person.”*

Furthermore, Researcher 1 also mentioned that, from her experience, there are two other important barriers for social integration of citizens: **intellectual extractivism**, which can also be related to the first barrier identified by researchers, and the **sensitivity of the topic** being discussed. The first refers to an exploitation of knowledge without a proper recognition or compensation of the public's contribution. According to her: *“These academics come, you know, they want to, they want to take advantage of us and then we won't gain much from it.”*The second one seems particularly important for the Climate Change and the Covid-19 topics, and for the target group of this researcher, which is young activists for environment. In her voice:

“One of the things we face has to do with the sensitivity of this topic: climate activism, radical kids who go around throwing things (...). Radical kids who go around throwing things and who are dangerous and, therefore, have to have a certain amount of secrecy.”

4.4 About public trust in science

Researchers' perception on citizens' concerns about science

Researchers perceive **few public concerns about science**, the way it is conducted, and its outputs. There were no repeated concerns in the interview data, meaning that each concern was mentioned once by one researcher. However, three researchers recognised that **they live in a “bubble”** of people who trust science, that is, they are surrounded by people who do not show major concerns about science, which is a limitation of the notion of public.

“I kind of live in a bubble. There are some people who are with me, they are concerned about the hierarchies of power in the construction of science, that is a very critical perspective of how science is seen, but no one is doubting science per se.” (R6)

Researcher 1 commented on the **appropriation** of the public's **ideas, aspirations, worldviews** as a concern, which in her view is not only a question of personal integrity, but also of scientific integrity. This is also related to the concept of intellectual extractivism previously discussed. In her voice:

“From the perspective of young people who are very involved and committed to these issues, how will this effort, this work, these aspirations, etc., be appropriated by researchers. (...) It involves values, it involves worldviews, it involves priorities, it involves ideologies, it involves a series of issues. And therefore, it is clear that there is a difficulty here in terms of managing all these things so far in the writing process of researchers.”

Researcher 2 mentioned the **fear** that some people feel about science, especially of vaccines, because they do not know the scientific process, for instance, how vaccines are developed. According to her:

“I think people tend to be a little afraid of science and particularly, for example, vaccines. I think a lot of this fear comes from the part where science exposed the way it should be.”

Researcher 6 also shared that one time she had one participant asking about **data protection**. She said:

“When we were doing interviews with refugee students, a student asked “How my data protection is, how are you going to guarantee that...? That’s it.”

Still, researchers considered that the public holds a **good image of science** and, especially, **scientists**, which tends to contribute to less concerns and **greater trust in science**, a topic that we further discuss in the next section.

“I think that, by default, and with regard to scientists (...), the group of scientists in general are well-regarded people.” (R3)

“I think so, that it [trust in science] is high, and it is high as it is high, for example, in relation to doctors or in relation to professions that people value and that they do not fully understand.” (R5)

Researchers' perception on public trust in science

As discussed before, the researchers interviewed believe that science and scientists in Portugal enjoy a **high level of credibility and trust**. Despite this positive image of science, the researchers pointed out some **challenges for public trust** in science. Firstly, the **concept of (general) science** vs. sciences or fields of knowledge. Researcher 1 had some difficulty answering questions about trust in science because she considered that there are many different fields of knowledge and that this influences the public's level of trust.

"I always find it difficult to answer these things about science in general. Look, we're talking about astronomy, microbiology, law, communication on climate change, ..." (R1)

The **lack of scientific literacy** of the Portuguese population was perceived as a challenge to trusting science as it can contribute to the false idea that trust is already high and no measures are needed to increase it, because people do not understand the scientific process, they trust in scientists and therefore do not question them, their practices or methods.

"I think this trust is an "idol with feet of clay". Because it's not a real trust, (...) it's made of the elevation of a profession." (R5)

Researcher 1 related this problem to the education system in Portugal where *"traditionally the children are much more spectators, the school is very top down, the teacher teaches, and the pupils learn"*.

Another challenge is the **misinformation** circulating among the public or the choice of information that confirms one's own beliefs. This challenge was discussed above all in relation to vaccines, the fear and hesitation associated with them, which, for Researcher 4, had a blast during the Covid-19 pandemic.

"I'm worried, and I think it's clearly misinformation or a biased choice of information, about these anti-vaccine movements." (R4)

Not only misinformation can hinder trust in science, but also the great **amount of scientific information** produced at a very fast pace and immediately available, combined with the **lack of certainty** in science where different studies can point to different and, sometimes, inconsistent results. This challenge relates to the lack of scientific literacy as people do not know the scientific process and traditional media could have an important role in explaining this process.

"Because journalism is also very much about showing people what's important, (...) showing the whole process, from start to finish." (R2)

"One study says one thing, another study says something else (...) I think that creates more confusion in people and some distrust." (R4)

4.5 Other themes

Nothing to report.

4.6 Synthesis of recommendations

Researchers showed no difficulty in answering the question about recommendations to strengthen trust in science, but their suggestions are very diverse and target different levels (from individuals to policies) and groups.

Regarding the social integration practices, researchers made few recommendations that can be summarised in one suggestion. It is to promote the **horizontality of science** by involving the traditionally most disadvantaged and excluded audiences in scientific activities, which may require researchers meeting these groups in their own community spaces or create new spaces for this purpose.

“To bring these traditionally more disadvantaged, more excluded audiences, etc. to bring them, (...) perhaps to take, to transport ourselves researchers to that space.” (R1)

“This thing of people going to the health centre to be vaccinated, for example, I think works for the vast majority of the population, it may not work for everyone, for example, for gypsy communities, for other migrant communities that are further away. And I think that for these communities and these groups, I think there needs to be a greater effort and an effort to get closer (...). And I think that’s the only way we can help, we can get closer, and not just solve problems.” (R4)

For REI-related issues, researchers made more recommendations and linked them to science communication. For researchers it is important to **show the scientific process** in a complete and rigorous way, but understandable to the public. This suggestion is related to one of the challenges previously presented.

“As I was saying, it’s about being transparent and showing the whole scientific process and showing how it’s done, and what’s done, and what fails, and not just showing that it worked.” (R2)

However, in the interviewees’ perspective, this is not just important for the public’s trust in science. The researchers also mentioned the importance of increasing the **transparency of the scientific process among peers**. Although there are already a great number of mechanisms and processes in place to guarantee and promote scientific integrity, researchers agree that it is still not enough, and more transparency would be important. According to Researcher 4, ethics committees can play a more prominent role in this.

“On the one hand, when we want to publish an article with our results, there is a whole set of criteria and rules that have to be met. There are a number of people who check our work. And they are in a position to reject the work if they detect any kind of problem. If you say to me, but is that enough? Does it detect everything? I’d say probably not.” (R3)

“I feel that the ethics committees aren’t as demanding of us as I think they could be, in terms of us defining or safeguarding from the outset the risks that our research may have for the participants (...) because sometimes it’s just raising problems without actually helping us to find a solution.” (R4)

Finally, researchers suggested several other recommendations. Some of them are related to **science communication**, including on how to engage younger audiences in science. Researcher 2 proposed that communication with young people should essentially be based on short, humorous videos, as she attempts to do in her Instagram account currently. However, this researcher argues that science education should be the primary responsibility of schools. In her words: *“I think that this work should be done more in schools than on an Instagram page.”* To this end, Researcher 6 advocates the need for **training researchers**. She says:

“Training. You finish a PhD, and nobody sees any of this, how I communicate, how I speak, I have different audiences, who is strategic for me to speak to, how I write a press release... I just know how to write a 20-page article that’s going to be published in a Q1 journal. I don’t know how to write a 3-page press release.”

For Researcher 4, science communication can give credibility to research and reinforce the dependability of researchers, for instance, by disseminating the project goals and results in a website that everyone can access, especially if they are asked to participate in the research. She said:

“See the website, see who’s working, I think that’s very important. Even for me, so that people can go and check (...) it’s very important to have dedicated websites or even for the FCT to have a small website on the projects that it funds, so that if I search for the name of the researcher or the name of the project, I can see it.”

Following these ideas, for half of the researchers interviewed, **formal education** (e.g., schools, universities) **and teachers** play the most important role in explaining science, which could ultimately contribute to the scientific literacy of the population, a challenge mentioned earlier. However, classes must be attractive to young people.

“Classes are more about theoretical exposure and not about dealing with laboratory materials. (...) I think that actually doing more experiments and having more contact with the world and explaining these theoretical concepts that science is everywhere, and not telling them to just memorise that there are different types of rocks.” (R2)

“I think this can only be solved with better education in Portugal. (...) By practice in the sense of demonstration, demonstration of exercises, (...) demonstration with objects, with things with... And group work between them; it could also be with that role-play thing. Something where they feel like they are doing something.” (R5)

Finally, Researcher 6 argues that scientific institutions should remove the **pressure to publish**, which is mainly focused on peer-to-peer scientific dissemination, and value other forms of communication, particularly with the public. In her voice:

“It’s about taking the pressure off this international publication and valuing something else, you know? It’s not how many times my tweets are reproduced, either. It’s not that algorithmic logic either. It’s really about valuing other communication channels, other ways of communicating the result. Value a Policy Brief, value a video, a participation in a newspaper, value a publication of something that isn’t academic.”

These are the top 4 recommendations of the researchers we interviewed:

1. Increase scientific literacy through science communication and formal education
2. Promote transparency in research for the public and among peers
3. Train researchers for science communication and social integration
4. Integration is welcome, but with limits and only in certain parts of the scientific process

5 Conclusion

Here we attempt to briefly answer the specific research questions posed at the beginning of the report. We also intend to integrate the responses of mediators and researchers in an attempt to identify similarities and differences in their discourses.

The first question addressed how information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the public, which actors play a role in this, and how it affects the public's trust in science. This topic was discussed considerably more by mediators than by researchers, but the ideas are similar to the two groups: cases of misconduct or lack of scientific integrity rarely reach the public, even if they are reported by the media. Traditional media, through journalists, appear to play an important role in sharing this information, despite the lack of attention from the public. Few participants mentioned that big cases of misconduct could negatively affect public trust in science. Still, its effect seems minor because the majority of participants believe that, in Portugal, scientists are perceived as trustworthy and there is lack of scientific literacy in general.

In the second question, we intended to identify the processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science in the experts' view. For mediators, communication of research by scientists is a responsible research practice, which may require participation in different activities, from interviews or texts for a newspaper to the creation of podcasts, social media pages or involvement in school programs. Researchers consider communication an important part of their work, but not all see it as a priority, and some recognise the need for training on these topics.

Finally, the third question examined what kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how. REI topics were only superficially mentioned by mediators and researchers, but they, and their residual impact on the public's trust in science, were still discussed mostly by scientists. Both mediators and researchers mentioned the importance of social integration in science, but the mediators and social scientists considered that public involvement should be more integrated, in a bottom-up logic, while the other scientists showed less flexibility for full public involvement. Some participants, both mediators and researchers, considered that manifestations of a lack of integrity could affect trust in science, but in a very marginal way.

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poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Expert Interviews - SPAIN

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: CSIC

Author(s): Irene Monsonís Payá, Richard Woolley (CSIC)

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1 Introduction

This section provides a brief background on the objectives of the POIESIS research project and the expert interview study (EIS). It highlights inputs to EIS from previous POIESIS empirical studies within the Spanish context and summarises the process of organising and conducting interviews with mediators and researchers.

1.1 Research questions for Task 2.3

The Expert Interview study contributes to answering the following research questions that guide POIESIS.

General research questions	More specific research questions
<p>RQ2: To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?</p> <p>RQ3: To what extent and how does the <i>integration</i> of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?</p>	<p>How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?</p> <p>Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?</p> <p>What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?</p>

1.2 Insights from Task 2.2 and Task 3.1

The POIESIS project implements a large empirical programme to respond to the project's objectives. The EIS presented in this report is the third empirical study of POIESIS.

In the summer of 2023, seven public deliberative workshops with citizens (one in each member country of the project consortium) were organized. The Spanish public deliberative workshop included a group of twenty citizens with interest and previous links to the system of science and, in general, with limited experience in engagement in science participation activities as citizens.

In the spring of 2024, 21 focus groups (three per country) with institutional actors were held. In the Spanish focus groups participants had professional backgrounds in issues related to REI (one

focus group), science communication, dissemination and citizen science practices (group 2), and management backgrounds in diverse science and innovation organisations (group 3).

The following patterns observed in the Spanish public deliberative workshop and the focus groups are expected to be relevant in relation to the expert interviews:

- Participants in the focus groups generally affirmed that trust in scientists, as a socially valued profession, had been historically high in Spain and remained so now. Also in the Public Deliberative Workshop no negative attitudes towards science were presented. Citizens' concerns were related to the scientific system and how science communication is done.
- The credibility of information sources of and the perceived rigour of individual science communicators were mentioned as factors determining participating citizens' trust in a particular piece of information.
- Participants in the Focus Group study considered that the strong level of public trust could be under threat, due to the new patterns of communication through social media platforms that had opened up a space in which scientific credibility was undermined by 'vocal minorities'.
- In the workshop there was a common attitude towards research integrity as an issue connected with specific cases where scientists did not execute "good science".
- Institutional and organisational development of research ethics and integrity (REI) in Spain was perceived by the focus groups participants to be in an early stage of its development and professional institutionalization.
- The citizens participating in the workshops did not share previous experiences of participating in science as citizens and the discussion about public integration in research aroused the interest of the group. Despite the general interest in participation, there were some concerns raised regarding the way in which the research would be designed to include citizens, how the results would be used, and a desirable level of participation of citizens in science.
- The institutional actors in the focus groups consistently identified barriers and difficulties that accompany efforts to enhance citizen participation in research in Spain. However, many examples were also given about the benefits of such integration. Some arguments against integration came from participants in institutional roles distant from research.
- Participants in the Spain Focus Groups believe that REI practices and the integration of citizens could be improved through sustained efforts to improve institutional governance and process management.

1.3 Brief summary of organising the interviews

For the Spanish study, six researchers and eleven mediators have been interviewed. The experts were recruited on the basis of their professional experience and taking into account the different pre-established criteria for the study.

Potential interviewees were identified through desk research and network recommendations and a total of 31 experts were contacted (16 women and 15 male). The Spanish study sample included two international profiles, one researcher with a prominent communication role during the COVID-19 pandemic and one mediator within an international working environment.

Potential interviewees received an invitation email to participate in the study and, in some cases, a reminder. A POIESIS information sheet was shared with the initial email, including the basic description of the project, its objectives, and the relevant information about data processing and data protection procedures. After acceptance, the informed consent form was sent to participants. The information sheet and the informed consent were translated into Spanish. The communication with the experts was made both in Spanish and in Valenciano.

All the interviews were conducted online and the average length was one hour, with the shortest being 40 minutes and the longest 90 minutes. The interviews took place between 10th May and the 31st of July, 2024.

1.4 Data processing

Interviews were recorded and transcribed through Microsoft Teams and with a face-to-face recorder. The transcription provided through Microsoft Teams were checked to assure accuracy. During this checking process, the transcriptions were pseudonymised and all the potential sensitive information that could lead to identification of the expert were identified and, where necessary, substituted by generic references. Subsequently, interview transcripts were coded in the software NVivo using the codebook contained in the EIS Protocol.

All interviews have been securely stored in a specified project system folder with access restricted to the two researchers participating in the Spanish study.

2 Participants in the Expert Interview study

This section contains ten tables compiling information about the researchers and mediators participating in the Spanish EIS. The information in these tables was added immediately after completing interviews in most cases, with additional information being added following preparation of interview transcripts in some cases.

2.1 Mediators

Tables 1-7 compile relevant information on the Spanish mediator sample.

Table 1. Demographics and occupation

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Mediator type**	Organization type (where applicable)	Occupational Description	Topic CV/CC#
ES_M01	Male	Early	Institutional mediator	Research organization	Head of communication (internal and external)	CV
ES_M02	Male	Mid	Professional science writer/communicator // Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. // Other content creator	Independent	Producer, author and editor	General science
ES_M03	Male	Mid	Professional science writer/communicator // Other content creator	Independent	Author and independent science communicator	CC
ES_M04	Male	Mid	Professional science writer/communicator	Communication consultancy	Author	CC
ES_M05	Male	Mid	Professional science writer/communicator	Think Tank, journal (previously)	Editor	CC, CV
ES_M06	Female	Senior	Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. // Other content creator	Science school	Coordinator	General science

ES_M07	Male	Mid	Author of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc. // Other content creator	Educational system and independent	Author	STEM
ES_M08	Female	Senior	Professional science writer/communicator	Independent	Author and illustrator	CV, CC
ES_M09	Male	Senior	Institutional mediator	Public university	Head of communication	General
ES_M10	Female	Senior	Institutional mediator // Other content creator	Research organization and independent	Head of communication (internal and external)	General
ES_M11	Male	Senior	Science Journalist	Newspaper	Editor of S&T news section	General

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior

** Mediator type:

- Institutional Mediators working at publishers / working at universities or research institutes;
- Non-institutional mediators: a) Professional science writers/communicators; Science/general journalists; Authors of science-related blogs, podcasts, etc.; Other content creators

Covid-19 or Climate Change or both (where applicable).

Table 2. Mediators' main communication tasks

Id.	Description of mediators' main tasks
ES_M01	`Translating' material from the research institute to various outputs and managing the internal communication of the institute
ES_M02	Identifying salient topics and conducting background research and producing various outputs
ES_M03	Conducting background research to produce various outputs
ES_M04	`Translating' material from RPO to other professionals of science communication
ES_M05	Conducting background research to produce various outputs
ES_M06	Developing educational scientific programs and conducting background research to produce various outputs
ES_M07	Conducting background research to produce various outputs
ES_M08	Conducting background research to produce various outputs
ES_M09	`Translating' material from the university community to various outputs
ES_M10	`Translating' material from the research institute to various outputs and managing the internal communication of the institute
ES_M11	Conducting background research to produce press articles

Table 3. Outputs produced by Mediators

Id.	Books	Articles	Audiovisual (TV)	Radio program	Podcast	Audiovisual (social media)	Text Post (Social media)*	Live (social media interaction)	Other: (please describe in a few words only)
ES_M01							X		Newsletters, posters, protocols, press releases, events (conference, seminar), satisfaction surveys
ES_M02	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	Live events
ES_M03	X	X	X	X	X		X		
ES_M04									Webinars and face-to-face interaction, press releases
ES_M05		X				X	X		Scripts for interviews in press, TV and radio
ES_M06		X	X	X					Scientific educational materials, training, live events
ES_M07	X					X			Conferences, art performance
ES_M08	X					X			Illustration, art exhibitions, Live events
ES_M09						X	X		Newsletters, press releases, events
ES_M10						X	X		Newsletters, press releases, events // Live performance
ES_M11		X							

*Includes memes, photographs, videos and text

Table 4. Channels used by Mediators

Id.	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)						Chat apps		Other: (please describe in a few words only)
	TV	Radio	Newspaper	Websites	Blogs	Newsletters	LinkedIn	YouTube	Twitter	Instagram	TikTok	Other SN	WhatsApp	Telegram	
ES_M01	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X						
ES_M02	X	X	X		X			X		X					Live events
ES_M03	X	X	X		X				X						
ES_M04						X	X		X						Webinars and face-to-face interaction
ES_M05	X	X	X				X		X	X					
ES_M06	X	X	X												Live events
ES_M07				X	X				X	X					Live events and shows
ES_M08				X				X	X	X					
ES_M09				X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	Live events
ES_M10		X		X			X	X	X	X		X			Podcast // Live events
ES_M11			X				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	

Table 5. Audience addressed by Mediators

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' audiences/size* estimate where known
ES_M01	Companies (for knowledge transfer), universities, media, the general public (especially: science professionals trained in similar topics as the ones of the research center, university students, high-school and vocational students, and senior students). Approximate size of the audience: more than 10.000 followers on LinkedIn and more than 3.000 followers on Twitter.
ES_M02	Varies across activities but in general terms: 30+, medium-high level of formal education and equally distributed by gender. Approximate size of the audience: From 10.000 and 50.000 followers in different social networks
ES_M03	Varies across activities: general public in live events and mainstream media, higher % of male and expert knowledge in X; interested in nature and higher % of women in Instagram. Approximate size of the audience: From 10.000 and 50.000 followers in some social networks
ES_M04	Other science professional mediators in the field of climate change.
ES_M05	General public and specific interest in profiles skeptical of climate change related issues
ES_M06	Varies across activities: Youth people from 3 to 18 years for science educational programmes and the general public for traditional media.
ES_M07	Younger adults, general public with at least secondary formal education, people interested in STEM. Approximate size of the audience: less than 10.000 followers
ES_M08	General public and some outputs are addressed to children and teenagers, specifically. Approximate size of the audience: less than 10.000 followers
ES_M09	General public. Approximate size of the audience: less than 10.000 followers
ES_M10	General public. Approximate size of the audience: more than 50.000 followers in some social networks
ES_M11	General public, including scientific communities. Approximate size of the audience: more than 1.000.000 followers in the social networks of the newspaper.

*Nanoinfluencers (less than 10.000 followers), Microinfluencers (from 10.000 to 50.000 followers), Influencers (50.000 to 500.000 followers) and Macroinfluencers (from 500.000 to 1.000.000 followers)

Table 6. Mediators' interactions with citizens

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' social interaction practices
ES_M01	Formal interaction through (online) social networks in an institutional style.
ES_M02	Live events and limited interaction with specific profiles in social networks
ES_M03	High level of interaction in live events and social media discussions
ES_M04	No direct interaction with citizens but with other mediators
ES_M05	No direct interaction with citizens but with other mediators
ES_M06	High level of interaction in live events
ES_M07	High level of interaction in live events and online social networks
ES_M08	High level of interaction in live events
ES_M09	High level of interaction in live events and follow-up of social media discussions
ES_M10	High level of interaction in live events and follow-up of social media discussions
ES_M11	No direct interaction with citizens but with other mediators and sources of information

Table 7. Mediators' sources of information

Id.	Interpersonal networks		Science press releases	RPOS	Publishers	Mainstream media	Social media	Other: (please add text)
	With researchers	With science communicators						
ES_M01	X	X						
ES_M02	X		X	X	X			Text books, other professional networks and institutions
ES_M03	X		X	X	X	X	X	Other professional networks
ES_M04	X	X	X					Other professional networks and institutions
ES_M05	X	X	X	X				Other professional networks and institutions, Legislation.
ES_M06	X	X	X			X	X	Other professional networks and institutions
ES_M07		X	X				X	Dissemination books and blogs; Wikipedia; other professional networks
ES_M08	X	X	X					
ES_M09	X	X	X					
ES_M10	X	X	X					Other professional networks
ES_M11	X		X	X	X			Repositories of legal cases

2.2 Researchers

Tables 8-11 compile information about the researcher sample for the Spanish EIS.

Table 8. Description of the Researcher interviews sample

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Position or title/Career stage**	Organisation type	Topic CV/CC#
ES_R01	Female	Senior	Leading researcher	Public Research Institute	CV
ES_R02	Female	Senior	Leading researcher	Public Research Institute	CC
ES_R03	Female	Mid	Associate professor, 5-year personal career grant	University	CV
ES_R04	Male	Senior	Senior researcher*	Public Research Institute	CV
ES_R05	Male	Senior	Senior researcher*	Public Research Institute	CC
ES_R06	Male	Mid	Recognised researcher	Public Research Institute	CC

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior

** ECR; recognised researcher; senior researcher; leading researcher (Professor)

Table 9. Researcher notes

Id.	Note
ES_R01	Researcher of natural sciences working in research related to the development of vaccines. Active communicator during the pandemic.
ES_R02	Researcher with background in natural and social sciences working in research linked to climate change with participatory methods. Actively engaged in IPCC.
ES_R03	Researcher on natural sciences working in research related to tracking genetic mutations of viruses and their geographic spread. Active communicator during the pandemic.
ES_R04	Researcher on social sciences developing social research of the impact of the pandemic.
ES_R05	Researcher on natural sciences working on research linked to climate change. Active communicator of climate change.
ES_R06	Researcher with background in natural and social sciences working in research linked to climate change with participatory methods.

Table 10. How Researchers work with the public

Id.	Brief description of how the researchers' work reaches the public
ES_R01	Through mass traditional media during the pandemic.
ES_R02	Through the IPCC communication outputs following the IPCC protocols of communication. Her specific research outputs reach the public mainly through the direct interaction of the stakeholders she works with.
ES_R03	Through a dedicated public website, designed for scientists and the public; through TV, radio interviews, both regular (fortnightly) and on demand; through Twitter and social media promotion; 80,000 personal followers on X
ES_R04	Through direct interactions and exchanges during all the research cycle with the stakeholders of his line of research
ES_R05	Through the channels used to carry out dissemination activities and live events.
ES_R06	Through the direct interactions and exchanges with the stakeholders he works with.

Table 6. Description of social integration practices of Researchers

Id.	Brief notes of Researchers' social integration practices
ES_R01	Participates in different dissemination events with the general public, including with primary and secondary students.
ES_R02	Develops transdisciplinary research with stakeholders of her research lines, developing a strong relationship based on confidence and cooperation in projects.
ES_R03	Citizens directly involved in data cleaning, preparation, and interpretation in GitHub community that identifies, annotates and names new Covid-19 variants based on sequencing data from around the world
ES_R04	Develop activities of cooperation and co-creation with societal actors in all the different phases of the research projects.
ES_R05	Limited to dissemination and communication practices
ES_R06	Develops transdisciplinary research with stakeholders of his research lines, developing a strong relationship based on confidence and cooperation in projects.

3 Analysis of Mediator interviews

This section analyses the results of the interviews conducted with our Mediators in Spain, three interviews were conducted with institutional mediators and 10 interviews with non-institutional mediators.

Institutional mediators are science communication professionals working in research performing organizations, this is research centres and universities. Non-institutional mediators are people who either professionally or as amateurs transmit scientific information through mediation chains. They are independent of scientists, researchers, and institutions performing the research that they communicate. Non-institutional mediators can be divided into two main groups. On the one hand, four science popularisers who develop professional or semi-professional communication outputs but have (or are looking for) another primary job as a way of living and, on the other hand, four science journalists and science communication professionals dedicated full-time to science communication activity. Concerning the last group, certain differences can be observed depending on whether their work is paid by mass media and aimed at mainstream communication (two mediators), or whether they are paid by private organizations (non-for-profit) and aimed at opinion creation and content mobilisation (two mediators).

3.1 Chains of mediation

The position in the mediation network is varied between the members of the three groups of mediators described above. Institutional mediators mainly cover the part of the mediation chain closest to the laboratory, limiting themselves to transferring the research carried out in their workplaces through the network. Science mobilisers describe networks that are very dispersed in terms of inputs received and also in terms of their ability to reach the public. Content creators in mainstream media also have a great diversity of input providers and a large reach to the general public, but with little interaction. Finally, science journalists working with private organisations to generate public opinion also have a wide diversity of sources and contacts for their outputs, passing information through mediation chains to other carefully selected specialised mediators. The position of mediators in the mediation chain and the characteristics of the creative process they develop through this chain are developed in more detail below.

Institutional mediators are characterised by having very close contact with the scientists who produce the science they communicate. In fact, the work of these mediators is characterised by the fact that it consists of communicating the science produced in the institution in which they work. They aim to do so in the

best possible way and try to achieve the greatest possible media impact for their organisation. Thus, the main source of information for these mediators is the scientists of the institution in which they work and the scientific articles or patents they produce. This type of mediator has a high level of confidence in the veracity of the scientific information they communicate. While There are some factors that may lead these mediators to be suspicious about the veracity of the information they work with, these are mentioned only in a very residual way.

The creative process described by the three interviewees in this category is very homogeneous. Firstly, they identify recent research results produced by their institutions that may be newsworthy. This identification process can occur either because the researchers themselves contact the mediator to articulate a communication strategy on the results obtained, or because the mediator reviews the articles or patents produced by the institution and contacts the researchers to propose a communication strategy. This is where the process of creating communication outputs, traditionally press releases, begins. The content creation process involves interactive work between the mediator and the scientist. Sometimes this process involves collaboration with other institutional mediators from centres that have participated in the research being communicated. Once the communicative output is prepared, the mediator moves it among his or her network of contacts, made up of scientific journalists who may be interested in the topic and who can communicate it to the public through the media.

Institutional mediators consider as key groups in their mediation network the scientists from whom they receive inputs, the community of institutional mediators and science communicators with whom they collaborate and share professional concerns, and the science journalists to whom they transmit their outputs to be placed in the media.

Institutional mediators also produce outputs to be communicated in institutional communication networks. These direct-to-public communication strategies, however, do not produce close interactions with the public. The mediators interviewed agree in describing the interaction with the public through networks as very institutionalised and describe their role in the institution as one that involves enhancing and favouring interaction with researchers, with the mediators remaining in a secondary role and with little visibility towards the public.

We are always in the shadows, that is, we don't have any kind of leading role, unless we have to present an event or we have to call someone and do a kind of, well, I don't know, moderate a table. In that case, yes, but not us. We don't have a leading role, the leading role always goes to those who do the research. ES_M10

With regard to the group of non-institutional mediators, the content creators we have called science popularisers are characterised by creating content whose end and direct user is the general population or, in some cases, a very specific population group such as children and young people. The science popularisers are characterised by the fact that they carry out their communication and dissemination activities autonomously, without having to follow the objectives of any institution. Thus, in this group we find mediators with a great deal of freedom in selecting the topics they deal with. The creative process begins with the identification of topics that are of interest to them and on which they carry out a research process. This process is characterised by the consultation of a wide range of sources and the development of strategies to verify the credibility of the sources and information they handle.

The creative process is practically the research process. I call all my things the scientific process, because it's the same thing: research, hypotheses, I could go this way, no... the creative process for me is the same. ES_M08

This group of mediators is also characterised by having direct contact with the general public, either through face-to-face events or through the use of social media, depending on the channels they use to promote their work. Furthermore, these mediators are characterised by the fact that they consider that success in their work is linked to having a direct impact on citizens.

The third group of mediators interviewed are science journalists or experts in science communication. This group includes four interviewees whose careers have been spent working to develop content for major media outlets or for consultancies, think tanks, or organisations with an interest in influencing public opinion. This group of mediators also has access to a wide range of information sources, including scientific articles (sometimes while embargoed by internationally prestigious academic journals) and reports from organisations or specialised repositories, among others. These mediators have high-level networks of contacts that enable them to cross-check the information they receive, access information and mobilise the results of their work throughout mediation chains. Thus, interviewees in these categories regard contacts with people in major media outlets, political parties, ministries, among others, as professional networks necessary to carry out their work.

Of the four people interviewed in this category, we identified similarities in the creative process carried out by the two professionals who work to create content in the mainstream media and the two professionals who work for private organisations (consultancy and think tank).

The professionals working for the media have a much wider margin to select the topics they work on, even though they may be limited by

subject matter. The creative process they develop involves the search for very diverse sources and contact with a large number of experts to cross-check the information and ensure the veracity of the sources, often using people from outside the institutional environment in which they work. The products of their work, once finalised, will reach the general public through mass media channels both on- and offline. The interaction of these mediators with the general public is relatively moderate. If it occurs at all, it is due more to their personal willingness to interact with end-users on social networks than as an integral aspect of their work. One interviewee in this category reflects on the dual role that some of the end users of their work have, as they are both consumers of information and sources of information for the development of future pieces.

Science journalists working for private organisations are more restricted in their choice of the topics they report on, as these are more tightly framed by the focus of the organisation they work for. However, the creative process is rich in the use of diverse sources and interaction with high-level contacts, both as sources and transmitters of information. The two interviewees in this category, when asked about the criteria used to evaluate the veracity of the sources, refer first of all to the importance of trust and the reputation of the people and institutions with which they collaborate in their work. They also report the use of verification strategies through specialised colleagues in the institutions and organisations in which they work. The objective of the work of these two mediators is linked to the creation of opinion, both among the general public and political decision-makers, but never aimed directly at the general public, but rather at mobilising the messages to be transmitted through other communication professionals, especially scientific journalists. Both interviewees state that they monitor the public opinion expressed on their social networks but do not implement direct communication strategies through these networks with their followers.

3.2 About research ethics and integrity (REI)

Mediators did not spontaneously refer to REI issues in the interviews, only mentioning relevant aspects when directly asked. Two interviewees referred to aspects related to research integrity when reflecting on the sources of information they handle and the credibility they give to them, referring to the fact that they sometimes come across unverified or incorrect information. In one case, the existence of accurate research results in projects is considered as an integrity issue that goes beyond the responsibility of the research team, with responsibility being assigned to the project's funding organization.

The sources I use, I rate them high, that is to say, in general everything is good. Sometimes I come across things that bother me a lot because I can't understand them. I'll give you an example because how the interview will be anonymized... I can't get into trouble. The [mentions an entity] fund projects that have information that is not verified at all. ES_M08

In general, interviewees understand what the ethical and integrity aspects of research are, although only a few distinguish between the two concepts in a precise way. When addressing these questions, some themes recur in several interviews. Several mediators refer to issues related to the correct citation of sources, non-plagiarism of research ideas or projects, or independence and honesty with respect to funding bodies or own research agendas.

Some interviewees incorporate aspects of ethics and integrity that intersect with the policies at institutional level in science and innovation systems. For example, they reflect on the moral role of scientists in ensuring that the results of their research are accessible or that the working conditions of the people who join their teams are adequate and dignified.

Another aspect that I would like to be able to take more into account is that they have a work ethic in terms of labour rights, but because of the way the communication sector and the research sector is, I can't always take this into account as much as I would like to. I apply it, but I have collaborators who do not. ES_M02

And then there's something about honesty, but many variables come into play, and that's the issue of accessibility, that is to say that what you're doing as a researcher is accessible to the whole world. I strongly believe in open access. ES_M03

Several interviewees highlight aspects related to the coherence of researchers as an expression of the ethical quality of the academic profession 'having a set of rationalised values and that you stick to them, basically' (ES_M02). References to researchers' coherence are not only limited to research activity but also to researchers'

lifestyles, as reflected in this quote from a climate change communicator.

Then in the tangible and real inconsistency, that is to say to be researching climate change and to be taking forty planes. I won't say names, but... ES_M03

Finally, a couple of researchers, when asked about REI aspects, reflect on aspects related to the choice of research topics and direction of science, linking research ethics and integrity with statements on the need to develop (and even prioritise) lines of research useful for solving real problems at the global level.

The most valuable thing in a scientific investigation is the integrity, in a global way, that is to say that this person. Yes, I really appreciate the scientists he works for, who research and work and give their lives for really urgent current issues. ES_M08

Then, for me, ethics and honesty are also very strict, but I think we should try to investigate more to solve the root of many problems, much more than to try to patch things up. In other words, many times I think we are investigating very partial solutions or a lot of "I don't want to change the big part, let's see how we can stop the water leaks". And I think that if you are honest, in itself, then you should understand that putting as much effort as you put in, I who know about things about carbon capture, well it's still not where we have to go, we still have to invest these resources in another field to be able to face the climate crisis as a guarantee. ES_M03

The mediators' descriptions of **how REI aspects affect their work** and the assessment strategies they use show patterns associated with the mediators' positions in mediation chains. Institutional mediators initially assume high reliability in the sources they use, which are those provided by colleagues in their institutions. The institutional mediators state that they do not have the scientific training necessary to assess the technical aspects related to research ethics. They trust the institutional mechanisms that oversee them (the ethics committees) as a criterion assuring the ethical quality of the work carried out in their institution.

I don't have the training to question the content of the articles or if what they are telling me is true or not, but they are usually articles already published in journals, usually with quite... well indexed, with quite good ranking. ES_M01

It is true that I am not a scientist, I cannot assess whether the content is more or less authentic. ES_M10

[Referring to the Ethics Committee] I do not really know if that is the procedure, but I think that the [ethics] committee always reviews all the projects or the research that is done.

So... Eh... I believe that research projects are usually based on ethical criteria. ES_M01

Let's see, we are speakers about the work that is carried out in the research laboratories of [mentions the organisation where he works]. And in this research body, research is all subject to a bioethics committee, etcetera. ES_M09

One of the institutional mediators reflects on the importance of the REI aspects for the whole institution, as a reputational problem would affect not only individuals but the whole group.

And also that your reputation is at stake, not only for the scientist, but for the whole centre. ES_M10

On the other hand, the non-institutional mediators made no mention whatsoever of institutional mechanisms for managing ethics and scientific. However, they did refer to the quality of scientific journals as a factor to be considered in the assessment of the technical and ethical solvency of research.

But as long as it makes moderate claims and I can see from the methodology that there is nothing strange, then I go ahead, especially if it also comes from a journal that has a certain impact, which is not a total guarantee. ES_M02

Above all, the first filter is the credibility we give to the source. It is not the same to read something in El País or in Nature as it is to read it in a digital Mediterranean or on a page, which is the first time you read it, that you find in a Ws [referring to www.] ES_M05

The group of science content creators who, as we indicated in the previous section, had access to very diverse sources, thus described the use of strategies through which they themselves evaluate the quality and reliability of the sources.

Science journalists, on the other hand, agree in using consultations with experts and their contact networks as a filter to assess the validity of the sources they handle.

It is, unfortunately, something that has more to do with smell and in terms of intuition and the times I have read about an article, but whenever they make statements that I know are outside the state of the art, of their discipline, I consult experts to tell me a little bit if this is possible, that is, if it is controlled, if they are totally disproportionate statements and if I have doubts about whether it is within the state of the art, I also ask, logically. ES_M02

I have several sources like that, experts in scientific ethics, so we send them the paper, as we have access to the papers under embargo, a few days before publication we have 5

or 6 days to send it to experts in ethics and they tell us, well, I don't see any problem in making an embryo with a mixture of human and monkey cells, or if this is controversial as it is ethics, there are opinions for all tastes, right?
ES_M11

In the case of science journalists working for private organisations, both interviewees refer to the importance of the reputation of sources in their professional network as well as the support with technical profiles within their own organisation and in their informal network of colleagues.

Well, I think it's partly based on the confidence of having worked with them before and also knowing that they have a profile, how can I say, that they have a publicly known profile, that they have published, well, that they have published in scientific journals or in the case of think tanks, that they participate, they participate in international forums, that is to say, external sources of legitimacy, right? We don't analyse the data again. It is true that what we do is review what is written and make sure that it makes sense. And then we trust them, because they are people who have a reputation. ES_M04

Credibility is one of our main, if not the main, currency we have to achieve our goals and if journalists can't trust us, then we won't achieve anything because they won't trust us.
ES_M04

What I also try to do is, as I have a team of technicians behind me, when I see something, I send it to them... [...] we are lucky that we have a top team of highly qualified people.
ES_M05

And then on the other hand, it is true that when there is something important, something big, I have always had contact with... I have a group, a chat with other colleagues from other media. The contact between us, between journalists who specialise in these issues, I think it is also key. ES_M05

Regarding the impact of fraudulent practices in research on mediators' work, several aspects are mentioned. On the one hand, a couple of mediators report experiences where they have felt pressure to publish information that might not meet the standards they would have considered by their employers.

When I have not given credibility to something and I have no choice but to publish because it happens, the way to do it is usually by not signing the piece. ES_M05

If I receive a paper and, for whatever reason, the alarm bells ring that the paper might contain false data. That affects my

integrity as well. I cannot lend a voice to a product that I know is not real; I am risking my own reputation and that of the whole centre. Another thing is that you are an errand boy and you have to publish it because the director tells you, 'This is going to be published'. ES_M10

Several mediators introduced views on the role of scientists in science communication. On the one hand, some interviewees consider it inherent to scientists' jobs that they should communicate research results to the public. Furthermore, in the area of climate change, several mediators reflected on whether or not scientists and communicators should participate in interviews or debates in which they share space with climate change deniers. The mediators presented different views on this issue, some advocating non-participation and others the opposite.

ID here	Additional quotes
ES_M05	The issue of, above all, ensuring that the final source of funding for publications is public, that there is no private entity.

3.3 About public trust in science

The mediators interviewed were very conscious and reflective about the impact of their work on citizens' trust in science, a topic they were particularly comfortable talking about.

Mediators' perceptions of the current degree of public confidence in science was mixed. On the one hand, some mediators felt that public trust is at very low levels "I believe that in order to build trust, and I don't say reinforce it because trust is at a low ebb in many respects right now, you have to be very transparent about how you come to your conclusions" (ES_M02). On the other hand, other mediators stated that there are high levels of trust in Spanish society and referred to data reported every two years by FECYT's Social Perception of Science and Technology Surveys, as well as other recently published studies on the perception of climate change among European citizens.

One of the project's case studies, the COVID crisis, was described as an event that changed the public's perception of science. One mediator linked this health crisis to a transformation of the public's interest in science, which came to accept scientific information at face value. Without expressly mentioning COVID, an excess of trust or faith in scientific results was also pointed out by another mediator:

It has been intuitively accepted that the scientist is almost like a magician, that s/he knows because s/he knows and therefore whatever s/he says goes and that scientists should all agree, that scientists should have immediate answers. The reality is that they don't, and when we are confronted with a situation that is relevant to the public and therefore goes on from day to day, they find very clearly that the reality is different from what they suspected and that affects trust.

ES_M02

The pandemic changed the way the public understands, listens, is interested in science in general, and then they were super on fire and super prepared and super interested to listen to you. and they went from 0 to everything, because they believed everything, you told them anything and it was an audience that you could deceive directly, telling them anything. What happened? Okay, we're talking about people who don't have to know about science, okay? So, explaining to them that science ... is very complicated because they need to start, develop and finish. The public needs to understand and live a complete scientific process, in their own flesh and in general in the flesh of the society around them. ES_M08

Much has also been said about the impact of the pandemic on the public's confidence in science, and I think it is a very positive impact. In other words, within the labyrinth that the COVID had us in, let's just say that I believe that researchers, their image and therefore that of science, came out better off.

ES_M09

The difficulties linked to the management of science communication related to the COVID crisis were also the subject of reflection by several mediators.

[In the scientific community with which I work] we have never had to deal with things similar to those faced in other sciences, such as COVID-19. ES_M10

Regarding the role of scientists and mediators in the trust-building process, several interviewees considered the professional roles and capacities of scientists and mediators to be central to building trust in science.

Let's say that both communication and scientific dissemination have become more professional, and this, I believe, has a direct effect on the public's confidence. ES_M09

I think there is a high level of concern in Spain [about climate change]. The polls, I don't know how much came out the other day, but I think people have a high level of concern and I think this is also because science and the people who disseminate science are doing things well. ES_M05

Some climate change mediators highlighted the idea that the success of their work was not limited to building trust in science but to go a step further and being able to encourage changes in people's lifestyles.

I don't write to learn more, to earn money, because you don't earn so much writing in this country, nor for the ego. I write to change consciences, to activate people, to transform reality.
ES_M03

I think that scientists and everybody in this Community are very aware that when we talk about climate impacts, if we lie, if we exaggerate too much, people will stop believing in what is being said and then more and more people will start to deny climate change or think that it is exaggerated. And then they won't act and they won't, and there won't be a change in society. [...] Without people's trust in scientists, well there will be no climate action and I think that's a priority. ES_M04

One mediator introduced an interesting reflection regarding the lack of scientific evidence on the real impact of the work of science communicators in building trust. According to this mediator, there are currently no indicators to identify the impact of their work on citizens. This is why the impact is measured through entertainment indicators, which may be a proxy for the ability to contribute to the creation of a more solid scientific culture.

As communicators, we are not getting a clear parameter to know how what we say is affecting society. So I stick to what I can verify, which is the level of entertainment. The normalisation of science as just another form of culture, like someone who goes to a concert and assumes that they can enjoy music without this having any repercussions on them wanting to be a musician. Without anyone, therefore, believing that just because they like science, they have to be a scientist. ES_M02

Along the same lines, this mediator reflected on the real impact that scientific dissemination through social networks can have, referring to the need to improve knowledge on whether or not the short live videos that have become popular in recent years have an impact on the population that accesses them.

We are focusing so much on obtaining numbers that we are betting on platforms such as vertical videos, whose impact on society has not yet been sufficiently studied, but everything suggests that it is very low, people who are scrolling for hours and do not remember what they saw five minutes ago. The numbers are huge, but it has less impact than YouTube and YouTube has very large numbers, but it has less impact than giving a talk in a village, so for me that's very important and that's why it's not the meter. ES_M02

Regarding the mediators' views on the impact of news about fraud and bad scientific practices on citizens' attitudes towards science, different narratives were also identified. On the one hand, regarding the direct impact on public trust in science, there were mediators whose perception was that news of fraud in science does not reach the public and therefore does not undermine the level of trust in science, while others pointed to the amplifying function that negative news has on the public.

Even when [Research Performing Organisations] fail to contain it with their levees [the news about fraud or malpractice], it still doesn't reach the public and therefore, I think the impact ends up being small. EN_M02

The existing trade-off between the positive and negative impact of the publication of news about fraud in science was exposed by a couple of mediators who consider that news about fraud has a positive impact. Although it might have a negative impact on the public's perception of science, in the long run it contributes to the improvement of the science system by exposing its weaknesses and discouraging lack of integrity among the scientific community that might be exposed.

It is true that there is a journalist who I think is doing a spectacular job [...] in the newspaper El País, who has uncovered different frauds and I think it is essential that they are uncovered. That this implies that citizens have more misgivings or that they don't see science as clean as possible. Well, I don't know, but I welcome the debate, I mean, what cannot be allowed is for fraudulent practices to be covered up and journalism one of its fundamental raisons d'être is to tell what others don't want you to tell. Always within the truth, obviously. And if the impact is negative, I think it will be negative in the first place, but not in the long term, because what is unethical is not intact, what is fraudulent must be exposed. EN_M09

I think they are positive because in the end what they achieve is to improve the system. [I think that in the end, the result is that the system is more reliable. ES_M11

Finally, most mediators do not report specific cases in which news of scientific fraud directly affects their work, although several of them report scandals that have occurred close to their professional network. Some mediators report having personally experienced or knowing of situations in which scientific mediators have been pressured by their superiors not to publish information (see previous section), or by scientists to not uncover scandals that could affect them. Regarding the impact of fraudulent practices in large Research Performing Organisations, one institutional mediator describes criticisms received in networks from citizens that encompass all the centres or departments of the

organisation when criticising a case that occurred in only one of them.

Personally, I don't personally feel that my work is controversial, but when, for example, there is a case in the Research Performing Organisation where I work, we all receive mentions on social networks. Or we get discrediting from people who, for personal reasons or political interests or whatever, want to stir up trouble against us or things like that. So, in the end it affects us negatively. EN_M01

ID here	Additional quotes
ES_M01	I think it has a lot to do with building trust in science, because I see it as a public service that is being provided, with public money, that people often don't know about. Without my work and that of the people who do my job, people would not know about it, or would know about it much less. At the end of the day, you are showing and making people aware of what society's money is being invested in and what kind of research is being done, and above all, for what purposes and with what criteria.
ES_M01	It is also true that I think that often the media are also to some extent to blame for the type of coverage they provide, which is often not entirely rigorous, so that in the end this contributes to generating a distorted image of what is being done, or of the research or the results. In this communication meeting, for example, we were shown a very paradigmatic and quite recent case, which is the politicisation we are seeing with the Doñana biological station, and how it is being used as a political weapon and how the media are often distorting the information or evidence and how, in the end, it is discouraging people from taking sides and taking action to solve the difficult situation that is being experienced there.
ES_M02	If we try on the one hand to normalise that science is culture and that it should not be treated as if it were on an altar with respect to other forms of Culture, I don't say other forms of obtaining knowledge, but other forms of Culture, that would already be a step. And I believe that the second step is that this normalisation should include talking about methodology, about how results are reached and not being afraid to use moderators of our affirmations such as 'can', 'almost' and these types of words.
ES_M05	I think it's very fashionable to say 'you won't see this in the media. They don't tell you this', but I think that

	<p>most serious media are not going to publish things that are fraudulent. I'd like to think that most of the time they are mistakes. And man, I think that when it happens, well, in the cases that have happened, maybe in newspapers that used to be serious, it does dynamite people's confidence a bit, but not only in science, but in information as such, as a right.</p>
ES_M06	<p>When people tell me that they have learned about a subject because of what I have told them, for example. Or that it seems simple and explainable. The fact that I really see that the message has arrived and then I realise, well, if someone comments on it, for example, or retweets what I have posted. Or that I see that there is a circulation, right, of my informative work, or that they call me to give more courses, or that, well, my students propose it to other people, right, so that I go more [to give training in other places], that my message really gets through and they like the way I have of transmitting it, but for me it is a real success and it is wonderful, it makes me feel very good.</p>
ES_M06	<p>If the people who disseminate science are not professionals, or are not scientists, or are not good science disseminators, then the audience receives not only a poor conception of science and dissemination, but also the science they are receiving is not authentic, it is not good, it is fakes and fallacies. So, well, I think that this link, this nexus is vital, that is, that the person who disseminates, the person who teaches science is reliable, trustworthy, it is vital.</p>
ES_M07	<p>Well, I'm telling you, I think that the public that mostly attends already has that confidence in science and that the talks I give [mention the area of knowledge he divulges] do not give rise to many doubts about what you are talking about.</p>
ES_M08	<p>So I consider it a success, I would like to think that [...] I have changed the way of seeing life, science, education and training to all the people who have passed through my workshops, conferences, who have bought my book or who have gone to my exhibitions.</p>
ES_M08	<p>Any fraudulent act in science seems to me a million steps backwards, but for everyone, for the colleagues of these people, and for the scientific world, for the general public, that is, for the people and the people, for the economy, it is for everything, for the people who try to communicate science from rigor and from trust because it gives me total hopelessness and distrust because in the end I am an intermediary, I'm nothing more than that.</p>

ES_M08	But apart from my case, the issue of fraudulent practices, of course, I see it a lot in scientific dissemination because projects that are not necessary are approved. And that's fraud for me.
ES_M10	So I think it is difficult to question a scientific result of a black hole that is in the wind from far away, you have no way as a citizen to put a telescope and compare these data, it is very difficult.
ES_M11	That's what I was saying, that we publish all the information with names and surnames, in other words, if I publish a lie, it won't take you a minute to get 20 insults or people saying 'you're lying', so, in other words, we wouldn't do it in any case. But it is also impossible to do so because we provide information that is totally transparent. We can't afford not to do something that is trustworthy.
ES_M11	And there is another important factor, which is that a few years ago the press went crazy with clicks. The objective was the click. There are still many newspapers that publish four paragraphs of information without a byline, signed the newspaper of... Toledo, four paragraphs with information that may not be directly false, but is misleading. [...] Maybe that gets you a lot of hits that I don't know if they bring you anything nowadays, but well, that model, at least in the [newspaper where I work], is over. Well, we never did that either, but now it's a subscription model.

3.4 Synthesis of recommendations

This section summarises the recommendations made by respondents to strengthen public confidence in science. These recommendations can be grouped into four categories, which are presented below.

A first group of recommendations focus on aspects linked to the first part of the mediation chain, this is, what happens in the laboratory. In this regard, recommendations to improve the impact on public trust linked to **improving the science and knowledge production system** are mentioned. In the first place, it is proposed that the percentage of research funding in Spain should be significantly increased.

And although it is very hackneyed, a real commitment to science in the country that is not subject to any political interest or political sway, and this translates into adequate investment, year after year, and that Spain should not be.... as I recently read that Spain, for example, is in 16th place

out of 27 in innovation in the European Union. The budgets, I don't know how many years we have been talking about 2% of GDP dedicated to R&D, I don't know how many years we have been saying that we need to move closer to Germany, because this is also essential for the public to have more confidence in science. EN_M09

The 'publish or perish' culture is seen as a possible impediment to increasing public confidence in science. Reducing the impact it has on scientific production linked to promotion and curricular valuation, particularly in limiting the publication of negative results, is proposed as a reform of scientific culture.

It is proposed that negative results should be published and that incentives should be provided, for example, so that there is no such pressure [publish or perish]. EN_M02

A third recommendation linked to research ethics and integrity is to toughen sanctions for researchers who engage in malpractice or fraudulent practices. The current sense of impunity enjoyed by scientists who engage in such practices neither strengthens public confidence in science nor has a discouraging effect within the scientific community. According to several interviewees publication of such news in the press does have a significant effect. Eliminating the perception of impunity and establishing a system of sanctions is thus suggested as a way to reduce dubious practices in science.

Yes, I believe that at least in Spain there is impunity, absolute impunity for cheats. I think that, I mean, not from the point of view of the press, but the system should be changed to put an end to impunity, I mean, it can't be that it is public, that there are people cheating. [...] Well, I think it would improve confidence in scientific integrity if there were punishment for cheats, which there isn't: absolute impunity. EN_M11

A second group of recommendations include those related to **investing in citizens' scientific literacy and scientific culture**. Mediators consistently suggested defining ambitious educational and cultural programmes to improve scientific literacy in formal education, and to create a solid scientific culture among citizens as a necessary tool to reinforce confidence in science. The need to improve citizens' ability to interpret information about science was stressed by several mediators.

It is very difficult to communicate uncertainty, for example, and I think that this is what Spain lacks, well, in general all of Europe, the western world and the whole world. In this country there is a very low level of scientific literacy, there is a very low level of understanding of what science is. They don't understand what science is, they don't understand

how science works. [...] I don't know how the baccalaureate or secondary school is organised now, but there may be people who don't know anything about chemistry from the age of 14 or 15, or biology, or physics, or maths, or very little about maths. So, of course, this makes us much more vulnerable to hoaxes, to being given bad scientific information, and then it also makes us much more difficult to understand what we are being explained. EN_M03

But it is true that I find, and I find many times, that there are terms, or that there are ideas that need to be explained more because they are not known to the public and should be known. EN_M03

On the other hand, they should understand the basic mechanisms. I do not suggest that they should do a master's degree in epistemology, but that they should understand how research can obtain a result from a large number of studies or from logical reasoning - if it is more theoretical physics research, for example - what degree of validity one thing has over another. EN_M02

In response to this situation, and as part of reinforcing scientific knowledge and culture in formal education, various actions are proposed, including the creation of spaces for access to scientific experiences, increasing the programming of scientific dissemination in cultural and social centres, and reinforcing the perception that science is a public good and can be enjoyed by the public.

And in between, it would be great if they could have, I don't know how it could be articulated; scientific experiences for normal people, just as you can join a reading club, and you are reading a book, in a nice environment, and you are at the same time talking to the person who has produced it. And yet, there are meeting points and experiences such as Pint of Science, which bring people together. EN_M03

What we usually comment in general is that, for example, in theatres or civic centres where these activities take place, one out of every 1000, perhaps, activities that take place in the theatre, in the civic centre, are about popularising science, and it's very sad because there is a lot of interest, really. And I think that interest is also contagious, ES_M07

We are making a mistake, science belongs to the citizens and that's what I think we have to get across to them. This is the idea that people have to have that it is theirs, that it is theirs, that they are paying for it, like health, roads, education, everything public is theirs and it is not something they cannot have access to. [...] So we will have to find a

way to reach everyone in the world, to let them know that it is theirs, that they can enjoy it. EN_M10

The third group of recommendations refers to **scientific dissemination practices**. With regard to science popularisation, the mediators interviewed made proposals in terms of the profiles of interlocutors, and the type of messages and the channels that can contribute to improving public confidence in science.

Regarding communication channels, several mediators reflect on the advantages and disadvantages of online and offline channels in the promotion of scientific literacy and scientific culture.

I think there is something very interesting that is being done and that is that although the vertical video does not take hold as information, or it seems that it does not take hold as information, this is a fact that I have not yet seen studies on the subject, but I am in contact with at least two people who are researching this in their doctorates and it seems to point in that direction. The information doesn't permeate, but it does normalise the situation: that you scroll through your feed and find that 1 in 5 videos has some scientific content and is more or less entertaining, because it's a curiosity or someone who is ironing their clothes and talking about something else. Or they're not even talking about it, but they normalise at one point in their daily anecdotes that they've been to the lab and they've been doing research. That makes science understood as something more organic in everyday life. They don't understand that barrier between science and everything else, and therefore, as science is alien, it makes me lazy because I have a series of very well-founded clichés about it. ES_M02

In fact, interviewees repeatedly mention the importance of digital channels in the strategy of access to information for citizens.

When you look at Reuters reports on international journalism, more and more people are only getting their information from social media. And for me, well, profiles like that are key to communicate science and to reach the majority of people. When we talk about people who get their information mainly through social networks, I think they are already a majority. In other words, I think that it's changing a lot and communication tactics also have to change, and it's not easy, eh? ES_M04

I also think that researchers or research staff, with the authority that their position and their work and their experience gives them, are the ones who have to confront this type of information [fake news] and... for young people, perhaps through channels that they consume [...] or through, in large dissemination centres, activities that are perhaps more playful and inoffensive, let's say, you can introduce

them to the scientific evidence of more controversial issues where there is more mistrust, more misinformation. EN_M01

The need to reconquer face-to-face spaces is also claimed by some mediators as vital for the communication of issues related to climate change, and for the fight against disinformation and fake news, especially among the younger generations.

Yes, to touch reality in our fingers and in our hands. I've just read a book about digital resistance, and I'm more and more convinced that we have to... not in a Luddite sense or in a technophobic sense, but that we have to take advantage of what the digital part gives us. [...]. But I think we need to get back to reality. We cannot explain climate change just through screens. If what I'm telling you is that the fields are drying up or that these birds are disappearing or that the sea is boiling. You have to go there to touch it, you have to go there to do things, you have to change and you have to experiment. ES_M03

In addition, several mediators recommend reinforcing the proximity between research centres and citizens in order to break down stereotypes about the scientific profession and improve understanding of what is carried out in research centres.

The children often go to a farm school at school, but they have never been to a laboratory, they have never seen a research centre.... very few, there are some, but very few. EN_M03

We have to try, I think, to bring the public to the research centres so that they can see what it is they do. Well, beyond communicating it, which is fundamental: without that communication, there will be no more approach, but I think we still need to open the doors of the research centres a little more for people to go, although as I said, they are opening up more and more, but we still have a long way to go. EN_M09

The impact of the media on the public is mentioned by several interviewees when asked about recommendations for improving public confidence in science. Specifically, interviewees refer to the importance of the people who appear in the media talking about science-related issues and the responsibility of editorial teams with regard to the time devoted to science-related news.

Trying to gradually disassociate, let's say, the magufos, let's call them that, those people who say they disseminate science, that they do science, and who do not do it, from the public. In other words, to try to gradually, as far as we can, remove these people from networks, from the media, from television programmes, so that, well, they leave a little bit to those of us who dedicate ourselves to it with reliability. EN_M06

The media, not the journalists, but the editorial boards, need to be very self-critical, both on television, radio and in the daily press, about the weight they give to the science sections, especially in the environment and climate change, right? Which I think is... the news, first there should be an exhaustive review of the tendency to publish things with a catastrophic bias, often reports do talk about consequences and the translation of the consequence is 'we're all going to die', which was never the case, and then it wasn't, which the scientists themselves happened recently with the issue of the AMOC. And I think the editorial line should be revised a little bit, shouldn't it? EN_M05

The last category of recommendations refers to **decision-making in times of crisis**, the **communication strategies needed when political decisions must be taken and scientific criteria play a relevant role**. This is the case for political decisions that are made under assumptions of high uncertainty, as in the case of the two POIESIS case studies, climate change and COVID-19.

One of the mediators presented an example to describe the negative impact on the public of confusion about decision criteria based on the scientific evidence available at a given time, combined with other criteria political decision-making processes.

During the pandemic there were many measures that were based on scientific studies, purely scientific, and others that were constrained by political issues or industrial issues, for example, how many masks can we produce? Which leads to the recommendation that only those who are coughing should wear masks. But it is not because that is the best possible solution, as those who are not coughing may also be cases of infection and should have a mask. The reason for not recommending this is that we can't, because there is no industry, so if you explain where it comes from, we would possibly avoid situations like the one we experienced with two communicators from Spain, [...] who got into an argument because one of them held this political view, which was true at the time, but without clarifying the origin of it. And the other one made it clear, as a doctor, that there was a second reading that we had to take into account and that in fact, when the change came, because if there was production of masks, we resolved that part of the problem. How do we justify that there has been a change of scientific opinion on this? There hasn't been, what happens is that a lot of decisions are mixed up. And with this kind of climate change situation it's the same thing. ES_M02

Recommendation 1: Increase investments in research ethics and integrity policies and procedures in universities and public research organisations, including through mandatory training for master and doctoral students.

Recommendation 2: Reform the structure of research career incentives by renouncing the 'publish or perish' culture and by rewarding researchers for high quality communication and dissemination work

Recommendation 3: Invest in sustained educational programme to raise the level of scientific literacy and culture in primary and secondary school and, through lifelong learning, among the general public.

Recommendation 4: Create stable local-level infrastructures supporting the promotion of scientific culture and social integration in science, including public laboratories, reading and resource rooms, interactive activities, expert talks, etc., accessible to the entire population.

Recommendation 5: Open up public laboratories for regular public visiting hours and for programmes of school excursions and work experience opportunities.

Recommendation 6: Invest in the provision of specialised training for early career researchers in science communication and media relations, including how to use social media platforms effectively.

Recommendation 7: Establish a system of effective sanctions for scientists who engage in fraudulent practices in order to reduce the perception of impunity.

4 Analysis of Researcher interviews

This section analyses the results of the interviews conducted with our Researchers. Of the six researchers, three work on climate change issues and three on Covid-19. Among the three climate change researchers, two of them have extensive experience of social integration of different actors in their research, and one of them specifically comes from the field of social sciences. Among the Covid-19 researchers, one of them is a social science researcher. Their academic and professional profiles are described in the following section.

4.1 Researcher contexts: Covid-19 and Climate Change

This section presents a brief summary of each researcher's work and experience. It also presents their reflections and perceptions on how the controversy in the context of climate change or Covid-19 affects their work.

4.1.1 Researchers working on Covid-19

Researcher ES_R01 is a senior virologist in a research centre with a consolidated scientific career and various responsibilities in the coordination of research teams, identification of research priorities and coordination with different actors in the event of a possible health emergency. The researcher points out that the current controversy regarding Covid-19 is practically non-existent given that we are not in an emergency situation. However, she reflects on how important it was at certain moments during the coronavirus crisis to engage in communication with the public. This was necessary in order to present the current state of knowledge and facilitate individual decision-making without falling into defeatism or pessimism.

Researcher ES_R03 is a virologist and is currently an assistant professor at a European university research centre. During the coronavirus pandemic, she focused her research efforts on sequencing new Covid-19 variants. She played a leading role in communicating the existing knowledge in her field of research in different social networks and traditional media, as well as implementing collaborative strategies with the public for the generation of knowledge in her field. Regarding the public debate and controversy, she stresses that her messages were taken out of context only rarely.

Researcher ES_R04 is a senior social scientist. During the pandemic, he was part of a group of researchers who advocated the need to integrate social sciences in the generation of knowledge and management of the pandemic. In the field of Covid-19 he developed research to improve knowledge on the correlation between

epidemiological factors and social and socio-economic factors. He considers that his work was not affected by the controversy due to the delay in funding social science projects after mass restrictions took effect.

4.1.2 Researchers working on Climate Change

Researcher ES_R02 is a researcher in the field of social sciences whose area of work is related to adaptations to climate change in the food sector. She defines the specific area of research in which she works as relatively unknown to the general public. Consequently, it is not an area affected by controversy and public debate. However, this controversy is deeply rooted in broader approaches the food sector, where there is a great deal of public debate.

Researcher ES_R05 is a researcher in the natural sciences who carries out research and outreach work on topics closely related to climate change. He actively participates in the public debate on controversial issues, both as a researcher and as an outreach worker.

Researcher ES_R06 is an environmental social scientist. He develops his work in close collaboration with different actors and considers that in the framework of his work there are sometimes controversial aspects perceived by certain actors with economic interests.

4.2 About science communication and public attitudes

The six researchers interviewed are engaged at different levels in science communication tasks. There are striking differences in the characteristics of communication described between climate change and Covid-19 researchers in terms of the intensity of involvement in such tasks.

The experiences reported by Covid-19 researchers are very much marked by the emergency situation and the need to communicate information to the public immediately, continuously, and intensively during the months of greatest uncertainty during the pandemic.

I had a standing weekly radio interview with them and then on top of this on a any given week I would probably have at least three to four additional interviews. But if it was when a variant was announced or something, I mean, sometimes it would be booked, you know, the whole day, sometimes it would really be crazy. ES_R03

In contrast, climate change communication has a decades-long history, and the researchers involved are aware of the dynamics and controversies that have historically affected communication in this field.

The interviewees included researchers with extensive exposure both in traditional media (television, radio and press) and on social networks and other types of formats (podcasts). One researcher interviewed has extensive knowledge of institutional science communication in the context of climate change. Two researchers bring experience in communication activities closely related to transdisciplinary research practices, in which there is a strong relationship between researchers and actors involved and affected by their lines of research.

With the exception of one interviewee, in general, the scientists have a positive perception of the communication carried out by third parties and especially by professional journalists in their field.

There was very good, in general, very good willingness to communicate it as well as possible by the media. ES_R01

But I believe that science communication and journalism specialising in environmental issues in general, and climate change in particular, are quite rigorous.' ES_R02

The Researchers also highlighted some negative aspects of being personally involved in these tasks, as well as strategies they use to counteract these challenges.

In the Covid-19 case, the use of sensationalist headlines by the media to present scientific information was a concern. The effects

of political polarisation, which could impact them personally as scientists actively participating in the mainstream media, was described as a challenge. So too was the incorrect interpretation and misrepresentation of their interventions and analysis in media contexts.

Everything that I did, every tweet thread that I wrote, I would always be thinking about how could this be misinterpreted. ES_R03

They created problems for me when they started to polarise. When it became polarised and there was one region against another, one [political] party against another, one city against another. Well, that worried me a lot and it really upset me because the only enemy was the virus, that is to say, there was no need to look for more enemies. It was big enough, wasn't it? ES_R01

There was an interesting reflection on the limited role assigned to the social sciences during the beginning of the pandemic. One social scientist reported facing internal resistance and delegitimation from natural science communities, who downplayed the importance of the knowledge that SSH could contribute to the management of the pandemic.

Well, I mean, with all due respect, but the research that can be done in virology or epidemiology, in other words, clinical or biological studies, etc., the results will be the same, whether they are done in Israel, Japan or Spain, but the social research that is done in Seville, Valencia or Madrid will not be done in Israel, Japan or Australia, in other words, either it is done in Seville, Valencia or Madrid or it is not done at all. ES_R04

In the case of climate change, negative factors impacting the presentation of scientific work were strongly linked to their political and economic implications. Experiences of sensationalism by the media were described, for example in the process of reporting negotiations between scientists and politicians about the terms to use in the drafting of reports, or through a perceived bias towards promoting controversy on the part of actors with economic interests.

One interviewee held a very critical and negative view of the treatment of the research and dissemination work done by himself and some colleagues. According to this narrative, in climate change communication there are strong economic and political interest that led to battles for public opinion in which different actors such as political parties, journalists, or others with economic interests are coordinated and involved. The use of social media 'trolls' as a strategy of attrition and personal discredit was described as a strategy to which certain actors are permanently subjected through social networks.

Well, since it is basically a battle for public opinion, what they did was to take a phrase from the journalist who interviewed me, not even a phrase of mine, and they attributed it to me. ES_R05

Talking about the impact of controversies, misinformation and negative impacts of science communication, the interviewees reflected on the different grades of potential effects on public trust in science. In the Covid-19 field, mentions were made of the need to be appropriately measured in communication to avoid false expectations or the generation of unnecessary suffering among the population. For example, when vaccines became available, the message that vaccination would bring an immediate end to the pandemic was broadcast, causing disenchantment and despair among those who had internalised this and saw that it was not happening.

In the case of climate change, two of the interviewees expressed concern public attitudes may be unduly influenced by the role and positions of vested economic and political actors.

So I believe that a large amount of misinformation is being promoted, of self-interested distorted information, and when it is in the interest of the economic powers themselves, a mistrust of science is being created. Because in the end, let's not fool ourselves, the best way to keep a population under control is for it not to have accurate information. So it is important to create distrust in science, especially when science talks about things that harm economic power. So it is no coincidence that the strongest points of confrontation right now are in the environmental field. ES_R05

I think that the risks come more from political agendas, from political agendas more towards ultra-liberalism, extreme right, that are not interested in scientific information because, for example, with regard to climate change, other impacts of global change, because it does not interest, let's say, their voters in general, nor big capital, big business, because basically what is being said is to stop the growth of production and industrial processes, as we understand them now, and consumption, I am speaking in general. And also people who, perhaps out of... I think it is born out of fear, resort to theories.... to understand what is being conveyed and place it within conspiracy theories. I think those extremes for me are extremes and they are not... it's not so generalised, what happens is that it makes a lot of noise, especially amplified by social media. It can generate negative attitudes and, moreover, by giving an opinion, very dangerous. ES_R06

One of the interviewees categorised two ways of approaching climate change communication which, according to his perception, could be irresponsible: on the one hand, very negative or catastrophic

visions (doomerism) and on the other, proposals based on extreme confidence in the capacity of technology and innovation to resolve the climate issue (techno-optimism).

When asked about the impact of climate change misrepresentations, one interviewee felt that certain discussions do not reach the general public, but are limited to people who work professionally in the area.

I find out about these things because..., but, for example, my immediate environment... I don't know how much people read the newspaper in general, no, I don't know. People have never asked me about this subject. The people I know and with whom I interact have never said to me: "Hey, ES_R02, I've read this in the newspaper, I've found out about this topic". So the feeling I often get, although you make the effort and because we also have the responsibility to participate in all these issues of dissemination, to participate in interviews, with the media, etc., eh? Then the feeling I get is that the impact is not that great. In other words, there really aren't that many people who look at these things or read these things, right?. ES_R02

ID here	Additional quotes
ES_R01	If we arrived on time, which was very rarely, and we asked them to please change it, they would change it. I would explain: "Look, I'm sorry. It's not exactly what I said and it might put fear into people like your grandparents, or it might put unnecessary fear or tremendous distress into young people, change it a little bit, right?" So we asked for changes and they accepted them, but we didn't always get it. Yes, sometimes there were sensationalist headlines.
ES_R02	What there is is a lot of media impact, also from leaks. This issue is also quite complex. In the IPCC there are like three phases, like three different drafts and each draft has its own process. You make the first draft, the draft then goes through a review process, the initial review is normally open only to scientists, that's Draft Zero and then there is Draft 1. Draft 1 is open to all the people who want to register to review these drafts. You have to put who you are, where you are from, from... for example, here there are a lot of people from the Public Administrations who are part of the climate change departments, climate change offices, environment, or whatever. This is true not only for the IPCC, but also for the [not understood] and for other UN reporting processes. So, of course, in reality, when you register to be a reviewer, although you sign a confidentiality

	<p>agreement, you have access to the draft and of course, uh..., there are the reports on the one hand and on the other hand there is the 'summary for policy makers'. What about the summary for policy makers? It is a text that comes from or draws on all the chapters of the report and has to be approved by the countries. So the wording, in other words, the words, what is said, how it is said, is very carefully measured to avoid vetoes by countries, to avoid interminable sessions, etc. So what happens? It could be that, from a draft, when the Summary for Policy Makers comes out, right? The first draft is made, which is usually done when we are in Draft 1 of the report, Draft 0 of the Summary for Policy Makers is made and then, of course, there are differences between one and the other and then, for example, in this last report there was a controversy. I remember that in the Summary for Policy Makers of Mitigation Group 3, the issue of degrowth came up in the report. In other words, the Summary for Policy Makers is based on the report. The report does not touch on it, but the issue of degrowth came out, let's say, from the Summary for Policy Makers, although it remains in the report, it is not in the Summary for Policy Makers, and so, well, There was, there was a lot of misrepresentation here because what was said was that politicians were influencing the results of the report and that is not the case, in other words, the report does not change, the report remains the same. What happens is that, let's say, it does influence what they later approve, which is the Summary for Policy Makers, in the sense that either the words are changed, and then, perhaps, instead of saying the word growth, you say an economy..., what is it called? I don't remember the word in English, stand-by or whatever, or zero growth or whatever. But well, I know that there was controversy here and here I, for example, I think that the journalists, whatever, also wanted to fuel this controversy. But, well, that's all right: it's part of every process.</p>
ES_R03	<p>But certainly I mean for [website], we certainly went through phases where screenshots were being used to spread misinformation and that was probably one of the most impactful because it was so incorrect and like in a way that you can't... You know, I'd say you can't even argue and take out of context. It really has been twisted. And so, it was maybe the most painful if that's the right word. So, we did have times where... I mean, anytime you're working with genetic sequences, there's always a chance that something is wrong. The sequence hasn't been made very well, that the metadata is wrong. Maybe they, you know, their fingers slipped and they typed the wrong month or the wrong year. And when you put these into a tree, they can be very striking. They can really stick out from the rest of the tree. And we tried</p>

	<p>really hard to catch all of these, but we didn't always. And unfortunately, people would really seem to watch the site when these would come up, they would take screenshots and try and use them as proof of something. I mean, any conspiracy theory you can think of. And then when we would catch them and fix them, we would use that as proof of a cover up.</p>
ES_R03	<p>And when we put that pre-print out, we actually put like a block at the beginning, a full text where we essentially said "this is what this pre-print means. This is what this preprint doesn't mean.</p>
ES_R03	<p>I mean, for the most part, I feel like it was represented fairly. I think part of this is because I worked very hard to try and if I was writing a Twitter thread to think very carefully about, you know, could any of these tweets on their own, could they be used in a way that I wouldn't want? So how can I change it up a bit? So that's not the case. And even when getting interviews and things, I'm sure I didn't get it right every time. But I would be very, very trying to word everything really specifically so that it was very hard to take anything I said out of context. I think largely that worked, but on the other hand, of course, I mean there were people that could really take anything and try and turn it into a conspiracy theory. So of course, there were people that would take an interview or, you know, me tweeting about a variant and would try and spin that into something else, unfortunately.</p>
ES_R04	<p>But my perception of one of the things that happens is that within science there are internal delegitimisations. So one thing that I found fascinating is how the social sciences are delegitimised.</p>
ES_R05	<p>So I believe that a great deal of misinformation and distorted information is being promoted, and when it is in the interest of the economic powers themselves, a mistrust of science is being created. Because in the end, let's not fool ourselves, the best way to keep a population under control is for it not to have accurate information. So it is important to create distrust in science, especially when science talks about things that harm economic power. So it is no coincidence that the strongest points of confrontation right now are in the environmental field. It is no coincidence that the research being done on climate change, water scarcity, pollution in general, particularly plastic pollution, energy, etc., is being contested. It is no coincidence, because in the end, what science is giving us on all these fronts, the best knowledge we have, is that things are being done very badly because we are taking an</p>

	<p>approach that is definitely wrong, conceptually wrong. But this wrong approach is fundamental for the economic approach. So the economic world doesn't want to hear about it, so what are they doing, in my view? They are financing disinformation. Well, the case of climate change is well known.</p>
<p>ES_R06</p>	<p>What happens is that you can intuitively perceive, often in meetings, that there are certain actors who you know come from a more denialist perspective. It is not a strong denial [...] but the actors who are, let's say, more dedicated to economic activities, do have positions that are a little bit... I notice that they are a little bit more polarised, but it is true that when it comes to talking about direct effects, for example, drought, lack of rainfall, how climate change affects processes that directly affect this economic activity, it is true that they start to talk in a more... more accepting way about this effect. This effect is linked to natural processes because droughts are natural phenomena, but it is true that the duration and intensity of these phenomena that are affected by climate change is changing and they notice it directly in their... So, there is no possible denial because the data is the data. How does it affect their activity? It is directly palpable, so there is no controversy.</p>

4.3 About the integration of citizens in research

All six researchers interviewed had a **positive view** of citizen participation in science. All interviewees had a **high degree of knowledge** about strategies and rationale around fostering socially inclusive practices in science.

The three researchers interviewed with social science backgrounds described their scientific practice under paradigms of citizen science and transdisciplinary science. These researchers described a high degree of stakeholder involvement in the different phases of the development of their research lines and projects. The two climate change researchers interacted with a large number of stakeholders and the relationship with them was described as based on trust. In addition, as a result of this stable relationship with stakeholders, both researchers had experience in co-creating research questions and problematising their lines of research.

The social science researcher in the Covid-19 area showed a solid theoretical and methodological knowledge of social integration practices in science. One SSH researcher critically assessed the current so-called “discourses of participation” in our environment as actions limited to the final phases of the research cycle.

What happens is that participation in science is in 99% of the cases... the discourses of participation are really discourses regarding dissemination and diffusion. [There is no co-design of research projects, in the best of cases there is a consultation at some point in the execution methodology and in most cases there is a final benchmarking to know how the results are contrasted and synchronised with the perceptions of citizens, but in the design phase there is zero. ES_R04

The two natural science researchers working on Covid-19 had experience in social integration in science related to data collection or interpretation.

Finally, only the interviewee in the natural sciences of climate change reported not incorporating social integration practices in his research beyond those linked to science dissemination processes. However, this researcher was able to reference examples of citizen science carried out by colleagues and identify the positive aspects that these practices bring as well as the barriers that limit their use.

Regarding the **positive aspects** related to socially inclusive practices, arguments were presented that can be grouped into four dimensions. Firstly, benefits were presented regarding the availability of and access to data as well as support in the interpretation of data.

But clearly having that be open and available showed that you can have signs or citizens involved in science like that in

ways where it can make sense and they can make really valuable contributions because we as scientists, we're stretched, we're stretched so thin for so long. That this was absolutely welcome and really necessary work because there wasn't enough of us to do it. ES_R03

Secondly, benefits related to improving the capacity to develop science steered to respond to social challenges were mentioned. Under this group of arguments, it was said that the participation of citizens helped to raise contextualised research questions and provided legitimacy to the research results and greater acceptance of the possible solutions proposed.

At the societal level, benefits linked to social integration in science were mentioned as improving the scientific culture of the public.

In other words, people don't understand that in science we work with uncertainty, that is, uncertainty is part of the scientific process. [...] They want very concrete data, concrete numbers, "this is how it's going to be" [...] So what I think is that we need a scientific culture and if the participation of citizens in the scientific sphere facilitates this approach and this understanding of what science is, I think it would be quite positive. ES_R02

And that people realise how all the inductive and deductive reasoning is done, which is part of scientific thinking. So my opinion is that it is not only positive, but also indispensable, because people have to understand what science is and why science is useful. ES_R05

I think that also helps, the fact that one participates helps to feel part of the great social enterprise, which is science, right? And it's not just a few people who are very closed in their laboratories. ES_R01

Also, the benefits linked to channelling citizens' anguish during emergencies were also discussed.

Those who like it, like to collaborate very much, because they also know that they are doing something and that they are doing it in a framework that is defined by scientists and that, therefore, it is a work that is not in vain and the harder a citizen perceives the situation to be, if one perceives that the epidemic is very strong, if one perceives that climate change is tremendous, the more one needs, probably to alleviate the anguish, the more one needs to participate personally, then, citizen science allows participation by contributing with data, etcetera. ES_R01

Finally, a more profound argument concerned the benefits associated with the epistemological deconstruction of science. The researcher

who made this reference pointed out that these benefits do not currently exist due to a lack of institutional impetus and a lack of knowledge of the scientific community that incorporates participatory practices.

What I want to say is that I would problematise the very concept of citizen participation, because I believe that the way it has been incorporated into the discourse of scientific policies is very White Wash and diluted, that is, it is an idea of making consultations, of..., but not of being incorporated into the design of the experiments, so to speak.
ES_R04

Two **negative aspects** were mentioned, one of a practical nature, linked to the possible frustration of researchers who dedicate resources, time and, energy to learn and introduce these practices. According to this argument, citizens might have a limited response to such activities and participation may be lower than expected, leading to feelings of frustration among researchers.

I think that if it is done in an organised way, it has many more positive effects than negative ones. Another thing is... the only negative aspect that I could see is more the frustration that it can generate for scientists to try to promote participation and that people don't participate because people also find it very difficult to participate.
ES_R02

A second criticism referred to the trivialisation of the concept of citizen science, which has been incorporated into institutional discourse but, lacking support and training, ends up being limited to experiences of scientific communication and dissemination without taking advantage of the transformative potential that is theoretically presupposed.

When asked about the **obstacles and barriers** to implementation, two types were mentioned. Firstly, barriers linked to the lack of institutionalization and incentives to engage in social integration activities.

I believe that it is not a project endorsed by the institutions, that they do not believe it, that is, that it is a project that is couched in rhetorical language, that it is a political correctness, that it is something that has to be done, but the means are not provided to do it. And what is more, I believe that in none of the phases of the management of science policy is participation really included. ES_R04

Regarding incentives, the implementation of stable participation strategies over time was seen as restricted due to the dependence

of these strategies on the budget availability of short-medium term projects.

I think that the main barrier is in general the strategy of designing research by projects of a fixed duration, which is beginning to change at the European level, for example, but also at the national level. There is a very strong investment in creating infrastructures. And some of them in their genetics carry that design, the funding itself and the governance of the infrastructure. ES_R06

The lack of incentives for the recognition of integration work as part of scientific careers was also mentioned, and the impact this has on the younger generation of scientists was reflected upon.

Young people have their whole careers ahead of them and they need all these activities that they can do willingly to be valued because if not, we lose them. And that is a barrier that is not valued and that there is not enough time. As it is not valued, young people's bosses don't give them the time to do it, right? As it is not valued, they end up abandoning it because there are other things that give you more, more security that you have the merits to later have a better contract, stability and be able to continue researching. ES_R01

And it is an activity [dissemination] that is considered minor, it is an activity that is not encouraged among young researchers. ES_R05

The lack of economic and scientific career evaluation incentives leads to a situation in which engaging in basic activities with the public, such as scientific dissemination, entails a personal cost and overload for researchers, who often do not have sufficient institutional support to carry out these tasks.

So, the first barrier is cultural within the scientific institutions themselves, because historically this has not been valued. And in fact, not only this, but also, when someone carries out an intense dissemination activity, this initially arouses a great deal of suspicion. ES_R05

And especially this second one, to realise one thing, normally the one who does the dissemination is doing it pro bono and with great personal effort and outside of his or her work. ES_R05

It was a double-edged sword in ways that I didn't necessarily expect. [...] And I think a lot of people would still maybe say that you know, yes, it's very nice and it's very good you did that. But at the end of the day, it's not research. And if

you're going to be a university professor, that's not, that's not the communications department. ES_R03

Secondly, barriers related to the capacities and competences needed to carry out social integration and dissemination actions were mentioned.

The other barrier there is probably that we are not born knowing. Learning to communicate takes time, doesn't it? ES_R01

They are barriers of experts or disciplines with great capacity to influence how decisions are made, purer disciplines and that do not have in their genetics, experts do not have during their training education in methodologies or in why we have to involve actors, but of course the problem is that their vision is also strong, legitimate and has an important rationality. So that is the third barrier, how to change the training on why and how, and then also the strong rationality: why should we involve people who do not generate knowledge in the same way that science does? ES_R06

Some researchers described what they considered to be the best and most effective ways of integrating or interacting with citizens. They mentioned establishing stable and trust-based relationships with stakeholders.

Because to work in this way you always have to have trust. If they don't trust you, it's very difficult for them to really participate. ES_R02

Also, requirements to properly execute social integration practices in sciences referred to embedding participatory practice in project theory and methodology, incorporating principles of responsibility on the part of researchers.

A research project that takes citizen participation seriously has to include it at least in the development.... well, it should include it in the theoretical part, but certainly in the methodological development. ES_R04

I think it is necessary, but it must be done with a lot of responsibility, with a very, very well designed methodology to understand how, why, who, as always, right? It makes no sense to involve more people, even though it is sometimes difficult to define the group of actors or stakeholders who are affected by the phenomena under investigation. This must be done with criteria of responsibility, fairness, participation and equality. In other words, you have to be very clear about the criteria, the principles, the methodology based on the questions you are asking. ES_M06

In summary, with regard to social integration in science, the Covid-19 natural science cases discussed were motivated by the need to respond urgently to high levels of need for data and its interpretation. The experiences described in the social sciences, both in Covid-19 and climate change, were based on more reflective considerations, both on the roles of citizens in science and the relationships between citizenship and science.

ID here	Additional quotes
ES_R02	So, encouraging and promoting participation requires a lot of time and energy, that you have to work in research in a different way. [...] so I think the only negative thing, more from the perspective of those of us who dedicate ourselves to research, is this: the frustration that can be generated by all the time you are putting in and then maybe you do something and just three or four motivated people come and that's it, but well, even so, I think it has to be done, that is to say that this is how it works.
ES_R04	That is to say, for example, when presenting a research project. A research project that takes citizen participation seriously has to include it at least in its development.... well, it should include it in the theoretical part, but certainly in the methodological development. The evaluation systems, the peer-reviews, give it zero importance, and so much so that one sees, for example, how in the last 30 years, the research project presentation forms have been forced to create specific boxes for dissemination, data management, etcetera. Which in reality is..., I think it's very interesting because it's like forcing us to meet these needs in 250 words, when in reality what we should do is force us to design the project theoretically and methodologically, of course. But solving the problem in 250 words is a way of saying I'll corner it, you know? I corner it and check it box
ES_R04	Data management is solved by the library, that is, the data policy project, it is something that is already there, a template, the things you have to do, which shows that no scientist, especially in the area of I think the Natural Sciences, takes Open Science seriously, that is, it is a problem that is solved with the check boxes that the library people give me. So you don't make the effort, so you don't... that's no longer a problem, you don't make the effort of how I design the project theoretically or methodologically, because I take care of it on the last page of the National Plan template. So, what I think is that in all phases it is completely diluted to pure check boxes of political correctness.

ES_R05	<p>So, basically it is the moment when you talk about something that is of interest and concern to citizens, which is typically what science deals with, because we don't do crossword puzzles. In other words, we work on problems. So, if you work on cancer, that is a problem that is of interest to citizens and is, therefore, something that is clearly political in nature, right? Another thing is that you tell me that you are introducing ideological or any other kind of bias. That we are not beings of light, and that can happen, obviously, and it does happen. But to say that science is not... For me it is a sign of the decadence, also of the understanding of everything, of the world we have, and if you don't understand that science is an eminently political activity, you don't understand what science is. In the end, politics is practically everything. Even when you are talking about whether I change the traffic light on the corner, that is a political decision. What happens is that there is this identification of politics with ideology and partisanship. So there are many negative connotations with partisanship, but hell, with politics... we reach a point where... In any case, precisely because it is a strongly political activity, I think we have to bring it closer to the polis, we have to bring it closer to the citizens.</p>
ES_R05	<p>Twenty years ago, I'll tell you, in general, dissemination activities were seen as a minor activity within the curriculum of a researcher; what a researcher has to do is to focus on producing articles.</p>
ES_R05	<p>And then there is another barrier, which is external and it is the moment you get involved in problems that bother you, you know that you are going to get beaten up and for example, as we have talked about before, people don't want to get into trouble. So it's also true, and I also understand this, you can't ask everyone to be a hero and stand in front of you and get slapped, because it's not nice, because it's also that, even if they are all words and deep down you say, nothing happens and say, but well, nobody likes to be insulted, nobody likes to receive ugly criticism, even if you know it's bullshit and that it's a lie. No, no, it's not nice. And that's another barrier, I mean, in that sense, I think that sometimes people who do science should be given more support. Tucking them in does not mean giving them carte blanche and allowing them to say whatever they want, but in the face of attacks that are clearly and manifestly unjust. I think there should be support mechanisms, defence mechanisms and so on. I have often felt very lonely.</p>
ES_R06	<p>I think it is important to involve them, especially for the second part that I wanted to say, which is problem solving. OK, now that we are answering the question, we have contextualised the problem, we have modelled it together, we have started to generate data on it</p>

	according to the method we are using What solutions do we propose to solve the problem we are looking at? No?
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4.4 About public trust in science

In general terms, the researchers interviewed consider that citizens have a good perception of science and scientists. In fact, several interviewees mention overconfidence, or faith in science to solve problems, as one of the possible factors that could potentially jeopardise this confidence if expectations of science are not met. With regard to scientists, respondents also consider that, in general terms, citizens have a good perception of their conduct and do not spontaneously refer to aspects related to ethics and integrity of research as minimising trust in science.

People have quite a lot of trust in science and in scientists in science in general and in scientists in particular ES_R02

When asked about the aspects that they believe worry citizens about science and that may undermine their trust, all interviewees gave a quick and well-founded answers. The issues that were predominantly raised were related to the consequences of the **lack of scientific culture**, an **excess of trust or hope placed in science**, and the difficulty in discerning between the **functions and roles of science and politics/policy**.

With regard to the lack of **scientific literacy**, different consequences are mentioned that can affect the public's ability to interpret scientific information. The interviewees consider that it is difficult for the public to understand the high levels of uncertainty that often surround science. Specifically, the handling of probabilities is pointed to as a paradigmatic case of uncertainty in science, as is often the case with the communication of possible future scenarios regarding climate change.

I think the fact that science can change is still something that's not very well understood and it's really hard to convey to people. ES_R03

This with the IPCC is very clear. Because in the IPCC all language is based on probability: Likely, very likely, confidence level... ES_R02

Similarly with regard to Covid-19, interviewee 1 mentions the constant revision of existing evidence during the management of the pandemic as a factor that can make citizens uncomfortable: "*yesterday they said one thing and today they seem to say the opposite*". The discomfort that uncertainty in science produces in the public could be exacerbated when citizens expect clear and unimpeachable answers to problems, such as the case of vaccines

during the pandemic or the energy transition in relation to climate change.

In fact, the **expectation that science can provide solutions to all problems** we face as a society has also been consistently presented as a problem that can undermine social trust in science. Several interviewees have expressly mentioned that citizens have faith in science, or in other words, that there is techno-optimism in society that trusts in science's ability to provide solutions to any kind of problem. This can then lead to disaffection if science fails to provide these answers or creates unexpected impacts.

Concerns are expressed at the level of technologies as options, as large-scale solutions to environmental problems, as the use of renewables as an option, the massive use of renewables to produce the same level of energy or more, to continue with the... to continue with the current growth models, to sum it up a lot. ES_R06

A third set of concerns raised relate to the **interaction between science and policy**. This interaction can be misunderstood by citizens, leading to confusion about how far science can provide tools for decision-making and where policy-making begins. One interviewee elaborates on this rationale by reflecting on the public's lack of understanding of the degree of independence of investigators and the possible perception of conflicts of interest when there are none.

'The misunderstanding of how science works as far as how, like, how do you scientists do this and how do we make these decisions and who's in control of what scientists say is also another thing that people really misunderstood in the pandemic. Some of this is just plain conspiracy theories. But on the other hand, I also think that it often reflects a genuine lack of understanding about, you know, who pays me, who decides what I say, who's pocket am I in? Whose line am I touting? And maybe a misunderstanding that, of course, at the end of the day, it seems always to say it, but we are people like, we're just not normal people. We don't get paid very well on an industry type scale. I'm certainly not well enough [paid], I would say to keep anybody's secret. Most of us are fairly precariously employed. And I think that misunderstanding of actually scientists are very independent is compared to employees of most other companies. Something that also could maybe help to build some trust that we are not mouthpieces for a university or anything else' ES_R03

One researcher points to the concern he perceives among the actors he interacts with regarding 'helicopter science', i.e. the concern that certain actors show about researchers extracting from them what they need (information, time, resources, etc.) and not engaging with their issues in the long term, returning to their "Ivory Tower". The reference to the Ivory Tower is mentioned by

several interviewees throughout the interviews to refer to reactions they perceive in the public to its very academic career-focused position and thus detached from social issues.

When explicitly asked about the **impact of REI issues** on public trust in science, the general perception is that malpractice cases could undermine trust among certain groups of people, but only in a very small minority and with little impact. Along these lines, news about unexpected consequences of scientific results or cases of lack of integrity and ethics in research are seen as evidence that the system is under observation and control. Furthermore, it is considered that in the case of news about malpractice by scientists, the fact that it comes to light is highly positive as it has an exemplary role among the scientific community.

When there are failures or when there is an adverse effect of a vaccine, to say look, precisely the fact that the adverse effect of the vaccine is detected, means that it is being thoroughly monitored, if nothing is detected, it means that it is not being looked at. The positive side of finding something negative is that it is being investigated. And the same goes for integrity and ethics. EN_R01

Another group of interviewees mentioned potential impacts on public trust in science linked with the **influence of economic or political interests** in science.

This problem has a lot to do with society's distrust of science, but there is also something else that is true, and that is the pressure of global capitalism to generate results, which sometimes leads to the introduction of untested technologies, and we have examples of this, unfortunately, throughout history. ES_R05

I think there is more concern at the level of science having a political agenda, or an agenda that is more directed at specific problems that do not interest citizens, but fraud... ES_R06

The lack of scientific literacy and understanding of the knowledge production system is predominant the narratives articulated by interviewees about the potential factors eroding public trust in science. But the consequences of the lack of scientific culture on trust may be aggravated by other factors that negatively affect the chain of mediation in science communication. Thus, on the one hand, the **capacity for amplification of false news** through social networks or the role of actors with economic or political interests in the mobilisation of conspiracy theories and fake news are mentioned.

The lack of integrity in science is also spurred on by this disinformation, favoured by economic interests, especially in those areas that are detrimental to them. So there are

tendencies, well, when you see death threats against Aemet technicians, you say that we have completely lost the plot, don't you? ES_R05

The use of **inappropriate communication strategies** during crisis communication, such as exaggeration in the presentation of research results or the creation of a sense of guilt, is also repeatedly pointed out as a mistake that undermines public engagement.

Finally, a couple of interviewees reflect on forces contributing to discredit **social sciences** in scenarios with a growing naturalistic conception of science, where social sciences are considered second class. Under this paradigm redirection that was felt to occur during the pandemic, science would lose proximity to society. An example of this trend is provided by Researcher 2 when reflecting on the type of expertise that science communication professionals had in the Covid-19 crisis compared with what journalists in her field previously had:

What is the relationship between citizenship and technology, citizenship and science? Well, it depends on the historical moment. So, for me, for example, a very important historical moment has been the pandemic. That is to say, I think that the pandemic has insights, in a very wild way, a naturalistic conception of science. ES_R04

So, there is a difference that is quite important when it comes to seeing how people work in the media and the type of profile of people who work in the field of science communication, isn't there? The specific journalist behind each type of news, of course the one who covers Covid-19, is perhaps a person who is more involved in biomedical news and therefore does not think about social issues, while the profile of the journalist who covers climate issues is much broader as well. I think this is an important difference, isn't it, in the way they approach each other? ES_R02

ID here	Additional quotes
ES_R03	The final thing I might add is the confusion between science and policy. Because I think that's another one. And this of course is also a line that can be genuinely blurred between scientists and politicians. And I think there's still a lot of discussion among scientists about what kind of advice do you give as a scientist? You purely send the numbers or do you give a recommendation, or do you downright tell people? If you don't do the stupid advice, where do you draw that line? What's your job as a scientist? How does that bounce up with perhaps your feeling of morality as a human? You know, can you live with yourself to just give numbers if you,

	<p>especially if you know the government might misinterpret them, but I think especially from the outside people can not... can also not understand that interaction. Where is that line drawn and who actually makes the decisions which I think is a big one. You know, even when we scientists may have been giving a recommendation at the end of the day, we were never the ones who implemented those recommendations and also we were never the ones that you know when we were called upon for advice, we would give advice as far as the virus, the health, the transmission mutations, we could not advise on and how do you mitigate the economic factors. We're not economists. Hopefully, they were talking to economists too, but they're, you know, it's at the end of the day, it's the government's job. Weigh up all of these opinions and decide what is the course of action that tries to balance them the best we can comment on, you know, should you pay businesses. But that's not our area of expertise"</p>
ES_R04	<p>All the social readings we had made of science in the last 30 years, I think the pandemic has closed them again, right? So, what relationship does science have with citizenship in the abstract, I think it is very difficult to say at this historical moment, I think we are experiencing a regression, a regression, and this regression can be blamed both on the proliferation of conspiracy theories, Fake news, I don't know how many, but also on science, that is, science, the institution of science is the one that is delegitimising certain internal currents such as the social sciences, the humanities, participation, so, I don't know if I'm answering your question, but it seems difficult in the abstract, it seems difficult to me, I think, but I do believe that we are at a historical moment in which what I understand as... . The paradigm of science or the structure, not in a Kuhnian sense, of the, the structures of scientific knowledge, is being eroded on two sides, on the side of society, with conspiracy theories, and on the side of science itself, with a naturalistic conservatism of what is good science.</p>

4.5 Synthesis of recommendations

This section summarises the recommendations made by respondents to strengthen public confidence in science. These recommendations can be grouped into four categories, which are presented below.

A first group of recommendations focuses on **improving science communication through the mediation chain**. This includes on the supply side of information both training scientists in communication skills through their careers and consolidating the

cooperation between professionals of science communication and scientists. On the demand side, the recommendations to improve the mediation chain involves increasing the public's ability and skills to understand and contextualize the scientific messages, incorporating scientific culture content in formal education, for example.

Then it seems to me that there should be more scientific culture in schools. It's not just biology, physics, chemistry and these things, which are what we can have as a more scientific subject. Bear in mind that everything else is also science, it's social sciences, but that's fine. But scientific culture, what it implies. Because, of course, what is studied in these subjects are facts, what science has already analysed and which, well, to this day remains so until proven otherwise: the law of gravity. It seems to me that there is a lack of scientific culture, not of facts, but of processes: What does doing science involve? What is the scientific method? ES_R02

A second group of recommendations refer to **institutional support and the shaping of scientific careers**. These include proposals related to the inclusion of dissemination activities in career evaluation processes, and ensuring that there are incentives and available time for researchers to participate in bidirectional engagement activities.

It is worth highlighting that two of the most publicly visible researchers interviewed coincided in proposing to increase institutional support for people involved in communication activities.

I think that sometimes people who do science should be given more support. Shielding them does not mean giving them carte blanche and allowing them to say whatever they want, but in the face of attacks that are clearly and manifestly unjust. I think there should be support mechanisms, defence mechanisms and so on. I have often felt very lonely. ES_R05

A third group concerns the **creation of new structures in the science and innovation system**. A first proposal concerns the creation of a public open data structure.

I think one of the first steps I would take would be to try to de-corporatise science and so what I would do is: I would cancel all the agreements with the big publishers, and I would sign... and I would deploy open science infrastructure at the publishing level. ES_R04

Another proposal that was mentioned by four of the interviewees refers to the creation of umbrella structures that, in a structured, timely, and sustained way, **promote science-society interactions**.

To take science to the neighbourhoods, to do neighbourhood science. And open laboratories, citizen laboratories, this has been theorised a lot by a colleague [he mentions the institute and the name of the colleague], but open it up, so that in the neighbourhoods, as well as having public libraries and sports centres, we have citizen laboratories, so that each neighbourhood has its own laboratory. ES_R04

Priority number 1 would be to design spaces for interaction, whatever form they take, depending on case problem contexts, levels of analysis. Spaces for continuous interaction, through well-designed and robust methodologies. ES_R06

Finally, a fourth group of recommendations includes proposals to **promote the social sciences** by increasing research funding allocations and **advance collaboration between social and STEM sciences** through dedicated interdisciplinary funding.

Recommendation 1: Improve the scientific information supply chain by training and developing communication skills among scientists and reinforcing their collaborations with professional science communicators.
Recommendation 2: Invest in permanent programmes designed to raise the level of scientific literacy and culture among school students and the general public.
Recommendation 3: Improve the recognition and rewards for science communication in the evaluation and career plans of scientists, particularly early career researchers
Recommendation 4: Create institutional policies and resource allocations to support and incentivise scientists committed to communication
Recommendation 5: Create an open public infrastructure of scientific data management and publications
Recommendation 6: Create stable local-level infrastructures of social integration into research, through institutions and key organisations
Recommendation 7: Enhance interdisciplinary research and collaboration among social and STEM sciences
Recommendation 8: Promote transdisciplinary research approaches

5 Conclusion

This section discusses the relationship between the results obtained in the EIS and the insights from the two previous empirical studies carried out during the previous year (see section 1.2).

First, the mediators and researchers interviewed mostly share, with a few exceptions, the perception that in Spain there is a high degree of trust in science and scientists. In fact, an excess of confidence (or faith) in science is sometimes presented as a possible problem, which can lead to disenchantment if science is not able to meet the expectations placed on it by techno-optimistic discourses. The perception that Spanish society has a high degree of trust in science is in line with the results obtained in the public deliberative workshop and focus group studies.

In the public deliberative workshop, participants reflected on various factors affecting their trust in the scientific information that they actively or passively access. Aspects related to the reputation and reliability of the sources and media that publish information, and the possibilities for cross-checking the credibility of this information in different ways, were also discussed, specially by mediators.

Citizens who participated in the workshop mentioned uncertainty and the lack of consensus as factors that generate distrust in science. This factor was strongly emphasized as one of the main threats to citizens' trust in science by both mediators and researchers. A sustained and coherent set of investments in the improvement of scientific education and culture was suggested as an essential element to alleviate existing distrust and reduce its future emergence.

With regard to social networks as a communication channel, there is a shared perception among the actors who participated in all three empirical studies. The capacity of social networks to transmit and disseminate scientific information in society is viewed as an opportunity to increase the scientific culture of the population. However, the 'viral' circulation of content without sufficient evidence and quality, along with 'fake news' is considered to be a great risk to public trust by the majority of participants in all studies.

Ethics and integrity in research are not considered to be of great relevance to current levels of public trust in Spain. These issues have not been prioritised in participants' reflections on factors affecting public trust in science. The public perception is that fraud and malpractice are isolated cases. The fact that there are reports of lack of integrity in science is evidence that the system is subject to oversight and researchers who lack integrity are exposed. However, there remains concern about the possible future

actions to restrict malpractice, which can be seen both in the reflections in the focus groups that institutional and organisational development of ethics and research in Spain is weak, and in some suggestions that greater publicity and punitive action for proven cheats could reduce perceived researcher impunity.

With regard to social integration practices, interviewees advocated these practices as a valuable strategy for improving citizens' trust in science. As was the case in the workshop and focus groups, various barriers, difficulties, and concerns were raised in the interviews about how to implement mainstreaming strategies. Limitations to the involvement of citizens in the research process were favoured. However, despite this, there is support among both researchers and mediators for the need to bring science closer to citizens. The main rationale for this is to improve citizens' scientific literacy and scientific culture, as strategies to increase public trust in science. On this point, the ambitious creation of spaces for citizen participation and access to science infrastructure and scientific culture for citizens is a recommendation shared by researchers and mediators in Spain.

Appendix A: Translation comparison

Sample comparison

A two-page section of one interview was translated using different freely available translation tools. This sample paragraph, with difficult passages highlighted, shows an indicative comparison of results.

Translating *altavoz* as loudspeaker is a simple error due to the ambivalence of the word. The translation of *conozca que se van a hacer* as 'going to be held' by DeepL is an example of a superior outcome in translating conventional language. On balance DeepL provided the best results for this type of challenges in translating from Spanish to English.

For this reason DeepL was used as the primary translating tool. Native Spanish and English speakers subsequently revised the machine translated text. It was necessary on only a few occasions for the reviewers to have direct discussions in order to finalise the translation of a term or text segment.

Translating two interviews from from Catalan/Valencian was more complicated. Google Translate was used as the primary tool, with more extensive revision work needed from a native speaker.

Sample

ES_M01 response

Bueno, pues ahí realmente funciono como altavoz de la investigación que se desarrolla en el centro, entonces la principal vía es difundir los actos que hacemos y si son públicos y abiertos, que muchos de ellos lo son, pues hacer la difusión para que la gente conozca que se van a hacer para que vengan, etcétera, y luego pues la difusión de la investigación que hacemos a través de las notas de prensa, las publicaciones en redes sociales.

DEEPL (<https://www.deepl.com/translator>)

Well, I really function as a **loudspeaker** for the research that is developed in the center, so the main way is to disseminate the events we do and if they are public and open, which many

of them are, then we disseminate them so that people know that they are going to be held and come, etcetera, and then the dissemination of the research we do through press releases, publications in social networks.

REVERSO (<https://www.reverso.net/text-translation>)

Well, because there I really function as a speaker for the research that is developed in the center, then the main way is to spread the acts that we do and if they are public and open, that many of them are, So do the dissemination so that people know that they are going to be made to come, etc., and then the dissemination of the research we do through press releases, publications on social networks.

TRANSLATE.COM (<https://www.translate.com/machine-translation>)

Well, there I really function as a loudspeaker for the research that is carried out in the center, so the main way is to disseminate the events that we do and if they are public and open, which many of them are, then to do the dissemination so that people know what they are going to do so that they come, etcetera, and then the dissemination of the research we do through press releases, publications on social networks

BING (<https://www.bing.com/translator>)

Well, there I really function as a loudspeaker for the research that is carried out in the center, so the main way is to disseminate the events that we do and if they are public and open, which many of them are, then to do the dissemination so that people know what they are going to do so that they come, etcetera, and then the dissemination of the research we do through press releases, publications on social networks.

GOOGLE

Well, there I really function as a speaker for the research that is carried out at the center, so the main way is to disseminate the events that we do and if they are public and open, which many of them are, then do the dissemination so that people know what they are going to do to get them to come, etc., and then the dissemination of the research we do through press releases, publications on social networks.

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Expert Interviews – *United Kingdom*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *CSIC*

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1. Introduction

This section provides a brief background on the inputs to Task 2.3 and summarises the process of organising and conducting interviews with Mediators and Researchers.

1.1 Research questions for Task 2.3

The Expert Interview study contributes to answering the following research questions that guide POIESIS. General research questions are:

1. To what extent and how does the alignment of research practices with principles of research integrity (or, conversely, scientific misconduct, questionable research practices, poor or absent science communication, and/or misinformation) impact public trust in science?
2. To what extent and how does the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in research practices (or, conversely, lack of co-creation and open science practices) impact public trust in science?

More specific research questions are:

1. How does information about (ir)responsible research practices reach the wider publics, which actors play a role in this, and how does it affect the public's trust in science, i.e. how are 'chains of mediation' organised and how do they impact levels of public trust?
2. Which processes and activities connecting (ir)responsible research practices and levels of public trust in science are identified by experts?
3. What kinds of manifestations of integrity and integration in the research cycle are likely to affect levels of public trust in science, and how?

1.2 Previous insights from Task 2.2 and Task 3.1

Findings from Tasks 2.2 and 3.1 that inform expectations for the Expert Interviews

1.2.1 Insights from Task 2.2

In our interviews with members of different groups of the general public, we found that ...

- a. ... different positions in the social space relative to science is not in itself a driver of high or low trust/distrust in science.
- b. ... concerns about the impact of disinformation and misinformation propagated on social media and undermining trust in science are widespread in the public.
- c. ... there is a need for the public to have critical thinking skills, to identify false information.

- d. ... there is a surprising, generalised lack of credibility of mainstream media such as the BBC;
- e. ... concerns over 'corrupting' corporate or funder influence on research findings is pervasive;
- f. ... scientific misconduct (such as data fabrication) hardly enters the picture, except for those who live and work close to science; unethical research, biased research, patronising elitism dominate the public worries about trusting science.
- g. ... people are aware of a dysfunctional peer review process, and career pressures arising from a 'publish or perish' culture;
- h. ... trust among scientists is based on 'who we know'; i.e. mutual distrust is widespread among scientists and active researchers;
- i. ... there is awareness and concerns about open 'twitter wars' among scientists.

1.2.2 Insights from task 3.1

In our interviews with groups of professional service staff (PSS) across UK universities, we found that...

- a. ... the image of science has not changed from the people in white coats but has been modified for gender inclusivity.
- b. ... the notion of a crisis of trust in science is not backed by evidence and surveys show trust levels are stable and in a positive direction.
- c. ... there may be pockets of distrust fed by social media and fake news.
- d. ... funders with vested interests may not have public interest in focus and are often a source of distrust.
- e. ... some areas of science, such as medicine, may experience the occasional crisis due to the nature of their research.
- f. ... misconduct is more often incompetence and negligence, than malevolent intent.
- g. ... the distance of society from science may also create distrust.
- h. ... there is a clear distinction between a researcher being trusted (relationship) and trustworthiness of research (science conduct).
- i. ... talk of a crisis is best avoided as it can become a self-fulfilling prophecy
- j. ... public engagement should be neither publicity nor marketing but a way to bridge the gap between science and its publics.
- k. ... public engagement could be risky and damaging without the right skill and more is not always better.
- l. ... there are potentials for conflict among the various groups involved: academics, professional staff, departments, institutional, and national coordinator.
- m. ... there is misalignment between REF and PE agendas; REF being the specific UK agenda of assessing universities on their 'research impact'.

1.3 Brief summary of organising the interviews

The present interviewees were identified using multiple access routes:

- Personal contacts: we leveraged personal contacts in academia and their recommendations on likely participants. We also asked those who recommended to reach the interviewees ahead of our contact to encourage participation. This method provided a personal touch to the interview selection process.
- Snowballing from interviewees: we also asked those we interviewed who were recommended to us to suggest other persons to contact. This method also provided a personal touch.
- We also reached out to institutions, both academic and non-academic, who recommended researchers to contact and spoke with them ahead to encourage participation.
- We searched online for likely participants on Google and social media pages using field specific keywords. While this was very successful for academics in climate change research, the response was poor from activists. Activists who responded demanded gratifications to be interviewed, which were not available.
- This process led to the identification of 46 potential interviewees.

We sent emails to all of them or their secretaries/personal assistant. 14 responded positively to the emails and we fixed dates and time for the interviews. Three were contacted directly and date and times also fixed. All in all, we succeeded in interviewing 17 people.

We interviewed six researchers (3 COVID, 3 climate change; 1 female and 5 male) and 11 mediators (3 COVID, 3 climate change, 5 science; 8 female, 3 male), some of whom were also active or retired academics or in advocacy.

Table 1 List of the interviewees and their social media followership

Researchers	Social media followers	Mediators	Social media followers
1. COVID-19	200,000 on X	7. Mediator (COVID)	210,000 on X
2. COVID-19	150,000 on X	8. Mediator (COVID)	90,000 on X; 1.7m YouTube
3. COVID-19	50,000 on X	9. Mediator (Science)	
4. Climate change	500 on X	10. Mediator (Science)	
5. Climate change	13,000 on X	11. Mediator (COVID)	5,000 on X
6. Climate change	(No social media)	12. Mediator (Climate)	
		13. Mediator (Climate)	
		14. Mediator (Science)	40,000 on X
		15. Mediator (Science)	4,000 on X; Magazine 2.5m on X
		16. Mediator (Science)	25,000 on X

		17. Mediator (Climate)	400 on LinkedIn
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We interviewed mediators with a focus on either general science issues, climate change or COVID as shown in Table 1.

We had difficulties recruiting non-institutional mediators from their social media handles as all the ones we identified and contacted requested to be financially compensated for the interviews and subtly declined when informed there was no budget for such. We then used personal contacts to snowball recruitment and were able to secure three non-academic mediators, who were activists on climate change. We also interviewed academics who in their dual role were prominent mediators given their activities on both social and mainstream media (see Table 1).

14 interviews were conducted online via Zoom and three were face to face. 13 were conducted by two persons while four were by only one individual from the team.

We summarised the interview guide into four sections that covered all the issues raised: personal profile, cases, crisis of trust, recommendations. This allowed us to delve flexibly into their areas of specialisation and topics that they were passionate about and wanted to elaborate on.

We also converted some questions, regarding types of media activity and use, to a short questionnaire attached to the consent form. This expectedly sped up the interview and allowed us focus on other questions.

The interviews length ranged between 46 and 70 minutes. One interview was however stopped at 40 minutes due to a fire alarm and we continued the remaining questions via e mail exchanges. Average length of interviews is about 55 minutes. All interviews totalled 946 minutes (15hrs 8mins).

Table 2. List of interviewees, date of interview, time, length and format

	Time (mins)	No. pages	No. words	Date of interview	Format
Researchers					
1	57	15	7824	20/06/2024	Zoom
2	47	12	6334	11/06/2024	Zoom
3	40	16	6961	06/06/2024	Zoom
4	55	22	9201	13/06/2024	Zoom
5	60	16	8339	17/07/2024	Zoom
6	60	19	8472	04/07/2024	Zoom
Mediators					
7	60	24	11953	03/06/2024	Zoom
8	60	22	11246	19/06/2024	Zoom
9	60	17	9209	18/06/2024	Zoom
10	42	11	5452	11/06/2024	Zoom
11	59	18	10426	02/07/2024	Zoom

12	60	23	10182	04/07/2024	Face to face
13	52	19	9805	12/07/2024	Face to face
14	59	15	9912	11/07/2024	Zoom
15	55	20	9461	19/06/2024	Zoom
16	60	36	14622	22/07/2024	Face to face
17	60	24	10809	16/07/2024	Zoom
Total	946	329	160.028		

1.4 Data processing and coding

The online interviews were recorded automatically by Zoom Client and both audio and video were sent to the university's online storage systems and retrieved through email links. The audio files were transcribed using online tools, but this only achieved about 70% accuracy and had to be supplemented with manual corrections. This approach saved a lot of time, nonetheless. All files relating to the interviews were saved on the university's online storage system in specified folders with access limited only to the project team members.

The analysis was aided by NVivo, a coding and indexing software. The format was deliberated upon by the team and some codes were identified upfront while others developed in the process of the analysis.

2 Participants - Expert Interview study

2.1 Descriptive tables

The tables in sub-sections 2.2 and 2.3 have a specific purpose in the reporting process. This purpose is to facilitate in an efficient manner a detailed description of the characteristics of our participants in the Expert Interviews study.

Information in the tables in sub-section 2.1 will be compiled to provide a comprehensive description of roles, outputs, channels, audiences, interaction types, and information sources of our Mediators. Information in the tables in sub-section 2.2 will be compiled to provide a description of the research, communication, and citizen interaction practices of Researchers.

This information is what is required for the description of participants in the Expert Interviews Global Report.

2.2 Mediators as interviewed

Table 3. Demographics and occupation

Id.	Gender	Career stage*	Mediator type**	Organization type (where applicable)	Occupational description	Main topic
UK_M01	F	Senior	Institutional	University	Lecturer	COVID
UK_M02	M	Emeritus	Institutional	University	Retired Lecturer	COVID
UK_M03	F	Senior	Institutional	University	Lecturer	COVID
UK_M04	F	Senior	Institutional	University	Lecturer	COVID
UK_M05	F	Senior	Institutional	University	Lecturer	COVID
UK_M06	F	Senior	Non-institutional	Climate activist	Teacher	Climate
UK_M07	F	Senior	Non-institutional	Climate activist	Teacher	Climate
UK_M08	M	Early	Institutional	Science advocacy	Media relations	COVID
UK_M09	F	Mid	Non-institutional	Magazine	Editor	COVID
UK_M10	F	Senior	Non-institutional	Radio	Editor, science and medical	COVID

UK_M11	M	Mid	Non-institutional	Independent producer	Producer	Climate
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Table 4. Mediators' main communication tasks

Id.	Description of mediators' main tasks
UK_M01	Huge involvement in COVID media campaign, media appearances, tweets, web platforms
UK_M02	COVID media campaign; promoting public understanding through media appearances on radio, TV, YouTube, podcasts also photography and writing newspaper columns
UK_M03	Science communication, trainer, educator of science communication, trustee in local science centre
UK_M04	Science communication, educator of science research
UK_M05	COVID media campaign; writing, teaching, talking to people, coordinating government policy and academics
UK_M06	Climate change campaign, educationist, mobilisation through mass media
UK_M07	Climate change campaign, educationist, mobilisation through mass media
UK_M08	Science communication, advocacy and engagement manager
UK_M09	Science communication, teacher, writer and science news and features editor
UK_M10	Program making, interviewing people, selecting speakers, writing for web, developing programme ideas
UK_M11	Climate change campaign, science documentary producer

Table 5. Outputs produced by Mediators

Id.	Books	Articles	Audiovisual (TV)	Radio program	Podcast	Audiovisual (social media)	Text post (social media)*	Live (social media interaction)	Other: (please describe in a few words only)
UK_M01		x	x	x	x		x	x	
UK_M02	x	x	x	x	x		x		
UK_M03									
UK_M04									
UK_M05	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
UK_M06	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
UK_M07									
UK_M08							x		
UK_M09	x	x					x		
UK_M10			x	x	x		x		
UK_M11									
Total	4	5	5	3	5	2	7	3	

Table 6. Channels used by Mediators

Id.	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)						Chat apps		Other: (please describe in a few words only)
	TV	Radio	Newspaper	Websites	Blogs	Newsletters	LinkedIn	YouTube	Twitter	Instagram	TikTok	Other SN	WhatsApp	Telegram	
UK_M01	x	x	x	x	x			x	x						
UK_M02	x	x	x	x	x				x						
UK_M03															
UK_M04															
UK_M05			x	x	x	x	x	x	x				x		
UK_M06	x		x	x	x	x		x	x		x		x	x	
UK_M07															
UK_M08			x	x	x	x	x		x						
UK_M09	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x				x		
UK_M10	x	x	x	x					x	x			x		
UK_M11	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x		

Total	6	5	8	8	7	5	4	4	8	2	1	1	5	1	
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Table 7. Audience addressed by Mediators

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' audiences/size estimate where known
UK_M01	200, 000 followers on X
UK_M02	90,000 followers on X' 1.7m views on You Tube
UK_M03	
UK_M04	
UK_M05	5,000 followers on X
UK_M06	
UK_M07	
UK_M08	40, 000 followers on X
UK_M09	4,000 followers on X
UK_M10	25,000 followers on X
UK_M11	400 followers on LinkedIn

Table 8. Mediators' interactions with citizens

Id.	Brief description of Mediators' social interaction practices
UK_M01	Mainstream media appearances and social media posts
UK_M02	Mainstream media appearances and social media posts
UK_M03	Public town hall meetings
UK_M04	Teaching and conferences
UK_M05	Mainstream and social media channels
UK_M06	Extinction Rebellion (xR) event participation; social media posts, public town hall meetings
UK_M07	xR event participation; social media posts, public town hall meetings
UK_M08	Social media posts
UK_M09	Mainstream and social media posts
UK_M10	Mainstream and social media posts
UK_M11	xR event participation; social media posts, public town hall meetings

Table 9. Mediators' sources of information

Id.	Interpersonal networks			Science press releases				Other: (please add text)
	With researchers	With science communicators	Scientific literature	RPOs	Publishers	Mainstream media	Social media	
UK_M01	x	x	x			x	x	
UK_M02	x	x	x			x	x	
UK_M03								
UK_M04								
UK_M05								
UK_M06	x	x	x		x		x	
UK_M07								
UK_M08	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
UK_M09	x		x			x	x	
UK_M10	x		x	x		x	x	
UK_M11	x	x	x			x		
Total	7	5	7	2	2	6	6	

2.3 Researchers as interviewed

We characterise our researchers as interviewed with a series of tables on demographics, occupation, main activities, and notions of their audiences.

Table 10. Description of the Researcher interviews sample

Id.	Gen.	Career stage*	Position or title/Career stage**	Organisation type	Topic CV/CC#
UK_R01	F	Senior	leading researcher	Public research institute	CV
UK_R02	M	Senior	leading researcher	Public research institute	CV
UK_R03	M	Senior	leading researcher	Public research institute	CV
UK_R04	M	Early	recognised researcher	Public research institute	CC
UK_R05	M	Senior	leading researcher	Public research institute	CC
UK_R06	M	Senior	leading researcher	Public research institute / retired	CC

* Career stage: Early, Mid, Senior ** ERC; recognised researcher; senior researcher; leading researcher (Professor)

Table 11. Researcher notes scientific discipline and the focus of their COVID or CC related work

Id.	Note
UK_R01	Medicine data collection, analysis, interpretation and public engagement
UK_R02	Medicine, computational systems, data collection, analysis, interpretation and public engagement
UK_R03	Medicine, public health, data collection, analysis, interpretation and public engagement
UK_R04	Low emission zones, political communication, data collection, analysis, interpretation and public engagement
UK_R05	Climate science and Policy data collection, analysis, interpretation and public engagement
UK_R06	Climate science, data collection, analysis, interpretation and public engagement

Table 12. How Researchers work with the public

Id.	Brief description of how the researchers' work reaches the public
UK_R01	Articles, TV, radio, newspapers, X and WhatsApp,
UK_R02	Articles, TV, radio, newspapers, social media posts, live interactions
UK_R03	Books, articles, TV, radio, podcasts, social media posts, live social media interactions, newspapers, websites, blogs, X
UK_R04	Books, articles, social media posts, live social media interactions, radio, newspapers, websites, blogs, newsletters, YouTube, X, Instagram, conferences, public meetings
UK_R05	Articles, TV, radio, social media posts, blogs, LinkedIn, X, conferences, public meetings
UK_R06	Books, articles, conferences, public meetings

Table 13. Description of social integration practices of Researchers

Id.	Brief notes of Researchers' social integration practices
UK_R01	Public consultations, seminars, mainstream and social media public engagement activities, conferences
UK_R02	Mainstream and social media public engagement activities, conferences, seminars
UK_R03	Mainstream and social media public engagement activities, conferences, seminars
UK_R04	Social media public engagement activities, conferences, lectures, seminars
UK_R05	Social media channels, public consultations, meetings with public administrators, international public engagements (EU and global), conferences
UK_R06	Meetings with public administrators, presenting papers at conferences

3 Analysis of Mediator Interviews (n=11)

This section aims to provide an analysis of key themes arising from the Mediator interviews. The analyses for description are organised into themes that should enable cross-comparison with other country's research.

3.1 Chains of mediation

Below is a brief description of the roles of the mediators in the networks of mediation

1. Senior academic in public health focused on enhancing service delivery. Member of the Independent Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (i-SAGE), a group of scientists who came together voluntarily to provide independent advice to the government, public and health care workers on how to minimise deaths during the pandemic. Mediator was active in both mainstream and social media during the pandemic.

2. Senior academic in public health, now a full-time communicator, post research activities. Mediator features on radio and television, writes books and newspaper articles, as well as engages in talk shows with very wide audiences. Involved with the i-SAGE during the COVID pandemic but maintained a middle ground; wrote newspaper articles on COVID during the pandemic; appeared on radio programmes and very active on X.

3. Mediator is a trainer and educator in science communication at Masters level and teaches people with a science training who want to become professional science communicators and scientists who find themselves in positions of having to communicate and want to be able to do it better by learning practical communication skills.

4. Mediator is a doctorate degree holder in natural science and oversees a post-graduate master's programme in science communication with focus on narratives in science and popular science, scientists' public discourse and the history of science communication. Comments mainly as an observant academic; also engaged in local politics.

5. Senior academic in public health and co-director of a research collaboration group. Mediator has worked with funders and decision-makers in the UK, EU and USA and is currently studying what happened during the pandemic and suggestions on how to make scientific advice more useful and good enough in future to make the public more accepting of it. Mediator is active on X, but less so than before COVID.

6. A teacher and climate activist, mediator has been involved with Greenpeace and Extinction Rebellion activities and now actively involved in advocacy for environmental consciousness and green

preservation. Mediator campaigns often on the streets of London, more involved in green issues in the local area, working with the local council and inviting experts from across the UK.

7. A teacher and climate activist, mediator has been actively involved with environmental action groups and teaches the principles of deliberative democracy on environmental themes. Mediator is building a local community coalition for a more sustainable transportation system that may include 24-hour bus lanes, more low traffic neighbourhoods and planning around 15-minute cities.

8. Mediator is advocacy and engagement manager for research and development (R&D) in the UK, representing about 115 organisations including research intensive universities, businesses, learning societies and similar organizations. A core concern of the institution is understanding how people think and feel about R&D. They have conducted and published several public attitude surveys, held deliberative workshops and focus groups on science and society issues.

9. A professional journalist with a doctorate degree in biological science. Mediator is editor of a science magazine performing multiple roles of communicating the results of science (peer reviewed articles), communicating to scientists (the magazines primary audience) and communicating science and its implications to the broader public. Mediator also teaches science writing at post-graduate level.

10. Former Executive Editor at the BBC with over 40 years' experience communicating science to a variety of audiences and maintaining the organisation's editorial standards in its science output. Mediator has covered many pivotal topics that are heavily interlinked with science communication, such as genetically modified crops, mad cow disease and climate change.

11. An award-winning artist and independent visual and documentary producer, mediator has made documentaries for National Geographic, Extinction Rebellion, museums etc., and as a climate activist, is actively involved in environmental action activities. Although not a scientist, mediator works with renowned researchers who provide historical and scientific information, and a recent work was the filming of the thawing permafrost in the Arctic Circle.

3.2 About public trust in science (mediators)

3.2.1 Public trust in science

Summary:

- Mediators are familiar with the concept of trust in science.

- They largely disagree with the claim that there is a serious crisis of trust between science and the public.
- In that context, while surveys show generally high levels of trust in science over the decades, science may be caught up in the general distrust of institutions that work with science such as NHS or utility companies.
- The discourse of a 'crisis of trust' may be a media construction, because of its news value.
- Awareness or worries about a crisis of trust may be limited to scientists and not of concern to citizens who are probably more worried about ethical use of data, profit motives of businesses and conflict of interest, sexual misconduct and career biases.

Note: the names of the mediators have been anonymised BM..7 to 11

Trust is high, a few dissenting voices is normal: BMA10 pointed to polls looking at trust in science going back 20 to 25 years which show that trust in science and scientific professions is higher than ever before compared with trust in politicians and journalists which are at their lowest. This position was supported by BME14 who said surveys also showed strong support for research charities and research and development by researchers and universities. investment. BMJ1 said because measurements have not indicated any crisis of trust, science is holding up very well in the minds of the public. BMA8 argued that the issue of distrust 'is probably a bit exaggerated', pointing out that although surveys can be trusted, they are not 'very terribly reliable statistics.' BMA8 acknowledged however that they show very strong trust in science and do not show any decrease. BMA8 also observed there are loud voices who are distrustful, but the objects of trust are often specific cultural obsessions with certain technologies such as dangers of nuclear power in Germany which the UK does not care about and France which opposes vaccines but is interested in alternative medicine.

BMA9 said the word trust is laden with 'all kinds of suspicion and danger and responsibility', recalling that the phrase trust in science came about as a response to the deficit model

(It) was as a response to the deficit model, and people were asking, well, we told people that vaccines are safe, and they still won't have one, trust came off as a sort of shorthand for an answer that said, well, it's not that they don't like the vaccine, they just don't like you ... -BMA9

BMA9 drew attention to the fact that if you ask the public to do something, 10% to 30% of them will not do it and there is never going to be anything where everybody is going to say, 'oh, yeah, great, well, we'll do that.' BMA9 said there will always be members of the public who will say 'no, I don't want to take that medicine,

or I don't want a wind farm on the hill outside my house' and they are going to have a multitude of reasons because decision making is complex and there are lots of different factors.

BMC17, like BMA9, noted that there will always be those in the population who drift from the main direction of travel. BMC17 drew inspiration for this from flocks of bird and swarms of fish where some show higher tendency to stay within the group and others to drift away, either out of fear (suspicion) or knowledge and bravery. Distrust, the mediator argued, may be a survival mechanism in the evolution of species. BMC17 also noted that although people in the 50s were more trusting of science, throughout history, there has been a lot of distrust of the scientific process, and the biggest factor at the moment is social media where people get information from channels that are just plain lying.

3.2.2 Issues with trust in science

Politics and polarisation: BMA10 argued that it is not that scientists are no longer trusted, but that the public understand correctly that science is used for political ends, and they distrust those specific instances of science, such as the controversy over the Measles Mumps and Rubella (MMR) vaccine

Vaccination rates only really started to tumble after Tony Blair (then British Prime Minister) went on the media and refused to say whether his son was being vaccinated with the triple vaccine, so that was ... [a] political fallout, it wasn't really the scientific question that was the problem. So, I think it's very difficult to talk about trust in science as an abstract ... it's the political uses of science that possibly are suffering from a decrease in trust. -BMA10

Moreover, on political influence in public trust in science, BMA8 observed that a general distrust can be connected to a general populism around the world and science almost gets caught up in that because science is seen as part of the establishment. Science, the mediator argued, 'is caught up as collateral damage in that, rather than it just being anti science.'

I think it's [distrust] tied up with ... move towards populism, general distrust of, you know, previous authorities, the remote expertise, elites and so on ... I kind of think this is just part of the current movement, hugely exaggerated by social media groupings and tribes ... in America, for example, you know the libertarian movement against state intervention and so on, scientists have just become aligned with state intervention. -BMA8

BMJ16 also observed that there has been less trust in authority in general over the last 15 years and quite a lot of the distrust has

been encouraged by various political statements. BMA11 was concerned about office politics and the academia and how this was made widely visible to the public during the COVID-19 pandemic arguing that this was 'very embarrassing for us as a profession.'

Science and business' profit motives: BMA10 argued that vaccine hesitancy may not be divorced of its development and production by organisations whose primary reason for being is to make profit for the shareholders. The history of the industry, BMA10 noted, includes instances of the most terrible abuses added to which are bad side effects for some small number of people, and in instances other than COVID, the immediacy of the threat has gone away. BMA10 said it was perhaps surprising that people even get vaccinated at all given they are being asked to take a vaccine as an insurance policy rather than as a barrier against a real and present threat in their life.

You're taking your little baby and shoving something into it that you know is potentially dangerous, albeit with very, very low risk, in order to ward off the threat of a disease which you've never seen and you've never had any contact with and the product having been produced by a multinational organisation that wants to make money out of it. -BMA10

Concerns over conflict of interest was also raised by BMA7 who observed that the public worry about scientists being paid by someone for their views.

From the public point of view, I would say people do worry about conflicts of interest and whether you're paid by someone, and whether, you know, if you're doing it for your own benefit. So, I've certainly had that accusation levelled at me. -BMA7

Specific to COVID and trust in science: For BMA7, when it comes to issues such as the COVID-19 pandemic and climate change, the public needs lots of different expertise to understand such issues. Since no one can understand it all, they will depend on individuals and institutions who have the expertise to enable them to form an opinion. The trust in their expertise, 'as a short cut', BMA7 argued, comes from knowing them and how their views align with individual beliefs. The problem with this, BMA7 however noted, is that there are other not-too-honest actors with eminent academic positions whose views the public are not able to falsify, thus splitting public opinion along different axes. This is made worse by the social media which rewards opposing sides.

You've got two people, as far as the general public is concerned, have equal credentials saying completely opposite things, so how do you decide which of them is right ... if you

don't know them personally and most people aren't going to know them personally, how do you do it? You go well, do I agree with other things that they've said? Do they align with my personal politics or whatever? And then you pick and that I think its really damaging ... -BMA7

When science does not deliver: BMJ16 observed that the pandemic was a novel experience, but the public wanted to think that science had the answers which it did not. People always seem to have a problem with scientists when they say, 'last year we thought X, now we think Y, that actually science is a process that does change' and this leads to disillusionment.

The expectations of the public who don't really understand science but have been kind of told that they should trust science and then when science doesn't deliver or it changes its mind, they're a bit confused. So, they possibly lose trust ... -BMJ16

Nefarious actors spreading disinformation: A recurring issue was nefarious actors, either scientists or non-scientists, spreading disinformation about specific issues or technologies. BMA11 cited an instance during COVID where a scientist made a categorical statement about COVID, and few days later made a U-turn on the same issue.

They'd say one thing with complete conviction, you know, like COVID is not an important thing, it's got a very low death rate ... in January and then, 7 days later, this is the biggest failure of science advice for a generation, I can't believe the government is full of you know, murderers or whatever - BMA11

BMA11 argued that while people have a right to participate in public debate, including scientists paid with public money, it comes with responsibilities, and they cannot speculate widely because people are listening and will respond. BMA7 argued that science has become coopted into the ongoing culture war as already happens in climate change, particularly in the United States, and was concerned that if we had another pandemic, people may see science as something where they look for the scientist that agrees with them.

BMA9 expressed surprise about the conspiracy theories circulating about the COVID-19 vaccine, that someone was 'trying to put a chip in my blood' but was not sure if the theory was conceptualised and circulated by a deceitful scientist or a deceitful industrialist trying to make even more money. When confronted with the conspiracy theory that the chips are going to be used to control what we do, BMC13 replied that they are doing it already through 'advertising and the best thing about that is we believe we're doing it out of our own free will.'

The public and uncertainty: On the uncertainties in science in the early days of the pandemic, BMA10 argued that assuming the public cannot cope with nuance is deficit model thinking, as we all live with contradictions in our daily lives.

You know, in our daily lives, we all deal with things that seem to be contradictory or ambiguous. There's something about the context of these, that the pronouncements made at a distance, we've got some sort of need for that to be more unambiguous than the things that happen in our daily lives. - BMA10

For BMA10, it is not the case that that people can't understand or were confused (in the early days of COVID-19), or thought the scientists were confused, but it sort of did not fit the template that we have of science held up as this way of determining policy.

The point of trust, BMA10 added, is that it is a type of shortcut to save us from having to make every decision, in full, every time.

3.2.3 Crisis among scientists

Crisis of trust among scientists often manifests as open 'Twitter wars' over findings, poor standards and allegations of misconduct. While some of these allegations have been attributed to the 'publish or perish' dilemma of academics, there is no consensus among the mediators that these feed into public trust in science.

The pandemic and twitter wars: The COVID-19 pandemic ignited the so called 'Twitter wars' as scientists argued over ways of containing the disease. At the receiving end of attacks during briefings on the pandemic, BMA7 was amazed science communicators turn on each other at the slightest opportunity and found depressing, comments eminent professors were prepared to write on Twitter. BMA7 was also more upset by polite attacks from other academics than unknown members of the public. Also at the receiving end of vile attacks, BMA8 recalled that some of the worst comments were from other scientists including an accusation of bullying.

I thought it really annoying to be publicly accused of bullying by someone with a lot of followers [on Twitter] ... other academics having a go at you ... because I was a critic ... I got really fed up with Independent SAGE and the Zero COVID crew ... and I got into arguments with them because they thought I was a minimizer -BMA8

Scientific malpractice: BMA10 argued that malpractices are probably symptoms of scientists working under immense pressures to deliver papers to get funding and REF scores they need in a research culture that is in a very 'stressed state'. BMA9 likewise attributed the problem to 'the impact agenda'.

BMKJ15 separated scientific misconduct, which is deliberate deceptive practices from sloppy practices or poorly done science. BMKJ15 however observed that the problem of poor-quality scientific output is quite pervasive and was evident during the pandemic when several studies were produced about potential therapies and the numbers in the clinical trials were just too small to produce any useful results.

BMA7 argued that since peer review is considered gold standard, we may end up, as happened during COVID, with people reporting papers that have been peer reviewed but saying completely opposite things, and this may take a long time to resolve. BMA7 was however of the view that while there might be contrasting findings from equally peer reviewed publications, in the normal run of scientific discourse, the wrong ones will be weeded out but that 'doesn't happen immediately, it doesn't happen in the space, in a couple of weeks, that's a year's long process.'

Scientists, BMA8 noted, are obsessed with distrust in science and scientific misconduct because they want to have a clean act and the current scientific publication process is broken. Despite these, BMA8 does not think the outside world is interested except in issues around conflict of interest.

There is the sort of, you know, you're in the pay of pharma argument, which could be considered misconduct, but ... it's more mis-motivation, rather than deliberate fabrication, you know. So, under misconduct and fabrication and so on, you know, messing about with images and all that sort of stuff that within our world, we get very obsessed with, quite right ... I don't think that's got much mainstream, you know, I don't think that's the big thing particularly. -BMA8

For BMA10 also, the issue is 'a bit niche' and may not reach the public as widely as is thought. BMA9 supported this view that it is mainly an issue among scientists. BMA7 does not think the issue feeds into why the public trusts or does not trust as most do not understand the concept of peer review or how science gets to the public. BMKJ15 would not call it a crisis, but a 'familiar problem' that is however a 'big problem' and would be interested in knowing if it filters down to the public. BMA7 however noted that such practices are less in some fields such as data sciences because there is less reward and less ability to fake results as there might be in a lab experiment.

For BMKJ15, when you hear about scientific discoveries on the radio or other media, most of it is about how cool it is and does not really get into this kind of weedy stuff about how much of it is accurate.

3.3 About research ethics and integrity (mediators)

Summary

- Mediators are concerned about the impact of honesty and transparency of research processes on integrity.
- There are limits to transparency.
- Scientists should be more honest with expected outcomes as the public is more interested in realisable achievements than unrealistic promises.
- There are ongoing initiatives to tackle the integrity question, but the appointment of inspectors may not be the solution to a problem that keeps changing in form.
- The Research Excellence Framework (REF) agenda may be driving fraudulent or unethical practises as it puts academics under immense pressures to deliver papers.
- The REF is not seen as able to adequately capture public engagement activities not directly related to the academic's research.

3.3.1 Honesty, transparency and integrity

A recurring issue with ethics and integrity as drivers of public trust in science is the need for transparency in research. BMA10 noted that while the rhetoric around evidence-based policy implies that science produces unambiguous recommendations, when confronted with reality, it contrasts the template of science that is sold to citizens who are now somehow left to reconcile the discrepancy. While not being transparent may be a driver of distrust, BMA10 noted also that there are moments, as with the pandemic, when too much transparency about the uncertainties would be counterproductive and would have made the policy decision seem uncertain creating other problems.

If the arguments about whether to lock down or not had had been public then, I think it would have been a lot harder to have the authority to lock down. So there does have to be a limit on transparency, or different transparencies, you know, context dependent. -BMA10

BME14 was of the view scientists can do a lot more to be honest about the timelines and outputs, that the research might not have the exact result that we want, but we might find something else out that is really helpful. The public, BME14 noted, also wants to see realism, as one of their focus group participants, when confronted with the message, 'a world free of cancer', replied that 'but that won't happen, why are you lying to me.'

Honesty and trustworthiness, BME14 noted, were crucial to the public messages from government scientists during the pandemic,

even as dire as the situation was. BME14 offered an anecdote from one of their focus group participants to illustrate this point.

He told us how many people had died and he was honest with us, you know, he levelled with us ... that sense of giving people the bad news as well as the good news. I think, brought a sense of honesty and openness like they weren't hiding something that was like unpalatable. They would be direct um, which I think was a really important quality that came through. -BME14

On integrity, BMKJ15 noted that there are ongoing initiatives all over the world trying to tackle questions around integrity and include training, improving the way scientists are rewarded and incentive systems. This, BMKJ15 added, may take the pressure off just counting publications or the impact factor of publications, more into looking at the quality of the work.

Another initiative is the appointment of officers to supervise the integrity of research. ACC1 said while not a bad idea, it is not the main solution to the problem because it is a technocratic solution.

It's a tick box solution. We need to ensure that scientists have integrity. It's an Aristotelian virtue. What we have at the moment is the emergence of scientists who lack integrity, not science, but scientists, and they have infiltrated every level of science ... Of course, there are plenty of people in all those roles who have lots of integrity, but what I'm saying is there are also people who are not following what Robert Merton described as the essential defining features of science. -ACC1

To appoint integrity officers as inspectors, ACC1 argued, is like putting a plaster on the wound, it is not getting to the root of what is going to be a constant battle like detecting doping in sports.

Every time we find a way of detecting doping, the corrupt athletes find a way of getting around that detection, and so there's this sort of cat and mouse, an arms race, we are never going to go back to a situation where athletes don't cheat. We are always going to have this continuing, having to respond to whatever the corrupt athletes do next. -ACC1

3.3.2 UK's Research Excellence Framework (REF) agenda

BMA10 observed that stories about university scientists engaging in fraudulent or unethical practises are symptoms of working under

immense pressures to deliver results to get funding and the REF scores, and it is recognised within higher education and government that the research culture is in a very stressed state. This view was supported by BMA8 who argued that the current scientific publication process is 'absolutely dreadful,' and the 'model is broken.' BMA9 also agreed the current state of play is due to 'the impact agenda' as British scientists have been told since the 1970s that they must have a marketable outcome. As a result, it is very difficult to do a research project and say, at the end, 'no, my idea didn't work.'

Another shortcoming of the REF highlighted is its inability to adequately capture public engagement activities not directly related to the academic's research. BMA7, a member of Independent SAGE, who was very active in public engagement during the pandemic, noted that such activities will not count as a REF case.

I think what's been quite interesting for me in terms of the role in COVID is that it is quite divorced from my research, so I can't use it as an impact case study, it's not REF able, what I do isn't part of my academic role, because it's not my research and that somehow communicating other people's research doesn't count as public engagement in the way that funders and universities and academics see it. -BMA7

BMA7 regarded this as an interesting paradox 'because REF should in principle be something to encourage public engagement.'

3.4 Other themes (mediators)

Uncaring elite: For BMA9, one of the drivers of distrust has been 'a lot of lying, not telling the truth', because there are too many people in it for personal gain only. The mediator argued:

Looking at the UK recently, [there] is a very strong sense that there are people who are in it for their own gain, and not in it for everyone, and that's kind of the opposite of the Enlightenment, isn't it? That's a kind of medieval social structure in which a small number of people benefit and a very large number of people go hungry, which is, is what the mood of the country is, at the moment, you know, whether it's true or not and science has always been one of those things that has seemed to be in the control of the elite. -BMA9

When asked if this is from the political elite or from the scientific elite, BMA9 said:

Just socially, it's an elite, and it's been more or less controlled by the political elite for a long time, despite the sort of widespread myth of sciences' independence. Scientists, doctors, in Britain, they are older white men, it's an elite, you know, and at the moment, the elite is not responsible,

caring, thoughtful, generous; it's money grabbing, deceitful, uncaring. -BMA9

BMC13 argued similarly that it is the sense of unfairness in the world and the inequality that is feeding distrust, and it just takes people in very different directions.

So that's why I think a lot of people don't believe the science and they've gone down a route where they think that science is in the hands of a particular group with a particular agenda. -BMA13

3.5 Synthesis of recommendations (mediators)

3.5.1 Models of trust suggested by mediators

Summary

Public engagement is necessary to build social capital, reduces social distance and leads to trust. The current model interferes with the mission of 'enlightenment' and 'reducing distance'.

Trust in science is a swarming problem between competing factors; the dilemma of curiosity and courage which allows venture into unknown and fear of getting lost, which keeps most within the flock, maintaining status quo.

Climate science is highly credible but undermined by scientists who are too cautious and those who engage in greenwashing and vested interests who distort evidence in public.

Public not opposed to using expertise for policy making and using science informed policy will encourage better public compliance.

Advocacy in science is a kind of 'misconduct', only tolerable for public health doctors. The key is trustworthiness, scientists have to deserve trust, and inform, not persuade.

3.5.2 How to improve trust (mediators)

Participants proffered recommendations on how to improve trust in science. Some of these measures, they however pointed out, could be double edged.

- Trustworthiness is key, not trust in science.
- Training the public for critical thinking skills.
- Public engagement is double edged.
- 'Electoral model' of PE is to be avoided.

- Ignore the trolls and bots.
- Advocacy for policy by scientists should be avoided.

Public engagement: For BMA9, public engagement creates social capital, showing that scientists are people like 'your next-door neighbour'. This interpersonal interaction makes a lot of difference to how the public reacts to the kind of advice the scientist might give. The BBC runs a few programmes aimed at 'making scientist as part of culture and society, rather than othering them' said BMJ16

For some reason in the UK, scientists have been kind of seen as 'other' and I think a lot of the rest of the media has not helped ... you often hear a news story, that would say that scientists have discovered that, as if they are another breed, that they are for Mars

Most [of] the media is run by people who are not scientists, who are very critical of science ... we would question science, we're not kind of totally pro what they do, we feel that we, as journalists, have the view to be able to question people on what they're doing, why they're doing it -MBJ16

BMA9 argued that since the scientist may be on a different kind of schedule or has different kinds of skills, the communication function needs not be by an active researcher and can probably be done by a professional. The problem, BMA9 noted, comes when engagement is tied to the impact agenda which indicates that active research, in its tiny, not yet known significance, gets shoved into the public domain, when that is not really what anybody wants, either on the delivery side or, or experiencing it in the public sphere.

BME14 noted that engaging the public badly, doing it without thinking about what people really want from it has the potential to do more damage than good. Engagement, BME14 argued, also requires funding, training and support from senior leaders, and should not be treated as a tick box exercise but as something that is really valued.

The electoral model of public engagement: Participant BMA9 recalled an engagement activity during the pandemic where science communication practitioners and journalists from around the country were assembled to deliberate on the results of some experiments on messaging about COVID. The data was divided along ideological lines, right and left leaning, and the issue was which message to choose. The pressure to accept the one with a majority, 'the electoral model' rather than using both messages to appeal to both sides. BMA9 also recalled a failed public engagement activity where children were shown the workings of the orchestra for basic music appreciation. This ended in a total failure as they could not control the room, mainly because what they asked the children to do

was just not what children wanted to do and this was despite the presence of four public engagement officers and 12 professional classical musicians, all due to poor planning.

Public engagement can however yield desired results and make an impact on public opinion. BMA7 had to refute allegations that the AstraZeneca vaccine was withdrawn because of errors discovered by the manufacturers, and this was playing out in the mainstream media and trending on twitter. BMA7 wrote a Twitter thread explaining what happened with the vaccine and why it was being withdrawn and why it was not scary. This, the mediator noted, turned out to be 'the most popular thing I've written in two years and it's something I didn't take seriously because I thought no one could believe this science, but then you realise actually, people do.'

Risk of abuse from public engagement: Engaging the public on social media puts the academic in touch with millions of people worldwide, including other scientists, expanding sources of information and reach of ideas but responses could be anything, including vile comments.

BMA7 was very active on social media during the COVID-19 pandemic, with independent SAGE, and was sent an e mail with the comment, 'you filthy kite, Hitler should have gassed you' and 'you should be in jail.' BMA8 was called a Nazi, who 'should be haunted down and destroyed for the genocide against humanity.'

ACC3 recalled experiences from the Brexit campaign and the work they did on the commercial determinants of health and the tobacco industry and the hate mails and threats to life and family that followed.

I was on Newsnight, and they tracked, not just me down, but tracked our daughter down and sent her an email saying your father should be gassed, shooting is too good for him. -ACC3

BMA11 got a lot of sexist abuse but noted, 'I get that from my student evaluations as well.' The mediator was however concerned about colleagues who behaved in very aggressive and confrontational way, with rather egregious comments.

BMKJ15 recalled that a colleague was at the receiving end of online abuse, and it was a difficult moment. BMC12 also recalled a colleague getting death threats for campaigning against felling of trees in the neighbourhood with the anti-campaigners using robots.

You don't know who's agitating, who's doing all those nasty contents, often it's bots (robots) ... when you look at the profile, you look at the history of that person. I mean, sometimes they've got like football, some of the ones that are really anti-cycling, they are thugs in other ways.' -BMC12

Women are also treated differently when it comes to online abuse. BMA8 said 'high status white male may fare better.' BMA7 was surprised that people treat women differently to men online.

Like I could just see this very same Twitter people talking very respectfully, even to people they disagreed with who are men ... women, treated like ... idiots and ... and then if you were not white you'd end up with the whole racist stuff as well coming in, and that was quite eye opening to me.

BMC12 said abusers are better ignored, 'you just ignore it. You don't give energy to it ... people hate cyclists and that's been, I mean, how can you hate the cyclist. It's a simple machine.' Another mediator agreed,

'Just don't engage, never get into an argument, it just never works ... I realised when I didn't listen to that, it always got worse, and so I just stopped, and you have to kind of fight against this innate desire to be polite, so if someone ask you question, you feel like you have to respond, but secondly, to realise that it's not about you, right ... it's not personal - BMA7

On the flip side, BMA7 got a lot of a lot of thank you from many people, 'emailing me or sending me letters ... or seeing me in conferences, occasionally on the street, saying thank you, I really appreciate what you did ... we felt we could trust you.'

Countering anti science campaigns by adopting their tools: The use of masks during the pandemic was very contentious and those against used very sophisticated skills in statistics, data visualisation and media knowledge to project their views as being scientific. ACC1 decided it was right and in public interest to play them back at their own game.

One of the things that I started doing in relation to masks was playing them back at their own game. So, there was one visualisation of the mask. It was a kind of graphic of 10 reasons why masks are harmful ... I changed the words on it ... played them back at their own game. -ACC1

YOUR HEALTH BE HEALTHY

YOUR LIFE BE INFORMED

YOUR CHOICE BE SAFE

FACE MASK SAFETY
KNOW THE FACTS **BEFORE** YOU WEAR ONE

- 1 DECREASES OXYGEN INTAKE**
BREATHING THROUGH A MASK DECREASES THE AMOUNT OF OXYGEN WE NEED TO LIVE & BE HEALTHY, INCREASES BLOOD ACIDITY & MAKES BREATHING DIFFICULT.
- 2 INCREASES TOXIN INHALATION**
TOXINS THAT WE NORMALLY EXHALE AS WE BREATHE BECOME TRAPPED IN THE MASK AND RE-INHALED INTO THE LUNGS, INCREASING SYMPTOMS.
- 3 SHUTS DOWN IMMUNE SYSTEM**
DECREASES OXYGEN INTAKE, INCREASES CARBON DIOXIDE & TOXIN INTAKE PUTTING BODY UNDER STRESS, RELEASING CORTISOL & SHUTTING DOWN IMMUNE PROCESSES.
- 4 INCREASES VIRUS RISK**
ENCOURAGES TRIGGERING & INFECTION FROM DORMANT RETRO VIRUSES ALREADY IN THE BODY, TAKING ADVANTAGE OF A WEAKENED IMMUNE SYSTEM DUE TO MASK WEARING.
- 5 SCIENTIFICALLY INACCURATE**
VIROLOGISTS MEASURE COVID-19 TO BE 80-140nm IN SIZE MAKING THE WEAVE OF MATERIAL MASKS TO BE THE EQUIVALENT OF A CHAIN-LINK FENCE TO A MOSQUITO.
- 6 EFFECTIVENESS NOT STUDIED**
ABSOLUTELY NO PEER-REVIEWED STUDIES HAVE BEEN CARRIED OUT OF MASK EFFECTIVENESS WITHIN A SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT TO CONTROL, PREVENT OR ELIMINATE THE SPREAD OF DISEASE.

YOUR HEALTH BE HEALTHY

YOUR LIFE BE INFORMED

YOUR CHOICE BE SAFE

FACE MASK SAFETY
KNOW THE FACTS **BEFORE** YOU WEAR ONE

- 1 NO IMPACT ON YOUR OXYGEN INTAKE**
Wearing a mask or face covering does not interfere with the amount of oxygen getting to your lungs. Surgeons wear masks safely for hours.
- 2 NO INCREASE IN TOXIC INHALATION**
Carbon dioxide from your exhaled air escapes harmlessly through the mask and around the edges.
- 3 NO DAMAGE TO YOUR IMMUNE SYSTEM**
A face covering is made of safe, familiar materials (cloth, paper, waterproof backing). It won't stress your system.
- 4 DECREASES VIRUS TRANSMISSION**
Depending on what it's made of, your face covering reduces emission of droplets from your mouth and nose (in coughs, sneezes and speech) by 60-95%, making others safer. It also reduces the amount of virus that you get exposed to by approximately 20-30%.
- 5 SCIENTIFICALLY ACCURATE**
The holes in a cloth face covering seem large in relation to tiny viral particles. But because the virus sits in droplets when it's in your mouth and nose, the holes are small enough to block them very effectively.
- 6 STRONG EVIDENCE OF EFFECTIVENESS**
There used to be doubt about whether face coverings protect against the spread of COVID-19. New research published in May-July 2020 has strengthened the evidence base. We now know they do protect.

Policy advocacy: Advocacy is linked with engagement activities. BMA8 was emphatic advocating for particular policy positions must be avoided at all costs by scientists, as it is not their duty but that of the political class to take decisions after considering all the consequences and to take responsibility for the outcome. The only exception was 'possibly a public health doctor' because it is in their professional code that they should be advocating for improved health of the population. The mediator argued:

Science does not lead the way, you're not following science, you should not follow science. There should be evidence informed policy. It's not the scientist that decides the policy, to possibly say what the consequences of different actions might be. But the politicians have to weigh it up, and I think one of the big problems during COVID was the fact that SAGE and other scientists were obsessed with only a couple of metrics about infections and hospitalisations, forgot about everything else. No concern with the damage to education from school closures, enormous harm done to poorer people, particularly young, poor people. -BMA8

BMA8 argued that numbers have limitations. Not being able to measure an issue does not mean it is not important. They can also be misused by scientists who engage in white hat bias, by selecting evidence, in order to argue or advocate for something that they personally believe in.

This position, on not advocating for particular policy directions, was supported by ACC5 who also always refrained from going beyond the scientific facts presented, leaving the political decisions to the administrators and politicians. ACC5 recalled an interview with journalists at the 2015 Paris Climate Conference where the Paris agreement was reached.

They asked me whether the outcome or the targets that was being discussed at that stage was strong enough ... my response is I know that this level of warming results in these impacts. I know that level of warming results in those impacts. I know the decision makers here know it because we have been talking to them, we have been presenting it to them ... It is there, they have been elected ... It's their job to make that decision -ACC5

ACC5 however noted that researchers make choices that look technical but are deeply influential in how the evidence is perceived and can be used. Before The Paris Agreement, ACC5 noted, nobody created pathways that described how the world could reduce its emissions for limiting warming to 1.5 degrees Celsius, adding that as long as there is no technical description, it was basically a target that was politically non-viable

So, although I did not make the decision, whether 1.5 needs to be in The Paris Agreement, I coordinated a scientific effort,

to develop those pathways and get them published in time, get them included in the UN report, and by doing that it enables certain factions in the negotiations to argue for a political choice more strongly. -ACC5

Training for critical thinking: One option suggested for improving trust in science is providing more science education and critical thinking skills. 'We have to start reaching further back' said BMKJ15

We have to teach the next generation ... I have reported on some quite interesting efforts to develop critical thinking in children, and I suppose I do tend to buy into that idea. - BMKJ15

The mediator also argued that everybody, politicians and the public, need to learn more science, and not the regular science education like you learn the elements, but being able to assess a claim which is being made and ask if it is supported authoritatively.

Whether that be a claim in medicine that this diet is going to cure your cancer or a claim by policymaker that this new policy is going to ... lift people out of poverty or whatever. I think to be able to approach claims like that critically and understand how science and research can support that, whether it supports that claim is a really powerful skill and ... I think would be a good way forward

-BMKJ15

BMA7 agrees adding that on the long term, it has to be education, acknowledging however that not everybody is good at it and not all scientists as well are good at it or even want to engage in public education. This has also now been made more difficult, BMA7 argued, with media outlets becoming less independent and picking sides on an issue rather than more consensus about the facts.

Trustworthiness is key, not trust in science: For participant BMA9, how we make science trustworthy is the important question and not how we make the public trust science. Arguing that there was never a golden age of everybody trusting scientists on an issue, BMA9 recalled that people were sceptical about 18th century natural history books and all through the 19th century, there was scepticism about different kinds of expertise. The crisis discourse, the mediator argued, is a kind of branding to focus resources on a problem away from others.

I think it was probably invented by politicians to deflect responsibility for all kinds of problems, whether it's environment, energy, water quality, you know, health. So, I don't like the language of a crisis of trust -BMA9

Rather than people saying, 'does the public trust science', they should be asking, 'is science trustworthy,' BMA9 argued.

Quoting the British Philosopher, Onora O'Neill, BMA8 said it is wrong for experts and organizations to ask why people are not trusting them. Rather than trying to persuade audiences to trust, they should be trying to demonstrate trustworthiness. This BMA8 argued, puts the responsibility back on to the scientists, 'we have to earn it. We have to deserve it.'

A lot of the time scientists don't deserve it because they're not acting in a trustworthy way. They're picking and choosing the evidence to argue for, with a point of view that they think is right and they probably are right, you know, people who pick and choose evidence to say the insects are declining ... to exaggerate the harms of things ... in a way they are right, but they're not being trustworthy they're not being scientists, they're being advocates -BMA8

Good scientific communication, BMA8 argued, should be informing and the information needs to be balanced with the benefits and the harms, both there with equal emotional salience which does not mean they are the same size, and then it has to admit the uncertainty and explain how good the evidence is.

For BME14 also, trust is earned, and scientists and organizations have to act in a responsible way by demonstrating they are being as honest and transparent as they can be, and that they embody the values that they expect of other people and behave in an ethical way, as these are the things with which they can show trustworthiness.

4 Analysis of Researcher interviews (n=6)

This section aims to provide an analysis of key themes related to the Researcher interviews. The analyses for description are organised into themes with guidance provided for international comparisons.

4.1 Researcher contexts: COVID-19 and climate change

Summary of researchers work in the context of COVID-19 or Climate Change.

1. Senior academic in primary health care services. Works with other professionals including sociologists, anthropologists and philosophers in the organisation and delivery of health care services. During the COVID-19 pandemic, researcher worked with the Independent SAGE, focusing on masks, indoor air and protection of workers.
2. Senior academic in epidemiology. Research areas include the reconstruction of disease outbreaks, epidemics of human and wildlife pathogens, drug resistance and virulence, and factors influencing the successes of particular lineages when compared with others. Researcher was a critic of the Independent SAGE.
3. Senior academic in public health. Researcher has worked in several universities in Europe and authored numerous reports on the management of infectious disease outbreaks that cross borders in the European Union, the impact of EU law on health care, and the contribution of health to the EU economy. Researcher worked with the Independent SAGE.
4. Political Science Researcher's focus is citizens' perceptions of governance that incorporates elements of scientific expertise and digital technologies. Researcher worked recently on public perceptions of the role of science in policymaking on COVID-19 and low emission zones, specifically, how research findings travel through policy to public discourse.
5. Senior academic in climate science and policy. Research focus is how science can transform societies towards more sustainable futures. Researcher has worked on the effectiveness of several international agreements such as the Copenhagen Accord, the Paris Agreement, carbon budgets and net zero emission targets.
6. A retired senior academic in meteorology, focusing on weather and climate. Researcher has been involved in climate change research for several decades and has held many United Kingdom roles on climate change and the environment and at the global level on climate change agreements as well as being a member of science academies of the UK, USA, China and Europe.

4.2 Science communication and attitudes (researchers)

4.2.1 Channel works as presented to public

This section focuses on researchers' channels of public engagement and other outreach activities, appearing on mainstream and social media. Note: The names of the mediators have been anonymised ACC1 to 5

- Public engagement via radio and TV appearances, social media posts
- Public talks and interactions with government officials
- Media appearances should be selective and with 'friendly' journalists

ACC1 was a scientist in public health and part of Independent SAGE, the group of scientists who felt very strongly that the development of the science of public health in the pandemic had to happen in dialogue with the public. They were concerned about government secrecy and worked together on public enlightenment during the COVID-19 pandemic. This led to the researcher becoming a public figure, appearing on mainstream and social media channels.

So, in that context, I responded to requests to appear on television, radio, be interviewed for newspapers. And, I have a big social media following. I've got 180,000 followers on Twitter. You know, so I started off at the beginning of the pandemic with 50,000. So, I was putting out tweets and things. So, I've got social media, I've got mainstream media. I did a couple of blogs ... -ACC1

ACC3 had media training and did a lot of media work during the pandemic, posting extensively on Twitter and engaging radio audiences in continental Europe and North America, as well as local stations using media networks cultivated over the years. ACC6 was not active on social media but gives public talks and interacts with government officials, prime ministers, heads of governments, heads of international bodies, politicians and businesses on climate change issues.

ACC4 engages in outreach, talking to public and private institutions and other audiences. The research on cleaner air zones has been shared with Asthma UK, British Lung Foundation, government office for science and other science advisors in public service. Research has also been shared with several student groups including professionals from the civil service and local government interested in clear air polities.

ACC5 had media training and engages with the public using national and international media, newspapers, radio, television and social media (Twitter and LinkedIn) and also speaks at public events. ACC5 was very cautious about how his research is presented by the media largely due to the charged nature of the climate change debate and the well-funded machinery of the anti-climate activists. Researcher thus carefully selects whom to talk to.

I have several kinds of long-standing media contacts that I trust will look for insight and understanding, and not for a kind of slip of the word to misrepresent my position

... at the institute, we have a communication scheme through which media requests will be funnelled. This is great because it's not just indiscriminate funnelling of media requests. I can ask OK, who is this journalist? Can you do background research on them? -ACC5

4.2.2 Characterisation of presentation

The section focuses on researchers' characterisation of their experiences with public engagement. In summary, they found that:

- Media coverage is polarised along party and ideology
- Science development has to be in dialogue with the public
- Science not enough for public acceptance
- Interested actors organise anti science campaigns
- At times both sides back conflicting claims with science, and hope better science will prevail

Politicisation and polarisation of issues: According to ACC5, media coverage of issues and events are polarised along political party and ideological lines, and this has crept into the climate change debate such that if those on the left approve, the other side will disagree. ACC6 however observed that this was not the case at the beginning, when Margaret Thatcher began to promote the issue in the UK with bipartisan support and elevated it to world attention.

Following Margaret Thatcher's promotion of that issue ... there was agreement across Parliament so that when the climate change Act went through ...

(it) was when those who are now the Reform party, if you like, the right-wing of the Tory [Conservative] party then became the sceptic party, there was a political bit, which said we're going too fast on this ... -ACC6

The researcher argued that it was after this that politicians, right wing press and some members of the public with vested interests started with campaigns like 'hey, they're stopping us driving our car', so it became something about regulation and stopping us doing what we want to do, and those businesses with the

money were very much happy about this and the fossil fuel companies were not at all unhappy that this push back was there.

The issue of polarisation was also prominent in public debates about the COVID-19 pandemic in the United States with implications for the rest of the world. ACC2 said it was 'pretty bad' that the US went into the pandemic with very weak CDC (Centres for Disease Control) and in an election year.

The polarisation was really political because in the very early stages when people were talking about the [COVID] vaccine, it wasn't politicians, there was not this clear cleavage, let's say that Republicans were against and Democrats for, and then it became just a political issue and that was a disaster.

Who's to blame for that? I don't know necessarily, it's complicated. -ACC2

For ACC4, some members of the public reject the relevance of science in setting the clean air zone debate because it had distribution implications, implications on their democratic sensibilities and the appearance they are being excluded from the debate, and 'that's the problem, it's not about science.' This, the researcher noted, is unlike the Genetically Modified foods debate.

It's unlike something like GM, where there are people who want GM experiments, people who don't want GM experiments, they all think science is on their side. It's like science versus science kind of debate ... social epistemologists would call them epistemic peers because they want to resolve this somehow with better science and more science, and eventually we'll get there kind of attitude. -ACC4

Senior scientists also had different views on the containment of the pandemic, and this led to two different camps; the Zero COVID group also called 'frownies' and the 'minimalists' also called 'smileys.' The difference in their perspectives was if the government was doing enough or not, if lockdowns were appropriate and for how long. ACC2 argued that the government SAGE was doing a good job but some members were communicating outside the official messaging, getting in touch with journalists to make 'sometimes, some pretty outlandish or pretty extreme claims' contradictory to SAGE.

There was this additional complication with this other body, which is called Independent SAGE, which included also, several members of SAGE, which led to the very weird situation where you had essentially ... official government advisers undermining the government. -ACC2

Climate change controversies: ACC6 was part of the Intergovernmental panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and involved in

the Climategate controversy when emails from the University of East Anglia were hacked and leaked to the media, misrepresenting the debates among the scientists as indicating the manipulation of findings. The issue was the use of the word 'trick' by one of the scientists as they attempted to reconcile data and this purely academic language use, was misrepresented as data falsification.

(It) was the word trick that he used, which in mathematics is quite usual to say this is the trick to solve the problem, and that's the way he'd used it, he was actually trying to reconcile two ways of looking at past data and they didn't quite match up, but he found a way of making them match up and that's the trick, and that's what they got him on. -ACC6

The opposition did not stop at this and continued to look for things that could undermine the climate community, making several freedom of information requests and it was in this context ACC6 wrote an email to colleagues on the need to present a united front, and this was also leaked and presented by the media as further evidence of collusion in the climate community.

ACC5, despite being very cautious about media interviews, recalled an incident with a reporter and an interview that barely lasted two minutes and the resulting news item was so bad it destroyed a collaboration with another institution.

Somebody called me out of the blue, a journalist, that I knew, but not too well and asked me two questions, that interview lasted less than two minutes ... and they took one quote of it, and because of that, a whole collaboration that I build up with a certain institution, all the bridges were burned ... since then, I became even more cautious.

4.3 About the integration of citizens (researchers)

This section focuses on citizens involvement in research, the issue of public engagement and participants' views of the merits and limitations thereof. In summary, participants said:

- Involving the public in research leads to a better understanding of what the problem is, what really matters to the public, and solutions they are looking for.
- Engaging front line workers also leads to better appreciation of reality of day-to-day issues.
- Co-designing solutions encourages acceptance by the public.
- Citizen involvement is not possible at all stages of research.

ACC1 presented a case study on the on the integration of citizens in health care research which led to a better understanding of the problem, the patients and the differences between trusting institutions and trusting someone because you know them. The study was about the use of interpreters in medical consultations in

London where over 300 languages are believed to be spoken and before the introduction of advanced technology in translation.

The official line then was that professional interpreters were better than family member interpreters, because they were independent, neutral, more accurate and it did not put the child in the position of having to interpret for their parents. What the researchers found however was in many of the minoritised groups, particularly refugees, they trusted their family members and did not trust the professional interpreters who they described as being 'on the side of the English', colluding with the system.

It [the study] emerged from a problem that we had, we ended up writing several academic papers about the importance of family member interpreters in the very power charged context of a GP consultation and the need to have someone who didn't just translate the words ... but who could advocate for that individual, and understood their 'life world', and so we brought in lots of theoretical work around the 'life world' and in the difference between institutional trust, trusting institution and interpersonal trust, trusting this person because you know them. -ACC1

For ACC3, researchers need to engage people on the front lines to know what is happening and what the reality of it is. Using the pandemic as case study, ACC3 argued that you cannot model risk of infection in care homes unless you realise that there is a dynamic of mobility of workers across different care homes whereas, the assumption in many people's minds was 'well, here's a care home, they've got staff, they work there, they come to work, they go home and they didn't take account of the fact that they work in that one on Monday and another one on Tuesday and so on.'

ACC3 encourages co-creation, citing research into cervical screening and the control of high blood pressure, a disease has had safe and effective treatment since the late 1950s in the West but not changed much in other parts of the world. One of the research programmes for addressing the blood pressure issue was a cluster randomised controlled trial in Malaysia and Colombia.

We spent the first year co-designing the package of care because, although both countries had low control of blood pressure, the detail was different, and it had to be reflective of the local context, but as importantly, of course, it had to have buy in, you know, buy in by those who were using it. -ACC3

According to ACC3, cervical screening is straightforward if you're a woman, 'you go to a doctor or a nurse, you get a cervical smear taken, it is sent to a laboratory or pathologist looks at it and you get a result back.' This the researcher added, works if you are not homeless or on the margins of society and the approach to this requires a technological leap, where the woman can take the sample

herself and post it back. Ensuring they can post it back is the main issue here and requires citizen participation, so they are co-designing a package, trying to understand what it means in reality and what are the issues people face.

Relatedly, BMA7's research involves everyone who is going to be affected and being in the health care, these might be a certain set of patients or a certain cohort of people or people living in a certain area. The main issues required from their perspective are, 'What is the problem? What really matters to you? What should we be looking at? What would you want from this? The researcher noted that current standards include having patient representatives, steering committee or a PPI group, but wants researchers to engage more.

BMA7 however noted the limitations of citizen involvement in complex areas as mathematical modelling.

4.4 About public trust in science (researchers)

In this section we examine the notion of a crisis of trust in science. Is there a crisis in popular discourse about science? How is this expressed in public? What is the role of scientific misconduct in public trust? How can trust levels be increased?

4.4.1 Is there a crisis of trust?

Summary

- If there is a crisis of trust, then it is a crisis of 'truth' in the public sphere in general; science can no longer appeal to 'truth' as all is only opinion.
- There is no crisis of trust in general; however,
 - There might be a perceived crisis of trust, cultivated and highlighted by mass media.
 - There are interested and nefarious actors, who would like to see science in crisis, in particular over climate change, but also during COVID-19.

One of the researchers argued that although there may be some problems, it is often exaggerated while another pointed out that surveys show there is no crisis of trust in science, but this may be a general attitude to science that varies across countries. There are also contexts where trust attitudes are moderated by political views or nefarious actors, or the public just don't have enough information to make informed decisions.

Is there a crisis of trust in science?

Well, I think there is, but I think it's often exaggerated, I mean, I think there are problems, but there are actors in society that are actively trying to make it more than it is and to undermine trust for all sorts of reasons ... There certainly is a problem. -ACC3

And I think science probably deserves it, that loss of trust ... I think scientific integrity has eroded I think the science the peer review process is broken. -ACC1

Cross national surveys would suggest there is no crisis of trust and by cross national I mean of course maybe there's a European bias to that. So, I understand that the parts of the world are different. The context that I know, certainly no good evidence to suggest that there is. I'm not saying it's impossible, but there is no good evidence to suggest that trust in science in general is in crisis. -ACC4

Yeah, absolutely. I think so, but then it's part of a much bigger challenge, a bigger societal challenge where ... evidence is malleable, facts are malleable to one's political views, particularly on social media and so once that is, once you allow that to be an accepted part of a societal conversation, well then it doesn't matter how rigorous you go about either doing or explaining what you doing in science, its dismissed with the wave of a hand. -ACC5

In climate change, I don't think there's a crisis of trust, I do think there's been a big effort ... to undermine using the right-wing media and has been a very big effort and considering that if I give public talks or when I give public talks, I give very many, I don't get the accusation, 'No', that would be we don't trust what you're saying', I usually get the reaction 'well if only I had heard this before I'd understand the issue and I'd go along,' so I don't see, when I'm up there, that am looked on as an untrustworthy person.

I don't think there is a crisis, I think there are some who'd like to think there's a crisis and make the thing that there is a crisis. -ACC6

4.4.2 Scientific misconduct and public trust

Summary

- Scientific misconduct is unlikely to be a driver of trust; there is a high threshold of public perception; misconduct does not reach the public.
- Misconduct at most an issue among scientists.
- Trust is lost from loss of autonomy, nefarious influences, vested interests such as the anti-climate lobby group at 55 Tufton street, London.

- Trust is lost by 'advocacy' which should be classed as a kind of misconduct.

Retractions, p-hacking and plagiarism: Scientific misconduct, evidenced in retractions of published papers even in high net worth journals, has always been touted as a source of public distrust in science and scientists.

ACC2 argued that retraction should not be seen as a problem but as part of the scientific process because science evolves through the constant accumulation of knowledge, and most contributions are very minor while some are incorrect. ACC2 argued that while there is 'always some fraud ... there are a lot of papers that are incorrect, and not necessarily fraudulent.'

You could say it's terrible there are many retractions, or you could say it's wonderful there are many retractions because actually its scrutiny and if something's incorrect then it gets retracted, in some sense, that's the way it should be, and even with the best will, let's say someone can write a paper which leads to wrong conclusions, that can happen, and so fundamentally, that things are retracted, to me, is not a bad thing ...

I think healthy science should have a process of retraction - ACC2

On p-hacking by researchers to find significant data, ACC4 was surprised that people may think the public worries about this. ACC5 said while p-hacking and plagiarism are very problematic and condemnable scientific practice, they do not concern the public (on climate change) who otherwise think scientists are politically motivated and part of a big conspiracy for world domination

The public has no clue about plagiarism, p-hacking and all that ... not any of these aspects concern the public and how they look at science. These are the debates that are there in academia, but they don't drive public debate, I have not heard anyone mentioning, oh, okay, because you're just a paper mill machine, we can't trust your science -ACC5

Retractions, ACC2 noted, tend to happen more often for papers that are very high profile or in fields that attract interest than fields of less interest.

4.4.3 How to improve trust

Summary

- Project uncertainty, honesty and transparency.
- Media regulation should be considered.
- Integration/engagement.

- More scientific information may not improve trust.
- Belief, economy social conversations crucial to trust.

Project uncertainty: ACC2 argued that science should avoid being overly dogmatic as what undermines science is the attitude of many scientists that what they say is the truth and not conveying properly the uncertainty around the claims.

The two most important qualities for scientists are epistemological humility, and not being dogmatic and I think that's particularly important for those who want to communicate to the public. -ACC2

For ACC3, politicians need to improve trust by being transparent

I think it is really important to look at how you've got to be open and transparent and just being honest, I think, but the difficulty is that politicians are terrified of being honest. -ACC3

ACC3 also called for some actions on the media or other voices that are actively undermining trust and spreading conspiracy theories

More information may not add value: ACC5 no longer believes in the deficit model approach, that giving people more education, enough information and data, they will understand what the issues are and act appropriately. Scientific evidence, ACC5 argued, no longer determines conduct as people have made up their minds and decided on which direction they want to follow either unconsciously by picking a party or unconsciously by having clicked certain links online and the social media algorithm now preselects, edits and creates the information they are getting.

Yeah, at this point, we, we know everything we need to know, I mean, we knew 10 years ago, everything we need to know, for any reasonable person to make a clear strong decision on positive action on climate change so that there shouldn't be a debate ... I don't think it's a role of science ... I don't think that by doing their role, they will convince the public. -ACC5

ACC5 argued that there are other variables that come in to play such as belief, the economy and the social conversations among peers.

Media regulation: ACC5 also suggested the introduction of watchdogs for regulation as obtained few decades ago when media organisations adhered to strict standards in what they published. The traditional media channels, ACC5 noted, are increasingly playing smaller roles and the social media channels that are taking over are not subject to that scrutiny, to the same quality standards.

4.5 Other themes (researchers)

Summary

- The phrase 'follow the science' was wrong as it did not project uncertainty.
- Nefarious actors are undermining the scientific process with a libertarian agenda

Follow the science: Commenting on phrases such as 'follow the science', 'If you stay at home for two weeks, the pandemic is over' and 'if everyone gets vaccinated, the pandemic is over' which became popular during the COVID pandemic, ACC2 argued that these claims are wrong since they assume that science is a set of unassailable established facts that cannot be challenged and will not change rather than its actuality; a process and a philosophical approach to life.

I think that was pretty bad, how this unfolded, and I think that things like that are absolutely terrible because they undermine trust of society in science ... there is no democracy possible without the minimum trust in the authorities and in science, which is part of, say, the authorities. -ACC2

Follow the science, ACC2 argued further, was not a good advice because there was so much uncertainty and it created a lot of conflict because some people will not, or cannot follow these kind of orders, and when these do not turn out to be the silver bullet, people get very upset against authorities and obviously undermines trust, and to some extent, rightly so.

For ACC3, you could just not say we are following the science and assume everybody will then trust you. Rather, you have to demonstrate that there are multiple sciences and of concern then was that sometimes the science that was being viewed by the government was a very narrow view of science, in part because people were working in silos.

BMA10 was however of the view the government did go far enough to say that there were uncertainties about exactly how the situation was going to play out and they were also clear that it would be a lot worse if we did not have a lockdown.

Ideological interests and nefarious actors: ACC1 expressed concern that nefarious actors are undermining the scientific process with a libertarian agenda which played out during the COVID-19 pandemic with the opposition to the wearing of face masks. These people, the researcher argued, are challenging institutional science, science that is done in universities and government departments, by doing

their own research, generating their own graphs and interpretations.

There is now, as you know, a very strong and very sinister movement of the kind of atomistic networks of individuals who are sitting at home, doing their own research, and that's a phrase that they love, they want the raw data from whatever study it is, and then what they do is they generate their own graphs ... and then they say, well, I don't trust this institution, my interpretation of the science is this, now that is problematic. -ACC1

ACC1 argued that the interpretations are fundamentally flawed and problematic because some of these people have quite sophisticated skills in statistics and data visualisation and they might know some language, which sound very academic.

With climate change research, ACC3 observed that there are also people who are opposed to measures aimed at reducing the effects of climate change for purely ideological reasons.

Because they are libertarians who believe that nobody should be telling them what to do and there are (also) people who are going to be opposed to that because they make these things, and it hits their bottom line ... and you can get a coalition coming together, you know, each echoing each other's voices ... astroturf essentially, so what seemed to be public grassroots organisations are entirely a creation of the people who are making money out of it ... marketing doubt, manufacturing doubt. -ACC3

ACC6 referred to the curious circumstances surrounding the climate change events of 2009, the phone hacking scandal, which was blamed on Russia hackers, and despite the University of East Anglia involving the police, nothing was done to identify how it was done. ACC6 said it was curious that the global warming policy foundation was ready to launch the same day the hacking was published.

Pure coincidence, probably not, there's no doubt there was an organisation of the rolling back on this climate change and global warming and this became quite serious then, there was a lot of freedom of information requests to all the scientists involved in IPCC, and it was quite detailed request where they wanted all our emails ... And the number of requests coming out, very organised, there was one particular person ... you felt this guy was not interested in this, it's the attempt to undermine the scientific effort again, and the people doing it ... and it was very well organised and really very difficult for the (climate) community at that time, and of course, it made a major public splash. -ACC6

When asked if there was any inkling of which organisation was behind it, the researcher said no, adding however that the global warming policy foundation was clearly very well briefed on what was

happening and the anti-climate lobby group at 55 Tufton Street, London, was also very much briefed, if not organising.

You've got the feeling this was something much bigger than we were used to handling, like we're on the stage, but most of us haven't really raised our heads too much in this sort of political and really low-level media stuff, so it was, it was quite an eye opener. -ACC6

4.6 Synthesis of recommendations (researchers)

Models of trust suggested by researchers

The various interview conversations developed along lines of arguments which we might characterise as 'implicit' models of trust; we specify these models as follows:

- Public engagement that promotes honesty and projects uncertainty will lead to a social justice agenda which ultimately results in a trusting, grateful, reassured public.
- Medialisation encourages too much 'gloss' on the facts and thus undermines science. Public engagement through impact and attention seeking distracts individual scientists from main focus which is research.
- The deficit model does not work; more information is not the solution when values are at stake.
- Science cannot guarantee the conditions of its own functioning as 'orientation on truth' in public sphere goes beyond science. Science in the public sphere relies on the respect for truth being there.
- Investing more in critical thinking skills will give public more tools to process information.
- Epistemic humility, demonstrating trustworthiness is the issue, not lack of public trust in science, i.e. the problem is not with the public.

5 Conclusions

In this concluding section, we revisit earlier sections of this report where we reported on results from WP2.1 (public deliberations) and WP3.1 (interviews with research services staff), and we here in addition list the results from the present study WP2.2 (expert interviews) in a summary table. These three sections combined allow us to gauge basic results cumulatively emerging from these three parts of the POIESIS project.

5.1 Findings from public deliberations (WP2.1)

1. We found in interviews with members of different groups of the general public, that different positions in the social space relative to science is not in itself a driver of high or low trust/distrust in science.
2. Concerns about the impact of disinformation and misinformation propagated on social media are widespread in the public.
3. The lack of trust in mainstream media such as the BBC was surprising.
4. Concerns over 'corrupting' corporate or funder influence in research findings is pervasive.
5. Scientific misconduct (data fabrication) hardly enters the picture, except for those who live and work close to science; unethical research, biased research, patronising elitism dominate the public worries about trusting science.
6. People are aware of a dysfunctional peer review process, and career pressures arising from a 'publish or perish' culture.
7. Trust among scientists is based on 'who we know'; i.e. mutual distrust is widespread among scientists.
8. There is awareness and concerns about open 'Twitter wars' among scientists.

5.2 Findings from research service staff (WP3.1)

1. The crisis of trust in science is unfounded.
2. Media is source of crisis discourse.
3. Some areas of science cause more public anxiety than others (genetic experiments brings moral and religious concerns, etc).
4. A good scientist is transparent, competent, industrious, risk averse, open and honest about findings.
5. Misconduct is more often incompetence and negligence, than malevolent intent.
6. Focus should not be on publicity or marketing but bridging the gap.
7. Risks of public engagement: not always a good thing, nor is more PE always better.

8. Tensions and potentials for conflict between professional staff and academic staff, within both professions and across institutions.
9. There is misalignment between REF and PE agendas; REF being the specific UK agenda of assessing universities on their 'research impact'.
10. Implicit Models of 'trust in science' in operation:

Causal model: PE has the capacity to mitigate the withdrawal of trust in science; PE works as 'good will' to cushion any fall from grace.

The 'Wellcome Trust Onion' model of degrees of public participation.

The 'diffusion model' of technical innovations and new ideas; linear top-down model considering local relevancies.

5.3 Findings from expert interviews (WP2.2)

1. There is no serious crisis of trust in science, maybe among scientists.
2. Misconduct concerns are about the peer review process, retractions, p-hacking and plagiarism, and in some cases may be part of the evolution of science.
3. Science cannot on its merits alone be accepted by the public.
4. Advocacy for policy direction should be left to politicians who have other issues to consider. Scientists should inform, balance benefits and harms, with equal emotional salience.
5. Projecting uncertainty is important for trust in science, being dogmatic reduces trust.
6. Scientists need to project trustworthiness rather expect to be automatically trusted by the public.
7. Engagement is double edged but needed.
8. Social media regulation should be considered to reduce spread of conspiracy theories and overtly wrong science.
9. Emerging 'alternate' science by untrained members of the public poses risk to science.

5.4 Cases and events discussed in expert interviews

In the course of our conversations the following events and cases were explored in some detail, as to the activities involved, the difficulties and impacts of communication and the way this illustrates the problems of public trust in science.

1. XR (extinction rebellion) events of April 2019 in London and country-wide

2. Doing messaging work for XR to counter omissions in mainstream media
3. Citizen juries and assemblies for neighbourhood campaigns on climate change issues
4. Developing 'citizen juries' ideas in primary schools: training for deliberation
5. Formats for tv documentaries commissioned by National Geographic: 'strangest things', 'methane sink holes in the permafrost'
6. The climate gate 2009; hacker attacks at UEA
7. COVID effect at Nature magazine; how to position its role in the concert of news?
8. How Margaret Thatcher discovered Global warming in 1990 and became a pioneer voice in Rio 1992
9. SAGE & I-SAGE, their mission, tensions, activities and impact
10. Evidence-based policy: ideas, practices and the tensions between civil servants and academics
11. Policy advice before and after the pandemic of 2020/21
12. Social media exposure attracts abuse; how to cope with it
13. Apparatus of PE bureaucracy interferes with actual PE activities on the ground
14. PE event in the South-West of England; what makes a failure
15. COVID lockdown period of October 2020, how we got into it
16. Urban air pollution control and the use of evidence in public debate
17. The massive surge in science communication during COVID-19
18. Comparing impacts across different channels: tv, radio, print news, social media
19. The UK REF paradox: potential non-alignment between REF and PE

5.5 Summary table of ‘trust models’ compared

Table 14. Comparison of trust models

	Mediators	Researchers
Crisis, what crisis?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trust is high, a few dissenting voices is normal The discourse of a crisis may be a media construction Awareness or worries about a crisis of trust may be limited to scientists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If there is a crisis of trust, then it is a crisis of ‘truth’ in the public sphere in general; science can no longer appeal to ‘truth’ as all is only opinion. There might be a perceived crisis of trust, cultivated and highlighted by mass media There are interested and nefarious actors, who would like to see science in crisis, in particular, over climate change, but also during COVID-19 Medialisation, too much gloss, undermines science.
Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public engagement is necessary to build social capital, reduces social distance and leads to trust. Current ‘PE apparatus’ model interferes with the mission of ‘enlightenment’ and ‘reducing distance,’ Trust in science is a swarming problem; the dilemma of curiosity and courage which allows venture into unknown and fear of getting lost, which keeps most within the flock maintaining status quo. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Epistemological humility, trustworthiness, not trust in science Project uncertainty, honesty and transparency Investing more in critical thinking skills will give public more tools to process information Science development must be in dialogue with the public Science not enough for public acceptance Media regulation must be considered

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate science is highly credible but undermined by scientists too cautious and those who engage in Greenwashing and vested interests who distort evidence in public. 	
Misconduct? Research integrity (RI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mediators are concerned about the impact of honesty and transparency of research processes on integrity Misconduct has news value There are limits to transparency Scientists should be more honest with expected outcomes as the public is more interested in realisable achievements than unrealistic promises. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unlikely to be a driver of trust; high threshold of public perception; misconduct does not reach the public Misconduct at most an issue among 'scientists' Trust is lost from loss of autonomy, nefarious influences, vested interests (the anti-climate lobby group at 55 Tufton street, London) Trust is lost by 'advocacy' which should be classed as a kind of misconduct
Public engagement (PE); public integration (PI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trustworthiness is key, not trust in science Training the public for critical thinking skills, Public engagement is double edged Advocacy for policy by scientists should be avoided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public engagement that promotes honesty and projects uncertainty will lead to a social justice agenda which ultimately results in a trusting, grateful, reassured public Public engagement through impact and attention seeking distracts individual scientists from their main focus, which is research. Involving the public in research leads to a better understanding of what the problem is, what really matters to the public and solutions they are looking for. Engaging front line workers also leads to better appreciation of reality of day-to-day issues.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Public engagement is necessary to build social capital, reduces social distance and leads to trust. Current model interferes with the mission of 'enlightenment' and 'reducing distance,'
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